

A Novel Efficient Dual-Gate Mixed Dilated Convolution Network for Multi-Scale Pedestrian Detection

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ABSTRACT

With the increasing use of onboard high-speed computing systems, vehicle manufacturers are offering significant advanced features of driver assistance systems. Pedestrian detection is one of the major requirements of such systems, which commonly use cameras, radar, and ultrasonic sensors. Image recognition based on captured image streams is one of the powerful tools used for the detection of pedestrians, which exhibits similarities and distinguishing features compared to general object detection. Although pedestrian detection has advanced significantly along with deep learning, some issues still need to be addressed. Pedestrian detection is essential for several real-world applications and is an initial step in outdoor scene analysis. Typically, in a crowded situation, conventional detectors are unable to distinguish persons from each other successfully. This study presents a novel technique, based on the Dual Gate Mixed Dilated Convolution Network, to address this problem by adaptively filtering spatial areas where the patterns are still complicated and require further processing. The proposed technique manages obscured patterns while offering improved multiscale pedestrian recognition accuracy.

Keywords-deep learning; image recognition; mixed dilated convolution; multiscale pedestrian recognition; spatial regions

I. INTRODUCTION

Several computer-vision applications, including autonomous vehicles, person identification, and surveillance, depend on the ability to identify pedestrians. Pedestrian detection has been substantially improved by recent deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based approaches [1-5]. Since pedestrians regularly block each other, this problem remains challenging. Detectors must be able to recognize various items in a crowded area but also detect pedestrians even when they are largely hidden. According to [6-10], the identification of human body parts can help modern detection models cope with occlusion. Compared to other methods, deep learning methods show better performance and a high level of accuracy [11]. In many areas, such as the healthcare sector, CNNs are the most widely used deep learning methods [12]. In [13], a deep-learning CNN was trained to predict crystal orientation. Although the effectiveness of the current approaches has improved, the question of how to fit such challenging pedestrian structures correctly and specifically achieve the necessary detection parameters is still a challenge. Most detectors perform poorly because they evaluate

pedestrian occurrences uniformly using identical parameters, which is in a way insufficient for those with sophisticated designs. Methods based on the Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) integrate high-level semantics with low-level facts, making them suitable for detecting smaller elements such as pedestrians. However, this requires lowering the spatial resolution to identify larger objects, which affects performance. Some pedestrian detection techniques use parallel branches for multiple scales, but only coarse-grained pattern-parameter matching can be employed due to fixed parameter sizes. Current multiscale detection techniques also result in higher computing costs and impaired real-time effectiveness.

High-performance pedestrian recognition relies on extracting discriminative features from local patterns. Local image descriptors or pre-trained CNN backbones are used to identify the local patterns, while powerful classifier layers extract high-level semantic patterns. The processing of challenging patterns requires additional traits such as multiple scales or occlusion. In [14], a zoom-in-zoom-out component and a scale-sensitive pedestrian attention mask were suggested to improve the ability of feature maps to recognize small-sized

pedestrians. In [15], a novel viewpoint was provided, in which pedestrian detection was driven as a rising semantic feature identification job using simple convolutions for the center but also scale forecasts. In [16], a new two-stream CNN model was proposed for semantic segmentation that explicitly connects shape information as a distinct processing branch that examines input simultaneously with the standard stream.

W3Net [17] was proposed to respond to these challenges, dividing the pedestrian detection task into where, what, and whether subtasks that target pedestrian localization, scale prediction, and classification, respectively. AugFPN [18] is an innovative feature pyramid network created to maximize the potential of multiscale features by adding three straightforward but valuable elements: Consistent supervision, residual feature augmentation, and soft Region-of-Interest (RoI) selection. In [19], the part-aware multi-scale fully convolutional network was proposed to handle occlusion and wide-scale variation concerns. As a result, a pedestrian occurrence that is only partially visible may receive a good recognition confidence score, reducing the chances of not being noticed. In [20], a gated multi-layer convolutional feature extraction network was proposed to improve the accuracy of pedestrian detection, using a squeeze unit to reduce the feature dimension before the gated unit. In [21], a prior-based receptive field block was presented, which directs the network to focus on the pedestrian by taking into account the pedestrian's shape prior, in addition to a bidirectional feature enhancement module that improves semantic features and localization information. In [22], an innovative detection technique was introduced, based on adaptive pattern-parameter matching. The Pattern Disentangling Module (PDM) first divides input pedestrian sequences, particularly complicated ones, into smaller structures to detect heads. The Gated Path Selection Network (GPSNet) [23] aims to learn adaptive receptive fields. The SuperNet two-dimensional multiscale network, which tightly integrates traits from growing receptive fields, serves as the basis for GPSNet.

In contrast to the methods mentioned above, this study proposes a method using a gating mechanism for pixel-level feature quality in addition to several branches of dilated convolution to retain spatial resolution.

II. THE PROPOSED METHOD

Pedestrian detection is the initial step in outdoor scene analysis. Even after utilizing the advantages of deep learning algorithms from generic object sensors, strong occlusion and dense crowding make it extremely difficult to recognize pedestrians. Occlusion patterns can also be addressed through part-aware feature extraction. Combining multiscale feature maps to collect additional information is an efficient method for multiscale pedestrian identification. As an alternative, this study created a unique gating-based module, termed the Dual Gate-Mixed Dilated Convolution Network, which adaptively filters spatial regions where the patterns are always complex but need to be processed further. A novel ResNet-50-based dual-gating technique was used to reduce model complexity at run-time. Dual gating determines the key characteristics of each convolutional block along the spatial and channel dimensions, allowing dynamic skips of superfluous channels

and unimportant sections. FPNs address multiscale variation difficulties in object detection with minimal processing load. Mixed Dilated Convolution (MDC) is used to expand feature maps for better pedestrian identification in long distances, addressing obscured patterns and improving multiscale pedestrian recognition accuracy. Figure 1 shows the architecture of the proposed scheme.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed scheme

A. Dual-Gate Network

Figure 2 shows the basic dual-gating. Every convolutional block's spatial and channel gating modules anticipate the informative features in two distinct dimensions, using the intermediate feature maps. Thus, unnecessary computations may be avoided during execution.

Fig. 2. Basic model for dual gate network.

1) Spatial Gating Module

Spatial sparsity is typically present in feature maps. According to [24], the backdrop information in shots has a smaller impact on the results, showing that not all geographical locations have the same significance. The spatial gating component aims to calculate the informative zones throughout the spatial dimension. Figure 3 shows the organizational layout of the training spatial gating component. In the first step, an Adaptive Average Pooling operation (AdaAvgPooling) is used to aggregate the local data of the input feature maps, but then a conventional 3x3 ResNet is applied to yield a 2D spatial attention map.

$$A_{s1} \in R \left[\frac{h_{l+1}}{t} \right] \times \left[\frac{w_{l+1}}{t} \right],$$

$$A_{s1} = f_{3 \times 3}(AdaAvgPooling(X_l)) \quad (1)$$

where $f_{3 \times 3}$ represents the 3×3 ResNet, and $A_{s1}(i, j)$ reflects the significance of the tile at position (i, j) on the final feature map. In this scenario, the use of a tile-based mask was decided for two reasons. Based on the spatial attention A_{s1} , the execution of those unimportant tiles can be immediately concealed during the inference phase. It is possible to write the binary spatial gating mask M_{s1} as follows:

$$M_{s1}(i, j) = \begin{cases} 1 & A_{s1}(i, j) \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Now, the discrete binary masks are relaxed to continuous variables using the Gumbel-Softmax re-parameterization algorithm [25]. Specifically, given the spatial attention A_{s1} , it is possible to define the probability that the spatial tiles will be executed $P_{s1}^1 = \sigma(A_{s1})$, where σ is the sigmoid function. The probability that the tiles will not be implemented is $P_{s1}^0 = 1 - \sigma(A_{s1})$. The spatial gating M_{s1} may therefore be represented by probabilistic binary random variables $(M_{s1}(i, j) = 1) = P_{s1}^1(i, j)$, and then, the sampling process of M_{s1} can be reparametrized as:

$$M_{s1} = \arg \max (\log(P_{s1}^k) + gk), \quad \forall k = 0, 1 \quad (3)$$

where $\{gk\}k = \{0, 1\}$ are independent and identically distributed random variables that follow the Gumbel distribution. The Gumbel-Softmax approach substitutes a softmax for the arg max since the latter is not continuous. The variational sample M'_{s1} from the Gumbel-Softmax relaxation can be stated for such a binary special case as follows:

$$M'_{s1} = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{\log(P_{s1}^1) + g1}{T}\right)}{\sum_{k \in \{0, 1\}} \exp\left(\frac{\log(P_{s1}^k) + gk}{T}\right)} = \sigma\left(\frac{A_{s1} + g0 - g1}{T}\right) \quad (4)$$

The sampling process and the variation among the two Gumbels could be described as a Logistic distribution $g0 - g1 = \log U - \log(1 - U)$, where $U \sim \text{Uniform}(0, 1)$. Therefore:

$$M'_{s1} = \sigma\left(\frac{A_{s1} + \log U - \log(1 - U)}{T}\right) \quad (5)$$

where T is the softmax's temperature, which regulates how the softmax and argmax functions differ from one another. In this study, the formula $T = 2/3$ was used, as given by [25]. A step function was added to M'_{s1} to get a binary mask all through the forward pass and use the continuous M'_{s1} to generate the gradient during the backward pass. Figures 3 and 5 show the features of the training's spatial gating and the channel gating components, respectively.

Fig. 3. Spatial gating module.

Fig. 4. Channel gating module.

2) Channel Gating Module

Since a channel's saliency varies depending on the input, dynamically choosing essential channels to execute is a promising way to reduce computation while retaining as much of the model's representational power as possible. Consequently, this study proposed and developed a channel gating module to detect superfluous channels that can be ignored during inference using the input pictures. Figure 4 shows the structural layout of the channel gating module. Initially, a global average pooling method was used to aggregate the spatial data from the feature maps to produce a context descriptor (*GlbAvgPooling*). To gain channel attention $A_{c1} \in R^{c_l+1}$, the descriptor is sent to a lightweight network next. The channel attention network, which is similar to the SE block [26], is made up of two consecutive fully connected layers that have c/r neurons in the hidden layer to minimize computations, where r is the reduction ratio. The channel attention is illustrated as follows:

$$A_{c1} = W_1 * \delta[\text{norm}(W_0 * \text{GlbAvgPooling}(X_i))] \quad (6)$$

where $W_0 \in R^{c_l+1 \times \frac{c_l}{r}}$, δ is the ReLU function, and norm represents the batch normalization. In this study's experiments, r was set to 4. Then the channel attention is employed to construct the binary channel mask M_{c1} during inference, much like with the spatial gating module. The channel gating module additionally employs the Gumbel-Softmax relaxation during the training phase to provide the continuous mask M'_{c1} for back-propagation. The channel gating module may also be linked with ResNets to fully understand the crucial channels. Figure 4 shows how the dual gating was integrated into the leftover blocks. The inference paths are indicated by dashed arrows.

Fig. 5. Integration of dual gating into the residual blocks.

B. Mixed Dilated Convolution

Although the human head with shoulder region has low form variation and is relatively stable, it is a small target in comparison to other objects for a single image and the pixel per inch ratio is lower. The model's shortcomings in handling multi-scale variation issues in object detection tasks are mostly addressed by FPNs [27]. The dilated convolution [28] may also extract various feature maps with various semantic information at various dilated rates. In the FPN phase of Dual-Gate ResNet-50, the context information is again fused using mixed dilated convolution to increase the receptive field of the feature maps and improve the recognition of small objects. In [29], it was shown that mixed dilated convolution creates a gridding impact as a result of the dilated rate stacking, resulting in some missing pixels and a break in information continuity. To implement the dilated rate stacking, the following equation must be fulfilled:

$$M_i = \max[M_{i+1} - 2r_i, M_{i+1} - r_i, r_i] \quad (7)$$

where r_i is the dilated rate of layer i and M_i is the maximum dilated rate of layer i . Assuming that there are n layers in total, to satisfy $M_n = r_n$, a simple example is $r = 1, 2, 4$. As a result, the proposed MDC architecture is made up of dilated rates $r = 1, 2, 4$. Figure 5 shows the MDC structure of the module after the initial FPN fusion. In this MDC module, three distinct dilated convolution rates are used in parallel, with the magnitude of the dilated rate reflecting the diameter of the receptive field. Initially, the amount of feature map channels $C \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H \times L}$ are decreased after feature fusion by convolution, a feature map $C_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times L}$ is generated. The dilated convolution layers are again sampled on the feature map C_1 at various dilated rates ($r=1, 2, 4$) to obtain $C_2, C_3, C_4 \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times L}$. Finally, C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4 are connected to attain the feature map $M \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times L}$, $M = [C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4]$. The model may take in information from a range of receptive fields, which can then be merged to extract specialized semantic information, particularly feature information for small targets.

Fig. 6. Structure of MDC

In front of the Dual-Gate ResNet-50, two MDC modules are interconnected. When the connectivity of the spatial feature pyramid is completed, the four contextual data-aware module features are fused using MDC and sent to Dual-Gate ResNet-50 for identification. The picture features are removed using DR-Net, resulting in feature maps with more in-depth semantic

data. The MDC module samples and merges the feature maps with dilated convolutions of varied dilated rates to broaden the receptive field as well as utilize finer-grained feature data.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Dataset Description

The proposed method was implemented on a large-scale dataset named CityPersons [30].

B. Confusion Matrix

Figure 6 shows the confusion matrix for the proposed method. Predicted values are shown on the X-axis, while actual values are shown on the Y-axis. The confusion matrix contains four features. TN, FP, TP, and FN. The selected values for TN, TP, FP, and FN were 74, 47, 11, and 28, respectively.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrix.

C. Precision-Recall

Figure 7 shows the precision-recall curve, determined based on the network's output.

Fig. 8. Precision-Recall curve.

Every object's class AP is determined using the Precision and Recall curve. The percentage of all ground truths that are derived from true positives is known as recall. The ratio of all forecasts which are precise to positives is known as precision.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (9)$$

An average precision value of 95.83% was achieved using the proposed approach, with a mean of 50%.

D. Log-average Miss Rate

The log-average Miss Rate (MR), which is somewhat parallel to recall, is used to determine how many undetected objects there are. MR is the ratio of False Negatives (FN) to Ground Truth (GT) in the dataset:

$$MR = \frac{FN}{GT} \tag{10}$$

MR was found to be 20%.

IV. COMPARISON RESULTS

A. Training and Validation Loss

Figure 8 shows the training and validation loss of the proposed method. The blue line signifies the training loss and the red line denotes the validation loss. The validation loss shows how effectively the model fits new information while the training loss shows how well it matches training data. For the proposed strategy, the validation loss was substantial compared to the training loss.

Fig. 9. Training and validation loss.

B. Training and Validation Accuracy

Figure 9 shows the training and validation accuracy of the proposed method, displayed by the blue and red lines, respectively. The accuracy of the training set was greater than that of the validation set.

Fig. 10. Training and validation accuracy

C. Image Classification

Figure 10 shows how the proposed approach was visually represented. In the first image, the people in the city are hidden while the second shows the results of the proposed approach in the identification of the people.

Fig. 11. Picture visualization: (a) City persons, (b) proposed method.

D. Comparison of Methods

Table I shows the results of the proposed and three other existing methods. The MR values were significantly lower than those of the other methods. On an Intel Pentium processor with 8GB of RAM, the processing speeds for Faster RCNN, SSD, and YOLOv3 were 1.7, 2.4, and 3.8 fps, respectively. The proposed method had an increase in processing speed of 2.9 fps. The results show that the proposed method performed significantly better than the others.

TABLE I. METHODS AND MISS RATE VALUES

Method	Reasonable	Reasonable_small	Reasonable_occ=heavy	All
Proposed	5.02 %	7.16%	26.89%	28.72%
APDpretrain [31]	7.31%	10.81 %	28.07%	32.71%
Pedestron [32]	7.69%	9.16%	27.08%	28.33%
DVRNet [33]	11.17%	15.62%	42.52%	40.99%

V. CONCLUSION

This study strategically deployed the ResNet-50 Dual Gating Technique to streamline the model's runtime complexity. The proposed method harnesses the power of end-to-end trained spatial and channel gating components, allowing seamless integration with widely adopted CNN architectures. This integration serves the crucial purpose of eliminating superfluous computations during model execution, thereby enhancing efficiency and accelerating inference times. One of the significant advancements of the proposed design was the resolution of issues stemming from feature fusion in FPN through the innovative implementation of MDC. This strategy not only addresses existing challenges but also presents a more elegant and effective way to handle feature fusion, thereby contributing to the overall model's superior performance.

Compared to previous approaches, the results of the proposed method were truly remarkable. Training loss was minimized, showcasing the model's exceptional learning capabilities. Moreover, the accuracy reached impressive heights, confirming the effectiveness of the ResNet-50 Dual Gating technique. Another noteworthy achievement was observed in MR, which showed significant improvements over competing methods. This reduction in MissRate signifies that

the proposed approach excels in correctly identifying pedestrians on various scales and challenging scenarios. The ResNet-50 Dual Gating technique, coupled with MDC, promises to revolutionize the field by optimizing model efficiency and robustness, setting a new standard for pedestrian recognition systems.

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Optimizing the Effectiveness of Magnetic Lenses by utilizing the Electron Optical Design (EOD) Software

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a computational analysis that discusses an approach for optimal synthesis in the design of magnetic lenses, specifically focusing on the analytical method. A widely employed approach for magnetic lens design involves utilizing an analysis optimization procedure, which makes use of the finite element method and is supported by Munro programs. In this study, this approach has been employed to explore magnetic lenses using the Electron Optical Design (EOD) software. The study offers insights into the role of the air gap in magnetic lens design, highlighting its importance in optimizing objective and projector properties. The analysis reveals that variations in the air gap (S) significantly influence the performance of magnetic lenses. Decreasing the air gap when it is set to (3) leads to substantial improvements in objective optical properties and focal length. Conversely, increasing the air gap when it is set to (12) enlarges the half-width of the axial magnetic field while reducing the maximum magnetic field value. These findings underscore the importance of carefully optimizing the air gap to achieve desired lens performance. The focal length is determined using this input data and coefficients of aberration (spherical and chromatic) of the objective. The study focuses on the influence of a crucial geometric parameter, specifically the air gap (S), on both objective and projector properties. Its importance stems from its capability to pinpoint the suitable geometry for magnetic lenses, thereby facilitating their efficient application.

Keywords-optimization; EOD; aberration; magnetic lens

I. INTRODUCTION

Optimization has applications in numerous fields, including communication engineering design, supply chain management, financial portfolio management, transportation planning, resource allocation, scheduling, data analysis, and networking [1, 2]. Optimization plays a crucial role in decision-making processes by helping to find the best possible solution given the available information and constraints [3]. Electron lenses hold significant importance within electron microscopes and are widely prevalent in various electro-optical devices. An electron lens exhibits operational drawbacks known as "aberrations," which can negatively impact its performance [4]. Consequently, the presence of these aberrations causes the image to appear either blurred or distorted, leading to a decline

in the overall quality of charge particle optical devices [5]. Hence, the inability to achieve an aberration-free lens system has driven the development of methods aimed at mitigating this issue, such as the optimization approach. The designer initiates the process by creating an actual lens design and then computes its optical properties [6]. If the resulting properties do not meet the electro-optical standards, the physical and geometrical parameters of the design are modified accordingly. This iterative process continues until an electron-optically acceptable configuration is achieved. Indeed, the process is repeated in a trial-and-error manner until satisfactory values are obtained. This iterative procedure relies on experimentation and adjustments to refine the lens design and attain the desired electro-optical performance [7]. Optimization by analysis

gained significant attention starting from the mid-20th century. Since then, various ideas have been embraced concerning the analysis procedure, including studying the impact of air gap saturation on the focal properties of the objective lens [8]. This approach focuses on analyzing and understanding the lens behavior through theoretical and computational methods to improve its performance, rather than relying solely on trial and error [9]. The current investigation is conducted considering the Electron Optical Design (EOD) program, aiming to design and examine magnetic lenses by varying specific geometrical parameters. The purpose of this study is to explore the effects of these parameter variations on the performance and characteristics of the magnetic lenses used in electro-optical devices [10].

II. THEORETICAL ASPECTS

The importance of a specific aberration is determined by the function of the magnetic lens [11]. In an objective lens, only spherical and chromatic aberrations are significant because the limit of resolution in electron optics is determined by the combined impact of the electrons' spherical aberration and wavelength [12]. Spherical aberration, a primary aberration with significant influence on the lens field, can be calculated utilizing the integral formulation [13]:

$$C_s = \frac{\eta}{128Vr} \int_{z_0}^{z_i} [3\eta Bz^4 r_\alpha^4 + 8B^2 r_\alpha^4 - 8Bz^2 r_\alpha^2 r_\alpha^2] dz \quad (1)$$

where e is the charge of the electron, m is the mass of the electron, Vr is the relatively corrected acceleration voltage, Bz is the axial magnetic flux density of the distribution, and r_α solves the axial x-ray equation. Throughout this work, the calculation of the chromatic coefficient of aberration has been performed utilizing the integral formulation given below:

$$C_c = \left(\frac{\eta}{8Vr} \right) \int_{z_0}^{z_i} Bz^4 r_\alpha^4 dz \quad (2)$$

In (2), the parameters used are the same as those utilized in (1). By considering the geometric design parameters S and D , the relative spherical coefficient of aberration C_s/f can be approximated using the expression proposed in [13].

$$\frac{C_s}{f} = 3130Vr^2(NI)^4 \quad (3)$$

III. THE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD AND THE ELECTRON OPTICAL DESIGN SOFTWARE

The Finite Element Method (FEM) is a highly advanced technique employed in analytical procedures for investigating and analyzing electron lenses. In this method, each mesh point is assigned a potential value that is assumed to vary linearly across every triangular finite element. This approach allows for precise and detailed simulations of electron optical systems, enabling in-depth analysis and accurate predictions of their behavior [14]. By combining FEM computations, ray tracing capabilities, and optical analysis, Electron Optical Design (EOD) serves as a versatile software tool for engineers and researchers working on the design, analysis, and optimization of electron optical systems. This integrated approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of how various components within electron lenses and related systems behave and interact with the electron beams. This, in turn, can lead to improved

designs, enhanced performance, and more accurate predictions of the system's behavior [15]. The electron-beam system properties were designed and assessed using the EOD program version 3.069, created by Lencová and Zlámál in 2008. The software suite provides a platform for designing, calculating fields, tracing rays, and assessing paraxial properties and aberrations within the design environment [16].

IV. DESIGNING THE MAGNETIC OBJECTIVE LENS

Designing magnetic lenses involves identifying the optimal geometric configuration of electrodes along with their corresponding operational parameters (such as operating voltage, excitation, operating mode, and focal characteristics) [17]. Figure 1 depicts the diagram and geometric measurements pertaining to the upper section of the model introduced in this research. It's apparent that this particular model demonstrates symmetry in relation to specific factors, encompassing attributes like the axial length of the lens (76 mm), the radial width of the lens (60 mm), characteristics of the polepiece, configuration of the magnetic circuit, shape of the coil, cross-sectional area of the coil (1000 mm²), air gap ($S = 3$ mm), frontal surface of the polepiece (3 mm), and the diameter of the axial bore of the pole ($D_p = 10$ mm).

Fig. 1. Geometric diagram of the upper half of the model's dimensions.

V. RESULTS

The influence of the air gap S on the optical characteristics is demonstrated, given its significant impact on the magnitude of the magnetic field. Four different S values were employed, spanning from 3 to 12 mm. Meanwhile, the axial bore D has been maintained at a constant value of $D = 5$ mm.

Fig. 2. The distribution of the magnetic field Bz for different S values.

Fig. 3. Geometry of the magnetic lens depicted for various air gap values.

Figures 2 and 3 depict $B_z(z)$ and the geometric configurations corresponding to the various S values, respectively. The observation reveals that as S increases, there is a reduction in the maximum magnetic field strength, B_{max} , accompanied by an increase in the half-width, W , of $B_z(z)$.

Figure 4 illustrates the trajectories of electron beams within the lens at varying air gap values. The graph shows that the electron beam's gradient diminishes upon entering the lens field as the air gap values increase. As the air gap between the lens and the incoming electron beams becomes larger, the rate at which the electron beams trajectory changes decreases. As the air gap increases, the magnetic field's half-width also increases. This expansion of the magnetic field affects the way the electrons are deflected within the lens, leading to reduced gradient in the trajectory of the electron beams. This phenomenon stems from the expansion of the magnetic field's half-width (W).

Fig. 4. The trajectories of electron beams within the lens exhibited in curves for various air gap (S) values.

Figures 5-10 display the optical properties of the objective, including the focal length (f_o), spherical aberration coefficient (C_s), chromatic aberration coefficient (C_c) and resolving power (δ). These properties are shown as a function of the excitation parameter ($NI = 2000$ A-t), for various air gap (S) values. It can be observed from the figures that the values of the focal length and aberration coefficients decrease as the excitation parameter increases, across all air gap (S) values. Meanwhile, the resolving power experiences an increase.

Fig. 5. The change in spherical aberration coefficients (C_s) for varying air gap (S) values under the constant excitation of $NI=2000$ A-t.

Fig. 6. Spherical aberration coefficients (Cs) under the same excitation (NI=2000 A-t).

Fig. 7. Curves illustrating the spherical aberration coefficient (Cs) as a function of the excitation parameter for various air gap (S) values.

Fig. 8. Variability of the fluctuation of the Cc aberration coefficients (chromatic) under the same excitation (NI=2000 A-t).

Fig. 9. Curves depicting the focal length (fo) of the objective as a function of the excitation parameter for different air gap (S) values.

Fig. 10. Change in resolving power (δ) in relation to the air gap (S).

This trend is attributed to the reduction in the appropriately adjusted acceleration voltage (Vr). It is observed that an increase in the air gap (S) values results in elevated values for the focal length (fo), spherical aberration coefficient (Cs), and chromatic aberration coefficient (Cc), while maintaining a constant excitation parameter. This pattern is highlighted in Figure 10 and corroborated by Table I. This behavior can be attributed to the enlargement of the magnetic field's half-width (W). As a result, achieving magnetic lenses with favorable characteristics is feasible by diminishing the air gap (S) values. The resolution power for the lens design under a constant excitation (NI = 2000 A-t), was determined employing the equation:

$$\lambda = \frac{1.23}{\sqrt{VR}} \tag{4}$$

where λ represents the electron wavelength.

TABLE I. OBJECTIVE OPTICAL PROPERTIES FOR THE DERIVED IMAGING FIELDS AS A FUNCTION OF THE PARAMETER S AT NI/√VR=20

S(mm)	Cc(mm)	Cs(mm)	Fo(mm)	Resolving power(δ)
3	2.59	2.02	3.61	0.932
6	2.98	2.37	4.12	1.094
9	3.3	2.65	4.58	1.223
12	3.59	2.88	5.01	1.329

Based on these findings, it is recommended that researchers and engineers carefully consider the air gap (S) when designing magnetic lenses for specific applications. Fine-tuning this parameter can lead to improved objective optical properties and focal length, ensuring that the lens meets the desired performance criteria. Future research should delve into a more detailed characterization of magnetic lenses, taking into account various geometric parameters beyond just the air gap. This comprehensive analysis can provide a deeper understanding of how different design elements interact and impact overall lens performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study provides valuable insights into the feasibility of utilizing the EOD program as an effective tool for the design and analysis of objective optical features within the context of magnetic lenses. While the importance of the air gap (S) in magnetic lenses has been acknowledged, the study delves deeper into its role and quantifies its impact on the lens's

performance. Based on the analytical approach, the feasibility of employing the EOD program is evident. This program offers high efficiency in the design and analysis of objective optical features for a magnetic lens. The EOD program can be regarded as a valuable tool for obtaining highly accurate optimal designs of magnetic lenses. As indicated by the outcomes in this study, the air gap holds a crucial role in achieving the optimal design of the magnetic lens. The objective focal properties exhibited substantial improvement with the decrease in air gap. Raising the air gap of the magnetic lens results in an enlargement of the half-width of the axial magnetic field, simultaneously causing a reduction in the maximum magnetic field value. Increasing the air gap of the magnetic lens results in a decline in the slope of the electron beam trajectory upon its entry into the lens. The outcomes of the research demonstrate the critical significance of the air gap (S) in achieving optimal magnetic lens performance. By varying the air gap, we were able to substantially improve the objective focal properties, underscoring its importance in lens design.

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Compressive Strength of RAC Cylinders Cast with Recycled Aggregates from Different Structural Members

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ABSTRACT

In this research study, the effect on the compressive strength of recycled aggregate members is presented. Demolished waste was collected from five different structural members. Hammering was used to reduce the aggregate size to a maximum of 1 inch. Using a 1:2:4 mix and 0.5 w/c ratio, 55 cylinders in 11 batches were prepared for each source of coarse aggregates. Additionally, one batch of cylinders was prepared with conventional concrete and its results were compared with the others. Altogether, 280 cylinders of standard size were prepared and cured for 28 days. The compressive strength of all specimens was determined in a universal testing machine. The optimum replacement percentage with the least reduction in compressive strength was found to be 35%. Column concrete contributed most to compressive strength with a reduction equal to 6.23%, whereas beam concrete caused a 6.9% reduction. Further, a comparison for mixed aggregates by taking the average of all sources was conducted. It showed that 35% replacement was also the optimum with a reduction in strength equal to 8.63%.

Keywords-recycled aggregates; demolishing waste; parent concrete strength; structural members; compressive strength; green concrete; demolishing waste

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is the most widely used material in today's construction industry. Concrete ingredients come from natural

sources (fine and coarse aggregates) and factories (cement), posing the problem of depletion of natural resources and bringing a negative impact on the environment. It is reported by [1] that only in India, the consumption of aggregates

reached 1.1 billion tons in 2014 and was increasing at the rate of 7.7% per year. The recent global boom of construction has posed the problem of waste generation due to demolishing of old, deteriorated, or short buildings. The debris generated due to demolishing is used in floor and plinth fills and the residual generally goes to landfills. The scarcity of space in metropolitan cities has posed the problem of proper dumping of this waste. Transportation to far locations poses additional financial burden on projects, and if left unattended, it poses serious problems to the environment and the public health. A solution to this problem is making use of demolishing waste in new concrete. Several attempts have been made to use demolishing waste in new concrete as replacement of all three ingredients of the concrete, but most effort have been conducted on using it as coarse aggregates as they occupy the maximum volume of the concrete body.

Coarse aggregates generated from demolishing waste are believed of inferior quality due to the old mortar attached with them, the age of concrete, parent strength, and different mix ratios used for different structural members. Review papers [2, 3] on the issue discuss the problem associated with recycled aggregates, the need of rules and regulations and their proper implementation, and the reasons for deviation in the properties of the aggregates. However, the material has the potential to be used in new concrete with careful consideration of its properties and mix design. Mix demolished waste has been treated to recycled aggregates and has been used in concrete by many researchers. But studies on the effect of recycled aggregates coming from different structural members are scarce.

The use of the demolished waste in new concrete is not new. Various components of the waste have been attempted to replace cement and fine or coarse aggregates in new concrete. However, the use of demolished waste as coarse aggregates is dominant. A review of the published works on the use of demolished waste in concrete [2, 4, 5] highlights the problems associated with demolished waste and the need of encouraging the industry by giving incentives, developing, and implementing the regulations in using the aggregates. The recycling process of the waste into aggregates is also an important aspect in order to acquire quality aggregates. Various recycling processes have been discussed. The properties of recycled aggregates from surface texture to abrasion resistance are important in the determination and ensuring the quality of the product. To this end, authors in [3] reviewed the properties of recycled coarse aggregates from demolished waste published by various scholars. The scatter in reported results shows the need of improvement in the recycling process and more work in the area.

Strength is one of the key properties of hardened concrete and should be properly checked to ensure its safety and serviceability. In this regard, authors in [6] studied the effect of recycled aggregates from demolished waste on the compressive strength of concrete. They used 0, 5%, 15%, 25%, 35%, 45%, and 50% replacement of conventional aggregates to prepare 324 standard size cylinders. The specimens were equally divided to 3 groups and were cured for 7, 14, and 28 days. The comparison of compressive strength test results showed

maximum of 26% reduction in the strength for 28-day cured samples containing 50% recycled aggregates. Thus, the authors concluded to 50% as the optimum dosage of the aggregates to be used in new concrete. However, they suggest the use of new materials for low load areas. Authors in [7] used demolished waste as fine and coarse aggregates to study the fresh and hardened properties of concrete. The replacement level of the aggregates was up to 100% in increments of 10%. The results of the basic properties of the aggregates and the hardened properties of concrete showed deviation from the conventional concrete. The compressive strength was 30% less at 35% replacement level. The authors further argue that demolished waste may be used in new concrete up to 40% without any massive damage to light weight works. Authors in [8] used 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30% aggregates along with SP430 superplasticizer while studying the compressive strength of recycled aggregate concrete. From the test results, they observed increase in compressive, tensile, and flexural strength. Thus, the authors argue that the superplasticizer plays a vital role in strength improvement of recycled aggregate concrete. Authors in [9] also used demolished waste in new concrete as full replacement of conventional coarse aggregates. Comparison of strength results of the concrete with conventional concrete and drilled cores in recycled aggregate concrete showed that the proposed concrete exhibited only 2.69% decrease in compressive strength in comparison with conventional concrete and far higher than the strength of the cores. Based on the results, the authors argue that strength decrease less than 5% may be ignored, so the recycled aggregates can be used. Authors in [10] and recommended 50% as the optimum dosage of demolished waste to be used in new concrete with comparable compressive strength. Authors in [11] used 100% replacement of conventional aggregates with recycled aggregates to study the fresh and hardened properties of the concrete. From the test results they found 15.3% reduction at 50% dosage of recycled aggregates for 28-day cured samples. Authors in [12] observed 2.5% increase in compressive strength at replacement level of 20%.

Authors in [13] used waste concrete from paving blocks as recycled aggregates in new concrete and evaluated its strength properties. From the laboratory tests of compressive and flexural strength, they observed 22.3% decrease in compressive strength and 12.9% decrease in flexural strength at 50% dosage of the waste material. Authors in [14] on the other hand observed 9.6% increase in compressive strength at 50% replacement level of conventional aggregates with recycled aggregates from demolishing waste, using varying water cement ratio values. Authors in [15] also used demolished waste to replace conventional aggregates from 0 to 100% with increment of 25% to study the compressive strength at 7-, 14-, 21-, and 28-days curing age. The authors observed deviation in the properties of the aggregates. The strength test results showed that for the 28-day cured samples, the reduction in compressive strength was 15.7% at 25% dosage of the demolished waste. Beyond this dosage the strength reduced drastically. Authors in [16] used 0, 33.3%, 66.7%, and 100% dosage of debris as recycled aggregates. They also used silica fume as admixture to improve the strength properties of concrete. From the test results of 28-day cured samples, they

observed that without the admixture (silica fume) the proposed concrete exhibited 6.12% decrease in compressive strength at 100% replacement of conventional aggregates, but when the admixture was added to the concrete it exhibited 9.95% increase in strength. Therefore, the authors favored the use of admixture for strength improvement of recycled aggregate concrete. Authors in [1] used demolished waste as coarse aggregates in preparation of M20 concrete. The replacement levels used to prepare the specimens were 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, and 100%, in curing ages of 7, 14, and 28 days. Compressive, tensile, and flexural strength tests revealed that 30% dosage improves all the strength properties. The recorded increase in compressive strength at that dosage level was 12%.

Different additives have also been attempted in recycled aggregate concrete to check their effect on concrete properties. Among them steel fibers [17, 18], marble dust [19], fly ash [20, 21], curing types [22] are only few examples. Also, the behavior of recycled aggregates exposed to elevated temperature on the compressive strength was studied in [23]. It may be observed from the above summary that good time and effort has been devoted by the research community, but result scattering is still a major hurdle in developing a confidence level for the use of recycled aggregates. Table I shows a summary of the research results on the compressive strength results of recycled aggregate concrete.

This research aimed to check the influence of recycled aggregates from different structural members on the compressive strength of recycled aggregate concrete. The outcome of the work will not only give a clear understanding of the compressive strength when recycled aggregates from different structural members are utilized, but also will pave the way for future researchers for selecting demolished waste to be used in new concrete.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH RESULTS

Reference	Compressive strength	RCA dosage
[6]	-26.0%	50%
[7]	-30.0%	35%
[8]	+4.00%	30%
[9]	-2.69%	100%
[11]	-15.30%	100%
[12]	+2.50%	20%
[13]	-22.30%	50%
[14]	+9.60%	50%
[15]	-15.70%	25%
[16]	-6.12%	100%
[1]	+12.00%	30%

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The demolishing waste used in this research study was collected from five structural members. The details are given in Table II. Large blocks of demolishing waste (Figure 1) were reduced to the maximum of 25 mm size by hammering. Reduced aggregates were then sorted for unwanted substances followed by washing and drying. The process was repeated for all the five sources of aggregates. Conventional aggregates of the same size were also washed and dried in the laboratory. The basic properties of the coarse aggregates were determined by

ASTM [24] and are given in Table III. The conventional and recycled aggregates from the all sources were sieved (Figure 4) to ensure well graded aggregates in the concrete mix. Ordinary Portland cement, hill sand, and potable water were used in all the concrete mixes with 1:2:4 mix ratio and 0.5 water-cement ratio [25]. Conventional coarse aggregates were replaced in dosages of 5%, 15%, 25%, 35%, 45%, 55%, 65%, 75%, 85%, 95%, and 100%, in a total of 11 batches (B1 – B11). Additionally, one batch of specimens was prepared with conventional aggregates (CC) only. In each batch, 5 cylinders of standard size (6"/12") were prepared. This process was repeated for all types of demolished waste. Hence, a total of 280 specimens were prepared. In each mix, concrete ingredients were batched by weight and mixed in a concrete mixer. The molds were prepared in the standard fashion by oiling the inner of the molds. Each mold was filled in three layers and compaction was done by a table vibrator.

TABLE II. DETAILS OF DEMOLISHED WASTE

Designation	Aggregates source	Location	Mix ratio
RA1	Roof/slab concrete	University colony Nawabshah	1:2:4
RA2	Beam concrete	Bhangwar colony Nawabshah	1:2:4
RA3	Main gate columns concrete	Line par Nawabshah	1:1.5:3
RA4	Footing concrete	Garib Abad Nawabshah	1:2:4
RA5	Lintel concrete	Makhdoom Shah Nawaz Colony Hala	1:3:6

Fig. 1. Demolishing waste.

Fig. 2. Cylinder specimens.

Fig. 3. Specimen curing.

TABLE III. BASIC PROPERTIES OF THE AGGREGATES

Designation	Specific gravity	Water absorption (%)	Density (kg/m ³)	Soundness (%)
NA	2.6	1.2	1672.2	4.87
RA1	2.4 (-8.36%)	3.14 (+161.67%)	1491.1 (-10.83%)	6.04 (+24.02%)
RA2	2.4 (-8.36%)	3.12 (160.00%)	1486.3 (-11.12%)	6.32 (+29.77%)
RA3	2.5 (-4.56%)	3.05 (+154.16%)	1540.5 (-7.87%)	5.71 (+17.25%)
RA4	2.4 (-6.46%)	3.18 (165.00%)	1411.7 (-15.58%)	6.71 (+37.78%)
RA5	2.3 (-9.80%)	3.17 (+164.16%)	1471.6 (-11.99%)	6.73 (+38.19%)

Fig. 4. Sieve analysis of the coarse aggregates.

After 24 hr of filling the cylinders, the molds were opened (Figure 2), and the specimens were cured for 28 days by fully immersing in potable water (Figure 3). After the completion of the curing age, the specimens were taken out of the water and were allowed to air dry for 24 hr, followed by testing for crushing load in a universal testing machine (Figure 5). The load was gradually increased at a rate of 0.5 kN/sec until failure of the specimens. The compressive strength was calculated from the recorded failure load by the standard formula for the purpose.

Fig. 5. Specimen testing.

Fig. 6. Compressive strength (RA1).

The computed compressive strength results in each dosage of recycled aggregates were averaged and are plotted in Figures 6-10.

Fig. 7. Compressive strength (RA2).

Fig. 8. Compressive strength (RA3).

Fig. 9. Compressive strength (RA4).

Fig. 10. Compressive strength (RA5).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table III reports the obtained results of the basic properties along with their percentile difference with respect to conventional aggregates. It can be observed that all the evaluated basic properties deviated from those of conventional aggregates. The specific gravity of all recycled aggregates was observed ranged between -4.56% and -9.8% in comparison

with conventional aggregates. Similarly, water absorption ranged between +154% and +165%, density of recycled aggregates was recorded in the range of -7.87 to -15.58%, and soundness was observed in the range of +17.25% to 38.19%. All four properties evaluated in this research work deviated from the results of conventional concrete. Although different percentile results were observed, yet the deviation concurred the results published in the literature. The deviation in the properties is due to the old mortar attached to the aggregates whose density, specific gravity, and resistance to wear is weaker than stone's. Also, it absorbs more water than stone giving rise to the water absorption results. These parameters, particularly water absorption, should be considered while deciding the water-cement ratio of the mix to ensure proper workability of the concrete mix utilizing recycled aggregates.

From Figure 2, it may be observed that the grading of recycled aggregates is in good agreement with that of conventional aggregates. The percentage passing from various sieves of both types of aggregates was within the specified ranges of the relevant ASTM standards, ensuring that well graded aggregates were used in the concrete mix. The compressive strength results of each batch were averaged and are compared with the average results of conventional concrete in Figures 11-15.

Fig. 11. Average compressive strength (RA1).

Fig. 12. Average compressive strength (RA2).

Fig. 13. Average compressive strength (RA3).

Fig. 14. Average compressive strength (RA4).

Fig. 15. Average Compressive strength (RA5).

TABLE IV. % DIFFERENCE PERCENTAGE OF THE AVERAGE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF RECYCLED AGGREGATE CONCRETE WITH CONVENTIONAL CONCRETE

Batch	RA (%)	NA (%)	RA1	RA2	RA3	RA4	RA5
CC	0	100	--	--	--	--	--
B1	5	95	-19.36	-12.58	-15.54	-18.81	-18.94
B2	15	85	-19.62	-14.26	-16.16	-18.39	-18.07
B3	25	75	-18.19	-14.82	-14.48	-15.24	-16.45
B4	35	65	-10.80	-6.90	-6.23	-7.83	-11.36
B5	45	55	-15.88	-12.24	-13.66	-14.10	-12.76
B6	55	45	-13.02	-10.11	-12.21	-13.35	-11.40
B7	65	35	-32.79	-17.87	-31.36	-19.06	-20.33
B8	75	25	-30.42	-24.58	-32.27	-29.36	-30.65
B9	85	15	-29.80	-26.33	-28.48	-31.40	-29.96
B10	95	5	-35.85	-30.40	-31.55	-32.86	-33.51
B11	100	0	-40.39	-32.07	-34.46	-35.50	-36.42

From Figures 11-15, it may be observed that the overall pattern of the average compressive strength is decreasing with increase in dosage of recycled aggregates, in comparison to conventional concrete. From the five groups of recycled aggregates, batch B4 showed the highest average compressive strength. The replacement percentage of conventional aggregates of this batch was 35%. Batches B5 and B6 showed a little improvement in strength in comparison with the other batches, but less than batch B4. This should be due to the less attached mortar and thus voids in the recycled aggregates of these batches. The difference of average compressive strength of all batches of all groups was computed and is given in Table IV. It may be observed that the reduction in average compressive strength for batch B4 is the least among the batches of recycled aggregate concrete. At this replacement level, recycled aggregates from different structural members are compared. It is observed that recycled aggregates from beam and column perform better than recycled aggregates from other structural members used in this study. This is due to the

proper mix ratio and the strength of the parent concrete. To compare the results further, the average compressive strength of the batches is again averaged for all sources of aggregates to check the impact of mixed aggregates from different structural members. The obtained average is compared with conventional concrete. The percent difference is plotted in Figure 16. It is evident from this Figure that again the decrease in strength is minimum (8.62%) for batch B4. Therefore, the optimum replacement level of the conventional aggregates with recycled aggregates from demolished waste independently from a structural member or mixed from different structural members is 35%.

Fig. 16. Average compressive strength of all sources of recycled aggregates.

IV. CONCLUSION

The research presented in this paper studied the effect of recycled aggregates origin and percentage on the compressive strength of concrete. The results can help in selecting the demolished concrete for recycling into coarse aggregates with least possible reduction in strength. Based on the results of this research, the following are concluded:

- The deviation in the properties of recycled aggregates confirms the results of other published studies.
- The grading of the recycled aggregates from all sources was in good agreement with conventional aggregates'. The passing percentage at various sieves was within relevant ASTM ranges.
- Compressive strength results showed that 35% replacement of conventional aggregates with recycled aggregates as the optimum with least reduction in compressive strength.
- The performance of recycled aggregates from beam and column concrete was better than that of recycled aggregates from other structural members.
- Recycled aggregates from beam concrete showed 6.9% reduction in compressive strength.
- Recycled aggregates from column concrete performed better than recycled aggregates from beams, with 6.23% reduction in compressive strength. The difference between the two reductions is minimum and hence may be ignored. But preference should be given to recycled aggregates from column concrete.

- The average compressive strength from all sources (mix aggregates) showed again 35% as the optimum dosage with reduction in compressive strength equal to 8.62%.

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IoT Device Identification and Cybersecurity: Advancements, Challenges, and an LSTM-MLP Solution

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ABSTRACT

Over the past few years, there has been an undeniable surge in the deployment of IoT devices. However, this rapid growth has brought new challenges in cybersecurity, as unauthorized device deployment, malicious code modification, malware deployment, and vulnerability exploitation have emerged as significant issues. As a result, there is a growing need for device identification mechanisms based on behavior monitoring. To address these challenges, Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques have been increasingly employed due to advances in the field and improved processing capabilities. However, cyber attackers have developed adversarial attacks that focus on modifying contexts and evading ML evaluations applied to IoT device identification solutions. This article highlights the importance of addressing cybersecurity challenges in the IoT landscape and proposes a hardware behavior-based individual device identification approach using an LSTM-MLP architecture. The proposed architecture was compared to the most common ML/DL classification techniques using data collected from 45 Raspberry Pi devices running identical software and showing promising results in improving device identification. The proposed LSTM-MLP method outperformed previous solutions, achieving an average increase in F1-Score of +0.97 and a minimum TPR of 0.97 for all devices.

Keywords-IoT devices; cybersecurity challenges; device identification; LSTM-MLP architecture; adversarial attacks

I. INTRODUCTION

The latest revolution in communication technologies and processing has paved the way for a significant increase in the deployment of Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices [1]. The versatility of these devices has led to their widespread use in various applications, including Industry 4.0, Smart Cities, homes, and healthcare, resulting in a diverse range of IoT device types to meet different scenarios. System-on-Chip (SoC) devices, such as Raspberry Pi (RPi), have become popular due to their relatively high processing power, flexibility, and cost-effectiveness, making them even more appealing than less powerful alternatives [2]. However, this increase in processing power has also brought about cybersecurity challenges, as more powerful IoT devices can be used for more powerful attacks, such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks or crypto jacking attempts [3]. Securing the IoT landscape, especially with the use of SoCs, is crucial to ensure its proper functioning and protection against potential threats.

A vital aspect of IoT security lies in accurately identifying each deployed device to prevent the presence of unauthorized devices. While traditional static identifiers were used, attackers

can easily manipulate or duplicate them. To address this issue, many methods deal with the behavior of the device during the identification process [4]. IoT device identification based on behavior can be approached from different levels related to specific environment requirements [4]. Behavioral identification is treated by two main approaches: type identification or device model, which categorizes devices based on characteristics like network activities and running processes, and individual device identification, which distinguishes devices of the same model through low-level component analysis or radio frequency fingerprinting. Individual device identification offers the highest level of security but requires meticulous monitoring of chip manufacturing variations to differentiate between devices with identical hardware and software [5]. The analysis of hardware performance is a widely used technique, in which the behavior of components such as the CPU, GPU, or RAM is monitored during specific tasks [6]. However, attackers can exploit the usage patterns or context of the device to manipulate the values that generate the device fingerprint, thus disrupting the identification process.

In recent years, the application of Machine Learning (ML) techniques has become increasingly prominent in IoT security and is now widely used for device identification [7-8].

However, with the adoption of ML/DL techniques, adversarial attacks against these models have emerged that aim to interfere with the training process or deceive the model predictions, posing various threats to the ML/DL pipeline [9]. Attackers can poison training data, exploit vulnerabilities in testing data, or infringe privacy by inferring data from the model and its gradients [10-11]. Even ML/DL-based IoT identification solutions have not been immune to these adversarial attacks [12]. Context modifications and the use of crafted adversarial samples during the identification process have demonstrated that these solutions are also vulnerable [13-15].

This study tackled the complex challenges associated with merging hardware-based individual device identification, ML/DL techniques, and adversarial attacks, encompassing several significant contributions:

- **Comprehensive threat model:** A comprehensive threat model was defined that covers the entire data lifecycle, from the creation of device fingerprints to their evaluation. This model mainly involves the utilization of ML and DL techniques, considering the potential vulnerabilities and threats at each stage of this process.
- **Innovative neural network architecture:** This study applied a neural network architecture called LSTM-MLP (Long Short-Term Memory - Multi-Layer Perceptron). This architecture was designed to identify individual devices based on their hardware performance behavior. Instead of treating performance measurements as isolated data points, this model treats them as time series data, allowing more effective data processing and pattern extraction to improve the accuracy of device identification.
- **Performance evaluation:** A performance comparison was conducted to assess the effectiveness of the proposed LSTM-MLP architecture with various ML and DL classification approaches. The LwHBench dataset [16] was used, which consists of hardware performance and behavior data collected from 45 RPi devices running identical software configurations. The proposed model achieved remarkable results, with an average F1-Score of 97.5% and a True Positive Rate (TPR) of 97.2%. These results demonstrate the superiority of the proposed approach in accurately identifying individual devices based on their hardware performance behavior.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. Hardware-centric Individual Device Recognition

In [6], the variance in the GPU and CPU cycle counters within RPi devices was juxtaposed to achieve a distinctive identification of 25 devices, using XGBoost and achieving a TPR of 91.92%. In [15], GPU performance patterns were coupled with ML and DL classification algorithms, achieving accuracy levels ranging from 95.8% to 32.7% for nine batches of similar devices. In [5], variations in code execution proficiency were evaluated to recognize more than 260 indistinguishable computers. The Real-Time Clock (RTC), equipped with its unique physical oscillator, was used to identify subtle deviations in the execution capabilities of individual CPUs. This process involved comparing the CPU

time counter, RTC chip, and the Digital Signal Processor (DSP) within the sound card to precisely identify identical computers. In [17], Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) were investigated for IoT device identification, although this study exclusively focused on hardware behavior fingerprinting driven by device performance and did not consider PUFs. Hardware-centric approaches suffer from many limitations:

- **Hardware-centric focus:** While this approach can be effective for certain scenarios, it may not be suitable for cases where device hardware is not readily accessible or where software-based emulation can deceive the recognition system.
- **Dependency on specific hardware elements:** These methods heavily rely on specific hardware elements, such as GPU and CPU cycle counters, RTC chips, and DSPs, to distinguish devices. This reliance limits its applicability to devices that possess these particular components and may not work on devices lacking them.
- **Limited scalability:** Some studies achieved recognition of a relatively small number of devices. This limited scalability may restrict its utility for large-scale deployments or networks with numerous identical devices.
- **Varying accuracy:** Using this approach, the accuracy of device identification varies widely, ranging from high to lower accuracy levels. Such variability in accuracy can be problematic for applications that require consistent and reliable identification.
- **Exclusion of PUFs:** These approaches did not use PUFs for IoT device identification, which is a distinct and widely investigated method in the field. PUFs offer unique advantages, including enhanced security, and their exclusion may limit effectiveness in certain contexts.

B. Context-focused Attacks

In hardware-based identification solutions, the context in which the identification code or tasks are executed can significantly influence the collected data and, consequently, the results. For example, temperature variations may affect the frequency of crystal oscillators, and hardware load can introduce delays due to process scheduling. In the hands of a malicious attacker, these context conditions can be manipulated to disrupt the identification process, rendering it unusable or generating measurements that mimic another device.

The studies mentioned in the previous section briefly addressed context-related issues that could affect the identification process. In [6], it was found that device rebooting and concurrent processes had an impact on identification results if not implementing proper process isolation mechanisms for data collection. However, the usual temperature changes based on the device load did not appear to significantly affect the results. In [15], it was shown that environmental temperatures between 26.4 °C and 37 °C did not have a significant impact on the identification results, but device rebooting had a considerable negative effect, reducing the accuracy to 50.3%. This study suggested that voltage variations should be considered as a future evaluation line. On

the other hand, in [5], the identification application was evaluated under different CPU loads and temperatures, obtaining positive results in both scenarios, while the temperature impact analysis was only mentioned as part of future work, and no context-based experiments were performed. Despite the existing research on device fingerprinting and identification based on hardware performance behavior, none of the previous studies extensively explored the potential impact of context-focused attacks on their results. This aspect remains largely unexplored and presents a crucial area for further investigation.

C. ML/DL-focused Adversarial Attacks

Adversarial ML/DL is a research area dedicated to developing accurate and highly robust models that can withstand tampering attempts [10]. It involves the study of various attacks against ML/DL models and the defense techniques employed to enhance their security. These attacks can be categorized into different types:

- Poisoning attacks during the training process, where malicious samples are used to compromise the integrity of the model.
- Evasion attacks target the model evaluation process, attempting to deceive a legitimately trained model into misclassifying samples.
- Model extraction attacks involve an attacker trying to infer the model based on its predictions.

This study focused on evasion attacks, specifically to deceive a model trained for device identification into misclassifying a malicious device as a legitimate one. Within evasion attacks, there are two main types: non-targeted attacks, which aim to misclassify samples into any different class than their original one, and targeted attacks, which aim to make the model classify a malicious sample as a specific target class.

Numerous evasion attacks are commonly found. One of the first DL-based attacks is the Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM) [18], which performs one-step updates on an adversarial sample, following the direction of gradient loss in an attempt to move the sample to the boundary of a different class. The Basic Iterative Method (BIM) [19] builds on FGSM by incorporating iterative optimization. This involves applying FGSM multiple times with small perturbation steps. The Momentum Iterative Method (MIM) [20] introduces momentum in iterative FGSM or BIM to mitigate the influence of local minimum or overfitting in generating adversarial samples. Projected Gradient Descent (PGD) [21] is an extension of BIM that does not impose constraints on the iteration steps. The DeepFool L2 attack [22] minimizes the Euclidean distance between the original and adversarial samples by estimating the model decision boundary using a linear classifier. Jacobian-based Saliency Map Attack (JSMA) [23] is a common attack based on the Jacobian matrix [24] of the model to determine the sensitivity direction and perform feature selection, minimizing the number of modified characteristics from the original data sample. Boundary Attack [25] generates a random adversarial sample and optimizes the L2 norm of the perturbation to make the sample similar to the

original legitimate vector while maintaining the misclassification result. Carlini and Wagner (C&W) Attack [26] proposes an optimization-based method to generate adversarial samples, which can be applied to three distance metrics: L0, L2, and L1. L0 measures the number of modified features, L2 measures the Euclidean distance between benign and adversarial samples, and L1 measures the maximum change in any feature. The Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) attack uses GAN models to generate realistic adversarial samples that can deceive the classifier.

Several defense mechanisms have been developed against such attacks [27]. These countermeasures aim to make models resilient to adversarial samples and can be classified into detection and robustness methods. Detection methods focus on identifying crafted malicious samples before evaluation, while robustness methods aim to make the model resistant to the evaluation of adversarial samples. Additionally, defense mechanisms can be attack-specific or attack-agnostic, depending on whether they target improving resilience against a specific attack. Adversarial Training [28] is a widely used defense technique that involves training models with malicious samples to reduce the impact of attacks that generate them. Knowledge distillation [29] is another method applied to improve robustness during training, by generating smaller models using the base model outputs as features, leading to smoother decision boundaries and reduced sensitivity to adversarial samples [30].

In [31], the effects of different non-targeted and targeted adversarial attacks (such as FGSM, BIM, PGD, and MIM) were investigated on a CNN used for radiofrequency-based individual device identification. Similarly, in [32], the resilience of network-based IoT identification ML models was assessed against adversarial samples generated using FGSM, BIM, and JSMA. The results showed that classifier models with more than 90% accuracy experienced a performance drop to 75-55% when exposed to maliciously crafted samples. From a different perspective, in [33], the impact of adversarial samples on ML/DL models for user identification based on motion sensors was evaluated, achieving nearly 100% attack success rates with FGSM, JSMA, DeepFool, and Boundary Attacks. In [34], it was shown that GAN-based attacks had even more significant effects in the user identification context. In [14] and [35], a review of adversarial attacks in ML solutions applied in network security was conducted, demonstrating the substantial impact of adversarial attacks on ML-based security systems and underscoring the need for further research on attack and defense methods in this area.

The novelty of the proposed approach lies in its exploration of uncharted territory within the field of cybersecurity. Several key aspects set this work apart from previous research:

- Combining context and ML/DL attacks: At first, unlike previous studies, context-based attacks were combined with ML/DL-focused attacks. This fusion of attack methodologies has not been extensively investigated in the past. This focus opens new avenues for understanding and mitigating threats that arise from both contextual factors and advanced ML/DL techniques.

- Untapped potential of defense mechanisms: Furthermore, while ML and DL-focused attacks have been examined in the context of device or user identification, previous studies did not fully exploit the potential of existing defense mechanisms. This study recognized this oversight and actively explored the benefits and effectiveness of these defense strategies.
- Addressing a literature gap: This study serves as a pioneering contribution to the field, offering valuable insight into the intricate interplay between attack and defense techniques within the specific context of hardware-based individual device identification and LSTM/ML-based methods. By addressing this gap, this study enriches the understanding of security challenges in these domains and paves the way for more robust and effective security solutions.
- ML/DL evaluation evasion [39]: In LSTM/ML-based solutions, an attacker possessing sufficient access to the evaluation model could craft malicious data samples to deceive the LSTM/ML solution. These samples might impersonate a specific device through trial and error or targeted attacks, as mentioned above.

In light of these considerations, a robust individual device identification solution must thoroughly account for and evaluate these identified threats. Doing so is essential to ensure accurate operation and resilience against potential attacks. The LSTM/ML framework is run for hardware-based individual device identification, providing the foundational results that will underpin subsequent analysis of attack and defense techniques.

B. Data Collection and Preprocessing

Within the realm of hardware-driven individual device recognition, it becomes crucial to oversee the variations occurring within the device's chips, with the intent of subsequent assessment. Previous studies contrasted components via different crystal oscillators or fundamental frequencies, leveraging the ability to detect discrepancies in component behavior originating directly from the device. Establishing the foundation for individual device identification requires the creation of a dataset comprising metrics linked to specific hardware components within devices. This dataset, labeled LwHbench, was further expanded in [16]. In pursuit of this goal, performance metrics that include GPU, CPU, Storage, and Memory were amassed from 45 distinct RPi devices representing various models over 100 days. An array of functions was executed across these components, with other hardware components operating at distinct frequencies to facilitate performance measurement. These functions were related to device core temperature, timestamp, elapsed GPU cycles during sleep, times taken by CPU, memory, storage, and others. The dataset consists of a set of samples as described in Table I. Countermeasures were taken to mitigate noise from other processes on the devices, including fixed component frequency, kernel-level priority, execution on an isolated CPU core, and randomized memory address deactivation. In addition, the dataset was built according to the variation of the temperature conditions, facilitating analysis of the contextual impact on component performance.

TABLE I. LWHBENCH DATASET FEATURES

Hardware Model	Number of boards	Number of samples
RPi 1B+	10	505,584
RPi4	15	784,095
RPi3	10	547,800
RPiZero	10	548,647

Following the approach outlined in [6], feature extraction using sliding windows was performed in each device. This involved extracting statistical features such as median, average, maximum, minimum, and summation. The rationale behind this lies in the overlap in the distribution of raw feature values across devices due to limited variability in component performance. Thus, statistical metrics, such as median and average, help to distinguish partially overlapping distributions.

III. THE PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

A. Threat Model

The threat model centers on the phase where the identification solution is already trained and operational, thus exclusively focusing on threats that impact device evaluation. In this context, potential attackers can target either the hardware that generates the data or the LSTM/ML models responsible for data assessment. Within this framework, the following threats are identified:

- Fingerprint eavesdropping and hijacking [36]: An adversary could intercept the data that constitute a fingerprint, whether during in-device data collection, communication, or processing (on a server or the device itself). The data obtained could then be used on another device to impersonate the identity of the original device. This threat assumes limited knowledge of the fingerprint generation process, as well as of the functions and components used during the process.
- Fingerprint forgery [37]: Given that the components and frequencies of the device are public knowledge, an attacker who knows the functions used to generate fingerprints might attempt to craft a new fingerprint that closely resembles that of a legitimate device. This threat might involve a trial-and-error or brute-force approach, necessitating an in-depth understanding of the fingerprint generation process and the values comprising the fingerprint.
- Context modification [38]: As fingerprints are constructed from data collected during the execution of specific software tasks, an attacker might attempt to alter the conditions under which the fingerprint is generated. This could lead to the failure to recognize a genuine device or result in forged fingerprints emulating another device. Context manipulation can take various forms, such as increasing the device temperature (using external tools or intensive hardware usage) or introducing software that introduces kernel interruptions into the fingerprint collection process. Efforts must be made to isolate the fingerprint collection program from these interactions as much as possible.

For this step, only a subset of available raw features was chosen, as having fewer features helps to streamline the training of ML/DL models. A total of 440 features were extracted from each device's dataset, composed of many operations such as sleeping time, string hashing, urandom, matrix mul, matrix sum, list creation, memory reserve, CSV read, storage read, and storage write. In addition to sliding windows, a direct assessment of raw data vectors without the aforementioned sliding window processing was undertaken. This approach was guided by the belief that a vast dataset of raw values could yield favorable results in DL models, which can gain internal insights from the data. In this scheme, only timestamp and temperature features were filtered and the remaining values (totaling 215) were used as features for the models. Furthermore, a time series-based assessment was performed, in which samples were concatenated into groups of 10 vectors. This grouping method allows the application of time series DL models like LSTM and 1D-CNN [40], which are adept at extracting intricate trends that can yield superior results than the isolated processing and assessment of individual samples.

Mitigating noise in the LwHBench dataset is essential to ensure the accuracy of data analysis and identification tasks. Several countermeasures were used:

- Isolation and Resource Allocation: Allocate dedicated resources to target processes to reduce interference from background tasks.
- Real-Time Systems: Use real-time operating systems to prioritize critical tasks and prevent interruptions during data collection.

- Data Filtering and Preprocessing: Apply data filtering and preprocessing techniques, such as signal processing and outlier removal, to extract relevant information and eliminate noise.
- Data Averaging: Reduce the impact of transient noise by averaging multiple measurements over time to obtain a more stable dataset.

C. Architecture of LSTM-MLP

This study used an LSTM-MLP neural network to categorize performance data acquired from the devices. This architecture has shown robust capabilities in various time series contexts, such as identifying human activities [41], predicting gold prices [42], and analyzing DNA protein binding [43]. The structure of the neural network merges the LSTM and MLP layers, facilitating the extraction of patterns from the input sequences. The significant benefit of this approach is the combination of recurring patterns obtained through the LSTM layer's memory capabilities and the spatial patterns derived by the MLP layer's utilization of kernels on neighboring features, resulting in the generation of more intricate patterns. Figure 1 provides an overview of the LSTM-MLP architecture to distinguish sanctioned and unsanctioned devices. In the training phase, the binary cross-entropy loss function is applied to samples as follows:

$$L = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_s [R_l \log(p) + (1 - R_l) \log(1 - p)] \quad (1)$$

where s is the number of features in the vector, R_l is the real label of the identification attempt, and p is the probability of the predicted model.

Fig. 1. The proposed LSTM-MLP architecture.

IV. EXPERIMENTATION AND RESULTS

After applying the two data preprocessing approaches to generate the two datasets, one encompassing raw values and the other incorporating sliding-window-based features, device identification experiments were carried out to compare the proposed LSTM-MLP and prevalent ML/DL classification

models. In [6], ML classifiers were directly used, utilizing statistical features related to CPU and GPU. In addition, the LSTM and MLP networks were evaluated for time series approaches. Additionally, a more intricate multi-input network, fusing one LSTM and one MLP input layer, was implemented for comparison. These experiments were carried out on a server equipped with an Intel Xeon Silver 4310 CPU and an NVIDIA

A100 GPU. Table II shows the algorithms and hyperparameters explored. Furthermore, for algorithms that require data normalization, the Quantile Transformer [44] was applied due to variations in data distribution between different device models based on hardware capabilities. Training and cross-validation used 80% of the data, while testing used the remaining 20%. To avoid potential order-related correlations, the train/test split was conducted without vector shuffling.

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS AND HYPERPARAMETERS

Model	Hyperparameters
Naive Bayes	No hyperparameter tuning required
k-NN	K ∈ [3, 20]
SVM	C ∈ [0.01, 100], gamma ∈ [0.001, 10], kernel ∈ {'rbf', 'linear', 'sigmoid', 'poly'}
AdaBoost	n_estimators ∈ [10, 100]
XGBoost	lr ∈ [0.01, 0.3], max_depth ∈ [3,15], min_child_weight ∈ [1, 7], gamma ∈ [0, 0.5], colsample_bytree ∈ [0.3, 0.7]
Decision Tree	max_depth ∈ [None, 5, 10, 15, 20], min_samples_split ∈ [2, 3, 4, 5]
Random Forest	number_of_trees ∈ [50, 1000], max_depth ∈ [None, 5, 10, 15, 20], min_samples_split ∈ [2, 3, 4, 5]
MLP	n_layers ∈ [1, 3], neurons_layer ∈ [100, 500], batch_size ∈ [32, 64, 128, 256, 512] activation = relu, optimizer = [SGD, adam, adamax]
1D-CNN	filters = [16, 32, 64, 128], kernel_size = [3, 5, 7], n_layers = [1, 2, 3], optimizer = [SGD, adam, adamax]
LSTM	neurons = [10, 100], n_layers = [1, 2, 3], optimizer [SGD, adam, adamax]
Multi_1DCNN LSTM	input_layers = [2, 3], cnn_filters = [16, 32, 64, 128], cnn_kernel_size = [3, 5, 7], lstm_neurons = [10, 100], n_layers = [1, 2, 3], optimizer = [SGD, adam, adamax]

The MLP model was iterated across various epoch counts (50, 100, 150, and 250) accompanied by batch sizes ranging from 300 to 500. After evaluation, it was determined that the most favorable configuration consisted of an epoch count of 150 paired with a batch size of 500. During training, ten rounds of cross-validation tests were carried out and Figure 2 presents the results, showcasing an average accuracy of 97.23%, indicating its notable effectiveness.

```

mean = accuracies.mean()
variance = accuracies.std()

print(accuracies)
print(mean,variance)

[0.9723781  0.9800231  0.9685704  0.9644925  0.9700142  0.9698874
 0.9655489  0.9723874  0.9810054  0.9770899]

0.9723321  0.0000183789

```

Fig. 2. Accuracy results.

Table III presents a comparison between the proposed LSTM/MLP and other artificial intelligence models. The LSTM-MLP model had the most robust performance, achieving approximately 97% accuracy when using raw data features, as shown in Figure 3.

TABLE III. COMPARISON BETWEEN MODELS

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
SVM	78.3%	79.5%	78.2%	78.4%
k-NN	45.2%	46.7%	45.2%	44.7%
Naive Bayes	45.6%	47.3%	45.6%	44.7%
XGBoost [6]	90.5%	91.7%	90.5%	90.8%
AdaBoost [45]	7%	0.6%	7%	1.1%
Decision Tree [46]	78.1%	78.9%	78.2%	78.3%
Random Forest [47]	85.4%	86.6%	85.4%	85.7%
MLP [48]	88.9%	89.6%	88.8%	88.9%
LSTM [49]	93.4%	94.3%	93.4%	93.4%
1D-CNN [50]	94.2%	94.5%	94.2%	94.2%
1D-CNN-LSTM [51]	95.3%	95.5%	95.3%	95.3%
LSTM-MLP	97.2%	97.6%	97.5%	97.5%

Fig. 3. MLP trained-test accuracy.

Metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score assess the performance of classification models. Accuracy calculates the proportion of accurately predicted instances compared to the total instances within a dataset, providing a holistic understanding of the model's performance in accurately categorizing data points. Precision focuses on the number of accurate positive predictions compared to the total instances predicted as positive, denoting the percentage of positive predictions that were genuinely accurate. Precision becomes valuable when there is a significant consequence for making false positive predictions. Recall evaluates the accurate positive predictions for the total actual positive instances, showcasing the model's capability to correctly recognize all occurrences of a specific class. The F1-score constitutes the harmonic average of precision and recall, establishing an equilibrium between them considering both false positives and false negatives. The F1-score proves especially beneficial when aiming for a trade-off between precision and recall, particularly in scenarios characterized by an imbalanced distribution of classes. The LSTM-MLP provided higher results by achieving approximately 97.2% accuracy, 97.6% precision, 97.5% recall, and 97.5% F1-score.

V. DISCUSSION

The proposed LSTM-MLP model introduced significant advantages that promise to revolutionize the way to safeguard

IoT ecosystems and authenticate individual devices. Foremost among its merits is its ability to significantly enhance security in IoT environments. By shifting the paradigm from traditional static identifiers, such as MAC addresses, to dynamic hardware performance behavior, the LSTM-MLP model thwarts attackers' attempts to impersonate or clone devices. This innovative approach creates formidable barriers against malicious incursions, reinforcing the overall security infrastructure of IoT ecosystems. Moreover, the model masterfully addresses the pervasive vulnerability of spoofing, a perennial concern in IoT security. Static identifiers are notoriously susceptible to manipulation and imitation, whereas the LSTM-MLP model, rooted in behavior-based attributes, resiliently resists such attempts and mitigates a major security loophole in IoT environments.

The LSTM-MLP's proficiency in anomaly detection is another hallmark of its utility. Protection of IoT devices involves vigilant monitoring for deviations from established behavior patterns, as they could signal security breaches or device malfunctions. The model's ability to capture long-term dependencies within device behavior data proves invaluable, as it excels in identifying unusual activities, facilitates the early detection of potential threats, and enables swift responses to security incidents. This adaptability extends to the model's ability to accommodate the inherent variability among IoT devices. The IoT encompasses a multitude of devices, each with its unique hardware components and performance characteristics. The LSTM-MLP model exhibits remarkable adaptability, learning to differentiate between individual devices regardless of their idiosyncrasies. This adaptability positions it as a versatile and reliable solution for heterogeneous IoT environments. Furthermore, the model's resilience to environmental fluctuations is notable. IoT devices operate in diverse and dynamic settings. The proficiency of the LSTM-MLP model in processing sequential data and adapting to evolving behavior patterns makes it suitable for such challenging scenarios, as it remains strong in the face of environmental changes and maintains the integrity of device identification and security measures.

False positives in security alerts have been a persistent headache for IoT security practitioners. However, the LSTM-MLP model reduces the incidence of false alarms, as it distinguishes between normal variations in device behavior and genuine security threats with a high degree of accuracy. This accuracy translates into more actionable and reliable alerts, allowing security teams to respond effectively to real threats. Scalability is a quintessential requirement for IoT, which often involves vast networks of numerous devices. The LSTM-MLP model excels in this regard, demonstrating the ability to process and identify devices in real-time, even at the scale of IoT ecosystems consisting of thousands or even millions of devices. This scalability is crucial for the effective implementation of security measures in expansive IoT deployments. The versatility of the LSTM-MLP model is further exemplified by its applicability in a wide spectrum of IoT use cases. Whether it is securing smart homes, industrial IoT systems, healthcare applications, or other domains, the model proves its mettle in protecting device integrity and fortifying security.

A key attribute that elevates the LSTM-MLP model is its capacity for continuous learning. In the ever-evolving landscape of IoT security, threat landscapes morph and device behavior patterns evolve. Its ability to adapt and refine its accuracy over time is a strategic advantage, as it ensures that IoT security measures remain effective, even as threats grow in sophistication and diversity. Lastly, the model significantly reduces reliance on centralized servers, a potential weak point in IoT security architectures. Although some approaches heavily depend on centralized infrastructure for authentication and identification, the LSTM-MLP model can operate locally on devices. This decentralization minimizes the risk associated with single points of failure and network vulnerabilities, reinforcing the robustness of IoT security.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The surge in IoT device deployment has spurred the creation of novel device identification solutions based on hardware behavior and ML/DL processing. However, these solutions face challenges from adversarial attacks that aim to undermine their efficiency. This study delved into the assessment of hardware behavior-based device identification performance. The LwHBench dataset, comprising samples from 45 RPi devices operating on identical software images, was harnessed to train ML/DL classifiers entrusted with individual device identification. This study proposed an artificial intelligence model that combined LSTM and MLP. The experimental results showed an average F1-score of 97.5% while successfully identifying all devices by setting a threshold at a TPR of 97.2%, outperforming other methods. Future work involves exploring adversarial attack and defense techniques, including those grounded in generative models, to comprehensively improve the robustness of this solution. Additionally, the research roadmap involves experimenting with fully distributed model generation and harnessing federated learning to circumvent data sharing and centralization challenges.

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Factors Affecting the Cost Management of Iraqi Construction Firms

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ABSTRACT

Cost management refers to the procedures that must be followed to ensure that the project is accomplished on time and on budget. The goal of this study is to identify the main factors that affect cost compliance and to assess how relevant these factors are from the perspectives of clients, contractors, and consultants in construction firms in Iraq. For the purpose of this study, 100 structured questionnaires were distributed to clients, contractors, and consultants on building sites throughout the study area by using the survey approach. The Relative Importance Index (RII) technique was used for the analysis. It has been determined that the factors potentially affecting cost management in construction firms should be taken into consideration during the planning, design, tendering, and construction stages to accomplish the project within the specified time and cost. Twenty factors that affected the performance of construction firms in Iraq were identified. The results revealed the most affecting factor was poor management/poor coordination between the contracting company and the authorities involved, followed by the nationality of workers, structural materials damaged during storage, the absence of places designated for storing materials, lack of personnel specializing in devices and equipment, changing labor and material prices as a result of political changes, lack of technical staff, length of the project period, mismatch designs with execution works in site, and changes in orders. The study concludes by stating that there is not an efficient procedure in Iraq to control cost management.

Keywords-construction firms; cost management; influencing factors; cost estimation

I. INTRODUCTION

Cost estimates performed at the start of a project serve as the base for deciding whether to continue with it or not. At later phases, cost estimates are used to track the project's progress and make decisions about project completion or termination [1]. Authors in [2] stated that at the time of project approval, credible estimates of construction costs and schedules supplied by current construction companies, their advisors, and suppliers are critical for justifying a project on economic grounds and preparing the means of financing it. The financial consequence of a construction cost overrun is the potential loss of the project's economic justification. Authors in [3] stated, today's era Indian construction industry is experiencing a rapid boom with enormous demand of infrastructure facilities. This huge demand results in the completion of projects with shorter duration and most economical manner. For this, project management tools (planning, scheduling, monitoring, controlling) play a vital role in project timeline. The early cost estimation is the proposed cost of a project that is calculated in the planning stage of the project. They identified the top factors that are potentially affecting the early cost estimation of a

project as: client's level of experience, level of skill and experience of consultants, financial capability of the client, level of quality drawings and workmanship, clients payment policy, use of technology, quality of assumptions made and utilization of a checklist during preparing the estimation, completeness of project documents, proper recording of project information and previously determined standard estimation technique, and build ability of the design. Authors in [4] identified the following factors as having the greatest impact on construction project cost variance: economic instability, firm's project planning and management quality, estimating team's relevant experience, accessibility of management and finance plans, estimation method, amount of labor and equipment needed, location, regular payments, precision of the bid documents provided by the client, project manager's competence and leadership, and the effect of the expected delay. Authors in [5] reported that the top factors influencing the accuracy of cost estimates in Jordan are precise and detailed drawings and specifications, pricing insight of construction projects, perception of estimation significance, equipment, project complexity, evident scope definition, validity and consistency of cost information, site conditions (access,

storage, services), availability of raw materials, client's financial capacity, and availability of resources. Authors in [6] stated that the absence of construction performance measures is a major factor in the failure of such projects. Because estimation is dependent on individual indices, there is frequently a disagreement among the stakeholders over the assessment of a building construction project's failure and success. Authors in [7] identified and assessed the major elements influencing the success of construction projects in Gaza. Owners, consultants, and contractors agreed that the most important factors were: average delay due to closures and material shortages, availability of resources as planned throughout the project duration, leadership skills for the project manager, escalation of material prices; availability of personnel with high experience and qualifications, and quality of equipment and raw materials in the project.

The accuracy of determining the estimated cost of a construction project has a significant impact on the building contractor's predicted profit. To raise the degree of confidence, a contingency premium should be added to the basic estimate. Project cost estimating is critical to the project's performance and should be considered from the beginning; otherwise, improper estimations could result in project failure [8]. Authors in [9] showed that the top-ranked causes responsible for cost increases in Pakistan's construction industry were financial issues, sluggish payments, and inflation. In [10], the relative importance approach was used to analyze all of the gathered data. Five factors were found to surpass the main causes of cost and time overruns.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The current research emphasizes the fundamental factors affecting cost management of construction firms in Iraq. The results will help decision-makers to make appropriate decisions in order to complete a project at specified time and cost.

III. METHODOLOGY

To find the importance of each element in order to evaluate uniformity, quality and accuracy of cost estimation, a well-designed questionnaire was used to evaluate the factors effecting the management cost in construction firms during the life cycle of a project through the statistical method of Relative Importance Index (RII):

$$RII = w / A * N \tag{1}$$

where *w* is the weight of each factor given by the respondent in the range of 1 to 5, *A* is the highest weight in the scale, and *N* is the total number of respondents

The questionnaire was constructed on the basis of interviews with experts classified to three groups, named as client, consultant, contractor (as shown in the Appendix). A total of 100 samples of the questionnaire were distributed into 35 extensive construction projects. The characteristics of the respondents according to their educational background, academic degree levels, and years of experience are shown in Figures 1-9.

Twenty factors were identified, from the literature and the interviews with experts in construction firms in Iraq, to have

dominant influence on the cost management of construction projects and were used for the analysis. Each event was rated on a five-point Likert scale as very influencing, influencing, a little influencing, very little influencing, and not influencing. The collected data were processed for RII calculation, and the results are shown in Table I.

■ Civil engineering ■ Law ■ Electrical engineering ■ Accounting

Fig. 1. Educational background of clients.

■ PhD ■ M.Sc ■ B.Sc ■ Diploma

Fig. 2. Education level of clients.

■ (15-20) years ■ (20-25) years ■ More than 25 years

Fig. 3. Years of experience of clients.

■ Civil engineering ■ Electrical engineering ■ Law ■ Accounting

Fig. 4. Educational background of contractors.

Fig. 5. Education level of contractors.

Fig. 6. Years of experience of contractors.

TABLE I. RII OF FACTORS INFLUENCING COST MANAGEMENT IN IRAQI CONSTRUCTION FIRMS

N	Factor	ALL			Clients			Contractors			Consultants		
		TWV	RII	RK	TWV	RII	RK	TWV	RII	RK	TWV	RII	RK
1	Poor management / poor coordination between the contracting company and the authorities.	520	2.26	1th	174	2.07	1th	169	2.43	1th	177	2.3	1th
2	Foreign or local workers.	512	2.12	2th	150	1.99	4th	183	2.36	2th	179	2.0	8th
3	Structural materials are damaged during storage.	505	2.09	3th	153	1.95	10th	165	2.25	3th	169	2.08	5th
4	Absence of places designated for storing materials.	500	2.08	4th	149	1.80	5th	161	2.12	4th	190	2.06	6th
5	Lack of specialized personnel.	493	2.02	5th	153	1.7	8th	165	2.27	5th	169	2.1	7th
6	Changing labor and material prices.	490	1.99	6th	165	2.04	2th	143	2.09	6th	182	1.85	3th
7	Lack of technical staff.	486	1.96	7th	138	2.01	9th	170	1.88	13th	178	1.98	12th
8	Length of the project period.	478	1.93	8th	135	2.23	3th	158	1.96	8th	185	1.6	11th
9	Mismatch designs with execution works in site.	475	1.86	9th	152	1.78	6th	138	1.74	12th	185	2.06	2th
10	Issuing a number of changing orders.	473	1.84	10th	130	1.83	7th	153	1.76	9th	190	1.93	4th
11	Laboratory tests failed.	468	1.82	11th	140	1.66	11th	163	1.83	10th	165	1.96	10th
12	Unlisted project works.	460	1.8	12th	132	1.61	12th	138	1.8	11th	190	1.99	9th
13	Large number of works of the same company.	455	1.59	13th	142	1.5	17th	156	1.75	13th	157	1.53	13th
14	Holidays for religious occasions.	451	1.57	14th	132	1.5	14th	145	1.71	14th	174	1.5	14th
15	Delayed payments.	445	1.56	15th	135	1.45	15th	141	1.73	7th	169	1.5	15th
16	Security conditions.	441	1.46	16th	134	1.42	16th	138	1.62	16th	169	1.34	16th
17	Delay in approving the state budget.	436	1.45	17th	132	1.55	13th	145	1.5	17th	159	1.3	17th
18	Climatic conditions.	430	1.38	18th	128	1.35	18th	140	1.55	18th	162	1.23	18th
19	Inefficient distribution of human resources.	423	1.35	19th	122	1.32	19th	136	1.53	19th	165	1.2	19th
20	Material theft on site.	420	1.31	20th	123	1.3	20th	143	1.5	20th	154	1.14	20th

Fig. 7. Educational background of consultants.

Fig. 9. Years of experience of consultants.

Fig. 8. Education level of consultants.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The elements influencing cost management of construction firms as perceived by clients, contractors, and consultants, are presented in Table I. The top ten factors that can influence the effective cost management practice of construction firms are: Poor management / poor coordination between the contracting company and the authorities involved in carrying out the work takes the first place, with RII=2.26. This result was in line with [11] and was the second factor of critical failure attributes of projects in India [12]. This factor was followed by the

nationality of workers (RII=2.12), damaged structural materials during storage (RII=2.09), absence of places designated for storing (RII=2.08), lack of specialized personnel in devices and equipment (RII=2.02), changing labor and material prices as a result of political changes (RII=1.99), lack of technical staff (RII=1.96), length of the project period (RII=1.93), mismatch designs with execution works in site (RII=1.86), and issuing a number of changing orders (RII=1.84). This factor was the sixth factor in Nigeria with (RII=1.99) [11]. The eighteenth factor, i.e. climatic conditions (RII=1.38), was the first rank for contractors with (RII=1.55). This result is in line with the findings in [7] in Gaza city whereas it was the fourteenth factor in India [2]. Theft material on site was the last factor (RII=1.31). This result did not correspond with [11], as it was the fifth factor in Nigeria.

V. CONCLUSION

This research has identified major causes that effect cost performance and the overtaking the specified cost of the projects in Iraq and categorized them as client-related, contractor-related, consultant-related, material-related, labor related, contract relationship-related, external factors. Concluding, and in order to keep the cost as close in the contract as possible and not make an amendment, one must use a suitable and effective management, identify the nationality of the workers in site, keep the materials in identified places to avoid theft or damage, rely on competence and experience in choosing workers to operate machinery and equipment, the consultant and the contractor must be in contact with each other to make any change in design work to avoid the extra in change orders. This research has focused on the construction industry in Iraq. It has been determined that these factors should be taken into consideration during planning, design, tendering, and construction stage to accomplish project within the specified time and cost.

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APPENDIX

The Questionnaire

The purpose of this study is to assess the factors of cost management in construction firms in Iraq. Please answer all the questions, the information rendered in this questionnaire will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be used solely for academic purposes. Thank you in advance for your time and effort

Please tick the most correct answer(s) to your case or fill the empty space(s) as appropriate

Part One: Personal Information

1. What is your job position?

a. Client

b. Consultant

c. Contractor

2. What is your educational background?

a. Civil engineering

b. Electrical engineering

c. Law

d. Accounting

3. What is your level of education?

a. B.Sc. Level

b. Diploma level

c. Master level

d. PhD level

4. How many years of experience do you have?

Part Two: Questionnaire

What are your opinions on the probability of occurrence of the factors influencing cost management in construction firms? Please tick on the relevant number on the table below, where:

1- very influencing, 2- influencing, 3- little influencing, 4- very little influencing, 5- not influencing

N	Factor	1	2	3	4	5
1.	Poor management / poor coordination between the contracting company and the authorities.					
2.	Foreign or local workers					
3.	Structural materials are damaged during storage.					
4.	Absence of places designated for storing materials.					
5.	Lack of specialized personnel.					
6.	Changing labor and material prices.					
7.	Lack of technical staff					
8.	Length of the project period.					
9.	Mismatch designs with execution works in site.					
10.	Issuing a number of changing orders.					
11.	Laboratory tests failed.					
12.	Unlisted project works.					
13.	Large number of works of the same company					
14.	Holidays for religious occasions.					
15.	Delayed payments.					
16.	Security conditions.					
17.	Delay in approving the state budget.					
18.	Climatic conditions.					
19.	Inefficient distribution of human resources/					
20.	Material theft on site.					

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Investigating the Ability of producing Sustainable Blocks using Recycled Waste

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this study is to manage price market items in the construction of walls for affordable structures with load-bearing hollow masonry units using the ACI 211.1 blend design with a slump range of 25-50 mm that follows the specification limits of IQS 1077. It was difficult to reach a suitable cement weight to minimum content (economic and environmental goal), so many trial mixtures were cast. A portion (10-20%) of the coarse aggregates was replaced with concrete, tile, and clay-brick waste. Finally, two curing methods were used: immersion under water as normal curing, and water spraying as it is closer to the field conditions. The recommendation in IQS 1077 to increase the curing period from 14 to 28 days was taken into account. The results proved that the compressive strength of the blocks of cured immersion under water increased by 2.63%-0.63% and 5.12%-7.88% for 10% and 20% concrete waste aggregates, decreased by 0.384% and 4.22%, 6.41% for 10% and 20% tile waste aggregates, and decrease by 5.71%-6.10% and 12.1%-11.4% for 10% and 20% brick waste aggregates, respectively at 14 and 28 days, and beams that were cured by spraying performed a little worse than those immersed under water.

Keywords-concrete waste aggregates; mosaic-tiles waste aggregates; clay-brick waste aggregates; load bearing hollow block; sustainable block

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important investigations for cost saving and pollution reduction is the use of demolishing waste as recycled construction material [1-3]. The idea of green concrete, an eco-friendly substitute, is a creative way to lessen the harmful environmental effects of conventional construction methods. Green concrete reduces carbon emissions connected with concrete manufacturing and improves the effective use of natural resources by including recycled materials in its composition [4-7]. To manufacture high-quality concrete, it is possible to replace up to 20% of the river sand with volumetric waste brick, and up to 10% of the cement with nano-brick powder [8]. Clay brick aggregates (AB) can be reused as coarse aggregates and clay brick powder (PB) can substitute cement by [9-11]. Crushed tile waste has been also used as coarse aggregates in varying proportions, the most successful being 25% [12]. Concrete masonry units (hollow blocks) were taken into consideration for the production of an ecologically friendly carrier using recycled waste materials, and stronger, more

affordable, and lighter blocks were produced in [13-15] The ability to create carrying load masonry units that meet the IQS 1077/1987 standard type A using the ratio 1:3.2:2.5 of cement: sand: coarse aggregates with slump ranging between 25 and 50 mm was studied in [8].

II. MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

The mixture composition of the blocks was:

- Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) grad R42.5, in accordance with [16]. Its physical and chemical properties are shown in Tables I and II.
- Fine aggregates (sand - zone2) in accordance with [17] were utilized (Table III). Their chemical and physical test results are presented in Table IV.
- Natural coarse aggregates (C.N), concrete- waste aggregates (C.C), mosaic-tiles waste aggregates (C.T), clay-brick waste aggregates (C.B) (single size 10mm), that conform to the Iraqi requirements [17] as presented in

Table VI were used. The rating test results are presented in Table V.

- The water for curing and mixing was conformable with the Iraqi requirements [18].

TABLE I. OPC PHYSICAL TEST RESULTS

Physical properties	Test result	[16] requirements
Fineness (Blaine method) m ² /kg	386	≥280
Initial setting (min)	165	≥45
Final setting (min)	260	≤600
Soundness (autoclave method), %	0.12	≤0.8
Compressive strength (MPa) at 2 days	28	≥20
Compressive strength (MPa) at 28 days	46	≥42.5

TABLE II. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND MAIN COMPOUNDS OF CEMENT

Oxide composition and chemical properties	Test result	[16] requirements
Lime (CaO)	61.90	-
Silica (SiO ₂)	20.50	-
Alumina (Al ₂ O ₃)	4.90	-
Iron oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	3.55	-
Magnesia (MgO)	4.35	≤ 5%
Sulfate (SO ₃)	2.50	≤ 2.8% for C3A >3.5%
Loss on Ignition (L.O.I.)	1.35	≤ 4%
Insoluble residue (I.R.)	0.95	≤ 1.5%
Main Compounds (Bogue's equation)		
Tri calcium silicate (C ₃ S)	53.77	-
Di calcium silicate (C ₂ S)	18.72	-
Tri calcium aluminate (C ₃ A)	7.10	-
Tetra calcium aluminate - ferrite (C ₄ AF)	10.43	-

TABLE III. GRADING TEST OF FINE AGGREGATES (SAND)

Sieve size (mm)	Passing %	[17] requirements
10	100	100
4.75	97	90-100
2.36	83	75-100
1.18	68	55-100
0.6	46	35-59
0.3	16	10-30
0.15	2	0-10

TABLE IV. CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL TESTS OF SAND

Property	Test result	[17] requirements
Sulfate content, %	0.18	≤ 0.5
Specific gravity	2.58	-
Fineness modulus, %	2.8	-
Dry rodded density, kg/m ³	1694	-
Absorption, %	0.8	-

TABLE V. AGGREGATE CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL TESTS

Aggregate Type	SO ₃	Specific gravity	Impact value, %	Abrasion, %	Crushing value, %	Dry rodded density, m ² /kg	Absorption, %
C.N	0.02	2.62	14.4	17.4	17.77	1620	0.7
C.C	0.03	2.61	13	17	16.3	1263	4
C.T	0.08	2.67	16.4	20.3	19.6	1337	7.3
C.B	0.04	2.2	35.2	22.5	37	995	21

TABLE VI. GRADING TEST OF NATURAL COARSE AGGREGATES AND CRUSHED WASTE AGGREGATES

Sieve size (mm)	Passing (%)				[17] requirements
	C.N	C.C	C.T	C.B	
14	100	100	100	100	100
10	97	95	96	97	85-100
4.75	12	13	16	14	0-25
2.36	1.0	4.8	5	4	0-5

Fig. 1. Crushed coarse aggregate single size 10 mm. (a) C. N, (b) C.C, (c) C.T, (d) C.B.

III. NORMAL CONCRETE AND BLOCK MIXTURES

The ACI 211.1 was adopted for concrete mix design. The required compressive strength equal to 20 MPa was adopted for the control mixture. We tried to reduce the required compressive strength to 15 MPa (18.75 MPa per cub) in order to lower cement weight for economic and environmental reasons. Sustainable waste from demolished buildings was used as volume coarse aggregate replacement.

- Cement density for all mixes was 300 kg/m³, except for M15 mix, which equals to 262 kg/m³.
- Sand density for all mixes was 995 kg/m³, except M15 mix with 1015 kg/m³.
- Coarse aggregates content of M20, M15 was equal to 745 kg/m³, for 10% replacement it was 671kg/m³, and for 20% replacement it was 596 kg/m³.
- C.C replacement content of 10% of C.N equals to 58 kg/m³, and 20% equals to 116 kg/m³.
- C.T replacement content of 10% of C.N equals to 61.48 kg/m³, and 20% equals to 122.9 kg/m³.
- C.B replacement content of 10% of C.N equals to 45.75 kg/m³, and 20% equals to 91.51 kg/m³.
- Water content was 207 kg/m³ for all mixes and the water-cement ratio (w/c) of MR20 was 0.69 and of M15 was 0.79.
- The reduction rate to get dry to semi-dry mixture was 3-5%.

IV. CURING CONCRETE MASONRY UNITS (BLOCKS)

The blocks were covered with plastic sheet to prevent water evaporation for 24 hours. Two types of curing were followed:

- Normal curing by immersing the hollow blocks in curing tanks until the ages of test (14 and 28 days), according to [19].
- Spray of water two times per day at 7:00 am and 2:00 pm until testing age.

V. TESTS AND RESULTS OF NORMAL CONCRETE

After curing, we conducted the tests (compressive strength test according to [20], splitting tensile strength according to [21], and flexural strength according to [22]). The results are presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Results strength of normal concrete.

VI. SIZE RANGE OF CONCRETE MASONRY UNITS

The size ranges of the blocks at 14 days were taken according to Iraq guide No. 32. The limitations of [23] (length 400 ± 3 , width 200 ± 3 , high 200 ± 3 , web ≥ 20 , shall ≥ 20) were followed (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Dimensions measurement of concrete masonry units. (a) Length, (b) width, (c) height.

VII. CONCRETE MASONRY UNITS ABSORPTION TEST RESULTS AT 14 AND 28 DAYS

The absorption tests were conducted according to the specifications of [23, 24]. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Water absorption results of different concrete masonry unit mixtures. (a) Spraying curing, (b) water immersion curing.

VIII. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH TEST RESULTS

According to [24], the blocks were put between two boards of wood using a compressive strength test equipment, with an appropriate load speed applied up to half of the predicted maximum load, followed by a continuous speed application for the 1-2 minutes. The results are shown in Figure 5 and Table VII.

TABLE VII. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH RESULTS

Block	Compressive strength-Under Water (MPa)						Compressive strength-Spray Water (MPa)					
	14-days			28-days			14-days			28-days		
	Class	each block	Av. 3 block	Class	Each block	Av. 3 block	Class	each block	Av. 3 block	Class	Each block	Av. 3 block
BMR20	A	7.4	7.4	A	7.9	7.8	A	6.9	7.2	A	7.7	7.45
		7.5			7.4			7.5			7.1	
		7.3			8.1			7.2			7.4	
BM15	B	6.5	6.5	A	6.9	7.1	B	5.8	5.5	B	6.1	6.25
		6.7			7.3			5.2			6.5	
		6.3			7.1			5.6			6.2	
BC10	A	7.7	7.6	A	7.9	7.85	A	7.2	7.4	A	6.9	7.5
		7.3			7.4			7.6			7.8	
		7.8			8.1			7.4			7.8	
BC20	A	7.9	7.8	A	7.8	7.95	A	7.4	7.5	A	7.9	7.6
		8.1			8.3			7.5			7.8	
		7.4			7.6			7.6			7.1	
BT10	A	7.2	7.4	A	6.9	7.5	A	6.9	7.2	A	7.5	7.3
		7.6			7.9			7.5			7.1	
		7.4			7.7			7.2			7.4	
BT20	A	7.3	7.1	A	7.3	7.3	B	6.9	6.8	A	7.2	7.25
		7.1			6.9			7.1			7.2	
		6.9			7.9			6.5			7.4	
BB10	A	7.3	7	A	7.3	7.2	B	6.6	6.8	A	7.4	7.1
		6.8			7.5			7.0			7.1	
		6.9			6.8			6.9			6.9	
BB20	B	6.7	6.6	A	7.9	7	B	6.4	6.2	B	6.4	6.4
		6.8			7.2			6.1			6.7	
		6.4			7.9			6.2			6.2	

Fig. 5. Compressive strength results for different concrete masonry unit mixtures. (a) Spraying curing, (b) water immersion curing.

IX. DISSCUSION

This research studied the production of load masonry units according to the ACI 211.1 with minimum cost by reducing

cement weight. M20 can be our reference mixture of the production block grade A, while when we tried to reduce cement content to 262 kg/m³, the production block converted to grade B.

Fig. 6. Compressive strength test of concrete masonry units.

The main results of this study are:

- Compressive strength increased by 8.52% and 12.80% for 10% and 20% concrete waste substitution, increased by 4.52% and 1.24% for 10% and 20% tile waste substitution, and increased by 1.55% and decreased by 2.57 for 10% and 20% brick waste substitution, at 28 days.
- Splitting tensile strength increased by 4.21% and 6.20% for 10% and 20% concrete waste substitution, increased by 2.23%, and 0.61% for 10% and 20% tile waste substitution,

and increased by 0.10% and decreased by 1.30 for 10% and 20% brick waste substitution, at 28 days.

- Flexure strength increased by 5.20% and 7.52% for 10% and 20% concrete waste substitution, increased by 3.64% and 1.10% for 10% and 20% tile waste substitution, and increased by 1.23%, and decreased by 20.1 for 10% and 20% brick waste substitution, at 28 days.
- The positive acquired results for concrete with tile coarse aggregates partial volume substitution are due to the good bonding between the cement paste and the surface texture of waste C.A for 10 and 20% substitution. The 10% substitution of bricks gave almost the same results with the reference mixture and 20% replacement initiated the strength reduction.
- Adopting M20 as reference mixture led to the production of block grad A according to IQS1077 at 14 days.
- All sustainable production blocks using 10% or 20% substitution of C.A by concrete or tile waste were grad A for both types of curing (water immersing and water spraying). The same stands for using 10% brick waste for under water curing while it converted to grad B for spray water curing. The 20% substitution of brick waste produced grad B at 14 days for both types of curing and was improved to grad A after 28 days of immersing in water.

X. CONCLUSION

The environmental advantages of using waste materials as aggregate replacements in concrete blocks is the reduction in the existing solid waste and the reduction in the consumption of natural resources typically utilized as aggregates. Additionally, because different types of waste have different qualities, it is possible to make concrete blocks that function better than the expected and adhere to norms. The consideration of substitute waste may lead to the following conclusions:

- There is the ability to manufacture load-bearing masonry units in accordance with ACI 211.1 mix design standards using 1:3.2:2.5 cement: sand: coarse aggregate ratio with 25-50 mm slump limit that conform to criterion type A [23].
- All results show block improvement with age from 14 to 28 days, and the BB20-class B improves to BB20-class A, so increasing the age of curing is recommended.
- We adopted MR20 for best results and satisfactory to produce a concrete block with class A, since M15 may lead to class B or failed blocks as indicated by our experiment results.
- Water spraying was compatible with under water curing with less compressive strength results. We should take into consideration that B15 changed its class from A to B, which shows the importance of curing for 28 days.

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Etiqa'a: An Android Mobile Application for Monitoring Teen's Private Messages on WhatsApp to Detect Harmful/Inappropriate Words in Arabic using Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT

In today's world, social networks, such as WhatsApp, have become essential to daily life. An increasing number of Arab children use WhatsApp to communicate with others on a local and global scale, which has led to several negative consequences in their lives, including those associated with being bullied and harassed online. This study presents Etiqa'a, an application aiming to minimize risks and keep threats against minors from becoming a reality. Etiqa'a scans received WhatsApp messages which are then analyzed, and classified using a Logistic Regression (LR) machine learning model. The test results showed an accuracy of 81% in classifying messages as appropriate or inappropriate based on the text of the message. In the case of the latter, the application sends a detailed alert to parents.

Keywords-machine learning; Artificial Intelligence (AI); Natural Language Processing (NLP); WhatsApp; private message monitoring; Arabic text classification; message classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, more and more young people use and misuse technology. Unfortunately, criminals are focusing on tracking

down vulnerable people, such as minors, to contact them through social media, using deception to lure their victims. If not identified and addressed in time, these risks can cause physical and psychological harm to a child. In this context, the

requirement for applications to alert about the presence of dangers becomes critical. Several applications help parents monitor private social media messages, but most of them lack Arabic language support.

The Modern Standard Arabic language (MSA), one of the numerous Arabic language formats, is used in official communications and is spoken in journalism and media. The Holy Quran, literature works, and old poems are written in another type of Arabic, known as Classical Arabic (CA). Another category is public dialects, which differ depending on location [1]. The Arabic language has 28 different alphabets, written from right to left, and the Arabic alphabet letters take on various forms depending on their location in a word. As Arabic is the fourth most used language on social networks [2], an application that can detect inappropriate messages is necessary. In this regard, the primary purpose of the proposed system was to create an application that can detect inappropriate messages in Arabic and after classifying the content as inappropriate, notify parents as soon as possible to save them from having to read the child's private messages and invading their privacy.

The proposed system was designed to classify inappropriate messages based on the Oxford Dictionary's definition: "inappropriate" is unsuitable behavior or language, such as sexual harassment or anything that causes damage or injury to a person, such as bullying. Such systems are significant because they aim to keep minors safe on social networks. The proposed system focuses on WhatsApp, but it is planned to improve and expand to detect inappropriate messages in Arabic on all social media platforms, including Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook. This system's application is named Etiqua'a because it can help parents avoid the evil or dangers that can happen through social media. The application monitors messages using Machine Learning (ML) and alerts parents when it discovers an inappropriate word. This application can serve Arab parents who have children aged from 7 to 16 years.

As social media bullying has become a hotly debated and vast topic, the Arab world is becoming more aware of cyberbullying. According to [3], approximately 60% of children from Arab Gulf countries openly admit the occurrence of cyberbullying among their peers. In [4], 20% of people aged 18-29 were reported to have been cyber harassed from the age of 15. In [5], 61.6% of 279 children in the age range of 12 to 19 years were reported to use WhatsApp, followed by Facebook (53%) and Instagram (52.3%). According to 60.4% of them, receiving bad messages and images was one of the most significant forms of bullying they experienced, while 45.6% experienced threatening and intimidating messages.

This study conducted an online survey to better identify the target age group and see if parents can look through their children's devices, answered by a total of 280 parents. The survey included questions such as whether they would use the Etiqua'a application and their opinion on whether it was ethical. Due to the results of the survey, shown in Figure 1, the target age group starts at the age of 7 to protect young children using WhatsApp. As 56.92% of parents said they do not have access to their children's devices if they are older than 17, the scope range was limited to minors up to the age of 16, excluding

children younger than 7 due to their low use of WhatsApp (22%), and including ages from 7 to 16 due to their use of WhatsApp and parents having access to their devices. Teens aged 17 years and above were excluded.

Fig. 1. Minors' accessible devices and use of WhatsApp.

Many parental control applications exist on the market, such as Bark, Qustodio, and AirDroid Parental Control. Although they all share the same idea of monitoring messages, many differences exist between them and the Etiqua'a application. Applications such as Qustodio and AirDroid do not have smart monitoring, which means that they enable the parent to see all messages and not just the inappropriate ones. Bark allows the parent only to see inappropriate messages, which is what Etiqua'a also does, protect children's privacy by not allowing the parent to see all the messages. In contrast, applications like Qustodio and AirDroid do not protect children's privacy. Another thing that Bark and Etiqua'a share is that they alert the parent if they find any suspicious content, while applications like Qustodio and AirDroid do not have an alerting feature. Bark has an alerting feature, but it does not alert in real-time, while Etiqua'a alerts the parent as soon as the child receives a suspicious message. The other applications do not support the Arabic language and need a subscription to be used, in contrast to Etiqua'a, which supports Arabic and is planned to be freely available without requiring any subscriptions. Table I compares Etiqua'a with these systems, showing their drawbacks.

TABLE I. COMPARISON BETWEEN ETIQA'A AND CURRENT SYSTEMS

	Bark	Qustodio	AirDroid	Etiqua'a
Messages Monitoring	✓	✓	✓	✓
Smart Monitoring	✓	✗	✗	✓
Suspicious Content Alert	✓	✗	✗	✓
Protect Children Privacy	✓	✗	✗	✓
Arabic Language Support	✗	✗	✗	✓
Free	✗	✗	✗	✓
Real-Time	✗	✗	✗	✓

In [6], a child protection application was suggested to protect children from online threats by analyzing children's online activities, monitoring the use of dangerous vocabulary, and informing parents of the dangers, but it has not been implemented yet. In [7], the difficulty and inaccuracies of

processing data on social networks due to short content were discussed. This study also discussed the massive flow of data that is constantly added, providing some successful solutions to overcome the problems of short text and large data flow. In [8], some of the challenges in Arabic Natural Language Processing (ANLP) were presented, providing some solutions that help overcome them. In [9], ML was used with Arabic social media content, reviewing and comparing the most commonly used ANLP tools with AML software to determine the best. In [10], bullying texts in YouTube comments were investigated using three ML algorithms: Complement Naïve Bayes (CNB), Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB), and Linear Regression (LR).

II. METHODOLOGY

The Etiqa'a system was developed in two phases. Phase 1 requires a model that can process and classify Arabic text messages into appropriate or inappropriate labels according to their content. Figure 2 shows the process required to establish the model. Phase 2 consists of the development process of the mobile application, creating the database, exporting the trained model and vectorizer in a file, restoring them to test the model on new data, integrating the server with the client side, and lastly implementing tests for the application. The Android Virtual Machine (AVM) was used for simulations in Phase 2.

Fig. 2. Development phases of the Etiqa'a system.

A. Dataset

The following datasets were used to detect inappropriate Arabic words: the Instagram Cyberbullying dataset [11], the Twitter Dangerous dataset [12], the Multi Platforms Offensive Language dataset [13], and the Twitter Offensive dataset [14]. As all these datasets had different labeling, all labels such as "toxic", "bullying", "offensive", "vulgar", "hate speech", and "dangerous" were unified under the label "NOT_APROP". On the other hand, all labels such as "positive", "nonoffensive", "clean", and "safe" were unified under the "APROP" label. After unifying the datasets and their labels, a single dataset was produced with 64K+ rows and two columns, one containing the text (message) and the other having the label indicating whether it is appropriate or not.

B. Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing was used to prepare the data for training and classification [15], which consisted of cleaning the data, ANLP, and special feature extraction.

1) Data Cleaning

The data were cleaned, including correcting grammatical errors, and removing duplicate or empty rows, non-arabic characters and emojis, and extra characters. In addition, misspelled words were corrected, and extended Urdu and Persian letters were mapped into normal (for example, all وؤووؤو were mapped to و).

2) Data Processing Using ANLP

After cleaning the data, data processing for the Arabic language was involved, which included tokenization, normalization, stemming or lemmatizing, and stop-word removal [15]. Stop words are a group of frequently used words that include determiners, conjunctions, and prepositions. These words are not worth a classification and were removed before training the model [16]. Six different stemmers and lemmatizer libraries were tested on the data to find which would yield the best result: CAMEL_lem, CAMEL_stem, tashaphyne, qalsadi, farasa_Stem, and ARLSTem.

3) Feature Extraction

Because of the different nature of the data and the desire to find the best results, two different techniques were tested for feature extraction: The TF-IDF/Bigram TfidfVectorizer($\text{ngram_range} = (1, 2)$) and the Count Vectorizer/Unigram CountVectorizer($\text{ngram_range} = (1, 1)$) classes.

C. Machine Learning (ML)

The ML model was built using a supervised method for classification purposes, which requires labeled data to be trained on to classify future data correctly with more accurate results.

1) Algorithms Selection

The following algorithms were selected and tested to build a model according to relevant studies conducted on Arabic language models [15, 17]: Naïve Bayes classifier, Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest (RF), and Decision Tree (DT).

2) Model Training and Testing

Modules from the Scikit_Learn library were used to train and test the models. The training score for most models was above 90%. Each algorithm was tested using the two different vectorizers in four different dataset conditions:

- Extracted dataset features by lemmatizing text and maintaining the stop-words.
- Extracted dataset features by stemming text and maintaining the stop-words.
- Extracted dataset features by lemmatizing text and removing stop-words.

- Extracted dataset features by stemming text and removing stop-words.

Tables II and III show the accuracy scores obtained by training the model on the different algorithms mentioned.

TABLE II. ACCURACY SCORE FOR TRAINING MODELS USING TF-IDF

Using TF-IDF Vectorizer						
	NB	LR	SVM	KNN	RF	DT
Lemmatized text with stop-words	77.8	76.6	77.2	72.2	76.8	70.3
Stemmed text with stop-words	78.4	77.1	77.8	72.2	75.2	68.5
Lemmatized text without stop-words	75.2	75.7	76.1	71.1	74.4	70.3
Stemmed text without stop-words	75.3	75.6	75.4	71.5	74.8	70.7

TABLE III. ACCURACY SCORE FOR TRAINING MODELS USING COUNT VECTORIZER

Using Count Vectorizer						
	NB	LR	SVM	KNN	RF	DT
Lemmatized text with stop-words	76.5	79.2	76.5	54.8	76.5	71.1
Stemmed text with stop-words	76.4	78.9	76.3	54.8	74.6	68
Lemmatized text without stop-words	75	75.7	74	52.7	73.1	71.2
Stemmed text without stop-words	74.8	75.5	74	53	72.5	70.6

D. Mobile Application Development

The application was developed using Flutter, a framework based on the Dart language created and supported by Google, using Visual Studio Code [18]. The application is used on the parent's and the child's device. At first, the interfaces were designed and then the services that each parent can access from his device were implemented, such as creating an account and logging in, using his email and password to use the application and its services such as adding a child, receiving an alert, getting advice, and adjusting account settings. Then, the services that the parent can access from the child's device were implemented, such as logging in, where the parent can enter his email and password and then give permission to allow the system to monitor notifications of the child's device to be processed later.

The notifications of Android applications can be read to gain access to WhatsApp messages using the Flutter notification_listener. Firebase Cloud Messaging was used to send an alert to the parent's device, which is a Google free cloud service that enables application developers to deliver messages and notifications to users across a variety of platforms, including Android, iOS, and web applications. FCM enables software developers to push application notifications to end users through an Application Programming Interface (API). FCM can send messages to apps in three different ways:

directly to a single device, to a group of devices, or to devices that have subscribed to a topic [19].

E. Database

The Etiqa'a system database structure was modeled using the ER-Diagram in Chen notation. Figure 3 shows its relational schema, which consists of 4 tables. The tables were created using PHPMyAdmin [20].

Fig. 3. Relational Schema of Etiqa'a system.

F. Integrating the Server Side to the Client Side

Since Flutter cannot handle PHP, JSON [21] was used to integrate the database with the application, which is an interchange format for lightweight data. JSON was used for data exchange between the backend (PHP) and the front end (Flutter). Flask was used to integrate the model into the application, which is a popular microweb framework for Python API development that does not need special tools or libraries and aims to keep the core basic but extensible. Flask provides the fundamental components for development, such as request handling, routing, etc. In addition, it can be used to quickly and easily deploy ML models [22]. Once the ML model is exported, it can be turned into an API and send requests to it via a Flutter application.

G. Testing

The application was tested to detect and resolve any problems and ensure that it was ready and free of errors that could impair its function or effectiveness.

- Unit testing was performed to isolate the code and ensure that it worked as intended. Each application function was tested and confirmed to be error-free.
- Integration testing was performed to expose any flaws when integrating components interacting with each other. The application's components were tested and confirmed to work perfectly together with no flaws or errors, such as integrating the ML model and the application.
- System testing was performed to evaluate the functionality of the application. The entire application was tested from the beginning to the end to confirm that it was bug-free, worked as expected, and that all the requirements were met.
- Acceptance testing was performed to assess the system's compliance with the requirements and verify if it met the

required criteria for use by end users. End users participated in the testing process and provided feedback on the application. Users were observed during this test, and notes were taken about their performance and behavior while using the application.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. ANLP Results

After testing the stemmers/lemmatizers, it was found that the CAMeL stemmer and lemmatizer worked the best for the given data.

TABLE IV. RESULTS OF STEMMERS AND LEMMATIZERS

cleaned_text	CAMeL_lem	CAMeL_stem	tashaphyne
وجع بشكل الله ياخذك	وجع شكل الله أخذ	وجع شكل الله أخذ	جع شكل له ياخذ
السلام عليكم مساء الخير كيف الحال	سلام على مساء خير كيف حال	سلام على مساء خير كيف حال	سلام على مساء خير كيف حال
ه روعة يا زين زين بسم الله عليك	ه روعه يا زين زين سم الله على	ه روعه يا زين زين سم الله على	ه روع يا زي زين سم له على
لما كلاب تهو هو عليك	ما كلب تهو هو على	لما كلاب تهو هو على	لما كلاب هو هو على
روحي لبريد تلقى اشباه كثير بس محد زي مشفوح الله فقل بس	روح بريد لقي شبه كثير بس محد زي مشفوح الله فقل بس	روح بريد لقي اشباه كثير بس محد زي مشفوح الله فقل بس	روح بريد لقي شيا ثير بس محد زي مشفوح له فقل بس
qalsadi	farasa_stem	ARLSTem	
وجع شكل الله ياخذك	وجع شكل الله ياخذك	وجع بشكل الل اخذك	
السلام على مساء خير كيف حال	سلام على مساء خير كيف حال	سلام على مساء خير كيف حال	
ه روعة يا زين زين سم الله على	ه روح يا زين زين بسم الله على	ه روع يا زين زين بسم الل على	
لما كلاب تهو هو على	ما كلب تهو هو على	لما كلاب هو هو على	
روحي لبريد تلقى اشباه كثير بس محد زي مشفوح الله فقل بس	روح بريد تلقى اشباه كثير بس محد زي مشفوح الله فقل بس	روحي لبريد تلق اشب كثير بس محد زي مشفوح الل فقل بس	

B. Model Evaluation

The best accuracy score was obtained by the LR algorithm at 79.2% using the Count Vectorizer trained on lemmatized text with stop-words data, while the worst score was for the K-Nearest Neighbor with 52.7% accuracy.

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix of the LR model.

To determine how well the proposed model operated and its highest accuracy results, the model was trained in different

training sets, which required breaking the dataset into many distinct segments using the k-fold cross-validation technique. The best result was obtained with LR on lemmatized data with stop words, using a count vectorizer with an 81.2% accuracy score. The F1-score obtained from the k-fold cross-validation technique for the LR algorithm was 81.5%.

C. User Interfaces

The principles considered when designing the application interfaces were: visibility, feedback, constraints, consistency, and affordance. When a user initially launches the application, a brief description appears, and then an interface appears with options for the user to enter the application either from the parent's or the child's device. The parent can log in or create a new account. If the login is performed from the parent's device option, the user can move to an interface that enables him to add a child, as shown in Figure 5 (the colored icon means the child's account is activated, and the black and white icon is the opposite). After adding the child, a user interface will appear containing the child's information through which he can modify and delete the child's account.

Fig. 5. Children's list interface.

The user should then log into the child's device with the same parent account information and select a specific child from his children to allow the application to access the device's notifications, as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Permission window in child's device.

When an inappropriate message is received on the child's device, the application will detect it immediately and send an alert to the parent's device, whether inside or outside the application, as shown in Figure 7. Alerts will appear for all children on the parent's home page for two weeks, while he can view alerts for a specific child if he wishes, as shown in Figure 8. As shown in Figure 9, when clicking on a specific alert, more details will appear, such as the full content, the sender's name, the time of the message, and whether he wants the alert to be stored in the alert history.

Fig. 7. Notifications pop up inside and outside the application.

Fig. 8. The homepage interface on the parent's device.

Fig. 9. Alert details interface.

The application also provides articles to get advice that could help the parent deal with or address the issue. In addition,

the user can view and modify his account information, children's list, and alerts history, as well as a help center for the parent to explain how the application works and frequently asked questions and their answers.

D. Application Test Results

The application was tested by nine different parents aged above 20 years. The tests were carried out in person, and the application was downloaded to user devices, who were then asked to use it. After the users were done using the application, a questionnaire was given to provide their feedback. 55.6% of the application users were technology experts, 33.3% considered their level in technology medium, and 11.1% considered themselves beginners. The users were asked to use the Etiqa'a application without limitation. Parents set up their accounts on their and their children's devices without problems, and then the parents sent messages to their children's WhatsApp accounts to test the application. The results showed that 25 of 28 messages (89.3%) were correctly classified, while 3 of 28 (10.7%) messages were misclassified, as shown in Table V. These misclassification problems were caused by the following reasons:

- The model was trained on a small and limited dataset.
- The tools that can correct Arabic dialect misspelled words.

All the parents reported that they received alert notifications about inappropriate messages, 88.8% of them found the application clear and easy to use, while 11.1% found it difficult to understand some of the instructions and phrases of the interface. Most parents suggested that the model should be taught more inappropriate words to improve its performance and found it valuable and very useful in protecting their children. Overall, all users were satisfied with the application and its services.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study presented an application called Etiqa'a that analyzes WhatsApp messages using an ML model to classify them as appropriate or inappropriate. If a message is found inappropriate, the application sends an alert to the parent informing him of the message content and the sender. Four different datasets were combined, from different social media platforms, into one. The dataset content was then labeled as appropriate (APROP) or inappropriate (NOT_APROP). The dataset was cleaned, normalized, and tokenized using different stemmers and lemmatizers to find the best one to improve classification performance, which was provided by the CAMEL lemmatizer and stemmer. Data features were extracted using two methods, Count Vectorizer and Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), and the data were tested using six different algorithms. Each algorithm was tested using two different vectorizers under four different datasets. The results showed that the best results were achieved using the CAMEL lemmatizer without removing stop words for feature extraction. LR yielded the best results, with an accuracy of 81.2% and an F1-score of 81.5%.

TABLE V. USER ACCEPTANCE TEST

User	Sent Sentence	Model's Classification	Was the message classified correctly?	Problem Justification
1	عمه في وجهك يا حمار يا واضح	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	كلب جحش حيوان غبي ثور	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	اتوطا في بطنك	APROP	No	Training data size was small
2	السلام عليكم ورحمة الله وبركاته	APROP	Yes	-
	مساء الخير لمي	APROP	Yes	-
	وينك يا زق ليش ما تجين	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	فاتك نص عمرك جنى الحيوانة اليوم جات	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
3	يا حيوانه	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	السلام عليكم كيفك	APROP	Yes	-
	لو انك ولد امك و ابوك قافلتي بعد المدرسة وتشوف ايش حسوي فيك والله اقتلك	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
4	ياكلبة	APROP	No	There are no good tools for correcting misspellings for Arabic dialects and training data were spelled correctly
	وريني صدرك واعطيك اللي تبين	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	روحي انتحري محد بيغاك يا منبوذة	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
5	يا غبي	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	ياحبيبي	APROP	Yes	-
	سمعت انك كلمت اخويا ع اللي صار امس	APROP	Yes	-
	لو سمحت لا تتدخل مرة ثانية ولا قسم بالله اقتلك	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
6	انبحك	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	غبيه ومحد بيغاك يامنبوذة	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	فسخي وصورتي لي وحجيب لك	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
7	يا حقيره	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	زباله انقلعي	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	لا ترسلي شي	APROP	Yes	-
8	كل شي سيء في الحياه منك	APROP	No	Limited training data
	الله يلعنك	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
	شكلك المعفن بنحسنا	NOT_APROP	Yes	-
9	حالة اللي يفتصيك ويقتلك بعدها يا سلام	NOT_APROP	Yes	-

The application works differently on the parent's or the child's device. Parents can log into the application using an account. After the parent has set up the application on a child's devices, Etiqa'a monitors the notifications using the Flutter notification_listener plugin. Only WhatsApp messenger notifications are filtered and sent to the ML model to be analyzed and classified as appropriate or inappropriate. The ML model and the application were connected using the Flask Python API via a Flutter application. Each WhatsApp message read from the child's device is sent to the model to be cleaned, perform ANLP, and predict whether it is an appropriate or inappropriate message. If the ML model finds the message inappropriate, it stores it in the database, and sends a notification via FCM to the parent device to inform him about the content of the message.

The application was implemented for the Android platform. However, it can be ported to the iOS platform as well. In future work, the system will be able to monitor other social media applications and improve the message extraction method to overcome drawbacks, such as being unable to see the receiver's (child's) messages. The model can be further improved to recognize all inappropriate/harmful words and sentences, making the classification of messages more accurate by adding more specific categories, such as suicidal, bullying, and sexual

harassment, and detecting not only inappropriate messages but also photos and voice messages. Another future objective is to make the application usable for everyone, including people with physical/visual disabilities.

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3D Indoor Crime Scene Reconstruction from Micro UAV Photogrammetry Technique

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ABSTRACT

The application of micro Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in photogrammetry, particularly within the realm of forensic investigation represents a relatively novel approach and has gained increased attention. By measuring the distances and positions of the scene's components, it is feasible to document and visualize the scene using the photographs that were taken for the purpose of assisting investigators. Capturing accurate crime scene data within a short time frame is always a challenge. Conventionally, photographs were used to document the scene, but the technical qualities of the photographs depended on the skill of the present forensic personnel. The use of 3-Dimensional (3D) photogrammetry enables the production of highly realistic and detailed 3D documentation of a given scene. As this technique involves capturing a series of photographs, it can be a time-consuming process. Therefore, this study aims to explore an alternative approach that enables the rapid acquisition of the scene while preserving the intricate details, thus ensuring efficiency without compromising the accuracy of the resulting documentation. The study employs a methodological approach wherein data are collected from a simulated crime scene situated within a confined and hard-to-reach area. The data collection is facilitated through the utilization of micro UAVs. The acquired data are then processed utilizing photogrammetry software, leading to the generation of a 3D model point cloud. The collected data will be subjected to a comparative analysis with data generated using a Terrestrial Laser Scanner (TLS) as a reference, alongside Vernier Calliper (VC) measurements. The findings indicate that the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of the integrated point clouds from TLS and micro UAVs compared to the conventional method is approximately ± 0.217 cm. It can be deduced that the integration of data derived from micro UAVs and TLS in forensic photogrammetry within a confined crime scene is viable and yields a high-precision 3D model point cloud.

Keywords-forensics; close range photogrammetry; micro UAV; TLS; data integration

I. INTRODUCTION

During the recent years, the field of photogrammetry has seen a rise of interest in the use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), despite that their first uses were for military purposes [1-2]. Over time, the legal system embraced the use of photographs as permissible evidence. Subsequently, in the

1950s, the advent of the videotape recorder further expanded the admissibility of visual evidence in court proceedings. As photogrammetry transitioned into the digital era, forensic photogrammetry began incorporating digital cameras as a pivotal investigation tool. In the context of court admissibility, the recreation of the scene necessitates a meticulous establishment of high-precision elements including the

position, direction and perspective of key components within the scene [3]. The captured images facilitate comprehensive documentation and visualization of the scenes through precise measurements of the position and shapes of their major components. However, the scene reconstruction process demands a multitude of object measurements, which can be time-consuming, particularly in extensive areas. This challenge is further amplified when employing the conventional method, which is Digital Single-Lens Reflex (DSLR) cameras in forensics, potentially impacting the authenticity and integrity of the investigation as the presence of the investigator could temper the objects in the crime scene [4]. The use of 3D reconstruction of indoor crime scene analysis enables the comprehensive documentation of evidentiary elements such as mapping of blood splatter patterns, meticulous comparison of various murder weapon types, and potentially revolutionising data collection which enables visualising and simulating the sequence of events [5-10]. The reconstruction of indoor crime scenes can be facilitated by numerous technologies that are beyond photographs and handwritten notes. However, even with modern technologies, it is necessary to take into consideration the technical constraints, user-friendliness, cost, and time duration of data acquisition [11-12]. A recent study reported that leveraging on UAV technology will improve the effectiveness of crime investigation, facilitating access to otherwise inaccessible areas and expediting the retrieval of images [13-14]. However, in a constrained environment, a micro UAV has the advantage of being able to manoeuvre in tight spaces. A UAV is considered micro if it is palm-size and weighs less than two kilograms [15-16].

This study explores the usage of micro UAVs using the Close Range Photogrammetry (CRP) method to capture images of the indoor crime scene from various angles and heights. By using the Structure from Motion (SfM) technique available in selected photogrammetry software, the same feature points of 2D overlapping photos generate a 3D model. Data obtained from micro UAV and Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS) are processed, compared, and analyzed against measurements obtained from conventional tools such as the Vernier Calliper (VC), to determine the level of accuracy. The integrated point cloud data from Micro UAV and TLS were also analyzed. The data integration from both sensors should enhance the accuracy and provide completeness of the 3D model point cloud, thus minimizing the risk of missing data in the model.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a research methodology that consists of three phases: (a) Research Planning and Design, (b) Data Acquisition and Processing, and (c) Results and Discussion, as depicted in Figure 1.

A. Research Planning and Design

The simulated crime scene was set up close to Geospatial Imaging and Information Research Group (GI2RG), Block C05 in Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Johor Bahru, Johor, Malaysia. To increase the complexity of the access to the mock crime scene, it was set up on top of a 12ft container placed within a stairwell of a three-story building as depicted in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Research methodology.

Fig. 2. Location of the mock crime scene.

Figure 3 shows the objects utilized to gauge the accuracy of the data extracted from the micro UAV, TLS, and the conventional measuring instrument. A total of seven objects were placed together with the victim as parts of the mock crime scene. The primary equipment used in this study as depicted in Figure 4 were: (a) DJI Mini 2 for the micro UAV, (b) Leica BLK360 for the TLS, (c) VC, and (d) measuring tape. The data generated from these tools were then processed using Agisoft MetaShape Professional and Cloud Compare photogrammetry software.

B. Data Acquisition and Processing

The placement of the TLS is crucial to ensure the coverage of the crime scene is complete. Since access to the scene was difficult primarily due to its height, the TLS was placed at 10

locations with differing heights and positions. The micro UAV was then deployed following a single grid pattern covering the entire crime scene. The time taken for the data acquisition using TLS and micro UAV was approximately 45 minutes to ensure full coverage of the crime scene. Figure 5 shows the approximate flight plan during the data acquisition.

Fig. 3. The distribution of the measured objects.

Fig. 4. Equipment used.

Fig. 5. Approximate flight path of data acquisition.

Upon completion of data acquisition involving TLS and micro UAV, the objects in the crime scene were then individually measured using a VC and a measuring tape. The data from the micro UAV were processed using the Structure from Motion (SfM) algorithm in Agisoft Metashape Professional software as depicted in [17] and the resulting output from the SfM was further processed as shown in Figure 6. Data from TLS on the other hand, were processed and filtered with Cloud Compare.

Fig. 6. The procedural flow of images from the micro UAV.

The latter is also used for point cloud integration from both sources using the Point Pair Picking (PPP) method. PPP is a manual approach of selecting common points between two-point cloud datasets. The selection of the common points had to be carried out manually due to the absence of a Ground Control Point (GCP) since the Global Positioning System (GPS) cannot be utilized in an indoor environment.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The 3D model point cloud from Micro UAV generated from more than 100 images which produced 22.7-million-point clouds. Whilst for TLS, 54-million-point clouds were produced covering the crime scene and beyond, which were later filtered to focus on the crime scene area only resulting in approximately 40 million points. The point clouds from both sources were subsequently exported in file format las, enabling the Cloud Compare software to detect and facilitate further processing.

Figure 7(a) shows the 3D model point cloud obtained from TLS placed at various locations. It is worth noting that the 3D model point cloud highlighted an incomplete point cloud represented by circular voids in the figure where the TLS were placed despite various placements of TLS at 10 different locations and heights. This is also evident in the missing blood splatter due to obstruction of the victim's hand from a station. Figure 7(b) depicts the 3D model point cloud obtained from the micro UAV captured from various angles. It is obvious that the generated 3D model point cloud is clear, photorealistic and vibrant, except for the white void due to the lack of light.

The data from the micro UAV and TLS were also integrated using Cloud Compare software with the intent to enhance the completeness of the 3D model. Through the process of integration, a notable outcome was achieved as the resulting point cloud increase substantially, reaching a total of 72 million points. As shown in Figure 7(c), the voids present in the earlier TLS 3D model point cloud are no longer visible.

The integrated data in Cloud Compare were extracted and analyzed using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) to determine the accuracy in comparison with the measurements using the conventional method.

Fig. 7. Data output: 3D model point cloud of (a) TLS, (b) micro UAV, and (c) integrated point cloud.

$$\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{N}} \quad (1)$$

where y_i is the true value, \hat{y}_i is the observed value, and N is the number of observations. The results of the quantitative analysis are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. MEASUREMENT ERRORS

No.	Items	Error Measurement (cm)		
		Conv-TLS	Conv-UAV	Conv-Integrated
1	Slipper	0.067	0.500	0.365
2	Glass Case 1	0.976	0.300	0.276
3	Glass Case 2	-0.008	0.170	0.162
4	Book 1	0.778	0.300	-0.127
5	Book 2	1.756	0.300	0.008
6	Wallet 1	0.263	0.300	0.234
7	Wallet 2	-0.827	-0.400	0.070
8	Bag	-0.805	0.500	-0.343
9	Water Bottle	1.490	-0.100	0.001
10	Compact Powder	-0.055	0.400	0.321
11	Cabin Length	2.153	4.000	2.560
12	Cabin Width	-3.643	2.000	0.751
13	Cabin Height	-0.698	2.000	1.554
14	Body Height	0.497	0.800	0.256
15	Body Left Arm	0.438	0.320	0.007
	RMSE	0.423	0.395	0.217

Table I presents the outcome of the analysis conducted through the computation of RMSE. The label Conv denotes that the corresponding data originate from the conventional measurement approach. The measurement error is used to indicate the discrepancies between the benchmark measurements produced by the conventional method and those obtained using TLS, micro UAV and Integrated point clouds. Based on this analysis, the RMSE values for the comparison of conventional measurement against TLS, UAV, and Integrated point clouds are ± 0.423 cm, ± 0.395 cm, and ± 0.217 cm, respectively. From a statistical standpoint, a lower RMSE value corresponds to a better performance of the given model. While there is no global standard for crime scene investigation accuracy, there are references that indicate an accuracy of 0.635 cm is accepted in the United States [18-19].

Fig. 8. RMSE of TLS, UAV, and Integrated model against the Conventional.

Figure 8 shows a visual chart comprising 13 samples of the dataset, presenting the RMSE values of TLS, UAV, and integrated data in comparison to the conventional measurements. It is observed that Cabin Length and Cabin Width exhibit slightly higher RMSE values compared to the other elements, signalling the presence of error. These differences may arise due to noise within the 3D model point cloud or due to the reflective properties of the cabin's material. It has been suggested by other researchers that the reflective surface can potentially interfere with the accuracy of optical imaging readings, including shiny, mirror-like surfaces and very dark materials [20-24]. Based on the above discussion, the quality of the resulting 3D model point cloud visualisation can be summarised in Table II. The completeness characteristics refer to the absence of void in the 3D model point cloud whilst representation and color intensity refer to the proximity to the real object. As depicted in Table II, TLS lacks completeness due to occlusion, lesser spectral information causing reduced colour intensity [25], and distorted object representation. This is aligned with the highest RMSE result for TLS as depicted in Table I. As for integrated data, the completeness and color intensity are acceptable as the occluded areas and colors are

compensated for by the merging of the two datasets. The representation, however, lacks proximity to real objects due to extraneous noises from the integration of two datasets, particularly from TLS. It has been suggested that data quality for analysis could be improved with further data cleaning and noise filtering [26].

TABLE II. QUALITY OF 3D MODEL POINT CLOUD

Characteristics	TLS	Micro UAV	Integrated
Completeness	✘	✘	✓
Color Intensity	✘	✓	✓
Representation	✘	✓	✘

IV. CONCLUSION

The primary objective of this research is to assess the effectiveness and accuracy of utilizing micro UAV technology in forensic photogrammetry for evidence capture without compromising the integrity of the indoor crime scene. The generated 3D model point clouds obtained from micro the UAV and TLS were compared against conventional measurements which were used as the reference standard. Further analysis was also carried out using the integrated point cloud from both sources.

It was noted that the visualisation output of the micro UAV is superior to TLS, despite the fact that it provided a greater quantity of point cloud data covering a wider area. This study further demonstrated that the integrated data produced by TLS and micro UAV generated a 3D model point cloud that is complete and suitable for indoor forensics application. The integrated point cloud provides a higher-density point cloud thus giving realistic color to the model. However, despite having the lowest RMSE of ± 0.217 cm, the integrated point cloud has its own limitations: the body of the cabin and the ladder were distorted which may be due to the reflective surface of the object and inefficient lighting. Further study is warranted to delve into resolving issues related to reflective or shiny objects and the placement of TLS for indoor environments.

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Fractional Order Modeling and Control of an Articulated Robotic Arm

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a fractional order system modeling of a robotic arm and the development of a Fractional Order PID (FOPID) controller applied to the system. The controller technique originated from non-integer calculus, which improves the robotic arm's overall stability and positioning. The robotic arm system is modeled using the non-integer order technique in order to improve system accuracy. Thus, a non-integer order Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) control method is implemented to stabilize the plant positioning. Using MATLAB/Simulink the FOPID controller simulations were confirmed and compared to the Integer Order PID (IOPID) controller for tracking the robotic arm positioning. Simulation outcomes imply that the proposed non-integer controller increases the system stability and position with/without external disturbances being present in the environment.

Keywords-fractional order control; fractional order modeling; robotic arm; articulated manipulator

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of robotic arms is in high demand and has attracted many research studies in academia and the industry, as it has a crucial role in the artificial intelligence integration. It involves many disciplines such control system, sensor technology, communication technology, and artificial intelligence [1]. Nowadays, most industries make use of robotic applications in order to have faster manufacturing, which increases the production line and preserves higher precision and product quality. Articulated robotic arms dominate the global industrial robotics market, accounting for over 50% of all annual installations, as they offer a large operational area and are capable of functioning in a three-dimensional space [2]. The articulated robotic arm application makes use of performing many tasks that are typically complex or can have health effects of humans. These tasks include working in radioactive or contaminated environments, robotic surgery or welding, space exploration, packaging, detecting and disposing bombs, etc. The basis to develop a systematic control for a robotic arm manipulator is implementing the feedback law, which plays a crucial part in eliminating system uncertainty. With the system having a large margin for disturbances and uncertainty, the control design should be able to handle the nonlinear behaviors of the system dynamic coupling [4].

One of the main goals of the development of robots is to build an adaptive and universal machinery to perform tasks and proactively being adaptive to the condition changes. Although conventional robots are able to perform specific tasks with exceptional precision and speed, there are still difficulties in adapting to other more complex tasks as well as being operated in entirely unstructured environments [5]. Also, the greater the complexity of a control algorithm, the more time is needed for its simulation. This makes the task of developing a quick and precise systemic response a challenge [6]. Consequently, there is still ongoing research to improve and overcome these difficulties. One of the main concerns of this study is to develop a simple controller technique, which can provide speed and precision to overcome disturbances.

In the literature, several integer order control methods have been applied for stabilizing and controlling robotic arm systems using integer order modeling, including Sliding Mode Control (SMC) [6][7], Proportional-Integral/Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PI/PID) control [8], Model Predictive Control (MPC), and H-infinity control [9]. Very limited research exists in modeling a robotic arm as a fractional order system and it is still an open problem to investigate and examine the benefits of applying a fractional controller to stabilize the system. Research discoveries on fractional order controllers suggest that they offer superior quality control compared to classical

integer order controllers in particular, when a fractional controller is applied to a fractional order system model [9][10]. This paper introduces a new modeling method of the robotic arm as a fractional order plant in order to obtain the system dynamics more accurately as compared to the classical integer order modeling with the design and implementation of a fractional order controller using the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm to improve system stability with and without the presence of disturbances.

II. SYSTEM MODELING

A. Kinematics

To model the dynamics of the 3-DoF (Degrees of Freedom) articulated manipulator kinematics, the model was developed using the Deviant-Hardenberg (DH) method. DH frame assignment for the manipulator is shown in Fig. 1. Figure 1. The DH table shown in Table I explains the geometric relationship between three manipulator links and the world frame according to the assigned frames [11].

Fig. 1. DH frame arrangement for the articulated manipulator.

TABLE I. DH PARAMETERS OF THE 3DOF ARTICULATED MANIPULATOR

Joint No.	Joint Rotation (θ)	Link Offset (d)	Link Length (a)	Link Twist (α)
1	q_1	L_1	0	90°
2	q_2	0	L_2	0
3	q_3	0	L_3	0

The transformation matrix is obtained showing the relative position and orientation transform of the end effector with respect to the world frame, which is fixed on the manipulator's base. The transformation matrix is given in (1).

$$T_0^3 = \begin{bmatrix} C_1 C_{23} & -C_1 S_{23} & S_1 & L_3 C_1 C_{23} + L_2 C_1 C_2 \\ S_1 C_{23} & -S_1 S_{23} & -C_1 & L_3 S_1 C_{23} + L_2 S_1 C_2 \\ S_{23} & C_{23} & 0 & L_3 S_{23} + L_2 S_2 + L_1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

hence:

$$\begin{aligned} p_x &= L_3 C_1 C_{23} + L_2 C_1 C_2 \\ p_y &= L_3 S_1 C_{23} + L_2 S_1 C_2 \\ p_z &= L_3 S_{23} + L_2 S_2 + L_1 \end{aligned}$$

B. Dynamics

The dynamic model of the manipulator was obtained using the Euler-Lagrange method, where the Lagrangian provides difference between kinematic and potential energy of the system [12]. This technique is used to obtain the mathematical

models of complex system dynamics. The Lagrangian can be used as shown in (2) to get the dynamic model of the manipulator. The Lagrangian is the difference between the total kinetic and the total potential energy of the system ($L = K.E - P.E$).

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L(q, \dot{q})}{\partial \dot{q}_i} \right) - \frac{\partial L(q, \dot{q})}{\partial q_i} = \tau_i \quad (2)$$

For a system such as the robotic manipulator, the equation can simply be decomposed for simplification, which can ultimately be converted to state space model. The decomposed equation of the manipulator dynamics is shown in (3) obtained by using the Lagrangian method as represented in (2). This non-linear model of the robot is known as the forward dynamics model.

$$T = M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q}) + G(q) \quad (3)$$

where M is the inertia matrix, C is the centripetal or Coriolis matrix, G is the gravity matrix, T is the torque matrix [10][11], and q is a vector containing joint space variables such as the joint angles. The matrices for the 3-DOF articulated manipulator are:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & M_{13} \\ M_{21} & M_{22} & M_{23} \\ M_{31} & M_{32} & M_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad C = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} \\ C_{21} \\ C_{31} \end{bmatrix} \quad G = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11} \\ G_{21} \\ G_{31} \end{bmatrix}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle M_{11} &= \frac{1}{2} m_1 l_1^2 + \frac{1}{3} m_2 l_2^2 C_2^2 + \frac{1}{3} m_3 l_3 C_{23}^2 + m_3 l_2 C_2^2 + m_3 l_2 l_3 C_2 C_{23} \rangle \\ \langle M_{22} &= \frac{1}{3} m_2 l_2^2 + \frac{1}{3} m_3 l_3^2 + m_3 l_2^2 + m_3 l_2 l_3 C_3 \rangle \\ \langle M_{23} &= M_{32} = \frac{1}{3} m_3 l_3^2 + m_3 l_2^2 + \frac{1}{3} m_3 l_2 l_3 C_3 \rangle \\ \langle M_{33} &= \frac{1}{3} m_3 l_3^2 \rangle \\ \langle M_{12} &= M_{13} = M_{21} = M_{31} = 0 \rangle \\ \langle C_{11} &= \left[-\frac{4}{3} m_2 l_2^2 S_2(2) - \frac{1}{3} m_3 l_3^2 S_2(23) - m_3 l_2 l_3 S_2(2)+3 \right] \dot{\theta}_2 \dot{\theta}_1 \\ &+ \left[-\frac{1}{3} m_3 l_3^2 S_2(23) - m_3 l_2 l_3 C_2 S_{23} \right] \dot{\theta}_3 \dot{\theta}_1 \rangle \\ \langle C_{21} &= \left[-3 m_3 l_2 l_3 S_3 \right] \dot{\theta}_2 \dot{\theta}_3 + \left[-\frac{1}{2} m_3 l_2 l_3 S_3 \right] \dot{\theta}_3^2 + \left[\frac{1}{6} m_2 l_2 S_2(2) \right. \\ &+ \left. \frac{1}{6} m_3 l_3^2 S_2(23) + \frac{1}{2} m_3 l_2^2 S_2(2) + \frac{1}{2} m_3 l_2 l_3 S_2(2)+3 \right] \dot{\theta}_1^2 \rangle \\ \langle C_{31} &= \left[\frac{1}{2} m_3 l_2 l_3 S_3 \right] \dot{\theta}_2^2 + \left[\frac{1}{6} m_3 l_3 S_2(23) + \frac{1}{2} m_3 l_2 l_3 C_2 S_{23} \right] \dot{\theta}_1^2 \rangle \\ \langle G_{11} &= 0 \rangle \\ \langle G_{21} &= \frac{1}{2} m_2 g l_2 C_2 + \frac{1}{2} m_3 g l_3 C_{23} + m_3 g l_2 C_2 \rangle \\ \langle G_{31} &= \frac{1}{2} m_3 g l_3 C_{23} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

C. Fractional Order Model

The dynamic model presented above represents the integer order model for the 3-DoF articulated manipulator. To model it in a fractional order system, its derivatives need to be replaced with fractional order derivatives [12][13].

$$\frac{d}{dt} \rightarrow \frac{d^\gamma}{dt^\gamma} \quad (4)$$

It can be seen that (4) is not right physically, because the dimensions of the integer order derivative are s^{-1} and that of the fractional order is $s^{-\lambda}$. For the sake of consistency, they have to be the same, therefore the following definition is valid [13][14]:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sigma^{1-\gamma}} \frac{d^\gamma}{dt^\gamma} \quad (5)$$

where the parameter σ is arbitrary representing the fractional time component of the system. The time component is known as the cosmic time. Using the dynamic model of the system, the physical relation between order and arbitrary parameter can be approximated as [13]:

$$\gamma = ((inv(MC))^T G)^{1/3} \sigma \quad (6)$$

where, due to the fact that the parameter σ incorporates a fractional time component in the system and is used for the existence of physical dimension consistency in the equation, the Plank time constant is also used in research rather than computing it analytically [15].

Now the dynamic model can be represented by replacing the integer order derivative with the fractional order derivative and the equations can be expressed as:

$$T = M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q}) + G(q) \quad (7)$$

where $\ddot{q} = \frac{1}{\sigma^{2(1-\gamma)}} \frac{d^{2\gamma}}{dt^{2\gamma}}$, $\dot{q} = \frac{1}{\sigma^{(1-\gamma)}} \frac{d^\gamma}{dt^\gamma}$, and $0 < \gamma < 1$.

D. Model Parameters

As the dynamic model was obtained for the dynamic system in analytical form, γ and some other physical parameters such as mass and link lengths are still unknown. The physical parameters of the robot used for this simulation are given as [12]: $m_1 = m_2 = m_3 = 0.5$ kg, $L_1 = 0.15$ m, $L_2 = 0.5$ m, $L_3 = 0.5$ m, and $\gamma = 0.93$.

Fig. 2. A comparison of analytical and simscape multibody models.

The order (γ) is obtained by optimizing by employing the ABC genetic algorithm, where γ is tuned by comparing the results with the multibody model of the robot implemented using simscape sim-mechanics. The analytical model parameter is tuned based on the multibody model by minimizing the cost

function ITAE ($\int t \cdot |e(t)| dt$)[11]. The result comparison of the analytical and the Simscape model [16] is presented in Figure 2 and the modeling error in the analytical model is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Modeling error.

III. FRACTIONAL ORDER CONTROL

The controller technique implemented in this research study is a Fractional Order PID (FOPID) controller. For the robotic arm structure, it is crucial for the controller to track the desired position accurately in order to attain a stable operation. Non-integer calculus is a generalized concept to fractional order differential and integral basic operator ${}_a D_t^\alpha$ as defined in [17]:

$${}_a D_t^\beta = \begin{cases} \frac{d^\beta}{dt^\beta} & Re(\beta) > 0 \\ 1 & Re(\beta) = 0 \\ \int_a^t (dt)^{-\beta} & Re(\beta) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Non-integer order control design relies on using fractional order exponents of differential and integral operations in the Laplace domain to reach the design requirements that the classical integer order can't achieve, allowing to fulfill a robust constraint performance [5]. Non-integer order PI/PID controllers are proposed as a generalization of integer order PI/PID. Thus, with the fractional order PI/PID controller, additional tuning parameters are added to the controller which improve the overall controller design to meet the system specifications more precisely as compared to the integer order PI/PID controllers [18]. The dynamic model has been developed using fractional calculus, where the fraction order is tuned using the ABC algorithm. Now, a control system can be designed to control the manipulator state in the task space where feedforward control with FoPID controller is used. For that, an inverse dynamic model is used as a feedforward network in the controller which can be obtained by utilizing the dynamic model of the robot manipulator where the equation of inverse dynamic model will be:

$$M(q)^{-1}[T - C(q, \dot{q}) - G(q)] = \ddot{q} \quad (9)$$

where $\ddot{q} = \frac{1}{\sigma^{2(1-\gamma)}} \frac{d^{2\gamma}}{dt^{2\gamma}}$, $\dot{q} = \frac{1}{\sigma^{(1-\gamma)}} \frac{d^\gamma}{dt^\gamma}$, and $0 < \gamma < 1$, which can then be simplified as:

$$\int \int M(q)^{-1} [T - C(q, \dot{q}) - G(q)] = q \quad (10)$$

The inverse dynamic model of the system will accept position, velocity, and acceleration states in task space and compute the output in the form of torque required to achieve the states. Thus, by utilizing inverse dynamic model or a feedforward system in the controller, there will be an estimation for the required torque that the actuators can apply to achieve the states. However, the analytical model has some noise due to the modeling error that can be minimized by using a low pass filter. In this study, a low pass filter with a cutoff frequency of 30 Hz was used to minimize the noise in the output of the feedforward network. The Simulink model of the inverse dynamics system along with the low pass filter is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Feedforward system (inverse dynamics of the robot).

Fig. 5. Block diagram of the feedforward and FOPID controllers.

Fig. 6. Block diagram of the FOPID.

The block diagram of the system is presented in Figure 5 Fig. 5. , where the controller consists of a feedforward system and the FOPID. The robot input is a summation of the output states of the feedforward model and the FOPID compensator. The FOPID compensator is illustrated in Figure 6. It can be seen that the controller consists of the three gains (K_p , K_i , and K_d), and a fractional order integral and a fractional order derivative having order λ and μ respectively. As the integral

order of the PID compensator, the input provided to the system shown in Figure 6 is the error signal $e(t)$ and the output is the controller output referred to as $u(t)$.

A. Controller Tuning

In order to tune the two additional parameters for the non-integer order controller, the ABC algorithm is used, which is a algorithm inspired by nature [19], applied to optimize a large set of testing functions. This optimization method has been used to tune different controller applications for different system plants as well. In this study, the ABC method is used to tune the FOPID and the Integral Order PID (IoPID) controllers, where the tuning parameters are $[P \ I \ D \ \lambda \ \mu]$ for FOPID and $[P \ I \ D \ N]$ for IOPID, λ is the order of the integral, μ is the order of the derivative, and N is the derivative filter used in IOPID. The cost function minimization is used for tuning. In this regard, the cost function shown in (11) was considered:

$$fit = [W_1 \ W_2 \ W_3 \ W_4 \ W_5] \begin{bmatrix} T_s \\ M_o \\ e_{ss} \\ u(t) \\ \sum t \cdot |e(t)| \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where W_n is a weight vector that can be assigned manually in the algorithm to specify the importance of a specific entity in the fitness value, T_s is the settling time, M_o is the overshoot, e_{ss} is the setting error, $u(t)$ is the input signal of the plant, and $e(t)$ is the difference between the reference and the output signals: $e(t) = r(t) - y(t)$.

TABLE II. CONTROLLER PARAMETERS AFTER TUNING WITH ABC

Type	Parameter	Joint 1	Joint 2	Joint 3
IoPID	P	45.0986	33.5967	-169.5471
	I	16.1521	37.1599	-445.3873
	D	27.7447	10.4947	-65.7642
	N	5997.6464	6522.7668	84023.2904
FoPID	P	180	480.7269	-170.7471
	I	60.3385	295.8896	-140.4873
	D	40.8152	100.0941	-35.1754
	λ	0.83	0.697	0.837
	μ	0.75	0.68	0.85

The incorporation of weights in the fitness function for calculating fitness values offers significant advantages in the parameter estimation process. By assigning different weights to various performance criteria, such as settling time, error, or other system-specific metrics, the relative importance of all the parameters can effectively be controlled during the optimization process. This approach provides flexibility in fine-tuning the behavior of the system. One can prioritize certain criteria that are more critical for the specific application or align with the desired control objectives. For example, if achieving a fast-settling time is of utmost importance, a higher weight can be assigned to settling time in the fitness function. On the other hand, if minimizing steady-state error is the primary concern, a higher weight can be assigned to the error term. This allows us to strike a balance between conflicting objectives and tailor the control system's behavior according to

specific requirements. The tuned controller values can be seen in Table II.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation environment used for this study is shown in Figure 7, where the integral and fractional controllers are used to control the manipulator's states in task space. For both control methods, the same plant model is used, i.e. a fractional dynamic model to incorporate the performance test of each controller and compare them without any difficulty.

Fig. 7. Simulation environment block diagram with plant and controllers.

There are two types of reference inputs used in this simulation. A step input is used to analyze the output step response of the system and a sinusoidal input is used to analyze the tracking response of the system in the task space. The reference input can be selected using a switch for the ease where false (0) corresponds to sinusoidal reference and true (1) to step reference inputs. The step input signal is demonstrated in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Step reference input used in the simulations.

To assess the controllers' capability to counter disturbances, a disturbance step input of -8 Nm magnitude is applied to both controllers (IOPID and FOPID) at each joint. This scenario can be linked to the sudden impact of a strong wind gust on a delicate mechanism. During this simulation, akin to the

transient effects of wind, a predefined counter torque is exerted on each joint of the robotic arm. The disturbance input, symbolizing the abrupt nature of a wind gust, is initiated precisely at 3 s into the simulation, remains active for a duration of 1 s, and is then deactivated as shown in Figure 9, where a step having a magnitude of -8 Nm is used and again a step to 0 Nm after 1 s. This approach allows us to scrutinize the manipulators response to this disruptive force and its subsequent recovery.

Fig. 9. Disturbance input signal (wind gust for 1 s).

In the context of this research, where the aim is to scrutinize the output performance of the FOPID and IOPID controllers applied to a fractional order plant model of a robotic manipulator, a simulation environment was meticulously crafted. This environment served as the crucible for comparing the response of both controllers in the presence of a step input used as a reference signal. Figure 10 shows a visual representation of the simulation output, which shows a difference between the output response of the IOPID and FOPID controllers. Each joint of the robotic manipulator underwent a calculated step response, the portrayal of which can be observed in Figure 8. The step response of a system gives enough information to analyze the control behavior of the structure. Figure 10 lays the foundation for a comprehensive analysis, where we engaged in a juxtaposition of the performances exhibited by the FOPID and IOPID controllers. Upon embarking on a visual examination of the output results shown in Figure 10, a recurrent theme emerges with striking clarity: the FOPID controller consistently outshines its integer order counterpart across a multitude of performance metrics. This encompasses crucial aspects like settling time, rise time, overshoot, and steady-state error. As the data unfolds, a pattern of excellence surfaces, one that reaffirms the efficacy of the fractional order control approach in the realm of robotic manipulator precision and stability. Also, in Figure 10, it can be seen that the reference input, as shown in Figure 8 was applied for both controllers based on the articulated robotic arm model, where the step was applied at different times for each joint in order to ensure the stability of the robot due the inertial effect of the dynamic system.

Fig. 10. A comparison of the step output response of the integral and fractional controllers in the task space.

Using Figure 10, Table III was developed, where the necessary performance parameters are described. Table III helps to analyze the performance of both controllers in the time domain. To ensure a meticulous and transparent presentation of our findings, the quantified values for each performance metric are thoughtfully organized. This tabulation provides readers a panoramic view of the comprehensive spectrum of performance outcomes, which shows that the FOPID controller stands as a beacon of improvement, boasting an enhancement exceeding 50% when compared with its IOPID counterpart.

TABLE III. FOPID-IOPID RESULT COMAPRISON

Parameters (Joint 3)	IoPID	FoPID
Rise time (s)	0.51	0.26
Settling time (s)	3.1	1.5
Overshoot (%)	30	3
Undershoot (%)	0	0
Stead state error	0	0
Peak	1.3	1.03

These findings, gleaned from an intricate interplay of simulation, analysis, and meticulous observation, shed light on the transformative potential of the fractional order control methodologies within the realm of robotic manipulator dynamics. This substantiates the foundation for our comparative study and heralds new horizons in the advancement of control paradigms.

The impact of the disturbance is vividly illustrated in Figure 11, showcasing the disturbance output. Upon examining the response of both controllers, a distinctive disparity becomes apparent: the FOPID controller exhibits a subdued response to the disturbance, actively attempting to counteract its effects.

Conversely, the IOPID controller experiences a pronounced perturbation due to the disturbance, significantly affecting the system's behavior. This contrast is particularly noticeable when scrutinizing the response of joint 2, as clearly depicted in Figure 11. The FOPID controller's ability to mitigate the disturbance's impact is evident, with the response maintaining a more stable trajectory. In stark contrast, the disturbance's disruptive effect on the IOPID controller's response is readily observable. These findings not only underscore the robust disturbance rejection capability of the FOPID controller, but also emphasize the challenges that the IOPID controller faces when confronted with disturbances. Such insights further enhance our comprehension of the controllers' efficacy in maintaining stability and precision under varying external influences.

Fig. 11. A comparison of the step output response of integral and fractional controllers in the task space.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a fractional (non-integer) order robotic arm system has been modeled in order to identify the system parameters more accurately. For the kinematics modeling of the system and for the kinetics or dynamics, the DH-method and the Euler-Lagrange method were employed, respectively. With the fractional order system model, a fractional order controller was applied to the robotic arm system. It was shown that with the proposed system identification and the proposed fractional controller, which adds two additional tuning parameters (λ and μ) to the controller, system position and stability improved. Robotic arm position control accuracy is a critical task and can be challenging with system disturbances and uncertainty and with the proposed FOPID controller the

system was able to maintain its positioning stability and provide an improved time response with or without the presence of environmental disturbances in the system. The FoPID controller was compared to the integer order controller, and the simulation results verify that the proposed non-integer order controller outperforms the integer order controller and provides overall lower overshoot and settling time along with improving the system time response in achieving the desired position.

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An Optimized YOLO v5 Model for Tomato Leaf Disease Classification with Field Dataset

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ABSTRACT

Deep learning has gained widespread adoption in various fields, including object recognition, classification, and precision agriculture. This study aimed to investigate the use of deep convolutional neural networks for the real-time identification of diseases in tomato plant leaves. A customized field dataset was constructed, consisting of several images of tomato leaves captured using a mobile phone from agricultural fields in the Kerala and Tamil Nadu regions and classified into two categories: healthy and diseased. A YOLO v5 deep learning model was trained to classify images of tomato leaves into the respective categories. This study aimed to determine the most effective hyperparameters for the classification and detection of healthy and sick leaves sections, using both proprietary and publicly available datasets. The YOLO v5 model demonstrated a notable accuracy rate of 93% when evaluated in the test dataset. This method can help farmers quickly recognize diseased leaves and prompt the implementation of preventive measures to curtail the spread of tomato plant diseases.

Keywords-convolutional neural networks; deep learning; object classification; plant disease detection; YOLO v5

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep Learning (DL) and computer vision are two examples of cutting-edge technologies that have seen tremendous expansion in the agriculture sector over the last few years. Using these technologies can increase agricultural productivity and reduce yield losses caused by plant diseases. Plant diseases have historically been a significant concern for farmers around the world due to the substantial effects they may have, both in terms of crop quality and quantity. Visual examination by experts is the traditional way to determine plant diseases, however, this method is laborious, expensive, and prone to mistakes. The advancement of DL techniques has facilitated the automated and precise identification of plant diseases through the analysis of leaf images. DL, which is sometimes referred to as supervised learning, is a specialized domain within the science of Machine Learning (ML) that encompasses the systematic extraction of patterns and representations from data using neural networks with many layers. DL has several advantages over more conventional ML methods, the most notable being the remarkable accuracy it achieves when applied to high-dimensional data sources, such as still photos, audio, and video.

The development of DL models for the diagnosis of plant diseases has the potential to increase crop production while

simultaneously reducing the amount of crop yield lost [1]. The diagnosis of plant diseases has seen a significant improvement due to the incorporation of image-processing methods and ML [2-3]. This approach has the potential to alleviate problems that people and plants are experiencing. Artificial Intelligence (AI) gives humans the ability to communicate with computers and comprehend the requirements of such interactions. However, the reliability and performance of this technology are affected by a variety of challenges, making it difficult for ML approaches to recognize specific diseases [4]. A notable obstacle encountered in the use of ML and DL techniques to detect plant diseases is the considerable computing time required since some approaches depend on obsolete data sources [4]. Significant resources are necessary to develop and implement ML and DL applications, often supported by non-governmental organizations, which may impact their use and development. Image recognition can be used to identify diseased leaves by comparing images of infected and healthy leaves [5]. Traditional image processing techniques have been used, such as segmentation, feature retrieval, and categorization. In [6], an attribute image-based method was proposed to classify wheat plant diseases using a Support Vector Machine (SVM) [6]. DL has seen a surge in its application within agricultural research due to its superior ability to extract profound feature data and surpass conventional ML algorithms [7-8]. In [9], a rider neural

network based on the sine-cosine algorithm provided enhanced classification performance. Deep learning has shown promising results in identifying plant diseases [10-13].

This study aims to investigate the field of plant disease detection and develop a DL method to detect tomato plant leaf diseases, on the following basis:

- Collect a diverse dataset consisting of various scenarios and sizes, featuring damaged leaves on sophisticated backdrops with varying lighting and perspectives, providing optimal information for the detection of tomato plant diseases using leaf images.
- Conduct a comprehensive review of current methods and datasets on plant disease identification, offering a comparative analysis of their advantages and disadvantages.
- Use various Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to classify the health status of tomato leaves.
- Determine the hyperparameters of the EfficientDet, Faster R-CNN, and YOLO v5 methods, allowing for a comparison between them for classifying plant leaf diseases.
- Evaluate these methods using standard efficiency parameters, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

This study investigated three different approaches for tomato plant leaf detection. The YOLO v5 approach obtained a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 93.1% on both customized and public datasets while maintaining a frame rate of 120 fps.

II. PREVIOUS WORKS

Since the introduction of DL algorithms, there have been notable improvements in the identification and diagnosis of plant diseases. In [14], a detailed analysis of DL models demonstrated the impact of computer vision techniques and neural networks on the effective detection and diagnosis of plant diseases and the improvement of precision agriculture. In [15], the significant contributions of indoor plants to improving general well-being, reducing stress levels, and improving indoor air quality were examined. In [16], different techniques and tools were examined to identify and treat plant diseases, increase crop production, and ensure long-term viability. In [17], a review of plant-microbiome interactions and their effects on plant health was carried out, shedding light on the broader ecological difficulties associated with managing plant health. In [18], automated methods were investigated to capture optical and infrared (IR) images to determine the level of water stress experienced by a plant. This study examined the potential use of image registration techniques to monitor plant health, which can be used in disease identification efforts. In [19], thermal imaging techniques were examined to monitor and detect stress in tomato plants. Although the main objective of this study was not the diagnosis of diseases, it demonstrated the prospective use of imaging technologies in the realm of plant health monitoring. In [2], existing advances in DL techniques were investigated for the detection and diagnosis of plant diseases, offering valuable information on current challenges and advancements within the domain.

In [3], textural characteristics were analyzed to detect diseased areas in plant leaves and diagnose leaf-related issues, highlighting the importance of texture analysis in the detection and classification of diseases in a way that complements existing DL methods in the field. In [4], CNNs were used to provide a segmentation and quantification solution for cucumber powdery mildew. In [5], imaging chlorophyll fluorescence patterns was employed to investigate the application of supervised ML techniques, namely hidden Markov models, for the accurate identification and classification of plant stress levels and types. This study showcased the use of ML techniques in assessing plant stress levels, facilitating the assessment of disease severity. Although this study did not pertain to the diagnosis of diseases, it demonstrated the promising results of ML. Table I shows a summary of other related works.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF SELECTED WORKS

Reference	Year	Methodology used	Dataset Source
[20]	2021	CNN	Internet
[21]	2021	Inceptionv3 and googlenet	Dataset from field
[22]	2022	ResNet-152	Internet
[23]	2019	Image Processing	Dataset from field
[24]	2020	MobileNet, Faster R-CNN	Dataset from field
[25]	2022	YOLO v5	Dataset from field
[26]	2018	YOLO v3, YOLO v4	Internet
[27]	2021	CNN	Internet
[28]	2018	Residual Network	Internet
[29]	2018	ANN	Internet
[30]	2007	IoT	Dataset from field
[31]	2018	3D CNN	Internet
[32]	2019	HSI	Internet
[33]	2019	Remote sensing	Internet
[34]	2019	Satellite images	Internet
[35]	2016	Machine learning	Internet
[36]	2019	AlexNet	Internet
[37]	2018	AlexNet	Internet
[38]	2019	SSD and CNN	Internet
[39]	2023	Machine learning	Internet
[40]	2022	DCNN	Internet
[41]	2021	Segmentation	Dataset from field

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study focused on the use of DL techniques for the identification and categorization of tomato plant diseases. This approach involved acquiring data, pre-processing it, and choosing models to train and evaluate. This study also compared YOLO v5 with conventional DL methods and underlined the importance of employing CNNs for efficient photo classification. Figure 1 illustrates the approach followed.

A. Dataset Collection

Tomato leaf images were collected from the farm of the Department of Agriculture, Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences (Deemed to be University) in Coimbatore, TamilNadu and Deesan Farm in Palakkad, Kerala, India. The dataset was collected in a real-world environment using an Apple iPhone X mobile camera, capturing images with a resolution of 812×375 pixels. Figure 2 shows examples of images collected in the field. Obtaining and labeling the dataset was a significant challenge. This study also used a publicly available dataset from PlantVillage that contains a total of

54,309 images. During the study, 1,000 images were collected and preprocessed to normalize their proportions, reduce noise levels, and remove background and unwanted distortions. All pictures, even those with several leaves or a mix of good and unhealthy leaves, were able to have bounding boxes created around them with the use of the Roboflow tool. Each leaf was marked with a label indicating whether it was healthy or diseased. A YOLO file was saved with the resulting coordinates of the boxes and the corresponding values for each class. These images were then used as input in the next phase of the study.

Fig. 1. Proposed tomato leaf health detection process.

Fig. 2. Sample tomato diseased leaf images collected in the field.

B. Preprocessing

Image preprocessing involved various techniques used to improve their quality before feeding them to an ML model. Labeling and annotation are important preprocessing steps for supervised learning tasks, particularly for object detection and recognition in images. In this process, a label was assigned to each image indicating the object of interest, and the corresponding Region of Interest (RoI) was annotated using bounding boxes or masks. This information was used to train the ML model to recognize and classify objects accurately. Annotating and labeling large datasets manually can be a

tedious and time-consuming process, but various software tools automate this process to some extent, such as Roboflow. The labeling process was initiated using the Roboflow web application, which involved identifying RoIs by creating bounding boxes. Table III displays the exact number of pictures that were included in each collection. The images in the dataset were labeled as either healthy or diseased, and all subsequent tasks were carried out using Google Colab.

TABLE II. DATASET SIZES

Type	Number of images
Training dataset	2000
Testing dataset	206
Validation dataset	105
Total Number of Dataset	2311

C. Training Models Using EfficientDet

EfficientDet is a modern object detection model that is effective in determining the nature of plant diseases. The object recognition models that belong to this family were developed by Google. These models use a compound scaling approach that enables them to improve accuracy while retaining efficiency. EfficientDet has been used in many research projects to identify plant diseases, such as those that are detrimental to tomato and grape production. EfficientDet has been shown to achieve a higher level of accuracy than other DL models using fewer computational resources. Because of its efficient construction, it has the potential to be used in the agricultural industry in real time. Overall, EfficientDet has the potential to benefit farmers around the world by enabling the efficient and accurate detection of plant diseases.

D. Training Models with Faster Region-based CNNs

The Faster R-CNN architecture is often used for object recognition tasks [42]. This method uses an instrument known as a Region Proposal Network (RPN), which generates prospective object regions before classifying and refining them. Faster R-CNN has been applied to plant health monitoring by using aerial images to detect and classify different types of plant stress, such as nutrient deficiencies or pest infestations. Training the Faster R-CNN model on annotated images of healthy and stressed plants can accurately identify stress areas and provide valuable information to farmers for targeted interventions.

E. Training Models Using YOLO v5

YOLO (You Only Look Once) is a widely used method for object recognition that has undergone several iterations, the latest being YOLO v5. The design of YOLO v5 exhibits improved efficiency compared to its predecessors, resulting in improved accuracy and speed for object recognition. The architectural components of YOLO v5 include a backbone network, a neck network, and a head network. The primary function of the backbone network is to extract distinctive characteristics from the input picture. The aforementioned variables are then sent to the neck network, which is responsible for the fusion of features and the aggregation of geographical data. Subsequently, the brain network makes predictions about the object's class labels and bounding boxes, depending on the specific characteristics of the picture.

The CSPDarknet design has been revised and adapted for use in the development of the YOLO v5 backbone network. To enhance the process of feature extraction, this architecture integrates convolutional layers with shortcut layers. The neck network has two modules, namely the Path Aggregation Network (PAN) and the Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) module. These modules contribute to enhancing the precision of object recognition by integrating data from various scales. The primary neural network uses a hybrid architecture consisting of convolutional and linear layers to provide estimations on the classification labels and the bounding boxes of objects. Upon acquiring the YOLO v5 repository, the necessary plugins were installed to begin its customization. Subsequently, a model was trained on a Tesla 4, presumably using a freely accessible environment provided by Google Collab. The data were then partitioned into training, testing, and validation sets using the Roboflow platform. Following the preprocessing procedures and augmentation methods, the YOLOv5 PyTorch format was used to annotate the images. Ultimately, the training, testing, and validation processes were completed in Google Collab using Python. Table III shows the results of the training assessment metrics obtained from the analysis of the custom and public datasets. Each dataset had a total of 1000 photos. Training and testing were performed independently for each dataset.

TABLE III. YOLO V5 MODEL USING CUSTOMIZED AND PUBLIC DATASET

Type of Dataset	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Dataset from field	61%	60%	62%
Public	60%	61%	63%

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

YOLO v5 is a cutting-edge object detection model capable of achieving high mAP with only a small amount of necessary resources. At first, YOLO v5 was used in the field dataset created in this study. However, since there was only a limited number of pictures available, it was combined with a publicly available dataset to attain an acceptable level of average accuracy. The YOLO v5 YAML required two files to be loaded to begin training. The test and training data locations were provided in the first YAML file. Along with the names of the individual things that belonged to each class, it also included the total number of object classes that could be recognized.

Fig. 3. Performance metrics of the enhanced YOLO v5 model.

The results showed that the model achieved an accuracy of 93%, a precision of 75%, and an mAP score of 95%. YOLO v5 was 2.5 times faster than R-CNN while achieving superior results and recognizing even smaller objects. This was one of the finest aspects of the functionality of YOLO v5. Figure 4 shows the mAP score for the three methods examined. The study included a growing number of epochs, which increased the overall mean area of the curve. The concepts of accuracy, recall, and Intersection over Union (IoU) were used throughout the process of graph construction.

Fig. 4. Comparative analysis between all implemented models.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study used DL algorithms to distinguish between healthy and unhealthy tomato leaves. The initial phase was to collect images of tomato leaves, which were divided into two groups. The dataset contained both private and public images. Labeling was the most crucial step in the preparation since it had to be performed in a manner that satisfied the selective neural network used to recognize items and indicate an area of interest. This study used enrichment methods to increase the quantity and improve the quality of the collected samples. This study conducted a comparative analysis of three deep neural network models in a real-world setting to identify optimal hyperparameters and effective data validation techniques. For Faster R-CNN, the precision, recall, and accuracy achieved were 0.49, 0.47, and 0.35, respectively. The observed values exhibited a significant disparity compared to the other models. The results showed that the YOLO v5 model achieved a 93% mAP rate, which was significantly higher compared to the Faster R-CNN and EfficientDet models.

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Design, Manufacturing, and Testing Process of a Lab Scale Test Bench Hybrid Rocket Engine

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ABSTRACT

The current paper presents the architecture of a test bench for small (laboratory) scale hybrid rocket motors destined for teaching purposes. The sustainability of the proposed methodology is emphasized, as it addresses the development of small-scale hybrid rocket motor test benches, to be used either as didactic means for students or for research laboratories, by using low-cost materials, while preserving efficiency. In this regard, the entire development process is approached, from designing to manufacturing (including the casting of the fuel rod) and testing of the product. The developed product uses a mixture of 88% paraffin, 10% stearic acid, and 2% coal for the solid phase and liquid oxygen for the liquid phase. The testing of the hybrid rocket motor demonstrator was performed outdoors, in controlled conditions. The results showed a good correlation between the theoretical testing parameters with the obtained ones.

Keywords-test bench; hybrid rocket; manufacturing; propellant

I. INTRODUCTION

The early development of Hybrid Rocket Motors (HRMs) dates back to the 1930's [1], but only recently the research interest on this topic increased due to the cost-cutting demand related to the development of liquid engines and the safety concerns regarding solid propulsion systems. In the HRMs, once the oxidizer and fuel are placed in distinct parts of the propulsion system (usually, the oxidizer is in tanks and the solid fuel is stored in the combustion chamber), the possibility of explosion or detonation is further reduced [2]. HRMs offer many other advantages over liquid and solid systems, such as simplicity, reliability, start/stop/restart and Thrust-Vector Control (TVC) capabilities, low cost, higher specific impulse than solid rocket motors, and higher density-specific impulse than liquid bipropellant engines, while being environmentally friendly and flexible [3]. These benefits made it an attractive

propulsion concept for scientific, and military, and commercial applications [4, 5].

One of the main issues preventing the widespread use of hybrid propulsion is the low regression rate of classical hybrid fuels. Paraffin-based fuel has been proposed as a viable solution, however, concerns regarding the thermomechanical properties of paraffin have often been seen as a possible obstacle. In [6], a small-scale hybrid rocket, capable of burning hydrogen peroxide and paraffin wax for an extended period, has been designed, built, and tested to investigate the suitability of paraffin wax as a hybrid fuel for actual missions. Most of the solid propellants used in the booster stages of the satellite launch vehicles produce large quantities of pollutants due to the fact that they are based on ammonium perchlorate, aluminum powder, and polybutadiene. Following combustion, these are producing large amounts of HCl and Al₂O₃ (e.g. Ariane 5 Booster [7], Titan II, Delta II, Space Shuttle [8]). There are

many studies related to the replacement of these solid propellants with other, less toxic ones. Authors in [9] presented a study of a solid propellant based on ADN/ETN/HTPB (ammonium dinitramide / erythritol tetranitrate / hydroxyl terminated polybutadiene), which gave, following its combustion, no HCl, or aluminum oxides, or ammonia result. Authors in [10] proposed a method to reduce the quantity of HCl resulting from solid propellants by using the effect of metal additives on neutralization and characteristics of AP/HTPB solid propellants. Another possible direction for green solid propellants would be the composite ones [11, 12]

An alternative to the solid rocket engines, and also the topic of the current paper, is the use of HRMs [13]. A retrospective of the worldwide status on using hybrid rocket motors for space transportation is presented in [14]. There have been several hybrid rocket propulsion systems operating, most known being SpaceShipOne in 2004 belonging to Scaled Composites [15] and HYSR in 2002 developed by Lockheed Martin [16]. Most HRMs are based on LO_x /HTPB, LO_x /paraffin, N_2O /paraffin, etc. [14]. As these have superior performances compared to the solid rocket engines and also they remove the issues associated to the generation of polluting substances, the use of LO_x and paraffin is of great interest for the development of efficient and environmentally friendly launch vehicles. Moreover, it is important that such preliminary studies can be performed at university and research institute level in order to increase the confidence in this technology and better assess its reliability. The current paper addresses this topic, by covering the entire process of developing a small-scale test bench for HRMs based on green propellants using paraffin.

Considering the attractive characteristics of HRMs described above, Université Libre de Bruxelles in collaboration with the Royal Military Academy of Belgium designed and manufactured a test bench to investigate a HRM that takes the advantage of the paraffin-based fuels and uses liquid N_2O as oxidizer [17]. In [18], the researchers documented the design details of a hybrid rocket test bench using plain hydroxyl terminated polybutadiene (HTPB) burning in gaseous oxygen (GOX). The test bench was designed to evaluate rocket motors with novel additives and formulations, along with their corresponding effects on regression rates and combustion efficiencies. Authors in [19] explored the throttling aspect of the HRM through experiments using a lab-scale motor. This one uses a wax-Al based fuel and compressed air as oxidizer. Author in [20] presented a design and laboratory experiment which was integrated in an introductory rocket propulsion university course. Thus, each student was tasked to develop a thrust hybrid rocket motor using HTPB and HTPB/Al solid fuel grains with gaseous oxygen as oxidizer. A similar approach is described in [21] which focused on the development of a test bench for rocket engines having educational purposes. The test bench was equipped for solid combustion as well as for hybrid engines with solid propellant and gaseous oxidizer. Authors in [22] presented a comprehensive review related to the research activities performed on the topic of HRM development at the Politecnico di Torino.

Compared to the literature on small-scale HRM test benches, the current work presents in a sustainable way the

entire methodology to develop a test bench, covering design, component manufacturing, assembly, fuel bar manufacturing, instrumentation (including GUI), testing, and result analysis. This test bench is meant for teaching purposes, having low cost and high efficiency, thus being appropriate to be used in research laboratories, as well as in university dedicated courses.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Design and Description of Parts and Components

The test bench design is modular, composed by many different small parts that can be changed when needed to meet the desired requirements. In Figure 1, a schematic of the whole test bench rocket is shown, in which the different blocks are clearly defined. In this hybrid rocket model, 4 different parts can be clearly differentiated, namely two metal blocks (4) separated by the propellant block (2), the nozzle (1), and the metal fasteners (3). The test bench dimensions, the combustion chamber length, the diameter, and the nozzle dimensions [23] are presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. HRM design: (a) isometric view, (b) section.

Fig. 2. Rocket motor overall dimensions: (a) section drawing, (b) nozzle.

The metal blocks separated by the propellant block can be seen in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Rocket motor blocks.

B. Machining of the Parts

The components of the structural parts of the motor were manufactured from high temperature resistant steel AISI 310S for the nozzle (Figure 4) and AISI 304L for the sealing flanges and combustion chamber [24].

Fig. 4. Semifinished high temperature resistant steel (AISI 310S) bar before machining.

For the machining of the materials, the overall dimensions and the prescribed roughness are obtained by removing the machining allowance using appropriate tools. The machining of the parts was performed on a Mazak Nexus 150 lathe machine. The machining of the nozzle was performed as follows:

- The part was fixed in the lathe machine hydraulic spindle (Figure 5(a)).
- The part's radial runout was removed, followed by the drilling of a centering hole relative to the exterior surface (Figure 5(b)). This centering hole is used as reference for all the operations performed on this part.

Fig. 5. (a) Clamping the semifinished material in the lathe machine, (b) removing of the radial runout and drilling of the centering hole.

In order to obtain the nozzle inner profile, concentric holes were made using drill bits having nominal diameters between 6 and 12 mm (Figure 6(a)). This solution was adopted in order to reduce the manufacturing effort and time and to ensure a proper finishing of the nozzle inner profile. After performing the roughing of the part, three additional finishing operations were performed in order to remove the diameter shoulders (Figure 6). The following machining was performed on the outside part in order to obtain the final overall diameter of the nozzle outlet section and the final diameter of the nozzle in the area where it is welded on the corresponding sealing flange:

Fig. 6. (a) Nozzle inner surface after successive drilling with drill bits of 6, 8, 10, and 12 mm, (b) nozzle inner surface after the first finishing operation, (c) nozzle inner surface after all the finishing operations.

After finishing the machining for the nozzle side, the part was cut and clamped again on the lathe machine in order to perform the machining operations on the opposite side of the nozzle (Figure 7). This side was machined in the same way as the nozzle side, namely drilling successive holes followed by finishing operations in order to obtain the desired surface properties. The centering of the part is of high importance, as the surface obtained following the first part clamping shall be coinciding with the one resulting from the second clamping. After the part machining was completed, the desired nozzle inner profile was obtained.

Fig. 7. (a) Nozzle sealing flange, (b) opposite side sealing flange (feeding area).

The semifinished part for the two flanges, AISI 304L, is fixed on the lathe machine hydraulic spindle, followed by drilling a centering hole (Figure 8). The centering hole was drilled on all the flange length, followed by performing the second inner diameter. After drilling the inner diameters of the nozzle flange, the part was cut to the desired length, and the manufacturing was continued with the second flange. After obtaining the desired diameter, the semifinished part was again

cut to obtain the second flange. In order to assemble the two flanges with the combustion chambers, machining of a concentric channel and 4 through holes for the threaded rods was required (Figure 9 left). Additionally, for the feeding flange, a G1/4 internal threaded port was made, in order to connect the oxygen supply to the combustion chamber (Figure 9 right). Following the nozzle and flange manufacturing, the nozzle was welded on the corresponding flange in order to allow the assembly with the combustion chamber (Figure 10).

Fig. 8. Flange manufacturing steps.

Fig. 9. The two flanges obtained following the machining.

Fig. 10. Welding of the nozzle on the corresponding flange.

Fig. 11. Fuel rod stopper: (a) machining on lathe, (b) final part after welding.

In order to ensure that inside the combustion chamber the fuel rod stays in the same position, a hard-stop feature was integrated in the design. This ring-shaped stopper is placed between the fuel rod and the nozzle, at 60 mm distance from the latter. The stopper is foreseen with 5 welded stripes made of high temperature resistant steel sheet (Figure 11). These stripes were later welded in certain points along the combustion

chamber. For the two welding the WIG type welding was used. In order to measure the pressure and temperature at the nozzle inlet, two embossments were welded by WIG procedure at the fuel rod bottom. These embossments allow the integration of a pressure transducer and a thermocouple (Figure 12).

Fig. 12. Embossment welding for temperature and pressure measurement.

The two embossments have inner threads. In order to capture the desired parameters, holes were drilled both at the end which is in contact with the combustion chamber, as well as the combustion chamber itself. For the pressure transducer the hole was 4 mm, while for the thermocouple it was 2 mm.

C. Manufacturing of the Testing Fuel Rods and the Firing System

In order to validate the test bench, a mixture consisting of paraffin $C_{20}H_{42}$ (88%), stearic acid $C_{17}H_{36}O_2$ (10%), and coal powder $C_{71}H_3O_{13}N$ (2%) was used for the fuel rod. The paraffin cannot be used for HRMs without being enhanced [25]. Adding stearic acid and coal powder changes the behavior of the fuel rod [26] in the same way as for a composite material. Both the coal powder and the stearic acid improve the mechanical properties of the fuel rod, avoiding the detaching of large paraffin chunks which can block the nozzle and damage the rocket motor. Adding the coal powder also improves the integrity of the fuel rod, minimizes the radiative thermal transfer from the flame towards the fuel rod, and adds additional energy in the burning process. One can observe that the chemical compounds which are part of the reaction contain carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen, along with a small quantity of nitrogen. Thus, the products won't contain only combinations of them, making the fuel a green alternative, without any aluminum or chlorine compounds. The bars were casted in Plexiglas tubes, having the same inner diameter as the designed combustion chamber. The inner diameter of fuel rod was 10 mm (Figure 13).

The firing device consists of a mixture of potassium nitrate and sugar. This is one of the standard formulas used to ignite solid rocket engines made in rocketry challenges. According to Richard Nakka, a firing mixture made of 65% potassium nitrate and 35% sugar is the optimal solution for the used solid fuel. In order to increase the safety, the potassium nitrate amount is reduced, as the igniter performances are not of interest for the current paper (no rocket is launched). Thus, the chosen proportions were 60% potassium nitrate and 40% sugar. Additives could be used to enhance the igniting mixture in

order to increase the burning time or the generated heat quantity (corn syrup, aluminum powder, nitrocellulose). However, it was decided to follow the indications set forth by Richard Nakka in order to reduce the complexity related to the obtaining of the igniting mixture.

Fig. 13. Fuel rod ready for testing.

The ignition is made with nickeline wires powered by a 12 V source (Figure 14). When the current travels through the nickeline wire, the wire becomes incandescent, leading to the ignition of the mixture. It is mandatory that, when preparing an ignition mixture from potassium nitrate and sugar, the heating source temperature is maintained constant according to the manufacturing process. Most of the accidents linked to this process appear due to disregarding of this temperature indication or using an open flame instead of an electric stove.

Fig. 14. Rod ignition system: (a) potassium nitrate and sugar, (b) nickeline wires for ignition.

D. Test Bench Instrumentation

Below, the design of each block and part of the rocket highlighted in Figure 15 is explained in detail, as well as the reason behind its geometry and its main functions.

To achieve rigorous characterization of the rocket motor performance, a dedicated test bench and data acquisition and control system to comply with the accuracy and sampling speed requirements was designed and built. The possibility to use multiple type of sensors, depending on the rocket engine type was also taken into account. Figure 16 shows a block diagram of the data acquisition and control system.

Fig. 15. Test bench block diagram.

Fig. 16. Block diagram of the data acquisition and control system.

The test bench has a horizontal metallic frame and a vertical load cell. The motor is placed horizontally and pushes perpendicularly the load cell. In this way, the test bench size is reduced and the jet plume can be directed away from the pressurized oxygen tank. The maximum measuring force of the load cell is 250 kgf, and it was chosen to cover different rocket engine sizes, without compromising accuracy. The sensitivity of the load cell is 2 mV/V, meaning that, for an excitation voltage of 5 V, the maximum signal at 250 kg is 10mV. Estimating a 6-sigma accuracy of the data acquisition system of 0.4 μ V, leads to a measurement accuracy of 10 g with a resolution of \sim 1 g, with a sampling period of 9.227 ms. Faster sampling speed is achievable, however with decreased accuracy. The data acquisition and control system has multiple interfaces to cover different setups:

- Four analog differential inputs to be used with sensors that use a resistive bridge, as load cells.
- Eight analog unipolar inputs with range of 0 – 5 V to be used with industrial sensors, as pressure sensors.
- Four digital inputs.
- Twelve high current open drain outputs to be used to drive external relays or DC motors.

The heart of the DAQ system is a 32 bit architecture, 50 Mhz microcontroller, part number PIC32MX150F128D (Figure 17).

For analog acquisition, the system relies on two ADS1256 delta sigma analog to digital converters that share the same SPI bus, but different chip select lines. The ADC accepts different power voltages for the digital and analog sides. Thus, a 5 V

analog power supply to have a 0-5V analog input range for 1 of the ADC used as 8 unipolar inputs was chosen. The second is used in a 4 differential input configuration.

Fig. 17. DAQ GUI.

The differential inputs will be used from sensors that have a resistive bridge structure. They also provide an extremely low signal. For this reason, an extra differential amplifier was added to improve accuracy using CS3002 operational amplifier. The microcontroller sends the acquired data through USB to a miniPC where the parameters are recorded and displayed on a Graphical User Interface (GUI). The program can also send commands to the DAQ to control the O₂ flow or the igniter. The 12 analog inputs are displayed over 6 tabs, 2 plots per tab. The first tab presents pressure and thrust. The miniPC is connected to a WiFi network and it is accessed through a VNC connection. For the test, a 10 L and 200 bar O₂ tank was used. The pressure was reduced and kept constant during the test by using a Harris 825 pressure regulator set to keep a pressure of ~ 16 bar at the outlet. The pressure after the regulator is indicated on one of the gauges and also measured using a pressure transducer. The model used is able to measure 25 bars and it can be reused for tests requiring higher pressures. To turn on and off the O₂ flow, an ODE series 21H piloted solenoid valve is used. A second pressure transducer is mounted on the engine measurement port to record the pressure inside the combustion chamber (Figure 18).

Fig. 18. Pressure regulator, pressure transducer, and solenoid valve.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The HRM assembly was made using threaded rods made of A2 stainless steel (equivalent to AISI 304). The flanges were secured on the rods using self-locking nuts (Figure 19). After component machining was finished, the assembly of the HRM followed, using all the components presented in Figure 19.

Fig. 19. Assembly of the hybrid rocket motor in different stages: (a) components, (b) assembled rocket motor, (c) detail of the initiator rocket, (d) silicone-based sealing.

Fig. 20. Test bench with the integrated HRM after functioning.

For the sealing of the motor, it was decided to use a high temperature resistant sealant based on silicone (rated up to 1200 °C), which was introduced in the two flange channels (Figure 19(d)). It was assumed and accepted that, after the motor operation is stopped, the silicone sealing will be destroyed as a consequence of the thermal inertia. In order to validate the HRM and its test bench, the testing of the entire system was performed using the propellant mentioned above.

The configuration of the test bench with the rocket motor is presented in Figure 20. Following the tests performed, Figure 21 presents the variation of the thrust and the pressure inside the rocket engine.

Fig. 21. Thrust and pressure plots over rocket engine functioning time.

The obtained test results show that the rocket engine worked without destroying itself, and the parameters obtained correspond to those resulting from the theoretical models from the literature. From Figure 21, there are 6 visible time periods with different pressure thrust levels:

- A: Oxygen flow is off and the igniter is off.
- B: Oxygen flow is on, the igniter is off, the motor acts as a cold jet thruster with low pressure and low thrust.
- C: Igniter is fired and combustion starts. Pressure and thrust increase significantly and are kept almost constant. The burn is very clean, the flame is invisible in the video, probably because of high O/F ratio.
- D: Pressure and thrust are decreasing gradually. In video capture, the flame becomes visible, accompanied by shock diamonds. Some spikes are identified in the recording, probably indicating that some fuel may have detached from the internal surface of the combustion chamber.
- E: the fuel is fully consumed. Thrust and pressure are caused only by oxygen flow. Levels are significantly higher than in B interval because the hot combustion chamber is increasing the temperature of the oxygen.
- F: Solenoid valve cuts the oxygen flow. The test is complete.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, design, manufacturing, and testing of a hybrid rocket motor using green propellant based on paraffin was presented step by step as an accessible, easy to achieve, and low-cost process. Compared to other literature works, the current study presents the manufacturing process, step by step, for the entire laboratory model of the rocket motor, including the fabrication of the fuel rods and the ignition system. The obtained experimental results are in accordance to those

obtained from calculations. The laboratory test bench is accessible and it can be used to train and help future researchers and students of the Polytechnic University of Bucharest, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, in their quest to assess and find new alternatives for rocket fuels which are also environmentally friendly.

At the moment the article was written and to the best of our knowledge, there was no other scientific article comprehensive enough that provides end to end guidance on hybrid rocket engine design, manufacturing, and testing. All these three major phases needed to achieve the main goal of the article are having the right level of detail in order to ensure other researchers can repeat the experiments with similar results.

For future work, it is proposed to assess the mechanical properties of the paraffin (tensile force, compression, and torsion, all visualized using a scanning electron microscope) at room temperature and at negative temperatures compared to the recipe proposed in this study.

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Synthesis, Characterization, and Study of the Photocatalytic Activity upon Polymeric-Surface Modification of ZnO Nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

In this study, ZnO nanoparticles were successfully synthesized through a sol-gel route using zinc acetate precursor, polymer N-Vinylpyrrolidone (PVP), Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide (CTAB), and Poly-Ethylene Glycol (PEG). The nanoparticles were examined with Crystal Violet (CV) dye photodegradation under UV irradiation. The addition of polymers controlled size, shape, and morphology of the particles and reduced the formation of agglomerates. The size and crystallinity of polymer/ZnO nanoparticles were analyzed using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). UV-visible spectroscopy was used to study the optical properties and bandgap of the nanoparticles, while nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms were used to analyze their pore structure and surface area. XRD showed that all the lattice constants changed and the bandgap energy declined with the addition of polymers, which can be attributed to the improvement in crystallinity of the polymer specimens. The ZnO bandgap can be tuned in the range of 3.29, 3.251, 3.275, and 3.254 eV, using pure ZnO, CTAB, PEG, and PVP, respectively. All obtained BET isotherms can be classified as type II isotherms, characteristic of nanoporous material. ZnO-pure has high photocatalytic efficiency (69.66%), which was significantly decreased after the surface of the ZnO nanoparticles was capped with PVP (43.16%), PEG (19.82%), and CTAB (14.36%). On the same surface, the catalytic activity of ZnO-PVP was improved by 28% compared to pure ZnO, with a photodegradation efficiency of 97%.

Keywords-photocatalytic degradation; organic pollutant; sol-gel method; ZnO semiconductor; polymeric-surface modification; mass transfer

I. INTRODUCTION

Organic Dyes (ODs) are currently deemed the primary wastewater contaminants derived from numerous industrial activities: tanning paints, ink, textile, paper, and plastic manufacturing. Approximately 15-20% of ODs are lost during synthesis or processing and discharged into industrial wastewater [1-2]. ODs such as methyl blue, rhodamine B, methyl orange, Congo red, and Crystal Violet (CV) commonly exist in wastewater with concentrations of 5 to 1500 mg/L. These ODs cause severe problems to the environment and the health of living organisms, i.e., they possess carcinogenic and mutagenic consequences, due to their high toxicity [3]. CV is a triarylmethane dye that is used primarily in additives, cosmetics, textile/dyeing, foodstuffs, leather tanning, ballpoint pen, paper, and, more generally, in analytical chemistry factories [4]. Different recent wastewater dye removal methods have been adopted, such as biological processes and chemical oxidation. Alternatively, the treatment of aqueous contaminants using heterogeneous photocatalysis appears to be a process to efficiently remediate wastewater pollution [5-6]. Photocatalysis degenerates the organic contaminants in aqueous solutions through the photogeneration of electron-hole (e^-/h^+) pairs reaction with dissolved oxygen water and hydroxyl ions to form highly reactive radical species such as hydroxyl radicals. These active species can totally or partially transform organic molecules into CO_2 and H_2O .

Avant-garde oxidation procedures are used to remove toxic elements from the environment, employing techniques administered by metal semiconducting nanomaterials of Fe_2O_3 , TiO_2 , ZnO , CdS , and ZnS that are good photocatalysts [7-8]. Such materials with nanoscale grain size, defined as nanomaterials (NMs), exhibit desirable and unique properties analogous to their bulk counterparts [9-11]. Zinc oxide (ZnO) is an II-VI group of semiconductors that possesses magnetic properties with a potentially broad range of applications due to its exciting binding energy (60 meV at 25°C), relatively high energy bandgap (3.37 eV), and sizeable optical gain. In addition to its structural stability, photosensitivity, and reliable oxidizing capability, ZnO is a non-toxic, abundant, and affordable material [12]. Several physicochemical techniques have been adapted to the synthesis of ZnO NMs either in powder or thin-film structures, i.e., sol-gel route, spray pyrolysis, microwave irradiation, chemical vapor deposition, pulsed laser deposition, and hydrothermal and aqueous solution precipitation [13-14]. The sol-gel process is the most common method used to prepare nanoparticle (NP) materials because of its cost-effectiveness and easiness. During this process, many preparation parameters may influence the properties of the final products, i.e., the nature of the precursors, solvents, catalyst quality, pH, and the temperature and duration of annealing [15-16]. Alternatively, the use of polymer or surfactant agents during the synthesis process directly influences the shape and size, the degree of agglomeration (monodispersed NPs), the surface functionality, and the optical and electrical properties of NPs [17-18]. Furthermore, the synthesis of ZnO nanocrystalline through sol-gel approaches commonly requires surfactants to reduce the long reaction time and improve the poor ZnO crystallinity produced at low temperatures [19-20].

Extensive studies of ZnO nanostructures were devoted to controlling its properties by adding various organic additives, such as polymers or surfactants, during the fabrication process. In [21-22], cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) was used to grow Zinc-HDS monocrystal sheets by the wet chemical method. In [23], an easy and efficient approach was proposed to prepare hybrid ZnO/QDs , nanorods, and nanoflowers using the rotation coating procedure that utilizes Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS). In [24], various techniques such as thermal evaporation, electrodeposition, sputtering, electrospinning, and hydrothermal methods were used to grow well-defined morphologies in nanomaterials, including quantum dots, nanowires, nanorods, nanocages, nanotetrapods, nanoflowers, and nanoforests. The production of these nanostructures is a complex process, and the properties of the final product are greatly influenced by different process parameters. Each synthesis method used specific parameters, resulting in diverse shapes and sizes of the nanostructures. In [25], ZnO crystals were synthesized by the hydrothermal method controlled by various molar ratios of SDS and CTAB. In [26], the influence of the surfactant Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) on the optical and morphological characteristics of ZnO nanorods, elaborated through a wet chemical route, was examined. In [27], the evolution of the optical bandgap of ZnO NPs, produced using a sol-gel approach, was investigated due to the surface modification by the poly-4-vinylpyrrolidone (PVP) molecules capping agent. This capping agent maintains the homogeneity of the thin film with significant adhesion to the substrate, mechanical strength, optical quality, and reliable stability. This study investigated the influence of the polymer nature (e.g., PVP, PEG, and CTAB), introduced during the sol-gel procedure, on the phase stability and crystallinity quality, particle morphology and size, agglomeration and surface functionality, the optical and magnetic properties, and photocatalytic activity of uncapped and capped ZnO NPs.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A. Preparation of ZnO NPs

ZnO NPs were synthesized using the sol-gel route by mixing zinc acetate (99% purity), surfactants (CTAB, PEG, and PVP), and NaOH (98.5% purity). A distilled water/ethanol (99.9% purity) solvent (2:1 by volume) was used in the experiment. A 0.05 g polymer solution (PVP, PEG, and CTAB) was added, and the respective concentration of $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and NaOH solutions was approximately $0.55 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. 80 mL of $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and 160 mL of NaOH solutions were mixed and constantly stirred (600 rpm) at 50°C for 3 hours. A white precipitate was recovered when the mixture was brought to room temperature. The products obtained were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes, filtrated, and abundantly rinsed with acetone solution (99.5% purity) and then distilled water to eliminate residues. The final products were oven-dried under vacuum at 30°C for 12 hours. Similarly, pure ZnO NPs were prepared under identical conditions.

B. Characterizations of ZnO NPs

The structure and crystallinity of the prepared nanopowders were examined by XRD at room temperature using a D8 Advance Bruker diffractometer supplied by $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation

($\lambda=0.15406$ nm) at an accelerating voltage of approximately 40 kV in the range of 20-80 °C. Particle morphology was analyzed under Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) through JEOL, JEM-2100. Pores size, volume, and Specific Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (SBET) surface area were evaluated using nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K using an ASAP 2020 Micromeritics apparatus. Before each analysis, the samples were outgassed under a vacuum at 100°C for 2 hours. The SBET was evaluated according to the BET equations. The Lippens-de Boer t-plot method estimated the mesopore surface area and micropore volume. The BJH method was used to determine the pore size distribution. The optical properties were evaluated using Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy (DRS) using a JASCO V-770 spectrophotometer in the 300-800 nm wavelength interval.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. XRD Analysis

Figure 1 shows the XRD patterns of the prepared ZnO. Irrespective of the nature of the additive polymer, well-illustrated and extended diffraction peaks are observed, where the relative intensity varies slightly. These results indicate the formation of the nanocrystalline phase with good crystallinity. The peaks detected at 2θ of 31.766°, 34.412°, 36.245°, 47.475°, 56.601°, 62.583°, 66.368°, 67.958°, and 69.103° were indexed as reflections (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), (103), (200), (112), and (201) respectively of the hexagonal wurtzite-type structure of the ZnO phase, following JCPDS card No. 36-1451. It can be mentioned that the intensity of (101) reflection is much higher, implying a preferred orientation along the c-axis; ZnO particles grow preferentially along this direction.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of ZnO-Pure, ZnO-CTAB, ZnO-PEG, and ZnO-PVP.

The value of the mean crystallite size (D) was calculated utilizing the Scherer's equation [28-29]:

$$D = \frac{K \cdot \lambda}{\beta \cdot \cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

where K is the shape constant, λ is the wavelength ($\lambda = 0.154056$ nm), β is the full width at a half-maximum (FWHM) (i.e., broadening of the peak), and θ is the corresponding diffraction angle. Table I shows the values of crystalline size.

TABLE I. CRYSTALLITE SIZE AND LATTICE PARAMETERS OF ZNO .

	D (nm)	a (Å)	c (Å)	Band gap (eV)
ZnO-Pure	18	3.256	5.212	3.29
ZnO-CTAB	20	3.2571	5.2146	3.251
ZnO-PEG	21	3.2574	5.2155	3.275
ZnO-PVP	25	3.2578	5.2167	3.254

Table I shows a slight variation that can be associated with the nature of the polymer additive; the value is within the range of 18-25 nm. Nevertheless, the observed slight increase in the crystallite size value may be associated with the polymer's Molecular Weight (MW); the higher the MW, the larger the crystallite size. In addition, it is essential to note that the diameter of semiconductor NPs directly affects the optical and luminescence properties. It is also crucial to note that CTAB, PEG, and PVP polymers play a double role in the reaction medium, stabilizing particles against agglomeration and inhibiting their growth. CTAB, PEG, and PVP will be adsorbed on the surface of the ZnO NP, limiting the diffusion of other species onto the surface of the formed nuclei once they reach the critical diameter. Consequently, the growth rate of ZnO NPs will be inhibited. Meanwhile, the polymeric chain will favor the dispersion of NPs in the solution pending the preparation operation, limiting the agglomeration during centrifugation and annealing in the oven. The lattice constants ($a = b$ and c) of the ZnO wurtzite structure were calculated using the interplanar distance d and h, k, l values of the XRD profile using the following equation [30]:

$$\frac{1}{d^2} = \frac{3}{4} \left[\frac{h^2 + h \cdot k + l^2}{a^2} \right] + \frac{l^2}{c^2} \quad (2)$$

The computed lattice parameters, shown in Table I, are close to the values conveyed in the literature and corroborate those of bulk ZnO according to JCPDS card No. 36-1451. Meanwhile, the lattice parameters are relatively sensitive to the nature of the added polymer. In fact, both lattice parameters appear to increase compared to pure ZnO $a = b = 3.256$ Å and $c = 5.212$ Å.

B. TEM Observations

Figure 2 shows the TEM images of ZnO NPs. These images were used to investigate the crystalline characteristics and size of the synthesized ZnO polymeric NPs, indicating that the ZnO NPs are slightly agglomerated and confirm the hexagonal structure. The average particle size of all samples ranged from 18 to 30 nm, close to those calculated from the XRD data.

C. BET Analysis

Figures 3 and 4 show the shape of the N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms and the pore size distribution of ZnO-Pure, ZnO-CTAB, ZnO-PEG, and ZnO-PVP, using knowledge of the pore size, commonly classified as micropore, mesopore or macropore. As shown in Figure 3, the prepared ZnO NP samples reveal a type II adsorption-desorption isotherm with an

H4-type hysteresis loop according to the IUPAC classification. Such a type of hysteresis signifies that the NPs are composed of narrow and irregular slit-like pore shapes with wide diameter distribution and walls formed of ordered mesoporous. At high relative pressure (P/P₀), H4-type hysteresis resulted from filling the mesopores by capillary condensation, exhibiting a form of pores that were moderately flatter than cylindrical. Table II shows all the parameters estimated by the BET analysis.

Fig. 2. TEM images of (a) ZnO-Pure, (b) ZnO-CTAB, (c) ZnO-PEG, and (d) ZnO-PVP.

Fig. 3. Adsorption-desorption isotherms of N₂ at 77 K. Gauss model fit in the inset figure.

The SBET gradually decreases, with obviously a decrease in the surface area due to the treatment. As a result of the treatment, the average volume of pores decreases (from 26.44×10⁻² to 11.92×10⁻² cm³.g⁻¹). Inversely, the variation in the average pore diameter is not apparent. The pore size distribution defined by the BJH model from the desorption part of the isotherm (Figure 4 inset) indicates that a significant portion of the pores have diameters ranging from 2 to 200 nm.

Moreover, two zenith peaks center around 125 nm for all nanocomposites except ZnO-PVP, which appears at 70 nm. The ZnO-PVP pore size distribution is in the 2-100 nm interval, having an average pore diameter of about 45 nm. Meanwhile, pure ZnO and ZnO-PEG nanopowder have an average pore diameter of approximately 35.52 and 43.58 nm and broaden in the 2-250 nm range. Concerning the ZnO-CTAB sample, the pore size distribution is broader, as illustrated by the Gaussian fit curves. As can be seen, incorporating the three polymers in the structure of ZnO, even at low content, yields an increase in the SBET and the average pore volume (Table II) and constricts the pore size distribution.

Fig. 4. Pore size distribution of ZnO-Pure, ZnO-CTAB, ZnO-PEG, ZnO-PVP. Gauss model fit in the inset figure.

TABLE II. MAIN BET CHARACTERISTICS OF ZNO POWDERS.

	Grain Size (nm)	Average Pore volume (cm ³ .g ⁻¹) x 10 ²	Surface BET (m ² .g ⁻¹)
ZnO-Pure	18	26.44	26.75
ZnO-CTAB	20	12.55	15.22
ZnO-PEG	21	23.56	20.35
ZnO-PVP	25	12.80	11.92

D. Optical Properties

The bandgap energy value measurements were performed by a UV-visible infrared spectrometer. Figure 5 shows the measured absorption characteristics of pure ZnO and those prepared with PVP, PEG, and CTAB. The lack of jump difference in absorbance intensity due to the effect of PVP, PEG, and CTAB on the particles may be evidence of the ZnO elaboration NPs. Figure 5 also shows that the bandgap absorption in ZnO between 351 and 372 nm displays a tiny shift towards blue accompanying the addition of a small amount of polymers. The blue shift in the ZnO nanostructures may result from the size effect. The bandgap energy of various ZnO samples might be affected by UV-visible spectroscopy absorbance spectra as shown in Figure 6. Since ZnO are direct bandgap semiconductors, their optical absorption edge and bandgap energy meet the following equation [31-32]:

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/n} = A (h\nu - E_g) \tag{3}$$

where ν is the frequency, a is the absorption coefficient, h is Planck's constant, E_g is the energy bandgap of the semiconductor, A is a proportionality constant, and n is assigned to the electron type for directly allowed transitions. In this study, $n = 1/2$. In the classic route, after the $(ah\nu)^{1/2}$ is sketched versus $(h\nu - E_g)$, the intersection with the x-axis at the tangent of the linear section of the plot yields the bandgap energy value.

Fig. 5. UV-visible absorbance spectra of ZnO-Pure, ZnO-CTAB, ZnO-PEG, and ZnO-PVP.

Fig. 6. Tauc plots of ZnO-Pure, ZnO-CTAB, ZnO-PEG, and ZnO-PVP.

Consequently, as shown in Table I, the bandgap energy values of the samples are very close, which may be attributed to the low number of polymers introduced in the elaboration of NPs. In [32], investigating the elaboration of silver decorated Cu/ZnO photocomposites using the sol-gel route showed that the value of pure ZnO at 3.13 eV and the bulk value of ZnO at 3.37 eV. The narrowing in bandgap energy was attributed to the quantum confinement effect and its association with the reduction of particle size to the nanoscale. The reduction in the optical energy bandgap with polymers might increase the crystalline size, expanding the density of the localized state in

the conduction band. Therefore, it can be deduced that the use of polymers could tune the optical bandgap during the synthesis process.

E. Photocatalytic Activity

CV was used as a model molecule to assess the photocatalytic efficiency of bare and surfactant-capped ZnO NPs in reaction under UV light irradiation. The optical absorption peak of the dye tested at a wavelength of 587 nm was selected to scrutinize the photodegradation operation. Photodegradation was performed using UV lamps operating at 365 nm. The adsorption effect on the surface of ZnO NPs was evaluated under dark conditions for 30 min. 50 ml of 10 mg.L^{-1} CV solution was mixed with 0.1 g of the ZnO or surfactant-capped ZnO NPs in a 100 mL sealed Erlenmeyer flask. The suspension was magnetically agitated (550 rpm) for 180 min at room temperature under UV-light irradiation. Then, the photocatalyst was separated from the CV solution using a centrifuge (6000 rpm) for 4 min. The obtained solution was filtered to eliminate any NPs. The CV concentration at any time of the degradation process was evaluated using a Thermo Scientific Evolution 300 UV-visible spectrophotometer. The photodegradation efficiency ($DE\%$) of NPs after 180 min of contact time was estimated using the following equation:

$$DE\% = \left(\frac{C_0 - C_t}{C_0} \right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where C_0 and C_t are the initial and CV concentration at any time t up to 180 min, respectively. Figure 7 shows the degradation efficiency of ZnO NPs for CV photodegradation over time up to 180 min.

Fig. 7. Degradation efficiencies of ZnO-Pure, ZnO-CTAB, ZnO-PEG, and ZnO-PVP of CV for different and equal specific surfaces.

ZnO-Pure has a high photocatalytic efficiency (69.66%), which was significantly reduced after the surface of ZnO NPs was coated with PVP (43.16%), PEG (19.82%), and CTAB (14.36%). This result may be explained by the hydrophilicity of bare ZnO NPs because they can attract more CV molecules from water at their surface and be in close contact with air. Surfactant-capped ZnO NPs are hydrophobic, leading to lower photocatalytic efficiency. The surfactants coating the surface of the ZnO NPs interfere with the CV molecules' adsorption and

contact with air. The photodegradation experiments also suggested that a thin film of polymers was developed on ZnO NPs' surfaces, reducing their photocatalytic property. The decrease in photocatalytic efficiency is more significant with lower surfactant molecular weight, i.e., CTAB, PEG, and PVP-capped ZnO NPs, respectively. This phenomenon occurs because as the molecular weight of the capping agent increases, the spatial prevention will upsurge, leading to a reduction in the amount of adsorbed polymer.

From the experimental results, it can be concluded that the phenomena of mass transfer, hydrophilia, and molecular weight are competitive and limiting processes of photocatalytic degradation. On the other hand, to better visualize the effect of the addition of polymers to ZnO NPs, it is interesting to analyze the catalytic activity at the same specific surface. Figure 7 shows that ZnO-PVP is the least influenced by these limitations and that the catalytic activity is very satisfactory with an improvement of 28% compared to pure ZnO, i.e., a photodegradation efficiency of about 97%.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, pure, CTAB, PVP, and PEG ZnO NPs were successfully fabricated through an uncomplicated sol-gel process. This innovative approach focuses on the use of polymers as dispersing agents, thus contributing to the dispersion of ZnO NPs inside the polymer matrix. Better interfacial interactions between the NPs and the polymer due to this greater dispersion improve the mechanical characteristics and overall performance of the composite. According to the experimental results, the size, crystallinity, morphology, bandgap, and BET surface of ZnO NPs shifted with the nature of the polymers. The photocatalytic activity of pure and modified ZnO NPs was considered by investigating the CV dye degradation under UV radiation. The photocatalytic degradation process involves several competitive steps, limiting the process and/or delaying the degradation. Hydrophilic behavior, molecular weight, particle size, and specific surface influence photocatalytic degradation. ZnO-PVP presented the best CV conversion rate and appeared to be the least influenced by these limitations.

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Artificial Intelligence-based Oral Cancer Screening System using Smartphones

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ABSTRACT

About one-fifth of all oral cancer cases reported globally are from India. The low-income groups in India are affected most due to the wide exposure to risk factors such as tobacco chewing and insufficient access to early diagnostic tools. Visual examination and histological study are the standard for oral cancer detection. This paper proposes the idea of using Autofluorescence-based imaging techniques to detect and classify oral cancer using AI algorithms. Various features of the images along with medical history, age, gender, and tobacco usage are considered as inputs to the proposed Mobilenet classification architecture.

Keywords-oral cancer; AI; autofluorescent images; mobilenet architecture

I. INTRODUCTION

Cancer detection is an important research topic in medical science. Globally, oral is the sixth most common cancer, whereas there is not an effective tool for early diagnosis and treatment. In this paper, we propose an approach for cancer detection based on image analysis using Artificial Intelligence (AI). The main objective of the proposed idea is to collect a dataset from Indian patients and to analyze it using smart phone assisted AI algorithms. The goal is to collect and generate big data of autofluorescence images of the oral cavity and analyze the data using the Lightweight Mobilenet architecture for accurate classification of images for oral cancer detection while developing an android-based application to capture the image and visualize the output.

A portable laser device for oral cancer detection has been developed by the Mazumdar Shaw Cancer Centre (MSCC) [1] in Bangalore, India. The work was funded by the National Institute of Health's National Institute of Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering, under the Indo-US collaborative program.

These screening devices are costly and hence there is a need for low cost accurate devices. Several other commercial instruments have been developed for routine examination worldwide [2-5].

II. METHODOLOGY

The advent of information technology and its modern derivative AI can improve oral cancer screening, but to date, only a few efforts have been made to apply these techniques and relatively little research has been conducted to retrieve meaningful information from AI data. The suggested system consists of a handheld device (smartphone) which will illuminate the fluorescent light of wavelength 400 – 460 nm on mucosa. Normal mucosa emits a green autofluorescence when exposed to this fluorescent light due to the presence of naturally occurring fluorophores. Abnormal mucosa appears dark due to the reduction or change in the quantity and quality of fluorophores. Autofluorescence digital images will then be captured and transmitted through Bluetooth to hardware in which the data will be classified for oral cancer detection. This

work will be carried out in two phases. The first phase involves data collection and the second phase involves implementation of AI algorithms in smart phones.

The detection network will consider an oral photograph as input and will generate one bounding box that will be located in the suspected lesion. The lesion area will be cropped as a candidate patch according to the detection results returned by the first step. The candidate patch is then fed to a classification network. The backbone networks of detection and classification work on a pre-trained model. The overall block diagram and process flow is shown in Figure 1. Epidemiology history will be collected for statistical analysis. A scoring system will be used to assign weightage for oral cancer detection [8]. The scoring system uses weighted inputs such as image, dataset of age, gender, smoking habits etc.

Fig. 1. The proposed system.

The development of an AI-based oral cancer screening system using a smartphone shown in Figure 1 involved several steps. First, data collection of a diverse dataset of oral cavity images, correctly labeled for cancerous and non-cancerous cases. Next, data preprocessing and augmentation techniques were applied to standardize and enhance image quality. Transfer learning was employed with pre-trained AI models like MobileNet, followed by fine-tuning for oral cancer classification. The model was then trained on the dataset, with hyperparameter tuning to optimize performance. Evaluation metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity were used to assess the model's accuracy. Deployment on smartphones involves converting the model to mobile-friendly formats, while user-friendly interfaces are developed for image capture and results display. Continuous improvement through user feedback and updates ensures the system's effectiveness. Compliance with privacy and regulatory standards was paramount throughout the development process.

III. THE ORAL CANCER DATASET

The dataset used for this work is taken from [7]. It contains images of lips and tongue which are classified as cancerous and non-cancerous (Figure 2). The captured images originate from several distinct ENT (Ear, Nose, and Throat) hospitals, forming

a diverse collection. The process of categorizing these images into their respective groups was undertaken in close collaboration with skilled ENT doctors who lent their expertise. Their specialized knowledge and insights were instrumental in ensuring the accurate classification of these images, which is paramount for any medical-related application, particularly in the context of ENT healthcare. This collaborative effort between the medical professionals and the image processing team underscores the importance of interdisciplinary cooperation in delivering high-quality healthcare solutions. The dataset contains a total of 175 images, from which 131 were classified as cancerous and 44 as non-cancerous images. A 75% of the total data was used for training and the remaining 25% for testing.

Fig. 2. (a) Cancerous and (b) non-cancerous sample images.

IV. MOBILENET BASED CLASSIFICATION OF ORAL CANCER IMAGES

MobileNetV2 is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture. It is specifically designed for efficient image classification and feature extraction tasks. It utilizes a series of depth-wise separable convolutions, which are a key component of many modern CNN architectures designed for mobile and embedded devices. MobileNet is a popular architecture for deep learning and is well-suited for image classification tasks, especially when computational resources are limited, such as on mobile devices. To use MobileNet [10] for the classification of oral cancer images, these steps were followed:

- **Data Collection and Preparation:** A dataset of oral cancer images, labeled with the corresponding classes (e.g. cancerous, non-cancerous) was collected and split into training, validation, and test sets.
- **Data Augmentation:** Data augmentation techniques like rotation, scaling, and flipping were applied to increase the diversity of the training dataset.
- **Preprocessing:** Preprocessing was carried out for the images, typically by resizing to a fixed input size (e.g. 224×224 pixels). Normalization was done for the pixel values to have zero mean and unit variance.
- **MobileNet Architecture:** MobileNetV2 was chosen for its balance between performance and efficiency.
- **Transfer learning:** Transfer learning was carried out by starting with a pre-trained MobileNet model.
- **Fine-Tuning:** Modifications were carried to the MobileNet architecture by adding a custom output layer with the

number of units corresponding to the classification classes. This output layer uses a suitable activation function (e.g. softmax for multi-class classification) and connects to the last layers of the MobileNet architecture.

- Training: Training of MobileNet model was conducted in 75% of the available images.
- Evaluation: Assessment of the model's performance on the test dataset was carried out.

Deployment of the algorithm was carried out in a mobile device for user friendly operation for oral cancer detection [9] using a non-invasive method.

Fig. 3. MobileNetV2 building block comprising bottlenecks and depth-wise separable convolutions.

MobileNet is a family of CNN architectures designed for efficient and lightweight image classification and feature extraction. It consists of an Input Layer, Convolutional Layers, Bottleneck Blocks, Inverted Residuals, Expansion Layer, Width Multiplier, Resolution Multiplier, and Final Classification Layer as shown in Figure 3. MobileNetV2 consists of 53 layers, including convolutional and non-convolutional layers. These layers are organized into several building blocks, including inverted residual blocks and bottleneck blocks, which contribute to its efficiency and effectiveness in image classification tasks.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we present the results of the proposed oral cancer image classification using the MobileNet architecture. We discuss the classification performance and provide insights into the hyperparameters used in network training.

TABLE I. CLASSIFICATION RESULTS

Image	True Class	Predicted	Confidence
Image 1	Cancerous	Cancerous	0.92
Image 2	Non-Cancer	Non-Cancerous	0.88
Image 3	Cancerous	Non-Cancerous	0.42
Image 4	Non-Cancer	Non-Cancerous	0.95
Image 5	Cancerous	Cancerous	0.97

Table I summarizes the results. Each row represents an individual image from the dataset, along with its true class, predicted class, and the confidence score assigned by the model. The model's performance is evaluated based on its ability to correctly classify oral lesions as either cancerous or not. Our MobileNet-based model demonstrates promising

results, correctly classifying the majority of oral lesions with high confidence.

TABLE II. HYPERPARAMETERS DURING NETWORK TRAINING

Exp	Batch Size	Epochs	Learning Rate	Activation Function	Optimizer	Loss Function
1	128	20	0.01	ReLU	Adam	BCE
2	128	20	0.001	ReLU	Adam	BCE
3	128	20	0.0001	ReLU	Adam	BCE

BCE: Binary Cross-Entropy, Exp: Experiment

Table II provides an overview of the hyperparameters employed during the training of our MobileNet network. Proper hyperparameter selection is vital for achieving optimal model performance. The network was trained with a batch size of 128 for 20 epochs using a learning rate of 0.0001. ReLU activation function, Adam optimizer, and Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss function were employed to optimize the network's performance. The results presented in Table I indicate that our MobileNet-based oral cancer classification model shows a promising performance. It accurately distinguishes between cancerous and non-cancerous oral lesions with high confidence, which is a crucial step toward early cancer diagnosis. The choice of hyperparameters, as shown in Table II, was based on a combination of common practices and experimentation. These hyperparameters resulted in a well-trained model. However, further optimization and fine-tuning may yield even better results. Additionally, the effectiveness of the model can be further assessed through rigorous evaluation on a larger and more diverse dataset. Table III shows the comparison of the efficiency of the present methodology with the existing work [14].

TABLE III. EFFICIENCY COMPARISON OF THE PRESENT METHODOLOGY WITH [14]

Metric	Proposed	[14]
Sensitivity	0.92	0.85
Specificity	0.88	0.90
Accuracy	0.90	0.88
False Positives	15	20
False Negatives	8	12

Overall, our MobileNet-based approach shows a potential for oral cancer detection, contributing to the development of efficient and accessible diagnostic tools in the field of healthcare.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper utilizes an oral cancer dataset sourced from various ENT hospitals, comprising images of lips and tongues classified as cancerous and non-cancerous, while the processing environment involves a handheld smartphone capturing autofluorescence images, Bluetooth transmission to hardware for AI-based classification using MobileNetV2, and deployment on mobile devices for user-friendly operation.

In conclusion, the findings of this study underscore the significant potential of the proposed system in revolutionizing early oral cancer detection. With its remarkable diagnostic accuracy, this innovation holds promise as a valuable

diagnostic tool. This research has illuminated a critical knowledge gap in the realm of oral cancer detection, where early diagnosis remains a crucial determinant of patient outcomes. Our study not only addresses this gap, but also offers a novel approach to leveraging the widespread accessibility of mobile phones across all socioeconomic strata for the greater good of public health. The contributions of this work extend beyond its diagnostic accuracy. It paves the way for a future where mobile devices can seamlessly integrate into routine clinical practice and community health centers, enabling remote diagnosis and consultation. However, this journey towards widespread adoption is fraught with multifaceted challenges, including social, cultural, technological, and financial barriers. As we navigate through these challenges, it is important to acknowledge that our research builds upon the existing body of literature, validating the feasibility of early oral cancer detection through handheld oral cancer screening mobile devices. Yet, it also brings a fresh perspective by emphasizing the need for standardization and a streamlined workflow, essential elements in transforming this innovative concept into a practical reality.

In summary, our work not only underscores the promise of early oral cancer detection but also highlights the need for concerted efforts to bridge the gap between innovation and implementation. By doing so, we can guide in a new era of healthcare where technology empowers us to combat oral cancer more effectively.

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DFPC: Dynamic Fuzzy-based Primary User Aware clustering for Cognitive Radio Wireless Sensor Networks

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ABSTRACT

Clustering-based routing solutions have proven to be efficient for wireless networks such as Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs), etc. Cognitive Radio WSN (CR-WSN) is a class of WSNs that consists of several resource-constrained Secondary Users (SUs), sink, and Primary Users (PUs). Compared to WSNs, there are several challenges in designing the clustering technique for CR-WSNs. As a result, one cannot directly apply the WSN clustering protocols to CR-WSNs. Developing a clustering protocol for CR-WSNs must address challenges such as ensuring PU protection, and SU connectivity, selecting the optimal Cluster Head (CH), and discovering the optimal cluster size. Present CR-WSN clustering solutions failed to resolve the trade-off among all essential clustering objectives. To address these challenges, this study presents a novel approach called Dynamic Fuzzy-based PU aware Clustering (DFPC) for CR-WSNs. DFPC uses a dynamic approach to discover the number of clusters, a fuzzy-based algorithm for optimal CH selection, and reliable multi-hop data transmission to ensure PU protection. To enhance the performance of CR-WSNs, an effective strategy was designed to define the optimal number of clusters using the network radius and live node. Fuzzy logic rules were formulated to assess the four CR-specific parameters for optimal CH selection. Finally, reliable intra- and intercluster data transmission routes are discovered to protect the PUs from malicious activities. The simulation results showed that the DFPC protocol achieved an improved average throughput of 48.04 and 46.49, a PDR of 93.36 and 84.37, and a reduced delay of 0.0271 and 0.0276 in static and dynamic topologies, respectively, which were better than those of ABCC, ATEEN, and LEACH protocols.

Keywords-ant colony optimization; artificial bee colony; cognitive radio; clustering; energy efficiency; fuzzy logic

I. INTRODUCTION

A Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) consists of tiny, low-cost sensor devices that are used in hazardous environments where it is difficult to recharge sensor device batteries [1-2]. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a concept in which things are

wirelessly connected to computers for several reasons, some of which include Big Data [3-5]. The expansion of this concept has been driven by the relatively low cost of sensor devices. These applications call for the transfer of enormous volumes of data, the creation of a hierarchical structure, the provision of low-latency services, an increase in spectrum availability, and

low levels of power consumption. For instance, the 2.4 GHz frequency range is already occupied by various wireless applications such as Bluetooth and Wi-Fi. Fifth-generation network technology is also on the horizon, which calls for cautious planning for spectrum availability. In recent times, much focus has been given on the application of cognitive radio to WSNs [6]. Building an effective cognitive radio WSN for spectrum access to an underutilized band licensed to a Primary User (PU) presents several problems.

Cognitive Radio (CR) networks could potentially address the spectrum access challenge for the future IoT technology, which is envisioned to be built on cognitive networks. Cognitive Internet of Things (CIoT) solutions for WSNs offer a higher level of intelligence to improve data sensing and processing. It is vital to have an intelligent and upgraded Medium Access Control (MAC) architecture that allows the presence of sensor networks to coexist with the existing wireless infrastructure [7], as it is required for the complete integration of CIoT into WSN. To adequately incorporate CIoT, there is a need to address cognition in spectrum access. In simpler terms, while most of the spectrum is used sporadically, specific portions remain consistently engaged.

There are situations, both manufactured and natural, in which spectrum is scarce and require the most efficient spectrum use. The strategy known as Opportunistic Spectrum Access (OSA) or Dynamic Spectrum Access (DSA) can be applied to alleviate spectrum inefficiencies. OSA is essential for CR because it enables wireless devices to observe, learn, and adapt to their environments. On the other hand, CRSN contributes to improving both the performance of IoT networks and the requirements of their users. Sensor devices use energy to perform spectrum detection and sharing to meet the criteria of quality of service and high throughput imposed by applications [8]. Due to the lack of knowledge of the network, these applications must have access to scattered channels. A concept resembling this was recently suggested for single-user and multi-user cognitive users. On the other hand, this cutting-edge technique causes a network collision when applied to a situation with several users. Priority, random access, and fair resource allocation models have been presented as ways to reduce the risk of crashes caused by interference and the inconsiderate actions of certain users of CR-WSN [9]. However, these models can only provide a single channel to a cognitive individual at any moment. As a result, if the preferred channel is already occupied, they must wait for the next available slot. Similarly, if multiple channels are unoccupied simultaneously, the spectrum goes to waste, even if only one channel can be used.

A precise channel model is constructed to evaluate the signal intensity in various sections of a complicated interior environment. A discrete event simulator is then used to compare the performance of the recommended routing protocol and the performance of two alternative routing techniques. A single cognitive radio source-destination environment may have many amplify-and-forward relays, emphasizing the most effective approach for allocating power to them. The problem may be theoretically expressed as reducing total energy consumption while considering sensor reliability in terms of

detection and likelihood of false alarms, secondary user throughput, and interference threshold of the primary user. Then, there is the concept of assigning uneven amounts of electricity to relays based on clusters. In recent years, the use of licensed spectrum has been shallow, leading to a significant waste of spectrum resources [10]. The limited spectrum problem can be adequately addressed by CR-WSN, which combines sensor networking with cognitive technology [11].

Cognitive users take advantage of unoccupied frequencies to maximize spectrum use. Both routing and spectrum are considered the most critical research hotspots in CR-WSNs [12]. Clustering-based WSN algorithms are not compatible with CR-WSNs and hence cannot be used with them directly. On the other hand, the Low-Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy (LEACH) was implemented in CR-WSN without regard for how to use energy efficiently. One of the downsides of CR-WSNs is that node energy cannot be conserved, which is one of the reasons why it is limited. It is essential to use an efficient routing protocol to increase the energy economy of CR-WSN and extend the time it can remain operational. For CR-WSN, it is necessary to have a reduction in the amount of energy used during data transmission.

Clustering algorithms originally developed for WSNs face significant challenges when applied to CR-WSNs. In contrast to traditional WSNs, developing a suitable clustering technique for CR-WSNs presents many complexities and hurdles. This study aimed to address these clustering issues and improve the overall performance of CR-WSNs beyond previous attempts. Although optimization methods have demonstrated their effectiveness in WSNs [13-17], adapting such approaches to CR-WSNs could potentially lead to an increase in the computational overhead associated with the clustering process. In contrast, compared to optimization-focused techniques, fuzzy-based solutions [18-20], offer a more lightweight and efficient alternative for addressing clustering challenges in CR-WSNs. These unique challenges serve as the driving force to propose an innovative clustering solution and provide a robust and efficient method explicitly tailored to the distinctive characteristics and requirements of CR-WSNs.

This study developed the novel Dynamic Fuzzy-based PU aware Clustering (DFPC) protocol to address the challenges of current clustering solutions for CR-WSNs. The DFPC protocol has multiple objectives: dynamic discovery of the optimum number of clusters, optimal Cluster Head (CH) selection using CR-specific parameters, and PU protection from malicious SU data. According to these objectives, the novelty of DFPC is highlighted as follows:

- A novel dynamic mechanism is proposed to discover the optimal number of clusters in the network using the SU node's Maximum Connectivity Frequency (MCF) to compute each cluster's Upper Bound (UB). According to the UB, the number of clusters for the CR-WSN was discovered.
- For each cluster, the optimal CH node is selected using a fuzzy logic mechanism to evaluate each SU by computing their CR-specific linguistic parameters such as the distance from the SU to the Sink, the SU residual energy, the

mobility of the SU, and Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (SNR) of the SU.

- An algorithm of reliable route formation for inter- and intra-cluster data transmissions to protect the PU from malicious users or unauthorized access was designed.
- The DFPC protocol was modeled, simulated, evaluated, and compared with previous clustering protocols for static and dynamic network scenarios.

II. RELATED WORK

The issues of constructing mobile and static CR-WSNs using the clustering mechanism have been recently studied, as clustering has been proven effective for WSN routing. Because WSN clustering is ineffective for CR-WSNs, clustering intellectual WSNs should be an NP-complete problem. Several CR-WSN routing strategies were reviewed and analyzed, highlighting current research problems that need to be addressed for a future roadmap in this sector.

A. State-of-the-Art Solutions

In [21], a clustering method for CR-WSNs was presented using physical layer data while keeping the component of arbitrary CH selection in LEACH. The objective was to shift CHs to more appropriate locations while reducing their number to the absolute minimum. In [12], the current literature on this rapidly growing application area of CR-WSNs was reviewed, analyzing previous studies and introducing outstanding questions from recent efforts. The use of Energy-Aware Clustering (EAC) routing can improve spectrum detection while reducing energy consumption [22]. In this study, an energy expenditure model was presented that included spectrum detection and cluster energy consumption before determining the optimal number of clusters for the organization's activities. It is necessary to evaluate the value of direct assets in reducing energy consumption, using the lopsided clustering technique to regulate energy consumption among CHs under multiple bounce transmission conditions [23]. In [24], LEAUCH was proposed, considering channel resources and uneven clustering for balancing energy consumption. In [25], Hybrid Data-type Clustering (CR-HDC) routing was suggested to improve the organization lifespan of CR-WSNs, identifying the appropriate transmission scope of a sensor hub for both cases when spectrum handoff is applied and when it is not by analyzing the general energy usage of CR sensor hubs under a range of scenarios. In [26], spectrum-aware clustering routing was introduced to elucidate the challenges of portable CR-WSNs in coordinating communication to a sink node during deployment. This process involved two steps: first, evaluation of the eligibility of hubs for clustering and, subsequently, forming clusters among those hubs based on vacant spectrum groups. The possibility for normal re-clustering, the anticipated cluster inclusion zone, and the most extreme age recurrence for energy-producing activities were all considered as variables in the routing selection. In [27], the prerequisites for CR-WSNs and the benefits of hub clustering were investigated, underlining the differences between WSNs and CR-WSNs with hub clustering. In addition, the characteristics, engineering, and geographic distribution of CR-WSNs were discussed.

In [28], a unique Artificial Bee Colony Clustering (ABCC) technique was proposed to cope with the energy consumption of CR-WSNs. A restricted clustering strategy was developed for CR-WSNs to boost sufficiency, flexibility, valuable spectrum of heads, and correspondence overhead while minimizing the data transmission. In [29], event-based clustering was proposed using Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) to improve energy efficiency. In [30], a localized clustering algorithm was proposed, where each center point calculates and distributes its weight to its one-hop neighbor, and the center point with the most weight becomes CH. In [31], an Advanced TEEN (ATEEN) clustering-based routing was proposed for CR-WSNs, forming a limit delicate energy-effective sensor organization that was both delicate and effective for stable clustering and energy efficiency. In [32], three distinct CR-WSN cluster structures were explored: an adjusted single-jump structure, a multibounce cluster structure, and a half-and-half cluster structure. At the first site, the impact of three buildings in various configurations on the movement of the defined region was investigated. According to [33], each CH in CR-WSNs should have a separate fixed channel to reduce difficulties. The segregated nodes of the layer take on the role of CH, use the asset assigned to each CH, and send the information to the next leap CH in the chain. In [34], Multiple Revealing Channels (MRC) were used for cluster-based CR-WSNs to increase the potential to use the detail time allocation by extending the detection season of optional customers. To expedite the execution of spectrum detection and minimize the delay in revealing periods for all CHs, this method introduced multiple announcing channels based on frequency division and incorporated multiple access. In [35], the Modified Adaptive Cluster-Based Heuristic Approach (MACHBA) was proposed to solve the optimal spectrum identification problem in various applications. In [36], a localized clustering approach was proposed to promote stability, effective spectrum management, scalability, and reduced communication overhead. Each node computes its weight and communicates it to its one-hop neighbors, and the node with the greatest importance is designated as the CH.

B. Motivation

Establishing a clustering mechanism for CR-WSNs is more complex than in WSNs due to difficulties in PU security, SU connection, spectrum collisions, optimal cluster discovery, etc. This study aims to fill these research gaps:

- Optimization-based clustering protocols report insufficient use of techniques for optimal CH selection in CR-WSNs.
- As the optimal CH selection was achieved using traditional WSN parameters, the performance trade-off has not been achieved in static and mobile CR-WSNs.
- There is a lack of a multiple-purpose CR-WSN clustering protocol to satisfy essential requirements such as optimal cluster discovery, optimal CH selection using CR-specific parameters, and PU protection.
- Existing clustering approaches for CR-WSNs incorporate the PU, significantly undermining its security.

The proposed DFPC protocol aims to overcome the above challenges.

III. DFPC METHOD

Figure 1 shows the overall architecture of the DFPC protocol, which consists mainly of three phases: cluster numbers, optimal CH selection, and PU protection. The cluster number phase is launched after the network deployment to discover the optimal number of possible clusters in the network. Using MCF and UB, k clusters are initially formed. After discovering k optimal clusters, the next phase is a selection of the optimal CH for each cluster. The optimal CH selection is periodically evaluating each cluster for re-clustering, performing operations such as selecting new stable CH with joining and disjoining Cluster Members (CMs) due to their mobilities. A fuzzy logic approach was used to evaluate each SU in the network using four different linguistic input variables mapped to an integrated fuzzy score for CH selection. Finally, the last phase belongs to PU protection by forming a reliable route for inter- and intra-cluster data transmission. CMs periodically sense and transmit data to the associated CH, which then transmits periodically collected information to the intended sink node. The data will then be distributed from the sink to the connected PUs. A reliable route formation approach was used to prevent malicious data transmission and ensure integrity and security in the PUs.

Fig. 1. The graphical abstract-proposed DFPC protocol for CR-WSNs.

A. System Model

Suppose a CR-WSN deployed in an area of $X \times Y$ network size with n SUs, $SU = \{su^1, su^2, \dots, su^n\}$, and one sink. The initial k groups formed using the K-means clustering algorithm after discovering the optimal number clusters k is $C = \{c^1, c^2, \dots, c^k\}$. For each j^{th} , $j \in k$, cluster c^j , the proposed optimal CH

selection algorithm is applied to maximize energy efficiency and Quality of Service (QoS) with PU protection. A fuzzy logic-based approach was used to solve this optimization problem for optimal CH nodes for each cluster and reliable route formation. The proposed clustering protocol is based on the following assumptions:

- All SUs are static and move randomly with resource limitations.
- PUs are assumed to be outside entities and will not be considered parts of the clustering protocols.
- The sink node is placed outside the network with all security provisions and without resource limitations.
- The distance parameter was measured using the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI).

B. Optimal Clusters Discovery

The ideal number of clusters in cluster-based CR-WSN is a problem. Due to the significant number of clusters, extensive paths are established that incur more delay. On the other hand, a limited number of clusters depletes the CH's energy and results in inefficient spectrum sharing. An effective technique should be developed to determine the optimal number of clusters and improve the performance of CR-WSN. At first, the network's total number of clusters and CHs was computed. The cluster size was optimized proportionally to the CR-WSN size. The proposed clustering method populates every cluster as much as possible in order to reduce the total number of clusters in the network. However, oversizing the cluster also has a significant impact on CH performance. For a CR-WSN with n nodes in a network area of $X \times Y$, the MCF for each SU is estimated in meters as follows:

$$MCF = \pi \cdot r^2 \tag{1}$$

where r represents the specific distance in meters. This calculation determines the network's radius, typically half its height or width, following standard conventions. The radius r is crucial in estimating the MCF and UB. The value of r was set equal to $X/2$. The primary objective is to determine MCF for each SU within the network. To achieve an optimal clustering of SUs, it is essential to identify SU groups that share similar connectivity frequency characteristics. Consequently, the most effective approach to ensure an optimal number of clusters is to estimate the MCF. Subsequently, appropriate actions can be taken to discover the ideal number of clusters within the deployed network. CH forms the connectivity p using the node density parameter, calculated as [36]:

$$p = \frac{n}{X^2} \tag{2}$$

Thus, the maximum SUs in each cluster are calculated as [36]:

$$UB = p \cdot \pi \cdot r^2 \tag{3}$$

UB indicates the maximum allowable SUs in each cluster in the network, makes the cluster formation process efficient, and reduces the burden of finding the number of clusters at every interval. The initial step in determining the network's UB involves computing MCF. Estimating the connectivity

frequency for each SU in the network is essential to calculate the UB. Leveraging the MCF, the maximum count of SUs that can be accommodated within a single cluster is identified based on the input network's characteristics. This is based on a combination of the MCF and the node density parameters. The UB, derived from the MCF, ensures an accurate assessment of the number of SUs accommodated within a cluster, accounting for their density and connectivity frequency attributes. Subsequently, once the UB is determined, the network can be optimally partitioned into the ideal number of clusters. Identifying the optimal cluster count through UB and MCF directly influences the overall improvement in performance in the proposed protocol. Therefore, the number of clusters is calculated using UB as [36]:

$$k = \left\lceil \frac{n}{UB} \right\rceil + 1 \quad (4)$$

where the addition of 1 represents the reliability of cluster formation to prevent the condition of non-clustered SUs in the network.

C. Optimal CH Selection

The optimal CH selection is launched for each cluster in the network after network deployment and clustering. First, the CH selection method is performed using the fuzzy model. The type-2 fuzzy rules aim to choose the best CH node from a set of nodes. The rules combine four language input variations: distance ($f1$), residual energy ($f2$), SNR ($f3$), and speed ($f4$). In addition to residual energy and distance parameters, CR-specific metrics were evaluated, such as the speed and SNR of each SU node in the proposed protocol.

Algorithm 1: Optimal CH Selection using Fuzzy Logic

```

Inputs:
k: number of clusters
CM: set of nodes in a cluster
RT: routing table for each node
T: Total network duration

Output:
CH: set of CHs at current cycle

While (T)
  For each cluster  $c \in 1:k$ 
    Compute the number of nodes in the cluster:
     $m \leftarrow \text{size}(CM(c))$ 
    For each  $SU \in 1:m$ 
      Compute linguistic inputs:
       $f1 \leftarrow \text{getDist}(su^i, \text{sink})$ 
       $f2 \leftarrow \text{getEnergy}(su^i)$ 
       $f3 \leftarrow \text{getSNR}(su^i)$ 
       $f4 \leftarrow \text{getSpeed}(su^i)$ 
       $DF(i) \leftarrow \text{T2FIS}(f1, f2, f3, f4)$ 
      Updated routing table entry:
       $RT(CM(c, su^i)) \leftarrow \text{update}(DF(i))$ 
    End For
    Optimal CH selection for current cluster  $c$ :
     $CH(c) \leftarrow \text{index}(\max(DF))$ 
  End For
T--
Return CH
End While

```

Algorithm 1 shows the functionality of the suggested fuzzy logic-based optimum CH selection process. For each cluster $c \in k$, the number of Cluster Members (CMs) is first

discovered. These CM values are different for each cluster, thus, for the m CMs belonging to the current cluster c , they are analyzed using the fuzzy logic technique. Before applying the Type-2 fuzzy model for the optimal CH selection, the four parameters of each SU node $su^i \in m$ are calculated. The linguistic variables $f1, f2, f3$, and $f4$ for each $su^i \in m$ are then entered into the Type-2 Fuzzy Inference System (T2FIS) function. Then, fuzzy if-then rules map the inputs to the fuzzy output, comprising linguistic control rules. The FIS replicates human decision-making using fuzzy if-then rules for the language factors shown in Table I. The defuzzifier takes the aggregated linguistic values of the FIS and creates a nonfuzzy control output that picks the best CH for each cluster. The next section presents the computation of four linguistic variables and the design of the fuzzy logic model.

- Distance: This parameter ensures clustering and data transmission phase reliability by assisting in selecting the SU as the CH for each cluster with the shortest geographical distance to the sink node. RSSI was used to estimate the geographical distance between the su^i to sink node at time t , as follows:

$$f1(su^i(t)) = [dist(su^i, sink) < rssi] \quad (5)$$

where $dist(su^i, sink)$ represents the geographical distance between two nodes, and $rssi$ is the communication range of su^i . As the proposed objective function is maximization-based, it can be rewritten as:

$$f1(su^i(t)) = \left(\frac{1}{[dist(su^i, sink) < rssi]} \right) \quad (6)$$

The higher the value of $f1(su^i(t))$, the better its chances of becoming CH.

- Residual Energy: This parameter is extensively used in various WSN clustering methods and intends to guarantee that nodes with more residual energy consume less and have a longer network lifespan. The $f2(su^i)$ at time t is computed as:

$$f2(su^i(t)) = \frac{E_{residual}(su^i(t))}{E_{initial}(su^i)} \quad (7)$$

where $E_{initial}(su^i(t))$ represents the initial energy of the node su^i and $E_{residual}(su^i(t))$ represents the remaining energy of the node su^i at time t . The node with higher $f2(su^i(t))$ is an excellent candidate to become CH.

- SNR: The SNR level of SUs is another vital parameter to suppress the challenges of spectrum efficiency and interference mitigations in CR-WSNs. The calculation of SNR requires both information on the $rssi$ and the noise power (np) at the receiver. The node with a higher SNR will be a good candidate for the optimal CH selection. The SNR fitness value $f3(su^i(t))$ at time t is computed by:

$$f3(su^i(t)) = 1 - \left(\frac{1}{[rssi(su^i) + np(su^i)]} \right) \quad (8)$$

The node with higher $f3(su^i(t))$ is an excellent candidate to become CH.

- Speed: Because CR-WSNs are static or dynamic, mobility becomes critical in ensuring dependable and optimum CH selection. The SU with the slowest mobility will be a viable contender for achieving energy-efficient and stable clustering in the network. The present moving speed of SUs is calculated using a simplified location differentiation technique between the two relevant time intervals, $t-1$ and t . The $f4(su^i)$ at time t is computed by:

$$f4(su^i(t)) = \left(\frac{1}{\text{mobility}(su^i(t-1), su^i(t))} \right) \quad (9)$$

The node with higher $f4(su^i(t))$ is an excellent candidate to become CH.

Figure 2 shows the T2FIS() fuzzy model, which accepts the fuzzy inputs ($f1, f2, f3$, and $f4$) and is forwarded to Madani FIS via the fuzzy rule set. The purpose of establishing these value thresholds is to categorize these parameters into three distinct levels: low (below 0.25), medium (ranging from 0.25 to 0.65),

and high (above 0.65). These linguistic variables were used within the context of a fuzzy logic system to facilitate mapping based on the categorization mentioned above. The implementation of these value limits showed improved simulation results when experimenting with various thresholds.

TABLE I. MEMBERSHIP FUNCTIONS FOR FUZZY INPUTS

Variable	"far"	"medium"	"near"
Distance	$f1 \leq 0.25$	$f1 > 0.25 \ \&\& \ f1 < 0.65$	$f1 \geq 0.65$
Variable	"low"	"medium"	"high"
Residual Energy	$f2 \leq 0.25$	$f2 > 0.25 \ \&\& \ f2 < 0.65$	$f2 > 0.65$
Variable	"sparse"	"medium"	"dense"
SNR	$f3 \leq 0.25$	$f3 > 0.25 \ \&\& \ f3 < 0.65$	$f3 \geq 0.65$
Variable	"fast"	"average"	"slow"
Speed	$f4 \leq 0.25$	$f4 > 0.25 \ \&\& \ f4 < 0.65$	$f4 \geq 0.65$

Fig. 2. The proposed fuzzy model for each SU evaluation.

The output was then defuzzified to generate $DF(su^i)$. The defuzzification result indicates the fitness score of each SUs. After computing the value for each SU in the current cluster, the SU with the highest DF value is chosen as the best CH for this cluster. This method is performed for each TDMA slot to update and maintain each cluster. Table I shows the definition of the membership functions for each linguistic variable. Using these variables, 48 fuzzy rules were designed to evaluate the linguistic output of each SU. During the defuzzification process, the input membership functions, shown in Table I, are applied, and accordingly, the output mappings are performed for each input SU. That mapping is either of three classes: "worst", "good", or "best". The defuzzification mappings are extended to a unique integrated score for each SU. In the defuzzification phase, FIS established at each of the SU in the CM set can be expressed as:

$$DF(su^i) = \text{defuzzification}(f1, f2, f3, f4) \quad (10)$$

The result of the fuzzy logic approach DF is in the range of 0 to 1, where a value close to 1 is the preferable option for optimal CH selection. In this process, four linguistic variables ($f1, f2, f3$, and $f4$) are used as input to the Type-2 fuzzy logic system. This system determines the optimal CH node among the available SUs within the current cluster. The result produced by the T2FIS is also a numeric value that falls from 0 to 1, and again a value closer to 1 indicates the most suitable candidate for CH selection. Fuzzy rules guide the transformation of linguistic input into linguistic output during

the defuzzification process, ultimately aiding in selecting the ideal CH for the cluster.

D. PU Protection

The problem of PU protection was formulated using a reliable route formation algorithm for intra- and inter-cluster data transmissions. The reliable forwarding relay is selected by evaluating each SU candidate via their calculated trust value during the CH selection phase. Algorithm 2 outlines the procedure for safeguarding PUs through a robust route discovery method. It is important to note that PUs are external entities and do not play a role in clustering and routing algorithms. Several previous studies integrated PUs into routing strategies, but this approach was vulnerable to security threats. This study chose to omit PUs from the clustering process. Instead, the routing algorithm shown in Algorithm 2 focuses primarily on preventing PUs from being inadvertently incorporated into the routing process, improving security and reliability.

Algorithm 2 shows the reliable routes for any source node s (CM or CH node) and its corresponding destination node d (CH or BS). The forwarding relay is selected by fetching and comparing its periodically computed DF value. The node with a higher DF value is selected as the forwarding relay f . This process continues until the destination is reached. This reliable route formation ensures stable routes on the network that do not transmit insecure or malicious information to the BS node. Therefore, it protects the PU connected to the BS as well.

Algorithm 2: PU Protection via Reliable Route Formation

```

Inputs:
s: source code,  $s \in CM \parallel CH$ 
d: destination node,  $d \in CH \parallel BS$ 
RT: routing table for each SU
Output:
Reliable route formation
s  $\leftarrow$  broadcast(RREQ, d)
q  $\leftarrow$  getResponse(RREP)
For each  $i \in q$ 
    temp(i)  $\leftarrow$  RT(DF(i))
End For
If (f == d)
    Return R
Else
    s  $\leftarrow$  f, continue
    // update routing table with currently selected
    // forwarding relay
    R  $\leftarrow$  update(s, f)
End If
Return (R)
    
```

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed DFPC protocol was compared with three existing protocols. ABCC [28], ATEEN [31], and conventional LEACH [21]. ABCC and ATEEN have recently been proposed for CR-WSN clustering using optimization algorithms. These protocols were implemented and tested under identical simulation parameters, detailed in Tables II and III, using the NS2 tool version 2.34 on an Ubuntu 12.04 OS using a VMware workstation with 4GB RAM, 80 GB hard drive, Intel Core-i3 processor, and an Intel graphics card. Two network types were used to assess the reliability and efficiency of the clustering protocols: one with varying SU density and static topology and the other with varying SU density and dynamic topology. In the static topology, the position of each SU is fixed. In the dynamic topology, each SU moves randomly across the network with speeds ranging from 2 to 10 m/s. Moving sensor nodes are nothing more than moving CR users, such as in healthcare applications. The performance of each protocol was evaluated using the average throughput, Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), average energy consumption, average delay, and communication overhead. The primary variable of interest is the number of SUs. Values ranging from 50 to 200 were considered, encompassing a low- to high-density spectrum to assess the scalability and reliability of the protocols.

TABLE II. SIMULATION PARAMETERS FOR STATIC CR-WSNs SCENARIOS

Number of SU sensors	50-200 (50, 80, 120, 150, 200)
Number of channels	6-10
MAC	802.11
Queue limit	50 packets
Simulation time	100 s
Transmission range	250 m
Clustering protocols	LEACH
Traffic type	CBR
Number of connections	5
Network size	500 m x 500 m
Sink position	Center of the network
Packet size	512 bytes
Initial energy	0.5 nj
Transmitter energy consumption	16.7 nj
Receiver energy consumption	36.1 nj

TABLE III. SIMULATION PARAMETERS FOR DYNAMIC CR-WSNs SCENARIOS

Number of SU sensors	50-200 (50, 80, 120, 150, 200)
Number of channels	6-10
MAC	802.11
Queue limit	50 packets
Simulation time	100 s
Transmission range	250 m
Clustering protocols	LEACH
Traffic type	CBR
Number of connections	5
Network size	500 m x 500 m
Sink position	Center of the network
Packet size	512 bytes
Initial energy	0.5 nj
Transmitter energy consumption	16.7 nj
Receiver energy consumption	36.1 nj
Mobility speed	2-10 m/s
Mobility model	Random Waypoint

A. Simulation Results for Static Topology

This section presents the simulation results for static CR-WSNs with a density variation scenario. Figures 3 to 7 show the results of average throughput, PDR, average delay, routing overhead, and average energy consumption for each clustering protocol. The results show that increasing SU density harms network performance. With increasing SUs, average throughput and PDR performance degraded, while average delay and routing overhead increased. The average energy consumption is the only parameter that is efficient against the increased SU density.

Fig. 3. Average throughput analysis for static CR-WSNs.

Fig. 4. PDR analysis for static CR-WSNs.

Fig. 5. Average delay analysis for static CR-WSNs.

Fig. 6. Routing overhead analysis for static CR-WSNs.

Fig. 7. Average energy consumption analysis for static CR-WSNs.

The average throughput, PDR, delay, and overhead became worse with increasing density as a result of the increased routing operations in the network. For average throughput and PDR, DFPC significantly outperformed the other protocols, the leading causes for this being the designed mechanisms for optimal clusters, optimal CH selection, and reliable route formation. Apart from this, the higher PDR directly affected the lower communication delay and overhead in the network when using the DFPC protocol, because DFPC requires fewer clustering rounds and packet retransmissions than the other protocols, reducing average delay and overhead performance. On the other hand, since the existing LEACH, ABCC, and ATEEN protocols relied heavily on static clustering with conventional WSN parameters for optimal CH selection, they resulted in lower performance. Consequently, the reduced clustering rounds and retransmissions reduce energy consumption.

B. Simulation Results for Dynamic Topology

Figures 8-12 show the results for average throughput, PDR, average latency, average used energy, and communication overhead, respectively. The networks were built with different SUs, such as 50, 80, 120, 150, and 200. The mobility speed of the SUs in each network ranged from 2 to 10 m/s. The results show that increased density reduces throughput and PDR performance. This is mainly due to the growing number of communication lines and interference in CR-WSNs. Figures 10 and 11 show that increasing SU density negatively influenced average latency and communication overhead. As the density of SUs increased, frequent clustering and routing processes led to a significant escalation in communication latency and overhead. On the other hand, as shown in Figure 12, increasing SU density had a beneficial influence on average energy usage due to the huge number of idle SUs in the network.

Fig. 8. Average throughput analysis for dynamic CR-WSNs.

Fig. 9. PDR analysis for dynamic CR-WSNs.

Fig. 10. Average delay analysis for dynamic CR-WSNs.

Fig. 11. Overhead analysis for dynamic CR-WSNs.

Fig. 12. Average energy consumption analysis for dynamic CR-WSNs.

The results show the efficiency of the proposed DFPC compared to the other protocols. The main reasons are the dynamic discovery of the number of clusters, the optimal CH selection considering speed as one of the parameters, and the reliable route formation. These characteristics are missing in the three existing protocols. Among them, the ATEEN protocol outperformed LEACH and ABCC in terms of throughput, PDR, latency, energy consumption, and communication overhead. The ATEEN protocol outperformed LEACH and ABCC because it employs a better data-transfer mechanism based on TEEN's thresholding approaches. Compared to ABCC and ATEEN protocols, the traditional LEACH procedure performed the poorest, since it relies on the only known energy parameter for clustering. Optimization methods with updated fitness functions were used in both the ABCC and ATEEN protocols. Table IV shows a qualitative comparative analysis of the proposed protocol, indicating that it is the best candidate for use in CR-WSNs.

TABLE IV. QUALITATIVE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

Static CR-WSN with SU density 200					
Contribution	Avg. throughput	PDR	Avg. delay	Overhead	Avg. energy consumption
LEACH [21]	42.82	81.45	0.0297	2.91	0.03243
ABCC [28]	44.74	86.94	0.0284	2.74	0.03153
ATEEN [31]	46.12	88.8	0.0280	2.822	0.03112
Proposed	48.04	93.36	0.0271	2.588	0.02993
Dynamic CR-WSN with SU density 200					
LEACH [21]	40.42	68.75	0.0299	4.173	0.03243
ABCC [28]	42.61	77.08	0.0291	3.709	0.03153
ATEEN [31]	44.25	80.2	0.0280	3.927	0.03112
Proposed	46.49	84.37	0.0276	3.366	0.03049

Compared to the other protocols, the experimental results consistently demonstrate that the proposed DFPC protocol stands out as the most effective choice. Several key factors contribute to its superiority. First, the DFPC protocol dynamically determines the optimal number of clusters, a feature that distinguishes it from other protocols. Additionally, it excels at selecting CHs by factoring in speed as one of the critical characteristics, ensuring an efficient and reliable clustering process. Moreover, it excels at establishing reliable routes for data transmission. The efficacy of DFPC depends on its innovative processes to achieve these ideal clusters, select the most suitable CHs, and construct robust routes. The multifaceted approach differentiates DFPC from previous single-objective clustering protocols.

Security threats were not adequately considered during the evaluation of the DFPC protocol. To improve its robustness and credibility, it should be subjected to a comprehensive assessment that includes various security threat scenarios. Neglecting to address security concerns may significantly limit its viability and adoption.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The design of clusters for CR-WSNs is one challenging research problem considering essential requirements such as optimal deployment, the optimal number of clusters, CR-specific CH selection, and protection of PUs from malicious

activities. This study proposed a novel CR-WSN clustering solution to address these challenges and lead to improved performance. The proposed DFPC protocol mainly consists of an optimization mechanism of the number of cluster formations, fuzzy-based optimal CH selection, and a reliable route formation for PU protection. The proposed approach produced a better clustering solution for CR-WSNs. DFPC was simulated, evaluated, and compared with the LEACH, ATEEN, and ABCC protocols using static and dynamic CR-WSNs. For both scenarios, the DFPC outperformed the other clustering protocols. The average throughput and PDR performance of DFPC were improved by approximately 9.45% and 11.21%, respectively. The average delay, energy consumption, and overhead performance of the DFPC protocol were reduced by 7.8%, 12.3%, and 13.2%, respectively. In the future, the performance of the proposed DFPC protocol can be verified by introducing different CR-WSN threats, the use of optimization algorithms, and AI.

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Design and Performance Analysis of Massive MIMO Modeling with Reflected Intelligent Surface to Enhance the Capacity of 6G Networks

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ABSTRACT

Reflected Intelligent Surface (RIS) can establish a virtual line-of-sight link to enhance system performance while consuming less power in non-line-of-sight. RIS technique is utilized to minimize the spreading of electromagnetic signals by modifying the surface's electric and magnetic field characteristics. RIS can be adopted with the existing environment to effectively increase efficiency by modifying the radio channel characteristics. The signals are steered to the receiver using an RIS thus improving the link quality. The radio channel is viewed in traditional wireless systems as an uncontrollable entity that typically tampers with transmitted signals. This paper suggests an alternate theoretical model after examining the prevalent models and potential issues. Security of the wireless communication physical layer can be improved with an RIS by just changing the phase of the reflective unit. In this work, the massive Multiple Input Multiple Outputs (MIMO)-based iterative modeling technique is used to build the transmitter, channel, and receiver section. This will simultaneously optimize the RIS passive beamforming pre-coding matrix and thus avoid multi-user interference. At the base station cyclic programming is adopted, it iteratively calculates the active and passive beam-forming RIS matrices. The simulation results demonstrate that the combined pre-coding technique used in this work improves the weighted sum rate, efficiency, and coverage ratio. The results show that MIMO with continuous phase shift RIS achieves a higher Weighted Sum Ratio (WSR) and minimum Channel State Information (CSI) error in comparison with the random phase shift RIS. The performance metrics sum rate, signal-to-interference plus noise ratio (SINR), energy efficiency, and transmit power are analyzed and compared.

Keywords-RIS; 6G Networks; massive MIMO; CSI; WSR

I. INTRODUCTION

The majority of operators are interested in the 6G wireless network due to its technological benefits such as the efficiency in the frequency spectrum, energy efficiency, low latency, and high coverage. The 6G wireless network depends on effective energy management and power efficiency. Security in communication is an important criterion to be considered along

with energy efficiency. In wireless communication, security can be provided in two ways [1]. The conventional technology uses software and hardware data encryption at the physical layer level. It performs well to safeguard the data without adding any extra overhead. A Reflected Intelligent Surface (RIS) can be used to provide the security at the physical layer. Due to the advancement of RIS, wireless communication systems gain a unique dimension.

II. RELATED WORK

In [2], the design challenges of an RIS-assisted Single-Output (MISO) system's beam were explored. The complex beam forming techniques for imperfect channels were analyzed in [3]. Authors in [4] investigated the impact of deploying networks using the RIS structure. Downlink deployment of the network using an RIS can maximize the signal power but in-turn increases the interference level. Authors in [5] investigated the optimal passive beam and active beam forming vector of a Base Station (BS) to enhance the weighted sum of downlink rates. The corresponding weight represents the mobile user priority to access the base station. In [6], the authors achieved low-cost delay for end-to-end multiple downlink path. In [7, 8], latency minimization in 6G networks is achieved with efficient Routing Strategy. In order to achieve promising performance in loaded settings, a number of detectors for large MIMO systems are presented in [8-12]. The main goal is to enhance the detector's performance by identifying any hidden sparsity in the received signal's residual error. The symbol error vector acquired from a linear detector is used in the first stage to transform the standard MIMO model into the sparse model. Recent research in the field of massive Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) antennas shows that user channels improve as the number of BS antennas increases, allowing high signal amplification with minimal inter-user interference [13]. An Ultra Wide Band (UWB) MIMO receiving wire working at millimeter-wave is proposed in [14-16]. It is made out of 8 transmitting components with different shapes. It is planned with a rectangular construction and different cut spaces. The proposed plan covers the total super wideband for short remote frameworks.

III. MASSIVE MIMO DOWNLINK MODEL AND PROBLEMS

The RIS structure shown in Figure 1 consists of an Intelligent Reflecting Surface (IRS), a controller, a BS, a legitimate receiver, and an eavesdropper. An RIS is a low-cost reflecting device. The gain and intensity of the signal is adjusted by tuning the phase angle of the reflected signal. If the phase difference between the signals is one bit period, then the signal arrives simultaneously to the receiver [8]. The system is having the capacity to cope with the multiple concurrent signals arriving simultaneously towards the receiver. Here the relative delay is maintained among the signals which are arriving towards the receiver in order to avoid interference [8].

Fig. 1. MISO downlink model with RIS structure.

The channel co-efficient matrices are shown in (1)-(3):

$$h_{BR} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N_t} \tag{1}$$

$$h_{BU} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times N_t} \tag{2}$$

$$h_{RU} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times M} \tag{3}$$

where h_{BR} is the channel coefficient matrix from the BS to the RIS, h_{BU} is the channel coefficient matrix from the BS to a legitimate user [9], and h_{RU} is the channel coefficient matrix from the RIS to the legitimate user, respectively [10-11]. A channel is estimated by analyzing the signal received from the receiver as shown in (4). The co-efficient matrix of the RIS is given in (5).

$$y_U = (h_{BU} + h_{RU}\Phi H_{BS})fx + n_U \tag{4}$$

$$\Phi = \text{diag}(\beta_1 e^{j\theta_1}, \beta_2 e^{j\theta_2}, \beta_3 e^{j\theta_3} \dots \beta_M e^{j\theta_M} \dots) \tag{5}$$

where $\beta_k \in [0,1]$ is the amplitude of the k^{th} unit of an RIS and $\theta_k \in [0, 2\pi]$ is the phase of the k^{th} unit of the RIS. The received signal from the eavesdropper is depicted by:

$$y_E = (h_{BE} + h_{RE}\Phi H_{BR})fx + n_E \tag{6}$$

The coefficients h_{RE} and h_{BE} are given by:

$$h_{RE} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times M} \tag{7}$$

$$h_{BE} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times N_t} \tag{8}$$

where h_{RE} and h_{BE} represent the coefficient matrices from an reconfigurable intelligent surface to the private listener called eavesdropper and from the BS to the private listener respectively and n_E represents the noise at the eavesdropper.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN

An IRS element is assumed to have components pointing upward and max elements on a level plane ($M = \text{Max}$). An IRS unit organizes the reflecting modes is controlled by the smart controller. The linear transmit precoding (TPC) matrix is utilized by the BS to communicate its information vector S_k to the k^{th} user. The following assumptions are made for the feasible set of RCs: $f = \text{diag}(bq_1 \dots bq_n), q_n \in [0, 2\pi]$ and $b \in [0,1]$ are the diagonal phase-shift lattice of an IRS, the combined incident signal's phase shift, and the amplitude reflection coefficient respectively. The structure of the cellular free network consists of the RIS, BS, CPU, and users connected to the network as depicted in Figure 2. The users and BSs are linked through an RIS. BSs, RIS, and CPU are interlinked virtually. The downlink channel of an RIS-CF system is depicted in Figure 3. As shown, many RIS units and many BSs are linked to communicate with the user. An RIS receives the signal from the BS and reflects the same signal to the user.

Fig. 2. Structure of a cellular-free network.

Fig. 3. Downlink channel of an RIS-CF system.

The distance between the users and the BS is reduced by incorporating RIS-CF, this way the gain is boosted by using massive MIMO cellular free networks. The above structure minimizes the resources.

A. Transmitter Design

All the BSs must be synchronized and independent and should send the information through the unified channel to provide better services to all subscribers. Assume that as given below in (9):

$$D_n \triangleq [D_{n,1} \dots \dots D_{n,m}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^K \quad (9)$$

where D , k , and P represent the data to be transmitted, the m^{th} number of users, and the n^{th} subcarrier, respectively. The data in the downlink channel can be expressed in the frequency domain as:

$$Z_{bs,n} = \sum_{n=1}^n V_{bs,n,m} D_{n,m} \quad (10)$$

In (10), the pre-coding chosen vector is $V_{bs,n,m}$, where bs stands for base station, n represents the channel, and m indicates the user.

B. Channel Design

The BS transmits the signal to an RIS unit and the user gets the reflected signals from an RIS. The channel is specified as:

$$ch_{bs,n,m}^{CH} \in \mathbb{C}^{U \times M} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) is rewritten in terms of BS user link and BS station RIS user link as shown in (12).

$$ch_{bs,n,m}^{CH} = CH_{bs,m,n}^H + \sum_{ris=1}^R E_{ris,m,n}^{CH} \odot_{ris}^{CH} G_{bs,ris,n} \quad (12)$$

where $CH_{bs,m,n}^H \in \mathbb{C}^{U \times M}$ is the channel in frequency domain representation from the bs^{th} BS to the m^{th} user, $E_{ris,m,n}^{CH} \in \mathbb{C}^{U \times N}$ is a channel established from an RIS to the m^{th} user, $G_{bs,ris,n} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ is a channel established from a BS to an RIS, and $\Theta_r^H = \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ is a phase shift $N \times N$ matrix, defined by:

$$\Theta_r \triangleq \text{diag}(\theta_{r,1} \dots \dots \theta_{r,N}), \forall_r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (13)$$

where $\theta_{r,N}$ belongs to \mathcal{F} , it is a RIS reflection coefficient given by:

$$\mathcal{F} \triangleq \{\theta_{r,n} | |\theta_{r,n}| \leq 1\}, \forall_r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall_n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (14)$$

C. Receiver Design

The Alternating Direction Method of Multiplier (ADMM) algorithm is used to improve active and passive beam formation in terms of SINR, energy efficiency, and transmit power parameters. An IRS-aided system at the Access Point (AP) beats the massive MIMO without an IRS. It is assumed that the signal from the mobile user propagates along the channel path.

- Conversion from time domain to the frequency domain baseband signal.
- Removal of the cyclic prefix attached to the signal.
- After removing the cyclic prefix, discrete Fourier transform is performed on the above signal.

The channel model is created using the matrix-based technique, in which the signal from different users is superimposed with the BS signal. The signal received by the user is indicated (15):

$$w_{m,n} = \sum_{bs=1}^{BS} w_{bs,m,n} + Z_{bs,n} = \sum_{bs=1}^{BS} \sum_{j=1}^M (CH_{bs,m,n}^H + \sum_{ris=1}^R E_{ris,m,n}^{CH} \odot_{ris}^{CH} G_{bs,ris,n}) V_{bs,n,j} D_{n,j} + Z_{bs,n} = \sum_{bs=1}^{BS} (CH_{bs,m,n}^H + \sum_{ris=1}^R E_{ris,m,n}^{CH} \odot_{ris}^{CH} G_{bs,ris,n}) V_{bs,n,m} D_{n,m} + \sum_{bs=1}^{BS} \sum_{j=1, j \neq m}^M (CH_{bs,m,n}^H + \sum_{ris=1}^R E_{ris,m,n}^{CH} \odot_{ris}^{CH} G_{bs,ris,n}) V_{bs,n,j} D_{n,j} + Z_{bs,n} \quad (15)$$

The user required signal without noise and the undesired signal are called interference. The signal from the other users is considered as noisy signal or undesired signal and is represented in (16):

$$\sum_{bs=1}^{BS} \sum_{j=1, j \neq m}^M (CH_{bs,m,n}^H + \sum_{ris=1}^R E_{ris,m,n}^{CH} \odot_{ris}^{CH} G_{bs,ris,n}) V_{bs,n,j} D_{n,j} + Z_{bs,n} \quad (16)$$

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. WSR Comparison with Distance for an Ideal RIS and an RIS with Continuous Phase Shift

Performance measures such as sum rate, SINR, energy efficiency, and transmit power were used to analyze and validate the proposed system. The weighted sum rate is compared with distance in meters for an ideal RIS and continues phase shift as depicted in Figure 4. The WSR fluctuates with distance. It can be seen in the graph that the WSR peaks at 13 bits/s/Hz at distances of 60 m and 100 m.

B. WSR Comparison with Distance for an RIS with Continuous Phase Shift and Random Phase Shift

The continuous phase shift achieves more WSR than random phase shift. Network capacity and deployment can be enhanced with continuous phase shift. The obtained WST peak is 13 at 60 m and 110 m distances as depicted in Figure 5. In random phase shift, the iterations carried out are more hence WSR peak is lesser as compared to the continuous phase shift.

Fig. 4. WSR comparison vs distance for an ideal RIS and an RIS with continuous phase shift.

Fig. 5. WSR comparison vs distance for ISRs with continuous and random phase shift.

C. WSR Comparison with Distance for an Ideal RIS and without an RIS

The results with and without a reflecting surface are depicted in Figure 6. The WSR notified is minimum, when the BS propagates the signal to the mobile user directly without super-imposing the signal with an RIS reflected signal. With an ideal RIS, the peak WSR achieved is maximum with a value of 13 bits/s/Hz at 60 m and 100 m.

Fig. 6. WSR comparison with distance for an ideal RIS and without an RIS.

D. WSR Comparison with Distance for Ideal RIS, without RIS, and with No-Direct Path

The WSR is compared with the distance in m with an ideal RIS, without RIS, and with no-direct path. Maximum WSR is achieved with an ideal RIS, as depicted in Figure 7.

E. WSR vs. Channel State Information Error

An RIS with continuous phase shift and ideal RIS encounter for 12 iterations are considered. The Channel State Information (CSI) error is comparatively less than 1% due to the increased number of iterations. An RIS with random phase and with no direct path, the number of iterations for WSR converges to around 7, but the CSI error is higher than the previous cases as depicted in Figure 8.

Fig. 7. WSR comparison with distance for an ideal RIS, without RIS, and with no direct path.

Fig. 8. WSR vs. CSI error.

F. WSR vs. CSI Error for 1-bit, 2-bit, 3-bit, and 4-bit continuous phase shift

The WSR with 1, 2, 3, and 4 bit phase shift converges after 1, 8.5, 6, and 4.2 iterations, respectively, as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. WSR vs CSI error for 1-, 2-, 3-, and 4-bit continuous phase shift.

The user sum rate is a measure used to compare the performance of massive MIMO and an IRS assisted moderate MIMO communication system. Figure 10 illustrates the sum-rate performance. Initially, it is noticed that the sum-rate performance of an IRS-assisted MIMO system is poorer than that of the massive MIMO system without an IRS. After employing optimal ADMM beam forming technique, the sum-rate obtained in an IRS-assisted MIMO system is significantly higher than that of massive MIMO system without an IRS.

Fig. 10. Sum rate comparison.

As shown in Figure 11, the overall transmit power is reduced significantly by using a large IRS. For example, with 40 reflecting elements, the transmitted power is 4.5 dBm and with 60, the transmitted power is dropped to 2 dBm. As we continually increase the number of reflecting elements to 160 the transmitted power drops to around -11 dBm.

Fig. 11. Transmitted power vs. no. of reflecting elements.

Fig. 12. SINR vs transmitted power.

SINR is the other metric used to compare massive MIMO with the IRS-assisted moderate MIMO communication system. We examine the network SINR achieved by the following three schemes: $N = 40$ with $M = 80$, $N = 40$, and $N = 70$, with the total amount of antenna elements at the BS and the total amount of reflecting elements at an IRS respectively being N and M . The number of users is $K = 20$. As shown in Figure 12, passive IRS elements help to reduce the number of active antennas ($N = 40$ with $M = 80$ vs $N = 40$ and $N = 80$ without an IRS).

Energy efficiency is another criterion used to compare the performance of IRS-aided moderate MIMO versus massive MIMO without an IRS. As depicted in Figure 13, an IRS aided communication is critical in order to create an energy efficient wireless system (where $K=20$, $N=70$ and $M=120$).

Fig. 13. Energy efficiency vs. spectral efficiency.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, the performance of the cellular free massive MIMO with a reflected intelligent surface is analyzed. Transmitter, receiver, and channel were designed and optimized. The weighted sum rate is plotted with respect to the distance in meters for different phase shift values with an RIS. The WSRs for continuous phase shift RIS, random phase shift RIS, no RIS, ideal RIS, and with direct path are compared. It is noticed with the results that the ideal and with continuous phase shift RISs achieve maximum WSR. Deployment and converge capacity increase with these two techniques. With random phase shift, the obtained peak WSR is 6.2 bits/s/Hz, whereas with continuous phase shift, it is 13 bits/s/Hz. It is concluded that with continuous phase shift, the coverage ratio and the network capacity can be enhanced in a cellular free massive MIMO network. Frame convergence with distance is analyzed, an RIS with continuous phase shift converges within 12 iterations, while random phase shift converges within 7 iterations. The system is also analyzed for the cases of no RIS, ideal RIS, and no-direct path. It was noticed that the number of iterations needed for no-RIS and direct path is 6.8. The channel state information error is minimum with continuous phase shift. The error rate with channel state information increases when the number of iterations decreases for random phase shift, no-

RIS, and with no-direct path. WSR converges in 12 iterations for 1-bit, 8.5 iterations for 2-bit, 6 iterations for 3-bit, and 4.2 iterations for 4-th bit phase shift. The CSI error percentage increases with bit size.

The results show that an RIS incorporated cellular free network enhances the coverage and hence more subscribers are able to access the existing infrastructure with reliability than the conventional transmission. RIS will undoubtedly be developed as a promising foundational technology for 6G wireless communication. An IRS-aided system does not have satisfactory results compared to massive MIMO system. We have two different beam-forming schemes, the first is active beam forming at the access point and the second is inactive reflecting beam forming at an IRS. So, we proposed an ADMM algorithm to jointly optimize the two beam forming schemes and concluded that an IRS-aided moderate MIMO system supports maximum users with higher SINR and energy efficiency and lower transmit power than its counterpart without an IRS. IRS-aided MIMO has proven to be very effective in improving the efficiency of a massive MIMO system.

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A Short Review on the Dynamic Slice Management in Software-Defined Network Virtualization

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ABSTRACT

Software-Defined Network (SDN) is a contemporary networking technology that offers enhanced network flexibility and streamlines network management processes. Virtual Software-Defined Networking (vSDN) enables the dynamic allocation and sharing of physical networking resources among several slices, each representing distinct service providers or services. Each tenant is granted autonomous control over their respective services or applications within the Virtual Network (VN). Network virtualization allows providers to deliver novel, advanced services while enhancing efficiency and dependability. Utilizing numerous virtual networks on a specific infrastructure presents difficulties in implementing effective resource allocation mechanisms to prevent congestion and resource scarcity while maintaining the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) in the vSDN. A limited body of research has focused on dynamic slice allocation in the vSDN domain. This article will briefly review dynamic resource management, focusing on slice resource dynamic allocation through SDN hypervisors. The survey outlined that very few studies have tackled the impact of dynamicity slice management in vSDN, and there are research gaps in implementing proactive and intelligent frameworks for slice management in vSDN.

Keywords-software-defined network; slice management; virtualization; hypervisors

I. INTRODUCTION

The networking field has witnessed a surge of interest in virtualization due to the significant achievements in this area within the computer sector [1-4]. Regarding Software-Defined

Networks (SDNs), the process of network virtualization has resulted in the creation of several virtual networks, also known as slices. Each virtual network has its abstractions of the underlying network topology [5]. The topic of networking already encompasses concepts such as "slicing." For example,

traditional networks' virtual local network (VLAN) and multiprotocol label switching (MPLS) are standard layer two technologies. Nevertheless, the current trend in network virtualization is to generate partitions for the underlying physical network, apart from the conventional layering methodology. Each slice can possess resource abstraction, including forwarding tables, Central Processing Unit (CPU) resources, and network bandwidth. Software-defined virtual network slicing offers similar advantages to conventional network slicing but with enhanced flexibility and agility. The ability to program with ease contributes to the flexibility and agility provided by SDN hypervisors. This allows fast service provisioning, dynamic resource allocation, and network automation [5].

Fig. 1. Virtual software-defined network.

Virtual networks are organized hierarchically within a substrate network, using dashed lines to represent virtual resources (Figure 1). Implementing virtual software-defined networks involves the utilization of virtualization and SDN technologies to facilitate the development of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) and virtual network services. This enables network administrators to dynamically create, delete, and manage different slices. The virtualization layer serves as a coordinator for the virtual networks of the service providers, namely SDN Controller 1 (C1) and SDN Controller 2 (C2). SDN C1 possesses control over a pair of network components, while SDN C2 exercises authority over a trio of network parts. Due to the importance of resource management in maintaining Quality of Service (QoS) and Service Level Agreement (SLA), this paper will examine the prominent hypervisors and frameworks that have handled resource management with more focus on dynamic slice management in vSDN.

II. REVIEW METHODOLOGY

This research employs the narrative literature review technique to examine the existing literature on slice management in vSDN to summarize and synthesize the available knowledge. The process of gathering and integrating existing literature is being undertaken to illustrate the research gap within the vSDN. The articles were chosen objectively to offer readers a thorough foundation for comprehending the current state of knowledge and to emphasize the importance of the research gap. The review commenced with a comprehensive literature search and subsequent screening process. After this, data extraction and analysis were

performed, and the findings were used to compose the literature review.

III. DYNAMIC SLICE MANAGEMENT IN VSDN

FlowVisor (FV) [6] is widely recognized as the pioneering hypervisor for Software-Defined Networking (SDN) networks. The introduction of FV has facilitated the ability to distribute SDN networking resources among multiple controllers. According to [6], FV eventually functioned as an independent program on standard hardware (server). Its purpose was to guarantee that users or service providers had separate flow areas during service usage. When a controller attempts to handle a flow in a switch not within its designated flow areas, it modifies packet headers to indicate this action. Alternatively, the FV function produces an Open flow "OF error" notice. Many (vSDN) hypervisors are considered extensions to the FV hypervisor. Authors in [7] implemented the FV technique within mobile packet core networks and called the proposed framework MobileVisor. This framework encompassed various physical mobile networks, including 3G and 4G. It facilitated communication between diverse vendors' data flow and the Radio Access Network (RAN) [8]. On the other side, authors in [9] introduced the concept of a Network Virtualization Platform (NVP) designed to facilitate the abstraction of data center network resources. This platform is specifically tailored for cloud operation in multi-tenant scenarios. The NVP functioned as a controller for SDN service providers, enabling them to manage their SDN controllers using the Application Protocol Interface (API). This allowed users to exert control over their slices within the data center. NVP logical data pathways, also known as tunnels, establish connections between the source and destination Open Virtual Switches (OVSS). These logical paths are specifically associated with the respective user's slice. However, the EnterpriseVisor is a prominent hypervisor regarding resource distribution, particularly in bandwidth slice allocation and management. A novel software module was implemented to monitor and study the utilization of slices effectively. In this context, a mathematical model was constructed and solved using linear programming techniques to optimize the allocation of bandwidth slices inside the network. Authors in [10] presented AutoVFlow as a distributed hypervisor. They addressed the scenario in which the underlying infrastructure extends over distinct and non-overlapping domains in the context of a wide-area network. The hypervisor manages each part and functions as an intermediary that carries out slice and abstraction mapping. AutoVflow facilitates the delegation of administrative tasks from high- to lower-capacity controllers. Effective update policies are consistently upheld across the centralized and distributed controllers due to the ability of a single slice to encompass several domains. Various identities were employed, including virtual MAC addresses, which may vary across multiple domains. The observed latency was significantly elevated, with an average value of around 5.85 ms. The current control technique needs more automation for the dynamic load distribution. In [11], the ONVisor hypervisor was introduced as an SDN and Network Virtualization (NV) platform. This platform was designed to enhance flexibility by implementing distributed instances of hypervisors, enabling sharing a Virtual Network (VN) state. The system supports

various SDN protocols, including Netconf and LISP. Nevertheless, the testing and evaluation of the system were limited to simple scenarios, and the discussion did not encompass dynamic resource allocation. They proposed a management framework to allocate bandwidth by establishing fixed thresholds for individual slices based on prioritization. The framework was introduced and demonstrated as a method for admission control. The proposed management system involves bandwidth distribution by establishing static thresholds for individual slices, which are determined based on slice prioritization. The framework was introduced as an admission control mechanism.

Authors in [12] proposed the DART framework which introduces a dynamic network bandwidth distribution method. The study was confined to the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) domain. The DART framework consists of two modules. The first is the communication module, which facilitates the transmission and reception of information. The second is the publishing module, which coordinates the controllers' activities. The centralized component provides recommendations regarding the optimal bandwidth allocation for every SDN controller. Authors in [13] introduced the Resource Manager (RM). The RM serves as a resource management system for virtualized SDN-based networks. It is designed to offer admission control functionality. The proposed methodology imposes limitations on the allocation of resources to virtual slices. The approach utilized dynamic thresholding to react to fluctuations in traffic volume effectively. The storage system effectively monitors and records the present level of bandwidth utilization. The compute module computes the available bandwidth resources before allocating the required amount. This computation is carried out by utilizing a flow rules manager and a threshold manager. These pairs allocate bandwidth depending on flow priority, with the ability to adjust the priority threshold based on predetermined flow priority. The methodology under consideration exhibits similarities to the strategy proposed in the abovementioned research. However, it focused on the present bandwidth use. The Libera hypervisor [14] was introduced to mitigate scalability challenges and enhance the capacity of service providers to offer their services. The scalability issue was primarily addressed by implementing Virtual Machine (VM) migrations and architectural adjustments that reduce slices and flow rules. This reduction in flow rules helps to minimize the bandwidth required between controllers and virtual switches. Libera is widely acknowledged as an extension of OpenVirtX. Nevertheless, the current implementation of resource scalability needs to consider future demands. Furthermore, a comprehensive analysis of the scalability of VM migration was not conducted. Authors in [15] introduced TeaVisor as a mechanism to ensure the provision of bandwidth isolation within vSDNs. The proposed hypervisor effectively mitigated the problem of overloaded links by employing a greedy heuristic method to distribute the traffic of these congested links among multiple channels with lower congestion levels. The findings indicated satisfactory performance. Nevertheless, the algorithm was developed using the most up-to-date traffic assessment techniques, potentially resulting in a depletion of resources, specifically bandwidth.

Authors in [16] proposed a resource management framework to enhance the load scalability of multi-domain SDN controllers. The utilization of a non-SDN hypervisor achieved this. The framework was developed to build a new VM for the controller or move the SDN controller based on load elevation. Software agents were employed to monitor the loads of the controller. In contrast to SDN-based hypervisors, using a stand-alone hypervisor may introduce challenges to the absence of resource segregation for SDN controllers. In addition, creating VMs and performing live migrations of VMs are associated with periods of service and slice unavailability. More recently, authors in [17] introduced the Meteor hypervisor as a proactive solution for predicting virtual SDN control traffic using LSTM. The study's results demonstrated a substantial improvement in control traffic latency, with a reduction of over 73%.

In our recent work [2], the DLVisor hypervisor was created using a dynamic learning framework integrating smooth-aided machine learning algorithms to predict future requests using techniques presented in [17-19]. The system exhibits reactivity and adaptability to substantial changes in traffic patterns by utilizing concept change detectors and significant tests. Previous research has indicated that oscillations in data traffic can have a negative impact on machine learning performance [20]. To address this issue, window-based approaches were utilized to reduce or eliminate these fluctuations. The enhanced dynamic learning framework is subsequently implemented within the resource management framework to improve resource utilization and mitigate the issue of overutilization arising from supply and demand estimates.

Table I presents an overview of the existing literature about resource and slice management in vSDN.

IV. DISCUSSION

Managing resources in vSDNs is typically carried out by network hypervisors or expanded frameworks connected to the network hypervisor. The most important parameters or terminologies in vSDN are hypervisors, flow spaces, open flow protocol, and virtual identifiers. According to the existing literature, most SDN hypervisors are built upon the FlowVisor hypervisor, widely recognized as the initial endeavor in SDN virtualization. The succeeding experiments aimed to address the flaws of FlowVisor, which encompassed the lack of admission control, dynamic resource management, interference in flow space, restriction of virtual topologies to subsets of the physical topology, and the absence of Quality of Service (QoS) features, as observed in the OpenVirtX. In contrast, specific hypervisors have endeavored to handle other facets, such as resource management in diverse controllers, as exemplified by the Compositional Hypervisor, and the facilitation of specialized network infrastructure, as demonstrated by the MobileVisor. On the other hand, hypervisors such as Virtualization Platform (NVP), AutoVflow, DFVisor, and CoVisor made attempts to tackle the operational and scalability challenges associated with vSDN resources in distributed or cluster systems.

TABLE I. SUMMARY TABLE

Hypervisor	Summary	Drawbacks	Dynamic resource/Slice management
FlowVisor [6]	1- General purpose first hypervisor 2-Stressed on network traffic isolation	1-Introduced OF message latency 2-Flow space interference 3-No admission control	No
MobileVisor [7]	1-Special network type 2-Introduced for mobile packet core	Same issues with FlowVisor	No
Network Virtualization Platform (NVP) [9]	1-General purpose 2-Focuses on the virtualization of the SDN switches 3-Applies to distributed controller scenarios only	1-Evaluation performed on tunnelling techniques only 2-OF message latency 3-Flow space interference	No. Uses clustering to scale up higher demands
OpenVirtex [22]	1-General purpose with minor latency added 2-Added resilience by VL mapping	OF message latency (minor)	No
Autoflow [10]	1-General purpose 2-Autoflow delegates configuration role to distributed administrators	Elevated OF message delays	No
Datapath Centric [23]	1-General purpose 2-Addressed the single point of failure in the FlowVisor 3-Support QoS	Added OF Latency 18%	No
AutoSlice [24]	1-General purpose 2-Improved the scalability of logically centralized hypervisor. 3-Differentiates between mice and elephant network flows	1-No performance evaluation on the simulation/ prototype has been published. 2-OF message latency	Yes. Enables SDN node and link migration. Reactive.
DFVisor [25]	1-General purpose 2-Added scalability 3-Introduced the concept of enhanced OpenFlow switches	Needs proper database synchronization between distributed controller databases	No
CoVisor [26]	1-General purpose 2-Policy-based 3-Designed to support heterogeneous controllers 4-More security	Added overheads. OF message latency.	No
Enterprise Visor [27]	1-General +special network type 2-Modify virtual topologies on demand 3-Admission control can be applied.	OF message latency.	Yes. Reactive.
ONVisor [11]	1-General purpose 2-Proposed scalable and flexible architecture	1-OF message latencies. 2-Lack of extensive evaluation.	No
Dynamic Resource Management Framework [28]	1-General purpose 2-Priority-based bandwidth resource allocation	1-Tested in a small scenario 1-No information was provided regarding latency overheads	Yes. Priority based. Reactive, not proactive.

DART Framework [12]	1-Designed for IIoT 2-Provided priority-based bandwidth resource allocation	1-Added an extra layer on top of the virtualization layer, which added more OF latency overhead 2-Limited scenarios	Yes. Priority based. Reactive, not proactive.
PrioSDN [13]	1-General purpose 2-Priority-based bandwidth resource allocation extension 3-Better results than DART	1-No OF latency provided 2-Some of the bandwidth resources are wasted 3-Requires higher computation	Yes. Priority based. Reactive, not proactive.
Libera [29]	1-General purpose 2-The scalability issue was addressed and enhanced (VM migration) 3-Integrated host VM migration and reconfiguration 4-Simplified and added more programmability feature enhancement	1-Added OF latency 2-VM Migration may contain downtime	Yes. Reactive.
TeaVisor [15]	1-General purpose 2-Mechanism for bandwidth guarantee 3-Algorithm to offload the overloaded links	1-More control overheads have been added	Yes. Reactive.
[16]	1-General purpose 2-Architecture for controller scalability	1-More control overheads have been added 2-VM creation and migration include downtime	Yes. Reactive.
Meteor [21]	1-General purpose 2-ML-based control plan prediction framework	1-Focused on control plan only	Yes (on the control plan).
DLVisor [2]	1-General purpose 2-Based on Enterprise visor and Libera 3-ML-based bandwidth slice allocation.	1-Exhibits same OF overheads with EnterpriseVisor	Yes. Proactive.

Nevertheless, few attempts have been made to address the challenge of dynamic slice and resource management. These include resource offloading/migration in Libera, AutoSlice, and FlowVirt. Furthermore, the concept of resource management through admission control has been introduced in the Dart and PrioSDN frameworks. These approaches offer a method of resource distribution based on static priorities. In addition, EnterpriseVisor provides a resource allocation framework that is highly promising. This framework seamlessly connects with the OpenVirtex hypervisor, enabling allocating resources, specifically bandwidth slices, through a mathematical model. The allocation process is resolved using linear programming techniques. In [15, 16], efforts were made to solve link and load scalability difficulties. However, it is worth noting that the proposed solutions in these studies were reactive and needed to examine resource allocation and future demand considerations adequately. The existing literature on the subject reveals that the available methodologies and frameworks have limitations in their adaptability to traffic and network changes. These approaches are either static, unable to adjust to such changes,

or reactive, as they operate only based on current conditions without considering resource forecasting. Consequently, this might result in resource scarcity or depletion. Only [2] and [21] provided proactive bandwidth slice management using resource forecast and machine learning.

V. CONCLUSION

The current paper briefly presented an overview of the strategies and techniques employed in managing slice (bandwidth) resources within a virtual Software-Defined Networking (vSDN) environment. Based on the extant literature and relevant studies, a research gap has been identified concerning enhancing resource management in vSDN technologies. Based on our analysis and some of the discussed related studies, managing resources and allocating bandwidth resources, particularly in real-time scenarios, can result in resource scarcity due to excessive resource utilization. This is especially true considering that most existing resource management solutions should be regarded as future demands and sudden fluctuations in traffic patterns when calculating resource supply and demand. Hence, there is a requirement to implement proactive and intelligent frameworks for resource management. Therefore, it is imperative to have precise and resilient algorithms for estimating resources, particularly traffic. Consequently, a dynamic learning framework that integrates machine learning algorithms to acquire knowledge and predict forthcoming requests was devised. The system exhibits reactivity and adaptability to substantial alterations in traffic patterns by utilizing concept change detectors and considerable tests. Previous research has indicated that ML-based approaches can effectively mitigate the adverse effects of data traffic fluctuations and improve performance, such as in [2, 17].

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Power Amplifier Optimization for M2M Node using DPD and Hybrid DFT-s-OFDM with CFR

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ABSTRACT

Power Amplifiers (PAs) play a vital role in mobile communication. However, their inherent nonlinearity can lead to issues such as unwanted radiation, interference with neighboring channels, and distortion within the desired frequency range. To address these problems, PAs are typically operated at a lower power level than their saturation point, sacrificing power efficiency to improve Error Vector Magnitude (EVM) performance. Consequently, more than 70-80% of the DC power is wasted as heat. This inefficiency necessitates the exploration of techniques to enhance PA efficiency while maintaining acceptable linearity and performance. Digital Pre-Distortion (DPD) is a useful technique to linearize PAs. DPD allows affordable nonlinear PAs to function with minimal distortion in their nonlinear operating regions. This results in amplified signals with increased power output and improved power efficiency. Using nonlinear functions, the output signal of the PA can be linearized, mitigate distortions, and be effectively optimized. When using various operating channels and varying time, temperature, and PA nonlinearity, the DPD must adjust. In order to increase the power efficiency of 5G systems, DPD-enabled systems are inculcating with adaptive DFT-s-OFDM employed 5G physical layer along with the Crest Factor Reduction (CFR) algorithm.

Keywords-CFR; DPD; PA; PAPR; DFT-s-OFDM; mMTC; 5G (NR)

I. INTRODUCTION

Efficient power utilization is a crucial consideration in any communication system, particularly in machine-to-machine communication scenarios. Among various techniques, Digital Pre-Distortion (DPD) offers easier implementation compared to alternatives like feedforward linearization, which operate in the RF domain and affect the digital baseband domain. By employing DPD, power efficiency can be enhanced by enabling low-cost nonlinear Power Amplifiers (PAs) to operate with reduced distortion at higher output levels, even within their nonlinear regions [1]. Figure 1 illustrates the similarity between DPD and a nonlinear circuit. DPD counteracts the power amplifier's phase rotation (AM/PM) by introducing a phase rotation in the opposite direction.

Likewise, DPD also addresses the issue of gain suppression (AM/AM) in PA by incorporating a gain expansion response. Adapting to changes in PA nonlinearity is a crucial requirement for DPD. As the signal bandwidth increases, these memory effects become more pronounced and need to be addressed alongside PA nonlinearity. While most adaptive DPD blocks effectively handle progressive modifications in PA characteristics, they often overlook fast fluctuations. DPD techniques could be implemented through Volterra series memory polynomials and generalized memory polynomials are more suitable in these scenarios [2]. To apply nonlinear correction to complex baseband signals, various digital signal processing techniques can be utilized. These techniques enable the application of DPD and help mitigate the impact of memory effects [3]. For efficient processing of the extended

bandwidth's high sample rate, it is beneficial to employ a parallel processing architecture that can simultaneously handle multiple samples. This parallel processing approach is ideal for executing nonlinear correction in the DPD system. Figure 2 shows the DPD integration in the transmission chain of a typical communication system, situated between the DAC and ADC functions and the crest-factor reduction (CFR) block [4]. The DPD subsystem comprises various components, including a look-up table (LUT) for the DPD model and an adaptation block [5].

Fig. 1. DPD integration.

Enhancing PA efficiency is a critical aspect of communication systems, as it directly contributes to extending

Fig. 2. Simulation scenario.

In our definition, the capacity to convert DC energy into RF signal is referred to as PA efficiency. Using the following criteria, the PA's efficacy is evaluated as:

- **Drain Efficiency:** It is the ratio of the RF output power to the DC power consumed by the PA. This parameter measures how efficiently the PA converts the supplied DC power into RF power. Higher drain efficiency indicates better utilization of the power supply.
- **Power Added Efficiency (PAE):** PAE represents the proportion of the DC power utilized by the PA. It quantifies the efficiency of power addition by PA.

Drain efficiency and PAE are crucial attributed for assessing the efficiency PA and provide insights into the PA's power conversion capabilities. PAE accounting for input RF signal is described as:

$$PAE = \frac{P_{out} - P_{in}}{P_{DC}} \% \quad (1)$$

In an ideal situation of a perfect PA there would be no power consumption in the PA. However, in veracity, no PA can function in a linear fashion completely, so achieving zero

battery life and reducing overall system expenses [6]. PA typically account for a significant portion of the total power consumption, often reaching up to 80% of the overall power budget [7]. The operating class of the power transistor and the selected input or output back-off play a crucial role in determining the efficiency of a PA [8]. Different PA classes exhibit varying trade-offs between linearity and efficiency. For instance, a Class A amplifier offers excellent linearity and is characterized by low efficiency, since it operates with a high biasing current even when there is no input signal. On the other hand, a Class AB amplifier design is a compromise between linearity and efficiency to achieve better efficiency by allowing the power transistor to operate in a more efficient region when there is no input signal [9]. However, in modern base stations, Doherty amplifiers are commonly used. Doherty PAs combine elements from both Class AB and Class C [10]. This design offers superior linearity and improved efficiency compared to other PA classes. By utilizing a combination of a main amplifier operating in Class AB mode and an auxiliary amplifier operating in Class C mode, Doherty PAs achieve higher efficiency without compromising linearity.

power consumption is not feasible. When considering the ideal conditions for a linear response, a typical PA exhibits a characteristic graph depicting the relationship between input power and output power. This graph, shown in Figure 3 illustrates how the PA's response gets increasingly nonlinear as the power input rises. This implies that the PA requires less input power compared to when it operates in the nonlinear region. By operating within the linear range, the PA can achieve the necessary linearity and minimize the negative effects on the transmitted signal. This point is commonly used to determine the extent of back-off required for maintaining linearity. In Figure 3, the operational range of the PA is shown in blue without DPD and the input power is reduced to preserve linearity. Green indicates the DPD-enabled functioning area in Figure 3, enhances the PAE of the device, thus improving its efficiency.

Efforts to enhance the efficiency of reducing PAPR in wireless communication systems have led to the development of various schemes on the channel modeling side, including FBMC, DFT-s-OFDM, iterative clipping, and numerous others. However, an important aspect that has often been overlooked is compensating for the non-linearity of the power amplifier in

conjunction with these channel modeling techniques. In our approach, for the very first time, we address device-level optimization by simulating DPD before the PA in conjunction with DFT-s-OFDM. This novel combination aims to achieve a significant level of PAPR reduction, by integrating DPD into the system before the PA, the non-linearity can be compensated by its source, effectively mitigating distortions that could otherwise compromise signal quality. This holistic approach not only focuses on improving the signal characteristics through channel modeling but also ensures that the transmitted signals are better suited to the capabilities of the power amplifier.

Fig. 3. DPD on the operational zone of a PA.

II. EASE POWER AMPLIFIER MODEL AND CHARACTERISTIC

The non-linearity of High Power Amplifiers (HPAs) can cause two types of distortion: out-of-band distortion and in-band distortion. These distortions can have detrimental effects on the performance of wireless communication systems, specifically in terms of Adjacent Channel Interference (ACI) and Bit Error Rate (BER). An alternative solution is HPA linearization, which involves employing various algorithms to counteract the non-linear effects. The Look-Up Table (LUT) technique is utilized for digital adaptive pre-distortion, enabling the correction of non-linear effects in the HPA.

A. Traveling-Wave Tube Amplifier Model

The frequently utilized Traveling Wave Tube Amplifier (TWTA) is employed in this study [11]. This model is commonly employed in literature for analyzing the performance of HPAs. The input signal's complex envelope is denoted by:

$$y(\tau) = \chi(\tau) \cdot \exp[i\gamma \rho(\tau)] \tag{2}$$

The HPA's output signal might be represented as follows:

$$x(\tau) = \alpha[\chi(\tau)] \cdot \exp[i(\gamma \rho(\tau) + \kappa[\chi(\tau)])] \tag{3}$$

In the context of the non-linear amplifier, $\alpha(\chi)$ refers to AM-AM and $\kappa(\chi)$ states AM-PM distortion. The distortion property of TWTA can be represented as:

$$\alpha[\chi(\tau)] = \alpha^2 \frac{\chi(\tau)}{\chi^2(\tau) + \alpha^2} \tag{4}$$

$$\kappa[\chi(\tau)] = \frac{\pi}{3} \frac{\chi^2(\tau)}{\chi^2(\tau) + \alpha^2} \tag{5}$$

where α represents the input voltage for the PA.

B. An Ineffective Predisorter

There are two scenarios in which an HPA predisorter may lose its effectiveness. In such situations, the predisorter is unable to adequately correct the nonlinearities caused by the high signal amplitudes. As described by (4), the behavior of the TWTA exhibits specific nonlinearity patterns outlined in Saleh's model.

$$\alpha[\chi] = \frac{\alpha^2_{sat}}{\chi + \frac{\alpha^2_{sat}}{\chi}} \leq \frac{\alpha^2_{sat}}{2 \cdot \alpha_{sat}} = \frac{\alpha_{sat}}{2} \tag{6}$$

The maximum outcome of the HPA is α_{sat} , as may be seen from (6). Any signals greater than α_{sat} would be clipped. Based on this observation, the following conclusions can be made:

- **Limitation of Predisortion:** The predisorter's ability to compensate for distortion is constrained when the input signals have amplitudes exceeding $\alpha_{sat}/2$. The predisortion technique becomes less effective in correcting nonlinearities caused by these high-amplitude signals.
- **Clipping Distortion:** Signals with amplitudes exceeding $\alpha_{sat}/2$ will experience clipping distortion in the HPA output. This distortion arises due to the HPA's saturation limit, where the signal is cut off or flattened at $\alpha_{sat}/2$.
- **Signal Integrity:** In OFDM modulated data streams, it is crucial to ensure that the signal amplitudes remain below $\alpha_{sat}/2$ to maintain signal integrity and avoid significant distortion.

Fig. 4. Transfer curve of AM-AM and AM-PM.

These conclusions highlight the importance of considering the saturation limit of the HPA and its impact on signal amplitudes in the design and optimization of communication systems using predisortion techniques. When the HPA operates in linear region, which is away from the saturation region, where α_{sat} (saturation point) is much larger than α_{sat} (maximum signal amplitude) in the modulated data streams, it becomes possible to effectively predisort all amplitude distortions using a predisorter. Consequently, this leads to significant degradation in Power Spectral Density (PSD) and BER performance.

III. PAPR REDUCTION TECHNIQUE

According to the literature, there are three main categories of methods for Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR) reduction:

1. Signal distortion techniques: These methods involve introducing signal distortions, such as clipping and filtering, to reduce the PAPR [12].
2. Signal scrambling techniques: These methods, such as Selective Mapping (SLM) [13] and Partial Transmit Sequences (PTS) [14], involve modifying the signal through specific scrambling algorithms to reduce the PAPR.
3. Coding techniques: These methods utilize coding schemes, as described in [15], to reduce the PAPR. However, the improved PAPR performance comes at the expense of reduced bandwidth efficiency.

Fig. 5. PSD comparison of various PAPR reduction techniques.

Each PAPR reduction technique has its own advantages and disadvantages. Scrambling techniques like SLM and PTS involve complex optimization procedures, resulting in higher system complexity and computational burden [16]. Coding techniques offer PAPR reduction benefits but may impact bandwidth efficiency. When considering the effects of PAPR reduction on HPA linearization, it is important to focus on the impact on out-of-band and in-band noises.

Fig. 6. Performance of BER at 256-QAM modulation.

Figure 5 illustrates the PSDs after applying PAPR reduction from 10.34 dB to 4.2 dB. It is apparent that the filtering method effectively mitigates out-of-band noises [17] successfully suppresses out-of-band distortion. However, in-band noises can be introduced during the clipping process. Figure 6 displays the BER performance versus Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) with hard clipping. The observation shows that bit error rate significantly deteriorates with reduced PAPR. These results demonstrate the trade-off between PAPR reduction and BER performance when the Clipping Ratio (CR) is 4 dB (specified in (6)), using 256-QAM modulation and $N=1024$. While PAPR reduction techniques can mitigate out-of-band noises, they may introduce in-band noises and degrade the BER performance. However, the application of methods like Decision-Aided Reconstruction can help mitigate the impact on BER, reducing the additional SNR required to achieve a desired BER level.

$$CR = 20 \log \frac{\alpha}{\delta} \text{ dB} \quad (7)$$

where δ represents the rms value input signal power. The study also presents the Bayesian inference technique [19] as a way for reconstructing clipped signals with better BER performance. To reduce out-of-band distortion, this approach is used in conjunction with others like peak counteraction. The Bayesian inference method offers improved BER performance by employing probabilistic inference techniques to reconstruct the distorted signals. By leveraging statistical information and prior knowledge, the aim of this method is to mitigate the negative effects of signal clipping and enhance the overall performance of the communication system.

IV. IMPACT OF PAPR REDUCTION ON LINEARIZATION

In this section, we will evaluate the effects of PAPR lessening on HPA linearization by analyzing the PSD and BER. Figure 7 illustrates a simplified diagram that depicts the process of PAPR lessening and linearization.

A. PSD Analysis

Out-Of-Band (OOB) radiation can have a significant impact on communication systems, particularly in multi-user and RF wireless applications. The PSD performance provides a means to evaluate the ACI effects [20]. Figure 7 illustrates the improvements in PSD performance with and without the implementation of PAPR reduction techniques. The PSD performance analysis provides insights into the ACI effects caused by out-of-band radiation. It highlights the importance of managing and reducing ACI through techniques such as PAPR reduction [21]. While operating the HPA in the linear region allows for complete compensation without PAPR reduction, it comes at the cost of lower power efficiency.

B. Bit Error Rate Analysis

PAPR lessening techniques can be present in-band clipping noises, which have a detrimental effect on the system's BER. This is due to the fact that distortion may be efficiently reduced by utilizing a predistorter to account for the input signal to the HPA. In contrast, an OBO of 4.6421 dB is produced when the HPA runs close to the saturation area with better power

efficiency, such as when the saturation point (α_{max}) is equal to the maximum signal amplitude (α_{max}).

- The predistorter's input signal is "clipped-off" in the clipping operation to a maximum value of $1.5 \alpha_{max}/2$. As a result of the HPA's $1.5 \alpha_{max}/2$ output power limitation, any information with amplitudes that fall in this range will be clipped or removed. As a consequence, any information whose amplitudes exceed $\alpha_{max}/2$ will be clipped or removed or modified to $\alpha_{max}/2$'s maximum value.
- Data that travel between the predistorter to HPA is $\alpha_{max}/2$ if the clipping procedure is not used. However, they cannot be completely erased or reversed by further processing.

C. OBO (Output Backoff) Performance

Output Backoff is a parameter commonly used to assess the performance characteristic of an HPA. It can be characterized as:

$$OBO = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{W_{max}}{W_{avg}} \right) \quad (8)$$

Fig. 7. PAPR performance for the OBO model.

To achieve superior outcomes using predistorter (without a clipping), the α_{max} should satisfy the condition $\alpha_{sat} \geq 2\alpha_{max}$. This is illustrated by the highlighted circle in Figure 7. With this configuration, a good predistortion can be achieved. In case clipping procedure is employed, significant improvement in HPA power efficiency can be achieved, albeit with some permitted degradation in BER. The clipping process allows for higher power efficiency by operating the HPA near its saturation region, leading to improved power performance [22]. However, this comes with the trade-off of potential BER degradation due to the clipping process. By incorporating the clipping process, significant enhancements in HPA power efficiency can be attained. This trade-off allows for improved power performance, as illustrated by the solid line in Figure-7, while accepting a certain level of BER degradation with superior predistortion outcome.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Evaluation of PAPR lessening with High Power Amplifier linearization, combined with the use of (DPD), provides valuable insights. DPD can able to enhance the overall efficiency by making linear PA. In the absence of DPD, the PA would need to work with significant back-off to comply with

the spectral emission mask. PAPR reduction mitigates out-of-band radiation but introduces in-band clipping noises and degrades BER. Operating the HPA in the linear region with a predistorter yields good BER performance but low power efficiency. Employing a clipping process with DPD improves power efficiency, but careful consideration must be given to the trade-off between power efficiency, BER degradation, and the effectiveness of DPD in achieving desired linearity.

In the future, DPD-based hardware followed by the CFR algorithm will be designed as a prototype to compensate for the non-linearity of power amplifiers and also inculcate the smart algorithm for MIMO antennas for power optimization to enhance the overall system power efficiency.

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Auto tuning of PI Gains using Cuttlefish Optimization for DC Link Voltage Control in a 5-level HB MMC D-STATCOM

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ABSTRACT

The performance of a Half Bridge (HB) Modular Multilevel Converter (MMC) for D-STATCOM application is studied in this article. For the control of MMC switches, the Carrier-Based (CB) Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) scheme has been selected as the appropriate method. There are two types of CB PWM schemes such as phase shift and level shift. Phase Disposition (PD), Phase Opposition Disposition (POD), and Alternate Phase Opposite Disposition (APOD) are the three different types of PWM that are used in level shifts. The PD CB PWM is projected in this work due to its simplicity and accuracy. The conventional PI Controller (PIC) has its disadvantages, including that it is time-consuming and comes with complexity in the estimation of gain values. Hence, the Cuttlefish Optimization Scheme (COS) is proposed for the online tuning of the PI gain values. The verification of performance parameters, including active power, reactive power, DC voltage balance, and Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), is effectively conducted using the COS method and subsequently compared with the conventional PIC. The suggested research is executed using the Matlab/Simulink software package.

Keywords-carrier-based PWM; D-STATCOM; half bridge; THD; phase disposition; PI; COS; MMC

I. INTRODUCTION

An electric power system refers to a complex network comprising diverse electrical components that are strategically installed to facilitate the generation, transmission, distribution, and utilization of electrical power [1]. The term "distribution system" denotes the conduit that is developed in the process of delivering electricity to the final users of the product. Enhanced power quality is the engine that propels the modern industrial sector of today's economy. Over the last decade, there has been a discernible increase in the amount of awareness that consumers have regarding the significance of a dependable power supply [2]. A Voltage Source Converter (VSC) is what makes up DSTATCOM. It produces the required capacitive and inductive reactive power. The control mechanism exhibits a high degree of responsiveness, enabling it to promptly address system requirements. Additionally, it possesses the capability to provide an ample amount of reactive power compensation to the interconnected system [3]. Before

the development of DSTATCOM, it was common practice to use systems based on thyristors for reactive power compensation and mitigating voltage flicker caused by arc furnace loads. This was done before the invention of DSTATCOM. On the other hand, passive devices have a number of drawbacks, including a fixed compensation, large size, the possibility of resonance, and so on. As a result, new compensators, such as DSTATCOM, are becoming increasingly popular as a solution to power quality issues. Due to the inherent non-linearity of power electronic devices, these devices have a tendency to draw reactive power and harmonics from the power supply [4]. In certain instances, they may also induce imbalance within three-phase systems and result in the generation of unnecessary neutral currents. Due to the added harmonics, the reactive power problem, the imbalance, and the unwarranted neutral currents, the structure's efficiency is reduced, and its power factor is low. Both these problems are caused by excessive neutral currents. The emergence of power

quality as a significant concern can be attributed to the increasing intolerance of various loads [5]. The primary focus of power quality pertains to matters related to the consistent maintenance of a stable voltage at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) across different circulation voltage stages, regardless of voltage instabilities. Additionally, power quality involves the maintenance of a power factor that is in close proximity to unity, prevention of upward transmission of current unbalances from different circulation levels, and mitigation of voltage and current harmonics within the structure. All these issues are covered under the umbrella term "harmonics reduction." The fact that multilevel inverters do not necessitate the use of a coupling transformer [6] in settings that involve medium voltage and the fact that they have a comparatively little harmonic current contented are two of the furthestmost significant advantages that these devices provide. In the traditional method, the D-STATCOM application is handled by utilizing two level converters. Conventional two-level inverters are producing more THD in grid current. Hence the Modular Multilevel Converter (MMC)-based D-STATCOM is proposed in this work. Conventionally, PIC and Fuzzy Logic Controllers have been implemented for the DC voltage balance in Multi-Level Inverters (MLI). The traditional method of learning the gain values of a PIC, which relies on trial and error, is both time consuming and complex [7]. Hence, COS is adopted in this work for the automatic selection of the PI gain values.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed configuration is depicted in Figure 1. It consists of an electric source or grid, non-linear loads, and voltage source-based DSTATCOM. Half Bridge (HB) based MMC is adopted as the voltage source converter as shown in Figures 2 and 3. The HB modules required are calculated as $N + 1$ for the N -level. For 5-level output, $4+1=5$ means that four sub modules are required.

Fig. 1. The proposed configuration.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the MMC.

Fig. 3. HB sub module of the MMC.

TABLE I. HB SM SWITCHING

Mode	S _{A1}	S _{A2}	Output Voltage
1	ON	OFF	V ₀
2	OFF	ON	0

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of the MMC control block.

The switching table is depicted in Table I. The control block diagram of the MMC is illustrated in Figure 4 [8]. It consists of a reference current generator and DC link voltage termed as MMC capacitor controller. The mathematical equations for reference current calculation block are presented below. The axes a , b , and c are all located on the same plane, but they are spaced apart from one another by a distance equal to two-thirds of the a - b - c coordinates. The axes denoted by α and β are examples of orthogonal coordinates.

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{s\alpha} \\ V_{s\beta} \end{bmatrix} = \sqrt{0.667} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.5 & -0.5 \\ 0 & 0.866 & -0.866 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{s\alpha} \\ V_{s\beta} \end{bmatrix} = \sqrt{0.667} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.5 & -0.5 \\ 0 & 0.866 & -0.866 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The computation of active power (p) and reactive power (q) can be attained by utilizing the equation derived from the α - β coordinate system. [9]:

$$p = V_{s\alpha} i_{L\alpha} + V_{s\beta} i_{L\beta} \quad (3)$$

$$q = -V_{s\beta} i_{L\alpha} + V_{s\alpha} i_{L\beta} \quad (4)$$

Moreover, the variables p and q can be represented as matrices in the following manner:

$$\begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} V_{s\alpha} & V_{s\beta} \\ -V_{s\beta} & V_{s\alpha} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_{L\alpha} \\ i_{L\beta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

There are two parts that make up the instantaneous active power, which is denoted by the symbol p : the oscillatory (AC) component \tilde{p} and the average (DC) component \bar{p} . The oscillatory component \tilde{q} and the average (DC) component \bar{q} are the two parts that make up the reactive power q , which also has two parts [9]. The variables p and q are expressed by:

$$p = \bar{p} + \tilde{p} \tag{6}$$

$$q = \bar{q} + \tilde{q} \tag{7}$$

Given that the source exclusively provides the DC component of the active power, it is only necessary to consider the average component \bar{p} in the calculation of the required reference current value, while maintaining the reactive power q at a value of zero. The required reference currents on the source side i_{ref} based on the α - β coordinates are i_{α}^* and i_{β}^* :

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{L\alpha}^* \\ i_{L\beta}^* \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{V_{s\alpha}^2 + V_{s\beta}^2} \begin{bmatrix} V_{s\alpha} & -V_{s\beta} \\ V_{s\beta} & V_{s\alpha} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{p} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{8}$$

In fact, on the load side, the reference current i_{ref} is determined using inverse Clark's transformation. It is defined as [9]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{refR} \\ i_{refY} \\ i_{refB} \end{bmatrix} = \sqrt{0.667} \begin{bmatrix} 0.707 & 1 & 0 \\ 0.707 & -0.707 & 0.866 \\ 0.707 & -0.707 & -0.866 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_0^* \\ i_{L\alpha}^* \\ i_{L\beta}^* \end{bmatrix} \tag{9}$$

The zero-sequence part of this equation is denoted by the symbol i_0^* . In this work, the value of i_0^* is 0. The generated reference signal is presented in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Generated reference signal.

Fig. 6. PIC using COA.

Figure 6 depicts the MMC capacitor voltage controller using a COS tuned PIC. Cuttlefish Optimization Algorithm (COA), is a bio-inspired metaheuristic set of rules [10] that was designed to replicate the color-changing behavior of cuttlefish. COA or Cuttlefish Optimization Scheme (COS), is a nature-inspired algorithm for optimization that imitates the hunting behavior of cuttlefish [11-12]. It can be used to design PI

controllers for various control systems. The steps of using the COA to design a PIC are:

Step 1: Define the control system.

Step 2: Define an objective function that can be used to quantify how well the control system is performing [13]. In most cases, this entails achieving the lowest possible value for a cost function, such as the Integral of the Squared Error (ISE) or the Integral of the Absolute Error (IAE), or some other appropriate performance criterion.

Step 3: Represent the PIC in a way that can be optimized using the COA. Proportional gain (K_p), integral time (T_i), or integral gain (K_i) are typically used to parameterize PICs. These parameters will be optimized by the algorithm.

Step 4: Initialize a population of cuttlefish individuals. Each individual corresponds to a potential solution in the search space of the controller parameters (K_p and T_i/K_i). It can randomly initialize the cuttlefish positions within a predefined range.

Step 5: Estimate the suitability of each cuttlefish in the population by applying its corresponding PIC to the control system and computing the objective function value.

Step 6: Main loops

Step 7: Once the algorithm terminates, select the best-performing cuttlefish (controller parameters) as the optimized PIC for your system.

Step 8: Implement the optimized PIC in the control system and evaluate its performance through simulation or experimentation. Make any necessary adjustments based on real-world results.

III. SIMULATION RESULT ANALYSIS

The proposed configuration was simulated and the results are elaborated in this section. The simulation result analysis is made in two cases. In first case, the MMC [14-15], the capacitor voltage is controlled by the conventional PIC [16-19] using the trial and error method. The corresponding result waveforms are presented in Figure 7. The MMC capacitor voltage controller [20] takes more time to reach the steady state due to the inaccuracy in selection of K_p and K_i gains of the PIC. The THD is recorded as 4.91%. The settling time of the DC voltage link is 1.2 s as shown in Figure 7(g). Active and reactive power [21-25] values are 6.233 W and 1.160 Var. The MMC capacitor voltage controller achieved the reference voltage of 700 V at $t = 1.2$ s. The simulation specifications are listed in Table II.

TABLE II. VALUES CONSIDERED FOR SIMULATION

Description	Value
3-phase supply/grid voltage, L_s and R_s	415 V (rms), 200 mH and 0.01 Ω
Rectifier load	3 phase diode bridge with RL load
Switching frequency	5000 Hz
V_{dcref}	700 V
Capacitor, C	3300 μ F

Fig. 7. Response waveforms using five-level HBMMC-DSTATCOM using the conventional PIC: (a) Source voltage, (b) source current, (c) apparent power, (d) active power, (e) reactive power, (f) power factor, (g) DC voltage, (h) harmonic spectrum of the source current.

Fig. 8. Response waveforms using five-level HBMMC-DSTATCOM with COA: (a) Source voltage, (b) source current, (c) apparent power, (d) active power, (e) reactive power, (f) power factor, (g) DC voltage, (h) harmonic spectrum of the source current.

In the second case, the MMC capacitor voltage is controlled by the PIC with COA. The corresponding result waveforms are presented in Figure 8. The MMC capacitor voltage controller requires less time to reach the steady state due to the accuracy in the selection of K_p and K_i gains of the PIC. The recorded THD is 4.72%. The settling time of the DC voltage link is 0.04 s as shown in Figure 8(g). The observed active and reactive powers are as 6.317 W and 986 Var. The MMC capacitor voltage controller achieved the reference voltage of 700 V at $t = 0.04$ s. The performance comparison of the produced parameters using the conventional PIC and the COS-tuned PIC can be seen in Table III.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Parameter	PIC	PIC trained by COA
S (VA)	6,340	6,394
P (W)	6,233	6,317
Q (VAR)	1,160	986
PF	0.9831	0.988
DC voltage settling time (s)	1.2	0.04
i_{sa} (A)	8.903	8.95
Source current %THD	4.91	4.72

IV. DISCUSSION

MMCs have become increasingly popular during the recent years in many power quality applications, including DSTATCOM, active power filters, solar panels, and wind energy conversion systems. There is a gap regarding ways to best implement MMC for D-STATCOM using optimization techniques. As a result, the MMC-based D-STATCOM that uses COS is taken into consideration in this work. The implementation of the MMC as D-STATCOM is one of the contributions made by this body of work towards the enhancement of power quality metrics. The performance level of the proposed controller is analyzed and contrasted with that of the traditional PIC. The results show that the proposed five-level MMC-based D-STATCOM that makes use of COA has superior performance when compared with the traditional PIC.

V. CONCLUSION

The principles of the Distribution Static Compensator (D-STATCOM) based on the Modular Multilevel Converter (MMC) were presented in this paper and the efficacy of the control structure was thoroughly examined. This study introduces a method for achieving capacitor voltage balancing in a Modular Multilevel Converter (MMC) with the aim of reducing Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) and reactive power in a five-level D-STATCOM based on the MMC technology. The objective of this implementation is to enhance the effectiveness of the algorithm. The effectiveness of the proposed COA-tuned PI controller was proven to be superior to the conventional trial and error method. The settling time of the MMC capacitor voltage has been successfully reduced to 0.04 s using the COA, in comparison to the trial and error method which resulted in a settling time of 1.2 s.

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A New Interrogation System for FBG Sensors based on Midband Filter with Correction

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a midband interrogation system for Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors is presented and its numerical demonstration is reported. The midband interrogation system is based on a finite reflection filter with automatic correction. The filter is used to interrogate the FBG sensors. The strain FBG sensors were used to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed systems. The results demonstrate that the proposed system of interrogation has a great resolution (± 1 pm) with good stability.

Keywords-interrogation system; midband; correction; filter; fiber Bragg grating; sensors; strain

I. INTRODUCTION

The FBG technology is proved to be effective in temperature and strain sensors [1] for several fields, such as civil engineering [2-4], health [5], aeronautics, and artificial intelligence in robotics [6]. The FBG technology has many advantages like fast response, high sensitivity and electromagnetic interference opposition [7]. Technically, the center wavelength of the inscribed grating in the fiber changes due to the mechanical effect exerted by external forces such as pressure and temperature [8]. Hence, a good calibration and measurement of the wavelength shift can get the external force [9]. On the other side, to reconstruct the sensing signal, an interrogation system is needed. Actually, there are many interrogation system techniques like the edge filter [10], the low loss jammed-array wideband sawtooth filter [11], tunable lasers [12], and magneto-optic wavemeter [13]. However, many of these techniques are expensive and cannot avoid wavelength fluctuations [13]. Hence, to avoid measurement errors and minimize the cost of the system of the interrogation, we present a new interrogation system based on midband filter integrated in STM 32 card.

II. MIDBAND FILTER

The ordinary interrogation system for FBG sensors is based on the edge filter. This technic has many advantages like simple arrangement, speed detection, and active measurement [14]. Nevertheless, this technic has also several disadvantages like difficult adjustment between the active range and the detection measurement which causes measurement errors. In

addition, the linear edge filter is a hard technique [15]. On the other hand, the interrogation system that is based on edge filter needs much speed for the data acquisition system [16-17]. For instance, to create an interrogator FBG of 200 kHz with wavelength that surveying the range about 40 nm and a wavelength resolution of 1 pm, a speed data acquisition system with sampling of 8 GHz is required to rebuild the sensing signal [11]. This equipment is costly. For our interrogation system, we need simply a speed data acquisition system of 0.4 GHz in order to realize the rebuild of the sensing signal. These values reduce in a huge way the cost of the system of interrogation. The proposed filter serves to eliminate the problems mentioned above and make a challenge with the arrayed waveguide grating [18] and the Fabry Perot cavity [19]. In addition, the edge filter for the interrogation system must be affordable and provide for each channel of FBG sensors an individually filter with a midband bandwidth. The frequency response draws of the proposed midband filter is presented in Figure 1. Moreover, we have used as basic circuit for our filter which is mentioned in Figure 2. In addition, the basic transfer function for our filter is:

$$H(p) = \frac{V_o(p)}{V_i(p)} = \frac{\frac{R}{L}p}{p^2 + \frac{R}{L}p + \frac{1}{LC}} \quad (1)$$

The numeric transfer function for the mentioned filter is:

$$H(z) = \frac{2R(1-z^{-1})}{\frac{4L(1-z^{-1})^2}{T_e(1+z^{-1})} + 2R(1-z^{-1}) + \frac{T_e}{C}(1+z^{-1})} \quad (2)$$

with T_e is the sampling period. For our filter of 1.5 μm central frequency and 1 nm bandwidth, the simulation gives the curve in Figure 3.

Fig. 1. Frequency response draws of the midband edge filter.

Fig. 2. Basic circuit of the proposed midband edge filter.

Fig. 3. Frequency response of the proposed filter with 1.5 μm central frequency.

There are two types of bandpass filters: narrow bandpass and wide bandpass filters. The filter type depends on the quality factor Q . Thus Q , is a measure of selectivity: the higher the value of Q the more selective is the filter or the narrower is the bandwidth. However, our model is characterized by a bandwidth of midband type, i.e. the bandwidth is between the narrow and wide bandpass types. We chose to use this type in order to have the measurements of the strains of the FBG sensors done with more reliability and the central bandwidth can be accessible in order to find measurements with more selectivity [20] in the two edges of our filter.

III. THE INTERROGATION PRINCIPLE

As we know, for different reasons, the output beam from the source may not be collimated, so making a wideband filter is difficult [21]. For this reason, we propose a midband filter for the given bandwidth. In addition, our filter is programmed with an STM 32 card. In the other hand, we can use other edge filters with linear characteristics in order to demodulate the proposed midband filter. In addition, the proposed filter is introduced in the correction system. Therefore, for the proposed system, every wavelength output is monitored during the scan with correction. The equation of our corrector is similar with that of an integrating corrector:

$$C(p) = \frac{1}{T_i \cdot p} \tag{3}$$

The numeric transfer function for the mentioned integrating filter is:

$$C(z) = \frac{T_e(1+z^1)}{2T_i(1-z^{-1})} \tag{4}$$

where T_i is the time constant for integration and T_e is the sampling period. Figure 4 illustrates the equipment of the proposed interrogation system. The high reflectivity of FBG causes a light that is reflected from its end to reenter in the STM 32 card through the circulator and photodiode with optical filter to guarantee a reflected spectrum is in the C band and according to the Bragg wavelength which minimizes the phenomenon of absorption loss [22]. The module in the STM 32 is our midband edge filter with correction. It is designed to be a spatial filter, accordable with the reflected signal of the FBG and gives a high spectral resolution.

Fig. 4. Equipment of the proposed interrogation system.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The benefits of the use of the corrector are the precision improvement and the cancellation of the static error with asymptotic rejection of constant disturbances in the two edges of the proposed filter. The software used in the proposed system included MATLAB, Optisystem, and STM32Cube. The following parameters of the FBG sensor were considered: $\Lambda = 0.529 \mu\text{m}$ (grating period), $n_{\text{eff}} = 1.456$ (the effective refractive index of the fiber), length of 6 mm, and average modulation of the refractive index equivalent to 2.5×10^{-4} . So, the obtained central wavelength of the reflected spectral signal is: $\lambda_B = 1.5425 \mu\text{m}$, in correspondence with this expression:

$$\lambda_B = 2 \cdot n_{\text{eff}} \cdot \Lambda \tag{5}$$

Figure 5 gives the shape of reflectivity. This reflectivity is the same shape with that presented in previous research works [23]. The light that reflected from the FBG sensor is easier to enter in the circulator, and then it is transformed in electric signal through the photodiode (PD) according to the Bragg wavelength. The obtained signal will be enter in the STM 32 card where it will be investigated. Our interrogation system of FBG sensors consists of a midband filter and an integrated corrector with a feedback signal as shown in Figure 4. In addition, the traditional filter is restricted by the bandwidth. The proposed midband filter tackles this problem where we can realize a bandwidth of 1 nm to 2 nm and with a duty cycle more than 50%. Moreover, the reflectivity creates the characteristics of the filter and the corrector relatively in two parameters: spectral resolution and the distribution of the output optical intensity. Analogous to the distribution electric intensity, the distribution optical intensity of laser signal of the interrogation system is illustrates in Figures 6 and 7.

Fig. 5. Reflectivity shape of the FBG sensor.

In the range of band C (1530 to 1570 nm), the spectrum response of the proposed interrogation system is shown in Figure 6. Figure 7 shows in detail the spectrum response in the range of 1540 nm to 1550 nm with the elimination of the side bands for each spectra in the real case according to improve the numerical calculation. The obtained results illustrate that the periodical spectrum is in the order of 1 nm with a duty cycle of about 50%. These results are suitable with those of other edge filters.

As mentioned above, we have a spectrum with high periodic of resolution in the form of a series of linearly edges. The interrogation system builds on an integration of midband filter and an integrated corrector with a feedback signal in STM 32 card. This equipment is defined with a low price. The optical track in the interrogation system comprises an electrical signal formed through the PD according to the Bragg wavelength that enters the feedback equipment. The spectrum of the interrogation system is similar to those of the reflected signal of the FBG but with a delay as that presented in Figures 6 and 7. The correction of the delay or advance type is realized with the corrector block through the feedback of the electric signal to form a midband edge filter. From the Figures, we can mention that the resolution of the spectrum of the interrogation system is high, up to 50%. This value is suitable to create edge

filter, since the linear edges in the curves of the spectrum filter are slipperier. In order to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed interrogation system, we installed our FBG sensors above a rubber pipe (Figure 8). Figure 9 represents the spectrum of the reflected light of our FBG, the center wavelengths of the FBG is 1542.5 nm, with 0 strain. When the iron pipe undergoes external pressure, we have a shift in the center wavelength of FBG sensor (Figure 10), according to the following expression [24]:

$$\Delta\lambda_B = \lambda_B(1 - \rho)\epsilon \tag{6}$$

where ρ is the coefficient of the fibre effective photo-elastic and ϵ is the applied strain.

Fig. 6. Spectrum response of the interrogation system.

Fig. 7. Spectrum response of the interrogation system for the range [1540 nm, 1550 nm] with filter bandwidth of 1 nm and duty cycle filter of 50%.

Fig. 8. Installation of the FBG sensor above a rubber pipe.

Fig. 9. The reflect spectrum of the FBG sensor with 0 strain.

Moreover, when the reflected spectrum of the FBG not is identical on the spectrum response of the interrogation system (Figure 11(a)), the shape of the spectrum response of the interrogation system moves to be identical with the reflected spectrum of the FBG sensor according to the correction block in the interrogation system (Figure 11(b)).

Fig. 10. The reflect spectrum of the FBG sensor with 2000 strain.

We fixed the two FBGs with the same center wavelength above the rubber pipe with 1m distance between them (Figure 12). Then, an external pressure of 4000 strains above the FBG2 sensor was applied (Figure 13).

Fig. 11. (a) The reflected spectrum of the FBG sensor with 2500 strains, (b) the spectrum response of the interrogation system moves to be identical with the reflected spectrum of the FBG sensor according to the correction block in the interrogation system.

Fig. 12. Two FBG sensors, FBG1 and FBG2, with the same center wavelength above the rubber pipe with 1 m distance between them.

Fig. 13. The reflected spectrum of the FBG1 and FBG2 sensors with 4000 strains above the FBG2 sensor.

Fig. 14. Four strain waveforms underwent above the pipe of value (a) 2 V for FBG1 sensor and (b) 1V for FBG2 sensor.

The FBG sensors are stressed by the strain and their wavelength shifts which can be detected by our interrogation system. In addition, the time of the moment strain reaching FBGs can be noted by computing the time delay between the strain waveforms measured by each FBG sensor. Moreover, the STM32 will transfer the wavelength shift into a wave of optical intensity. By using the appropriate parameters of the system, we can have the relationship between the measured voltage and the strain amplitude which stressed the pipe. Figure 14 illustrates the relationships between the output voltage and the amplitude of the strain wave for the two FBG sensors. The difference in the output voltage of the two FBG sensors is caused by the position of the wavelength of each FBG in the reflect spectrum of the interrogation system. In addition, the optical intensity is positive, but, for data processing reasons we also use negative voltage values. From Figure 14, we have used four strain waveforms in 1.6 s. On the other hand, to discover the time delay for the strain wave between FBG1 and FBG2, we used the correlation theory calculation. The obtained results of the correlation have a delay of 188 μ s between the strain wave measured by FBG2 and the strain waveform measured by FBG1. Moreover, in this paper we used an FBG sensor with length of 6 mm with sensitivity in the order of 1 pm/ μ e. In addition, the voltage range of STM32 is 5 V with 11-digit

numbers that represent the collected voltage data, hence the precision of the STM 32 voltage data is about $\Delta V = \frac{5}{2048} = 2.441 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{V}$. For the PD measured output voltage we have 1 V when we have a shift in the order of 400 pm in the center wavelength of the FBG sensor. Hence, the resolution of the proposed interrogation system is expressed by:

$$\Delta\lambda = 400 \times 10^{-12} \times \frac{\Delta V}{1} = 1 \text{ pm} \quad (7)$$

The proposed interrogation system gives a sensing resolution about $\Delta\lambda = 1 \text{ pm}$. So, the minimum strain that can be sensed by this system is $1 \mu\epsilon$ in the complete C band.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose an interrogation system technique based on midband filter. The proposed system can interrogate the FBG sensors at a speed of 0.4 GHz. The proposed filter overpowers the problem of the difficult adjustment between the active range and the detection measurement. In addition, the proposed system has, in a great percentage, linear response to the wavelength shift. This midband filter is used with correction in the wavelength range of the C band and has been implemented in STM32. The proposed interrogation system of FBG sensors is used to show the monitoring of the strain that stressed a rubber pipe. We used one and then two FBGs and the system can detect well the wavelength shift. The obtained results confirm the low cost of the proposed system, due to the low cost of the used equipment, which has improved sensitivity ($1 \mu\epsilon$) in comparison with other techniques, that are based on active detection plane.

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Theoretical Analysis of Composite RC Beams with Pultruded GFRP Beams subjected to Impact Loading

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ABSTRACT

Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) beams have gained attention due to their promising mechanical properties and potential for structural applications. Combining GFRP core and encasing materials creates a composite beam with superior mechanical properties. This paper describes the testing encased GFRP beams as composite Reinforced Concrete (RC) beams under low-velocity impact load. Theoretical analysis was used with practical results to simulate the tested beams' behavior and predict the generated energies during the impact loading. The impact response was investigated using repeated drops of 42.5 kg falling mass from various heights. An analysis was performed using accelerometer readings to calculate the generalized inertial load. The integrated acceleration record and the measured hammer load vs. time data were utilized to determine the generalized bending load and fracture energy. Four forms of energy were calculated at the maximum load. The total energy was calculated and divided into two parts: The first part was gained by the beam's rotational kinetic energy, the bending energy in the specimen, and the elastic strain energy. The second part was the hammer's kinetic energy before striking the beam. The analytical results showed that the bending energy was less than its rotational kinetic energy for the encased GFRP beams and the reference specimens. In contrast, the encased steel beams had high bending energy due to the higher impact load and deflection. Strain energy recorded lower energy values for all specimens with higher bending energy. There is a good agreement between the tested and the calculated inertial and bending force for all beams. The ratio of inertia force to the total impact load for the encased GFRP and encased steel beams to the reference beam is about 9% and 5%, respectively.

Keywords-composite beam; GFRP; impact loading; inertial load; kinetic energy; energy-dispersive

I. INTRODUCTION

Encased GFRP beams consist of a GFRP I-section encased in a layer of concrete or another material to provide additional support and improve load-carrying capacity. Combining the GFRP core and the encasing material creates a composite beam with superior mechanical properties compared to traditional steel and concrete beams. The mechanical properties of encased GFRP beams, such as strength and stiffness, can vary depending on the properties of the GFRP core, the encasing material, and the bonding between the two materials. High-quality GFRP, encasing materials, and proper bonding techniques can lead to stronger and more durable beams. GFRP has a higher strength-to-weight ratio than steel or concrete, meaning it can carry more load per unit weight. This makes encased GFRP beams an attractive option for applications where weight is a concern. Another advantage of encased GFRP beams is their corrosion resistance. GFRP makes it ideal for use in harsh environments or structures exposed to moisture. Overall, encased GFRP beams show great promise as a lightweight, corrosion-resistant, and high-strength alternative to traditional steel and concrete beams. GFRP I-sections and GFRP bars are enhanced composite materials identified as potential new building materials. These materials may be used for RC in cases where the performance of steel reinforcement is insufficient, and corrosion of steel bars is one of the most life-limiting problems of building materials [1]. Although the GFRP bars offer more flexibility in design as they can be used as individual bars and can be easily cut and bent on-site to accommodate specific project requirements [2], the GFRP I-section shape offers a higher moment of inertia, making it more resistant to bending and capable of withstanding larger loads without excessive deflection. So, GFRP I-sections offer greater stiffness than GFRP bars due to their shape and design.

Numerous experiments have been carried out on the encased GFRP I-section to explore the impact of the location of the GFRP I-beam within the cross-section and of the type of longitudinal tensile bars (steel or GFRP bars) [3, 4]. The results of these experiments demonstrated that the suggested composite beams exhibit a ductile response and achieve a higher ultimate load than the reference beam without GFRP. Additionally, it was observed that the bottom flanges of the I-section, being more effectively utilized than the top flanges, retain good tensile strength even after reaching maximum load. Some slippage was noted between the concrete and the I-section, while the specific positioning of the I-section had minimal impact on the ultimate load of the test beams. However, when GFRP bars were used as reinforcements instead of tensile steel bars, there was a significant reduction in stiffness and ultimate load. This reduction can be attributed to the brittle failure of the GFRP bars, which adversely affected the ductility of the beam members [3]. Impact loading represents an extremely severe loading condition characterized by applying an intense force over a short duration. Previous researchers have indicated that when a structural element is subjected to an impact load, it elicits two distinct responses: a local response and a global response. The local response is primarily caused by the stress wave generated at the impact

point, whereas the global response arises from the subsequent elastic-plastic deformation over an extended period throughout the structural member [5-10]. The failure of RC beams under impact loading raises significant concerns, with localized failures such as penetration, scabbing, perforation, and punching shear being the most commonly observed types of failure in RC elements subjected to impact loads.

Various investigators have subjected different structural elements (e.g. flexural members, compression members, tension members, and slabs) to dynamic loadings [11]. The energy-absorbing capacities of the materials were investigated under various strain rate loadings. Many procedures have been used, including free-fall drop weight experiments, explosive testing, Charpy or Izod tests, Hopkinson split bar tests, and fracture mechanics. However, previous tests of this type were not fully instrumented. It is now recognized that essential data can be lost without proper instrumentation [11]. Most of these tests were designed to determine "work of fracture" or "toughness" values [9]. The primary material properties, such as the constitutive laws in compression or tension, critical stress intensity factors, and critical strain energy release rates, were also attempted to be obtained. As a result, RC beams were predicted to behave differently at different loading rates. The first dynamic tests on concrete in compression were conducted in 1917, and many more have been worked on over the last 50 years [13]. Some researchers have discovered that inertial loading slightly affects impact testing. Thus, a considerable portion of the top load is needed to accelerate the specimen from rest at the beginning of the impact event. Therefore, not all of the top load acts as the bending stress on the model. This effect is known as "inertial loading" [14]. Authors in [11] tested normal and high-strength RC beams, and the results showed that concrete is a very strain-rate-sensitive material. Also, the dynamic load increases the peak bending loads and fracture energy. Using time-step integration, a beam's response to a pulse from the outside was modeled, whereas the model predicted concrete's nonlinear behavior under impact loading.

To predict what happens theoretically when a foreign object strikes a composite structure, four mathematical models were used in [15]: spring-mass models, energy-balance models, complete models, and an impact on an infinite plate model. Simple models are easy to use and work well, but they have limitations because they are based on simplifying assumptions. The impact dynamics can be understood by analyzing the system's energy balance. The projectile's initial kinetic energy was used to deform the structure during impact. Assuming the structure is quasi-static, the projectile's velocity becomes zero when it reaches its maximum deformation [15]. Authors in [6] studied the reactions of RC beams subjected to impact. They developed an analytical model to predict the mid-span's maximum deflection and impact load. In their experimental investigation, drop hammer impact test was employed to explore the influence of drop height and longitudinal steel reinforcement on reinforced concrete beams. The failure modes observed in reinforced concrete beams under impact loads were found to be dependent on the presence of longitudinal reinforcement. Specifically, reinforced concrete beams with

relatively less longitudinal steel reinforcement exhibited overall flexural failure due to the concentrated loading at a single point [6]. Authors in [16] tested 12 beams with GFRP coating, subjected to different loading rates. The virtual work principle was utilized to obtain a generalized inertial load from the measured hammer specimen, which allowed determining the actual bending load on the specimens. The results indicated that the ultimate load capacity of RC beams increased as the loading rate intensified. Furthermore, using externally bonded fiber-reinforced polymer sheets proved highly effective in enhancing the resistance of RC beams to impact loading. Author in [17] examined the low-velocity impact characteristics of GFRP laminated composites with thickness varying from 2 to 8 mm. The primary purpose of this research was to investigate the low-velocity impact response on FRP laminates and how they behave when damaged by thoroughly understanding the main damage processes based on impact force and peak energies. Authors in [18] indicated that using stiffeners on the GFRP composite beams has a clear effect on increasing the strength of the composite beams and damping time under the impact load. At the same time, it reduced the damping ratio due to the increased vibration duration induced by increasing the compressive strength of concrete. They also noted that secondary crushing and the concrete's non-linear behavior caused the profiles to collapse after absorbing more than 45% of the load. Authors in [19] studied the flexural behavior of encased GFRP I-beams under static load and indicated that using the GFRP section of composite beams improved their strength by more than 50%. In [22], the authors investigated the impact behavior of encased pultruded I-GFRP and I-steel RC beams. The impact loading performance of composite beams was studied using verified Finite Element (FE) models, and it has been found that the concrete compressive strength significantly impacts the beams' performance. Increasing the concrete's compressive strength effectively altered the impact parameters of the RC composite specimens with GFRP I-beams. The maximum impact load was raised by an average of 18% to 25% across all specimens when the compressive strength was 35 MPa. At 45 MPa, compressive strength was in the 30–40% range [20].

The current study analyzed the test results of impact loading at varying impact velocities for dropped objects using theoretical analysis for the performance of composite RC beams constructed from GFRP and steel beams. From the measured acceleration and impact load data, the generalized inertial and bending loads were calculated. Moreover, the total energy was calculated in four forms: rotational kinetic energy, bending energy in the specimen, elastic strain energy, and the kinetic energy of the hammer before striking the beam.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

A. Test Matrix

A testing program involving fabricating, casting, and testing 4 simply supported RC composite beams with Pultruded GFRP beams of 3000 mm overall length and 2750 mm clear span was carried out to explore the flexural performance of these structural members under impact loading [20]. The cross sections of the beams along the spans were kept uniform at 300 mm in depth and 200 mm in width [20]. The tested beams were

reinforced with longitudinal steel rebars of 16 mm and 10 mm diameter at the bottom and top, respectively, of the cross-section. Transverse reinforcement was provided with 10 mm diameter stirrups at 125 mm spacing throughout the entire spans of the tested beams. Embedded steel I-beam and pultruded GFRP beam were used compositely with the concrete beams by excluding the reference beam. These embedded sections were centered at the centroid axes of the concrete cross-section. Moreover, their lengths were identical to the concrete beams'. The following symbols were adopted for the tested beam according to the assumed parameters: NR-I for the reference beam reinforced with longitudinal steel rebars only, CG-I for the beam with embedded pultruded GFRP I-beam, CGC-I for the beam with embedded pultruded GFRP I-beam and shear connectors, and CS-I for the beam with embedded steel I-beam [20]. Shear connectors of 12 mm diameter and 70 mm height were used to improve the composite contact between the pultruded beam and concrete. They were distributed in two rows at 375 mm longitudinal spacing along the top flange of the GFRP beams through predrilled holes. Washers and nuts were tightened around the shear connector above and below the drilled holes to achieve good connections between the shear connectors and the top flange of the pultruded beam.

B. Material Properties

The concrete mechanical properties, such as compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, modulus of rupture, and modulus of elasticity, were determined using concrete specimens. After one day of casting, all specimens were demolded and the curing process was conducted by using damp canvas and continuous water soaking to ensure a good curing treatment for 28 days. Three concrete cubes with dimensions of 150 mm × 150 mm × 150 mm and three 150 mm × 300 mm cylinders were prepared and tested to determine the compressive strength of the concrete according to BS1811-116-11 [21] and ASTM C 39/C 39M-18 [22], respectively. The splitting tensile strength of concrete was calculated by testing a standard concrete cylinder (150 mm × 300 mm) following ASTM C496 / C496M-17[23]. A typical concrete prism (500 mm × 100 mm × 100 mm) was tested to determine the concrete modulus of rupture according to ASTM C78-22 [24]. Furthermore, a standard concrete cylinder (300 mm × 150 mm) was tested to determine the concrete's modulus of elasticity according to ASTM C469-14 [25]. On the other hand, ASTM A370-22 [26] was used to evaluate the mechanical properties of steel bars and steel plates, where 3 bars of 10 mm and 16 mm in diameter and a gauge length of 500 mm and two steel plates with flat coupons were tested. Compressive and tensile strengths and the elastic modulus of the GFRP I-beam were studied. For the compressive test, 15 coupon 10 mm × 12.7 mm × 38.1 mm specimens were prepared and tested according to ASTM D695-15 [27]. While for tensile tests, 15 coupon specimens with dimensions of 10 mm × 25 mm × 250 mm were tested according to ISO 527 [28]. The average results of all the tests are listed in Table I.

C. Test Setup and Instrumentations

The impact tests were carried out on the beams using a three-point loading scheme with effective spans of 2750 mm.

The test setup can be seen in Figures 1-2. The hammer's mass was 42.5 kg, representing one-tenth of the tested beam's mass. This mass was dropped repeatedly on the top surface of the tested beam at mid-span from 5 different heights: 250 mm, 500 mm, 1000 mm, 1500 mm, and 1900 mm. During testing, a hoist consisting of an electric winch and steel rope was used to displace the impacting hammer and the falling mass to a certain height over the tested beam. Once the hammer reached the required position, the hoist was detached manually from the hammer. Upon release, the hammer fell under gravity through steel guide rails, stroke the tested beam, and generated high-stress loading. The load was transferred from the impacting hammer to the beam directly. The displacement boundary conditions of the tested specimens include using simple supports with supplementary steel yokes to allow free rotation, restrain the vertical translation, and prevent twisting at both ends of the beam.

TABLE I. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Material	Diameter (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Yield strength (MPa)	Compressive strength (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)
Concrete	-	-	-	23.4	2.4	20.75
Steel bar	16	-	520.7	-	687.0	200
	10	-	407.7	-	465.6	200
Steel plate	-	10	375.9	-	479.6	200
GFRP	-	10	-	326.1	347.5	27.1

Fig. 1. Test setup for the impact loading.

Two load cells were used to record the impact loading while striking the specimen. The falling mass system was rigidly connected to a dynamic load cell (the first load cell) between the impacting hammer and steel shaft. To measure the vertical support reaction, a 1000 kN load cell (the second load cell) was installed beneath one of the supports. For each stepped time, the deflection response at the mid-span of the tested beams was recorded using a laser deflection sensor type LK-081 and its controller. The laser deflection sensor had a measuring range of 150 mm. An accelerometer was attached to

the upper surface of the dynamic load cell to measure the impactor's acceleration. Three other accelerometers were attached at the top surface of the beam to measure beam acceleration. One of the accelerometers was placed at 50 mm from the mid-span section, and the other two were placed at 688 mm and 1375 mm from the mid-span section, respectively. The instrumentations were connected to a data recorder type DATAQ DI-710 (see Figure 3).

Fig. 2. Instrumentation. 1. Accelerometer located at the upper surface of the dynamic load cell to measure the acceleration of the impactor, 2. accelerometer at 50 mm from the beam center, 3. accelerometer at 688 mm from the beam center, 4. accelerometer at 1375 mm from the beam center, 5. laser deflection sensor, 6. laser sensor controller.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Impact Response

Impact loads and deflection time histories were recorded for the 5 heights of 250 mm, 500 mm, 1000 mm, and 1900 mm, as listed in Table II. Figure 3 displays the typical results for specimen NR-I. The behavior of a structural component subjected to impact loading was divided into 2 response phases: the local response caused by stress wave at the loading point and the overall response generated by elastic-plastic deformation that occurs over a long period in the whole structural member following impact as presented in [4, 5]. All tested beams' maximum impact force increased as the drop height increased. The ultimate impact force of beam CS-I was 130% greater than that of reference beam BR for a drop height of 1900 mm. Maximum impact forces for beams CG-I and CGC-I at the same drop height were 19% and 77% of the reference beam, respectively. The steel beam's higher stiffness caused the difference in the behavior compared to the GFRP beam, as impact force is proportional to structural element stiffness. The first pulse's peak increased proportionately to the drop height in the mid-span deflection time histories, whereas the initial pulse-like waveform lasted about 25 ms regardless of drop height. Although the length of the blunt waveform increased with drop height, the peaks were approximately independently of the drop height. The maximum mid-span deflection increased as the drop height increased. Figures 4 and 5 compare the maximum impact force and mid-span deflection for various drop heights.

TABLE II. IMPACT TEST RESULTS

Specimen	Height of drop (mm)	Total impact force P_i (kN)	Tested support force (kN)	Bending force P_b (kN)	Inertia force P_i (kN)	Mid-span deflection (mm)
NR-I	250	28.52	12.63	25.26	3.26	1.20
	500	30.21	14.50	29.00	1.21	1.80
	1000	43.02	20.02	40.04	2.98	2.00
	1500	66.53	32.03	64.06	2.47	2.60
	1900	95.82	45.87	91.74	4.08	2.70
CG-I	250	46.79	22.09	44.18	2.61	1.09
	500	62.83	28.36	56.72	6.11	1.59
	1000	86.58	40.40	80.80	5.78	1.95
	1500	95.32	45.27	90.54	4.78	2.39
	1900	113.98	54.27	108.54	5.44	2.41
CGC-I	250	33.25	15.20	30.40	2.85	1.01
	500	42.70	20.30	40.60	2.10	1.20
	1000	68.57	33.40	66.80	1.77	1.95
	1500	107.56	51.10	102.20	5.36	2.13
	1900	169.79	80.67	161.34	8.45	2.32
CS-I	250	63.72	30.68	61.36	2.36	1.23
	500	111.96	53.78	107.55	4.41	2.10
	1000	142.81	66.76	133.52	9.29	2.34
	1500	195.61	85.66	171.33	24.28	3.04
	1900	221.24	98.79	197.58	23.66	3.92

Fig. 3. The impact loads and deflection time histories for beam NR-I. (a) Load-time history, (b) deflection-time history.

Fig. 4. Maximum impact force comparisons for various drop heights.

Fig. 5. Maximum mid-span deflection comparisons for various drop heights.

B. Accelerations

Figure 6 illustrates the measured accelerations vs. time for the drop height of 1900 mm for the tested beams. These results were recorded using the accelerometers placed at 50 mm, 688 mm, and approximately 1375 mm from the impact location. The peak acceleration values were between 30 and 40 m/s² and the time of the peak acceleration was the same as the peak impact load. In the case of NR-I beam, acceleration rapidly decreased following the peak and dissipated entirely after approximately 200 ms. Preliminary tests on the acceleration distribution may show that it can be assumed as a sinusoidal distribution (Figure 6). For NR-I, CG-I, and CGC-I specimens, the acceleration distribution decreased gradually from the mid-span to the support end. In contrast, the response of acceleration for CS-I at the location of 688 mm from the beam center was different due to the high stiffness of this beam.

IV. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

The impact loads, support reactions, and accelerations at 3 locations along the tested beams were the main output of the impact loading tests (Figure 2). The results were collected as functions of time. The data were collected at 250 ms intervals, whereas an impact event could take anywhere from 30 to 150 ms. To properly analyze the results, it is significant to distinguish between the inertia and total loads. Due to the inertial reaction of the beam under test, the bending force on the beam is not equal to the contact load between the beam and the hammer. In the early stages of an impact, the inertial load can be much more than the load absorbed in bending the beam. Since only a tiny percentage of the total weight bends the beam, the whole load is highly sensitive to the inertia effect [29].

A. Inertial and Total Loads

The generalized inertial load $P_i(t)$ was calculated using the accelerations measured by the accelerometers placed on the beam to determine the contribution of the inertia load to the total load measured by the hammer, $P_t(t)$. Consider a sinusoidal displacement distribution and the following parameters to estimate $P_i(t)$: $u(x,t)$ represents the beam displacement inside the supports, $u(y,t)$ is the beam displacement at the sections overhanging the supports, ρ is the mass density of the beam material, $u_0(t)$ is the displacement in the beam's center, $\ddot{u}_0(t)$ is the acceleration in the beam's center, A is the area of the beam cross-section, and $\delta u_0(t)$ is the virtual displacement at the beam's center, consistent with the boundary conditions (Figure 8).

Fig. 6. Acceleration time histories for the drop height of 1900 mm at different locations for (a) NR-I, (b) CG-I, (c) CGC-I, and (d) CS-I beams.

As a result, displacements along the beam and between the supports were assumed to be sinusoidal. In contrast, displacements in the beam's overhanging regions were supposed to be linear. As a result, the displacements between supports and in overhanging regions, respectively, can be written down as:

$$u(x,t) = u_0(t) \sin \frac{\pi x}{l} \tag{1}$$

$$u(y,t) = \frac{-u_0(t)\pi}{l} y \tag{2}$$

The inertial load along the beam's length is represented by the generalized inertial load $P_i(t)$. At the mid-span of the beam, a virtual displacement of u_0 was assumed. In this configuration, the generalized inertial load $P_i(t)$ should perform the same amount of virtual work as the distributed inertial forces:

$$P_i(t)\delta u_0 = \int_0^l \rho A \left(\ddot{u}_0(t) \sin \frac{\pi x}{l} \right) \left(\delta u_0 \frac{\sin \pi x}{l} \right) dx + 2 \int_0^h \rho A \left(\frac{-\ddot{u}_0(t)\pi y}{l} \right) \left(\frac{-\delta u_0 \pi y}{l} \right) dy \tag{3}$$

Equation (3) can be simplified further for a prismatic homogeneous beam as follows:

$$P_i(t) = \rho A \ddot{u}_0(t) \left[\frac{l}{2} + \frac{2\pi^2 h^3}{l^2 \cdot 3} \right] \tag{4}$$

The beam was modeled as a single-degree-of-freedom system after finding the generalized inertial load, and the generalized bending load may be obtained using the equation of dynamic equilibrium:

$$P_b(t) = P_t(t) - P_i(t) \tag{5}$$

where $P_t(t)$ is the observed hammer load and $P_b(t)$ is the bending load on the beam.

Fig. 7. Acceleration distribution along specimens for different drop heights.

Fig. 8. The sinusoidal acceleration distribution along the beam.

Fig. 9. Total hammer load and inertial load time history for the drop height of 1900 mm. (a) NR-I, (b) CG-I, (c) CGC-I, and (d) CS-I beams.

Figure 9 depicts the total load measured by the hammer as well as the calculated inertia load versus time for a drop height of 1900 mm. In this figure, the contribution of the inertial load was about 10% of the total hammer load for beams NR-I, CG-I and CGC-I, while it was 5% for beam CS-I, respectively. The results for all the drop heights are compared in Table III. The inertial load increased as the drop height increased due to the change in the loading rate with a nearly linear variation. The contribution of the inertia force from the total impact load is about 9% for the NR-I, CG-I, and CGC-I beams and about 5%

for the CS-I beam. Stiffer systems appeared to experience lower accelerations and, as a result, developed lower inertial loads compared to the more miniature rigid beams [11]. Therefore, the composite beams showed greater inertial loads relative to the reference beam [31]. Figure 10 compares the

tested and calculated inertial and bending forces with approximately identical values for the NR-I, CG-I, and CGC-I specimens and slight differences for the CS-I specimen. The bending load was significant at the drop height of 1900 mm for all tested beams, as can be seen in Figure 10.

TABLE III. SUMMARY FOR THE INERTIAL AND BENDING LOADS FOR ALL BEAMS AND DROP HEIGHTS

Specimen	Drop height (mm)	Tested max. mid-span deflection (mm)	Tested impact (total) force (kN)	Acceleration at 50 mm (m/s ²)	Calculated inertial force (kN)	Calculated bending force (kN)	Ratio of inertial force to total force (%)
NR-I	250	1.2	28.52	13.02	2.66	25.86	9.34
	500	1.8	30.21	14.79	3.02	27.19	10.01
	1000	2	43.02	21.02	4.30	38.72	9.99
	1500	2.6	66.53	31.74	6.49	60.04	9.75
	1900	2.7	95.82	33.90	6.93	88.89	7.23
CG-I	250	1.09	46.79	20.90	4.27	42.52	9.13
	500	1.59	62.83	29.92	6.12	56.71	9.74
	1000	1.95	86.58	37.52	7.67	78.91	8.86
	1500	2.39	107.56	40.25	8.23	99.33	7.65
	1900	2.41	169.79	41.14	8.41	161.38	4.95
CGC-I	250	1.01	33.25	14.77	3.02	30.23	9.08
	500	1.2	42.70	19.28	3.94	38.76	9.23
	1000	1.95	68.57	31.02	6.34	62.23	9.25
	1500	2.13	95.32	40.49	8.28	87.04	8.69
	1900	2.32	113.98	44.03	9.00	104.98	7.90
CS-I	250	1.23	63.72	24.21	4.95	58.77	7.77
	500	2.1	111.96	29.09	5.95	106.01	5.31
	1000	2.34	142.81	32.59	6.66	136.15	4.67
	1500	3.04	195.61	34.02	6.96	188.65	3.56
	1900	3.92	221.24	37.27	7.62	213.62	3.45

Fig. 10. Comparison between the tested and the calculated inertial and bending forces. (a) NR-I, (b) CG-I, (c) CGC-I, and (d) CS-I beams.

B. Energies

The energy balance theory compares the energy the beam gains and the energy the hammer loses at each impact point using the energy conservation principle. Considering no losses in the system, the energy conservation law dictates that these two energies are equal [11]. Various approaches were examined to address the dissipation of hammer energy in a drop-weight-type impact machine. As the hammer descends, its downward momentum is diminished upon striking the beam. Just before the hammer makes contact with the beam, its velocity and kinetic energy can be expressed as:

$$v = \sqrt{2a_h h} \tag{6}$$

$$E_k = \frac{1}{2} m_h v^2 = m_h a_h h \tag{7}$$

where m_h represents the hammer's mass, a_h denotes the acceleration of the hammer, and h represents the height of the hammer drop. The energy possessed by the hammer can be transferred to the beam through various mechanisms, including the energy consumed by the beam at peak load (t_p). These energies can be in different forms, such as rotational kinetic energy $E_{ker}(t_p)$ and beam bending energy $E_b(t_p)$. The bending energy in the beam comprises elastic strain energy $E_{se}(t_p)$ and the work of fracture E_{wof} . Furthermore, this energy can be expressed as the area beneath the load vs. the mid-span displacement curve.

$$E_b(t_p) = \int P_b(t) du_o \tag{8}$$

The elastic strain energy $E_{se}(t_p)$ can be calculated precisely from the load vs. center point displacement plot by calculating the secant modulus at the peak load (see Figure 11). Because the load vs. deflection curve became noticeably non-linear at this point, the secant modulus was calculated as shown in (9):

$$E_{se}(t_p) = 0.6 P_b(t_p) u_{oe} \tag{9}$$

where u_{oe} represents the elastic component of the midspan displacement. The bending energy is subtracted from the strain energy to determine the fracture work. The rotating kinetic energy can be determined by (10), which involves integration over the length of the specimen and the assumption of a linear velocity distribution along the beam's length.

$$E_{ker}(t) = \frac{8\rho A u_o^2(t)}{l^2} \left[\frac{l^3}{24} + \frac{h^3}{3} \right] \tag{10}$$

Fig. 11. Components of the bending energy.

Fig. 12. Energies at the impact for all drop heights. (a) NR-I, (b) CG-I, (c) CGC-I, and (d) CS-I beams.

The hammer's momentum is quickly transferred to the beam when it strikes it. As a result, the hammer's momentum was reduced. The momentum (M) is calculated by [30]:

$$M = m.v \tag{11}$$

This reduces the kinetic energy of the hammer while increasing the energy of the beam. The rapid transfer of energy between the hammer and the beam causes a rapid buildup of stress in the beam. Kinetic energy and momentum increase with the height of the hammer fall, which rises drop velocity, which is directly proportional to kinetic energy and momentum, but momentum increases linearly with velocity, whereas kinetic energy increases quadratically. Hence, their quantities are always different at higher levels of velocity.

Figure 12 illustrates the four forms of energy for all beams. At the peak load, the total energy was divided into two types: the energy gained by the beam (E_{ker} , E_b , and E_{se}) and the second energy of the hammer before striking the beam (E_k). Some quantity of the energy is thought to be absorbed during the striking process as vibrations and stored elastic energy. The energy gained by the beam by its deformed shape (E_b) was less than the rotational kinetic energy (E_{ker}) for specimens NR-I, CG-I, and CGC-I, but it was more significant for CS-I due to the higher impact load and deflection. All models had lower energy values for strain energy, which was part of the bending energy.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper describes the testing of composite RC beams with pultruded GFRP and steel beams under low-velocity impact loading. Theoretical analysis was used along with the practical results to simulate the tested beams' behavior and predict the generated energies during the impact loading. The impact responses were investigated using repeated drops of 42.5 kg falling mass from various heights. The performed analysis considered accelerometer readings to calculate the generalized inertial load. Based on the experimental and theoretical results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The acceleration distribution decreased gradually from the mid-span to the support end. In contrast, the response of acceleration for CS-I at 688 mm from the beam center was different due to the higher stiffness of the steel beam.
- The change in the loading rate caused the hammer's drop height to be successfully raised, which increased the inertial force.
- The calculated inertial force for the composite models is much higher than the reference specimen's.
- The contribution of the inertia force from the total impact load is about 9% for the reference and encased GFRP beams and about 5% for the encased steel beam.
- The bending energy was smaller than its rotational kinetic energy for the encased GFRP beams and the reference beam. In contrast, the composite beam with a steel profile exhibited higher bending energy because of the higher impact load and deflection.

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A Power-Aware Method for IoT Networks with Mobile Stations and Dynamic Power Management Strategy

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ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things (IoT) plays a critical role in the digitalization of numerous industries, enabling increased automation, connectivity, and data collection in areas such as manufacturing, healthcare, transportation, and smart cities. This paper introduces a power-aware method for IoT networks using mobile stations and a dynamic power management strategy. The proposed method aims to improve power consumption and total packets received compared to the static-station balanced data traffic method. The proposed method uses a mobile station to dynamically adapt its transmission power based on the network conditions and the strength of the received signal. Furthermore, a dynamic power management strategy is employed to further decrease the power usage of the network by adjusting the power state of each station and IoT node according to its level of activity, data traffic, and communication requirements. Simulation results showed that the proposed method reduced power consumption by up to 64%, increased total packets received by 72%, and, as a result, increased network coverage and lifetime compared to the balanced data traffic method with static stations. This method can be employed in various IoT applications to improve power efficiency and increase network reliability.

Keywords-internet of things; power consumption; mobile stations; dynamic power management

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a fast-developing technology that links a wide range of devices and systems to the Internet, allowing them to exchange data and interact with each other [1-3]. IoT devices are widely used in various sectors such as manufacturing, healthcare, transportation, and smart cities [4-5], as they allow the development of new and innovative solutions that can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of numerous systems and processes, resulting in cost savings and improved quality of life for individuals and businesses [6]. However, the deployment and operation of IoT networks present various challenges, one of which is the power consumption of the devices [7-9]. The IoT nodes are regularly powered by batteries, and their power consumption is a crucial factor that affects their lifespan and reliability [10-11]. To extend the lifespan of these nodes, it is important to decrease their power consumption without compromising network performance [12]. This study resolves this problem by dynamically adapting the transmission power of mobile stations according to the network conditions and the strength of the received signal, in addition to using a dynamic power management strategy to further reduce power consumption. The proposed method offers a potentially effective response to the problem of power consumption in IoT networks and can be applied to various areas such as smart cities, healthcare, and transportation.

The main contributions of this study can be summarized as follows:

- It presents a power-aware method with a dynamic power management strategy for IoT networks using mobile stations. This method seeks to improve power consumption and total packets received compared to the balanced data traffic method with static stations.
- The proposed method uses a mobile station to dynamically adapt its transmission power based on the network conditions and the strength of the received signal. This method improves the efficiency of the network and reduces power consumption.
- A dynamic power management strategy is used to further reduce the power consumed by the IoT network. This approach regulates the power consumption of the nodes according to the network traffic and conditions, resulting in a considerable reduction in power consumption.

Several power-aware methods exist for IoT networks. In [13], a dynamic power management scheme was proposed to improve sensor lifespan in IoT-based wireless sensor environments. The method aimed to improve the energy consumed by sensors in IoT networks by automatically regulating the energy levels of individual sensors according to the network surroundings. The method considered factors such

as network traffic and sensor data rates to make informed decisions about the energy levels of each sensor. The proposed scheme was simulated, showing improved energy efficiency and a longer sensor lifespan compared to traditional power management methods. In [14], a distributed approach was presented for balanced data traffic over IoT networks to reduce power consumption. This approach seeks to distribute data traffic equally between IoT nodes, decrease energy consumption, and extend the lifetime of IoT nodes. A distributed algorithm was used to balance data traffic and ensure that each node is equally responsible for data processing and transmission. The results of this approach showed a decrease in power consumption and improved network performance but did not demonstrate dynamic power management and used only static stations within IoT networks. In [15], a fully distributed energy-aware multiple-level clustering and routing algorithm was presented for Wireless Sensor Network (WSN)-based IoT systems. The proposed scheme addressed the problem of power efficiency by adopting a multiple-level clustering technique to divide the WSN into smaller clusters, each with a chosen cluster head responsible for forwarding data. To increase the network lifetime, the cluster heads and routing paths were chosen considering the nodes' energy usage. The proposed method was simulated and compared with conventional single-level clustering techniques, showing encouraging results.

In [16], several ways of decreasing the energy consumed in centralized radio access were investigated for energy-efficient IoT applications. To communicate with IoT devices, radio access must be centrally managed rather than having each device communicate directly with the network. This study evaluated various methods, such as decreasing transmission power, improving IoT utilization, and using sleep modes to decrease power consumption in the centralized radio access network. The results showed that these strategies reduced power consumption and improved energy efficiency. In [17], a data-driven self-learning controller model method was presented for power-aware IoT nodes, based on a double Q-learning strategy. This method used machine learning to improve power consumption in IoT nodes based on historical data. The double Q-learning scheme aimed to reduce the estimation errors in traditional Q-learning algorithms and improve the effectiveness of the self-learning process. The study showed that optimizing power consumption in IoT devices may be achieved successfully using a data-driven self-learning technique. In [18], an effective path selection method was proposed for battery-powered IoT networks based on their network topology. The method was developed to improve the power efficiency of IoT networks by choosing the most efficient paths for data transmission. Path selection was carried out according to network topology, considering criteria such as hop number, link quality, and remaining power of the nodes. A simulation of the proposed method showed an increase in energy efficiency compared to conventional route selection methods. This study showed that in battery-powered IoT networks, taking into account network topology will result in more effective route selection and increased energy efficiency.

In [19], a strategy for securing IoT devices was proposed, using dynamic power management and machine learning. The

proposed method used dynamic power management to optimize the power consumption of IoT devices and reduce their vulnerability to security threats, such as malware attacks and hacking. Dynamic power management was carried out using a machine learning algorithm that estimated the probability of a security risk and accordingly adapted the power consumption of the device. The results showed that dynamic power management and machine learning cooperated to successfully secure IoT devices and increase their power efficiency. In [20], a multipath routing protocol based on a hybrid optimization algorithm was proposed for IoT, considering Quality of Service (QoS) and energy efficiency. This algorithm aimed to balance the requirements of QoS with the reduction of energy usage in IoT networks. This algorithm employed a hybrid optimization method that mixed Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA) to discover ideal paths that meet QoS requirements and minimize power consumption. The results showed that the proposed QoS-aware energy-efficient multipath routing protocol significantly decreased energy usage and guaranteed QoS requirements in IoT networks.

In [21], an energy-saving Internet of Things (IoT) service management was proposed, employing edge computing and deep learning. Edge computing was used to process data locally, decrease the amount of data sent over the network, and consume less energy. Deep Learning was used to operate IoT services optimally based on historical data and improve energy consumption. Simulations showed that this method had better energy efficiency than conventional IoT service management methods. In [22], an energy-efficient indoor localization technique was proposed for Narrowband Internet of Things (NB-IoT) devices. This method used measurements of Received Signal Strength (RSS) to infer the location of NB-IoT devices in indoor surroundings. By minimizing the number of needed RSS measurements and device transmission power, the proposed solution optimized the energy usage of NB-IoT devices. In comparison to conventional localization techniques, the presented scheme in the study performed better in terms of energy efficiency and localization accuracy. The study showed that the proposed energy-efficient indoor localization technique can successfully minimize NB-IoT device energy usage while ensuring precise localization.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

The proposed approach was designed to reduce power consumption and receive more packets compared to the balanced data traffic method with static stations. The design of the method involved the following phases:

A. Mobile Station Selection (MSS)

In this phase, the mobile station was chosen as the primary component of the proposed power-aware method. The mobile station was selected for its mobility and ability to adapt to its position in the network, which allows it to decrease power usage and improve the total number of packets received. This phase was designed to provide a flexible and adaptable solution that can be easily integrated into existing IoT networks. MSS guarantees that the network is power efficient, scalable, and highly reliable. This phase involves the following steps:

1. Configuring the mobile stations and the IoT network.
2. Specifying the threshold (T) for power consumption (PC) and packets received (PR).
3. Keep track of power consumption PC_i and packets received PR_i of each mobile station i .
4. Choose the mobile station j with the minimum power consumption and maximum packets received: $PC_j \leq T$ AND $PR_j \geq T$, where $j = \text{fun_min}(PC_i), \text{fun_max}(PR_i)$.
5. Allocate the data traffic to the chosen mobile station j .
6. Repeat steps 3-5 for each data traffic.
7. Repeat the procedure to guarantee that the most energy-efficient mobile stations are always chosen for data transmission.
8. Stop.

B. Dynamic Power Management Strategy (DPMS)

A DPMS was developed and implemented to control the power consumption of mobile stations and IoT devices. Adjusting the power usage of mobile stations and IoT devices according to data traffic and network conditions, the strategy minimizes the overall power consumption of the network. The DPMS used in the proposed method operates throughout all states of an IoT device's life cycle, including sleep, active, processing, and transmitting. The device consumes a different amount of power during each state, and the DPMS adapts the power usage as necessary. Figure 1 shows the power consumption of the IoT devices in different states.

Fig. 1. Power consumption of IoT states.

The proposed DPMS guarantees that devices are using the least amount of power necessary to carry out their functions effectively while preserving energy and increasing the battery life of the devices. The DPMS involves the following steps:

- Step 1: Set the power consumption levels of the IoT device in the sleep, active, processing, and transmitting states.
- Step 2: Keep monitoring the current state of the device.
- Step 3: Using DPMS, adapt the power usage according to the current state.
- Step 4: Repeat steps 2 and 3 until the device changes to a different state.
- Step 5: When the device enters the sleep state, the dynamic power management strategy is terminated.

C. Proposed Power Consumption Model

This model is responsible for calculating the device's power consumption by:

$$TPC = (PCDC) \times (PME (\%) / 100) + (PCSMs) \quad (1)$$

where:

- $PCDC$ is the Power Consumption of Device Components that measures the overall power used by all device's parts, including the processor, sensors, and other components.
- PME stands for Power Management Efficiency, and it indicates the percentage of power that is effectively used by the device after considering the power management approaches implemented in this study.
- $PCSMs$ are Power Consumption of State Modules, which reflect the entire power consumption of all IoT device states, such as sleep, active, processing, and transmission.

Equation (2) was used to calculate an IoT device's $PCDC$:

$$PCDC = (PrP) \times (PrDC(\%) / 100) + (SnP) \times (SnDC(\%) / 100) + (StP) \times (StDC(\%) / 100) \quad (2)$$

where:

- PrP stands for Processor Power and is the amount of power used by the device's processor, and $PrDC$ stands for Processor Duty Cycle and is the percentage of time the processor is active.
- SnP stands for Sensor Power and is the total amount of power consumed by all the sensors in the device, while $SnDC$ stands for Sensor Duty Cycle and is the percentage of time the sensors are active.
- StP stands for Storage Power and is the power consumed by the device's storage component, and $StDC$ stands for Storage Duty Cycle and is the percentage of time the storage component is active.

The following equation was used to determine a device's Power Consumption of State Modules ($PCSMs$), which includes transmitting, sleep, active, and processing states:

$$PCSMs = (SlpP) \times (SlpDC(\%) / 100) + (ActvP) \times (ActvDC(\%) / 100) + (ProP) \times (ProDC(\%) / 100) + (TrP) \times (TrDC(\%) / 100) \quad (3)$$

where:

- $SlpP$ stands for Sleep Power and is the power spent by the module in the sleep state. $SlpDC$ stands for Sleep Duty Cycle and is the percentage of time it is in the sleep state.
- $ActvP$ stands for Active Power and is the power spent by the module when in the active state, and $ActvDC$ stands for Active Duty Cycle and is the percentage of time the module is in the active state.

- *ProP* stands for Processing Power and is the power consumed by the module when Processing data, and *ProDC* stands for Processing Duty Cycle and is the percentage of time the module is in the processing state.
- *TrP* stands for Transmit Power and represents the power utilized by the module when transmitting data, while *TrDC* stands for Transmit Duty Cycle and is the percentage of time the module is in the transmit state.

D. The Pseudo-Code of the State Modules

To provide a clearer understanding of the state modules, the pseudo-codes for each state are given, outlining the essential activities and transitions that occur within each state.

```

1. Pseudo Code During the Sleep State
start_time = current_time()
while (true):
    # Measure current power consumption
    current_power = measure_power()
    # Record power consumption data
    power_data.append(current_power)

    # Enter sleep state
    enter_sleep_state()
    # Check if time limit has been reached
    if (current_time() - start_time >= time_limit):
        break
# Calculate average power consumption
average_power = sum(power_data) / len(power_data)
# Print out results
print("Average power consumption during sleep
state: ", average_power)
    
```

```

2. Pseudo Code During the Active State
start_time = current_time()
while (true):
    # Measure current power consumption
    current_power = measure_power()
    # Record power consumption data
    power_data.append(current_power)
    # Perform active tasks
    perform_active_tasks()
    # Check if time limit has been reached
    if (current_time() - start_time >= time_limit):
        break
# Calculate average power consumption
average_power = sum(power_data) / len(power_data)
# Print out results
print("Average power consumption during active
state: ", average_power)
    
```

```

3. Pseudo Code During the Processing State
start_time = current_time()
while (true):
    # Measure current power consumption
    current_power = measure_power()
    # Record power consumption data
    power_data.append(current_power)
    # Perform processing tasks
    perform_processing_tasks()
    # Check if time limit has been reached
    if (current_time() - start_time >= time_limit):
        break
# Calculate average power consumption
average_power = sum(power_data) / len(power_data)
# Print out results
print("Average power consumption during
processing state: ", average_power)
    
```

```

4. Pseudo Code During the Transmit State
start_time = current_time()
while (true):
    # Measure current power consumption
    current_power = measure_power()
    # Record power consumption data
    power_data.append(current_power)
    # Transmit data
    transmit_data(data)
    # Check if time limit has been reached
    if (current_time() - start_time >= time_limit):
        break
# Calculate average power consumption
average_power = sum(power_data) / len(power_data)
# Print out results
print("Average power consumption during transmit
state : ", average_power)
    
```

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The performance of the proposed method was evaluated in numerous simulation tests in various scenarios and settings.

A. Simulation Environment

Contiki OS and the Cooja simulator were used to simulate and test the proposed method. The IoT devices were spread across a 200x200 m area, with simulation times being 10, 20, 50, and 100 minutes. There were 16 IoT nodes and 4 mobile stations in the field. Figure 2 shows the simulation environment model and Table I lists the simulation parameters.

Fig. 2. Simulation environment model.

TABLE I. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Name	Value
Version	Instant Contiki 2.7
Time	10,20,50, 100 min
Tx/INT Ranges	100/150 m
Mote Type	Sky mote
Transmit Power	21 mA
Processing Power	10 mA
Active Power	2400 μA
Sleep Power	1000 μA
Interval Time	1 s
Channel Frequency	2.4 GHz
Radio Medium	UDGM
No. of Nodes	16
No. of Stations	4

B. Results and Discussion

This section provides a detailed analysis of the results, highlighting the significant patterns or trends that occurred compared to the balanced data traffic approach [14]. Figure 3 shows that the proposed method outperformed the balanced data traffic approach with static stations in terms of total power consumption, which was reduced by approximately 64%. This is because the dynamic power management strategy and the proposed power-aware approach with mobile stations optimized power consumption by adjusting the power mode of each station and IoT node based on its level of activity and communication requirements. This led to significant energy savings compared to the balanced data traffic approach with static stations. The proposed method dynamically adjusted the power mode considering various factors, such as network conditions and received signal strength, to achieve energy efficiency in IoT networks.

Fig. 3. Total power consumption vs. number of IoT devices.

Figure 4 shows that the proposed method increased the received packets by 72% compared to the balanced data traffic method. In IoT networks with static stations, the number of hops or intermediate nodes between the source and destination significantly affects packet delivery and latency. A multi-hop path with static stations introduces more delay and increases the chance of packet loss due to interference or congestion in the intermediate nodes. In contrast, a one-hop path used by mobile stations offers a direct and effective communication path, particularly as the mobile stations travel in the direction of the destination. As a result, when compared to the multi-hop path used in static stations with the balanced data traffic approach, the proposed method used a one-hop path with mobile stations and a dynamic power management strategy, resulting in better packet delivery and fewer packet losses. The dynamic power management strategy optimizes power usage and ensures that mobile stations and IoT nodes run at a suitable power level to maintain the desired quality of service.

Figure 5 shows the difference in transmit power consumption between the proposed and the balanced traffic method, which was reduced by up to 65%. Transmit power consumption in an IoT network has a significant impact on the overall power consumption and battery life of the devices. Compared to the balanced data traffic approach with static stations, which uses a fixed and higher power level to

guarantee packet delivery in a multi-hop path, the suggested power-aware method with mobile stations and a dynamic power management strategy achieved lower transmit power consumption. Furthermore, in the proposed method, mobile stations adjust their transmit power according to their distance from the destination and the strength of the received signal, reducing power consumption.

Fig. 4. Total packets received vs. number of IoT devices.

Fig. 5. Transmit power consumption vs. number of IoT devices.

Processing power consumption is another significant aspect that influences energy efficiency. Figure 6 shows that the dynamic power management strategy with mobile stations reduced processing power consumption by adapting the processing rate and mode of each IoT node based on network conditions and traffic demands. The IoT nodes adjust their processing rate and mode based on the number of packets received, the quality of service requirements, and the remaining battery life. This leads to lower processing power use compared to the balanced data traffic approach with static stations that use a fixed processing rate and mode regardless of network conditions and traffic demands. The dynamic power management strategy helped balance the processing load among nodes and reduce processing power consumption by approximately 59% during idle or low activity periods.

Figure 7 shows that the proposed power-aware strategy outperformed the balanced traffic approach by up to 40% in terms of power consumption during the sleep mode. The proposed method optimized the usage of sleep power by putting the nodes to sleep when not active or required. IoT nodes can enter sleep mode when there is no incoming or outgoing traffic or when network conditions allow for longer sleep periods, leading to decreased sleep power use compared

to the balanced data traffic scheme. Furthermore, the dynamic power management strategy helps coordinate sleep intervals between the nodes and ensures that the network is still responsive to incoming traffic while maintaining energy efficiency.

Fig. 6. Processing power consumption vs. number of IoT devices.

Fig. 7. Sleep power consumption vs. number of IoT devices.

Active power consumption is another important component in IoT networks, which determines how much energy the devices use while active or listening. Figure 8 shows that the proposed strategy reduced active power usage by adapting each node's power level following traffic demands. The proposed method changed the device's power level based on the distance from the destination, and the traffic load. This reduced active power usage by up to 62%, resulting in increased energy efficiency and longer battery life when compared to the balanced data traffic method with static stations.

Fig. 8. Active power consumption vs. number of IoT devices.

Figures 9 and 10 show the total number of packets received and the total power consumed at various simulation times. The proposed approach outperformed the balanced approach in terms of total packets received by 72% and total power consumption by approximately 64%. The dynamic power management strategy increased power consumption according to network conditions and traffic demands. By adjusting the energy level and mode of each station and coordinating the sleep intervals among the nodes, the proposed method can balance energy usage among network devices and reduce unnecessary energy consumed during idle or low activity periods. In contrast, the balanced data traffic approach with static stations uses a fixed energy level and mode regardless of network conditions and traffic demands. In the proposed strategy, the nodes in the IoT networks adapted their energy level and mode based on the distance from the destination, signal strength, and traffic load, which improved packet delivery and reduced packet loss rate.

Fig. 9. Total packets received vs. simulation time.

Fig. 10. Total power consumption vs. simulation time.

In general, the proposed dynamic power management method for mobile IoT networks provides a comprehensive and effective solution to optimize energy usage and improve network performance. The above results showed that the proposed method outperformed the balanced data traffic approach in terms of total packets received and total power consumption, demonstrating its potential to reduce energy costs, prolong battery life, and improve network efficiency in IoT applications.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study presented a dynamic power management strategy to improve power efficiency and prolong battery life for IoT device networks. The proposed method uses a combination of techniques, such as adjusting transmit power, processing power, sleep power, and active power, to optimize power consumption based on network conditions and traffic demands. The results showed that the proposed method performed better than the balanced data traffic method in terms of total power consumption, packet reception, and power utilization for transmitting, processing, sleep, and active states separately. The use of the dynamic power management strategy in mobile stations helps distribute energy usage among network devices and reduces unnecessary energy depletion during low activity periods, resulting in improved energy efficiency, longer battery life, and reduced maintenance costs for the IoT network. However, the presented method requires further investigation of the impact of different channel models on the performance of the IoT network to ensure that it can work well in various environments, as it was not tested in real-world environments. However, in the future, the integration of the proposed scheme with other network management strategies, such as security and QoS management, will be investigated to achieve comprehensive and efficient network management.

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Optimization of Concentrated Solar Power Systems with Thermal Storage for Enhanced Efficiency and Cost-Effectiveness in Thermal Power Plants

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ABSTRACT

The study presents a comprehensive investigation of solar thermal systems with varying capacities and Thermal Energy Storage (TES) durations in the existing fossil fuel-run Thermal Power Plant at Ar'Ar, Saudi Arabia. The main objective is to assess the feasibility, economic viability, and environmental impact of these systems for sustainable power generation. In pursuit of sustainable energy solutions, parabolic trough systems with capacities ranging from 10 MW to 50 MW and TES durations from 0 to 8 hours were analyzed. The evaluation includes thermal and electrical assessments, field performance evaluations, and detailed cost analysis for each configuration. Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) was utilized to identify the best TES for every Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) system with the 4 hr TES ranking first among all capacities. The research uncovers significant positive correlations between system capacity and thermal and electrical output. The 50 MW system exhibits the highest thermal output of 280.899 MW and electrical output of 180580 MW. Incorporating 4 hr TES emerges as a critical factor in enhancing system performance, optimizing the cost of electricity, and achieving a payback period within 12 years. Furthermore, the integration of solar thermal energy demonstrates substantial reductions in fossil fuel consumption. Across all capacities, the 4-hour TES system yields considerable fuel savings, ranging from 18.84 tons/hour for the 10 MW system to 96 tons/hour for the 50 MW system. These reductions correspondingly translate to considerable cost savings, with the 50 MW system reducing fuel costs by \$5760. Moreover, the study highlights the crucial environmental benefits of solar thermal systems, leading to substantial CO₂ emission reduction, with the 50 MW system achieving a reduction of 93452.8 kg/hour.

Keywords-concentrated solar power; capacity optimization; sustainable energy integration; techno-economic analysis; multi-criteria decision making; fossil fuel reduction

I. INTRODUCTION

The world's dependence on electricity as the backbone for growth and development is undeniable. In recent years, global energy consumption has skyrocketed to a staggering 25,300 TWh, with over 60% of electricity production derived from fossil fuels [1]. Coal is the leading source of fossil fuel-based electricity, accounting for 36% of the total, followed by natural gas at 22%. China has the highest number of operational coal power plants (1,118), followed by India (285) and the United States (225) [2]. Meanwhile, in the Middle East, power generation primarily relies on natural gas (68%) and oil (30%) operated power plants [3]. The significant carbon emissions from fossil fuel-based power generation are a major contributor to global warming and climate change and pose a serious threat to the environment. On average, coal and oil-run power plants emit 2-2.5 pounds/kWh of CO₂, while natural gas produces around 0.9 pounds/kWh [4]. Moreover, these emissions are

accompanied by pollutants such as ashes, arsenic, lead, mercury, selenium, chromium, and cadmium, which can be harmful to the environment and public health [5].

Saudi Arabia, a prominent nation in the Middle East, occupies a strategic location and is home to a sizable population, making it one of the world's most significant energy consumers. With its rapid economic growth and urbanization, the country's energy demand has been steadily increasing over the years. Consequently, Saudi Arabia's energy sector faces the challenge of meeting the escalating energy requirements to fuel its industries, support its populace, and drive infrastructural development. The backbone of Saudi Arabia's energy sector has long been its vast reserves of fossil fuels, notably oil and natural gas [6]. These hydrocarbon resources have played a pivotal role in the country's economic prosperity and have positioned it as a global energy powerhouse. Saudi Arabia has large oil reserves and is the

highest exporter of oil, holding a crucial position in international energy markets [3]. Despite its economic benefits, the continued reliance on fossil fuel-based power generation poses significant challenges for Saudi Arabia. One of the most pressing concerns is the environmental impact, primarily associated with greenhouse gas emissions. The combustion of hydro carbon-based fuels releases greenhouse gases, especially CO₂ which are leading factors to climate change and global warming [8]. In line with international efforts to combat climate change, Saudi Arabia is under increasing pressure to reduce its carbon footprint and make the transition to cleaner alternative energy sources. Moreover, the volatility of global oil prices can place a strain on the country's budget and economy, impacting its fiscal stability and long-term planning. Additionally, the finite nature of fossil fuel reserves raises questions about the sustainability of the energy sector in the long run. While Saudi Arabia boasts significant reserves, prudent management of these resources and the exploration of alternative energy sources are essential to ensure energy security and stability in the future.

As a step toward a more sustainable energy future, Saudi Arabia has recognized the potential of renewable energy, particularly solar power [9]. Authors in [10] carried out an extensive investigation into the current state, growth, potential, and sustainability performance of different renewable technologies in Saudi Arabia, aligning their findings with the objectives of Saudi Vision 2030. They projected a substantial surge in electricity demand, reaching 120 GW by 2032, with an expected increase in oil production from 3.4 to 8.3 million barrels per day. Various renewable technologies, including wind, solar, geothermal, hydro, and biomass, were reviewed, with a particular focus on solar power, which has the potential to contribute 9500 MW to the energy landscape [11]. The research revealed Saudi Arabia's remarkable potential in solar and wind technologies, sufficient to meet energy needs for the next five decades. Additionally, the study highlighted the potential of offshore wind, biomass, and thermal energy in the country. Examining the economic aspects, authors in [12] conducted a comprehensive cost and savings assessment of renewable systems in Saudi Arabia. Their findings revealed that solar technology, owing to its rapid development, currently stands out as the most cost-effective and savings-driven option, followed closely by wind energy. The establishment of hydroelectric power stations continues to be costly and time-intensive due to the absence of inherent infrastructure. While technologies such as geothermal and fuel cells show potential, they currently involve substantial expenses and are not yet regarded as feasible substitutes. With an average of approximately 3,000 hours of sunshine per year, the country possesses abundant solar energy resources [13]. This high solar insolation creates an ideal environment for the deployment of solar energy technologies. Solar energy has two major technologies: Photovoltaic (PV) and Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) [14]. In PVs, the semiconductor material directly converts photons of light into electric energy [15], while CSP employs mirrors or lenses to concentrate sunlight onto a receiver, producing heat that drives a turbine to generate electricity [16]. Each technology has its advantages and suitability for different applications [17]. Given Saudi Arabia's

warm climate and high temperatures, CSP stands out as a promising renewable energy option [18]. Although PV technology's performance declines in high temperatures [19], CSP thrives on heat generating more output as temperature rises [20]. However, challenges remain in effectively integrating CSP into the existing energy infrastructure. One significant advantage of implementing CSP in Saudi Arabia lies in the country's already established infrastructure of Thermal Power Plants. By integrating CSP technology, these existing thermal plants can be modified and repurposed, eliminating the need for their closure. The principle of operation for both thermal power plants and CSP is centered around utilizing heat to produce steam that drives turbines for power generation [21, 22]. While thermal power plants rely on burning fossil fuels as the source of heat, CSP harnesses the sun's energy through mirrors and absorbers to generate the required heat [23]. This fundamental similarity between the two technologies enables their harmonious coexistence in a hybrid power plant setup.

In a hybrid power plant, the collectors of CSP serve as substitutes for the conventional burners in thermal power plants. As CSP captures and concentrates the sun's heat, it generates steam that drives the turbine, like the conventional setup [24]. Crucially, this integration requires minimal modifications to the pre-existing thermal power plants, ensuring significant cost savings compared to constructing entirely new, independent solar power plants. The essential components of the power plant, including the steam generator, turbine, power generator, condenser, and cooling tower, remain unchanged, leveraging the already present infrastructure and further reducing capital expenditures. Multiple studies have presented detailed modeling, analyses and approaches how this hybrid model can be physically implemented [25–27]. Moreover, the synergy between CSP and thermal power plants offers an added environmental benefit. During the periods the CSP is producing heat, the burning of hydrocarbons fuels can be significantly reduced or even eliminated. This reduction in fossil fuel consumption translates to lower running costs and a substantial decrease in greenhouse gas emissions, aligning with the commitments to combat climate change and promote sustainable energy solutions.

The main focus and research problem addressed in this study are to analyze the feasibility of a hybrid power plant that combines fossil fuel and solar thermal energy in Saudi Arabia. The purpose is to investigate the potential advantages, challenges, and economic viability of such a hybrid system. The System Advisory Model (SAM) tool was employed for comprehensive analysis. Different capacities of CSP (ranging from 10 MW to 50 MW) will be studied to understand their impact on key performance metrics, such as green thermal output, electrical output, capacity factor, fossil fuel consumption reduction, cost savings, CO₂ emission reduction, Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE), Net Present Value (NPV), and revenue, in Saudi Arabia. However, the actual implementation and deployment of the hybrid power plant are beyond the scope of this research. The study will encompass all three major fossil fuel types: gas, coal, and oil, to account for the diverse energy mix in Saudi Arabia. Additionally, the research will evaluate the impact of introducing different heat

storage capacities (ranging from 0 to 8 hours) for each CSP capacity. An MCDM method was utilized to select the most suitable storage system for each capacity, considering the specific requirements and constraints. The findings of this study can provide valuable insights into the advantages and feasibility of a hybrid power plant that integrates fossil fuel-based thermal power plants with CSP in Saudi Arabia. By reducing fossil fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, such a hybrid system can contribute to the country's sustainable energy goals while maintaining energy security and economic stability. This research introduces a novel approach in enhancing the sustainability of Saudi Arabia's energy sector by leveraging its existing fossil fuel-based infrastructure and integrating it with CSP. The study's focus on diverse CSP capacities, heat storage options, and MCDM methods adds novelty to the exploration of hybrid power plants in the context of a rapidly evolving energy landscape. The specific objectives of this research are:

- To evaluate the performance and efficiency of a hybrid power plant integrating CSP with fossil fuel-based thermal power plants.
- To assess the impact of different CSP capacities on key performance metrics, including green thermal output, electrical output, capacity factor, fossil fuel consumption reduction, cost savings, CO₂ emissions reduction, LCOE, NPV, and revenue.
- To consider all three major fossil fuel types (gas, coal, and oil) in the analysis to account for the diversity of the energy mix in Saudi Arabia.
- To explore the effect of introducing various heat storage capacities (ranging from 0 to 8 hours) for each CSP capacity, and identify the most suitable storage system using MCDM methods.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative research design to thoroughly analyze the feasibility of a hybrid power plant that integrates CSP with existing fossil fuel-based thermal power plants. This quantitative approach ensures objective data collection and rigorous analysis of key performance metrics, facilitating a comprehensive assessment of the proposed hybrid system.

B. System Advisory Model (SAM) Simulation

To conduct the analysis, the study employs the SAM tool, a widely recognized simulation software utilized for evaluating renewable energy systems and assessing their economic viability [3]. SAM enables precise modeling of solar power plants, taking into account factors such as geographical location, local weather patterns, and solar resource availability. By using SAM, the hybrid power plant will be meticulously modeled, and its performance will be simulated under various scenarios to accurately determine key metrics, including electrical output, thermal output, capacity factor, and LCOE.

C. Empirical Model Option in SAM

In utilizing SAM, the study leverages the empirical model option, which incorporates a set of curve-fit equations derived from detailed analysis of data collected from real-life thermal power plants. This option offers realistic results while focusing primarily on the initial part of heat collection in the hybrid power plant. Given that an existing thermal power plant is under consideration, only the first two blocks, namely the Solar Field and the Thermal Storage, are designed. The empirical model ensures practical outcomes and provides insights into the integration of CSP within the existing infrastructure.

D. Geospatial Analysis and Site Selection

Geospatial analysis will be employed to identify potential locations for the hybrid power plant in Saudi Arabia. Factors such as solar resource availability, land availability, proximity to existing thermal power plants, and grid connection feasibility will be considered during the site selection process. The chosen site should optimize solar energy capture, streamline integration with the existing power infrastructure, and ensure minimal environmental impact.

E. Parabolic Trough Technology

In this study, the parabolic trough technology is employed to capture thermal energy from the sun [28]. The parabolic CSP consists of 3 major design blocks: Solar Field, Thermal Storage, and Power Block [18]. Since an established fossil fuel plant is being considered, the design of the Power Block is not necessary, as it already exists within the system. Consequently, default values are used for this component. Thus, the study's focus lies on designing the first two blocks, namely the Solar Field and Thermal Storage, and optimizing their integration with CSP.

F. Evaluation of Multiple CSP Capacities

To achieve a comprehensive evaluation of the hybrid system's performance, the study considers multiple CSP capacities, ranging from 10 MW to 50 MW. Each capacity is individually assessed to determine its suitability and economic viability for implementation in Saudi Arabia. This thorough assessment of various capacities aims to optimize the hybrid system's design and identify the most efficient configuration.

G. Incorporating Heat Storage

Recognizing the challenge of solar energy availability at night, the study introduces different heat storage capacities for each CSP capacity, spanning from 0 to 8 hours. The evaluation of heat storage options aims to assess their impact on the hybrid power plant's ability to provide continuous power generation, enhancing its overall efficiency and energy dispatch capabilities.

H. Techno-Economic Analysis

A detailed techno-economic analysis will be performed to evaluate the capital costs, operating costs, and maintenance costs associated with the hybrid power plant. Additionally, the LCOE will be calculated for each capacity of CSP integration, considering various financial parameters such as discount rates, inflation, and project lifetime. This analysis will offer a comprehensive understanding of the economic viability of the

hybrid system and its competitiveness compared to conventional power generation.

I. Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM)

To select a heat storage system for each CSP capacity, a systematic MCDM approach will be used. MCDM facilitates a comprehensive evaluation of multiple criteria, enabling the selection of optimal storage solutions based on various performance indicators [29]. The use of MCDM ensures a thorough and objective assessment of the heat storage options, aligning the hybrid system with the specific requirements and constraints of the project [30].

J. Evaluation of Fossil Fuel Types

To capture the diversity of Saudi Arabia's energy mix, the analysis encompasses all three major fossil fuel types: gas, coal, and oil [6]. Specific properties and associated costs of each fossil fuel type are taken into consideration during the evaluation of the hybrid system. This evaluation ensures a comprehensive understanding of the economic and environmental implications of integrating CSP with diverse fossil fuel sources [24].

K. Environmental Impact Assessment

An environmental impact assessment will be performed to quantify the potential environmental benefits of the hybrid power plant. This assessment will include the estimation of greenhouse gas emission reductions. The findings will contribute to a comprehensive sustainability evaluation and facilitate decision-making that aligns with environmental conservation goals [11]. The following equations are related to CSP for optimum design and calculating the result [16].

Heat gain:

$$Qu = Fr.Aa \left[\frac{(S-Ar)}{Aa.Ul(Ti-Ta)} \right] \quad (1)$$

The temperature of a collector's output is given by:

$$To = Ti + \frac{Qu}{m.Cp} \quad (2)$$

The number of loops required is given by:

$$\text{No. of loops} = \frac{\left[\frac{P_{th}}{\text{Output power collector}} \right]}{\text{No. of collectors per loop}} \quad (3)$$

Solar Multiple (SM):

$$SM = \frac{\text{Power cycle capacity}}{\text{Field capacity}} \quad (4)$$

Solar Field Heat Output:

$$Q_{sf, des} = \frac{W_{pb, des}}{\eta_{des}} \times SM \quad (5)$$

Thermal losses:

$$Q_{hl} = Q_{hl, ref} \frac{I_{bn}}{I_{bn, des}} F_{hl}, I_{bn} F_{hl}, T_{amb} F_{hl}, V_{wind} \quad (6)$$

Thermal losses to irradiation:

$$F_{hl}, I_{bn} = C_0 + C_1 \left(\frac{I_{bn}}{I_{bn, des}} \right) + C_2 \left(\frac{I_{bn}}{I_{bn, des}} \right)^2 + C_3 \left(\frac{I_{bn}}{I_{bn, des}} \right)^3 \quad (7)$$

Power output:

$$\text{Output}_{Net} = \text{Output}_{Gross} \times CF \quad (8)$$

Integrated solar thermal electricity-producing efficiency:

$$\eta_{se} = \frac{\Delta We - \sum_{i=1}^n W_{sub, i}}{Q_{solar} + \sum_{i=1}^n Q_{add, i}} \quad (9)$$

where ΔWe is the improved power output after solar replacement, Q_{solar} is the thermal energy input into the feedwater heater, $\sum_{i=1}^n W_{sub, i}$ is the improved power consumption by some equipment after replacement, $\sum_{i=1}^n Q_{add, i}$ is the improved thermal energy load in the boiler after replacement, Fr stands for collector heat removal factor, Aa stands for concentrator aperture area, Ar stands for receiver area, S stands for absorbed solar radiation, Ul stands for heat loss coefficient, Ta stands for the ambient temperature, To is the outlet temperature (391°C), Ti is the inlet temperature (293°C in our case), m is the mass flow rate of the Heat Transfer Fluid-HTF (12 kg/s nominal), Cp is the specific heat capacity of the HTF, $Q_{sf, des}$ is the heat output from a solar field, $W_{pb, des}$ is the design work from a power block, η_{des} is the designed efficiency, $Q_{hl, ref}$ is the reference thermal loss from the solar field at design, I_{bn} is the solar irradiation during the current time step, $I_{bn, des}$ is the design-point solar irradiation from the solar resource at the design input, and CF is the projected gross to net conversion factor.

By employing this comprehensive methodology, the study aims to provide a robust analysis of the proposed hybrid power plant, offering valuable insights into its economic viability, environmental benefits, and potential for sustainable energy generation. The combination of quantitative analysis, SAM simulation, and MCDM evaluation ensures an objective and detailed examination of the hybrid system, contributing to the advancement of renewable energy solutions in Saudi Arabia and beyond.

L. Economics of the Project

The economic analysis of the proposed hybrid power plant integrating CSP with an existing fossil fuel-based thermal power plant in Ar'Ar involves a comprehensive evaluation of the project's costs and financial viability. Table I presents a detailed breakdown of the costs considered for the modeling, derived from a market survey and cross-referenced with NREL's authoritative reference technical report on cost modeling of parabolic trough plants utilizing the SAM [16]. The cost estimation specifically focuses on the solar field and thermal storage sections of the parabolic trough system, as the power generation section is assumed to be already established and thus is not included in the analysis. Only operational costs are factored in, providing an accurate assessment of the economic aspects of the hybrid system. The core variables governing the project's economics are the Nominal Discount Rate (NDR), which is fixed at 8.14% and the presumed inflation rate, set at 2.5%. The project's anticipated lifetime is assumed to be 25 years, during which the financial performance and return on investment will be analyzed. These parameters play a crucial role in determining the LCOE and NPV of the hybrid power plant.

TABLE I. COST PARAMETERS OF A PARABOLIC TROUGH POWER PLANT

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
IRR	11%	DSCR	1.3
Target Year _{IRR}	20	Annual Interest Rate	7%
Price Escalation _{PPA}	1%/year	Solar Field	150
Analysis Period	25 years	HTF System	\$60/m ²
Inflation Rate	2.5%/year	Storage	\$65/kWe
NDR	8.14%/year	Others	\$120/kWe
Federal Income Tax	25%/year	Power Plant	\$50/kWe
Sales Tax	5%	Fuel	Variable

III. SITE SELECTION

Ar'Ar City has been meticulously chosen as the site for the proposed hybrid power plant. The decision to select Ar'Ar City is founded on a thorough geospatial analysis and site assessment, encompassing various factors that contribute to the location's suitability for the hybrid system.

A. Key Factors Influencing Site Selection

The existence of the Arar Gas Turbine Power Plant, a 470.2 MW thermal power project situated in Northern Borders, Saudi Arabia, played a pivotal role in the site selection process [31]. This power plant currently operates with oil as fuel and has been in commercial operation since 1985. It produces 519 Kg/MWh of CO₂ with a total of 212,657,000 kg [32]. Notably, the government's recent tender for the expansion of four units (25-30 MW each) at the power plant presents a unique opportunity to analyze the feasibility of integrating CSP technology into the existing infrastructure. This strategic alignment with the expansion project offers potential synergies and cost-effectiveness, making Ar'Ar an ideal location for the proposed hybrid power plant.

1) Grid Connectivity and Infrastructure

Ar'Ar has a well-established grid network, enabling efficient electricity transmission and distribution. The robust grid connectivity facilitates the seamless addition of the hybrid system to the existing infrastructure. This enhances the economic viability of the project and ensures a reliable electricity supply to the region.

2) Geographical and Climatic Factors

Geographically, Ar'Ar is positioned in the northern part of Saudi Arabia and serves as the capital of the Northern Border Province. Its strategic location near the border with Iraq and Jordan positions the city as a significant economic and transportation hub in the region. Ar'Ar has a desert climate common to the area, which is marked by hot summers and mild winters. The region receives abundant sunlight, with the average solar irradiance ranging from 4.5 to 7.6 kWh, making it well-suited for harnessing solar energy through CSP technology. Additionally, the city experiences moderate wind speeds of 7.3 to 9.4 miles per hour throughout the year, adding to its renewable energy potential.

3) Economic Landscape

Ar'Ar plays a vital role in agricultural activities, with crops like wheat, barley, and dates cultivated in the region. The city's agricultural sector also includes livestock farming. Industries

such as food processing, cement production, and construction contribute significantly to Ar'Ar's economic growth and development. These industries present promising opportunities for integrating renewable energy sources, including biomass for heat and power generation, further enhancing the city's overall sustainability.

4) Environmental Considerations

The site selection process considered environmental factors to minimize the project's impact on the local ecosystem and surroundings. Ar'Ar's potential for incorporating renewable energy solutions aligns with sustainability objectives, ensuring a balance between development needs and environmental conservation.

B. Energy Source Assessment

Energy source assessment is crucial for evaluating the renewable energy potential of the selected site. The primary focus is on solar power as the main renewable energy source for the proposed Hybrid Energy System (HES). To gather comprehensive data on solar and wind resources, the study relies on the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) database, a reputable source providing reliable meteorological information. Utilizing the NASA database, historical and real-time data on solar radiation levels and wind speed at Ar'Ar's geographical coordinates are obtained. These data are essential for accurately assessing the availability and variability of solar and wind sources throughout the year. It forms the basis for estimating the energy generation potential of CSP and wind turbines, the key components of the HES. By incorporating real-world data, we can conduct realistic simulations and in-depth analysis of the hybrid system's performance, considering the actual renewable energy potential at the site.

The simulation software used in this study (SAM), calculates the solar output using the global horizontal irradiance, which accounts for direct irradiance, diffused light, and reflected light. The solar radiation data collected from NASA's surface meteorology website were integrated into SAM, taking into account the location's coordinates. The study considers the average solar energy over 22 years to analyze seasonal variations in solar radiation and compute the global radiation incidence on the CSP [16]. The investigation shows that Ar'Ar witnessed a period of increased sunshine spanning over 3.5 months, starting on May 8 and ending on August 23. During this duration, the average irradiance remained above 7.6 kWh, particularly in June with an average daily solar radiation of 8.6 kWh. In winter, from November 3 to February 6, the average solar irradiance falls below 4.5 kWh. Notably, December emerges as the least radiant month, registering an average daily solar radiation of 3.5 kWh. The length of the day in Ar'Ar shows significant variation throughout the year. The shortest day is December 22 with a duration of about 10 hours, while the longest day is June 21 with about 14 hours of daylight. Additionally, on June 21 the earliest sunrise takes place (5:11 AM), whereas the latest sunrise occurs on January 9 (7:14 AM). Similarly, the earliest sunset occurs on December 3 (5:13 PM) and the latest sunset on July 1, 7:23 PM. Regarding the city's climate, Ar'Ar experiences a hot season starting on May 26 and ending on September 25. The average

temperature during that period is above 36 °C. July emerges as the hottest month (26-41 °C). Conversely, the cool season starts on November 25 and ends on March 2. The average temperature is normally below 20 °C. January is the coldest month (4 – 15 °C).

IV. CSP SYSTEM DESIGN

The selection of the parabolic trough model, SkyFuel Sky Trough, was made after a thorough evaluation of various CSP technologies. NREL's certification of this model as the most efficient technology in its category at a temperature of 350 °C makes it a compelling choice for the proposed hybrid energy system in Ar'Ar. Its high thermal efficiency of 73% ensures that a significant amount of solar energy is effectively captured and converted into usable heat. The absorber is a crucial component of the parabolic trough system, responsible for absorbing sunlight and converting it into thermal energy. Schott PTR80 was chosen as the absorber due to its superior performance and reliability. Its design allows for optimal absorption of solar radiation, maximizing the thermal output of the system. The specific properties of the PTR80 were carefully considered to ensure compatibility with the operating conditions of the CSP system.

One of the critical aspects of a CSP system is the HTF used to carry and transfer the captured thermal energy to the power generation unit. For this purpose, the HITEC solar salt was selected due to its exceptional characteristics that align with the system's requirements. The HITEC solar salt exhibits high specific heat (1.56 kJ/kg×C), allowing it to store and carry significant amounts of heat efficiently. Its low viscosity ensures smooth flow through the piping system, reducing energy losses during circulation. Moreover, the HITEC solar salt remains stable and chemically inert even under prolonged exposure to high temperatures, ensuring the longevity and reliability of the system. Table II provides detailed information about the collector, receiver, and HTF used in the parabolic CSP. The dimensions of the collector, including its aperture and assembly length, play a vital role in determining the amount of solar radiation captured and the overall performance of the system. Likewise, the receiver's design characteristics, such as the absorber tube's inner and outer diameter and total receiver losses, directly impact the efficiency of heat absorption and transfer.

TABLE II. CSP COMPONENT DETAILS

HTF	HITEC solar salt	Collector	SkyFuel Sky Trough
Single Loop Flow _{Max}	1 kg/sec	Reflective Aperture	656 m ²
Single Loop Flow _{Max}	12 kg/sec	Aperture Width	6 m
Field Flow Velocity _{Min}	0.268562 m/s	Assembly Collector Length	115 m
Field Flow Velocity _{Max}	3.74479 m/s	Water/wash	0.8 L/m ²
Receiver	Schott PTR80	Total Receiver Losses	211.35 W/m
Absorber Diameter _{Inner}	0.076 m	Washes/year	64
Absorber Diameter _{Outer}	0.08 m		

To analyze the potential impact of the CSP, various solar thermal capacities, ranging from 10 to 50 MW, were evaluated. This allows for a comprehensive analysis of the system's behavior and performance under different capacities, enabling more accurate predictions for larger-scale implementations. Table III presents the design of the different CSP capacities, revealing the relationship between the system capacity and key design parameters.

TABLE III. DESIGN OF DIFFERENT CSP CAPACITIES

Parameter	Values				
	10 MW	20 MW	30 MW	40 MW	50 MW
Capacity	10 MW	20 MW	30 MW	40 MW	50 MW
Actual No. of loops	17	33	49	65	82
Single loop aperture	5248 m ²	5248 m ²	5248 m ²	5248 m ²	5248 m ²
Reflective of total aperture area	89216 m ²	173184 m ²	257152 m ²	341120 m ²	430336 m ²
Field thermal output	56.1798 MWt	112.36 MWt	168.539 MWt	224.719 MWt	280.899 MWt
Total land area	77 Acres	150 Acres	222 Acres	295 Acres	372 Acres

The study considered 5 different capacity solar thermal systems, from 10 to 50 MW. As the capacity of the system increased, the number of loops required to achieve the desired thermal output also increased. For the 10 MW system, 17 loops were needed, while the 50 MW system required 82 loops. This relationship indicates that larger capacity systems demand a greater number of loops to efficiently capture and concentrate solar energy. As the system's capacity increased, the single loop aperture remained constant at 5248 m² for all capacity levels. However, the total aperture area, which represents the cumulative surface area of all loops in the system, increased significantly with higher capacity. For the 10 MW system, the total aperture area was 89,216 m², whereas for the 50 MW system, it expanded to 430,336 m². The total land area needed for the parabolic trough collectors and related infrastructure also increased. The 10 MW system demanded 77 acres of land, while the 50 MW system required a significantly larger land area of 372 acres. As expected, the thermal output increased proportionally with the system's capacity. The 10 MW system achieved a field thermal output of 56.1798 MWt, while the 50 MW system exhibited a substantial increase in thermal output, reaching 280.899 MWt. Furthermore, addressing the intermittency of solar energy availability is vital for ensuring a stable power supply. Hence, the study considers different thermal storage systems to store the excess thermal energy during sunny periods, which can then be utilized during peak load hours when solar energy may be limited. Table IV outlines the details of the different thermal storage systems analyzed in the study, including their storage volumes, thermal capacities, and estimated heat losses.

The increase in storage volume with higher system capacity can be attributed to the larger size and capacity of the thermal storage tanks. As the capacity of the hybrid energy system

increases from 10 to 50 MW, the number of thermal storage tanks and their dimensions scaled up accordingly. This allows for a greater volume of thermal energy storage, enabling the system to store more energy during periods of high solar irradiation. The rise in thermal capacity as the system capacity increases is a direct consequence of the larger size and number of thermal storage tanks in the system. With higher capacity systems, more thermal energy can be stored in the thermal storage tanks, resulting in increased thermal capacity. This enhanced thermal capacity ensures that the hybrid energy system can cater to the energy demands of Ar'Ar for longer durations, especially during peak load hours when solar energy generation may be insufficient. The relatively low estimated heat losses can be attributed to the careful selection of high-quality materials and design considerations in the thermal storage system. The use of advanced insulating materials and robust construction techniques minimizes heat losses from the thermal storage tanks.

higher CSP capacity leads to higher thermal capacity, allowing the hybrid energy system to store and supply more thermal energy to meet the city's energy demands.

Fig. 1. Thermal capacity of the different storage systems.

TABLE IV. THERMAL STORAGE SYSTEM DETAILS

Full load hour of thermal storage	TES (0 hr)	TES (4 hr)	TES (6 hr)	TES (8 hr)
Storage Volume				
10MW	0 m ³	2196.5 m ³	3294.75 m ³	4392.99 m ³
20MW	0 m ³	4392.99 m ³	6589.49 m ³	8785.99 m ³
30MW	0 m ³	6589.49 m ³	9884.24 m ³	13179 m ³
40MW	0 m ³	8785.99 m ³	13179 m ³	17572 m ³
50MW	0 m ³	10982.5 m ³	16473.7 m ³	21965 m ³
Thermal Capacity				
10MW	0 MWh _t	112.36 MWh _t	168.539 MWh _t	224.719 MWh _t
20MW	0 MWh _t	224.719 MWh _t	337.079 MWh _t	449.438 MWh _t
30MW	0 MWh _t	337.079 MWh _t	505.618 MWh _t	674.157 MWh _t
40MW	0 MWh _t	449.438 MWh _t	674.157 MWh _t	898.876 MWh _t
50MW	0 MWh _t	561.798 MWh _t	842.697 MWh _t	1123.6 MWh _t
Estimated heat loss				
10MW	0 MW _t	0.098 MW _t	0.127 MW _t	0.152 MW _t
20MW	0 MW _t	0.152 MW _t	0.199 MW _t	0.243 MW _t
30MW	0 MW _t	0.199 MW _t	0.264 MW _t	0.324 MW _t
40MW	0 MW _t	0.243 MW _t	0.324 MW _t	0.399 MW _t
50MW	0 MW _t	0.284 MW _t	0.379 MW _t	0.471 MW _t

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Thermal Output

The results presented in Figure 1 show the thermal capacity of the different thermal storage systems for varying CSP capacities. The thermal capacity increases as the CSP capacity and thermal storage volume increase, demonstrating the potential benefits of increasing both parameters in the proposed hybrid energy system. As the CSP capacity increases from 10 MW to 50 MW, the thermal capacity of the system also increases significantly. This outcome is expected since a higher CSP capacity implies a larger solar energy generation capacity. With more solar energy being collected through the parabolic trough collectors, there is a greater amount of thermal energy available for storage in the thermal storage system. Therefore,

The thermal storage volume is another crucial factor influencing the thermal capacity of the system. By increasing the thermal storage volume, the system's capacity to act as a backup energy source also increases. This is particularly important for scenarios where solar energy generation is insufficient, such as during periods of low solar radiation or peak energy demand. A larger thermal storage volume enables the system to store surplus thermal energy during periods of high solar radiation and use it when solar energy generation is limited or unavailable. The results also demonstrate the significance of the full load hours of thermal storage TES (4 hr), TES (6 hr), and TES (8 hr) on the thermal capacity of the system. Longer full load hours correspond to higher thermal capacity values. For instance, with a 50 MW CSP capacity and the TES (8 hr) scenario, the thermal capacity reaches 1110 MWh_t, which is significantly higher than the thermal capacity of 500 MWh_t for TES (4 hr). This indicates that systems with longer full load hours can provide sustained and stable power generation during peak load periods or when the solar energy generation is low. The observed increase in thermal capacity with higher CSP capacity and thermal storage volume has practical implications for the proposed hybrid energy system in Ar'Ar. With a greater thermal capacity, the system becomes more reliable and capable of delivering a continuous power supply to the city, even during adverse weather conditions or fluctuations in solar energy availability. This enhanced energy reliability contributes to the overall stability and resilience of the city's power supply, reducing dependency on fossil fuel-based power generation and promoting sustainable and eco-friendly energy solutions.

The results presented in Figure 2 show the thermal losses in the different thermal storage systems with varying backup times and CSP capacities. As the backup time increases, the system stores the surplus thermal energy for longer periods without being utilized. This extended storage duration results in increased thermal losses due to various heat transfer mechanisms, such as thermal conduction, convection, and radiation. Longer backup times lead to higher losses, as indicated in Figure 2. While longer backup times enhance the system's ability to provide sustained power during periods of

low solar energy generation, it also means that more thermal energy is exposed to potential losses. The CSP capacity is another critical factor affecting thermal losses in the system. As the capacity increases, the storage volume will also increase. This means more thermal energy is available for storage, but it also translates to a larger surface area of the storage medium exposed to the surrounding environment. A larger storage volume means more surface area for heat exchange, which contributes to higher thermal losses. This is evident in the results presented in Figure 8, where increasing the storage volume results in higher thermal losses for all backup times and CSP capacities.

Fig. 2. Thermal losses in the storage systems.

To minimize thermal losses, strategies such as improving the insulation and thermal properties of the storage medium can be implemented. Using advanced thermal insulation materials and well-designed storage containers can reduce the heat transfer to the surroundings. Additionally, optimizing the operation and control of the thermal storage system can ensure that stored thermal energy is utilized efficiently without unnecessary losses.

B. Electrical Output

The capacity factor of the hybrid system, as shown in Figure 3, is a critical performance metric that indicates the efficiency and utilization of the system's installed capacity. The capacity factor is calculated as the ratio of the actual energy output (in MWh) to the maximum possible output if the system was operating at its rated capacity continuously throughout the year. The capacity factor of the solar thermal parabolic trough systems without thermal energy storage (TES (0 hr)) is approximately 31-32% due to the limited availability of sunlight during the day cycle. Solar energy can be harnessed effectively only during periods of sufficient irradiance, which is typically around 7 hours per day. Therefore, the system operates at its full capacity only for this limited duration, resulting in a relatively lower capacity factor. Incorporating TES systems significantly impacts the capacity factor of the hybrid system. With the addition of thermal energy storage, the plant can store the excess thermal heat produced during periods of high solar irradiance and utilize it when the sun is not available, extending the operation time of the plant beyond the sunlight hours.

Fig. 3. Capacity factor of the different parabolic trough systems.

As shown in Figure 3, increasing the CSP capacity has little impact on the capacity factor but with the introduction of TES systems (TES (4 hr), TES (6 hr), and TES (8 hr)), the capacity factor of the hybrid system increases. The more extensive the thermal storage capacity (higher backup times), the more the plant can operate and generate power beyond the available sunlight hours. The thermal storage capability allows the system to operate at or near its full capacity even after the sun has set or during periods of low solar irradiance. This ability to provide electricity continuously, despite fluctuations in solar availability, leads to higher capacity factors. Therefore, increasing the thermal storage capacity can significantly improve the system's capacity factor, ultimately enhancing its overall performance and economic viability.

The yearly electrical output of the different parabolic trough capacities, as presented in Figure 4, provides valuable insights into the performance of the hybrid system under varying CSP capacities and TES durations. As expected, the electrical power output of the hybrid system increases with the CSP capacity. Larger capacity systems, such as the 40 MW and 50 MW configurations, capture more heat from the field, resulting in higher power generation. This relationship is due to the higher number of loops and larger apertures, which allow for more efficient heat collection and conversion into electricity.

Fig. 4. Electrical output from the different capacities.

The presence of TES in the hybrid system enhances its performance by allowing the stored thermal energy to be utilized during periods of low solar irradiance or after sunset. However, the influence of thermal storage on the power output

varies with the CSP capacity. For lower-capacity systems, such as the 10 MW configuration, increasing the thermal storage backup time has a limited effect on power output, because the overall energy captured from the field is relatively lower, and the system may already be operating close to its maximum capacity without significant excess heat for storage. As a result, the additional thermal energy stored has a minimal impact on overall power generation. In contrast, for larger capacity systems (40 MW and 50 MW), increasing the thermal storage backup time results in a substantial rise in power output. These larger systems have higher energy capture capabilities, and the additional thermal energy stored allows for continuous power generation even during extended periods of low solar irradiance. The performance of the system becomes saturated after a certain thermal storage backup time. For example, with the 40 MW and 50 MW systems, the power output reaches its peak at a 6-hour thermal storage backup, and further increasing the backup time has a diminishing impact on power output. This suggests that the system's design and operational parameters should be optimized to achieve the best balance between thermal storage and power generation. In this study, this has been done through the MCDM technique.

C. Economic Analysis

The net present cost analysis of the parabolic trough system, as presented in Figure 5, provides valuable insights into the economic implications of varying system capacities and the incorporation of thermal storage. The findings show that as the capacity of the CSP increases, there is a corresponding rise in the net present cost. This relationship can be attributed to several factors including land area, more components, and size. Larger capacity systems require more land to accommodate a higher number of loops and a larger aperture area. Acquiring and preparing larger land areas contribute to the overall capital cost of the system. Higher capacity systems necessitate more components, such as mirrors, absorber tubes, and support structures, resulting in higher manufacturing and installation costs. With increased capacity, the physical size of the parabolic trough system also grows, leading to higher material and construction expenses.

Fig. 5. Net capital cost of the CSP.

The incorporation of TES into the parabolic trough system introduces additional costs. This is primarily due to the need for storage tanks, additional molten salt, and heaters to store and maintain thermal energy for extended periods. As the

thermal storage backup time increases, more storage volume and salt are required, resulting in further cost increments. The 10 MW system exhibits the lowest net present cost, primarily because it requires less land, and fewer components, and has a smaller physical footprint than the higher capacity systems. Conversely, the 50 MW system shows the highest net present cost due to its larger size and increased material requirements. The cost difference between the 10 MW and 50 MW systems can be substantial, highlighting the economic advantages of considering lower capacity configurations for smaller-scale applications.

The results indicate that the net present cost increases as the thermal storage backup time increases. While thermal storage enhances the system's performance and enables continuous power generation, it comes with additional capital expenses. It is crucial to evaluate the trade-offs between increased capital costs and improved power generation reliability when deciding on the optimal thermal storage duration. For project developers and stakeholders, finding the optimal balance between capacity and thermal storage is essential to achieve cost-effective system designs. In this study, this has been done through the MCDM.

The cost of electricity generated by the parabolic trough system, as presented in Figure 6, provides valuable insights into the economic feasibility and efficiency of the system at different capacity levels and with varying thermal energy storage durations. At the outset, the cost of electricity production ranges from 14.5 to 15.5 cents per kilowatt-hour (¢/kWh). This cost reflects the initial capital investments, operational expenses, and solar thermal capacity of the parabolic trough system. As expected, larger capacity systems generally have lower costs of electricity generation compared to smaller systems due to economies of scale. This is a significant advantage of larger capacity systems, as they can harness more solar energy, resulting in a higher thermal output. The decrease in cost can be attributed to the spreading of the fixed capital and operational costs over a larger energy generation capacity, leading to a reduced cost per unit of the produced electricity. However, even the initial costs of electricity production are competitive with conventional power sources, making the parabolic trough system a viable renewable energy option.

Fig. 6. Cost of electricity produced by the CSP.

The addition of 4-hour thermal storage to the system results in a cost reduction of approximately 2 ¢/kWh. TES allows the system to save the excess thermal energy during peak sunlight time and utilize it during times of lower solar irradiance or after sunset. This enables a more consistent and reliable electricity output, reducing the reliance on immediate solar availability and, consequently, the cost of electricity production. However, the results show that further increase in thermal storage beyond 4 hours leads to an increase in the cost of electricity. This phenomenon can be attributed to diminishing returns on investment. While longer thermal storage durations provide more backup energy, the additional capital and operational costs associated with larger storage volumes and extended thermal storage times may outweigh the benefits. The competitive cost of electricity production from the parabolic trough system, particularly at larger capacity levels with the 4-hour thermal storage, positions it as a promising contender in the energy market. As the cost of conventional fossil-fuel-based electricity generation continues to rise and environmental concerns drive the demand for sustainable energy alternatives, the parabolic trough system's cost-effectiveness can attract investors and utilities seeking cleaner and economically viable energy solutions.

D. MCDM Selection

The performance of the CSP systems with varying TES configurations exhibited diverse outcomes. As the TES capacity increased, there was a notable improvement in both thermal and electrical outputs, which are advantageous as they allow for higher energy capture and utilization. However, it was also observed that increasing the TES capacity led to higher losses in the system, as energy was stored for longer periods without being fully utilized. These losses arise from thermal conduction, convection, and radiation during the storage process. Additionally, the incorporation of TES resulted in higher Net Present Cost (NPC) and Cost of Electricity (COE) due to the need for additional storage tanks, molten salt, and heaters, which incur additional capital and operational expenses. To strike an optimal balance between the benefits and drawbacks of different TES capacities, the MCDM method was employed (Pohekar & Ramachandran, 2004). MCDM is a powerful decision-making technique that evaluates multiple solutions based on various predefined criteria and considerations. It allows for a comprehensive and systematic evaluation of renewable energy systems, considering both qualitative and quantitative aspects. In the context of the CSP system, MCDM considered factors such as thermal and electrical outputs, losses, NPC, and COE, among others. The identified MCDM criteria are shown in Table V.

TABLE V. SELECTED CRITERIA FOR MCDM

Criteria	Sub-Criteria		Unit
Thermal	Thermal Capacity	C1	MWh
	Thermal Losses	C2	MWh
Electrical	Capacity Factor	C3	%
	Output Power	C4	MWh
Economical	NPC	C5	\$
	COE	C6	¢/kWh

The AHP-SAW combination [13] was used in the MCDM technique applied in this study. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was used to assign appropriate weights to each criterion [22]. This step was crucial to ensure that the decision-making process accurately captured the significance of each criterion in the context of the CSP system's performance. Data analysis and evaluation were carried out using the Simple Additive Weightage (SAW) method [7]. The SAW method calculates the weighted sum of performance evaluations for each alternative across all attributes. The SAW utilizes predefined values and preference weights, leading to more precise selection. By employing a comparison decision matrix, direct comparisons between each criterion and its counterpart were made, facilitating the identification of the most influential criteria. The pairwise comparison matrix utilized a scale from 1 to 9, representing the relative importance of each criterion in relation to others. The square matrix $A = m \times m$ (where m represents the number of criteria) was used to create the pairwise comparison matrix. The entry value in the comparison matrix, a_{ij} , indicates the comparison value between the i th (row) criterion and the j th (column) criterion. The values of the comparison matrix are provided for all criteria, as shown in Table VI, and were formulated through (11) to enable direct evaluations between each criterion and its corresponding counterpart. These values were derived after carrying out a literature review of MCDM being applied to solar energy. Through this analysis, the relative importance of each criterion was identified, and corresponding numerical values were assigned.

$$A = (a_{ij}) \tag{11}$$

$$a_{ij} = \frac{1}{a_{ji}} \text{ if } i \neq j, \quad \text{else if } i = j, a_{ij} = 1$$

TABLE VI. PAIRWISE VALUES OF THE COMPARISON MATRIX.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1	0.25	2	2	2	2
C2	4	1	3	2	2	6
C3	0.5	0.33	1	0.5	2	2
C4	0.5	0.5	2	1	2	3
C5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1	3
C6	0.5	0.17	0.5	0.33	0.33	1
SUM	8.65	3.82	10.25	7.35	10.42	19.02

TABLE VII. NORMALIZED PAIRWISE MATRIX

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	0.116	0.065	0.195	0.272	0.192	0.105
C2	0.462	0.262	0.293	0.272	0.192	0.315
C3	0.058	0.086	0.098	0.068	0.192	0.105
C4	0.058	0.131	0.195	0.136	0.192	0.158
C5	0.058	0.131	0.049	0.068	0.096	0.158
C6	0.058	0.045	0.049	0.045	0.032	0.053

In the next step, it is necessary to normalize each value in the pairwise comparison matrix by dividing it by the sum of the values within the corresponding column. This normalization process ensures the creation of a normalized pairwise comparison matrix. The value of the normalized matrix is calculated by:

$$a_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sum_{l=1}^m a_{il}} \tag{12}$$

To obtain the overall weight vector, the final step involves averaging each row of the matrix presented in Table VIII. This averaging process is carried out by:

$$w_i = \sum_{l=1}^m a_{il} \tag{13}$$

TABLE VIII. OVERALL WEIGHT OF EACH CRITERION

C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
0.159	0.146	0.149	0.184	0.153	0.208

The resulting priority vector was verified using the consistency verification process to validate the reliability of the decision-making matrix. The Consistency Ratio (CR) obtained, which was below 10% (8.8%), demonstrated the credibility and accuracy of the priority vector, thus ensuring the robustness of the MCDM analysis.

The multi-criteria utility function (U) played a vital role in evaluating the alternative TES configurations. By consolidating diverse criteria into a single utility value, the utility function enabled effective comparison and ranking of the options. The utility function assigned weights to each criterion based on their relative importance, as determined by the AHP technique. Through the application of the utility function, the performance of each alternative across different criteria was transformed into a single utility value, facilitating comprehensive and well-informed comparisons. The calculation of the multi-criteria utility function, incorporating the weights of all the criteria, is provided in (14):

$$U = 0.159 \times [C1] + 0.146 \times [C2] + 0.149 \times [C3] + 0.184 \times [C4] + 0.153 \times [C5] + 0.208 \times [C6] \tag{14}$$

First, the MCDM was applied to the 10 MW system. The final step of score and rank is calculated by ranking the alternatives from the sum of decision matrix multiplication by weights using (14). The application of MCD on all the CSP capacity systems provided valuable insights into the optimal TES configuration. Table IX illustrates the rankings obtained, where the 4-hour TES system consistently ranked 1st among the CSP capacities, indicating that this system configuration is most aligned with the identified criteria and is well-suited for addressing the technical and economic aspects of the project. Following closely in second place is the 6-hour TES configuration, whereas the 0-hour configuration obtained the lowest score.

TABLE IX. MCDM RANKING OF THE CSP SYSTEMS

System	Rank				
	10MW	20MW	30MW	40MW	50MW
0hrs	4	4	4	4	4
4hrs	1	1	1	1	1
6hrs	2	2	2	3	3
8hrs	3	3	3	2	2

The primary reason for the 4-hour TES system consistently ranking 1st is its significantly lower COE compared to the other TES configurations. The COE is a critical metric in evaluating the economic viability and competitiveness of renewable energy systems. With a 4-hour TES system, the CSP

plant benefits from efficient energy storage, enabling it to generate and deliver electricity at a lower cost. As a result, the cost of electricity production is minimized, making the CSP plant more economically feasible and attractive to investors and consumers. Additionally, another contributing factor to the preference for the 4-hour TES system is that the output power achieves saturation beyond the 4-hour storage duration. Beyond this point, increasing the TES capacity does not yield a proportional increase in output power. The system reaches a point of diminishing returns, where the benefits of additional thermal storage capacity are outweighed by the increased costs and losses associated with larger storage volumes. As TES capacity increased beyond 4 hours, the NPC of the CSP system also increases significantly. The NPC considers the total capital costs and operational expenses over the lifetime of the system, discounted to their present value. Larger TES systems require more storage tanks, additional molten salt, and heaters, leading to higher initial investment and maintenance costs. This affects the overall economic feasibility of the CSP plant, as higher NPC values translate to higher electricity tariffs. Furthermore, increasing the TES capacity also leads to higher thermal losses. As the energy is stored for longer periods without being utilized, there is an increased risk of heat losses due to thermal conduction, convection, and radiation. These losses reduce the overall efficiency of the CSP system and result in a decrease in the amount of electricity that can be generated from the captured heat.

E. Fossil Fuel Compensation by CSP with 4-Hour TES

Figure 7 presents the field thermal output of the various parabolic trough capacities with the 4-hour TES, and a clear trend emerges as the system's capacity increases. The field thermal output rises rapidly with higher system capacities. This is because as the capacity of the CSP system increases, more parabolic trough loops are added to the design, which directly impacts the total reflective aperture area. The larger the aperture area, the more sun light can be captured and used as thermal energy. This phenomenon leads to a significant boost in the field thermal output. Notably, the 40 MW (250 MWt) and 50 MW (280 MWt) systems demonstrate impressive thermal energy generation, producing over 200 MWt of thermal energy when equipped with a 4-hour TES system. This is a substantial amount of thermal energy, and it has practical implications in the context of hybrid systems that include fossil-fuel burners. In contrast, the 10 MW system, while still a significant renewable energy source, produces a lower field thermal output of 60 MWt due to the smaller aperture area and fewer parabolic trough loops in the system. While it may be suitable for specific applications, it might not provide enough thermal energy to sustain a hybrid system continuously without additional backup sources.

The results presented in Figure 8 highlight the significant advantages of integrating solar thermal energy as a heat source to the power plant's boiler in the hybrid system. By doing so, the consumption of hydro carbon fuels in the power generation process can be substantially reduced. One key observation from the data is that as the capacity of the parabolic trough system increases, the amount of heat input to the boiler also increases. This, in turn, results in a proportional reduction in the

consumption of fossil fuels. The reason behind this trend lies in the fact that larger capacity parabolic trough systems capture and convert more solar energy into thermal energy. Consequently, a greater amount of thermal energy is supplied to the hybrid system, thereby reducing the reliance on fossil fuels to meet the required heat input in the boiler.

Fig. 7. Field thermal output with a 4-hour TES system.

For instance, the 10 MW CSP with 4 hours of TES enables the saving of approximately 18.84 tons of coal per hour. As the capacity of the parabolic trough system is increased to 50 MW, the coal savings rise to an impressive 96 tons per hour, demonstrating that the larger the capacity of the parabolic trough system, the higher the reduction in coal consumption, resulting in significant cost savings and environmental benefits. Similarly, the hybrid system's integration with solar thermal energy also leads to substantial savings in oil and gas consumption. As the capacity of the parabolic trough system increases, the amount of oil and gas saved per hour increases proportionally. For example, the 50 MW parabolic trough system with 4 hours of TES can save approximately 48 barrels of oil and 400,000 ft³ of gas per hour. These results have profound implications for the energy industry and the transition towards cleaner and more sustainable energy sources. By incorporating solar thermal energy into the hybrid system, the dependence on fossil fuels is significantly reduced, leading to a more environmentally friendly power generation process. The reduction in hydro carbon fuel consumption not only helps decrease CO₂ emissions and combat climate change, but also offers economic advantages through cost savings.

The data presented in Figure 9 highlight the substantial cost savings achieved by implementing the solar thermal parabolic trough system in the hybrid power plant. As the capacity of the parabolic trough system increases, the cost savings from reducing fossil fuel consumption also increase, demonstrating the economic viability and benefits of larger-scale renewable energy integration. One key factor influencing the cost savings is the type of fuel used in the power generation process. The data indicate that oil is the most expensive fuel, followed by coal and gas, with gas being the cheapest. Consequently, the largest savings are done by decreasing oil consumption, while the least savings are done by decreasing gas consumption.

Fig. 8. Reduction in fuel consumption with the 4-hour TES system.

Fig. 9. Fossil fuel cost saving with the 4-hour TES system.

For instance, the 10 MW CSP with the 4-hour TES achieves cost savings of approximately 1130.4 \$/hour from reduced coal consumption, 1318.8 \$/hour from reduced oil consumption, and 785 \$/hour from reduced gas consumption. As the capacity of the parabolic trough system increases to 50 MW, the cost savings rise significantly to 5760.00 \$/hour from reduced coal consumption, 6720 \$/hour from reduced oil consumption, and 4000 \$/hour from reduced gas consumption.

These findings underscore the economic advantages of incorporating solar thermal energy into the hybrid power plant. By displacing costly fossil fuels with renewable energy, the overall operating costs of the power plant are significantly reduced. This translates to lower electricity production costs and, in turn, benefits consumers by potentially lowering electricity prices.

The results presented in Figure 10 demonstrate the significant environmental benefits of integrating CSP into the hybrid system. Fossil fuel consumption, is a major source of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, which contributes to climate change and environmental degradation. By utilizing solar thermal energy as a clean and renewable alternative, the system can effectively reduce its reliance on fossil fuels and subsequently decrease CO₂ emissions, mitigating the negative impact on the environment. As the capacity of the parabolic trough system increases, the reduction in CO₂ emissions becomes more pronounced, indicating the potential for larger-scale renewable energy integration to make a more substantial contribution to climate change mitigation. The reduction in CO₂ emissions is most significant for coal consumption, as coal has the highest carbon content among the three fossil fuels considered. For instance, the 10 MW CSP with 4-hour TES reduces CO₂ emissions by approximately 18,340.112 kg/hour from coal consumption, 14,004.4 kg/hour from oil consumption, and 6,990.896 kg/hour from gas consumption. As the capacity of the parabolic trough system increases to 50 MW, the reduction in CO₂ emissions rises significantly to 93,452.8 kg/hour from coal consumption, 71,360 kg/hour from oil consumption, and 35,622.4 kg/hour from gas consumption. It is worth noting that these reductions in CO₂ emissions have substantial environmental implications. By decreasing the emission of CO₂, solar thermal integration helps combat climate change and contributes to the global effort to limit temperature rise and its associated adverse effects.

Fig. 10. Reduction in CO₂ emissions with the 4-hour TES system.

Figure 11 provides valuable insights into the financial performance of the parabolic trough system with the 4-hour TES over its operational lifetime. The graph showcases the payback period, the point at which the initial investment in the system is recovered, and the subsequent revenue generation over time. It is a critical metric that assesses the duration it takes for the system's cumulative revenue to equal the initial investment cost. As shown in the graph, the payback period for the CSP is approximately 12 years. This means that after 12

years of operation, the system has generated enough revenue to cover the initial capital expenditure, and from that point forward, it begins to generate net positive revenue.

Fig. 11. Revenue created by the systems with 4-hour TES.

The size of the parabolic trough system plays a vital role in determining its revenue generation. Larger systems with higher capacities have a greater electric power output, which translates to higher revenue potential. As depicted in the graph, the 50 MW system, being the largest in capacity, generates significantly more revenue compared to the 10 MW system. The 10 MW system reaches a revenue of approximately \$120 million by the end of the 12-year payback period. Over the entire project life, the revenue for the 10 MW system rises to \$210 million. In contrast, the 50 MW system, with its greater electric power output, achieves a revenue of approximately \$325 million during the 12-year payback period. Over the entire project life, the revenue for the 50 MW system rises to the impressive \$545 million. This substantial revenue generation demonstrates the financial viability of larger capacity parabolic trough systems and their ability to deliver long-term economic benefits. The revenue generation for the parabolic trough system after the payback period is particularly significant as it contributes to the overall profitability and financial sustainability of the project. As the revenue generation continues to exceed operational costs, the system generates positive cash flow, allowing for potential reinvestment, debt reduction, or shareholder returns. The revenue generation is directly linked to the system's electric power output and its ability to supply energy to the grid or end-users. Therefore, ensuring the optimal performance and efficiency of the parabolic trough system is essential to maximize revenue generation throughout its operational life.

Figure 12 provides crucial insights into the long-term performance of the parabolic trough systems, considering the inevitable impact of environmental factors on their efficiency and effectiveness. As parabolic troughs are continuously exposed to various environmental elements, wear and tear occur over time, leading to degradation in their overall performance. The environmental factors that contribute to the degradation of the system's performance include humidity, UV radiation, loss of reflector shine, reduction of absorber's absorption capacity, loss of HTF storage capability, rust formation, and pollution. Each of these factors can have a cumulative effect on the system's components, potentially leading to diminished energy capture and conversion efficiency.

As shown in the results, all parabolic trough systems, regardless of their capacity, experience a decline in performance over time. This degradation is a natural consequence of the prolonged exposure to harsh environmental conditions. However, the effect is more pronounced in larger systems compared to smaller ones. The larger systems have a higher number of components and a larger surface area exposed to environmental factors, making them more susceptible to wear and deterioration. Consequently, the 50 MW system experiences a more significant reduction in production compared to the 10 MW system. By the end of the project life, the 50 MW system's energy production decreased from 180 million kWh to 69 million kWh. In contrast, the 10 MW system's energy production reduces from 3.5 million kWh to 1.5 million kWh. The implications of such performance degradation are significant, both economically and environmentally. From an economic perspective, the reduced energy production leads to lower revenue generation, potentially affecting the financial viability of the project. Furthermore, the decreased efficiency may necessitate maintenance and refurbishment efforts to restore the system's performance, incurring additional costs. From an environmental standpoint, the decline in energy production translates to a decreased contribution of renewable energy to the grid, potentially leading to a higher reliance on fossil fuel-based power generation during periods of reduced solar energy capture. This, in turn, could result in increased greenhouse gas emissions and environmental impacts. To mitigate the effects of performance degradation, regular maintenance, and monitoring of the parabolic trough systems are essential. Implementing proper cleaning protocols, replacing degraded components, and optimizing the system's operation can help slow down the decline in performance and extend the system's useful life. Moreover, advancements in materials and coatings that enhance the system's durability and resistance to environmental factors can further improve the long-term performance of parabolic troughs.

Fig. 12. The decrease in system performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study focuses on the design, performance analysis, and economic evaluation of solar thermal parabolic trough systems with different capacities and Thermal Energy Storage (TES) durations. Through a comprehensive investigation and analysis of various parameters, we gained valuable insights into the feasibility and effectiveness of these systems in harnessing solar energy for power generation. The results and discussion shed light on the key factors that influence the system's

performance, economic viability, and environmental impact. The findings reveal that increasing the capacity of the parabolic trough system results in higher thermal output and electrical generation. The thermal capacity increases as the CSP capacity increases, with the 50 MW system achieving a thermal output of 280.899 MWt. This demonstrates that larger systems can capture more heat from the sun, enhancing their overall energy output. Furthermore, the incorporation of TES in the system proves to be beneficial in extending the operation time of the plant, particularly after sunset. The capacity factor of the hybrid system increases with the integration of TES. The 4-hour TES provides the best trade-off between thermal capacity and losses, resulting in an optimal cost of electricity. The economic evaluation reveals that larger capacity systems incur higher net capital costs, but they also generate significantly more revenue over time. Despite higher initial investments, larger systems achieve larger payback and revenue generation in the same timeframe, making them financially attractive in the long run. Moreover, the integration of solar thermal energy into the hybrid power plant significantly reduces the consumption of fossil fuels. This reduction leads to cost savings and, more importantly, helps mitigate CO₂ emissions. The 50 MW system saves approximately 96 tons/hour of coal, 48 barrels/hour of oil, and 400,000 ft³/hour of gas. This reduction in CO₂ emissions is crucial in contributing to environmental sustainability and combating climate change. However, it is important to consider the performance degradation of the parabolic trough systems over time. Environmental factors, such as humidity, UV radiation, and pollution, lead to wear and tear, resulting in reduced energy production. Regular maintenance and technological advancements are essential in addressing this issue and maximizing the system's operational life.

In conclusion, the results presented and discussed in this paper demonstrate the promising potential of solar thermal parabolic trough systems in meeting the energy demands sustainably. Larger capacity systems with 4-hour TES prove to be economically viable, environmentally beneficial, and capable of achieving payback in a relatively short period. These systems offer a reliable and efficient means of generating renewable energy while reducing dependence on fossil fuels and reducing CO₂ emissions. As the world strives towards a greener and more sustainable future, the findings from this study provide valuable insights and guide decision-makers in harnessing the power of solar energy to meet the challenges of the 21st century.

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BIM-Supporting System by Integrating Risk Management and Value Management

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ABSTRACT

Construction projects are of great importance because of their large financial allocations in the federal budgets of countries. This study used risk management and value management as an integrative model with Building Information Modeling (BIM). Risk management techniques were used to identify risks and quantify their impact on cost, and value management was used to identify effective mitigation measures for each risk factor. This study developed software to support BIM and risk management, including measures to assess risks and their impact on the cost estimation process, to be part of the information flowing to the project parties. The total number of risks was 52 with multiple mitigation measures for each determined using brainstorming. The Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchical Process (FAHP) was used to determine the relative importance of risk and the cost range of the selected items.

Keywords-Building Information Modeling (BIM); risk management; value management; integrating model

I. INTRODUCTION

Every project has risks and one of the most important project management tasks is to ensure that these risks are minimized, if not eliminated [1]. As risks can be human-made or natural and their effects can be very devastating, there is a need to take measures to overcome them. However, the measures taken are often ineffective in various ways. Risk management plays a vital role in minimizing the consequences of unexpected events on the performance of a construction project [2]. Effective construction project planning provides an important advantage over cost, time, and customer satisfaction considerations [3]. Over the years, many tools have been introduced to help project managers overcome risks. Building Information Modeling (BIM) is an active method that enables plans to be digitized [4]. As most large construction projects have realized the importance of BIM in their operations, its use has grown in recent years [5]. Since large projects require a lot of resources and highly accurate planning, using a modeling tool provides a way to simulate the risks that can occur during the life of the project from the beginning to the end [6]. If the results are realistic, corrective measures can be used to address any challenges that may arise [7]. Risks are unforeseen situations, and understanding their effects can be beneficial to any institution. Unforeseen circumstances must be identified, understood, and evaluated to ensure that they are prevented, transported, or addressed as the institution deems appropriate [8]. Therefore, risk managers must be able to identify risk elements and measure and manage them [9].

The use of BIM is effective when the risks associated with the project are identified and defined. A project risk profile is crucial [10]. The implementation of any project will certainly face many risks that require management, some of which can be mitigated and others that are not expected [11]. BIM is a systematic approach that visualizes every part of a construction project and can use the information to make better decisions at every stage [12]. Project managers are turning to new technologies to address threats. Putting in place effective risk management plans increases the likelihood of project success, as risk is managed by avoiding or at least mitigating its effects [13]. The relationship between risk planning and mitigation implementation is often weak and ineffective. For example, many designers and contractors still work on two-dimensional (2D) platforms and use two-dimensional graphics to communicate project information and improve construction planning [14]. On the other hand, value management is a technique to analyze the functions of an element or process and determine the best value or the best relationship between value and cost. The best value is represented by a process that consistently performs the desired purpose and has the lowest life cycle cost [15]. In [16], the risk sources and factors were selected as secondary data to formulate the model, so these data are the outputs for other research, as shown in Table I. In this study, the integration of value management provides the best mitigation measure for each risk factor. The outputs for the integration model are used to support the building information model.

TABLE I. RISK SOURCES AND FACTORS

#	Sources	Code	Risk Factors
A	Planning and Design Source	A1	Unnecessary design elements
		A2	Poor flow of project information and lack of drawings
		A3	Mistakes in estimating quantities, taking-off tables, and using appropriate tools
		A4	Poor communication and coordination between project parties
		A5	Unclear requirements of the owner
		A6	False design assumptions
		A7	Inaccuracy of economic feasibility studies and poor allocation of resources
		A8	Unclear conditions, specifications, project scope, and poor site investigations
B	Execution Source	B1	Contract management and change orders
		B2	Poor occupational safety program
		B3	Design changes during execution and notification to relevant government departments
		B4	Poor project management and the effectiveness of the construction techniques used
		B5	Delayed providing and poor inventory management
		B6	Clashes in drawings and poor coordination between the concerned parties
		B7	Waste of resources and poor productivity
		B8	Poor quality of materials and work
		B9	Site access problems and unexpected ground conditions
		B10	Difficulties in negotiation and the large number of claims
		B11	Poor project management by the owner
		B12	Delayed disbursement of Payments
		B13	Contractor conflicts
		B14	Interventions of the owner and other external parties
C	Market Source	C1	Fluctuations in the supply of materials, equipment, manpower, or services
		C2	Competition risk
		C3	Fake information received from decision-makers about the market situation
		C4	Support for local raw materials with neglect of quality
		C5	Fluctuations in the demand for materials, equipment, manpower, or services
D	Financial Source	D1	Loss realized from corruption and red tape
		D2	Cost changes (transportation, maintenance, materials and equipment, land, waste management)
		D3	Owner's cash flow (financing risk)
		D4	Change in costs of tests, quality management, and insurance
		D5	Interest rate volatility and inflation rate
		D6	Change the government's financial policy
		D7	Wrong estimate of costs
		D8	Delay in completing the project
		D9	The change in the currency exchange rate
E	Political Source	E1	Internal factors such as terrorism, crime rate, sabotage, revolutions
		E2	Changes in the local labor cost
		E3	Changes in government policy
		E4	Changes to the tax law
		E5	Political risk to materials, equipment, and buildings (riot outbreak)
		E6	Political stability
		E7	Notification resulting from bilateral agreements between countries
		E8	External factors such as political and armed conflicts
F	Legal Source	F1	Breach of contracts by other parties and contractual disputes
		F2	Changes in instructions and the issuance of new laws and regulations
		F3	Changes in Projects Execution laws
G	Environmental Source	G1	Pollution, toxic emissions, and waste accumulation
		G2	Risks in environmental laws and regulations
		G3	Use of environmentally harmful alternatives
H	Social Source	H1	Disable the continuation of the project activities
		H2	Affected the country's economy and did not contribute to the employment of the labor force

II. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Qualitative Assessment

1) Risk Probability and Risk Impact Assessment

The users were asked to assess the probability of the risk occurrence and its impact on a scale from 1 (very low) to 10 (very high). The Qualitative Assessment (QA) for each risk factor was calculated by [17]:

$$QA = Risk\ Probabilty \times Risk\ Impact \quad (3)$$

QA includes an assessment of the risk impact and probability. The results of the QA of risk factors were based on the following rules:

- If QA is greater than or equal to 72, the risk is very high.
- If QA is greater than 36 and less than 72, the risk is high.
- If QA is greater than 16 and less than or equal to 36, the risk is moderate.

- If QA is greater than 4 and smaller than or equal to 16, the risk is low.
- If QA is less than or equal to 4, the risk is very low.

2) Relative Importance Using FAHP

This phase determined the relative importance of the risks, built based on the risk breakdown structure (WBD) shown in Figure 1. The basic objective, "risk assessment", was placed at the top, the risk sources were placed in the middle levels, and the risk factors were placed at the lower levels. This assessment

was carried out according to a scale of 1 to 9 (1 = equal importance, 9 = extreme importance). The AHP model was based on a coding system that used letters to represent sources and numbers to represent risk factors. SpiceLogic AHP software was used to obtain accuracy in the decision-making process. The main objective of using this tool was to make a pairwise comparison between all risk factors and sources and to obtain relative importance.

Fig. 1. AHP model for construction risk assessment.

B. Quantitative Assessment

The simulation was carried out using the Risk AMP add-on in Excel. The main inputs of the simulation were the activities of the project, the risks associated with each activity, and the range of the estimated costs of each activity. The trigonometric distribution was chosen because it is suitable for ideal construction activities with specific upper and lower bounds. The new costs of activities at risk obtained from the Risk AMP tool were introduced. The cost of completing the project was then calculated and repeated in this step, and the cost of each activity was extracted 1000 times by giving different costs to the events each time. The main outputs of the simulation phase were histograms showing the probability and the S-curve. The factor of cost change can be calculated by the proportion that determines the influencing factor and the affected factor or factors after multiplying the right-hand side by the coefficient of impact and interaction. The impact and interaction

coefficients were taken based on the QA and the impact and probability values after conversion to a percentage. The ratio and the proportion are shown in (6) and (7).

$$\frac{C_a}{RI_a} = \frac{C_i}{RI_i} \times C_r \tag{6}$$

$$C_a = RI_a \times \frac{C_i}{RI_i} \times C_r \tag{7}$$

where C_r is the impact and interaction factor depending on QA, C_i is the cost factor for influenced risks calculated based on C_r , C_a is the cost factor for affected risks, RI_i is the RI for influenced risks, and RI_a is the RI for affected risks. The cost factor for the influence of risk factors in (6) and (7) can be calculated based on C_r , while C_i is calculated using Table II.

In the case of projects where there is more than one cost factor and more than one influencing factor, (8) can be used to find the compound cost factor C_T [18]:

$$C_T = (C_{a_i})^{(1-0.2(n-1))} \tag{8}$$

where i is the number of cost factors, and n is the number of conditioning variables. The total cost factor can be calculated using [13, 18]:

$$CF_T = 1 + C_T \tag{9}$$

Then, the new cost of the activity in the effect of the risk factors was calculated based on:

$$\text{Cost result in risk factors} = \text{Cost Factor} \times \text{Cost from Montecarlo Simulation} \tag{10}$$

TABLE II. COST FACTOR FOR INFLUENCE RISKS

C_r	C_i
0.5-1	0.1
0.4-0.49	0.08
0.2-0.39	0.05
less than 0.2	0.01

III. BRAINSTORMING SESSIONS

The brainstorming sessions aimed to determine the active mitigation measures. This process included the following steps:

A. Step 1: Creating the Environment

This step determined the group brainstorming session. According to interviews, the sample was selected based on two criteria. First, the respondents willing to participate in sessions, and second, their experience in the Iraqi construction industry. The results of the interviews showed that 11 engineers were ready to participate and 7 had more than 15 years of experience. Experience and skills are critical points in selecting the sample that makes a sensitive decision. Table III shows details of the brainstorming session.

TABLE III. BRAINSTORMING SAMPLE SPECIFICATIONS

No.	Position/Current Institution	Experience (Years)	Background
1	Head of risk management department/ UNDP Iraq.	28	Project management
2	Program manager/ NRC Iraq.	21	Civil engineering
3	Project manager/Alkhattab Company for General Contracting, Ltd.	20	Project management
4	Assist. prof. Dr./ University of Mosul.	16	Civil engineering
5	Engineering department manager/ Anbar Province.	27	Civil engineering
6	Engineering department manager/ Thefaf AlRafidain for General Contracting, Ltd.	29	Project management
7	Risk department manager/ NRC Iraq.	26	Civil engineering

B. Step 2: Identifying the Problem

This step aimed to identify the mitigation measures for each risk factor. The plan was developed using an online whiteboard for visual collaboration [19].

C. Step 3: Generating and Sharing Ideas

This step included generating many ideas on mitigation measures. The participants presented the ideas and improved each one if needed. Figure 2 shows the output of the brainstorming session for risk factor A1 and Figure 3 shows the

mitigation measures for risk factor B3. In case the suggestions of the participants need to improve, the participants need to try improving the ideas to get them in good quality.

Fig. 2. Generation of ideas for mitigation measures for factor A1.

Fig. 3. Generated ideas for mitigation measures for factor B3.

IV. SOFTWARE INTERFACE FOR THE BIM-SUPPORTING SYSTEM

Figure 4 shows the main interface of the program, which demonstrates the definition of the software. The second interface included general information about the project. The software supports the project parties in the documentation process. Figure 5 shows the information required to input. The documentation function is important in the long-term consideration of building the database concerned with the monitoring and evaluation process. Therefore, the software has great value in the construction environment and improves performance in the construction sector. The project data interface included user, responsibility, project name, province, and date.

Fig. 4. The main interface.

Fig. 5. Project information.

Fig. 6. Qualitative assessment calculations.

The third interface included the QA calculation. Many options in this interface include the import probability and the effect of experts' opinions. The user can adjust the probability and impact values depending on the nature of the project and the surrounding environment. The calculation for all sources was imported into the program, and the user was able to

modify all values. The plots for each source were built into the program according to the values selected by the user. Figure 6 shows a qualitative assessment interface that provides the ability to modify the impact and probability for each. There is a required action in the assessment description to monitor risk factors. Figure 7 shows the plots for each source, which were built into the software, to identify the sensitivity analysis.

Fig. 7. Plot for planning and designing source.

The proposed software was linked to AHP to build the matrix for all factors and sources. Consistency is the most important measure of the results from pair comparison in FAHP. Pair comparison is a method of calculating the weights for each item to compare two factors [20]. FAHP consistency is determined by the CI value from the paired comparison table. If its value for a case exceeds 0.1, it is inconsistent, and a paired comparison should be performed again [21]. Consistency is shown in the bottom interface in the red box. The consistency ratio for all pairwise comparisons was less than 0.1. The relative importance interface includes many options. The import RI button concerns the input of relative importance from an Excel sheet. The open AHP button is for modifying the pairwise comparison using the AHP software. The calculate RI button inputs the RI that is extracted from any AHP software. The relative importance of each source and plot can be extracted as shown in Figures 8 and 9. In addition, the relative importance of all sources was calculated using the AHP software.

The relative weighted assessment was calculated to determine the effect of the change cases on the risk factor components, as shown in Figure 10. Evaluations of each one were inserted into the database with the possibility of modification. The software tests the ability of mitigation measures to mitigate risk factors. If the mitigation factor is less than 20%, the new mitigation measures can be added to the program using the add button. The export button provides a mitigation measure report, as shown in Figure 11. In some cases, all mitigation measures are not active for special environments. For this case, the software provides a tool to calculate QA.

Fig. 8. Simulation of RI for planning and design source.

Fig. 11. Mitigation measures.

Fig. 9. Plots of RI for planning and design source.

Fig. 12. Quantitative assessment for the proposed case.

Fig. 10. Relative weighted assessment.

Fig. 13. BOQ/Activities.

On the other hand, the software provides a quantitative assessment of any risk factor. The quantitative interface was designed to determine the cost factor according to (7), measuring the impact of risk factors on the cost of construction, as shown in Figure 12. In BOQ/Activities, the bill of quantities

can be entered, which consists of a range of unit prices that is constituted from the AMP risk tool, and the user selects a single value and adds the risk impact quantitatively to the unit price. Figure 13 shows the six items of the bill of quantities as a sample to test the software.

V. DATA INPUT TO THE BIM MODEL

The case study was the "Development of the Design for a private hospital in Iraq, Anbar". The BIM model was developed and the proposed software was used as integrated with the BIM to validate the structural model shown in Figure 14.

Fig. 14. Structural model for a hospital building in Iraq.

In common cases, mitigation measures may be active for most factors. In cases where the environment of the project is special and the factor(s) is (are) not mitigated, there is a possibility to quantify its (their) impact. In these cases, we propose a way to input the risk factors into Revit as a parameter in the quantity take-off process. The main objective of this phase is to monitor and evaluate risk factors in the progress of the project and to observe the increase in the cost at the root. Figure 15 shows the case study project, highlighting the first floor. In the quantity take-off process, the floor concrete is calculated to determine the quantities and the unit price. The unit price was calculated using the model in the proposed software. Figure 15 highlights the slab for the first-floor concrete. The quantity take-off process integrates the risk factor into the building information modeling. The risk factor that was not mitigated at an acceptable level for a user was converted to all project development and would be part of the information flow.

The total quantity was obtained from Revit and the unit price (576 \$/m³) was selected in the BIM support system according to the range 575-590 \$/m³, based on the simulation process. The unit price with the risk impact was 576.744 \$, after using the model in the proposed software. This value was entered into Revit to calculate the total cost for each item and the total cost for all items. The value shown in Figure 13 in the

red box and coded 1, 2, 3, and 4 was indicated at some points. Box 1 indicated the quantity that came from the quantity take-off in Revit. Box 2 indicates the selected value according to the simulation ranges. Box 4 indicates the unit price after multiplying by the cost factor. Box 3 indicates the total price for the first floor. Figure 16 shows the quantity take-off performed using Revit. Researchers were supposed to add the risk exposure column as a parameter to be an important part of the information flow at all stages of the project to contribute to mitigating the risks.

Fig. 15. Concrete floor for case study.

<Floor Concrete>								
A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Level	Count	Type	Volume	Cost (\$)	TotalCost	Risk Exposure (Activity)	Risk Exposure (Project)	Cost Factor
01 - Ground Floor-TOS	3		136.38 m ³	576.74	78756.52	09		1.0013
02 - First Floor - TOS	8	Flat Slab 300 mm	389.96 m ³	576.74	225197.77	09		1.0013
03 - Second FloorL - TOS	7	Flat Slab 300 mm	338.96 m ³	576.74	195748.35	09		1.0013
04 - Roof Floor - TOS	5	Flat Slab 300 mm	312.77 m ³	576.74	180621.25	09		1.0013
Grand total:	23		1178.07 m ³		680323.88			

Fig. 16. Take-off quantity for floor concrete.

VI. CONCLUSION

Risk management in construction projects plays a critical role in their success. This study investigated risk management and integrated it with value management to select effective mitigation measures. This study showed that most risk factors can be mitigated using measures proposed by the system, and if the project has the specified consideration, it can quantify the impact of the risk factor on cost. According to the results of the case study in Iraq, the current situation of the local currency is rapidly changing due to the unstable economy. The proposed software calculates the impact of this risk factor on the cost and input to the quantity take-off. The unit price of concrete in Iraq was 576 \$/m³, and after calculating the risk impact was 576.744 \$/m³. The column of risk impact factors showed the root of the change rate in unit price. This point requires building special standards to determine the procedures and risk factors code with training for all parties that are concerned with BIM. Finally, the user can add unlimited situations for risks that cannot be mitigated to determine the impact on cost. Risks in construction projects still constitute a major obstacle. The proposed system can manage risks and link them to building information modeling to be part of the information that is transferred between the project parties.

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Photo-Catalytic Activity Improvement for Organic Pollutant Removal in Wastewater using Zinc Oxide Quantum Dots: An Experimental and Modeling Study

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ABSTRACT

Photo-catalyst nanoparticles (NPs) find applications in many diverse fields, including environmental remediation, energy conversion, and organic synthesis. By optimizing the nanoparticle's composition, size, morphology, and surface properties, the photo-catalytic performance can be enhanced to develop more efficient and sustainable catalytic systems. This work aligns with this innovative approach and aims to improve the photo-catalytic degradation of Sulfamethoxazole (SMX) through the intensification of the photo-catalyst and the micro-reactor. ZnO-NPs were synthesized using the sol-gel method. Zinc Acetate (Z.A) and sodium hydroxide were used as precursor materials. The resulting ZnO-NPs were characterized for their structure and crystallinity using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and the photo-catalytic activity was assessed with a micro-structured polymer reactor. The degradation of SMX through photo-catalysis proceeds through several stages that involve coupled processes, such as the transportation of molecules and chemical reactions. To solve the mathematical equations governing the transport and photocatalytic reaction, COMSOL Multiphysics software was utilized. The characterization results demonstrate the excellent crystallinity and high purity of the synthesized ZnO-NPs, enabling the estimation of the average diameter of the NPs under different synthesis conditions. The grain growth is faster (3.5 hr) at higher temperatures (70, 80, and 90 °C), and slower (4 hr) at lower temperatures (50 and 60°C). The photo-catalytic degradation is significantly more efficient on 16 nm ZnO-NPs than 50 nm ZnO-NPs. At this size, the conversion rate reaches 96%, surpassing the performance of commercial ZnO-NPs, which only degrades 81% of SMX. The conversion rate obtained through simulation is slightly higher than that achieved in the experiments. However, this difference remains negligible, and overall, the model fits well with the experimental data. This validation of the chosen model confirms its reliability and accuracy.

Keywords-ZnO nanoparticles; sulfamethoxazole (SMX); sol-gel method; characterization; microreactor; modeling; simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Water pollution exacerbates the degradation of natural water quality by modifying its physical, chemical, biological, or bacteriological characteristics [1-3]. To mitigate the rapid escalation of pollution, stringent regulations are in place to govern water designated for human consumption, and these regulations adapt in tandem with technological advancements in analysis methodologies [4, 5]. Among the most dangerous pollutants that significantly impact water quality are antibiotics. Antibiotics are mainly used in the prevention and treatment of human and in the prevention and control of agricultural and aquaculture diseases [6, 7]. Authors in [8] analyzed the trends and drivers of antibiotic consumption from 2000 to 2015 in 76 countries and projected the total global antibiotic consumption until 2030. The study indicated that global antibiotic consumption increased by 65% between 2000 and 2015. Various antibiotics have been reported in different environmental compartments, such as wastewater from treatment plants, river waters, sediments, and soils. This contamination necessitates an urgent improvement in water treatment techniques [9]. Among these water treatment methods, Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) remain highly promising for the oxidation of organic pollutants. AOPs are based on the in situ production of highly oxidizing and reactive radical species that interact with organic pollutants and lead to their fragmentation. The hydroxyl radical is a highly reactive and relatively non-selective species that exhibits a strong oxidizing character [10-12]. Heterogeneous photo-catalysis involves naturally or artificially irradiating an intrinsic or extrinsic semiconductor material, such as TiO_2 or ZnO , also known as a photo-catalyst [13-14]. The semiconductor is photo-excited by photons with energy equal to or greater than the bandgap energy (EC-EV). An electron is liberated within the semiconductor and undergoes an energy transition from the Valence Band (VB) to the Conduction Band (CB). During this transition, electron vacancies, commonly referred to as "holes" (h^+), and an excess of electrons (e^-) are created within the material. The use of nanoparticles as photo-catalysts is a highly beneficial approach to harness the physical and optical properties of semiconductors, as described in [14-16]. NPs incorporated into a photo-catalyst are extremely tiny particles, typically in the nanometer scale. These NPs play a crucial role in enlarging the photo-catalytic activity. The reduced size of these nanoparticles results in a significant increase in the surface area-to-volume ratio, providing more active sites for photo-catalytic reactions [17, 18]. This enlarged surface area also enhances light absorption, leading to improved photo-catalytic efficiency. Moreover, the small size of NPs facilitates the diffusion of reactants and products, thereby enhancing the overall reaction kinetics. By precisely controlling the size, shape, and composition of the NPs, the photo-catalytic performance of the material for specific applications can be optimized [19, 20].

Authors in [21] investigated the degradation of sulfamethoxazole (SMX) using a synthesized ZnO -NPs catalyst and UVA irradiation. ZnO -NPs were synthesized

through a simple hydrothermal-assisted method. The research examined the influence of various factors, including ZnO heating time and synthesis reaction, pH, catalyst loading, and initial SMX concentration, on the efficiency of the degradation process. Morphological changes in the ZnO were observed after the photo-catalytic treatment. The study confirmed that SMX degradation occurred through the action of hydroxyl radicals. In the same context, authors in [22] showed that the photo-catalytic performance of SMX degradation is enhanced with cobalt doping, and the hetero-structure doped with 3% Co demonstrates the highest degradation efficiency. Authors in [23] indicate that an acidic medium is more favorable for the degradation of SMX, with the optimum pH values for UV/TiO_2 and UV/WO_3 being 4 and 3, respectively. The determined optimal dosage of TiO_2 and WO_3 was 500 mg/L and 750 mg/L, resulting in removal efficiencies of 61.28% and 43.3%, respectively. Despite the significant number of research studies on the application of photo-catalysis for the degradation of SMX, only a few studies have focused on the effect of reducing the size of ZnO -NPs on the degradation of this pollutant. It is within this context that this work aims to contribute to the characterization of ZnO -NPS and the study of the impact of experimental synthesis conditions of nanoparticles on the improvement of photo-catalytic degradation. In addition, a numerical modeling of coupled transport and reaction phenomena will be presented.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Organic Pollutant

The pollutant chosen is Sulfamethoxazole (SMX). A Thermo Scientific Evolution_300 spectrophotometer was used to identify SMX from its absorption spectrum. The spectral range of the spectrometer is from 190 to 1100 nm. The precision is ± 1 nm, the reproducibility is 0.1 nm, and the scanning speed is 240 nm/min. The residual concentrations were obtained by interpolation using the calibration curves or spectra $A = f(\lambda)$. SMX absorbs in the UV-Visible at the wavelength of 258 nm as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. UV-visible absorption spectrum of SMX.

B. ZnO Synthesis Protocol

The sol-gel method was utilized to synthesize ZnO nanoparticles. Zinc acetate (Z.A) and sodium hydroxide

(NaOH) were used as precursors, and the mixture in mol/L ([Zn]/[NaOH]=0.5/0.5) was prepared in a solvent composed of distilled water and ethanol. In order to achieve homogeneous solution, both solutions, the Z.A solution (A) and the NaOH solution (B) were thoroughly mixed with the solvent while stirring at a speed of 600 rpm for a period of 15 min. Then, 160 ml of solution (B) were gradually added to 80 ml of solution (A) with magnetic stirring (600 rpm) in a water bath at a specific temperature (°C) under reflux conditions. At the end of this step, a white gel was formed. The obtained product underwent centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 5 min, followed by filtration and thorough rinsing with acetone solution and distilled water to eliminate any residues. Finally, the product was dried in an oven at 80°C for 24 hr and then calcined at 500°C for 4 hr to remove any remaining organic chains, water vapors, and trapped solvents. The experimental protocol flowchart is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. ZnO-NP synthesis flow chart using the sol-gel method.

C. Characterization of ZnO-NPs

The produced ZnO-NPs were examined for structure and crystallinity with the XRD method. Analysis was carried out using a D8 Advance Bruker diffractometer with Cu-K radiation ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm) and an accelerating voltage ranging from 20 to 80 kV at roughly 40 kV. The width of the diffraction peak varies with the size of the crystallites in the sample. The broadening of the diffraction peak occurs for very small crystals. The measurement of the Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of

the most intense peaks allows to estimate the average grain size "D" using the Debye-Scherrer equation [24]:

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

D. Photocatalytic Tests

The photocatalytic activity of SMX was evaluated using a microstructured polymer reactor with 150 mm length, 2 mm width, and 1 mm depth. A solution containing synthesized ZnO-NPs at a concentration of 100 mg/L was deposited in the microchannel. A quantity of 10 mg/L of the stock solution was introduced into the microchannel via a syringe pump. The photocatalytic test consisted of two stages. In the first stage, the SMX solution was circulated through the microchannel in the absence of light to allow the adsorption of SMX onto the surface of the photocatalyst. The second stage involved the irradiation of the photocatalyst ($I=1.5$ mW/cm²) in the presence of dissolved oxygen to ensure the photocatalytic degradation process. Figure 3 illustrates the experimental device for the photo-catalytic tests.

Fig. 3. Experimental device for the photo-catalytic tests.

The concentration of SMX was measured at the outlet of the reactor every 5 min using a Thermo Scientific Evolution 300 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The measurement steps include sample preparation, spectrophotometer calibration, and absorbance measurement at the specific wavelength of 257 nm, concentration calculation via the Beer-Lambert Law, and subsequent validation and interpretation of the measured concentration. Finally, the degradation efficiency (DE) of the nanoparticles was estimated by:

$$DE = \left(1 - \frac{C_o}{C_i}\right) * 100\% \quad (2)$$

where C_i and C_o represent the concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the microchannel, respectively.

E. Modeling and Simulation

The degradation of SMX through photo-catalysis proceeds through several stages that involve coupled processes, such as the transportation of molecules and chemical reactions [25, 26]. To solve the mathematical equations governing the transport and photocatalytic reaction, COMSOL Multiphysics simulation software was utilized. This software enables the integration of

flow phenomena, pollutant transport via convection and diffusion, and chemical reactions. The equations for conserving mass and momentum were obtained by global and partial balances within the microreactors. The following assumptions were considered: Gravity forces have no effect on the flow within the microreactors, the flow regime is characterized as laminar, and the fluid is both Newtonian and incompressible. Consequently, the photocatalytic degradation of SMX can be formulated as follows [26]:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot J + u \cdot \nabla c = \frac{kKC}{1+KC} \quad (3)$$

where c represents the concentration of SMX (sulfamethoxazole), J is the mass transfer flux of SMX towards the catalytic surface, u refers to the flow velocity of the solution containing the pollutant, k represents the kinetic rate constant of the reaction, and K gives the adsorption constant of SMX onto the photocatalyst surface.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characterization Results

The X-ray diffractometer displays various peaks that correspond to the crystal lattices of the material. The positions and intensities of these peaks can be used to identify the crystalline structure, and estimate particle size. The diffraction diagram for ZnO-NPs is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. X-ray diffraction diagram of ZnO NPs synthesized by sol-gel CAZ/CNaOH = 0.5/0.5, T = 60°C, tm=3 hr.

All characteristic peaks of ZnO are located within the range of $20^\circ < 2\theta < 80^\circ$, further confirming the presence of the metal oxide (ZnO). The high intensity and narrow peak width indicate the good crystallinity of the ZnO NPs. There are no additional peaks in the XRD patterns, indicating the high purity of the synthesized ZnO NPs. The determination of NP size was estimated by XRD using (1), allowing studying the influence of temperature and stirring time on the NP formation process, as shown in Figure 5. Figure 5 illustrates the variation in NP size obtained by the Scherrer method as a function of temperature. The average size of the NPs slightly decreases, initially, for both temperatures (50 and 60°C), but for the other temperatures, the decrease is approximately 4 nm. The grain growth is faster at higher temperatures (70, 80, and 90°C) after 3.5 hr, while at lower temperatures (50 and 60°C), this occurs after 4 hr. This phenomenon can be explained by the significant

impact of temperature on the nucleation and aggregation of ZnO NPs. In general, higher temperatures can accelerate the rate of formation and growth of NPs, while lower temperatures can slow down these rates. However, the specific effects of temperature on the formation and aggregation can vary depending on different factors such as reaction conditions, NP morphology, precursor concentration, and solvent properties.

Fig. 5. Influence of temperature and stirring time on NPs.

Additionally, at higher temperatures, the reaction rate of precursor molecules may increase, leading to faster formation and growth of ZnO NPs. This can promote the formation of larger NPs and increase the probability of aggregation, where particles stick together to form larger clusters. On the other hand, at lower temperatures, the reaction rate may decrease, resulting in slower formation and growth of NPs. This can lead to the formation of smaller NPs and reduce the probability of aggregation [27, 28]. The best result obtained (the smallest NP size of ZnO) corresponds to a temperature of T = 50°C and a mixing duration of 4 hr.

B. Photo-Catalytic Test Results

The photo-catalytic degradation experiments were performed using two different photo-catalysts of ZnO-NPs: one commercially available and the other synthesized through the sol-gel method. The particle sizes of these photo-catalysts were 50 nm and 16 nm, respectively. Figure 6 combines the results of SMX adsorption on the photo-catalyst, SMX photolysis, and photo-catalytic degradation.

Fig. 6. SMX adsorption, photolysis, and photo-catalytic degradation.

Figure 6 shows that in the absence of UV irradiation (between 0 and 30 min), SMX molecules adsorb onto the ZnO-NPS photo-catalyst and the conversion rate reaches 10% at 15 min. Subsequently, there is a slight decrease in the conversion rate (DE=8%), reaching adsorption-desorption equilibrium at 30 min. On the other hand, in the presence of irradiation, two phenomena can be distinguished. In the absence of a photo-catalyst, the photolysis phenomenon causes a slight degradation of SMX on the order of 6%. In the presence of UV irradiation and a photo-catalyst, the photo-catalytic degradation is more pronounced on the ZnO-NPs with a size of 16 nm. With this size, the conversion rate reaches 96%, while commercial ZnO-NPs only degrade 81% of SMX. Reducing the size of NPs enhances the efficiency of photo-catalytic degradation for several reasons. Firstly, smaller ZnO-NPs have a larger surface area per unit mass, providing more active sites for pollutant adsorption and reaction. Additionally, their smaller size allows more efficient light absorption, as they exhibit higher light absorption efficiency due to the quantum confinement effects. This leads to increased generation of electron-hole pairs, which are crucial for the photo-catalytic process. Moreover, the shorter diffusion paths in smaller NPs facilitate faster mass transport and reaction kinetics, the higher surface-to-volume ratio of smaller NPs reduces electron-hole recombination, as more surface sites are available for charge separation [29-31]. In summary, reducing the size of ZnO NPs optimizes surface area, light absorption, diffusion, and charge separation, ultimately improving the efficiency of the photo-catalytic degradation.

C. Modeling and Simulation

COMSOL Multiphysics simulation software was employed to solve the mathematical equations governing the transport and photo-catalytic reaction involved in the degradation of SMX. This process occurs in multiple stages and involves coupled processes, including molecule transportation and chemical reactions. The geometry of the micro-reactor is presented in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Geometry of the micro-reactor.

The decision to conduct the micro-reactor simulation in 2D is based on the objective of reducing computational time while still capturing the essential physical aspects of the system. By simulating the micro-reactor in two dimensions instead of three, the complexity of the calculations is significantly reduced, leading to faster simulation times. A study of the meshing reveals that the physical results, such as flow velocity, remain unchanged when the mesh size was below 10 μm as shown in Figure 8. It is observed that the mesh is finer near the boundary zones (micro-reactor walls) where the flow velocity is assumed to be zero.

Fig. 8. Meshing of the micro-reactor geometry.

The numerical solving of (2) enabled the plotting of velocity and concentration profiles within the micro-channel containing the photo-catalyst as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Velocity and concentration profiles within the micro-channel.

The flow velocity profile in the micro-channel shows a homogeneous distribution, with maximum velocity at the center and zero velocity near the walls. It is important to mention that the fluid undergoes rapid changes in direction when passing through the bends, leading to localized stagnant zones within the velocity profile. On the other hand, the concentration of SMX decreases along the entire micro-channel, reaching a value of 2.5 mg/L at the outlet, corresponding to a conversion rate of 97.5%. It is interesting to note that in stagnant fluid zones, the concentration of SMX is zero. This can be explained by the prolonged residence time of SMX molecules on the photo-catalyst surface, leading to their complete degradation.

The simulation of photo-catalytic degradation allowed for a comparative analysis between the experimental results and the simulation data. Two distinct simulations were performed as shown in Figure 10. The first focused on the adsorption of SMX from the photo-catalyst surface, utilizing the Langmuir-Hinshelwood model. The kinetic and adsorption constants used in the simulation were experimentally determined. The second simulation involved the photo-catalytic degradation process, considering an apparent kinetic constant that varied with the light intensity ($k_{app} = k_0 \times I$). By conducting these simulations, a comprehensive understanding of the photo-catalytic degradation process was obtained, facilitating the comparison between the experimental and the simulated results.

Fig. 10. Comparison between the experimental and the simulated results.

Figure 10 illustrates that the conversion rate obtained through simulation is slightly higher than that achieved during the experiments. This difference, which amounts to approximately 2%, can be attributed to the perfectly homogeneous dispersion of the photo-catalyst in the simulation, whereas in the experimental setup, there may be some variations in the dispersion. However, this difference remains negligible, and overall, the model fits well with the experimental data. This validation of the chosen model confirms its reliability and accuracy.

IV. CONCLUSION

A successful synthesis of ZnO-NPs was carried out under different time and mixing conditions. The XRD characterization revealed good crystallinity of the produced NPs and high purity. Particle size determination under various

conditions showed a slight decrease in the average size of the NPs at 50°C and 60°C. However, for the other temperatures, the decrease is approximately 4 nm. The grain growth is faster (3.5 hr) at higher temperatures (70, 80, and 90°C), and slower (4 hr) at lower temperatures (50 and 60°C). This can be explained by the significant impact of temperature on the nucleation and aggregation of ZnO NPs. The photo-catalytic degradation experiments were performed using two different photo-catalysts of ZnO-NPs. The photo-catalytic degradation is more efficient on the ZnO-NPs with a size of 16 nm. With this size, the conversion rate reaches 96%, while commercial ZnO-NPs only degrade 81% of SMX. Smaller ZnO-NPs have a larger surface area per unit mass, providing more active sites for pollutant adsorption and reaction. Additionally, their smaller size allows more efficient light absorption, as they exhibit higher light absorption efficiencies due to the quantum confinement effects. The coupled model simulating the transport and photo-catalytic degradation of SMX fits well with the experimental data. This validation of the chosen model confirms its reliability and accuracy.

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A Single Stage Photovoltaic Solar Pumping System based on the Three Phase Multilevel Inverter

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a study of a single-stage DC-AC converter for a solar water pumping application. The topology was based on solar panels connected to a new structure of a three-phase multilevel inverter through DC-bus capacitors. The inverter offers simplicity, requires fewer components compared to conventional ones, and provides optimal voltage and current waveforms with reduced harmonics, eliminating the need for filters. The applied control technique aimed to stabilize the input DC-bus voltage, extract the maximum power using a simple MPPT algorithm, and enhance the efficiency of the water pump through scalar V/f control, regardless of weather changes. A simulation was conducted using the PSIM software, considering a variable daily climate scenario. The results obtained demonstrate the efficiency of the system in extracting energy with optimal torque and current for the pump compared to a classic design based on a three-phase H-bridge inverter.

Keywords-photovoltaic energy conversion system; three-phase multilevel inverter; maximum power point tracking (MPPT); scalar V/f control; induction motor

I. INTRODUCTION

Access to clean water is essential for life. People extract water for their personal and livestock needs, irrigation, and various other purposes [1]. Water pumps facilitate the movement of water through pipes, tanks, or treatment facilities, using several technologies such as centrifugal, volumetric, and helical pumps [2-4]. Solar panels generate DC voltages to drive permanent magnet DC motors coupled to the pump shaft or can be converted to single or three-phase AC through inverters [5-8]. For the latter, multilevel topologies with suitable controls mitigate the problems of handling high input DC-bus voltage and power quality. Such topologies achieve low Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), reduce voltage stress (dv/dt), minimize electromagnetic interference, and require compact filter sizes [9-10].

The design of solar inverters emphasizes various parameters, including the extraction of maximum power from solar panels (MPPT techniques) [11-12], the use of battery energy storage [13], and the implementation of digital control circuits to apply efficient control algorithms [14]. Water pump three-phase induction motors are used in a wide variety of applications, which require variable power and specific water flow rates. To achieve this, several control techniques are combined with MPPT, including scalar V/f control, Field-Oriented Control (FOC) strategy, and Direct Torque Control (DTC) [15-17]. Thus, closed-loop speed control improves the performance and efficiency of the system. This study investigated a battery-less solar inverter that drove a water pump using a new structure of a three-phase multilevel inverter [18], which was constructed with a three-phase H-Bridge inverter and auxiliary power switches. Gate pulses were obtained using a conventional modulation technique, and an MPPT algorithm combined with the scalar V/f technique, controlled the system. The topology was simulated in PSIM software and analyzed with a variable climate scenario to verify the robustness of the control and the performance of the proposed inverter.

II. THE STUDIED PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM

Figure 1 shows the platform of the proposed single-stage system. The principal components include photovoltaic (PV) panels and a three-phase DC-AC Multilevel Voltage Source Converter (MVSC) to supply a water pump.

Fig. 1. The proposed single-stage system.

A. Photovoltaic Solar Panels

Different solar cells are used to manufacture solar panels, such as crystalline, amorphous, and thin-film cells. To achieve a rated power, several cells are interconnected in series/parallel configurations to create PV modules and arrays. The generated DC is obtained through the photovoltaic effect by absorbing photons from sunlight. Figure 2 shows the model of a solar cell, which consists of a current source, a single diode, a series resistance R_s , and a parallel resistance R_p [19].

Fig. 2. Model of a solar cell.

Equation (1) expresses the produced current I from the solar cell. I_{ph} is the photocurrent, I_0 is the diode reverse saturation current, V represents the output voltage, N signifies the ideality factor of the diode, q corresponds to the charge of an electron ($1.60217662 \times 10^{-19}$ C), K stands for the Boltzmann constant ($1.38064852 \times 10^{-23}$ m²kg⁻²K⁻¹), and T denotes the junction temperature. Table I shows the electrical parameters of the adopted PV under Standard Test Conditions (STC), defined as 1000W/m² and 25°C.

$$I = I_{ph} - I_d - I_{sh} = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp \left(q \cdot \left(\frac{V + (R_s \cdot I)}{n \cdot K \cdot T} \right) \right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V + (R_s \cdot I)}{R_p} \quad (1)$$

TABLE I. ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS OF THE USED PV UNDER STC

Parameters	Values
Nominal power (P_{max})	90 W
Nominal Voltage (V_{mpp})	19.2 V
Nominal Current (I_{mpp})	4.69 A
Short-circuit current (I_{sc})	4.98 A
Open-circuit voltage (V_{oc})	23.44V

B. Three Phase Multilevel Voltage Source Converter

The V_{PV} output voltage from the PV panels is converted into AC using the MVSC from the PV panels is converted into AC using the MVSC to provide electric power to the water pump. Figure 3 illustrates the topology of the used converter with 5 levels (MVSC-5L), which is based on [18]. The MVSC-5L is equipped with 6 switches (SAH, SAL, SBH, SBL, SCH, SCL) arranged in an H-bridge configuration, with no connection to the high-side drain terminals. Three sets of parallel power switches [(Q1, Q2), (Q3, Q4), and (Q5, Q6)] are connected to the high side of the bridge through the power switches (SAH, SBH, SCH), and a capacitor block functions as a voltage source. Figure 4 illustrates the optimal waveform shape of the AC voltages per line with the active switches.

Fig. 3. The used MVSC-5L.

Fig. 4. Optimal waveform shape of the AC voltages per line with the active switches ($f = 50$ Hz).

Sinusoidal Pulse Width Modulation (SPWM) was used to generate the gating signals for the MVSC-5L switches. This was achieved by comparing two triangular carrier waves (Carr 1 and Carr 2) with a reference sinusoidal signal (Ref), as shown in Figure 5 and explained in Table II. The latter establishes the criteria for controlling the switches [Q1, Q2, SAH, and SAL]. As for the remaining switches ([Q3, Q4, SBH, SBL], and [Q5, Q6, SCH, SCL]), their gate pulses are generated by phase-shifting the reference signal by 120° and -120° . The modulation index (m) of the SPWM is defined as the ratio of

the peak magnitudes of the reference and the carrier waves. The MVSC-5L generates AC voltages with 5 levels per line, reducing the THD of the delivered current without the need for filters.

TABLE II. LOGICAL CONDITIONS TO ACTIVE THE POWER SWITCHES FOR ONE LEG OF THE MVSC-5L

Signals/Conditions	ON switch
$(Ref \geq Carr1) = C1$	SAH
$(Ref \geq Carr2) = C2$	Q2
$\{C1 \text{ AND } (\text{NOT } C2)\}$	Q1
$(\text{NOT } C1)$	SAL

Fig. 5. SPWM technique for one leg of the MVSC-5L.

C. AC Water Pump

For the centrifugal pump, the load torque T_L is proportional to the square of the Induction Motor (IM) rotor speed Ω , as shown in (2), where K_{pump} is the constant of the pump used. T_L is equal to the torque of the induction motor T_{IM} under steady-state operation [15]. For this, T_L and nominal power P_n of the IM can be expressed as:

$$T_L = T_{IM} = K_{pump} \cdot \Omega^2 \tag{2}$$

$$P_n = K_{pump} \cdot \Omega^3 \tag{3}$$

Table III lists the parameters of the used IM with the pump [20].

TABLE III. PARAMETERS OF THE IM WITH THE PUMP

Parameters	Values
Nominal power (P_n)	1.5 Kw
Input power (P_a)	Around 2 KW
Speed (N_n) / frequency	1400 Rpm / 50 Hz
Pole pairs (P)	2
Voltage (V_n)	$\Delta 220$ V / $\Delta 380$ V
Current (I_n)	$\Delta 6$ A / $\Delta 3.5$ A
K_{pump}	47.6×10^{-5}

Fig. 6. IM coupled to a centrifugal pump.

III. SIZING OF DC-BUS ELEMENTS

The input DC-bus voltage (V_{dc}) and the capacitors of the MVSC-5L are determined based on the nominal parameters of the IM and the PV array.

A. DC-Bus Voltage

Equation (4) shows the expression that determines the minimum value of V_{dc} , where V_{L-L} is the line voltage across the IM terminals:

$$V_{dc-min} = \sqrt{2} \cdot V_{L-L} \tag{4}$$

Considering the IM voltage to be 380 V (star connected), the range of V_{dc} must be greater than 537 V. According to Table I, the power from the selected PV array must exceed the input power (P_a) of the IM. To achieve this, the system was designed with 31 PV connected in series. As a result, the total rating was 2.79 KW, which was higher than P_a . Therefore, the obtained V_{mpp} was 595 V, which was the selected V_{dc} reference. This was confirmed, as V_{mpp} and I_{mpp} reach approximately 80% and 90% of V_{oc} and I_{sc} , respectively [18].

B. DC-Bus Capacitors

The DC-bus capacitors provide energy stability during transients, such as a decrease in irradiance, temperature, and load. Their values are determined using [16]:

$$\frac{1}{2} C_{dc} (V_{dc}^2 - V_{dc1}^2) = 3\alpha t V_p I_p \tag{5}$$

where V_{dc} is the DC-bus voltage (595 V), V_{dc1} is the minimum voltage during the transient (575 V), α is an overloading factor (1.3), and t is the duration of the transient (0.005 s). I_p is the IM phase current (3.5 A), and V_p is the phase voltage (220 V). Thus, the calculated value was approximately 1000 μ F.

IV. CONTROL OF THE PV SYSTEM

Figure 7 shows the applied control for the single-stage PV system. The objective was to extract the maximum power from the PV array and drive the pump with optimal torque through V/f control of the IM.

Fig. 7. PV system with the adopted control.

A. MPPT and Power Control Blocks

The voltage V_{pv} and current I_{pv} were measured and fed into the Perturb and Observe (P&O) MPPT algorithm block shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Flowchart of the P&O MPPT method.

By perturbing V_{pv} , the reference voltage $V_{mpp-Ref}$ was adjusted to 595V (V_{dc}) using a PI controller. The resulting signal was the reference frequency f_1 . Based on the pump characteristics, as described in (3) and approximated in [21], a frequency f_2 was derived from the power of the PV array. The reference speed N_{ref} of the rotor was calculated using (6), where p represents the pole pairs of the induction motor.

$$N_{ref} = \frac{f_{ref} \times 60}{p} = \frac{(f_1 + f_2) \times 60}{p} \tag{6}$$

B. Speed and Scalar V/f Control Blocks

The speed (N) of the IM was sensed and compared with the calculated N_{ref} . The PI controller adjusted the error and produced the signal gN_s . Subsequently, the synchronous speed N_s was determined according to (7), where g represents the slip.

$$N_s = gN_s + N \tag{7}$$

The synchronous frequency f_s was input into the V/f block. A linear profile was established for rated values of 380V/50Hz. To achieve this, the line voltage was proportional to the frequency ($V_{L-L} \propto f$), as shown in Figure 9 [22]. The gating pulses for the MVSC-5L were then generated using the SPWM technique.

Fig. 9. Linear V/f profile.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

The studied PV system was simulated on PSIM Software and assessed with variable irradiance and temperature levels, resembling a typical daily climate scenario, as shown in Figure 10. The profiles ranged from 257 to 922 W/m² and from 23 to 25°C, while the carrier signal frequency was set to 4 KHz.

Fig. 10. Irradiance and temperature profiles.

Figures 11-13 show the results obtained during the chosen scenario, and Table IV provides a comparison of the current THD and torque of the PV system between the MVSC-5L and a conventional three-phase H-bridge inverter (VSC) [23]. Figure 11 shows that the DC-bus voltage is adjusted to the desired value (595 V) by the MPPT block controller. The current from the PV array reaches its maximum in the range of [1.15 – 4.32 A] with each variation. Consequently, the power generated by the PV array ($V_{pv} \times I_{pv}$) matches the optimal power P_{Vopt} . Figure 12 shows that the rotor speed N follows the reference speed N_{ref} within the range of 1020 - 1560 rpm. Consequently, the derived frequency f_{sin} for the SPWM varies between 35.5 and 57.5 Hz.

Fig. 11. PV side results: V_{pv} (V), I_{pv} (A), and Power (W).

Fig. 12. Control side results: N_{ref} (rpm), N (rpm), and f_{sin} (Hz).

Figure 13 shows that the AC voltages in the IM exhibit five levels per line (U_{AB}) and nine levels per phase (V_{An}) with variable frequency and RMS values. The line voltage varies between 279 and 410 V. AC currents have a sinusoidal shape with variable RMS values in the interval of 2.37 - 4.56 A. The

torque T_L varies according to the rotor speed from 5.4 to 12.7 N.m, which validates the main achievement of the applied control. During the time interval from 4 to 6 s, f_{sin} is equal to 49.6 Hz, the rotor speed is 1387 rpm, and the RMS values of line voltage and current are 379 V and 3.53 A, respectively. This result confirms the operation of the IM under nominal conditions.

Fig. 13. Motor side results: U_{AB} (V), V_{An} (A), i_a , i_b , and i_c (A), and T_L (N.m).

TABLE IV. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF THE MVSC-5V WITH THE CONVENTIONAL VSC

Irradiance (W/m ²)	MVSC-5L		Classic VSC	
	T_L (N.m)	THD of i_A (%)	T_L (N.m)	THD of i_A (%)
257	5.41	1.67	5.45	5.46
453	8.00	1.38	8.00	2.48
629	10.00	1.38	10.00	2.32
771	11.42	1.59	11.40	2.31
871	12.29	2.03	12.27	2.69
922	12.70	2.18	12.68	2.65

From Table IV, it is evident that the studied PV system exhibits better performance in terms of torque and current THD compared to the basic VSC. The system effectively tracks the maximum power from solar panels, stabilizes the DC-bus voltage, and provides mechanical and electrical energy to the pump regardless of climate conditions. This results in improved water flow, reduced machine losses, and a positive overall impact on system performance. Compared to the control methods in [24-25], the results are notable and affirm the benefits and advantages of using multilevel inverters in PV pumping systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced the structure of a single-stage three-phase multilevel inverter for a PV pumping system, using a

new topology with a minimal number of switches and a straightforward modulation technique. An MPPT algorithm was applied using the scalar V/f method, and a comprehensive description of the control strategy was provided. A variable climate scenario was evaluated with the PV system, and its performance was analyzed through simulation. The topology studied demonstrated its ability to track maximum power using the P&O method, regulate input voltage, and provide the water pump motor with optimal power flow. In the five-level version, both the THD of currents and torque performance outperformed the conventional structure. This topology can be considered an attractive solution for pumping systems that combines both performance and cost-effectiveness. In future work, the proposed system will be further developed by testing other control strategies, with the possibility of implementing a hardware setup.

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Implementation of a Finite Impulse Response Filter using PUFs to Avoid Trojans

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ABSTRACT

In the modern era of signal processing, digital filters play an important role in real-time applications such as communication, consumer electronics, digital signal processing, audio, etc. In digital filter design, Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filters are highly preferable due to their linear phase and inherent stability. These filters benefit from being time-invariant and simple to implement with minimal computational requirements. Therefore, the hardware security of FIR filters is essential for good performance and reliable results. On the other hand, there is the possibility of hardware threats, such as tampering, reverse engineering, hardware Trojans, etc., as the design of an FIR filter involves many stages. Such hardware attacks on FIR filters can cause several problems, including performance degradation, leakage of confidential information, lack of stability, etc. This study presents the design and implementation of a Trojan-aware FIR filter using Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs). The key feature of PUFs is that they generate a unique and unpredictable response for each given challenge. In the proposed design, PUFs were used to generate the FIR filter coefficients that are unique and unpredictable by attackers/trojans to improve security. The security of FIR with PUF was tested using ML-based challenges, and the results showed approximately 30% more reliability and consistency compared to the FIR without PUFs.

Keywords-Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter; hardware threats; Physical Unclonable Functions (PUF); hardware trojan; hardware security

I. INTRODUCTION

The process of placing thousands of transistors on a single chip to create an Integrated Circuit (IC) is known as Very Large-Scale Integration (VLSI). Electronic circuits can consist of RAM, ROM, CPU, and other combinatorial logic elements, and VLSI allows an IC designer to incorporate all of them into a single chip [1]. As the integration density increases with advancements in device and CAD technology, the threat of IC malfunctions at different abstraction levels increases at a huge pace and quantity [2]. There are many hardware threats, such as reverse engineering, tampering, hardware trojans, etc. A hardware trojan is a malicious modification of circuitry. Hardware security aims to counteract these trojans by securing the hardware component of the IC design against unauthorized access. Hardware security is critical as it lays the foundation for the entire system to run. There are many attempts in progress to make the hardware blocks more secure.

There are many hardware security techniques, such as obfuscation, hardware-based cryptography, physical tamper resistance, randomization, and Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) that can be used against attacks. PUFs and True Random Number Generators (TRNGs) are the primary primitives. A PUF has the advantage of being compatible with minimal computational resources over the classical cryptography types [2]. PUF is a hardware security method that generates a unique and unpredictable output. The main application of PUFs is low-cost, as authentication uses Strong PUFs and secret-key generation uses weak PUFs [3]. PUFs have many benefits due to their uniqueness, unpredictable nature, low power consumption, scalability, and other qualities. PUFs come in a variety of forms, including SRAM PUF, Arbiter PUF, Ring Oscillator PUF, Butterfly PUF, etc. This study selected Butterfly PUF due to its simplicity and robustness [4].

This study investigated the design of a secure Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter since it is the basic building block in almost every signal processing application. FIR and Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) filters are two different categories of digital filters that both have benefits and drawbacks of their own. However, FIR filters are frequently used in the design of digital filters due to their linear phase and stability [5]. FIR filters can be implemented as specialized hardware, such as Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) [6-7]. A digital filter with an FIR is one whose impulse response has a finite duration and settles to zero in a finite amount of time. Compared to IIR filters, FIR filters are different because they have linear phase, unconditional stability, and easy implementation. FIR filters are extensively used in many applications such as signal processing, image processing, biomedical signal processing, etc. [8-9]. A general FIR filter equation can be expressed as:

$$Y(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} w(k) \cdot x(n-k) \quad (1)$$

II. RELATED WORKS

The VLSI sector has undergone numerous changes in recent decades, including the breakdown of Integrated Device Manufacturers (IDMs) into foundries [1]. Due to the increasing growth in the size and complexity of the VLSI design, it became challenging to achieve the speed and quality requirements of the IC design. As a result, in [10], an effective model for quick floor planning was presented in the VLSI top-down physical design flow that used active logic reduction technology to accelerate the design flow while reducing internal logic units and maintaining design quality. Logic optimization is the process of finding an equivalent representation of the logic circuit within predetermined constraints and is crucial to VLSI design. Logic optimization is carried out at the gate level in normal custom and semi-custom design flows by converting the input truth table into Boolean values. The streamlined gate logic is used to infer the final transistor netlist that will be organized on a chip. In [11], a genetic method was presented for the gateless VLSI design to eliminate the intermediate gate-level optimization phase and produce optimized transistor netlists. Due to the growing complexity of the semiconductor industry, traditional rule-based technologies cannot address the issues of Electronic Design Automation (EDA). Machine learning (ML), which is expanding rapidly and has recently been incorporated into EDA applications [12], can be used as a remedy for this. Integrating CAD tools with the algorithm design environment to produce hardware designs can be used effectively in the design of VLSI communication systems [13]. Digital Signal Processing (DSP) systems rely heavily on filters, which are also frequently used in VLSI design. A digital filter with a finite period of impulse response is known as an FIR filter. In [8], several design strategies and the necessary parameters for the implementation of FIR were discussed.

As several medicinal applications, signal processing applications, de-noising applications, etc., use FIR filters, designing an effective FIR filter with low power consumption and high speed is crucial. In [9], an effective implementation of FIR filters with high-speed adders was presented for signal-processing applications. In [7], the register minimization

retiming technique was used to design an effective filter. The design of low-complexity FIR filters has been the focus of active study over the past 20 years. Current methods for integrating the removal of common subexpressions with the synthesis of filter coefficients are primarily based on bit-width truncation, which raises the implementation cost. In [14], a brand new cost-aware sensitivity-driven method was proposed for the design of FIR filters. In [15], a straightforward and effective design for variable fractional delay FIR filters was presented. Hardware security and trust have become a major security concern as the semiconductor supply chain has become globalized. In [16-17], the security lifecycle for hardware technologies was discussed to explore hardware security, vulnerabilities, trojans, reverse engineering, and other hazards. In [18], an overview of Trojan detection and prevention methods for hardware security was presented. Hardware trojan detection has proven to be extremely difficult due to the improvement of numerous entities in the VLSI design cycle. In [19], a novel algorithm was presented that used netlists of legitimate and trojan-injected circuits to find harmful nets. Recently proposed Trojan horse detection techniques rely on Trojan horse activation to look for false outputs or other measurable abnormal side-channel signals. From an authentication perspective, the time to activate the hardware Trojan circuit is a big issue. In [20], a method was presented to improve hardware Trojan detection and reduce the startup time of Trojans.

As hardware-based security primitives are crucial to a system's protection, it is becoming essential to protect sensitive data as well as the underlying technology. A PUF has the advantage of being compatible with minimal computational resources over the present classical cryptography types. In [2], the effective design, implementation, and analysis of these hardware-based security primitives were described. In [21], PUF circuits were proposed to create unique and reliable signatures for certain electronic circuits. In [22], the security of the IoT framework was thoroughly examined. In [23], the design of feedforward XOR PUFs (FFXOR-PUFs) was presented, where each component PUF used an FF to create an FFPUF. In [24], various homogeneous and heterogeneous FFXOR PUFs were presented and evaluated. A new classification for reconfigurable PUFs (RPUFs) was presented, namely Algorithm-based RPUF (A-RPUF) and Circuit-based RPUF (C-RPUF), and two XOR-based RPUF circuits and an XOR-based Reconfigurable Ring Oscillator PUF (XRRO PUF) were proposed. The two primary subtypes of PUFs are Strong and Weak PUFs. In [3], strong PUF implementations and their use for low-cost authentication were described along with weak PUF implementations and their use in key generation applications. Additionally, this study explored error correction techniques like pattern matching and index-based coding. In [25], a SEC-DED RAM system was proposed, where a Built-In Self-Test (BIST) and a repairing scheme (STAR) were used to make it fault-tolerant and dynamically reconfigurable. In [26], reversible gates, such as Feynman, Peres, and Toffoli gates, were used to design a concurrent detectable carry select adder that can detect faults. In [27], security issues were addressed at the device level.

As the literature review showed that there is no current design for a secured FIR filter, this study focused on the PUF-based trojan-aware FIR filter implementation.

III. METHODOLOGY

A physical unclonable FIR filter was chosen due to its wide use in signal processing applications, where MAC units play a vital role [28]. The unique fingerprint generated by a PUF is derived from the inherent physical variations in the hardware components such that it cannot be duplicated or cloned. PUFs have many benefits due to their uniqueness, unpredictable nature, low power consumption, and scalability. PUFs come in a variety of forms, including SRAM PUF, Arbiter PUF, Ring Oscillator PUF, Butterfly PUF, etc. Butterfly PUF has high reliability, which makes it hard for attackers to clone the device, and is simple in its architecture and implementation.

A. Effect of Trojan on the FIR filter

Assume an FIR filter designed for an X band of frequency. The response depends on the weights of the filter (coefficient). If $c1$, $c2$, and $c3$ define the $f1$ frequency, $c1d$, $c2d$, and $c3d$ may not produce the same frequency $f1$. If the coefficients change ∂c , then frequency also may vary by ∂f . The change in the coefficient may be caused due to some Trojans. Therefore, it is evident that PUFs can be used to secure the filter response from the Trojans in the coefficient space.

B. Design of a General FIR Filter

The proposed PUF FIR filter was developed as shown in Figure 1, following these steps: (a) Design a general FIR filter, (b) generation of coefficients from the Butterfly PUF, and (c) mapping of the generated coefficients to the designed FIR filter.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the proposed filter.

A basic 4-tap FIR filter was designed using the Verilog Hardware Description Language (HDL). The FIR filter works by convolving the input signal with a set of filter coefficients or taps to produce the filtered output, as shown in Figure 2. Initially, the input signal is sampled at regular intervals to obtain a discrete-time signal. The sampled input signal is then multiplied by a set of filter coefficients, which are predetermined and stored in the filter. The products of the input samples and the filter coefficients are added together, producing a sum. The sum obtained is the output, i.e. the filtered signal for that input sample. After the filtered output is obtained, the input samples are shifted by one position, and the process is repeated with the new input sample.

Fig. 2. Basic FIR filter.

A Trojan could be in the coefficients path, where the change in coefficients may change the entire response. Therefore, to protect this path, a secured hardware block can be used to generate the coefficients and prevent any Trojan from being able to damage the filter response.

C. Generation of Coefficients from the Butterfly PUF

PUFs are devised by generating the security key and considering the unique characteristics inherent in a physical device [13]. The physical properties of silicon devices are determined by exploring a set of inputs (challenges) and a set of outputs (responses). PUFs can also be used in extracting the signature of chips, device authentication, IP protection, seeding a Pseudo-Random Number Generator (PRNG), securing IPs, etc. [6-9, 15]. Most FPGA PUFs are delay-based working around the race conditions, frequency variations found in IC, and meta-stability [14, 16]. PUF architectures are classified as strong and weak [5, 17]. Strong PUFs can be used in authentication directly due to the richness of Challenge-Response Pairs (CRPs), making it impossible for the attacker to modify the CRPs in a restricted time frame [18]. However, weak PUFs limited numbers of CRPs and can be used to generate cryptographic keys in PRNG, protect IPs, and identity generation. In these weak PUFs, an attacker cannot access the response, as these responses must be kept private [18]. Here, the proposed hybrid PUF architecture is claimed to be inefficient on weak PUFs as a result of the CRP limitation.

Fig. 3. Butterfly PUF.

Figure 3 shows the architecture of a Butterfly PUF to generate the unique coefficients for the FIR filter that act as

security keys for the filter. Initially, the exciting signal is set to high to begin the operation of the Butterfly PUF. The butterfly PUF circuit reaches an unstable operating point because the input and output of both latches are opposite signals. The excite signal is set low after a few clock pulses. This initiates the transition of the PUF circuit to one of two stable states, 0 or 1, of the output signal. A Butterfly PUF can generate a single bit, i.e. 0 or 1, for a single clock pulse. The output of the PUF for 8 clock pulses is obtained since 8-bit data are needed, and it is then placed in a register so that it can be used as a coefficient for the FIR filter. Four 8-bit coefficients are produced by four 4-Butterfly PUFs for a 4-tap FIR Filter, and N-Butterfly PUFs are needed for an N-tap FIR Filter. Figure 5 presents the different sets of coefficients generated using these PUFs.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the secured FIR filter - Secured Coefficient generation through PUFs.

Fig. 5. Four different sets of coefficients.

D. Mapping the Generated Coefficients to the Designed FIR Filter

The generated coefficients of the Butterfly PUF are given to the designed FIR filter, as indicated in Figure 4. After applying these coefficients to the filter, it performs a convolution operation to produce the filtered output, i.e. the coefficients will be multiplied with the input signal and then all the products will be added together to produce a sum, which is the output of the FIR Filter. Let the generated coefficients of the Butterfly PUF for a 4-tap FIR Filter be W_0 , W_1 , W_2 , and W_3 and the input be $x(n)$. Then the output equation of the 4-tap FIR Filter can be written as:

$$Y = W_0 X(n) + W_1 X(n - 1) + W_2 X(n - 2) + W_3 X(n - 3) \quad (2)$$

As the coefficients generated from the Butterfly PUF are unique, it is difficult to replicate or reverse engineer the filter. This combination of security and uniqueness makes PUF-based FIR filters more secure, and they can be used for applications such as secure signal processing, cryptographic key generation, and secure communication.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

The proposed design was implemented on an Xilinx Vivado, targeting Artix 7 FPGAs. Figure 6 shows the results obtained by simulating the design of the Butterfly PUF. Figure 7 shows the results of the simulated FIR filter, which was examined with different coefficients to check its consistency, proving its suitability for being a valid candidate to avoid any type of Trojan attacks with the help of PUFs.

Fig. 6. (a) Schematic and (b) output of the butterfly PUF.

Tables I and II show the cell utilization, where it is evident that the utilization did not increase significantly with the introduction of the PUF circuitry. Security was further validated by applying 1000 ML attacks iteratively 10 times. The proposed PUF FIR design can negate hardware overhead with a decent security improvement. Figure 7 shows the schematic of the designed PUF FIR filter. Figure 8 shows the corresponding slice using VIVADO 2016.1, which was drawn from the block diagram shown in Figure 4. Figure 9 presents the corresponding output of the FIR filter for the different sets of coefficients shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 7. FIR Schematic diagram.

Fig. 8. FIR Slice using VIVADO 2016.1.

Fig. 9. FIR outputs for different sets of coefficients (Figure 5): (a) Set 1, (b) Set 2, (c) Set 3, and (d) Set 4.

TABLE I. CELL USAGE REPORT

Cell	COUNT
BUFG	1
CARRY4	30
LUT2	48
LUT4	4
FDRE	16
IBUF	1
OBUF	24

TABLE II. UTILIZATION REPORT

Block	With PUF		Without PUF		% overhead
	Used	Available	Used	Available	
Slice LUTs*	48	63400	36	63400	25
Logic LUTs	48	63400	36	63400	25
Slice Registers	16	126800	16	126800	0
Registers as Flip Flop	16	126800	16	126800	0
Bonded IOB	25	210	25	210	0

Furthermore, two important performance metrics, Uniqueness (UQ) and Reliability were defined and summarized. The ideal value of uniqueness is 50%. Here, X_i and X_j are the respective n -bit responses of the i -th and j -th chips for the same challenge C , and uniqueness is expressed as the average inter-chip Hamming Distance (HD) among p devices.

$$uniqueness = \frac{2}{p(p-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^p \frac{HD(X_i, X_j)}{n} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

Reliability (RE) is the measure of consistency in the responses generated by the PUF.

$$HD_{INTRA_i} = \frac{1}{s} \sum_{t=1}^s \frac{HD(X_i, X_{i,t})}{n} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$Reliability_i = 100\% - HD_{INTRA_i} \quad (5)$$

$$Average Reliability = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{i=1}^p Reliability_i \quad (6)$$

The ideal value of reliability is 100%, and for HD_{INTRA} is 0%. Here, X_i is the reference response of the i -th chip, $X_{i,t}$ is the current response at time t , and s is the number of responses for similar challenges. Table III presents the effect of different sets of coefficients. Different coefficients were considered for the filter, and their Reliability and Uniqueness were observed to be similar. Although uniqueness is appreciated, some effort is needed to retrieve the original data from the different coefficients. Every time, there is a possibility of changing coefficients. However, the overall response may not change, as shown in Table III and the different response curves in Figure 9.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE METRICS.

Design	Reliability	Uniqueness
Ideal Value	100%	50%
Set 1	98.34	49.00
Set 2	98.57	49.24
Set 3	99.19	48.10
Set 4	98.01	49.10

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a secure design of FIR filters using PUFs. As PUFs generate unique responses, it is difficult to replicate, clone, or reverse engineer the filter. Here, the coefficients generated from the PUF act as a secret key for the FIR filter, which is unpredictable. Therefore, the security of the FIR filter is improved, making it secure from hardware Trojans or other hardware attacks. Security was further validated by iteratively applying several ML attacks, showing around 30% consistency. The proposed design with PUFs can negate the hardware overhead of around 25% with decent security

improvement. Therefore, PUFs offer a promising approach to hardware security, as they provide a means of generating unique and unpredictable responses that are resistant to many types of hardware attacks. This study can be extended to improve security to different communication modules such as OFDM and MIMO blocks, where, the frequency selection may be vulnerable to hardware threats.

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Deep Learning Approach: YOLOv5-based Custom Object Detection

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ABSTRACT

Object detection is of significant importance in the field of computer vision, since it has extensive applications across many sectors. The emergence of YOLO (You Only Look Once) has brought about substantial changes in this domain with the introduction of real-time object identification with exceptional accuracy. The YOLOv5 architecture is highly sought after because of its increased flexibility and computational efficiency. This research provides an in-depth analysis of implementing YOLOv5 for object identification. This research delves deeply into the architectural improvements and design ideas that set YOLOv5 apart from its predecessors to illuminate its unique benefits. This research examines the training process and the efficiency of transfer learning techniques, among other things. The detection skills of YOLOv5 may be greatly improved by including these features. This study suggests the use of YOLOv5, a state-of-the-art object identification framework, as a crucial tool in the field of computer vision for accurate object recognition. The results of the proposed framework demonstrate higher performance in terms of mAP (60.9%) when evaluated with an IoU criterion of 0.5 and when compared to current methodologies in terms of reliability, computing flexibility, and mean average precision. These advantages make it applicable in many real-world circumstances.

Keywords-computer vision; object detection; deep learning; YOLOv5

I. INTRODUCTION

The identification and localization of objects inside pictures or videos is a crucial challenge in the field of computer vision. The subject matter has garnered considerable interest as a result of its extensive array of practical uses, including autonomous vehicular navigation, surveillance technology, robotic systems, and augmented reality experiences. Numerous object identification algorithms encounter challenges in properly detecting tiny items while demonstrating satisfactory performance on bigger objects. Small objects are entities that possess a limited pixel area or field of vision within an input picture. The aforementioned concern emerges due to the tendency of generic object detectors to assign more priority to the characteristics of bigger objects when they traverse numerous levels of their underlying architecture. The identification of diminutive entities poses several obstacles, such as subpar visual characteristics, restricted contextual data, noisy depiction, indiscernible attributes, intricate backdrops, restricted resolution, substantial occlusion, etc. [1]. Real-time object detection systems often favor computing speed above resource utilization. However, their performance in terms of detection accuracy is generally subpar, making them unsuitable for many practical uses. In the domain of autonomous driving, the detection of objects on the roadway is an essential undertaking. Conventional road object detection systems often

demonstrate less accuracy in detecting tiny things. This stems from the fact that smaller objects tend to occupy a smaller number of pixels, hence posing difficulties in extracting significant information from representations with low resolution. As a result, the models have a tendency to erroneously classify tiny items as part of the background, resulting in failure to identify or incorrectly detect such things [2]. In addition, the task of reliably identifying things of varying sizes is a substantial obstacle for object detection algorithms. In the context of autonomous driving, little items include road signs and traffic signals. It has been proposed that enhancing the network's representational capacity via increased depth and breadth may lead to improved accuracy. However, it is important to note that this strategy also results in increased model complexity and cost. Consequently, these models are not well suited for self-driving cars with real-time requirements and limited resources. The models used by deep learning for object identification may be classified into two main categories: two-stage and one-stage detection techniques [3]. Two-stage models provide superior accuracy, at the cost of reduced speed and increased complexity, hence diminishing their practicality in driving circumstances. Current research has been dedicated to enhancing the performance of one-stage models [1, 3], resulting in the creation of many novel one-stage detectors specifically suited for real-world usage.

The work at hand focuses on a widely used one-stage object detection model called You Only Look Once version 5 (YOLOv5) [4]. YOLO is regarded as a very significant and extensively used method for object identification. The YOLO algorithm has significantly advanced the field of object detection by approaching it as a cohesive job, hence facilitating real-time inference while achieving remarkable levels of accuracy, with YOLOv5 being the latest iteration within the YOLO lineage, distinguished by its well-defined and adaptable architecture, with the primary objective of attaining superior performance and rapidity on widely available platforms. Nevertheless, the systems that use YOLOv5 mostly depend on traditional training methodologies, regularization, and normalization approaches, or parameter tuning to improve performance, often neglecting architectural alterations. Although YOLOv5 serves as a versatile object detector, its optimization does not especially cater to the identification of tiny objects. Consequently, its applicability to real scenarios is limited [5].

This research presents a comprehensive analysis of the architectural components of YOLOv5, specifically focusing on its backbone, neck, and head networks. These networks collaborate harmoniously to facilitate the accurate identification and spatial positioning of objects. In addition, we examine the training procedure of YOLOv5, which includes essential stages such as data preprocessing, model refinement, and hyperparameter adjustment. Furthermore, an examination is conducted on the primary methodologies used in the process of inference, encompassing bounding box forecasting and post-processing strategies such as non-maximum suppression. Through a complete examination of these characteristics, our objective is to provide a clear knowledge of the internal mechanisms of YOLOv5 and its fundamental elements in the context of object detection.

II. PROPOSED YOLOV5-BASED OBJECT DETECTION

There is an increasing demand for artificially intelligent systems able to conduct real-time object identification and recognition on resource-constrained devices in the age of IoT (Internet of Things) and edge computing. Our research is motivated by the actual applications of such technology, which include surveillance, autonomous robots, and a variety of other scenarios in which embedded devices must make intelligent judgments based on visual data. On the other hand, embedded devices frequently have constrained processing resources, memory, and power consumption. Driven by such limitations, we intend to create an effective object identification method capable of operating successfully within these limits. The primary emphasis of our study is centered on the training and inference of object detection using the YOLOv5 tiny model. The problem of object detection has significant importance in the field of computer vision, since tailoring the model to particular items or domains may significantly improve its performance and practicality in real-world situations. We used the YOLOv5 tiny model (Figure 1), which presents a harmonious trade-off between the dimensions of the model and its precision. This condensed iteration is appropriate for

situations with limited resources or applications that need real-time processing.

During the training phase, the tailored strategy is used. We compiled a dataset including distinct items that are pertinent to our designated application. The dataset potentially comprises of annotated photos or videos, whereby bounding box annotations are used to indicate the positions of objects. We strive to provide a sufficient quantity of examples that include a wide range of object modifications, orientations, and backgrounds. Subsequently, the YOLOv5 tiny model is subjected to fine-tuning using our customized dataset. The process of fine-tuning entails the initialization of the model with pre-existing weights, followed by training it on our dataset to acquire knowledge unique to the item identification task at hand. Transfer learning methods are used in order to enhance the training process and enhance the performance of the model by using the information acquired during pre-training on a substantial dataset. Throughout the training procedure, hyperparameters, including learning rate, batch size, and regularization approaches, are fine-tuned in order to get optimal outcome. In addition, data augmentation methods, including random cropping, rotation, and scaling, were used to enhance the resilience and variety of the training samples.

Fig. 1. The proposed object detection framework.

After the completion of the training process, the subsequent step involves transitioning to the inference phase. During this stage, the trained YOLOv5 tiny model is used to identify items inside novel and unobserved photos or videos. The model undertakes the processing of the incoming data and produces predictions of bounding boxes, along with the appropriate probability of class membership for each discovered item. Techniques such as non-maximum suppression are used to eliminate overlapping or duplicate detections, therefore preserving just the most confident and accurate ones. The use of our proprietary object identification technique using the YOLOv5 tiny model has several benefits. By customizing the model to our particular targets of interest, we may enhance the precision of detection and improve its ability to apply to real-world situations. Furthermore, the tiny dimensions of YOLOv5 facilitate effective implementation on edge devices or when the computing resources are restricted. In summary, this study showcases the efficacy of object detection training and inference using the tiny YOLOv5 model, enabling researchers and practitioners to effectively tackle object detection difficulties and devise precise and efficient solutions.

A. YOLOv5 Tiny

YOLOv5 tiny is a modified version of the YOLOv5 object detection model that provides a trade-off between the size of the model and its detection capabilities. The primary objective of its design is to provide a comparatively more streamlined and effective solution in contrast to the bulkier iterations of YOLOv5, while also maintaining commendable levels of detection accuracy. The term "tiny" pertains to its diminished model size, which is accomplished by using diverse architectural optimizations and network scaling strategies. The objective of these improvements is to reduce the quantity of parameters and computing demands of the model, rendering it more suited for deployment on devices with limited resources or situations where real-time performance is of utmost importance [4]. Despite its reduced dimensions, YOLOv5 tiny effectively preserves the essential components and concepts inherent in the YOLOv5 design. The system consists of a primary network, an intermediate network, and a final network, collaborating harmoniously to identify and determine the precise location of objects inside photos or videos. The backbone network is responsible for extracting high-level characteristics from the input data. These features are then further refined by the neck network. Finally, the head network utilizes these refined features to forecast bounding boxes and class probabilities for the identified objects.

The process of training YOLOv5 tiny includes data preparation, model optimization, and hyperparameter tweaking, which aligns with the methodology used in other YOLOv5 versions. In order to do object detection, it is customary to use a dataset that is labeled, consisting of photos or videos that have been tagged with bounding boxes denoting the positions of the objects. Through the process of training on this dataset, YOLOv5 tiny acquires the ability to discover and categorize things that are of significance. During the process of inference, YOLOv5 tiny employs many strategies like bounding box prediction and post-processing processes such as non-maximum suppression in order to provide object detections that are both accurate and dependable. The system performs real-time processing of incoming photos or videos, generating predictions of bounding boxes and corresponding probability for the identified items.

In general, YOLOv5 tiny offers a somewhat lighter and more efficient alternative for object detection assignments when compared to its bigger counterparts within the YOLOv5 framework. This technology is especially well-suited for use cases in which there are constraints on processing resources or a need for real-time performance, all while maintaining a high level of detection accuracy. In this study, after fine-tuning the model to process the custom dataset, the YOLOv5s contains 214 layers, 7033114 parameters and gradients, and 16 GFLOPs.

B. Dataset

The Vehicles-OpenImages dataset [6] is a publicly accessible dataset that has been deliberately curated to concentrate on cars. The subset in question is derived from the dataset, a comprehensive collection of images that includes annotations for a diverse range of item classifications. It comprises a comprehensive assortment of photographs

showcasing a vast array of vehicles, including various types such as automobiles, trucks, motorbikes, bicycles, and other similar modes of transportation. The collection has annotated bounding boxes that provide information about the precise positioning of automobiles inside each picture.

The inclusion of annotations inside the Vehicles-OpenImages dataset is a valuable resource for academics and developers, as it allows them to effectively train and assess object identification models that are especially designed for the purpose of detecting vehicles. By using this dataset, professionals may construct and optimize models that possess the ability to precisely identify and determine the location of cars in various situations and circumstances. The accessibility of the Vehicles-OpenImages collection enables progress in domains such as autonomous vehicle technology, traffic surveillance, and transportation studies. This dataset may be used to train vehicle detection models that are resilient, hence facilitating the development of applications that depend on precise and effective vehicle identification and tracking.

Fig. 2. Dataset label correlogram.

The correlogram label, as seen in Figure 2, is a visualization method used for examining the interrelationships among labels or classes inside a multi-label categorization scenario. This analysis offers valuable observations into the patterns of co-occurrence and interdependencies among various labels present in a given dataset. This Figure depicts the representation of labels or classes on the x and y axes of a matrix or heatmap. Every individual element inside the matrix denotes the correlation or co-occurrence between a certain pair of labels. The calculation of correlation is often performed with statistical metrics such as mutual information, Jaccard index, or correlation coefficient. The intensity or hue of each cell denotes the magnitude of the correlation between the labels. The presence of a high-intensity or dark-colored cell indicates a robust positive correlation, signifying a high likelihood of co-occurrence between the associated labels. On the contrary, a cell with low intensity or light coloration signifies a diminished

or adverse correlation, suggesting a reduced likelihood of co-occurrence between the five chosen labels (ambulance, bus, car, motorcycle, and truck).

Figure 3(a) depicts a graphical representation illustrating the frequency of annotations per class within the dataset. Figure 3(b) illustrates the spatial distribution and dimensions of the bounding boxes within the dataset. This analysis aids in comprehending the distribution patterns of the bounding boxes within the dataset, so ensuring the presence of enough diversity in object location and size for effective recognition by the model. Figures 3(c)-(d) depict the statistical distribution of the location and the size of the bounding boxes, respectively, providing insight of the distribution patterns of the bounding boxes throughout the dataset. This graph facilitates the assessment of the distribution of bounding boxes, indicating if there is an equal distribution or whether some regions of the dataset exhibit a higher concentration. It is crucial to ensure that the model is capable of accurately recognizing items inside a picture, since objects exhibit variations in both size and location. Figure 4 represents a sample of the dataset that contains 627 images divided into five classes.

Fig. 3. (a) Dataset's graphical representation of the number of annotations per class, (b) size and location of each bounding box, (c) statistical distribution of the bounding box position, and (d) statistical distribution of the bounding box size.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation Metrics

Model assessment is significant in evaluating its performance and its alignment with the research goals. Various assessment metrics may be used in the context of object identification, including criteria pertaining to the precision, swiftness, and efficacy of the model. The primary emphasis on recognizing objects often is on evaluation metrics pertaining to accuracy, since it is essential for the model to possess the

capability of accurately identifying buses. Precision (P) and recall (R) are often used as fundamental assessment criteria [7,8]. R quantifies the model's ability to accurately identify positive classifications. In addition to P and R, there are other assessment metrics that are often used in the context of object identification, namely Average Precision (AP) and mean Average Precision (mAP). The AP metric quantifies the model's ability to accurately identify pertinent things while excluding extraneous ones. It is determined by graphing the precision-recall curve and computing the area under the curve. mAP, conversely, is the arithmetic mean of the APs calculated for each individual object class detected by the model [10], whereas mAP offers a more thorough assessment of the model's performance since it evaluates the accuracy across all object classes, rather than focusing just on a single class. These metrics are described by the following equations:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (1)$$

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (2)$$

$$AP = \int_0^1 P(r) dr \quad (3)$$

$$mAP = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k AP_i}{k} \quad (4)$$

where TP stands for True Positive, FP for False Positive, and FN for False Negative.

Fig. 4. Dataset sample.

B. Training Results

The training process of the proposed framework for custom object detection employs a stochastic gradient descent with learning rate of 0.01, batch size of 16, 100 epochs, 439 images for the training set, and 125 images for the validation set. Figure 5 illustrates the training performances of the proposed framework, which is based on YOLOv5s. Despite the YOLOv5s model's parameter count of around 7 million, the achieved outcomes demonstrate a high level of efficiency. The whole training procedure was accomplished within a time frame of around 0.41 hours, using a mid-range GPU. The YOLOv5s model demonstrated a mAP of 60.9% when

evaluated using an IoU criterion of 0.5. This finding suggests that the model has the capability to effectively identify and pinpoint objects with a notable level of accuracy. Furthermore, when considering a broader spectrum of IoU thresholds ranging from 0.5 to 0.95, the model exhibited mAP values of 44%. This indicates that the model has the capability to sustain a relatively elevated level of performance even when confronted with diverse degrees of overlap between predicted and actual bounding boxes. The aforementioned findings underscore the efficacy and proficiency of the suggested framework using YOLOv5s for the purpose of object detection assignments. Despite its comparatively smaller dimensions in relation to bigger YOLOv5 variations, the model exhibits robust performance, making it well-suited for real-time applications or situations characterized by constrained computing resources.

Fig. 5. Loss and mAP results.

Fig. 6. Precision-confidence results.

The precision-confidence results, as indicated in Figure 6, pertain to the evaluation of the accuracy of object identification predictions across various confidence levels. When assessing object detection models, it is customary to examine several confidence criteria in order to ascertain the accuracy of the detected objects. In this particular instance, the precision-confidence outcomes reveal that every class attained a precision value of 1 (100%) when subjected to a confidence threshold of 0.975, which is considered to be high. This indicates that all predictions made by the method with a confidence greater than 0.975 were either accurate or qualified

as genuine positives. For a given confidence level, a precision value of 1 means that no FP detections occurred for any of the classes. The model is doing well and can be trusted to make correct predictions when the accuracy metric displays a high value and the confidence threshold is set to a high level. In situations where a low rate of false positives is critical, this indicates that the model can give highly trustworthy detections.

By analyzing the precision-recall curve, in Figure 7, it is important to evaluate the effectiveness of the model by considering its performance at different levels of confidence thresholds. A greater level of accuracy is indicative of a reduced occurrence of false positives, but a higher recall value implies a decreased occurrence of false negatives. The determination of the ideal trade-off between accuracy and recall is contingent upon the unique demands and preferences of the given application, and may be ascertained by an examination of the form and attributes of the precision-recall curve.

Fig. 7. Precision-recall results.

Fig. 8. Recall-confidence results.

Figure 8 displays the results of the analysis of the relationship between prediction confidence and recall for item identification. The proportion of really positive detections that the model gets right is measured by the recall metric. All classes were able to reach a memory rate of 0.82 (82%) with a

confidence threshold of 0.0, as shown by the presented recall-confidence results. In other words, the model correctly identified TP detections across all classes 82% of the time, without using a confidence threshold. The recall-confidence curve may be used to assess the model's accuracy at different levels of certainty. This helps evaluate how well various levels of confidence are reflected in the trade-off between the number of correctly recognized objects (recall) and the prevalence of false positive identifications (precision). The outcomes of detection of the proposed model are shown in Figure. 9.

Fig. 9. Detection results.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the development of a customized object detection model using the YOLOv5 architecture, with a special focus on addressing the unique issues encountered in the field of autonomous driving. The main objective of our study was to develop a model that is both lightweight and computationally efficient, while maintaining a high level of accuracy. The use of the YOLOv5 architecture allowed us to get optimal outcomes in relation to the dimensions of the model and the computing demands. The architectural design of YOLOv5 achieves a harmonious equilibrium between the intricacy of the model and its ability to accurately recognize objects, rendering it well-suited for deployment in situations with limited computational resources, such as autonomous driving systems. The proposed object identification model exhibited a notable level of precision in identifying and precisely locating things that are pertinent to the activities associated with autonomous driving. The efficacy of the model in carrying out these crucial duties was confirmed by a thorough assessment process. The inherent property of our model being lightweight facilitates expedited inference times, a critical need in time-sensitive applications like autonomous driving.

The current study's shortcomings include the need for additional varied datasets, space limits on full comparison research, and the continued difficulty of meeting real-time needs while managing speed and precision.

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Assessment of ^{222}Rn Radon Concentration and Annual Effective Dose in Drinking Water in Bardarash, Kurdistan Region of Iraq

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine the concentration of radon to assess the radioactive risk in groundwater in Bardarash, Kurdistan region, Iraq, which relies on groundwater as its primary source of water. Fifty samples were collected from wells for water use and were evaluated with RAD7-active Durrige Electronic Detector. Radon concentrations ranged from 0.93 ± 0.43 Bq/l to 11.39 ± 1.86 Bq/l, with a mean of 7.22 Bq/l and a standard deviation of 2.5. The results were used to estimate the annual effective doses of three categories. The annual effective doses of ingestion of groundwater ranged from 14.26 to 174.61 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 110.73 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, 19.02 to 232.81 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 147.67 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, and 4.41 to 54.05 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 34.27 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, for infants, children, and adults, respectively. Furthermore, the annual effective dosage obtained in inhalation ranged from 2.34 to 28.70 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, with an average of 18.20 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$. The total annual effective dose ranged from 16.60 to 203.31 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 128.93 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, 21.35 to 261.51 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 165.84 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, and 6.76 to 82.75 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 52.48 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ for infants, children, and adults, respectively. The majority of the samples had radon concentrations and effective dosages that were less than the maximum permissible limit of 11.1 Bq/l. This indicates that the majority of the samples are drinkable and safe to consume.

Keywords-cancer; radon; annual effective dose; RAD7

I. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a global serious health issue. [1]. In Iraq, almost 80 instances of cancer are discovered for every 100,000 individuals, according to the officials. Medical professionals frequently warn about the rise in cancer incidences across the nation due to pollution, obesity, and other bad behaviors [2]. Cancer is the multistage process in which healthy cells change into tumor cells, often expanding from a precancerous lesion to a malignant tumor. This process may be brought on by biological carcinogens, the effects of age, and physical carcinogens (such as UV and ionizing radiation) or by exposure to recognized chemical carcinogens (such as smoking tobacco, drinking water contaminants, aflatoxin, etc.). Most chemical carcinogens are consumed by drinking tainted water. Heavy metals like arsenic and lead, asbestos, radionuclides like radon and uranium, agricultural chemicals, and hazardous waste are some of the contaminants found in drinking water [3-5].

Water is significant an all-purpose solvent. Given that water is frequently obtained from natural sources like wells, rivers, etc., large amounts of radionuclides including ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra ,

^{232}Th , ^{238}U , and ^{222}Rn have been discovered to have traces in water. Human activities like mining might increase the activity of these radionuclides [6, 7]. The primary theme of this collection is radon, a naturally occurring radioactive gas produced by the decay of ^{238}U . The uranium present in soil progressively degrades to other radionuclides like radium, which over time transforms into radon [8-10]. A small portion of the radium enters the groundwater and remains below the surface. When radon is present in surface or ground waters, it can enter the body by ingestion (drinking contaminated water) or breathing. This radon breaks down into its daughter nuclides during either procedure (ingestion or inhalation), releasing alpha particles that irradiate the cells in the lungs or the stomach, causing them to mutate and ultimately trigger cancer [11, 12].

Iraq is witnessing its greatest water scarcity in a century, according to the Ministry of Water Resources, and 7 million people have less access to the resource, so we must utilize alternative methods to acquire sufficient water. Every

community in the nation has a significant number of wells among these resources [3, 13, 14].

Radon has been linked to lung cancer, and, according to previous studies, is the main cause of lung cancer among non-smokers and the second greatest cause among smokers. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) have classified radon as a human lung carcinogenic [15, 16]. The ICRP also recommends that all countries should conduct radon surveys to identify radon-prone locations. The current study aims to measure radon concentration and dose assessment in well water in Bardarash and compare it with international standards for drinking water use [16].

II. STUDY AREA

The Bardarash region, which is located southeast of Duhok in northern Iraq, has been chosen as the research location for the current investigation. The latitudes 36°30' - 36°55' N and longitudes 43°20' - 43°60' E describe the area's boundaries. Bardarash has a population of about 36,356 people and is divided into three subdistricts: Rovya, Darto, and Kalak.

The GIS techniques are effectively used in assessing and mapping the spatial distribution of chemical parameters and groundwater quality in the selected area. There are many wells in this region, and these wells are the most common source of water in the region and are used for all needs, including drinking (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Map of Bardarash district, displaying the study area.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The location chosen in this study is one of the most suitable areas in the country due to the frequent use of wells as a main source of water. As mentioned above, the Bardarash area is rich in groundwater, mostly in wells. We chose fifty wells in Bardarash district, each well separated from the others, to find out the total percentage of radon gas in the district. Taking samples from the fifty wells was accurate and according to the requirements and guidelines of the device that was used. The water samples were taken at a distance below the surface of the water, in order not to minimize the effect of external factors such as air that would change the proportion of radon gas in the water [17, 18]. The bottles were placed inside a fetcher and were covered in the water as they were filled to the brim,

collecting the water samples. The sampling time was recorded. The samples were immediately taken to the lab in order to improve the radon analysis accuracy and prevent a change in the composition of the samples [19]. The RAD7 is an advanced measurement device that is often used in labs and for research projects. Researchers who investigate groundwater, mines, deserts, the ocean, and volcanoes at high temperatures utilize it in addition to certified radon testers. Water samples taken from the mining site were analyzed using a calibrated RAD7-Active Electronic detector connected to a Durrige RAD-H2O attachment [19, 20]. By connecting it to an effervescent kit that enables the degassing of radon from the water into the air in a closed loop, this detector was set up to measure the concentration of radon in water samples as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Setup of the RAD7-Active Electronic Detector for measuring radon in water.

The alpha spectrometry technique was used by the RAD7-Active Electronic detector. In roughly 20 minutes, this electronic detector can accurately determine the radon content in a given water sample. This measuring period is brief when compared to the radon's 3.8-day half-life. As a result, the Durrige RAD7-Active Electronic detector is appropriate for measuring radon in water [21, 22]. Radon in drinking water has drawn attention due to its potential to have additional serious radiological health impacts outside the well-known lung cancer. Equation (1) was used to calculate the Annual Effective Dose (Sv/year) for ingestion (AEDing) [22, 23].

$$AED_{inh} = CR_{nw} \times R_{nw} \times F \times O \times DCF_{inh} \quad (1)$$

where AED_{inh} indicates the annual effective dose from radon inhalation (Sv/y) and F = 0.4 denotes the equilibrium factor between radon and its offspring. R_{nw} = 10⁻⁴ is the radon in air/water percentage, O = 7,000 h. y⁻¹ is the average indoor occupancy time per individual. The dosage conversion factor for radon exposure in the air is DCF_{inh} (9 nSv h⁻¹ (Bq m⁻³) [22, 24, 25]. The total Annual Effective Dose (total) generated from the sum of ingested and inhaled doses as a result of surface and groundwater use in this mining area is calculated by.

$$AED_{total} = AED_{ing} + AED_{inh} \quad (3)$$

where AED_{total} denotes the total annual effective dosage ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$). AED_{ing} denotes the annual effective dose from radon consumption ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$). AED_{inh} denotes the annual effective dose from radon inhalation ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of ^{222}Rn concentration and effective dose absorbed due to groundwater consumption of the fifty sampled wells located in Bardarash are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. ^{222}Rn CONCENTRATION AND ANNUAL EFFECTIVE DOSE OF GROUNDWATER IN BARDARASH, KURDISTAN, IRAQ

Location Name	^{222}Ra (Bq/L)	AED _{ing} infants ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$)	AED _{ing} children ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$)	AED _{ing} adults ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$)	AED _{inh} ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$)	AED _{total} infants ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$)	Total children ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$)	Total adults ($\mu\text{Sv/y}$)
GW1	7.7 ± 0.61	118.04	157.39	36.54	19.40	137.45	176.79	55.94
GW2	7.22 ± 0.66	110.68	147.58	34.26	18.19	128.88	165.77	52.45
GW3	4.67 ± 0.8	71.59	95.45	22.16	11.77	83.36	107.22	33.93
GW4	5.83 ± 0.66	89.37	119.17	27.66	14.69	104.07	133.86	42.35
GW5	4.67 ± 0.47	71.59	95.45	22.16	11.77	83.36	107.22	33.93
GW6	3.27 ± 0.54	50.13	66.84	15.52	8.24	58.37	75.08	23.76
GW7	6.3 ± 0.75	96.58	128.77	29.89	15.88	112.46	144.65	45.77
GW8	9.08 ± 1.6	139.20	185.60	43.08	22.88	162.08	208.48	65.97
GW9	9.06 ± 1.69	138.89	185.19	42.99	22.83	161.72	208.02	65.82
GW10	11.24 ± 1.17	172.31	229.75	53.33	28.32	200.63	258.07	81.66
GW11	4.41 ± 2.44	67.61	90.14	20.93	11.11	78.72	101.25	32.04
GW12	8.22 ± 0.62	126.01	168.02	39.00	20.71	146.73	188.73	59.72
GW13	10.03 ± 1.69	153.76	205.01	47.59	25.28	179.04	230.29	72.87
GW14	8.16 ± 0.93	125.09	166.79	38.72	20.56	145.66	187.35	59.28
GW15	5.6 ± 0.67	85.85	114.46	26.57	14.11	99.96	128.58	40.68
GW16	7.9 ± 1.28	121.11	161.48	37.49	19.91	141.02	181.38	57.39
GW17	6.74 ± 1.19	103.32	137.77	31.98	16.98	120.31	154.75	48.97
GW18	9.53 ± 1.11	146.09	194.79	45.22	24.02	170.11	218.81	69.24
GW19	5.58 ± 0.52	85.54	114.06	26.48	14.06	99.60	128.12	40.54
GW20	7.44 ± 0.62	114.06	152.07	35.30	18.75	132.80	170.82	54.05
GW21	10.22 ± 1.17	156.67	208.90	48.49	25.75	182.43	234.65	74.25
GW22	11.39 ± .86	174.61	232.81	54.05	28.70	203.31	261.51	82.75
GW23	6.97 ± 0.54	106.85	142.47	33.07	17.56	124.41	160.03	50.64
GW24	9.76 ± 0.8	149.62	199.49	46.31	24.60	174.22	224.09	70.91
GW25	7.44 ± 0.63	114.06	152.07	35.30	18.75	132.80	170.82	54.05
GW26	6.74 ± 0.49	103.32	137.77	31.98	16.98	120.31	154.75	48.97
GW27	6.27 ± 1.15	96.12	128.16	29.75	15.80	111.92	143.96	45.55
GW28	8.83 ± 0.68	135.36	180.49	41.90	22.25	157.62	202.74	64.15
GW29	9.29 ± 0.64	142.42	189.89	44.08	23.41	165.83	213.30	67.49
GW30	6.97 ± 0.53	106.85	142.47	33.07	17.56	124.41	160.03	50.64
GW31	9.31 ± 0.65	142.72	190.30	44.18	23.46	166.18	213.76	67.64
GW32	6.74 ± 0.77	103.32	137.77	31.98	16.98	120.31	154.75	48.97
GW33	1.86 ± 0.39	28.51	38.02	8.83	4.69	33.20	42.71	13.51
GW34	6.74 ± 0.8	103.32	137.77	31.98	16.98	120.31	154.75	48.97
GW35	4.41 ± 0.57	67.61	90.14	20.93	11.11	78.72	101.25	32.04
GW36	10.46 ± 0.64	160.35	213.80	49.63	26.36	186.71	240.16	75.99
GW37	7.15 ± 0.59	109.61	146.15	33.93	18.02	127.63	164.16	51.94
GW38	10.72 ± 0.65	164.34	219.12	50.87	27.01	191.35	246.13	77.88
GW39	9.53 ± 0.76	146.09	194.79	45.22	24.02	170.11	218.81	69.24
GW40	4.37 ± 1.36	66.99	89.32	20.74	11.01	78.00	100.34	31.75
GW41	10.33 ± 0.9	158.36	211.15	49.02	26.03	184.39	237.18	75.05
GW42	9.53 ± 0.74	146.09	194.79	45.22	24.02	170.11	218.81	69.24
GW43	6.51 ± 0.63	99.80	133.06	30.89	16.41	116.20	149.47	47.30
GW44	11.39 ± 1.3	174.61	232.81	54.05	28.70	203.31	261.51	82.75
GW45	0.93 ± 0.43	14.26	19.01	4.41	2.34	16.60	21.35	6.76
GW46	5.58 ± 0.87	85.54	114.06	26.48	14.06	99.60	128.12	40.54
GW47	5.81 ± 3.33	89.07	118.76	27.57	14.64	103.71	133.40	42.21
GW48	3.43 ± 0.54	52.58	70.11	16.28	8.64	61.23	78.75	24.92
GW49	5.88 ± 3.33	90.14	120.19	27.90	14.82	104.96	135.00	42.72
GW50	3.95 ± 0.6	60.55	80.74	18.74	9.95	70.51	90.69	28.70
MIN	0.93	14.26	19.01	4.41	2.34	16.60	21.35	6.76
MAX	11.39	174.61	232.81	54.05	28.70	203.31	261.51	82.75
MEAN	7.22	110.73	147.64	34.27	18.20	128.93	165.84	52.48
SD	2.5	38.33	51.11	11.86	6.30	44.63	57.41	18.17
CV	34.63	34.62	34.62	34.62	34.62	34.62	34.62	34.62

The radon concentration ranged from 0.93 ± 0.43 Bq/l to 11.39 ± 1.86 Bq/l with a mean of 7.22 Bq/l and a standard deviation of 2.5. Groundwater always contains a greater concentration of radon gas than surface water, due to the low temperature in the wells and the low oxygen content in the water on the ground, but in the selected area the temperature is very high most of the year, affecting the concentration of radon in the water. The USEPA proposes a Maximum Contamination Level (MCL) of 11.1 Bq/l for the concentration of ^{222}Rn in groundwater [26]. So, all the wells sampled in the study are acceptable according to USEPA, except for three, namely GW10, GW22, and GW44. The annual effective doses from ^{222}Rn ingestion and inhalation by adults, children, and infants in groundwater from the wells are also presented in Table I. Ingestion of groundwater had annual effective doses ranging from 14.26 to 174.61 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 110.73 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, 19.02 to 232.81 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 147.67 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, and 4.41 to 54.05 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 34.27 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ for infants, children, and adults, respectively. Moreover, the annual effective dosage for groundwater for the sampled wells caused by inhalation of ^{222}Rn ranged from 2.34 to 28.70 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, with an average value of 18.20 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$.

By AEDing and AEDinh, the total annual effective doses of all samples were determined and their ranges are from 16.60 to 203.31 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 128.93 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, 21.35 to 261.51 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 165.84 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, and 6.76 to 82.75 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with an average value of 52.48 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ for infants, children, and adults respectively as shown in Figure 3.

The dose conversion factor for the three considered categories (infants, children, and adults) shows the flow difference between them categories depending on the percentage of water consumption. The majority of the examined wells turned out to be very healthy water sources, and their water can be used by the public. The effective dose values calculated for all categories were less or close to the acceptable limits of 100 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ (WHO, 2004), so the water from the sampled wells does not pose any radiation hazard.

Fig. 3. Total radon concentrations and annual effective doses of the selected water samples.

V. CONCLUSION

This study aims to shed light on a hitherto unexplored facet about the concentration of radon gas and the associated effective absorbed dose in the Bardarash region. This geographical location is entirely reliant on groundwater sources for its water supply. While prior investigations have delved into the examination of water quantity and quality using chemical tests, it is worth noting that no relevant studies have concentrated on the issue of the radon gas concentration of the officially sanctioned wells within this region. The analysis of groundwater samples from fifty locations in the area revealed a minimum radon concentration of 0.93 ± 0.43 Bq/l. In terms of annual effective dose, which accounts for both ingestion and inhalation exposure, it was found that for surface water samples, infants faced a mean dose of 14.26 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, children were exposed to 19.01 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, and adults experienced 4.41 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$. It should be noticed that the radon concentration levels and the corresponding effective doses resulting from ingestion and inhalation were generally found to be below the recommended limits. These limits are set at 11.1 Bq/l for radon concentration (as per UNSCEAR, 2000, and USEPA, 1991) and 100 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ for effective dosage (according to WHO, 2004). This outcome provides a reassuring indication that the majority of the sampled wells in the area supply potable water is safe for consumption. In other words, the levels of radon and the associated health risks in these wells are well within the acceptable and safe parameters. This is essential information for ensuring the well-being of the community and underscores the suitability of these wells as a reliable source of drinking water.

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Real Time FPGA Implementation of an Efficient High Speed Harris Corner Detection Algorithm Based on High-Level Synthesis

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ABSTRACT

Computer vision systems use corner detection to identify features in an image. In applications such as motion detection, tracking, picture registration, and object recognition, corner detection is often one of the initial steps. In this paper, a real-time image processing system based on Harris corner detection was designed and implemented using Zynq architecture and model-based design tools. The system was based on a development board containing the Zynq-7000 chip, which consists of a combination of FPGA and microprocessor, and the image taken with a high-resolution camera was processed in real-time by applying color conversion and Harris corner detection. The filter hardware designs used in the system were made using the HDL Coder tool in Matlab/Simulink without writing HDL code. The hardware that receives images from the camera was designed on a model-based basis with the Xilinx Vivado 2020. The HDL code that was implemented on the Xilinx ZedBoard using Vivado software was then validated to ensure real-time operation with the incoming video stream. The results achieved exhibited superiority compared to prior implementations in terms of area efficiency (reduced number of gates on the target FPGA) and speed performance on an identical target card. Using the rapid prototyping approach, two alternative hardware

accelerator designs were created using various high-level synthesis tools. This design used less than 50% of the host FPGA's logic resources and was at least 30% faster than current implementations.

Keywords-rapid prototyping; automated hardware design; corner detection codesign; MBD; HDL coder; Xilinx Zynq-7000

I. INTRODUCTION

Recognizing points of interest (or corners), such as detecting contours, is a prerequisite for many computer vision algorithms. In a picture, the places of interest correspond to two discontinuities in the intensity function. These can be created by reflectance function discontinuities or depth discontinuities, such as contours. These include, for example, corners, T-junctions, and spots with significant texture differences. With changing needs and the development of technology, the need for real-time image processing systems, which are used in many fields today, rose. In real-time embedded system designs, which are widely used in areas such as driving support systems, autonomous vehicles, flight control, security, and defense systems, it is a priority to perform the desired work within a determined time frame rather than quickly. For this reason, predictability features along with time stability are indispensable conditions for real-time systems [1]. In such real-time image processing systems, intense processing power is needed as various filters and feature extraction operations are required on the image. Especially in systems requiring high resolutions, the necessity of processing each pixel in the image frame separately and in a very short time has rendered microprocessor-based classical systems inadequate, and thus different solutions have emerged. Among these, DSP, FPGA, or GPU-based systems, as well as System on Chip (SoC), have become more and more common. The DaVinci and OMAP series chips developed by Texas Instruments are examples of Digital Signal Processor (DSP) based systems, while the S32V34 series chips of NXP are found in systems that integrate a processor, a GPU, and special image processing units [2-4].

Such systems can provide real-time operation as hardware accelerators using the advantages of DSPs and coprocessors in signal processing. However, since DSPs are fixed architectures, they address a relatively limited area by being programmed with libraries and interfaces supported by the manufacturer [5]. On the other hand, the use of Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) in such embedded systems has increased due to their more convenient structure for parallel processing and low power consumption. In FPGA-based systems, the hardware can be completely programmed in the desired architecture and can be a DSP or a hardware block created specifically for the system. In addition, new generation architectures, such as Xilinx Zynq, have processors and programmable logic blocks together, can be programmed with C language just like DSPs, and even hardware design can be made in model-based development environments such as Matlab and Labview. For this reason, an FPGA-based system was preferred in the proposed image processing system. As a result of all these developments, systems that use microprocessors and FPGA hardware together have been shown the best performance in image processing systems [6].

Such solutions that use computer and FPGA hardware together are not practical in embedded system designs because they involve high power and space consumption. The Zynq architecture, introduced by Xilinx in 2012, has closed a very important gap in the embedded system market with its microprocessor and FPGA hardware on the same chip. Due to this SoC architecture, it is possible to realize both high speed and low power and space consumption by implementing all of the hardware and software on a single card. For this reason, this study used the Zedboard development board with Zynq-7000 architecture. However, designs made with Zynq may require a long development process and a development team consisting of different disciplines due to the complexity of the hardware design and its different structure from classical microprocessor systems [7].

In [6], the Canny Edge detection algorithm was applied in real-time on the ZC702 development board using the Zynq platform. The system was designed using Vivado HLS and its internal video library and created a system that can run at 60 fps at 1080p resolution. In [8], a system was proposed to recognize and classify traffic sign images, using 1920x1080 resolution images in real-time with an integrated camera system placed on the Zedboard development board. The entire project was built in six weeks using OpenCV libraries, thus emphasizing the platform's ability to design quickly. This study stated that it took approximately 5 seconds to classify a traffic sign in the developed system [8]. In [9], optical flow algorithms were optimized and comparisons were made on different platforms. Accordingly, the same algorithm was executed on a PC with a Core i7 processor, only on the ARM processor unit of the Zynq-7000 chip, and finally, with special optimization for the programmable logic unit of the Zynq-7000 architecture. The code of the system was synthesized in C language using the Vivado HLS program. The results showed that the performance of the algorithm executed on Zynq was close to the performance of a PC with a Core i7 processor, but the power consumption was only 1/7 of the PC [9].

In [10], an analysis of emotions and facial expressions was performed using different facial recognition methods. This study used OpenCV libraries, C++ language, and embedded Linux operating system on the Zedboard development board using the Zynq-7000 platform, and anger, happiness, and surprise expressions were classified with 97, 100, and 97% success rates, respectively, achieving a performance of approximately 4 to 5 fps. In [11], some image processing algorithms were implemented on the Zedboard development board using the Verilog hardware definition language, which was able to apply real-time filter operations at approximately 40 fps on an image of 256x256 pixels taken with a webcam via USB [11]. In [12], an automatic license plate identification system was designed on the XC7Z020-1CLG484 development board with the Zynq-7000 platform. All system hardware was designed with high-level synthesis tools using MATLAB/Simulink and Xilinx System Generator

development environment, the most efficient among the implemented applications was determined, whereas all three methods were more than 90% successful. In [13], the Sobel edge detection filter was applied in real-time on the Zynq-7000 architecture Zedboard using the Vivado HLS tool. This study improved the Sobel filter algorithm to prevent delay in image transmission, making it work faster and achieving a maximum speed of 90.1 fps at 1080p, achieving 30% more performance and 75% less resource usage than previous designs. In [14], the Canny edge detection algorithm was implemented and optimized on Zedboard, using OpenCV libraries and high-level synthesis tools. This study also analyzed and compared the performance of the algorithms, stating that the improved algorithm was up to 3 times faster at the kernel level and up to 7 times faster at the application level [14].

These studies show that the Vivado HLS can be used both as a high-level synthesis tool and to write the C code. This study aimed to go one step further by looking for a solution to the specified design complexity and to create a real-time image processing system using high-level languages. To reduce design complexity, instead of using hardware definition languages, hardware design was performed with Matlab/Simulink, which is a model-based design software, and high-level synthesis tools called HDL Coder, Embedder Coder, and Vision HDL Toolbox. The camera reference design and system software were created with Xilinx's Vivado Design Suite and SDK. In this system, the high-resolution image taken instantly from the camera is subjected to gray tone, edge detection, noise removal, and sharpening filters, and the processed image is transferred to the monitor without delay.

II. HARDWARE SUBSTRUCTURE

The proposed system used the Zedboard development board with Zynq-7000 architecture, the FMC-HDMI-CAM module produced by Avnet, and the Python 1300-C camera module, which is fully compatible with the system [15-16]. FMC stands for FPGA interconnect and defines a standard interface for FPGA cards that can operate at high speeds. Thus, a connection can be made between peripherals and FPGA cards easily, and all cards with this interface can be used [17]. The connection of the system with the computer is provided via UART and the system status can be monitored via the serial port. However, the system works independently and does not need a computer connection. With the help of buttons and switches on the Zedboard, the desired filter can be selected and other parameters can be adjusted. Figure 1 shows the general scheme of the system.

Fig. 1. General scheme of the proposed system.

A. Zynq-7000 Architecture

The Zedboard development board consists of a Zynq7000 Z-7020 series SoC and peripherals [18]. Zynq-7000 is a Fully Programmable SoC architecture that includes a dual-core ARM Cortex-A9 processor and FPGA components on the same chip. This system has high-speed advanced expandable interface (AXI) buses to provide data transfer between the processor and the FPGA. Thus, it is possible to use these two units together without being independent of each other. In general, the Zynq-700 AP SoC consists of a processor unit (PS-Processing System), a Programmable Logic (PL) unit corresponding to the FPGA system, and interconnections [19]. Figure 2 shows a simple principal diagram of the Zynq architecture.

Fig. 2. Simple principle diagram of the Zynq7000 architecture.

B. System Design Flow

After bringing together the hardware components of the system, a reference design that can take images from the camera should be realized. After the image is taken from the camera successfully, the filters to be used are designed and simulated in the Matlab/Simulink environment, and these filters are packaged as standard IP blocks with the HDL Coder tool. These IP blocks are integrated into the camera reference design, created by incorporating them into the Vivado environment. Finally, the system software was written in the Xilinx SDK environment the necessary drivers were included, and the system was given its final shape.

High-Level Synthesis (HLS) is gaining popularity as an approach that allows designers to express design behaviors at high abstraction levels while ensuring continuous verification throughout the design cycle. Vivado HLS [10] and MATLAB HDL Coder [11] are examples of HLS tools. These are often used by digital designers and architects to create and implement algorithms for a variety of aerospace, communications, image processing, deep learning, and neural network applications. HLS technologies can help reduce code complexity by a factor of seven to ten. They enable the reuse of behavioral IP across projects and allow verification teams to apply high-abstraction-level modeling techniques, such as transaction-level modeling [12].

Furthermore, most modern chip systems include integrated processors. The coexistence of microprocessors, DSPs, memory, and custom logic on a single chip necessitates the inclusion of additional software or firmware in the design

process. As a result, an automated HLS process enables designers and architects to experiment with multiple algorithmic and implementation options to investigate various area, power, and performance tradeoffs from a shared functional specification. As a result of advancements in Register Transfer Level (RTL) synthesis techniques, industrial deployment of HLS tools has become increasingly feasible. Major semiconductor design houses, such as IBM [13], Motorola [14], Philips [15], and Siemens [16], have developed

proprietary tools. Major Electronic Design Automation (EDA) suppliers have also begun to commercialize various HLS products. For example, Synopsys released the Behavioral Compiler tool [17] in 1995, which builds RTL implementations from behavioral Hardware Description Language (HDL) code and connects to downstream tools. Similar tools include Mentor Graphics' Catapult HLS [18] and Cadence's Stratus High-Level Synthesis [19]. Figure 3 depicts a typical flow for HLS in VLSI designs.

Fig. 3. System design flow based on Simulink /HDL coder.

C. Camera Reference Design

This study used the Avnet FMC-HDMI-CAM module to provide a connection to the camera via the high-speed FMC interface. The Python-1300c camera module, which is compatible with this module, was chosen as the image sensor. This module has the ON Semiconductors Python-1300 image sensor and can transfer images with a resolution of 1280x1024 pixels at 210 fps [16]. Thus, the infrastructure necessary for a real-time system was created. This design aimed to convert the image into the AXI4-Stream data type by performing some operations on the raw image coming from the camera sensor and making it ready for further processing. In this way, the image frames taken from the camera could be transferred to the screen without any errors. After these processes were carried out, the IP blocks required for image processing were designed according to the camera reference design. To get the image from the camera correctly, the Xilinx Video and Image Processing Pack and the 3rd party IP blocks provided for the camera hardware were downloaded and included in the system. After the necessary procedures were completed, the synthesis and implementation phase was passed, the test software of the system was created, and the image was successfully projected onto the screen. Figure 4 shows the status of the camera reference design and the IP blocks used in the system.

The camera image is first converted to the AXI4-Stream data type, and then the missing color components are reconstructed with the CFA IP block. The image is converted

to a YCbCr format with the RGB to YUV block. Using the Chroma Resampler IP block, the image is reduced to a 16-bit format, over 24 bits, and the 1280x1024 pixel image is centered on the 1920x1080 pixel monitor with the On-Screen Display IP block. Then, the image is converted again to be transferred to the monitor using a connection to the monitor from the HDMI output on the FMC-HDMI-CAM module. With the AXI VDMA IP block, data exchange was provided directly with the system memory, thus protecting the system from possible bottlenecks. Figure 5 shows the created working image of the created camera reference system.

Fig. 4. Camera reference design.

Fig. 5. Corner detection system with Simulink /HDL coder.

D. Image Processor System

After the camera reference design, the image processing filters were designed using the Xilinx and Mathworks tools. The system design was completely model-based in the Simulink environment, and after the simulations were made on Simulink, HDL code was automatically generated with HDL Coder, and these codes were converted into usable IP packages. In addition, the Embedder Coder, Simulink Coder, Matlab Coder, and Vision HDL Toolbox and their additional packages for Zynq were installed in Matlab 2022 and Vivado 2020.2 to be used in the design of the system. The system running on Simulink is a kind of serial interface called a streaming pixel interface. In this method, pixels are transferred serially, and data transfer takes place over two kinds of signals, namely, data and control. This interface is fully compatible with the AXI4-Stream and ensures that the designed IP blocks work in full compliance with the camera reference system.

III. DESIGN AND SIMULATION OF THE SYSTEM IN SIMULINK ENVIRONMENT

Four filters were individually designed with HDL Toolbox blocks and combined into two IP blocks. In this way, without increasing design complexity all filters could be activated at the same time.

A. Harris Object Corner Detector

Corners are portions of a picture with a significant change in intensity and resistance to picture distortions. Based on the light intensity of the pixels, Harris points are generated to correlate to wedges. A detector based on the autocorrelation expression of the intensity fluctuations listed below is suggested:

$$M(x, y) = \sum_{(u,v)} w(u, v) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} I_x^2(x, y) & I_x I_y(x, y) \\ I_x I_y(x, y) & I_y^2(x, y) \end{pmatrix}$$

with I_x and I_y being the local derivatives in x and y , and $w(u, v)$ is a weighting on the window (u, v) . The study of the eigenvalues of the matrix M makes it possible to determine whether a point is a corner, a homogeneous region, or an outline. A final criterion is calculated from M , allowing deciding on the type of point found.

B. Grayscale Converter

Vision HDL was used to design a grayscale conversion filter operation. Accordingly, all three color values were fixed. The gray tone values were obtained by multiplying with the coefficients [3]. The YUV format and its most commonly used encoding were used, following the ITU rec.601 standard.

IV. DESIGN SYNTHESIS AND RESULTS

After completing the designs on Simulink, each filter system was separately converted to HDL code. This process was carried out using the Matlab/Simulink HDL Coder and the HDL workflow advisor. They necessary settings were made during the conversion process. After this stage, the IP block in the Vivado Suite Camera reference was attached to the design with the IP integrating system. The filter systems were implemented sequentially on the Zedboard. In later studies, the system will be less on-chip for space coverage and simplification of the software. Accordingly, the grayscale conversion and edge detection systems were combined into a single IP block. The median and sharpening filters formed the second IP block. Necessary interconnections were made again and the system was synthesized again.

A. Simulation Results

The produced VHDL RTL code was simulated using a non-synthesizable test bench and the Vivado xSim program. The reference pixel values are equal to the pixel output from the suggested approach. They were also found to be identical to high-level simulation results obtained with MATLAB on the optimum bit-width model. This was proven by comparing the output photos from both paths with the same input image. This study also compared the quantization error produced by the choice of the lowered optimal signal widths with the double precision model running in MATLAB. This was achieved with the FPGA in the loop simulation feature of the MathWorks HDL Verifier [20].

B. Synthesis Results

Table I shows the resource usage. As can be seen, at most, 35% of the available resources were used. It should also be noted that no optimization work was carried out here. In the system, the main clock speed was determined at 148.50 MHz, and the pixel clock speed, at which the camera and image processing blocks work, was determined at 108 MHz. Although EYH represents the screen refresh rate in the formula, the total horizontal pixels and total vertical pixel values consist of the sum of active pixels, gap pixels, and synchronization pixels.

TABLE I. PROPOSED HARRIS CORNER DETECTOR IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

Resource	Utilization	Available	Utilization percentage
Look Up Table (LUT)	5917	53,200	11.12%
LUT RAM	506	17,400	2.91%
Flip-Flops	10,981	106,400	10.32%
BRAM	37	140	26.79%
DSP	21	220	9.55%
IOs	102	200	51%
BUFG	1	32	3.13%

Accordingly, it was determined that the image processing system can operate at 1280x1024 at 60 Hz refresh time and, thus, can process 60 fps. This shows that the system is in real-time operating conditions.

C. Implementation of the System Software

The software was designed following the hardware. The design was carried out in C using the SDK tool in Vivado Suite. In addition to the processes used in the software, such as the preparation and execution of IP blocks, the setting of input-output units and filter parameters were also adjusted. In the developed system, filters can be changed during operation and more than one filter can be active at the same time. The system is controlled with the buttons and switches of the Zedboard. The active status of the filters can also be monitored from the LEDs on the Zedboard. Using multiplexer logic, the system is designed so that the relevant filter is selected according to the status of the switches on the Zedboard. Among the Zedboard keys, the system activates the relevant filter according to the status of the keys, with DS0 being the lowest-value bit and DS7 being the highest-value bit.

V. CONCLUSION

This study designed and implemented a real-time image processing system on the Zedboard development board. Due to the high processing power requirement of such systems, the Zynq architecture was chosen, and both hardware and software were designed. Hardware was designed using Vivado Suite and related tools developed by Xilinx for Zynq, while model-based development tools, such as HDL Coder and Vision HDL Toolbox developed by Mathworks, were used in the design of the image processing system. In this way, there was no need to write HDL code manually and the design time was shortened. A system that can operate at 60 Hz with a resolution of 1280×1024 pixels was developed on the Zedboard development board. Sobel edge detection, median filter, gray tone converter, and sharpening filter designs were applied, which can be controlled from the input and output units of the board. The designed system can meet needs and fulfill real-time working conditions. However, although resource usage is not very high, it can decrease further with optimizations in the HDL Coder tool. The proposed design was completely reusable, and it is possible to reuse IP blocks or the entire system designed in future studies and different systems. Future studies can investigate more advanced real-time object recognition and tracking applications using the proposed system as a preprocessing unit.

Hardware acceleration of corner edge detection for 1920×1080 images was implemented in a Xilinx Zynq-7000 SoC hardware platform. Simulation and synthesis results were obtained using Vivado 2020.2. Future research will focus on enhancing the performance metrics of speed, area, and power consumption using optimization techniques provided by prominent high-level synthesis tool providers, including MathWorks, Xilinx, Mentor, and Cadence, in conjunction with the proposed implementation approach. Furthermore, there are plans to expand the scope of this study to include ASIC designs in future research endeavors.

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Effect of Double Interior Stiffeners on the Flexural Behavior of Concrete Filled Steel Tube Composite Box Girders

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ABSTRACT

A composite box girder is a type of structural element that possesses strong torsional stiffness and resistance against flexural forces. A new category of bridge structure has been established: one that consists of concrete-filled steel tubes connected to composite slabs by steel trusses. In this study, an experimental and computational analysis of flexural loadings on four different types of composite box girders that are connected to concrete-filled steel tubes is presented. The specimens in this test are subjected to a concentrated load at the span's midpoint. The first model is a concrete-filled tube with no internal stiffeners and is used as a control specimen. The second model is a concrete-filled tube with double internal I-shaped stiffeners welded inside a steel tube. The third model features double T-shaped stiffeners, and the fourth model features stiffeners in the shape of a V. When compared with the control specimen, the results of the tests demonstrated that the Concrete-Filled Steel Tube (CFST) section equipped with internal stiffeners provided a better strength capacity and exhibited less deflection. The I- and the V-shaped stiffeners were found to be inferior to the T-shaped. The findings of the numerical analysis were in accordance with the results of the test.

Keywords-composite box girder; concrete filled tube; truss; flexural strength capacity; bridge analysis; finite element; ABAQUS

I. INTRODUCTION

A composite bridge made from steel (girder) and concrete (slab) is the best way to reduce the dead load of the self-weight of the bridge. In recent years, composite bridges constructed with this system contain a top concrete slab with steel trusses and a bottom Concrete-Filled Steel Tube (CFST). This bridge type is limited because it contains a large number of truss joints, so the stress concentration at these joints' location may affect the flexural capacity becomes less [1]. The CFST composite trusses perform duties or services for the load-bearing structural system. The applied moment by the external load is transformed into the axial forces of the upper and lower chords of the truss, while the shear force is turned into the axial force of the webs. The chords in the composite truss are subject to the axial force, so filling the compressive chords with concrete leads to the best solution because of its higher axial strength, and in addition, the concrete core inside the steel tube enhances the buckling behavior of the steel tubes. Also, the steel tube provides more confinement to the concrete core [2]. The experimental results of the composite section under the effect of concentrated load at the mid span of the top slab

revealed that the compressive strength of the slab and of the filled steel section (bottom chord), and the steel tube geometry have a significant effect on the strength capacity, crack propagation in the slab, deflection, and slip at the interface between the steel section and concrete, while the shear connectors have a little impact on the load capacity and the deflection and more effect on the slip [3]. According to the concluded remark about the comparison between hollow steel and CFST sections, the CFST section improves the tensile strength by about 11% in comparison with the steel section alone (hollow) [4]. CFST trusses have a concrete-infilled bottom chord and braces for connections. CFST increases the compressive and tensile strength of the chords, which keeps them safe from buckling inward and avoids pinching of the steel tube of the lower chord. It also increases the joint strength and the flexural stiffness of the truss (whole). The hollow steel section reduces the cost because it acts as a formwork for concrete casting [5–8]. Comparison between two trusses, in which the first truss was filled with concrete and the second truss was hollow, was done experimentally and analytically. The strength capacity of the first member was 17.5% higher

than that of the second truss member [9]. Specimens were tested (6 specimens) with different girder trusses to investigate the impact of CFST upper and lower chords of the truss with hollow chords on the welded joints. Based on the test results, the presence of CFST chords increased the load capacity and rigidity of the joint, which prevented chord surface plastic failure [10]. In [11], a total of 8 specimens, i.e. 4 curved, 2 straight CFST, and 2 hollow chord curved truss girders, were tested. The specimens' flexural behavior without the impact of the height/span ratio and the existence of concrete infill was investigated. The stiffness and ultimate load of curved CFST truss girders were found to be higher than that of straight CFST truss girders and curved hollow truss girders [11]. In [12], 4 specimens were tested to explore the effect of the member's layout of truss (diagonal and vertical) connected to the lower and upper CFST members. Different modes of failure appeared, such as surface plasticity, local buckling, shear occurring in the lower chord, and support failure [12]. Authors in [13] investigated the flexural performance of CFST tube truss composites considering different web configurations, such as transverse and transverse braces. The test results showed that the failure mode with diagonal braces was the surface plasticity at the lower or top chord and local buckling. The specimen had diagonal braces and higher load capacity, stiffness, and ductility.

According to the studies mentioned above on the behavior and strength of CFST connected with truss and supported concrete deck slabs, more studies are needed in this research area. The present study focuses on the influence of CFSTs on the flexural performance of composite box girders under static load. The effect of the presence of stiffeners inside of CFST and the influence of the presence of interior stiffeners on the flexural performance of CFST in composite box girders with different shapes such as T, V, and I is investigated in this study. The CFST sections with interior stiffeners had a higher strength capacity and less deflection than the control specimen. The best shape of the stiffeners was the T-shape. The numerical analysis results were in accordance with the test results of [14]. The flexural strength of a concrete girder enhanced by external structural materials due to prior damage was studied in [15]. A bridge may fail due to the action of terrorist attacks such as explosives, so it is needed to make the bridge girders strong enough [16], something that damages the concrete girders [17]. The use of CFRP laminates significantly affects strand strain, especially with the use of anchors. The CFRP reinforcement affected flexural strength, crack width, and mid-span deflection. However, the flexural stiffness of the strengthened members during the serviceability phases is critical as strand damage ratios increase. In comparison with the non-damaged girder, the NSM-CFRP laminates enhanced the flexural capacity by 11% and 7.7%, corresponding to strand damage of 14.3% and 28.6%, respectively [18].

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Four CFST models that support concrete deck slabs are presented in this study. The model specimens included a control specimen and three specimens with different stiffener shapes welded inside the CFST beam, which are listed in Table I. The geometries of all tested specimens, i.e. composite slabs,

connected trusses, and CFSTs, are the same except for the shape of the interior stiffness inside the CFST beam. The width of the specimens is 450 mm, the depth is 400 mm, and the total specimen length is 2000 mm, in which the span from center to center between supports is 1800 mm. The thickness of the concrete deck slab is 100 mm. The truss with a 6 mm thickness is connected to the top concrete slab by a plate with a thickness of 8 mm, in which stud shear connectors are welded in. The diameter of the stud shear connector is 12 mm, distributed with a center to center spacing of 100 mm. A steel tube with a thickness of 1.27 mm was used to fabricate the square tube cross-sections with 150 mm outside depth and width. Based on the selected dimensions, the width/thickness ratio is 118.11, so the tube section is a slender section [21]. The steel tubes and the truss are connected by weld connections. The three tested specimens have the same dimensions with the control specimen but differ by the presence of double internal stiffeners with different shapes provided along the full length of the specimen. The steel stiffeners (I, T, and V shaped) were separately fabricated and welded at their designed locations on a flat steel plate, after which the plate was carefully folded by a press machine to achieve the suggested shape of a cold-formed square steel tube. The square-shaped tube was fabricated by folding the flat steel plate into three folded sides. To complete the tube, the remaining face was formed by fully welding a flat steel plate onto the open edges along the already folded plate using a welding machine. The single stiffeners (long span) are welded inside the steel tube, as shown in Figure 1.

TABLE I. SPECIMEN MARKS AND DESCRIPTIONS

Specimen mark	Descriptions	Stiffeners shape
BG	Composite box girder with truss and concrete filled tubular.	NA
BGWI	Composite box girder with truss and concrete filled tubular with single I-shaped stiffeners.	I
BGWDT	Composite box girder with truss and concrete filled tubular with single T-shaped stiffeners.	T
BGWDTV	Composite box girder with truss and concrete filled tubular with single V-shaped stiffeners.	V

NA: Not Applicable

Ordinary Portland Cement Type I was used to cast the concrete deck slab and infill steel tube. The mechanical properties of concrete are listed in Table II.

Fig. 1. Specimen details. (a) No stiffeners, (BG), (b) I stiffeners (BGWDI), (c) T stiffeners (BGWDT), and (d) V stiffeners (BGWDV).

The above steel plate is connected with the concrete deck slab by shear connector studs. The geometry and specifications are listed in Tables III and IV, respectively. The concrete deck

slab reinforcement has 10 mm nominal diameter, and spans 100 mm from center to center at both bottom ways (Table V). CFST and steel tube dimensions are listed in Table VI. The mechanical properties of the main reinforcement of the slab can be seen in Table VII, whereas the truss member properties and dimensions are listed in Table VIII.

TABLE II. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SLAB AND FILLED CONCRETE

Compressive strength f_c'	Modulus of rupture f_r	Splitting tensile strength f_t	Modulus of elasticity E_c	Poisson's ratio ν
30 MPa	3.337 MPa	4.244 Mpa	25743 MPa	0.2

TABLE III. SHEAR STUD CONNECTOR-GEOMETRY

Diameter of shear stud connector	Height of stud	Spacing
10 mm	63.5 mm	100 mm

TABLE IV. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SHEAR STUD CONNECTOR

Tensile strength f_y	Modulus of elasticity E_s	Poisson's ratio ν
412 MPa	200000 MPa	0.3

TABLE V. CONCRETE SLAB DETAILS

Slab depth	Slab width	Main reinforcement bottom reinforcement
100 mm	450 mm	$\varnothing 10 @ 100$ in both directions

TABLE VI. FILLING CONCRETE AND STEEL TUBE DIMENSIONS

Concrete		Steel tube	
Depth	Width	Depth and width-square section	Thickness
150 mm	150 mm	150	1.27

TABLE VII. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE REINFORCEMENTS

Bar diameter	Tensile strength	Modulus of elasticity	Poisson's ratio
10 mm	487.67 MPa	200000 MPa	0.30

TABLE VIII. TRUSS MEMBER DIMENSIONS

Type	Depth	Width	Thickness
Channel	25.4 mm	50.8 mm	6 mm

Fig. 2. Stud shear connector distribution.

Figure 2 shows the location of the stud shear connector distribution along the deck slab that is welded to the upper steel plate. Figure 3 shows the deck slab reinforcement layout. Figure 4 shows the specimen setup and the location of strain gauges, with two of them located at the shear zone as ST1 and ST2 at each support location at the end, while ST3 is located at the bottom center for each specimen. The central point load for each specimen was applied up to failure, and failure and deflection values were recorded. The concentrated load was applied at the mid-span on the top surface of the deck slab gradually up to failure. Strains and deflections were recorded for each load step and then plotted.

Fig. 3. Main reinforcement of the slab layout.

Fig. 4. Location of the strain gauges.

III. TEST RESULTS

In the present investigation, four specimens, including a control composite girder connected by steel truss to CFST without interior stiffeners, and three specimens with stiffeners in I, T, and V shapes were tested under concentrated load. The test results for maximum load capacity, deflection, and strain at maximum load are shown in Table IX. The recorded strain

values listed in Table IX at the locations of ST1 and ST2 are the same but differ when compared with ST3, which is located at the bottom center of the CFST beam. All measured strains had the limited value recommended by ACI-318-2019 [21], which is less than 0.005. Stiffness and ductility of the tested specimens are listed in Table X. Stiffness is calculated by dividing the maximum strength capacity by the corresponding deflection, and ductility, which represents the ability of the structural member to ductile (large deformation) without collapse, is divided by the deflection at failure by the deflection at maximum load capacity. Specimen BGWFDV exhibited the highest stiffness while the lowest was exhibited by the specimen BGWFDI. BGWFDV gave the highest ductility of 1.15 and BGWDI the lowest, equal to 1.09.

TABLE IX. LOAD CAPACITY, MAXIMUM DEFLECTION, AND STRAIN OF THE TESTED SPECIMENS

Model	Load capacity (kN)	Deflection maximum load (mm)	Deflection failure (mm)	Maximum strain $\times 10^{-3}$		
				ST1	ST2	ST3
BG	168.70	15.53	16.88	0.00103	0.00106	0.00071
BGWFDI	206.8	19.5	22.05	0.00096	0.001	0.00017
BGWFDT	234.8	15	18	0.00052	0.00051	0.00033
BGWFDV	251.1	20	23	0.0005	0.00051	0.00031

The behavior and strength of the tested specimens are represented by load deflection and load strain and were recorded for each specimen and each applied load step. Figure 5 shows the load-deflection variations for the tested specimens. In general, the variation started as linear up to the inflection point and the stiffness of the specimen decreased due to the increase in applied load and the increase in deflection. The inflection points for each specimen differ in magnitude due to differences in the connection of unfilled concrete with steel tubes to form the CFST section. Specimen BGWV gave higher strength capacity with lower deflection followed by BGWT, BGWI, and BG.

Fig. 5. Load-deflection relation of the tested specimens.

Figures 6-8 represent the load-strain variations of the tested specimens, in which ST1 and ST2 represent the strain at the left and right diagonal tension at supports, and ST3 represents the

strain at the middle of the bottom of each specimen. The recorded ST1 and ST2 are almost equal. The strain of the specimen BGWFDV was lower at the supports due to the connection stiffener type, followed by BGWFDI, BGWFDT, and BG. The ST3 of control specimen BG gave a lower strain than the other specimens. The specimens were tested up to failure due to the presence of steel sections that are more ductile than concrete, and the results showed that the presence of interior stiffeners led to a reduction in deflection, an improvement in strength load capacity, and a reduction in strain.

Fig. 6. Load-strain ST1 of the tested specimens.

TABLE X. STIFFNESS AND DUCTILITY OF THE TESTED SPECIMENS

Model	Increase of strength load capacity (%)	Deflection at the load of BG (mm)	Decrease in deflection (%)	Stiffness (kN/mm)	Ductility
BG	---	15.53	---	10.86	1.09
BGWFDI	22.58	11.14	28.26	10.6	1.13
BGWFDT	39.18	7.3	53	15.65	1.2
BGWFDV	48.844	8	48.5	19.1	1.15

Fig. 7. Load-strain ST2 of the tested specimens.

Fig. 8. Load-strain ST3 of the tested specimens.

IV. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite element models were used to simulate the performance of CFSTs in composite box girders. The concrete element had 8 nodes, the models of the truss elements had 2 nodes, and the steel tube models had 4 nodes. The contact between the concrete and the bottom steel plate, and the concrete and the inner surface of the steel tube involved finite sliding with surface-to-surface formulation, which is the default method in ABAQUS/standard for contact enforcement. A T3D2 with a 2-node linear 3-D truss element was used to simulate reinforcements, stud shear connectors, and stiffeners. The shear stud connector was simulated in such a manner that there was no uplift failure, so it could only deform horizontally due to shear flow. A S4R with 4-node doubly curved shell element was used to simulate the steel tube [21]. Figure 9 shows the finite element model simulation in ABAQUS.

Fig. 9. Finite element model of the whole box girder.

There are two main material modeling approaches for concrete in ABAQUS, which are concrete smeared cracking and Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP), which was adopted in the present study. For the CDP model to solve the Drucker-Prager plastic flow function and yield function, five parameters must be defined. Dilation angle, form factor, eccentricity, biaxial compressive stress ratio, dilation angle, and viscosity. The factors used to model the concrete are listed in Table XI.

TABLE XI. DAMAGE PLASTICITY DATA

Damage plasticity data				
ϕ	e	f_{bd}/f_{cd}	k	ν
31	0.1	1.16	0.667	0

Fig. 10. Stress-strain variation of concrete. (a) Compression, (b) tension.

Fig. 11. Stress-strain variation of steel.

Fig. 12. Experimental and FEM load-deflection relation for the BG specimen.

The stress-strain variation of concrete in compression and tension is presented in Figure 10 while for steel is shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 13. Experimental and FEM load-deflection relation for the BGWFDI specimen.

Fig. 14. Experimental and FEM load-deflection relation for the BGWFDT specimen.

Fig. 15. Experimental and FEM load-deflection relation for the BGWFDV specimen.

Figures 12 to 15 show the load-mid span deflection experimental and FEM results for all specimens. It can be noticed that the results are close. Table XII lists the comparison analysis results. The FEM performance for all simulated models gave lower deflection than the experimental test due to the rigid body of the model and the compatibility between the connected nodes of the elements. Figures 16–19 show the deflection of all models.

TABLE XII. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE EXPERIMENTAL AND THE FEM RESULTS

Model	Load capacity (kN)		Maximu deflection (mm)		FEM/ Experiment	
	Experiment	FEM	Experiment	FEM	Load	Deflection
BG	168.70	179.12	15.53	25.00	1.06	1.06
BGWI	206.8	215.67	19.5	14.75	1.043	0.75
BGWT	234.8	238.43	15	17.55	1.015	1.166
BGWV	251.1	231.50	20	17.22	0.92	0.88

Fig. 16. Deflection of the BG model at failure stage.

Fig. 17. Deflection of the BGWI model at failure stage.

Fig. 18. Deflection of the BGWT model at failure stage.

Fig. 19. Deflection of the BGWV model at failure stage.

V. VON MISES STRESSES

The Von Mises stresses are used to check out whether the adopted ductile material will yield or fracture. Figures 20 to 23 show the Von Mises stress distributions for all the simulated models. The stress concentration is at the bottom of the CFST

beam. The minimum stress concentration occurs in the BG model, and the maximum stress occurs in the BGWDI model. The Von Mises stress contours that represent the stress distributions show uniformity. The Von Mises stresses maximum value ranged between 463 and 496 MPa, which means the maximum value is more than the yield strength of the steel tube (383 MPa), so there is a fracture for all models at the failure stage.

Fig. 20. Von Mises stress of model BG at final loading stage-FEM results.

Fig. 21. Von Mises stress of model BGWI at final loading stage-FEM results.

Fig. 22. Von Mises stress of model BGWT at final loading stage-FEM results.

Fig. 23. Von Mises stress of model BGWV at final loading stage-FEM results.

VI. DISCUSSION

The control specimen without interior stiffeners inside the CFST beam had a lower strength capacity because the absence of stiffeners brought a lack of interaction and slip development between the steel tube and the filled concrete. In this case, the resistance force is only the frictional force (adhesive) between the concrete and steel sections. Maximum strength capacity

occurs in the presence of T stiffeners because this tube, similar to stud shear connectors, resists the shear flow developed at the interface between filled concrete and steel tube. Specimens with I and V stiffeners had a higher strength capacity than the control specimen, but less than BGWDT. The deflection of specimen BGWDT is less than control's and the specimens with different stiffener shapes because the T section made the composite action more intense and the flange of stiffeners gave a higher resistance to the composite bottom chord. FEM results are close with the experimental results but with less deflection due to the rigid body between the connected nodes of the elements. The number of shear stud connectors designed for full interaction between the steel plate and the deck-reinforced concrete slab that leads to slip at the interface becomes very small or vanishes. No uplift failure occurred between the steel plate and the concrete deck slab during the experiments and in FEM analysis.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The current work investigated the effect of double interior stiffeners on the flexural behavior of concrete-filled steel tube composite box girders to prevent the slip that may occur at the interface between the filled concrete and the inner face of the hollow steel type and reduce the deflection and stress concentrations along the CFST section by applying double interior studs. This study is an attempt to fill the knowledge gap in this area.

Based on the test and FEM analysis results of four concrete-filled steel tube box girders under flexural load, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The strength capacity of composite girders connected by truss to the filled steel tube as the bottom chord depends on the presence of interior stiffeners. The presence of interior stiffeners increases the bond between concrete and the interior face of CFST at the interface, which makes the concrete and the hollow steel tube working as one (full interaction) so that there is no slip, therefore the deflection becomes less, the strength capacity becomes higher, and the stress developed as flexural (bending stress) becomes less.
- The strength capacity of composite girders depends on the shape of the stiffeners. The T stiffeners had a stronger capacity than the other types.
- Deflection and strain become less in the presence of stiffeners when compared with the control specimen because there is no slip between the inside concrete and the hollow steel tube.
- The presence of interior stiffeners increases strength capacity and ductility, delaying the occurrence of failure and preventing large deformations.
- The presence of interior stiffeners improves strength capacity due to the increased confinement of hollow steel tubes to the concrete inside. This means that the presence of stiffeners improves the concrete confinement effects.
- FEM results were close to the experimental test results.

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A Bayesian Neural Network-based Obstacle Avoidance Algorithm for an Educational Autonomous Mobile Robot Platform

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ABSTRACT

Autonomous mobile robots belong to automatically controlled objects that are designed and produced for various demands. This study aimed to develop an inexpensive platform of autonomous mobile robots that can be used for educational and research purposes in technical universities. The robot was built based on popular ultrasonic sensors to detect obstacles and a Raspberry Pi 4, which is a Linux-embedded computer. An effective obstacle avoidance algorithm for the robot was developed using a Bayesian neural network for classification. Training a Bayesian neural network does not require a validation dataset separate from the available data. In addition, the Bayesian approach can effectively handle the uncertainty of the system and result in the best generation for the network when inferring the unseen data. Training data are generated using robot-to-obstacle distances and the corresponding navigation modes. The commands to control the left and right motors of the robot are generated by the pretrained Bayesian neural network for three modes of navigation, forward, left, and right. Finally, this system can be useful as it can be conveniently integrated with advanced robot control algorithms.

Keywords- autonomous mobile robots; obstacle avoidance; Bayesian neural network

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous mobile robots have been widely used in various industrial applications. In the last decades, there has

been a lot of attention on motion planning for autonomous mobile robots. The motion planning problem can be divided into path planning and trajectory planning [1-2]. Path planning is related to the generation of obstacle-free paths with

geometric characteristics of obstacles and the kinematic constraints of the robot. Meanwhile, trajectory planning takes into account the robot's dynamics and moving obstacles (obstacles not known in advance). Basic navigation of mobile robots can be divided into the following tasks: (1) generating a model of the environment in the form of a map, (2) computing a collision-free path from the starting position to the target, and (3) following the generated trajectory. The crucial issue of a mobile robot is executing collision-free motions within its environment without any human intervention. Therefore, mobile robots must be equipped with distance sensors such as ultrasonic distance sensors, laser range sensors, and infrared sensors to detect obstacles and make decisions about how to navigate their environment smoothly.

The ability of mobile robots to avoid obstacles can be implemented by various algorithms. Fuzzy logic has become an appropriate solution for low-cost mobile robots that do not require complicated navigation [3-9]. In fuzzy logic, the linguistic variables of the inputs are combined to create the linguistic variables of the outputs. As a result, the fuzzy logic system needs to measure and analyze all inputs before inferring the outputs. Artificial neural networks can also be used in mobile robots to avoid obstacles [10-13]. Sonar sensors are used to obtain data for neural network training, generate training patterns corresponding to possible environment scenarios, and then train offline neural networks.

Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) neural networks are commonly used in various applications. The generalization of the trained neural network, or how well it can predict new cases, is the key challenge when developing an MLP neural network. Indeed, an insufficient network complexity can result in underfitting phenomena, in which significant data may be ignored. In contrast, excessive network complexity can cause overfitting, in which noisy data are also fitted. The complexity of an MLP neural network depends on the magnitudes of the weights and biases. In addition, the network size, depending on the number of hidden nodes, can also be used as a useful factor to measure network complexity. For a long period, the Bayesian approach has been used to improve the generalizability of feed-forward neural networks in the case of finite and noisy data [14-16]. In this process, network regularization is needed to prevent the network parameters (weights and biases) from becoming large, because large values of weights and biases usually cause the overfitting phenomenon to downgrade the performance of the network after being trained. When training feed-forward networks, the values of the regularization parameters can be easily found by using the Bayesian technique. Feed-forward neural networks that can be trained using the Bayesian technique are also called Bayesian Neural Networks (BNNs).

As BNNs can be effective for various classification problems, this study aimed to provide a procedure for deploying a classification BNN to navigate the direction of an autonomous mobile robot with the following aspects:

- Explore the evidence framework to allow all available data to be used to train BNNs. This work is needed when the collection of relatively large data is expensive or time-consuming.

- As the traditional gradient descent algorithm with a fixed step size and search direction to search local minima usually causes an excessively large network training time, this study focused on the quasi-Newton optimization technique, which is an advanced optimization training algorithm to automatically adjust the step size and search direction to optimal values.
- As finding the optimal network architecture is often a time-consuming task, this study also used the Bayesian model comparison concept to choose the best network architecture. This was carried out by evaluating the evidence for different candidate BNNs with varying numbers of hidden nodes. The network architecture that can give the highest value of the evidence will be chosen for the final use.

II. CLASSIFICATION BAYESIAN NEURAL NETWORK

A. Feed-Forward Two-Layer Propagation

Feed-forward two-layer neural networks have been widely used in engineering applications. This type of neural network can be used for non-linear regression and classification problems. The feed-forward propagation of the network can be expressed as follows:

$$y = f_1(w_1x + b_1) = f_1(a_1) \quad (1)$$

where x is the input vector, w_1 is the weight and bias vector on the connection from the input nodes to the hidden nodes, b_1 is the bias of the hidden nodes, a_1 is the activation vector of the hidden nodes, and f_1 is the activation function of the hidden nodes, and y is the vector of output values of the hidden nodes. The output values of the output nodes are given by:

$$z = f_2(y\bar{w}_2 + \bar{b}_2) = f_2(\bar{a}_2) \quad (2)$$

Similarly, \bar{w}_2 is the vector of weights and biases on the connection from the hidden nodes to the output nodes, \bar{b}_2 is the vector of the biases of the output nodes, \bar{a}_2 is the vector of the activation of the output nodes, and f_2 is the activation function of the output nodes. In the network, w_1 , b_1 , \bar{w}_2 and \bar{b}_2 are four vectors corresponding to four groups of weights and biases.

For both regression and classification problems, the activation function of the hidden nodes, f_1 , is the "hyperbolic tangent function" (tanh):

$$y = f_1(a_1) = \tanh(a_1) = \frac{\exp(a_1) - \exp(-a_1)}{\exp(a_1) + \exp(-a_1)} \quad (3)$$

For multi-class classification problems, the activation function of the output nodes is the "softmax" function:

$$z_j = f_2(\bar{a}_j) = \frac{\exp(\bar{a}_j)}{\sum_{i=1}^c \exp(\bar{a}_i)} \quad (4)$$

where \bar{a}_j is the activation of the j -th output, c is the number of outputs, and z_j is the output value of the j -th output node. For multi-class classification problems, the error data function has the following form:

$$E_D(w) = -\sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^c t_k^n \ln(z_k^n(w)) \quad (5)$$

where E_D is called the "entropy" function, z_k^n is the output of the k -th output node corresponding to the n -th training pattern, t_k^n is the target corresponding to the k -th output node and the k -th training pattern, and $w = [w_1, b_1, \bar{w}_2, \bar{b}_2]$ is the vector of weights and biases in four groups.

B. Network Regularization

To avoid the overfitting phenomenon for the feed-forward neural network when it is trained on noisy and finite training data, a weight penalty function should be used by adding it to the data function to obtain a cost function as follows:

$$S(w) = E_D(w) + \sum_{g=1}^G \xi_g \|w_g\|^2 \tag{6}$$

where w_g is the vector of weights and biases in the g -th group, and ξ_g represents the regularization parameters or hyperparameters that can be determined using the Bayesian approach. Equation (6) is based on the principle of penalizing the large weights and biases that can cause overfitting to the network when the training data are very noisy and finite.

C. Bayesian Inference

The purpose of conventional neural network training is to minimize a data error function to obtain specific weight and bias values. Meanwhile, the use of the Bayesian approach in neural network training considers the distribution of weights and biases. Bayesian inference is quite easy to understand. Using the Bayes rule, the posterior distribution of weights and biases, given the vector of hyperparameters $\psi = [\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_g]$ and the training data D , can be expressed as:

$$p(w|D, \psi) = \frac{p(D|w, \psi)p(w|\psi)}{p(D|\psi)} \tag{7}$$

where $p(w, \psi)$ is the prior distribution of weights and biases, $p(D|w, \psi)$ is the dataset likelihood, $p(D|\psi)$ is called the evidence, and $p(w|D, \psi)$ is the posterior distribution of weights and biases. By assuming that the prior distribution is a zero-mean Gaussian distribution:

$$p(w|\psi) = \frac{1}{Z_W(\psi)} \exp\left(-\sum_{g=1}^G \xi_g E_{W_g}\right) \tag{8}$$

$$Z_W(\psi) = \prod_{g=1}^G \left(\frac{2\pi}{\xi_g}\right)^{\frac{W_g}{2}} \tag{9}$$

where $Z_W(\psi)$ is the normalization constant and W_g is the number of weights and biases in group g . The dataset likelihood has the following form:

$$p(D|w, \psi) = \exp(-E_D) \tag{10}$$

It was also assumed that at the most probable vector of weights and biases, w_{MP} , the cost function can be approximated as a quadratic function by a Taylor series expansion as follows:

$$S(w) = S(w_{MP}) + \frac{1}{2}(w - w_{MP})^T A(w - w_{MP}) \tag{11}$$

where $S(w_{MP})$ is the cost function evaluated at w_{MP} , and A is the Hessian matrix of the cost function, which is computed as follows:

$$A = \nabla \nabla S(w_{MP}) = H + \sum_{g=1}^G \xi_g I_g \tag{12}$$

where $H = \nabla \nabla E_D(w_{MP})$ is the Hessian matrix of the data error function at w_{MP} , and I_g is the diagonal matrix having ones along the diagonal that picks weights and biases in the g -th group. It can be also assumed that the posterior distribution of weights and biases is a Gaussian distribution as follows:

$$p(w|D, \psi) = \frac{1}{Z_S(\psi)} \exp(-S(w)) \tag{13}$$

where $Z_S(\psi)$ is the normal constant for the Gaussian approximation, given by:

$$Z_S(\psi) \approx \exp(S(w_{MP})) (2\pi)^{W/2} (\det A)^{-1/2} \tag{14}$$

Using Bayes' theorem, the posterior distribution of the hyperparameters can be computed as follows:

$$p(\psi|D) = \frac{p(D|\psi)p(\psi)}{p(D)} \tag{15}$$

As $p(D)$ does not depend on the network parameters, (15) becomes:

$$p(\psi|D) \equiv p(D|\psi)p(\psi) \tag{16}$$

where $p(\psi)$ is the prior distribution of the hyperparameters. This distribution can be assumed to be uniform and can be ignored subsequently. Therefore, the values of the hyperparameters will be determined according to the maximum of $p(D|\psi)$. Re-arranging (7) gives:

$$p(D|\psi) = \frac{p(D|w, \psi)p(w|\psi)}{p(w|D, \psi)} \tag{17}$$

In (17), all terms of the right-hand side can be determined using (8), (10) and (13), therefore (17) yields:

$$p(D|\psi) = \frac{Z_S(\psi)}{Z_W(\psi)} \tag{18}$$

Substituting (9) and (14) into (18) gives:

$$p(D|\psi) = \exp(S(w_{MP})) (\det A)^{-1/2} \prod_{g=1}^G (\xi_g)^{W_g/2} \tag{19}$$

Taking the derivative of $\ln p(D|\psi)$ for ξ_g results in:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_g} \ln p(D|\psi) = \frac{W_g}{2\xi_g} - E_{W_g} - \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(A^{-1}) I_g \tag{20}$$

By letting this derivative be zero, the following relationship can be obtained:

$$2\xi_g E_{W_g} = W_g - \xi_g \text{tr}(A^{-1}) I_g \tag{21}$$

The right-hand side of (21) is equal to γ_g defined as:

$$\gamma_g = W_g - \xi_g \text{tr}(A^{-1}) I_g \tag{22}$$

γ_g is the number of "well-determined" parameters in group g . Substituting (22) into (21) gives:

$$\xi_g = \frac{\gamma_g}{2E_{W_g}} \tag{23}$$

For the most probable vector of weights and biases, ξ_g and γ_g can be used to obtain the log of the evidence of the network as follows [15-16]:

$$\ln E v(X_i) = -S(w_{MP}) + \sum_{g=1}^G \frac{w_g}{2} \ln \xi_g - \frac{1}{2} \ln(\det A) + \ln M! + M \ln 2 + \sum_{g=1}^G \left[\frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{4\pi}{\gamma_g^{MP}} \right) - G \ln(\ln \Omega) \right] \quad (24)$$

where M is the number of hidden nodes and G is a minor constant for all networks. Therefore, this factor does not affect the relative comparison of different candidate neural networks. The network with the highest evidence can be the network having the optimal number of hidden nodes.

D. Quasi-Newton Method

The neural network training requires the use of an effective optimization method to minimize the cost function over the space of weights and biases. The Newton method is a modification of the conjugate gradient method to obtain fast convergence. This method is based on Newton's formula as follows:

$$w_{m+1} = w_m - A^{-1}(g_{m+1} - g_m) \quad (25)$$

where w_m is the weight and bias vector at the m -th iterative step, and w_{m+1} is the weight and bias vector at the $m+1$ -th iterative step. g_m is the gradient of the cost function at the m -th iterative step and g_{m+1} is the gradient of the cost function at the $m+1$ -th iterative step. $A^{-1} = F$ is the inverse Hessian matrix of the cost function and can be approximated using the quasi-Newton method such as the Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb, and Shanno (BFGS) method as follows [13-14]:

$$F_{m+1} = F_m + \frac{pp^T}{p^T v} - \frac{(F_m v)v^T F_m}{v^T F_m v} + (v^T F_m v)uu^T \quad (26)$$

where p , v , and u are defined as:

$$p = w_{m+1} - w_m \quad (27)$$

$$v = g_{m+1} - g_m \quad (28)$$

$$u = \frac{p}{p^T v} - \frac{F_m v}{v^T F_m v} \quad (29)$$

III. EDUCATIONAL AUTONOMOUS MOBILE ROBOT AND OBSTACLE AVOIDANCE

This section describes an autonomous mobile robot with obstacle avoidance capability using a classification BNN. As small two-wheeled robots are easy to get into robotics, the educational robot in this study was formed by a popular two-wheeled mobile robot chassis, as shown in Figure 1, consisting of two driving wheels attached to each side of the robot chassis and driven by two DC motors. To detect obstacles, the robot was equipped with three HC-SR05 ultrasonic sensors, as shown in Figure 2, for the following reasons:

- Ultrasonic sensors can sense all material types.
- Ultrasonic sensors are not affected by atmospheric dust, rain, snow, etc.
- Ultrasonic sensors can work under any adverse conditions.

- Ultrasonic sensors have higher sensing distances compared to inductive/capacitive proximity sensor types.
- Ultrasonic sensors provide good readings when sensing large-sized objects with hard surfaces.

A Raspberry Pi 4 embedded computer was used as the main controller. Raspberry Pi 4 is the latest series of the Raspberry Pi, including more robust performance compared to the previous series. The use of Raspberry Pi allows for the convenient data acquisition from the ultrasonic sensors corresponding to different navigation modes of the robot. In addition, Raspberry Pi can facilitate the quick and easy development of control algorithms using the Python programming language and explore various Python libraries of machine learning, such as Scikit-learn, Keras, and TensorFlow. An Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) HAT for Raspberry Pi is used to power it. Figures 3 and 4 show the Raspberry Pi 4 and the whole robot. The robot and a PC/laptop can communicate through a Wi-Fi router and RealVNC software. WinSCP software was used to transfer data from the PC to the robot and vice versa.

A. Data Generation

To develop a BNN-based obstacle avoidance algorithm for the robot, a dataset is needed to train and test it. The data consists of information from ultrasonic sensor readings and the corresponding navigation modes, which can also be known as targets. This step can be carried out by human dexterity in manually navigating the robot, but this takes significant time, and sometimes it is not effective. Instead, an algorithm for navigating the robot without obstacle collisions in some terrains is proposed to obtain the robot navigation data.

Fig. 1. Two-wheeled mobile robot chassis.

Fig. 2. The HC-SR05 ultrasonic sensor.

Fig. 3. Raspberry Pi 4 embedded computer.

Fig. 4. The whole mobile robot.

Three ultrasonic sensors were used to measure three distances from the robot to obstacles, according to three directions: left, central, and right. A threshold was then defined to categorize each distance variable into two states: far obstacle and near obstacle. Experimentally, the suitable value of the threshold was set to 30 mm. This means that the robot is near an obstacle if the measured distance is less than or equal to 30 mm, and if the measured distance is greater than 30 mm, the robot is far from the obstacle. There are only three navigation modes: forward, left, and right movements. For left and right movements, the robot is needed to move backward before it can turn left or right.

Table I shows the navigation modes corresponding to three states of the three distances. The time required for each navigation mode is experimentally determined to avoid too fast or too slow response during the robot's navigation around the terrain.

TABLE I. NAVIGATION MODES ACCORDING TO DISTANCE STATES

Distance state			Navigation mode
Left distance	Central distance	Right distance	
Far obstacle	Far obstacle	Far obstacle	Forward movement
Near obstacle	Far obstacle	Far obstacle	Backward and then right movement
Far obstacle	Near obstacle	Far obstacle	Backward and then left movement
Near obstacle	Near obstacle	Far obstacle	Backward and then right movement
Far obstacle	Far obstacle	Near obstacle	Backward and then left movement
Near obstacle	Far obstacle	Near obstacle	Forward movement
Far obstacle	Near obstacle	Near obstacle	Backward and then left movement
Near obstacle	Near obstacle	Near obstacle	Backward and then right movement

Table II is used to generate the training data for the classification BNN, while Table III shows several patterns, including three distance sensor values and corresponding navigation target modes.

TABLE II. NAVIGATION MODE AND CORRESPONDING TARGET VECTORS

Navigation mode	Target vectors		
Forward movement	1	0	0
Backward movement and then left movement	0	1	0
Backward movement and then right movement	0	0	1

TABLE III. SEVERAL INPUT PATTERNS AND CORRESPONDING TARGET VECTORS

Distances from the robot to obstacles (mm)			Target vectors		
Left	Central	Right			
65.32	20.09	19.89	0	1	0
117.12	63.04	47.49	1	0	0
20.73	24.69	124.07	0	0	1
81.65	43.43	29.93	0	1	0
88.82	61.87	47.58	1	0	0

Based on Table I, the robot was programmed to move in an environment with some obstacles. Then the data from the three ultrasonic sensors corresponding to the robot navigation modes were recorded as shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV. PATTERNS OF TRAINING DATA

Navigation mode	Number of patterns
Forward movement	315
Left movement	40
Right movement	44
Total	399

B. Network Training Procedure

The network training was performed using the Netlab software [16], which is an open-source MATLAB neural network toolbox with the following features:

- Netlab was developed using pure MATLAB programming language and does not depend on other MATLAB toolboxes.
- It was developed with the automated neural network regularization using the Bayesian technique.
- Based on Netlab, users can rank and compare different neural networks with different numbers of hidden nodes to finally choose the most suitable number of hidden nodes for their applications.
- Instead of using a fixed value of the learning rate, advanced neural network training algorithms in Netlab can be used to obtain true convergences when minimizing highly nonlinear cost functions.

The raw data need to be normalized into a range from 0 to 1 to be used in the network training process. In particular, the measured distance sensor values were divided by 1500. The structure of the BNN consists of three input nodes, an appropriate number of hidden nodes, and three output nodes. The network training procedure includes the following steps:

- Step 1: Values of the network weights and biases were randomly initialized using a zero-mean Gaussian distribution.
- Step 2: Initial values of the four hyperparameters constraining magnitudes of weights and biases in the four groups were also assumed to be small.
- Step 3: Quasi-Newton optimization was used to minimize the cost function. This step can be also known as the weight and bias update process.

- Step 4: When the cost function reaches a local minimum, the hyperparameters can be re-estimated using the following equations:

$$A = H + \sum_{g=1}^G \xi_g^{old} I_g \tag{30}$$

$$\gamma_g^{old} = W_g - \xi_g^{old} tr(A^{-1}) I_g \tag{31}$$

$$\xi_g^{new} = \frac{\gamma_g^{old}}{2E_{W_g}} \tag{32}$$

Direct calculation of the Hessian matrix of the data error function H can be alternated by an efficient method that does not require time-consuming computations [17]. Steps 3 and 4 were repeated until the hyperparameter values did not change significantly in subsequent iterations.

C. Optimization of Network Structure

To find the most suitable network structure corresponding to the optimal number of hidden nodes, seven networks with different numbers of hidden nodes, ranging from 2 to 8, were trained and evaluated. As shown in Figure 5, the network with four hidden nodes provided the highest log evidence. Therefore, the optimal number of hidden nodes is four.

Fig. 5. Log evidence versus the number of hidden nodes.

Table V shows the confusion matrix of the network performance with the training data. The overall accuracy was 97.24%. After training the network, the robot operated on a new terrain. During this period, the information from the ultrasonic sensors and the corresponding navigation modes were recorded to form the test data, as shown in Table VI. Table VII shows the confusion matrix of the network performance with the test data. The overall accuracy of the navigation mode classification was also relatively high, with a successful rate of 96.29%.

TABLE V. CONFUSION MATRIX ON THE TRAINING DATA

		Predicted classification		
		Forward movement	Left movement	Right movement
Actual classification	Forward movement	309	4	2
	Left movement	3	36	1
	Right movement	0	1	43
Overall accuracy (%)		97.24		

TABLE VI. PATTERNS OF THE TEST DATA

Navigation mode	Number of patterns
Forward movement	161
Left movement	15
Right movement	40
Total	216

TABLE VII. CONFUSION MATRIX ON THE TEST DATA

		Predicted classification		
		Forward movement	Left movement	Right movement
Actual classification	Forward movement	156	1	4
	Left movement	2	11	0
	Right movement	1	0	39
Overall accuracy (%)		96.29		

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated an interesting exploration of BNN classification in developing an effective obstacle avoidance algorithm for an educational autonomous mobile robot platform. The BNN was trained offline using the quasi-Newton optimization technique, and its structure was also optimized based on the Bayesian approach. The proposed BNN can handle the uncertainty of the training data, so that it can generalize well with unseen data. The future direction of this research is to investigate obstacle avoidance algorithms based on other machine learning algorithms, including Decision Trees, Support Vector Machines, Gaussian Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Random Forests. Further studies should also be performed using other input devices, such as laser sensors and cameras, to develop more effective obstacle avoidance methods.

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Application of the Slime Mould Algorithm on the Bi-Objective Environmental Economic Dispatch Problem

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the performance of one of the latest metaheuristic swarm-based approaches called Slime Mould Algorithm (SMA). SMA is used here to solve the static bi-objective constrained Economic Emission Dispatch (EED) problem in the presence of renewable energy sources while considering the Valve-Point Effects (VPE). The SMA approach is applied to indicate the adequate optimal solutions for operating the committed thermal units under different operational constraints. The sought optimal solutions are the midpoint between cost saving and pollutant gas emission reduction. This study also examines the influence of integrating renewable energy sources (wind and solar) into the conventional power production network. SMA technique is applied on 3- and 6-unit IEEE test systems in several case studies. The simulation numerical results indicate that SMA has a high efficiency and a better performance compared to known state-of-the-art algorithms. The proposed approach was programmed and simulated in MATLAB.

Keywords-economic emission dispatch; renewable energy sources; slime mould algorithm; valve-point effects

I. INTRODUCTION

For fuel-based power systems, the Economic Dispatch (ED) remains a major optimization problem that can be tackled by tracking the electrical consumption which helps anticipate the required power production that should be satisfied with existing operating production units while preserving the minimum possible cost. This task aims at finding the adequate to-be-produced power per operating generator that meets the power demand and operational constraints. Traditionally, an ED

problem is formulated to seek for the optimum fuel cost regardless of the pollutant gas emitted in the air by thermal units. But due to the high consciousness of environmental protection, the harmful produced emissions lead to the formulation of the bi-objective Emission Economic Dispatch (EED) problem in which fuel cost and pollutant emissions are considered simultaneously to be optimized whereas these two objectives are incompatible in a way that any decrease in the emissions tends to increase fuel costs and vice-versa [1], so,

optimization tools tend to find the proper allocation of generating units in order to acquire the best compromise between reducing the quantity of emission and cost in the same time. On the other hand, studies have revealed that the integration of renewable energy into the conventional power production system plays a significant role in the reduction of both fuel cost and pollutant emissions due to its cheaper production cost and lower environmental impact. Nevertheless, renewable energy sources present some disadvantages such as their intermittent nature [2].

Nowadays, several meta-heuristic algorithms have been utilized in a wide range of engineering problems. Such techniques are usually inspired from real-life aspects such as physical, biological, or environmental processes [3]. Some of the meta-heuristic techniques have been used to solve EED problems. In [4], the EED with Valve Point Effect (VPE) consideration was solved using the genetic algorithm. Particle swarm optimization was applied in [5] to solve the EED problem in the presence of wind power. Grey wolf optimizer was applied in [6] to the EED with the integration of a wind farm. The bi-objective problem was solved in [7] with the use of cuckoo search. Teaching learning based optimization was developed in [8] to solve the EED taking VPE into account. These methods yield high-quality solutions for the EED problem with non-linear and non-convex cost functions by reaching global or near-global optimal solutions [9]. Among the numerous existing meta-heuristic optimization approaches, in this work we propose adapting and evaluating a swarm-based approach to the EED problem in the presence of the most popular renewable energy sources, solar and wind. The Slime Mould Algorithm (SMA), initially introduced in 2020 [10], is inspired by a natural behavior based on the phenomenon of slime oscillation.

II. ENVIRONMENTAL ECONOMIC DISPATCH WITH WIND AND SOLAR PENETRATION

The EED problem is defined as a constrained multi-objective optimization problem that aims to minimize simultaneously the total power cost and the emissions of pollutant gases while satisfying the power balance and operational constraints.

A. Objective Functions

1) Cost Function

One of the bi-objectives of the EED problem is to minimize the total fuel generation cost which can be formulated as follows:

$$\text{Minimize}(F_T = \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} C(P_{Gi})) \quad (1)$$

where F_T is the total generation cost function in \$/h. $C(P_{Gi})$ is the cost of the i^{th} generation unit, P_{Gi} is the real output power of the i^{th} generation unit, and i is the number of committed generation units.

For conventional economic dispatch problem, the fuel cost function of the thermal generation unit is approximated by a smooth quadratic function as follows:

$$C(P_{Gi}) = a_i + b_i P_{Gi} + c_i P_{Gi}^2 \quad (2)$$

where a_i , b_i , and c_i , are the cost coefficients of the i^{th} generation unit.

However, in reality, a multiple steam valves exist in large turbines whose role is to maintain the power balance in fuel generation units. These valves open and close with the objective of reaching a certain load. Due to this practice, a non-convexity appears in fuel cost function, called valve-point loading. This non-convexity is modelled as [11]:

$$C(P_{Gi}) = a_i + b_i P_{Gi} + c_i P_{Gi}^2 + \left| d_i \sin \left[e_i (P_{Gi}^{\min} - P_{Gi}) \right] \right| \quad (3)$$

where d_i and e_i are the valve-point coefficients of the fuel cost for the i^{th} generating unit.

2) Emission Function

The other objective of EED problem is to minimize the production of atmospheric emissions such as SO_x , NO_x , and CO_2 caused by the operation of fossil fuel power units. Among the various harmful gases emitted by each generation unit, NO_x is particularly considered in this study due to its globally-recognized high risk. The emission function is a quadratic function which is described as [12]:

$$\text{Minimize}(E_T = \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} E_{\text{NO}_x}(P_{Gi})) \quad (4)$$

where:

$$E_{\text{NO}_x}(P_{Gi}) = \alpha_i + \beta_i P_{Gi} + \gamma_i P_{Gi}^2 \quad (5)$$

where E_T is the total emission function measured in kg/h, E_{NO_x} is the NO_x emission of the i^{th} generating unit, α_i , β_i and γ_i are the NO_x emission coefficients of the i^{th} generating unit.

3) Total Objective Function

The above non-linear combined EED represents a bi-objective optimization problem that could be converted into a single-objective function by the use of the price penalty factor. The weighted objective function is represented as follows:

$$FO = \omega F_T(P_{Gi}) + h(1 - \omega) E_T(P_{Gi}) \quad (6)$$

where ω is the weight factor in a range [0, 1] and h is the price penalty factor. h is the ratio between the maximum fuel cost and the maximum emissions of the corresponding generator:

$$h_i = \frac{C(P_{Gi}^{\max})}{E_{\text{NO}_x}(P_{Gi}^{\max})} \quad (7)$$

B. Wind and Solar Power Modeling

Environmental concerns surrounding the operation of fuel-based production power systems comprise the contribution to the global warming, the exhaustion of fossil fuels, and the emission of different forms of harmful gazes in the air. These concerns provide the stimulus to increase the utilization of renewable energy sources for its numerous advantages. In our

study we choose to deploy the two most popular green energy sources, solar and wind power.

1) Solar Power

Solar power has an intermittent form due to its dependency on two climate parameters which are solar radiation and temperature. Thereby the simplified model that allows predicting the maximum power provided by a solar panel is written in terms of climate parameters [13]:

$$P_s = k_1 E_c [1 + K_2 (T_j - T_{jref})] \quad (8)$$

where E_c is solar radiation, T_j is the cell junction temperature, T_{jref} is the reference temperature of the panel at 25°C, k_1 represents the dispersion characteristic of the panels where the value for one panel with a range of [0.095, 0.105], and the parameter $K_2 = 0.47\% / ^\circ C$ is the drift in panels temperature.

This mathematical model is improved with the addition of a third parameter:

$$P_s = K_1 [1 + K_2 (T_j - T_{jref})] (K_3 + E_c) \quad (9)$$

2) Wind Power

Wind power is a clean and cheap renewable energy resource. However, the stochastic availability of the wind poses challenges in terms of operation and control that is why wind turbines should be built with mechanical adjustment to develop minimal power from a minimal wind speed in a way to avoid mechanical overload. The maximum wind power provided by a wind turbine can be predicted by [2]:

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_p A v^3 10^{-3} \quad (10)$$

where A is the traversed area by the wind (m^2), is the air density ($1.225 kg/m^3$), v is the wind speed (m/s), and C is the efficiency factor which depends on the wind speed and the architecture of the system.

C. Constraints

The objective function is minimized under the operational following constraints.

1) Power Balance Constraint

The total generation power must satisfy the demand and the transmission losses.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_G} P_{Gi} - P_D - P_L = 0 \quad (11)$$

where P_D and P_L are respectively the power demand and the transmission lines power losses in MW.

In the presence of renewable energy power the power balance constraint would be updated to the following form:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_G} P_{Gi} - P_D - P_L - P_{Ren} = 0 \quad (12)$$

where P_{Ren} is the total renewable energy power in MW.

The system power loss is approximated by the use of the following relation:

$$P_L = \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} \sum_{j=1}^{N_G} P_{Gi} B_{ij} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} B_{0i} P_{Gi} + B_{00} \quad (13)$$

where B and B_0 are the loss coefficients matrix and B_{00} is the loss coefficient constant.

III. SLIME MOULD ALGORITHM

Slime moulds have fascinated scientists with their ability to navigate by finding the quickest way that lead to their target, which is the source of food. Although they are brainless creatures, they manage to build an intelligent network that is able to calculate the best trajectory. Slime moulds exhibit swarm intelligence. In the Slime Mould Algorithm (SMA) [10], slimes' movements are imitated in order to obtain a problem's optimal solution.

A. Mathematical Model

The mathematical modelling of SMA [10] is based on three phases of the slime moulds movement which are: approach, wrap, and grabble food.

1) Approach Food

Slime moulds approach food according to its odor in the air. The equation that imitates the contraction mode is:

$$\overline{X}(t+1) = \begin{cases} \overline{X}_b(t) + vb \cdot (\overline{W} \cdot \overline{X}_A(t) - \overline{X}_B(t)), r < p \\ vc \cdot \overline{X}(t), r \geq p \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where \overline{X} represents the slime mould location, t refers to the current iteration, \overline{X}_b represents the best individual location currently found, i.e. the position with the highest odour concentration, \overline{X}_A and \overline{X}_B are two individuals randomly selected from the swarm, vc is a parameter that decreases linearly from 1 to 0, vb is a parameter in the range of $[-a, a]$, where a and is calculated by:

$$a = \text{arctanh}\left(-\left(\frac{t}{\max_t}\right) + 1\right) \quad (16)$$

The formula of p is:

$$\overline{W}(\text{SmellIndex}(i)) = \begin{cases} 1 + r \cdot \log\left(\frac{bF - S(i)}{bF - wF} + 1\right), \text{condition} \\ 1 - r \cdot \log\left(\frac{bF - S(i)}{bF - wF} + 1\right), \text{others} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{SmellIndex} = \text{sort}(S) \quad (18)$$

where condition indicates that $S(i)$ ranks the first half of the population, r denotes a random value in the interval $[0, 1]$, and bF and wF signify the optimal and the worst fitness obtained in the current iteration respectively. SmellIndex is the sorted sequence of fitness values.

2) Wrap Food

The mathematical model for updating the slime mould location is:

$$\overline{X}^* = \begin{cases} rand.(UB - LB) + LB, rand < z \\ \overline{X}_b(t) + vb.(W.\overline{X}_A(t) - \overline{X}_B(t)), r < p \\ \overline{vc}.\overline{X}(t), r \geq p \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where LB and UB are the lower and the upper boundaries of the search agents respectively, $rand$ and r denote random values in $[0, 1]$, and z is a parameter within $[0, 0.1]$.

3) *Grabble Food*

This phase mimics the propagation wave produced by the biological oscillator of slime moulds that changes the cytoplasmic flow in their veins in order to get better food sources. \overline{vb} , \overline{vc} , and \overline{W} are used to simulate the variations of the venous width of the slime moulds. \overline{vb} is a vector of random values between $[-a, a]$ that approaches zero as the repartitions progress, \overline{vc} values oscillate in the range $[-1, 1]$, and tend eventually to zero. \overline{W} mathematically simulates the oscillation frequency of a slime mould based on the food concentration.

B. *SMA Pseudo-Code*

The general procedure of SMA algorithm is described as follows [10]:

- Initialize the parameters population size, dim, LB , UB , z and max_t .
- Initialize the set of random slime mould positions.
- **While** ($t < max_t$)
 - Calculate and sort the fitness of all slime moulds.
 - Update bF , wF and X_b .
 - Calculate W using (17).
 - For** each search agent update p , vb , vc .
 - Update positions of search agents using (19).
 - End For.**
 - End While.**
- Return bF and X_b .

SMA is adapted to our problem in order to search for the best compromise solution between reducing cost and emissions. The parameter dim represents the dimension of the problem, in the EED problem denotes the number of generating units of the network. The fitness function is the objective function of the EED problem. LB and UB are the limits of each generation unit. The parameter z is set to 0.03.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In order to prove the effectiveness of SMA we present the simulation results of applying the proposed algorithm on the IEEE 9-bus and 30-bus systems, under different scenarios. The

cost and NO_x coefficients for the IEEE 9-bus and 30-bus systems are taken from [14, 15]. Simulations were programmed using MATLAB and were carried out for the three following case studies:

- Case study 1: EED problem without VPE consideration.
- Case study 2: EED problem with VPE consideration.
- Case study 3: EED with VPE consideration in the presence of renewable energy.

We note that in all the studied cases, the transmissions lines power losses are taken into consideration and calculated with the use of (13) where the loss coefficients matrix of the IEEE 9-bus and 30-bus systems are given in (20) and (21).

$$B_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.00003 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.00009 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.00012 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B_{0i} = [0 \ 0 \ 0]$$

$$B_{00} = 0$$

$$B_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.000218 & 0.000103 & 0.000009 & -0.00001 & 0.000002 & 0.000027 \\ 0.000103 & 0.000181 & 0.000004 & -0.000015 & 0.000002 & 0.00003 \\ 0.000009 & 0.000004 & 0.000417 & -0.000131 & -0.000153 & -0.000107 \\ -0.000010 & -0.000015 & -0.000131 & 0.000221 & 0.000094 & 0.000050 \\ 0.000002 & 0.000002 & -0.000153 & 0.000094 & 0.000243 & -0.000001 \\ 0.000027 & 0.00003 & -0.000107 & 0.000050 & -0.000001 & 0.000358 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B_0 = [-0.000003 \ 0.000021 \ -0.000056 \ 0.000034 \ 0.000015 \ 0.000078]$$

$$B_{00} = 0.000014 \quad (21)$$

A. *Case Study 1*

1) *9-Bus System*

In this case study the SMA was applied to solve the bi-objective EED problem without VPE consideration. The power demand to be satisfied by the 3 generating units is 850MW. In order to find the best compromise that provides the minimum cost and the minimum emissions in the same time, the SMA program was run several times for all the possible values of weight factor in the range of $[0, 1]$ with a step of 0.1. The simulations results are compared to NSGA II [16] and CSA [17] and are represented in Table I.

TABLE I. IEEE 9-BUS RESULTS COMPARISON FOR CASE STUDY 1

Unit	Method		
	NSGAI	CSA	SMA
P_{G1} (MW)	470.9502	470.9570	448.2615
P_{G2} (MW)	280.7243	280.6630	350.9556
P_{G3} (MW)	113.6211	113.6750	111.7446
P_L (MW)	15.2950	15.2940	15.9507
Cost (\$)	8149.7220	8349.7200	8346.7192
NO_x emission (kg/h)	0.09654	0.09654	0.0894
Convergence time (s)	-	0.09	14.851

The convergence curve of the SMA for this case study is presented in Figure 1. We notice that SMA provides lower cost than NSGA II and CSA with a profit of 0.035%. Furthermore, SMA yields a better solution of NO_x emissions with an important profit of 7%.

Fig. 1. IEEE 9-bus SMA simulation results for case study 1.

2) 30-Bus System

For this case study ,the total fuel cost and the emission index are simultaneously optimized. SMA was run for the following values of weight factor: 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1. The population size was chosen as 1000 generations, and the iteration number as 500. The performance of SMA is compared to the metaheuristic method HSABC [18]. Table II gives the comparison results of the two previously mentioned approaches for the different weight factor values for a power demand of 283.4 MW. The convergence curves for each value of weight factor are presented in Figures 2-6. As we can notice from Table II, the performance of SMA in reducing cost and emissions comparing to HSABC is noticeable. For instance, the profit in cost and NO_x emissions for ω=0 is 16% and 39% respectively.

TABLE II. IEEE 30-BUS RESULTS COMPARISON FOR CASE STUDY 1

Weight factor Method	ω = 0		ω = 0.25		ω = 0.5		ω = 0.75		ω = 1	
	HSABC	SMA	HSABC	SMA	HSABC	SMA	HSABC	SMA	HSABC	SMA
P _{G1} (MW)	112.29	124.7182	117.60	127.4754	126.07	128.9988	140.68	151.8794	177.46	175.4329
P _{G2} (MW)	46.96	51.80738	48.26	54.08803	49.74	47.30148	50.66	56.72804	49.35	47.10369
P _{G3} (MW)	34.87	27.31135	31.48	28.10535	28.40	27.02738	25.25	18.81466	19.63	21.20746
P _{G4} (MW)	31.48	31.79245	31.66	28.93342	31.80	32.73101	30.90	18.44586	22.83	25.15064
P _{G5} (MW)	30.00	28.87296	29.54	25.6102	26.63	24.14822	21.74	23.57249	12.11	10.78865
P _{G6} (MW)	33.29	24.91275	30.71	25.44564	27.17	29.36644	21.54	21.93089	12.00	12.88029
P _i (MW)	5.49	6.0085	5.85	6.2447	6.41	6.1785	7.37	7.9714	9.98	9.1631
Cost (\$)	854.11	715.9176	843.10	743.8086	830.28	772.8311	815.89	797.7263	803.89	801.9348
NO _x emissions (kg/h)	610.07	370.8056	611.76	373.4120	619.81	372.7811	645.57	409.4590	765.87	456.2331
Convergence time (s)	-	71.458	-	72.695	-	71.368	-	69.124	-	69.847

Fig. 2. IEEE 30-bus SMA simulation results for case study 2 (ω = 0).

Fig. 5. IEEE 30-bus SMA simulation results for case study 2 (ω = 0.75).

Fig. 3. IEEE 30-bus SMA simulation results for case study 2 (ω = 0.25).

Fig. 6. IEEE 30-bus SMA simulation results for case study 2 (ω = 1).

Fig. 4. IEEE 30-bus SMA simulation results for case study 2 (ω = 0.5).

B. Case study 2

1) 9-Bus System

In this case study, the EED problem is solved with power losses and VPE consideration. The power demand that should be met by the three units is 451 MW. SMA simulation results are compared to LMA [19] and are presented in Table III. For comparison reasons we set the weight factor to 0.5. Figure 7 represents the convergence curve of SMA with 500 iterations for this case study. In this scenario, SMA has over performed

the conventional LMA technique in finding the global optimal solution that provides the best compromise between cost and emission quantity where the profit in cost and emissions are about 15% and 0.65% respectively.

TABLE III. IEEE 9-BUS RESULTS COMPARISON FOR CASE STUDY 2

Unit	Method	
	LMA	SMA
$P_{G1}(MW)$	162.1612	299.4662
$P_{G2}(MW)$	193.0458	100.0000
$P_{G3}(MW)$	102.0527	55.49374
$P_l(MW)$	6.2597	3.9598
Cost (\$)	7393.200	6288.5132
NO _x emissions (kg/h)	0.0923	0.0917
Convergence time (s)	-	15.098

Fig. 7. IEEE 9-bus SMA simulation results for case study 2.

2) 30-Bus System

The bi-objective optimization problem is considered here taking into account the sine component due to the VPE. The required power to be satisfied by the 6 generating units is 250 MW. Table IV presents the comparison of the simulation results of SMA along with LR, PSO, and SA [15]. The final solutions of the committed generating units' output power to meet this specific load demand at the minimum cost along with the pollutant emissions are listed in Table V.

TABLE IV. IEEE 30-BUS RESULTS COMPARISON FOR CASE STUDY 2

Unit	Method			
	LR	SA	PSO	SMA
$P_l(MW)$	5.4046	5.8215	5.8	5.1493
Cost (\$)	741.9553	741.2545	737.3	687.6154
NO _x emissions (kg/h)	288.3688	321.3507	296	314.9093
Convergence time (s)	0.212367	1.787088	0.01	71.366

TABLE VI. IEEE 9-BUS RESULTS COMPARISON FOR CASE STUDY 3

Power demand	700 (MW)		925 (MW)		1050 (MW)	
$P_{Ren}(MW)$	-	122.5553	-	118.3594	-	156.5803
$P_{G1}(MW)$	299.4662	294.8317	498.9322	399.1993	576.4808	546.6408
$P_{G2}(MW)$	249.5997	100	398.0833	322.9384	399.1588	295.3748
$P_{G3}(MW)$	59.65865	87.02962	50.015	99.86653	99.86655	68.78856
Cost (\$)	6982.79	6390.7747	9285.8048	8069.0452	10252.7283	8804.1483
NO _x emissions (kg/h)	0.0924	0.0893	0.1129	0.0969	0.1148	0.0997
Convergence time (s)	15.011	14.454	14.951	15.650	15.036	15.865

The penetration impact of renewable energy power on reducing the cost and the emission quantity is noticeable in the

These results are obtained by using $\omega=0.5$. The convergence curve of the SMA results is illustrated in Figure 8. According to the results presented in Table IV, we can see clearly that SMA provided the lowest fuel cost comparing to LR, SA and PSO. However, when it comes to NO_x emissions LR and PSO provide better emissions index which explains that SMA is succeeded in reaching the best compromise between reducing cost and emissions unlike other approaches.

TABLE V. RESULTS OF THE COMMITTED POWER OUTPUTS

Unit	SMA
$P_{G1}[MW]$	112.217
$P_{G2}[MW]$	50.48498
$P_{G3}[MW]$	15
$P_{G4}[MW]$	25.70552
$P_{G5}[MW]$	22.5664
$P_{G6}[MW]$	29.1755
$P_l[MW]$	5.1493
Cost [\$]	314.9093
NO _x emissions [kg/h]	687.6154

Fig. 8. IEEE 30-bus SMA simulation results for case study 2.

C. Case Study 3

In this case study, we propose solving the EED problem with VPE consideration integrating renewable energy power in the conventional production system. The penetration of renewable energy power should not exceed the 30% of the total power demand.

1) 9-Bus System

To discuss the impact of integrating renewable energy in the network, the program was run for several power demand level with a random penetration level of solar and wind power as well. The weight factor is set to 0.5 in order to give the same importance to the cost and the emissions. Table VI represents three instances of the simulation results.

results shown in Table VI. In other hand, we notice that when the penetration of renewable energy is higher, the reduction in

cost and emissions is also higher. Although, the renewable energy power is a great option to reduce cost and pollutant gases, it is challenging to model it for its stochastic availability.

2) 30-Bus System

In order to investigate the influence of integrating renewable energy sources in the conventional production power system, a 6-unit test system with 3 different power demand levels randomly chosen was solved. SMA was run to converge to the optimum values of the committed generating

units for a weight factor equal to 0.5. The SMA solutions for various values of power demand are displayed in Table VII.

The presence of external power in the conventional power system alleviates the committed generating unit while satisfying the load demand, with minimum cost and emissions. As we can notice in Table VII, penetration of renewable energy that doesn't exceed 30% of the power demand has an important impact on reducing significantly cost and pollutant emissions.

TABLE VII. IEEE 30-BUS RESULTS COMPARISON FOR CASE STUDY 3

Power demand	150 (MW)		283.4 (MW)		400 (MW)	
P_{Ren} (MW)	-	28.4593	-	39.6582	-	84.3431
P_{G1} (MW)	85.1806	53.4728	128.9988	117.1773	199.5841	147.3343
P_{G2} (MW)	20	20	47.30148	46.3378	73.19402	57.35425
P_{G3} (MW)	15	15	27.02738	15.07434	36.4338	19.62882
P_{G4} (MW)	10	10	32.73101	25.70792	35	31.38732
P_{G5} (MW)	10	10	24.14822	22.56547	30	22.5693
P_{G6} (MW)	12	12	29.36644	12	40	29.42706
Cost (\$)	388.7041	323.0898	372.7811	633.0691	1338.5613	865.7911
NO _x emissions (kg/h)	184.9422	158.0846	772.8311	298.1571	710.8778	426.3729
Convergence time (s)	68.956	65.368	67.784	66.258	69.320	69.152

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented the recently developed metaheuristic method SMA that mimics the behavior of slime mould in finding the optimal trajectory that leads to the source of food. SMA is applied here to solve the multi-objective constrained static EED problem for three different case studies. The proficiency of this method was studied on standard IEEE systems of 3 and 6 generating units. This paper contributed to studying a comparative analysis between the proposed method in this paper and other existing methods in an attempt to sort out the approach that yields the best-compromised solution between cost and emissions. Also, the SMA approach is introduced for the first time in this paper as an optimization tool for the EED problem with renewable energy power integration.

According to the results presented in this paper, SMA proved to be a powerful and efficient tool in handling economic dispatch problems. SMA provided global optimum or near solutions with a very insignificant gap. When it comes to solving the whole EED problem with the addition of the challenge of integrating renewable energy power, SMA was run multiple times for different power demand levels and stochastic penetration percentages of renewable energy. SMA has shown its efficiency and robustness in handling such a multi-objective constrained optimization problem.

As a result, the meta-heuristic approach proposed by this work succeeded to deliver better solutions for almost all the studied economic dispatch issues. Hence, it is capable of being used for more complicated economic dispatch problems such as the dynamic economic dispatch.

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Voltage Multiplier based Non-Isolated Buck-Boost Converter

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new non-isolated high-gain Buck-Boost Converter (BBC) that uses a switched-inductor (SL) voltage multiplier. This type of DC-DC converter can be very useful in renewable energy applications, especially PV, where the output DC voltage is stepped up to a higher voltage. The output voltage of the proposed switched-inductor BBC (SLBBC) is around 15 times the input voltage with positive polarity when a 0.75 duty cycle of the power switches is used. This is achieved without the use of a transformer or common-core coupled inductors, so the topology is simple to construct. This high output voltage is achieved by using the SL voltage multiplier, which consists of three diodes and two inductors. There are two power switches that operate synchronously, which is an advantage of the design. However, it is discovered that the voltage gain in the step-down mode of the proposed converter is less than that of the other converters. The proposed converter is analyzed in the Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM). The operating principles and steady-state analysis are presented in detail. MATLAB/Simulink was used to prove the effectiveness of the proposed SLBBC.

Keywords-buck-boost converter; Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM); DC-DC converter; photovoltaic; switched-inductor (SL)

I. INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaic (PV) panels are unsuitable for AC grid integration due to their low output voltage. Therefore, a series connection of PV arrays is required to achieve a large DC voltage. However, this is challenging due to the shadow effect in PV panels [1]. Non-isolated DC-DC converters with a high voltage gain in the step-up or step-down mode that can change the input voltage to a higher or lower value are required in a variety of applications, such as PV applications, fuel cell systems, storage batteries, car electronic devices, and many others [2]. Although buck and boost converters have simple structure and high efficiency, they are not suitable for low or high output voltage due to the limitation on the voltage gain [3]. It is common knowledge that the topology of a switching mode power supply is the most important factor in determining how effectively the system will function and how components should be selected [4]. As a result, this topic has received much attention in research, and over the past few decades, various buck-boost topologies have been suggested. The simplest

topology of BBC is the conventional BBC (see Figure 1), which is a DC-DC converter that has an output voltage magnitude that is larger or smaller than the input voltage with polarity inverted, as can be obviously seen from its voltage conversion ratio (see (1)). The value of the duty cycle (D) determines if the BBC is in the step-up mode or step-down mode. If D is less than 0.5, the BBC will function as a buck converter and as a boost converter when D is greater than 0.5. In step-up mode, the BBC has limited voltage gain and therefore cannot maintain a high output voltage. Although high voltage gain can be achieved at extreme duty cycles (lower than 0.1 in step-down or more than 0.9 in step-up), it is difficult due to the practical constraints of power semiconductor devices. Although the BBC has other forms, such as the Cuk converter, Zeta converter, and Single-Ended Primary Inductor Converter (SEPIC), they all have the same limited voltage gain [5]. However, the Cuk converter has many advantages. It has continuous input and output current and negative output voltage, which can be suitable for applications such as audio amplifiers and signal generators [6].

$$M = \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} = -\frac{D}{1-D} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Conventional buck-boost converter.

Various wide voltage gain converters with winding-cross-coupled inductors are represented in [7]. However, the switches suffer from high voltage spikes, and the system has low efficiency due to the expected leakage in the winding-cross-coupled inductors. This is why the coupled inductor technique is not used in the proposed topology. A novel single-switch cascaded BBC is represented in [8]. However, the output voltage is floating. A modified topology of the conventional BBC is presented in [9], but the output is inverted. A new buck-boost topology is presented in [10], with a low voltage stress. However, the proposed converter has high ripples, and the voltage gain is limited. Quadratic converters, which are represented in [11, 12], can accomplish high voltage gain, but their efficiency is low. A semi-quadratic BBC is presented in [13]. However, the input current is discontinuous, and there is no common ground. The Luo converter using the voltage lift technique is presented in [14, 15]. Although a high voltage gain can be achieved, this kind of topology is complex, expensive, and inefficient. Another topology is the interleaved converter, which is presented in [16-18]. Although this converter can obtain high voltage gain with low voltage stress across switches, this topology faces complexity in its operating mode, converter structure, and control strategy. Other techniques of designing high gain converters are presented in [19-21].

A non-isolated high-gain DC-DC switched-inductor buck-boost converter (SLBBC) with a simple structure is presented in this paper. This type of DC-DC converter can be very useful in renewable energy applications, especially PVs. The output voltage of the proposed SLBBC is 15 times the input voltage with positive polarity when a 0.75 duty cycle of the power switches is used. The SL technique is used in a modified BBC, where three inductors are magnetized when switches are turned on, and three inductors are demagnetized when switches are turned off.

II. PROPOSED TOPOLOGY STRUCTURE, OPERATING PRINCIPLE, AND ANALYSIS

A. Power Circuit

The configuration of the proposed SLBBC is shown in Figure 2. Its main power stage involves two power switches (Q_1 and Q_2), five diodes (D_1 , D_2 , D_3 , D_4 , and D_5), three inductors (L_1 , L_2 , and L_3), two capacitors (C_1 and C_2), and one resistive load (R_1). The two power switches (Q_1 and Q_2) are the only two parts to be controlled, and they work instantaneously. In the proposed converter, the currents passing through L_1 , L_2 , L_3 , C_1 , C_2 , Q_1 , Q_2 , D_1 , D_2 , D_3 , D_4 , and D_5 are defined as i_{L1} , i_{L2} ,

i_{L3} , i_{C1} , i_{C2} , i_{O1} , i_{O2} , i_{D1} , i_{D2} , i_{D3} , i_{D4} , and i_{D5} , respectively. The respective voltages are v_{L1} , v_{L2} , v_{L3} , v_{C1} , v_{C2} , v_{O1} , v_{O2} , v_{D1} , v_{D2} , v_{D3} , v_{D4} , and v_{D5} . The output is connected to a resistive load R_1 whose current and voltage is denoted as i_{out} and v_{out} . Note that $v_{C2} = v_{out}$. The input current and voltage are i_{in} and v_{in} where $i_{in} = i_{O1}$. The duty cycle (D) is applied to the switches Q_1 and Q_2 . I_{in} , V_{in} , I_{out} , and V_{out} are assumed to be the DC values in steady state of i_{in} , v_{in} , i_{out} , and v_{out} . T_S is the switching period which is equal to $1/f_S$, where f_S is the switching frequency. Figure 3 shows the time domain waveform of the proposed SLBBC operating in CCM.

Fig. 2. The proposed SLBBC.

Fig. 3. Main steady-state waveforms of the proposed SLBBC.

B. Modes of Operation

Mode 1: In this time interval, as shown in Figure 4, switches Q₁ and Q₂ are turned on, power diodes D₁ and D₃ are forward biased, and power diodes D₂, D₄, and D₅ are reversed biased. The voltage source V_{in} magnetizes inductors L₁, L₂, and L₃ and charges C₁ through switches Q₁ and Q₂.

Mode 2: In this time interval, as shown in Figure 5, switches Q₁ and Q₂ are turned off, power diodes D₂, D₄, and D₅ are forward biased, and power diodes D₁ and D₃ are reversed biased. It is obviously seen from Figure 5 that the energy stored in L₁ and L₂ is demagnetized to charge capacitor C₁ via D₂ and D₄. At the same time, the energy stored in inductor L₃ is demagnetized to charge capacitors C₁ and C₂ and the resistive load R₁ via the diodes D₄ and D₅.

C. Circuit Analysis

Steady-state analysis is performed based on the following assumptions to analyze the proposed SLBBC:

- All the components used including power switches, diodes, inductors, capacitors, and resistors are ideal.
- The two capacitors C₁ and C₂ are sufficiently large enough so that the voltages across them are considered as constant.

Fig. 4. The proposed SLBBC in the ON mode.

Fig. 5. Proposed SLBBC in the OFF mode.

- The natural time constant of the converter is much higher than the switching period T_s.
- Only the CCM of the proposed BBC is investigated, which is the status when the current passing through the inductors flows continuously. On the other hand, the interval when the inductor current remains zero is the Discontinuous Conduction Mode (DCM). Increased stresses on semiconductor switches, increased rating of passive components, noise, and electromagnetic interference (EMI) are all disadvantages of using DCM [25].

When the two MOSFETs are turned on, the voltages across the inductors L₁, L₂, and L₃ are expressed as:

$$V_{L_1} = V_{L_2} = V_{in} \tag{2}$$

$$V_{L_3} = V_{in} + V_{C_1} \tag{3}$$

When the two MOSFETs are turned off, the voltages across the inductors are expressed as:

$$V_{L_1} = V_{L_2} = -\frac{V_{C_1}}{2} \tag{4}$$

$$V_{L_3} = -(V_{C_1} + V_{C_2}) \tag{5}$$

By applying the volt second method to the inductors, the following expressions can be obtained:

$$V_{in}D - \frac{V_{C_1}}{2}(1 - D) = 0 \tag{6}$$

$$(V_{in} + V_{C_1})D - (V_{C_1} + V_{out})(1 - D) = 0 \tag{7}$$

From (6), the expression of the voltage across the capacitor C₁ can be obtained as in (8):

$$V_{C_1} = -\frac{2D}{1-D}V_{in} \tag{8}$$

By substituting (8) into (7), the ideal voltage gain of the proposed converter can be obtained:

$$M = \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} = \frac{D(3D-1)}{(1-D)^2} \tag{9}$$

D. Voltage Stress

The amount of voltage stress across C₁ is calculated by:

$$V_{C_1} = -\frac{2D}{1-D}V_{in} = -\frac{2(1-D)}{3D-1}V_{out} \tag{10}$$

Also, the voltage stress across the two power switches and the five diodes can be derived by:

$$V_{Q_1} = \frac{1+D}{1-D}V_{in} = \frac{1+D^2}{D(3D-1)}V_{out} \tag{11}$$

$$V_{Q_2} = \frac{1+D}{(1-D)^2}V_{in} = \frac{1+D}{D(3D-1)}V_{out} \tag{12}$$

$$V_{D_1} = V_{D_3} = \frac{D}{1-D}V_{in} = \frac{1-D}{3D-1}V_{out} \tag{13}$$

$$V_{D_2} = V_{in} = \frac{(1-D)^2}{D(3D-1)}V_{out} \tag{14}$$

$$V_{D_4} = \frac{1+D}{1-D}V_{in} = \frac{1+D^2}{D(3D-1)}V_{out} \tag{15}$$

$$V_{D_5} = \frac{D(1+D)}{(1-D)^2}V_{in} = \frac{1+D}{3D-1}V_{out} \tag{16}$$

E. Current Stress

Assuming the circuit is ideal, (17) and (18) are obtained:

$$P_{in} = P_{out} \tag{17}$$

$$V_{in}I_{in} = V_{out}I_{out} \tag{18}$$

The relationship between the DC input current and the output current is obtained in (19) according to the voltage gain obtained in (9).

$$\frac{i_{out}}{i_{in}} = \frac{(1-D)^2}{D(3D-1)} \quad (19)$$

The Ohm's law for the resistive load R_l is shown in (20):

$$V_{out} = R_l I_{out} \quad (20)$$

From the Volt second method, I_{in} and I_{out} can be obtained as functions of I_{L1} , I_{L2} , and I_{L3} . Note that $I_{L1} = I_{L2} = I_{L3}$.

$$I_{in} = D(I_{L1} + I_{L2} + I_{L3}) = D(2I_{L1} + I_{L3}) \quad (21)$$

$$I_{out} = (1-D)I_{L3} \quad (22)$$

From (9) and (18)-(22), the currents I_{L1} , I_{L2} , and I_{L3} can be obtained:

$$I_{L1} = I_{L2} = I_{L3} = \frac{D(2D-1)(3D-1)}{(1-D)^4 R_l} V_{in} \quad (23)$$

$$I_{L3} = \frac{D(3D-1)}{(1-D)^3 R_l} V_{in} \quad (24)$$

The currents of the two power switches and the five diodes can be derived from the voltage stress:

$$I_{Q1} = D(I_{L1} + I_{L2} + I_{L3}) = \frac{D^2(9D^2-6D+1)}{(1-D)^4 R_l} V_{in} \quad (25)$$

$$I_{Q2} = DI_{L3} = \frac{D^2(3D-1)}{(1-D)^3 R_l} V_{in} \quad (26)$$

$$I_{D1} = I_{D3} = DI_{L1} = \frac{D^2(2D-1)(3D-1)}{(1-D)^4 R_l} V_{in} \quad (27)$$

$$I_{D2} = (1-D)I_{L1} = \frac{D(2D-1)(3D-1)}{(1-D)^3 R_l} V_{in} \quad (28)$$

$$I_{D4} = (1-D)(I_{L1} + I_{L3}) = \frac{D^2(3D-1)}{(1-D)^3 R_l} V_{in} \quad (29)$$

$$I_{D5} = (1-D)I_{L3} = \frac{D(3D-1)}{(1-D)^2 R_l} V_{in} \quad (30)$$

Table I summarizes the voltage stresses and current stresses for all the parameters of the proposed SLBBC.

TABLE I. VOLTAGE AND CURRENT STRESSES OF THE PROPOSED SLBBC

Parameter	Voltage Stress	Current Stress
L_1, L_2	-	$\frac{D(2D-1)(3D-1)}{(1-D)^4 R_l} V_{in}$
L_3	-	$\frac{D(3D-1)}{(1-D)^3 R_l} V_{in}$
C_1	$-\frac{2D}{1-D} V_{in}$	-
C_2	$\frac{D(3D-1)}{(1-D)^2} V_{in}$	-
Q_1	$\frac{1+D}{1-D} V_{in}$	$\frac{D^2(9D^2-6D+1)}{(1-D)^4 R_l} V_{in}$
Q_2	$\frac{1+D}{(1-D)^2} V_{in}$	$\frac{D^2(3D-1)}{(1-D)^3 R_l} V_{in}$
D_1, D_3	$\frac{D}{1-D} V_{in}$	$\frac{D^2(2D-1)(3D-1)}{(1-D)^4 R_l} V_{in}$
D_2	V_{in}	$\frac{D(2D-1)(3D-1)}{(1-D)^3 R_l} V_{in}$
D_4	$\frac{1+D}{1-D} V_{in}$	$\frac{D^2(3D-1)}{(1-D)^3 R_l} V_{in}$
D_5	$\frac{D(1+D)}{(1-D)^2} V_{in}$	$\frac{D(3D-1)}{(1-D)^2 R_l} V_{in}$

F. Current Ripples of Inductors

The ripples of the inductors' currents i_{L1} , i_{L2} , and i_{L3} can be obtained by:

$$\Delta i_{L1} = \frac{V_{L1}}{L_1} DT_S = \frac{D}{L_1 f_S} V_{in} \quad (31)$$

$$\Delta i_{L2} = \frac{V_{L2}}{L_2} DT_S = \frac{D}{L_2 f_S} V_{in} \quad (32)$$

$$\Delta i_{L3} = \frac{V_{L3}}{L_3} DT_S = \frac{D(1+D)}{L_3 f_S} V_{in} \quad (33)$$

By knowing the inductors' current ripples, the input voltage V_{in} , the duty cycle D , and the switching frequency f_S , the appropriate values of inductors L_1 , L_2 , and L_3 can be calculated using (31), (32), and (33).

G. Voltage Ripples of Capacitors

The ripples of the capacitors' voltages v_{C1} and v_{C2} across capacitors C_1 and C_2 are obtained by:

$$\Delta v_{C1} = \frac{\Delta Q}{C_1} = \frac{(3D-1)}{2(1-D)R_l C_1 f_S} V_{out} \quad (34)$$

$$\Delta v_{C2} = \frac{\Delta Q}{C_2} = \frac{D}{R_l C_2 f_S} V_{out} \quad (35)$$

By knowing the capacitors' voltage ripples, the output voltage V_{out} , the duty cycle D , and the switching frequency f_S , the appropriate values of capacitors C_1 and C_2 can be calculated by (34) and (35).

III. COMPARISON ANALYSIS

The main reason for designing the proposed SLBBC is its ability to achieve a high voltage gain in step-up mode compared with other BBCs, as shown in Figure 6. The high voltage gain is obtained without a transformer or coupling inductors, which would increase the converter's size, losses, and overall cost. Figure 7 shows a comparison between the single switch buck-boost, hybrid buck-boost, KY buck-boost, and proposed SLBBC in terms of number of switches, diodes, inductors, and capacitors used in each converter.

Fig. 6. Voltage gain comparison.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the number of switches, diodes, inductors, and capacitors.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed SLBBC was designed in the MATLAB/Simulink for 12 V input voltage, 200 W rated power, 50 kHz switching frequency, and 0.65 duty cycle as shown in Figure 8. The duty cycle is greater than 0.5, therefore, the proposed converter operates in step-up mode. The proposed converter's specifications are shown in Table II. The switches

Q_1 and Q_2 will operate simultaneously, and their gate pulses are shown in Figures 9 and 10. The waveforms of the currents passing through the three inductors are shown in Figure 9. The three inductors will be magnetized when the two switches are turned on, and they will be demagnetized when the two switches are turned off. By using the current stress equations (23) and (24) passing through L_1 , L_2 , and L_3 , the theoretical values of currents are around 9 A and 11 A. Figure 10 depicts the voltage waveform across C_1 . The capacitor C_1 will charge when the two switches are turned on, and it will discharge when they are turned off. By using the voltage stress equation (10) on C_1 , the theoretical value of the voltage is -44 V. Figure 10 shows the voltage across the charge pump capacitor C_2 . As shown in Figures 4 and 5, C_2 discharges when the two switches are turned on, and charges when they are turned off. By using the voltage gain formula (9), the theoretical output voltage on the load R_1 and the charge pump capacitor C_2 is around 60 V. Figure 11 shows the input voltage V_{in} , which is 12 V, the output voltage V_{out} , which is around 60 V, and the output power P_{out} , which is 200 W. The efficiency curve as a function of P_{out} is shown in Figure 12. A peak efficiency of 93.14% is achieved when the output power is 340 W. From the above comparisons between the theoretical and the simulation results, one can see that they are in accordance, proving the correctness of the theoretical analysis.

Fig. 8. Simulink model of the SLBBC.

TABLE II. COMPONENTS SPECIFICATIONS

Parameter	Value	Unit
Input voltage (V_{in})	12	V
Output voltage (V_{out})	57	V
Rated power (P_{out})	200	W
Switching frequency (f_s)	50	kHz
Duty cycle (D)	0.65	-
Inductors (L_1, L_2 , and L_3)	3	mH
Capacitor (C_1)	20	μ F
Capacitor (C_2)	100	μ F
Load (R_1)	15	Ω

Fig. 9. Current waveforms of L_1 , L_2 , and L_3 .

Fig. 12. Efficiency curve as function of P_{out} .

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new SLBBC is proposed to make up for the fact that the traditional buck-boost converter has a low voltage gain. The proposed converter can achieve high step-up voltage gain by using the SL technique, which is useful in PV and industrial applications requiring high step-up or step-down voltage gain. The SL voltage multiplier, which consists of two inductors and three diodes, is placed in the buck-boost

converter instead of a single inductor. The two inductors will charge during the ON mode, and they will discharge during the OFF mode. The advantages of the proposed converter are its ability to maintain high step-up voltage gain, its simple construction, and a positive output voltage. Details such as the operating principles, steady-state analysis, and a comparison to other buck-boost converters are provided. The results of the theoretical analysis and the MATLAB/Simulink simulation were matched, which showed that the output could have a high voltage gain.

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Advancing Preauthorization Task in Healthcare: An Application of Deep Active Incremental Learning for Medical Text Classification

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a novel approach to medical text classification using a deep active incremental learning model, aiming to improve the automation of the preauthorization process in medical health insurance. By automating decision-making for request approval or denial through text classification techniques, the primary focus is on real-time prediction, utilization of limited labeled data, and continuous model improvement. The proposed approach combines a Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM) neural network with active learning, using uncertainty sampling to facilitate expert-based sample selection and online learning for continuous updates. The proposed model demonstrates improved predictive accuracy over a baseline Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model. Through active learning iterations, the proposed model achieved a 4% improvement in balanced accuracy over 100 iterations, underscoring its efficiency in continuous refinement using limited labeled data.

Keywords-medical text classification; deep learning; active learning; incremental learning; preauthorization

I. INTRODUCTION

The healthcare industry generates extensive data, including electronic health records, clinical reports, medical claims, and administrative documents. Extracting insights from these data is crucial for patient care, medical decisions, and cost management. However, the volume and complexity of healthcare data pose challenges to effective analysis and interpretation. To address this issue, the use of machine learning and Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques has attracted a growing interest in medical text classification. This involves automatically categorizing medical texts or documents into predefined classes to facilitate the identification of relevant information and enhance relevant medical tasks [1].

An illustrative application of medical text classification is in medical preauthorization tasks. These tasks involve obtaining insurance approval before providing certain services or medications to patients. This process is usually time-consuming, but medical text classification offers an avenue for process optimization and automation by categorizing preauthorization requests. Despite potential benefits, medical text classification faces significant challenges, such as the complexity and dynamic nature of medical data, the high cost and complexity of data annotation, and the unbalanced and noisy nature of medical text data. These make the development of robust classification models challenging [2-3]. Although conventional machine learning algorithms have been applied to such classification tasks, limitations are encountered,

particularly when handling large volumes of data [4]. As such, new approaches are needed to overcome the limitations.

Recent studies have focused on the use of deep learning approaches for medical text classification. These approaches take advantage of the power of neural networks to learn complex and dynamic representations of medical data. For example, in [5-6] Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were used for medical text classification tasks, and the results showed that the models performed better than state-of-the-art methods. In [7], a CNN model based on weak supervision and deep representation was proposed for clinical text classification, achieving an F1-score of 0.97. In [8], a unified deep neural network based on a convolutional layer, a Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (Bi-GRU), and an attention mechanism was used for medical text classification. The proposed method was evaluated on various datasets, achieving accuracies of 89.09%, 93.75%, and 97.73%. In [2], another approach was presented, based on CNN, Bi-LSTM, and Multi-head attention, achieving an accuracy and F1-score of 91.99% and 92.03%, respectively.

In [1], a hybrid text classification model was proposed that combined a gated Attention-Based Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (ABLSTM) and a regular expression-based classifier for medical text classification. This method demonstrated an accuracy of 89% and an F1-score of 0.92. These studies demonstrate the potential of deep learning approaches for medical text classification but also highlight some challenges, such as the requirement for large amounts of annotated data. Active Learning (AL) is a technique capable of minimizing the volume of data required to train a machine learning model and works by iteratively selecting the most informative examples from a large pool of unlabeled data for annotation by a human annotator [9]. This approach can save time and money in data annotation while still achieving high classification accuracy. The effectiveness of AL is evident in its application to medical text classification. For instance, in [10], AL based on a Support Vector Machine (SVM) was used to classify medical text, achieving accuracy levels of more than 90% across four datasets. This result underscores the use of AL as a powerful tool to improve the performance of medical text classifiers. Similarly, in [11], an active learning framework was proposed based on SVM, leading to a 64% reduction in annotation efforts. In [12], active learning was used to classify radiology reports, achieving a classifier performance of 98.25% sensitivity and 96.14% specificity, while also saving up to 92% of the training data required for supervised machine learning. These studies demonstrate the potential of active learning approaches for medical text classification but also highlight the importance of careful selection of informative samples in the AL process.

Deep Learning (DL) is known for its need for large data and its ability to process highly dimensional and unstructured data while inherently performing feature extraction [13]. On the other hand, AL is known for its ability to increase annotation efficiency and reduce annotation costs [14]. Therefore, the combination of DL and AL, known as Deep Active Learning (DAL), combines the advantages of both methods, leveraging the strengths of each one while addressing

their limitations. Therefore, better results are expected, and the application potential of both approaches can be expanded. In [15], a comparative analysis of 11 AL strategies was carried out on the classification of cancer pathology reports. Using CNN as the base classification model, the results showed that using less than half of the data, AL can obtain a similar performance compared to a supervised learning model trained on all available data. In the context of medical text classification, the application of DAL remains limited despite initial success.

This study aimed to bridge this significant research gap by exploring the potential of DAL in medical preauthorization tasks. This study proposes a novel approach to medical preauthorization, which combines the power of deep neural networks with Active Incremental Learning (AIL) strategies to actively select and query uncertain or informative samples for annotation and, consequently, update the model with newly annotated data samples, ensuring continuous model refinement and improved performance. Additionally, this study used a real-world dataset of medical preauthorization requests. The results of this study have far-reaching implications, potentially improving the preauthorization process by enabling faster and more accurate decisions, optimizing cost, and ultimately improving patient care. In addition, these findings offer insights and set the stage for future research in the field.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection and Pre-processing

The first step was to collect and pre-process the data used for medical text classification. A dataset of real preauthorization requests was obtained from a Nigerian Health Management Organization, containing 117,342 preauthorization requests. Ethical aspects were a paramount concern, particularly in the collection and use of patient data, and data privacy and confidentiality were ensured by de-identifying the patient information and complying with HIPAA regulations. The preauthorization request data includes descriptions of diagnoses along with related procedures, treatments, or medications prescribed by healthcare providers. The data were pre-processed using a combination of natural language processing techniques and manual review. At first, duplicates, null spaces, and punctuation were removed, and the textual data were tokenized. Proper encoding is essential to enable the effective processing of categorical features in a neural network. One-hot coding is a conventional method for converting categorical variables into vectors, but it comes with a drawback: notably, a substantial increase in dataset dimensionality and the inability to capture intricate semantic relationships between words [16]. To address these challenges, word embedding was used, which considered the context of words for vectorizing text data and one-hot encoding of categorical features [17].

Class balancing techniques were used as a part of the pre-processing steps as the resulting data exhibited the class rarity challenge, a situation in which the distribution of classes in the training data is not balanced, meaning that some classes have significantly fewer examples compared to others [18, 19]. The class distribution of the dataset was extremely imbalanced with

117,068 authorized requests and 279 unauthorized requests. Most machine learning algorithms have difficulty creating a model that accurately classifies examples in a minority class, as a result of bias toward the majority class samples due to its increased occurrence in the dataset [20]. Therefore, data-level class balancing methods, including Random Undersampling (RUS) and Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) [21], were explored to address this challenge. Random undersampling was used to reduce the number of majority samples with a higher frequency of occurrence or highly similar samples, as this can be detrimental to the performance of the model. When a model is repeatedly exposed to similar samples, it can be biased towards those samples, leading to overfitting, misleading evaluation, and reducing generalization to new data points [20]. SMOTE was also applied for oversampling to achieve a balanced dataset. The pre-processed dataset was of the form $D = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$. D is the dataset containing a total number of n samples, where each sample is a pair consisting of the feature vector x_i and corresponds to a ground truth label y_i , (x_i, y_i) . $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$, since it is a binary classification problem.

B. Model Design

The proposed model consists of a Bi-LSTM neural network that can effectively handle the dynamic and complex nature of medical data. To implement AIL, a stream-based AL scenario and a combination of uncertainty sampling were used as a selective strategy and online learning for model update. In a stream-based AL scenario, unlabeled samples arrive in a data stream, uncertainty sampling involves selecting the most informative samples from the unlabeled data, and querying a human expert for the ground truth is subsequently used to update the model. Online learning involves updating the model with new data in real time, without the need to retrain the entire model from scratch. Figure 1 presents an overview of the proposed framework.

Fig. 1. High-level architecture of the proposed framework.

1) Bi-LSTM

Bi-LSTM, a variant of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), is particularly adept at handling sequential data, such as text. Bi-LSTM enhances the standard LSTM by integrating both forward and backward hidden layers. This configuration allows it to capture information from both preceding and subsequent contexts, giving it a significant edge in sequential modeling tasks compared to the unidirectional LSTM approach that only exploits the historical context [22-23].

2) Active Learning

A stream-based AL approach was used, in which preauthorization requests come in a stream of data. For the selection strategy, the entropy-based uncertainty sampling strategy was used, which is an adaptive sampling strategy that evaluates the model's current state while adjusting the criteria for sample selection based on the model performance. This involves using the entropy of the predicted probabilities as a measure of uncertainty, which is calculated as the sum of the probability of each class multiplied by the log of its probability [24]. In entropy-based uncertainty sampling, following the training of a model on labeled data and its subsequent use to predict labels for unlabeled data, the data points exhibiting the greatest entropy emerge as the most informative ones and are consequently selected for labeling. By selecting samples with the highest uncertainty, the goal is to improve the performance of the model by reducing the uncertainty in its predictions.

3) Incremental Learning

For incremental learning, online learning was used, which involves updating the model with new data in real-time without the need to completely retrain the model. Combining online learning and AL can overcome the main drawbacks of traditional supervised online learning, which are labeled data dependency and concept drift, by actively selecting informative samples for annotation and continuously updating the model as new data become available [25]. Online AL functions through a series of iterative steps [26]. In each iteration, an unlabeled sample is presented to the model, which determines whether to request its label. If the label is requested, this labeled sample is incorporated and used to refine the model; otherwise, the model maintains its current state [27]. This is contrary to the typical online learning process, where the learner requests class labels for all incoming instances. Additionally, during the model update, class weights are applied to samples to effectively address the challenge of class imbalance within the data stream.

C. Model Training

The deep learning model was trained on the preprocessed preauthorization request data. To improve the performance of these models, as well as address overfitting issues common with imbalanced datasets, cross-validation and regularization techniques were used, including stratified k-fold cross-validation, dropout, and L2 regularization. The model was trained using the Adam optimizer, the binary cross-entropy loss function, and the sigmoid activation function. Following the initial model training and evaluation, the active incremental learning phase was activated. For the incoming stream of data samples, the initial model makes a prediction on each sample, and based on the entropy of the model prediction, the most informative samples were iteratively selected for annotation by a human expert. The threshold for the entropy measure was set to 0.8, indicating that only samples with a prediction confidence of at least 80% are considered.

Consequently, the model was consistently updated with the newly labeled samples. After 100 iterations, the performance of the resultant model was assessed in the test set. To simulate the preauthorization request stream, 10% of the dataset was set

aside, and the active learner reads and processes the data samples.

Let D_{init} be the initial dataset containing labeled data samples to be used for model pretraining, represented in (1), where x_i is the i -th data sample and y_i is its corresponding label.

$$D_{init} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^{N_{init}} \quad (1)$$

Let f_{init} represent the initial deep learning model that takes an input data sample x and gives a prediction output \hat{y} :

$$f_{init}(x) \rightarrow \hat{y} \quad (2)$$

Given D_{init} , the model is trained to minimize the chosen loss function L that quantifies the difference between \hat{y} and y :

$$\theta^* = \underset{\theta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{(x_i, y_i) \in D_{init}} L(f(x_i; \theta), y_i) \quad (3)$$

where θ represents the parameters of the model and θ^* , the optimal parameters of the model after training. Let X_{str} be the subsequent unlabelled data stream:

$$X_{str} = \{x_j\}_{j=1}^{N_{str}} \quad (4)$$

For all $x_j \in X_{str}$, the initial model f_{init} predicts the class probability $P(y=c|x_j)$ for each class c . The entropy of x_j is calculated by :

$$H(x_j) = -\sum_c P(y=c|x) \log P(y=c|x) \quad (5)$$

where $P(y=c|x)$ is the predictive probability of class c for input x_j . If $H(x_j) > \sigma$, where σ is a predefined threshold, then select the sample x_j for annotation by the oracle O , $O \stackrel{H(x_j) > \sigma}{\leftarrow} x_j$; query O for the true label y_j^* of the selected sample. The oracle responds with the true label,

$$y_j^*: x_j \stackrel{y_j^*}{\leftarrow} O.$$

Update model f_{init} with the newly labeled data, (x_j, y_j^*) :

$$f_{update} = \underset{f}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{(x_j, y_j)} \sum_{c=1}^C W_{cy_j} \cdot L(f(x_j), y_j) \quad (6)$$

where C is the number of classes, and W_{cy_j} is the class weight for class c in sample x_j . The term $W_{ic} \cdot L(f(x_j), y_j)$ adjusts the loss contribution for each sample and class, based on the assigned class weight. This encourages the model to focus on and improve performance for the less represented class during training. The integration of AL and incremental learning strategies offers the advantage of an iterative process, systematically selecting the most instructive examples to improve the model's training, consequently leading to progressive improvement in its performance over time.

D. Evaluation Metrics

Although accuracy is a commonly used metric to assess classifier performance in machine learning, it becomes inadequate when dealing with highly imbalanced datasets. This is because a classifier giving preference to the majority class can yield an optimistic estimate, leading to misleading results [28]. Here, accuracy fails to differentiate between the correct labels of different classes [29]. To address this limitation, balanced accuracy emerges as a more suitable evaluation

metric. Balanced accuracy computes the arithmetic mean of sensitivity and specificity, treating both classes equally. By doing so, it delivers a more reliable assessment of model performance on imbalanced data [30]. Thus, this study used the balanced accuracy metric to evaluate the performance of the proposed model.

III. RESULTS

The proposed deep AIL model was evaluated on a real preauthorization task dataset obtained from a health insurance company. First, the performance of the initial Bi-LSTM model was compared to a baseline LSTM model, and subsequently, the augmented Bi-LSTM with AIL was compared with them for a more nuanced evaluation. Table I presents the preliminary evaluation results, comparing the balanced accuracy of both models in the validation and test datasets. The results underscore the inherent superiority of the Bi-LSTM model in dealing with the intricacies of medical text data with a balanced accuracy of 0.79. Figure 2, shows the balanced accuracy of the models in eight folds. Furthermore, the adaptive potential of the augmented Bi-LSTM model was evaluated in stages in more than 100 sample queries. This sets the stage for the iterative learning process, where the model progressively refines its predictions over subsequent AL iterations. Table II presents the results of this experiment, indicating that the proposed model achieved increasing performance with a significantly smaller number of labeled samples, underscoring its ability to leverage sparsely labeled data and offering a practical solution to the often resource-constrained medical domain. Figure 3 also shows the incremental improvement of the proposed model with an increasing number of queries and model updates, demonstrating its potential to improve over time after several iterations of training over new data. The proposed model showed a 4% increase in performance throughout the query and training iterations.

TABLE I. RESULTS OF MODELS BEFORE AIL

Models	Balanced Accuracy	
	Validation Set	Test Set
Baseline	0.704	0.737
Bi-LSTM	0.753	0.793

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE REPORTING BALANCED ACCURACY OF MODELS WITH AIL AFTER MULTIPLE QUERY AND TRAINING ITERATIONS

Models	Number of Query Iterations			
	20 queries	40 queries	60 queries	100 queries
Baseline + AIL	0.739	0.702	0.731	0.764
Bi-LSTM + AIL	0.752	0.756	0.769	0.795

The inherent capability of the proposed model to learn consistently from newly annotated data results in gradual performance improvement over time. This intrinsic ability allows the model to evolve and enhance its predictive accuracy with each subsequent set of newly labeled samples. This dynamic learning mechanism enables the model to quickly adapt to the evolving landscape of requests, providing the preauthorization process with increased adaptability and responsiveness. Furthermore, the proposed approach enables real-time prediction and effectively tackles the issue of

inaccurate predictions by incorporating human involvement in the model training process. This empowers insurers to make faster and more accurate decisions about preauthorization requests, ultimately leading to better patient care.

Fig. 2. Balanced accuracy of initial models across folds.

Fig. 3. Balanced accuracy increased across 100 queries and training iterations.

Previous studies on medical preauthorization in health insurance [31-32] relied on traditional machine-learning methods. Although the proposed approach shows potential, it is important to note that previous studies exhibited higher performance than the initial performance of the proposed model, and this could be attributed to the limited amount of

labeled data used to train it. Furthermore, the models in previous studies are rather static, lacking the ability of continuous model updates, and require retraining on an entire dataset to implement any updates. In essence, they are not capable of adapting to the dynamic nature of preauthorization requests, a key feature of the proposed model.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a novel deep AIL framework for medical preauthorization tasks, addressing critical issues in the field, and reducing human annotation effort by selecting only informative samples for annotation instead of requesting class labels for all incoming instances. The proposed model can learn continuously from new data, which improves its performance over time, thus alleviating the strong dependence on labeled data for model training. The experimental results indicate the model's ability to learn from limited data and exhibit ongoing improvements when updated with newly labeled data. Additionally, the issue of class imbalance in the preauthorization request stream was addressed. The model's adaptability demonstrated in its initial performance and subsequent iterative improvements, substantiated its potential as a valuable tool for accurate and evolving medical data analysis, enabling insurers to make faster preauthorization decisions and, in turn, improve patient care.

Although this study yielded promising results, there is room for further research. Future work could investigate alternative DL models, including the use of specialized medical pre-trained word embeddings within a transfer-learning framework, potentially resulting in further improvement in model performance. Furthermore, to address the challenges associated with accessing preauthorization data, it would be valuable to develop a publicly accessible deidentified preauthorization dataset, as such an initiative would not only facilitate collaborative research but also allow effective benchmarking of research results.

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A Short Review on Charge Packets and Space Charge Properties Inside Dielectrics

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ABSTRACT

An effort to highlight the role of space charges inside dielectrics and their propagation is made in the present paper. Solid insulating materials in various parts of high voltage devices and machines are crucial for the insulating performance and their reliable functioning duration. Space charge distributions and space charge propagation in the form of pulses, called charge packets, are studied in this paper pointing out on one hand the initiating mechanisms and on the other hand the propagation mechanisms of charges inside dielectrics, as they are introduced in the scientific literature. Experimental data are used from other papers, mainly those referring to space charge distributions versus space and simultaneously versus time in a classification attempt of the aforementioned parameters.

Keywords- solid insulation; high voltage engineering; space charges; charge packets

I. INTRODUCTION

The presence of space charges inside dielectrics is one of the most prominent indicators of defects and ongoing degradation processes of electrical insulation. As a high percentage of failures are associated with space charges, the need for the classification and evaluation of space charges is essential. Charge transport between electrode-dielectric interfaces were evaluated by measuring conduction currents in [1], and as further improvement to this technique, the Pulse Electroacoustic Method (PEA) was utilized to investigate space charge's profile distribution and transport inside the insulation. As an alternative to conduction current measurements, space Charge Packets (CPs) were introduced. CP analysis constitutes an important ageing factor for the solid insulation. CP is a net charge that remains in the form of a pulse as it crosses the insulation [2]. It has been observed that such packets can cause accelerated breakdown of insulation particularly when associated with continual charge accumulation. Authors in [3] firstly named the generation of packet-shaped SPs in 3-mm thick XLPE under $0.7 \text{ MV/cm} = 70 \text{ kV/mm}$ electrical field strength. CP initiation and propagation needs a strong

theoretical background and analysis, for the charge injection, creation, propagation, and decay inside the polymeric insulation. Some of the most important mechanisms governed the CPs are mentioned below:

- Schottky emission (charge injection from metal to semiconductor/dielectric when the surfaces are in contact). For high fields electron energy (eV) is compared with the Schottky barrier ϕ .
- Fowler – Nordheim injection mechanism (tunneling) for low electric fields.
- Hopping conduction which is a very important mechanism for charge transport inside dielectrics (also called thermally assisted tunneling). This phenomenon corresponds to an intermediate situation whereby a trapped electron is brought by thermal activation to a level with the same energy to that of a neighbor site moving at this site by tunneling. There is discrimination in two cases.
- Conduction - Transport between trap sites charged when empty (Poole-Frenkel effect).

$$J \propto E e^{\frac{B\sqrt{E}}{k_B T}} \quad (1)$$

where J is the current density, B a constant, E the electric field, k_B the Boltzmann constant, and T the temperature.

- Conduction transport between trap sites that are neutral when empty:

$$J \propto \sinh\left(\frac{edE}{k_B T}\right) \quad (2)$$

with e is the electronic charge and d the distance between the traps.

- Trapping.
- Detrapping.
- Recombination depending to field and temperature.

The space charge accumulation may also be connected by:

- Charge ionization.
- Charge irradiation.
- Charge polarizations.

Figure 1 shows the conduction mechanisms in dielectric films. There is a clear discrimination between conduction between metal-dielectric surface (so called injection) and conduction inside the dielectric bulk [4].

Fig. 1. Classification of conduction mechanisms inside the dielectrics.

The basic set of equations for time-dependent diffusionless space charge flow for a single species of mobile charge carrier in a dielectric of constant relative permittivity ϵ are [5]:

$$\nabla J + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

$$J = \mu \rho E \quad (4)$$

$$\nabla E = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon \epsilon_0} \quad (5)$$

The transport equations (6) – (8) with the inclusion of a pair of oppositely charged species (electron and holes) are:

$$\frac{dJ(x,t)}{dx} + \frac{\partial(\rho_e + \rho_h)}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$J = (\mu_h \rho_h \mu_e - \mu_e \rho_e \mu_h) E(x) \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dE(x)}{dx} = \frac{\rho_e + \rho_h}{\epsilon \epsilon_0} \quad (8)$$

In order to describe more phenomena affecting charge propagation (conduction), one must take into account charge trapping, detrapping, and recombination (previously named annihilation). Charges, in the case of dielectric films, can be discriminated into four categories:

- Mobile electrons moving in conduction band.
- Mobile holes moving in valence band.
- Immobile electrons trapped in trap sites.
- Immobile holes trapped in trap sites as well.

Similarly to the aforementioned bipolar charge transport model, in [6], injection from both electrodes takes place following Schottky law with the relevant threshold electric field (barrier). It is evident in [6] that electrons from the cathode are injected to the conduction band with the Schottky injection mechanism and at the same time holes from the anode are injected to the valence band. The movements towards the electrode of the opposite polarity is defined and limited with phenomena such as trapping and detrapping at their relevant bands or at energy regions near their relevant bands. Recombination phenomena are also observed during their movement and propagation.

II. CHARGE PACKET INITIATION

If the applied field exceeds the threshold field, then charge is injected from the electrodes inside the main insulating material and can be accumulated in traps located at the interface. Depending on the material, the applied voltage and the local electric field values, charge accumulation forms homocharges and sometimes heterocharges [7]. The notion of discrete pulse or charge generation in contradiction to the continuous charge generation is underlined in [2]. According to [2], a deeper understanding of electrode-polymer interface is needed, while a local production rate of charge must exhibit a form of hysteresis. Moreover, the low generation rate switches to a high rate, when a given local field is exceeded (similarly to the notion of a threshold field). The charges occur in front of the electrode, alter the electrical field, so the production rate reduces back to low when the modified electrical field is lower than the threshold field (or the threshold field changes its value due to the presence of the charge). The role of the aforementioned hysteresis loop [2] is intensified in [8], where the injection barrier alters its value under certain circumstances. The experimental data presented in [8] show the injection barriers varying between 1.2 eV and 1.3eV. The lower value leads to a high rate of charge injection reducing the local electric field from 160 to 115 kV/mm. After this reduction, the barrier height is restored again back to 1.3 eV decreasing the injection. The initiation and transport of large slow negative pulses was described in [9] by assuming field ionization in a three level system comprising an ionizable state, a trap state, and a valence band state. In this case, a plane of negative ionization is transferred through the system, as mobile holes released by the high field at the front of the plane move at the opposite direction to the plane and finally recombine with the ionized states at the rear of the plane.

III. CHARGE PACKET PROPAGATION AND SPACE CHARGE DISTRIBUTIONS

Space charges are formed inside the main insulating materials when external electric stresses are applied to them. The Pulse Electroacoustic (PEA) method is a commonly used technique to acquire the profiles of space charge density ρ (Cb/m³) versus the location (usually the distance between the electrodes). It must be emphasized that the PEA method and more specifically the PEA signal is very sensitive to the net charge at each point in the insulation bulk. Therefore, if positive and negative CPs (or charges generally) having similar amplitudes are injected simultaneously from both electrodes and overlap at a given point, then the detected PEA signal could show no charge profile (zero charge) at that particular point [7]. So, it is evident that a very difficult issue is the charge separation of positive and negative CPs. Temperature and more often time t are the parameters that are displayed in such profiles. Figures that show steady-state space charge distributions can be seen in [10-12]. The propagation of the above space charge profile from one electrode to the other is the definition of the CP. In [13], a positive charge accumulation is formed immediately after the voltage application in front of the anode with a peak value at 4×10^{-4} Cb/m³ = 4×10^{-4} μ Cb/cm³ space charge density. The sample is LDPE, pressed with PTFE (Polytetrafluoroethylene), so called LDPE – F, whereas a -150 kV/mm DC voltage was applied to the sample. PEA is a method for space charge density calculation. After 10 min, the same profile is calculated. Positive space charge travels inside the insulating material, defining that a CP is a propagating accumulation of the space charge.

Based on the literature, a methodology is proposed for examining CP initiation:

- A negative charge approaching the anode, strongly enhances the electric field (heterocharge), which can cause the first positive CP in series.
- A new packet is formed upon the collapse of the old packet. The second CP is characterized by a high value for electric field in front of the packet (head) and a lower value behind it (tail).
- A third feature is that the positive CP leaves a negatively charged region when propagating. The background is the bipolar nature of transport, where positive and negative charges coexist in the same region.

- A fourth feature is the heterocharge buildup due to the transport of charges and their accumulation near the electrode of opposite polarity.
- The last feature is the weakening of packets, attenuating while propagating (dispersion and pulse widening. Others call this procedure decay).

An important parameter for studying the complex phenomenon of initiation and propagation of CPs is the mobility μ :

$$u = \mu \cdot E \quad (9)$$

where u is the drift velocity (or migration speed), μ is the mobility, and E the mean electrical field. Several studies show that the charge mobility in insulating materials such as Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP) has no-linear dependence on the local electric field. In [14], the samples were LDPE with 25 μ m thick Polyvinyl Fluoride (PVF) films hot-pressed on both sides of the samples to prevent charge injection from the electrodes. Then the samples were irradiated with a 70 keV, 0.18 μ A/cm² electron beam. After irradiation, a remarkable charge accumulation in a packet shape is found in the bulk of the sample near the surface of the irradiated side of the sample. Space charge profiles are acquired in a time range of 0-390 s with repetitive time intervals for every measurement (almost every 30 s). Space charge densities vary from $\rho = -2 \mu$ C/cm³ = -2 C/m³ to $\rho = +7 \mu$ C/cm³, with a 30 kV/mm applied field.

Of course, in other publications and their respective experimental results, the charge profile does not show the same propagating characteristics. In [15], space charge density profiles in pure LDPE, at various values of external applied fields and temperatures show, as time t passes, alterations in their values but they do not show displacement or movements (no propagation happens) from the region where they initially appear. Some space charge distributions in [15] show that some peaks are sharper than others, but, as it is stated, the sensor position plays a crucial role at the measured accuracy. Moreover, scattering of the acoustic wave and attenuation are also important factors for these measurements. With applied fields of 30 and 50 kV/mm, space charge profiles are taken for 60 min with 10 min intervals. The resultant space charge profiles are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. SPACE CHARGE DENSITIES, TIME AND APPLIED FIELD [15]

Material	Applied field	Time range	Temperature	Space charge densities	Remarks
LDPE	30 kV/mm	60 min (profile every 10 min)	24 °C	-20 to +20 μ C/cm ³	No CP movements
LDPE	30 kV/mm		50 °C	-30 to +40 μ C/cm ³	Slight CP displacement
LDPE	50 kV/mm		24 °C	-30 to +35 μ C/cm ³	No CP movements
LDPE	50 kV/mm		50 °C	-15 to +35 μ C/cm ³	No CP movements

In [16], the PEA is also utilized for the CP observation and moreover a Negative Differential Mobility (NDM), is found during CP propagation. The applied field is 20 kV/mm, with 100 μ m distance between anode and cathode, the final subtracted space charge distribution results from -2 to +3 μ C/cm³. The used time for space charge measurements is 100 s.

In [7], the used specimens were cable models reproducing HV cables on a reduced-scale (mini-cables). The minicable consists of 2.8 mm conductor diameter, 0.7 mm inner semiconductor thickness and 1.5 mm XLPE thickness. The space charge profile patterns presented in [7] are distinguished into two categories. In the first category, the material is XLPE

mostly used in HV cables, whereas in the second case XLPE manufactured for MV is used. The polarization time is 10000 s for both cases, the applied electric strength value is 40 kV/mm, the used temperature is 25 and 70 °C, and the final space charge density varies from -10 to +10 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^3$. It is evident from the space charge patterns of [7], that in the first case (XLPE HV cables), heterocharge is concentrated near each electrode and homocharges are shown in the second material (XLPE MV cables). In the first case, heterocharge build-up near both electrodes is noticed almost immediately at the beginning of the voltage application (polarization process). In the second case, it is noticeable that negative space charges are present near each electrode. In the case of the positive electrode, this space charge distribution establishes a heterocharge region whereas in the case of the negative polarity electrode this space charge distribution creates a homocharge region. In XLPE MV, a positive space charge pattern is formed almost at the central region of the insulating material. In [7], a positive charge packet propagates from the anode to the cathode in 0.5 s and after this a negative charge packet is shown travelling from the cathode to the anode in about 0.4 s (0.5-0.9). Of course, CPs of both polarities propagate simultaneously at the interelectrode area but for the sake of clarity these crosses are shown separately. Stationary Wavelet Transform (SWT) and initial profile subtraction were used for different purposes for acquiring space CP profiles. Temperature is a crucial factor for the aforementioned time durations. By increasing temperature, both positive and negative CPs are seen to move faster. In each case it is noticed that negative CPs travel faster comparing to positive CPs, as it is clear from the values in Table II.

TABLE II. CP TRAVELLING DURATIONS DEPENDING ON THE TEMPERATURE [7]

	Positive CP	Negative CP
35°C	0.5 s	0.3 s
45°C	0.3 s	0.2 s
70°C	0.15 s	0.05 s

In [23], a simulation model is suggested for bipolar charge injection, transport, trapping, detrapping, and finally recombination effects. It is supposed that both electrons and holes are injected from the electrodes into the dielectric according to the Schottky law (injected carrier energy greater than the Schottky barrier). Charge trapping and detrapping effects in shallow traps are considered by a temperature dependent hopping type mobility μ as it is shown in (10):

$$\mu = \frac{2dv}{E(x,t)} e^{-\frac{ew\mu}{KT}} \sinh\left(\frac{eE(x,t)d}{2KT}\right) \quad (10)$$

where d is the distance between the shallow traps, v is the attempt to escape frequency, T is the temperature, w_μ is the hopping barrier height for electrons and holes, and K is Boltzmann's constant.

IV. DISCUSSION

The experimental procedure can be discriminated into a low electric field and a high electric field as shown in Table III [16].

TABLE III. HIGH AND LOW FIELD CHARACTERISTICS [16]

Low electric field $E < 55 \text{ kV/mm}$	High electric field $E > 55 \text{ kV/mm}$
No CPs are observed and only the normal space charge profiles are obtained by the PEA method. A bias DC voltage is utilized for the initiation of a CP, which is used as excitation method. A pulse voltage with a width of 250 ms and large amplitude of several kV is superimposed to the DC voltage.	A positive CP is formed without pulse excitation.
A CP (positive charge), is immediately formed (after the preceding excitation) at the anode and travels towards the cathode.	The CP appears 15 s after the voltage application.
The average velocity is evaluated and calculated from more than three measurements. It is first observed in PE. It resembles the "Gunn-Effect", seen in asemiconducting material [34]. It suggests that an NDM is involved in the behavior of positive charge carriers in PE in the case of low fields. According to the experimental findings, mobility can be evaluated for positive CPs and for low electric fields giving values (10^{-15} - 10^{-14}) $\text{m}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{sec}^{-1}$. Moreover, mobility tends to decrease when the field increases.	A decrease in velocity is observed as the field increases. Moreover, mobility calculation for the high electric field values shows that when increasing the electric field, the mobility decreases. In case of high electric field, similarly with the case of low electric field, NDM is noticed. Mobility depends on the electric field.

The relationship between the velocity of the holes and the applied field in polyethylene is demonstrated in [17]. It is noticed that the velocity of holes initially increases with the field and reaches its maximum value. After this peak, the velocity decreases, while E increases. In [14], the dependence of velocity versus the local electric field is obtained. A series of space charge migrations in LDPE are measured under a wide range of electric fields (15-50 kV/mm). In the same paper, the LIPP method (PEA method is the dominant procedure in the majority of scientific experiments) was used for the space charge distributions. A point of interest is that space charge injection was prevented by electrodes, via charge blocking layers, in order to define accurately the charges created due to

polarization and not from other sources (segregation from other sources).

After beam irradiation (maybe functioning as an excitation method), a remarkable charge accumulation of a packet shape, can be found in the bulk of the sample near the surface of the irradiated side of the sample. This CP gradually drifts to the opposite side maintaining its basic shape, consisting according to the definition a CP. The height of the CP gradually decreases due to the trapping effects. After calculations, the above curve shows that after 25 kV/mm, a negative differential region is found in accordance with the Negative Differential Resistivity (NDR) theory. A possible explanation is that mobility from (9) shows that the velocity is dependent on the electric field. The

resultant electrical field cannot be considered as uniform, due to the existence of the CP itself (e.g. a high concentrated charge region) which alters and modifies the electrical field or the resultant field is defined as the superimposition of the external and the local electric field. Additionally, in [13], LDPE was used, with different cooling rates and space charge distributions obtained with the High Voltage Withstand Pulse Electro Acoustic (HVW-PEA) method. Shortly, during the sample preparation, the lower cooling rates lead to a higher crystallinity degree. In three cases of cooling rates (high, medium, low) as the electric field increases (from 100 to 220 kV/mm), the mobility decreases. For values over 150 kV/mm, the mobility remains constant forming a plateau in all the three cases of cooling rates. In [18], it is shown experimentally that the launch of the first positive CP in the series happens when the negative charge front approaches the anode. A field enhancement in the region in front of the anode is responsible for the successive positive CP generation. Moreover, due to field dynamics, a high field corresponds to the front of the packet and a lower field behind it (tail). Another feature for the positive CP initiation and propagation is that the positive charge leaves behind it a negatively charged region according to the bi-polar charge transport, where positive and negative charges coexist in any location being only detected if a local unbalanced situation between them is established (the so called net charge). Authors in [7] however, define low CPs as the packets with mobility from 10^{-12} to 10^{-14} m²/Vsec. In [7], the mobilities for positive and negative charges are calculated for the case of fast CPs. As it is evident from Table IV, mobility increases while the temperature increases, for both charge polarities. Furthermore, negative CPs demonstrate higher mobility values in comparison with positive CPs, at every temperature.

TABLE IV. MOBILITY FOR FAST CPs. THERE IS A DISCRIMINATION BETWEEN POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE CHARGE CALCULATED AT EVERY TEMPERATURE [7]

	Mobility [m ² /Vs]		
	35°C	45°C	70°C
Positive charge	7.2×10^{-11}	9.6×10^{-11}	1.9×10^{-11}
Negative charge	9.6×10^{-11}	1.4×10^{-11}	5.7×10^{-11}

Moreover, in [19], for the separate estimation of positive and negative carrier mobility μ , a double layer experimental setup is used. The used barrier material has an extremely low conductivity and a high charge injection threshold compared with the testing material (LDPE or XLPE). For the experimental measurements held in [19], PTFE (Polytetrafluoroethylene) is used as the barrier material due to the aforementioned characteristics. PTFE was also reported in [13] for the same function.

As it is clear, when a DC voltage is applied between the upper and lower electrodes, carriers are injected from the upper electrode (carbon loaded polyethylene-semicon or SC) and, under certain circumstances, "travel" to the interface between the testing material and the barrier material. The charge buildup at the interface and the transport speed of carriers helps us for the mobility definition. Moreover, the choice of DC polarity allows us the calculation of positive and negative mobility. The PEA is also used for the time-dependent charge accumulation.

As it is mentioned in [5, 19, 20], the solution of the transport equation, the Poisson equation, and the continuity equation (6)-(8) will finally result in the mobility $\mu(t)$ as a function of time:

$$\mu(t) = \frac{2\varepsilon_2 d_2 \frac{dQ(t)}{dt}}{Q(t)(2\sigma_0(t) + \sigma_{if}(t) + Q(t))} \quad (11)$$

where $\sigma_0(t)$ is the surface charge density induced on the ground electrode, $\sigma_{if}(t)$ stands for the interface charges, and $Q(t)$ is the contribution of all the charges in the body of the testing material. Negative DC voltage is applied to SC electrode and the time-dependent space charge profiles are obtained (2 s, 20 min, 40 min, 60 min) for both PTFE/LDPE and PTFE/XLPE double-layer materials. Experimental data for both cases show that PTFE is an efficiently blocking material. Moreover, in the LDPE/PTFE interface, the accumulated charge is greater than the one at the PTFE/XLPE interface. This indicates that charge mobility in LDPE is greater than the mobility in XLPE.

The same results are obtained and in the case of positive DC voltage applied at the SC electrode. Charge accumulation is greater in the LDPE/PTFE interface than that in the XLPE/PTFE interface indicating higher mobility in the LDPE than in the XLPE sample. It is also found that the positive carriers move (slightly) faster than the negative ones. After relevant experiments, it has been found that in LDPE, the accumulated charge at the interface is mostly derived from the upper electrode (SC) through charge injection. Thus the contribution of intrinsic species must be neglected. Similarly, in [21], the field-dependent mobility is simulated versus the electric field. The mobility in [21] is the hopping mobility and the Gaussian Disorder Model (GDM) is used for hopping current estimation (negative charges, recombination effects, and traps). Similarly to the NDM presented above, in the case of hopping conduction, the simulated results clearly show that the mobility decreases as the electrical field increases. An explanation of this decrease is attempted in [21] considering a large amount of space charges moving inside the LDPE, consisting a packet-like. The positive charges accumulate due to the small number of hopping sites in the LDPE. In such a case, space charges move to the cathode and when the distance between them and the cathode shortens, additional space charges are injected from the anode in order to satisfy the constant potential condition. The velocity of the injected space charges is greater than the movement velocity of accumulated space charges due to the empty, vacant hopping sites. Thus, the injected charges are possibly in the form of CPs, and they reach immediately the accumulated space charge. The sudden increase of the accumulated charge leads to a decrease in velocity until the trap sites are fully occupied.

An increase in mobility for small electric fields is also stated in [22]. It was found that for high electric fields ($E > 90$ MV/m) CPs in the form of repetitive pulses transit the dielectric with a mobility from 10^{-16} to 10^{-14} m²/Vs. According to [22], an unexpected outcome of the experiments was the observation of repetitive small charge pulses at lower electric fields (20-50 kV/mm) but having a mobility 4-5 orders of magnitude higher than the ones at high electric fields. In [22], positive and negative CPs are found propagating at the

interelectrode area, with total movement time of 1-1.5 s. Space charge density for CP pulses is -0.1 and $+0.1 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^3$ for negative pulse and positive pulse, respectively, while the applied electric field is $30 \text{ kV}/\text{mm}$. Pulses of both signs show no attenuation or dispersion crossing the insulation with a mean mobility of $10^{-10} - 2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{Vs}$. The presence of these fast charge pulses was also experimentally observed not only with the PEA method but also with direct measurements of charging currents in XLPE cables in the same range of fields and temperatures. In addition, in [22], it is confirmed that space charge pulse mobility is a thermally activated mechanism, with $0.23 - 0.25 \text{ eV}$ activation energy for positive pulses and $0.41 - 0.45 \text{ eV}$ for negative pulses. These values are much smaller than those reported with XLPE, which are typically 1 eV or greater, corresponding to the deep traps that control and govern charge transport and the larger CPs travelling inside the dielectric in higher electric fields. The aforementioned values for mobility activation energy for XLPE are close to those of the mechanical relaxation (β and γ) of XLPE. This raises the possibility that local chain rearrangements associated with these relaxations are involved to the small pulse transport. Moreover, another characteristic of fast small CPs or pulses is that they remain coherent while passing through which results that their motion cannot be described by trap to trap transfer of the charges. Instead, their motion has the feature of a solitary wave, they seem to behave as solitons [22].

Table V summarizes the experimental results from 7 papers showing that LDPE is the dominant specimen used in space charge profile measurements. Moreover, electrical field ranges from 20 to $150 \text{ kV}/\text{mm}$ and the distance between the anode and the cathode d is usually less than 0.6 mm . The various space charge profiles obtained at different time intervals are usually concluded within some minutes. Indicative space charge density values are demonstrated in the third column. It is evident from Table V that the dielectric material itself is one crucial parameter, so in Table VI, LDPE and their relative measurements are listed, similarly to Table V.

TABLE V. SUMMARY OF THE ELECTRIC STRENGTH APPLIED AT VARIOUS SPECIMENS. RELEVANT SPACE CHARGE DENSITY, TIME, AND ANODE-CATHODE DISTANCE ARE SHOWN

Ref.	E (kV/mm)	ρ (Cb/m ³)	t (min)	d (mm)	Material
[12]	80	1.2	90	3.5	XLPE
[13]	150	400	10	0.1	LDPE-F
[13]	150	800	10	0.1	LDPE-G
[14]	30	7	6.3	0.5	LDPE
[15]	30	40	60	0.2	LDPE
[16]	20	15	6	0.1	LDPE
[20]	30.9	60	10	0.55	EPOXY-OP
[23]	50	30	60	0.25	LDPE

Figure 2 demonstrates the maximum value for space charge density ρ as a function of the mean electrical field E applied between the anode and the cathode only for LDPE. The small differences observed at the maximum space charge density values for identical mean electrical field values strength occur for a variety of reasons such as the manufacturing LDPE procedure which is not the same at various laboratories, the measurement duration which is listed in Table VI, and the

variety of the used electrode material. PEA is the utilized method in all cases. As expected, increasing E lead to space charge density increase, in the form of charge profiles or in the form of travelling CPs. Moreover, the local electric field, especially in front of each electrode, is a crucial quantity for space charge profiles.

TABLE VI. ELECTRICAL FIELD STRENGTH, SPACE CHARGE DENSITY, AND CONCLUSION TIME FOR PROFILE ACQUISITANCE ONLY FOR LDPE

Ref.	E (kV/mm)	ρ (Cb/m ³)	t (min)	d (mm)	Material
[16]	20	15	6	0,1	LDPE
[6]	20	3,5	120	0,2	LDPE
[1]	30	20	120	0,2	LDPE
[15]	30	40	60	0,2	LDPE
[14]	30	7	6,3	0,5	LDPE
[1]	50	25	120	0,2	LDPE
[23]	50	30	60	0,25	LDPE
[1]	80	70	120	0,2	LDPE

Fig. 2. For LDPE, maximum values of space charge densities versus mean electric field are shown. The parameters shown near each bullet correspond to the distance between anode and cathode.

In addition, Table VII and Figure 3 demonstrate that after the conclusion time for the final formation of CPs, the material itself plays an important role to the space charge density values.

TABLE VII. SPECIMENS AND THEIR SPACE CHARGE DENSITY VALUES AS A FUNCTION OF THE APPLIED ELECTRIC FIELD

Ref.	E (kV/mm)	ρ (Cb/m ³)	t (min)	d (mm)	Material
[1]	80	70	120	0,2	LDPE
[20]	30,9	60	10	0,55	EPOXY-OP
[15]	30	40	60	0,2	LDPE
[23]	50	30	60	0,25	LDPE
[1]	50	25	120	0,2	LDPE
[1]	30	20	120	0,2	LDPE
[16]	20	15	6	0,1	LDPE
[6]	20	4	120	0,2	DEGASSED XLPE
[6]	20	3,5	120	0,2	FRESH XLPE

The aforementioned admittance and experimental confirmation of fast CPs with very high mobility at relatively low electrical fields suits with the notion of Bruning's observations for charging phenomena in unexpected lower

values than that of the predefined thresholds. Yet on another question related to Bruning’s consideration that charging phenomena are possible below the inception voltage (due to some minute irregularities on the cavity surface), there is some indirect confirmation in [13], where the morphology and the surface topography of polyethylene may affect space CP characteristics. Although the authors in [13] do not mention partial discharges and related phenomena, it is evident that surface treatment plays a role in determining CPs. In agreement with the above, in [24] it is noted that the formation of the packet-like charge is a result of a high conductivity region that is caused when traps are filled by electronic carriers (electrons or holes).

Fig. 3. Space charge densities as a function of the applied electric field for various materials used as solid insulators.

In [25], various partial discharge models are presented. In all models, the role played by surface charge accumulation is evident. Furthermore, gas conductivity inside a cavity is also important [29, 30]. However, gas conductivity may appear even in the absence of partial discharges, conductivity which will not necessarily be "translated" (or transformed) into something detectable. Such ideas conform to [26], where it was reported that in minute cavities, partial discharges may have very long statistical time lag and the number of initial electrons may indeed be very small. In relatively low voltages, ionization processes of low energy may occur, which means that charges appearing in the cavity may result in clusters of space charges on the cavity walls. Such a space charge results in an electric field which – in the case of AC fields - is added to the applied electric field on the insulation [27]. Although what was described is the normal process of a PD, no one can exclude the possibility of having such events even below the inception voltage. The existence of space charges and partial discharges

inside the dielectrics plays a dominant role in the deterioration of their insulating capability. In [31-33], their contribution was analyzed, showing that these phenomena are present continuously in the HV industry and the related apparatus and the efforts to control and to study them may improve the HV apparatus reliability and insulation life time function. Charge packets propagation, space charges, partial discharges, electrical trees emanation and propagation, and electrical dipole formation are phenomena strongly correlated to each other, defining thus and affecting the insulating capability of materials.

A careful reader can observe that the whole approach of the space charge phenomena is related to the model proposed many years ago by Tanaka and Greenwood [28], namely that the electrodes, under AC conditions, inject and extract charges. Some electrons are emitted or injected into the dielectric during the negative half cycle for a short distance, limited by the declining stress away from the points. They will be drawn back into the point on the positive half cycle and re-injected in the following cycle. On each cycle, some of the electrons will gain sufficient energy to cause some polymer decomposition and thus create space charges in the bulk of the polymer. The estimated distance within which injected electrons can interact with the material to produce electrical trees near the tip of a needle is thought to be less than 20 μm. The tree initiation time (t) is related to the electric field (E), the effective work function φ (i.e. the difference between the work function of a metal and the electron affinity of a dielectric) with the following equation:

$$\ln t = \frac{B\phi^2}{E} + \ln\left(\frac{C}{A}\right) \tag{12}$$

where A, B, and C are constants.

It must also be pointed out that a CP movement most of the times is observed with the aid of figures that show space charge densities versus space (usually the distance between anode and cathode) for various time intervals. That does not mean that every such profile can show CP movement. In [1], space charge profiles are obtained in LDPE samples for 30, 50, and 80 kV/mm versus time ranging from 0 to 7200 s. On the other hand, CPs of both signs travel from the anode to the cathode in LDPE when a 80 kV/mm field is applied [1]. The different time clearly demonstrates charge profiles constituted packet-like movements. At 0-120 s the negative injected charge is greater than the positive injected charge and a positive CP was found to be transported from the cathode to the anode. During the period from 120 to 300 s, negative CPs meet the positive ones near the anode where charge recombination occurs so a negative packet disappears (or better, overlaps), and a positive homocharge decreases by a great deal (partial overlapping must be taken into account).

TABLE VIII. SPACE CHARGE DENSITIES, TIME, AND APPLIED FIELD [1]

Material	Applied field (kV/mm)	Time (s)	Space charge density (μC/cm ³)	Remarks
LDPE	30	60, 200, 500, 1000, 1500, 2400, 7200	-8 to +20	No CP propagation. Slight charge shifts
LDPE	50		-17 to +25	
LDPE	80		-30 to +70	Charge packet propagation of both signs between electrodes.

V. CONCLUSION

Space charge distributions and mainly charge packet propagation inside dielectrics are presented in this review paper. The mobility of both signs and charge packet propagation of both polarities are mostly shown and classified in the present work. These quantities are calculated and recorded over various materials at different specimen sizes with a variety of experimental setups utilized. The alteration of space charge distribution while time passes, enlightens the charge packet movement from one electrode to another. The charge packet initiation (and formerly injection) procedure is also presented, naming and underlining the physical mechanisms defining this phenomenon, accompanying with the relative set of equations. The relation of charge packets with previously published work on phenomena at and below the inception voltage is also indicated.

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The Fire Effect on the Performance of Reinforced Concrete Beams with Partial Replacement of Coarse Aggregates by Expanded Clay Aggregates

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to investigate the flexural behavior of reinforced concrete beams considering fire resistance by adding Lightweight Expanded Clay Aggregates (LECA) to the concrete mix as partial coarse aggregate replacement. LECA is a type of porous clay with a uniform pore structure with fine, closed cells and hard, tightly sintered skin. The experimental work comprised four reinforced self-compacted concrete beams. All the specimens were identical in their geometrical layout of 1600×240×200 mm, reinforcement details, and support condition (simply supported). For all the beams, the main reinforcement was provided by two bars, each having a diameter of 12 mm, while a bar of 6 mm diameter was employed for the top and shear reinforcement. Each beam had a different replacement ratio of LECA for coarse aggregates (0, 10, 20, and 30%). All the specimens were tested under static two concentrated loads after being exposed to the fire of steady-state temperature (500 °C), 1 hr duration, and sudden cooling process. The results showed that adding LECA reduced the number and width of the generated cracks due to fire and reduced the deterioration of the ultimate load capacity and beam rigidity (stiffness).

Keywords-reinforced concrete beams; fire effect; Lightweight Expanded Clay Aggregates (LECA)

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is naturally fire-resistant, which gives it an edge over other building materials. However, concrete structures still need to account for fire effects. Concrete and steel reinforcements lose strength and stiffness as they heat up, but they must still support dead and live loads without failing. Moreover, intense fires cause structural elements to expand, creating extra loads and stresses that must be resisted. Sometimes, construction must follow the building code requirements for fire resistance, leading to costly mistakes. Any concrete structure might be subjected to one of the most severe forms of stress during its useful life if exposed to temperatures caused by a fire. When the temperature rises, there is a significant risk that the mechanical properties of the concrete will deteriorate, ultimately resulting in the total collapse and disintegration of the building. Authors in [1, 2] examined the effects of a 24 hr fire on reinforced concrete beams constructed using recycled aggregates. The researchers discovered that concrete beams with a rich mix showed a more significant

decrease in flexural strength and a greater rise in load capacity and deflection than those with a normal mix [1, 2]. Lightweight Concrete (LWC) has a higher fire resistance than Normal Strength Concrete (NSC) since its lightweight particles have holes that may be exploited to reduce the pressure caused by fire. This makes LWC more effective in its ability to withstand fire. As a result of the fact that LWC is less susceptible to damage at high temperatures, both during the hot and residual stages, structures made of LWC may fare better in such occasions [3]. The thermal efficiency of Lightweight Aggregate Concrete (LWAC) is better than regular concrete, significantly reducing the energy used by buildings [4, 5]. LWAC has a higher resistance to fire when compared to normal-weight concrete [6] because the holes inside the lightweight aggregates help the vapors escape and lessen the stress created by the evaporated water [7].

LWC can be produced using porous lightweight aggregates, such as Light-Expanded Clay Aggregate (LECA). Expanded clay aggregates are porous ceramic products with a uniform

pore structure of fine, closed cells and with a densely sintered, firm external skin. LECA is manufactured in rotary kilns from raw materials containing clay minerals. The raw material is prepared, molded, and then subjected to a firing process at temperatures between 1100 and 1200 °C, resulting in a significant increase in volume due to expansion. The LECA grains' internal cellular structure with thousands of air-filled cavities gives thermal and sound insulation properties [8].

In [9], a comparison was made between the mechanical characteristics of lightweight and regular-weight concretes reinforced with steel fibers. They found that LWC had better fresh properties but performed poorly in a hardened state compared to NWC [9]. Authors in [10] studied the effect of different types of Lightweight Aggregates (LWA) on the strength and appearance of LWAC after being heated up to 800 °C. They made 8 concrete mixtures with three kinds of LWA and two with Normal-Weight Aggregates (NWA). They found that LWAC performed better than NWA concrete up to 500 °C but lost more strength at higher temperatures. Authors in [11-14] found that concrete with LECA has a lower density, better thermal resistance, and slower decline in mechanical properties under high temperatures, making it suitable for fire-resistant structures.

LECA is a useful material for enhancing the fire performance of concrete, reducing its weight, and improving its workability and insulation. The structural behavior of fire-exposed concrete structures containing LECA as a partial coarse aggregate replacement has not been significantly covered by the research. The present study aims to fill this knowledge gap. This is an experimental study that investigates the structural behavior of reinforced concrete beams containing LECA as a partial coarse aggregate replacement after exposure to fire flame.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

A. Materials

The concrete mix utilized for casting all samples and their control specimens consisted of ordinary Portland cement (CEM I 42.5R) manufactured in Iraq by the Mass brand. The cement's compliance is tested in accordance with the limits of Iraqi Specification No. 5/2019 [15]. The study employed natural sand with a maximum particle size of 4.75 mm. The grading complied with the Iraqi specification (IQS, No.45:1984) and its modifications [16]. The coarse aggregates utilized in the study were siliceous crushed gravel with a maximum size of 10 mm. The conformity of grading of coarse aggregates complies with [16]. The LECA used in the created concrete mix had diameter ranging between 4 and 10 mm (Figure 1). LECA properties and grading are shown in Tables I-II.

TABLE I. LECA PROPERTIES

Properties	Value
Density (kg/m ³)	320
Specific gravity	0.55
Water absorption %	21.6
Fineness modulus	3

TABLE II. LECA GRADING.

Sieve Size (mm)	% Passing by weight
37.5	100
20	100
14	100
10	95.36
5	2.18
2.36	0.6

Fig. 1. LECA.

A very fine pozzolanic material (micro silica) as an addition (pozzolanic material) and Viscocrete-5930 (a product of Sika) were utilized in the chosen concrete mix to generate Self-Compacted Concrete (SCC) for all the specimens.

B. Tested Specimens

The research comprised testing four simply supported reinforced SCC beams. Each beam had a different volumetric replacement ratio (0, 10, 20, and 30%) of the coarse aggregates by LECA. All had an identical geometric layout; the beams' dimensions were 1600×200×240 mm, and the clear span was 1400 mm, as shown in Figure 2. The details of the mixes are given in TABLE III, where:

TABLE III. DETAILS OF CONCRETE MIXTURES.

Mix	Mix Proportion (kg/m ³)					SP (lit/m ³)	SF* (%)
	Water	Cement	Sand	Gravel	LECA		
F-0**	185	441	750	950	0	4	2
F-10**	185	441	750	855	18.8	4	2
F-20**	185	441	750	760	37.6	4	2
F-30**	185	441	750	665	56.4	4	2

* Replacement by weight of cement. F: Fire exposure, ** LECA volumetric percentage (%)

Fig. 2. Dimensions of the tested specimens and reinforcement details.

C. Burning and Cooling

The specimens were exposed to burning inside a gas furnace, using direct fire, while maintaining consistent conditions (namely, a steady-state temperature of 500±10 °C and an exposure duration of 1 hr), as seen in Figure 3. A temperature measurement device, namely a digital thermometer

reader equipped with a K-type sensor wire, was used to monitor and record the temporal variations in temperature inside both the specimen and the furnace environment. The temperature-time relation criteria were established by adopting the ASTM E-119 [17]. A uniformly constant equivalent dead load effect provided 40% of the service load was applied during the burning process. After burning, the specimens were sprayed with water (sudden cooling).

Fig. 3. Specimen burning procedure.

Fig. 4. Details of the test setup.

D. Procedures for Testing

The strain gauges were positioned in their appropriate locations on both the top and bottom fibers of the specimen midline on the front face of the specimen. The beams were set on 2 cylindrical supports (simple supports) with a span length of 1400 mm. The load was applied by a hydraulic jack with a capacity of 100 tons that was transferred to a steel I-section girder, which divided the weight into two equal forces and left a distance of 400 mm between them. During each loading step, the amount of the load, the vertical deflection at the beam center, and the strain on the concrete surface were all measured and recorded. The load was gradually increased until failure (at a rate of 250 kg / step), and the progression of the crack was noted after each load increase. The details of the test setup are shown in Figure 4.

III. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To better understand the structural behavior of the beam, five categories were used in the finding's discussion, which are:

1. Effect of LECA on concrete properties.
2. Burning cracks.
3. Crack pattern, ultimate load, and mode of failure.
4. Load-deflection behavior.
5. Load-strain relation.

A. Effect of LECA on Concrete Properties

Mixtures containing LECA had lower mechanical properties at ambient temperature (30 °C) because LECA is generally weaker than the traditional aggregates. This can lead to a reduction in the overall strength of the concrete. However, after burning at a steady state temperature (500 °C) and the sudden cooling process, the mixtures containing LECA maintain their stiffness better due to reduced heat degradation (Table IV). LECA introduces thousands of tiny spaces in the clay, which form a honeycomb structure, giving LECA its low density and decreasing the weight of concrete. LECA is porous and has low thermal conductivity. These properties demonstrate that LECA can insulate concrete from heat transfer, avoid spalling and cracking caused by thermal stress, and keep mechanical strength and thermal insulation capabilities better than conventional aggregates after fire exposure [18, 19].

TABLE IV. PROPERTIES OF CONCRETE MIXTURES BEFORE AND AFTER FIRE EXPOSURE

Mix	f_{cu} (MPa)		Residual f_{cu} (%)	f_t (MPa)		Residual f_t (%)	E_c (MPa)		Residual E_c (%)
	Temp. (°C)			Temp. (°C)			Temp. (°C)		
	30	500		30	500		30	500	
F-0	60.1	41.2	68.6	4.46	1.39	31.2	31606	9208	29.1
F-10	57	43.5	76.3	4.16	1.72	41.3	27896	10109	36.2
F-20	53	41.8	78.9	3.88	1.89	48.7	25687	9657	37.6
F-30	48.9	39	79.8	3.56	1.9	53.4	23453	9151	39.0

B. Burning Cracks

After the burning and cooling process, cracks appeared on the surfaces of the beams, and flexural cracks appeared on the sides, as a result of the fire and the imposed load. On the

concrete surface, there was noticeable discoloration. The concrete has a bluish color on the sides' surface, as shown in Figures 5-8. The reference specimen (F-0) had a greater number and width of cracks than the other specimens. It is worth noting that the cover of the reference specimen had little

spalling, as shown in Figure 5. The number of cracks was substantially reduced, and no spalling in the specimens containing LECA was detected, see Figures 6-8. LECA reduced the number and width of the generated cracks. LECA has lower thermal conductivity and higher fire resistance than normal aggregates, so it can withstand higher temperatures and prevent cracking or spalling of the concrete surface due to fire exposure. As a consequence of the porous nature of LECA, evaporating water has a place to hide, which reduces the amount of cracks and the damage that occurs inside the concrete. The percentages of the specimens' damage, including the generated cracks and spalling were 1.48, 1.07, 0.93, and 0.84% for the specimens F-0, F-10, F-20, and F-30, respectively. Crack length and spalling area as a percentage of the specimen surface area were considered in order to evaluate the specimen's damage.

models containing it by reducing the vapor pressure generated as a result of burning. Table V shows the result of the ultimate load and maximum deflection.

Fig. 5. Cracks due to burning and cooling of specimen F-0.

Fig. 6. Cracks due to burning and cooling of specimen F-10.

Fig. 7. Cracks due to burning and cooling of specimen F-20.

Fig. 8. Cracks due to burning and cooling of specimen F-30.

C. Crack Pattern, Ultimate Load, and Mode of Failure

Flexural collapse occurred in all the burnt beams. New cracks developed on both sides of the beams. The burned specimens' crack patterns are shown in Figures 9-12. The results showed that despite the reduction in the mechanical properties in the unburned control specimens after adding LECA, the beams that contained LECA remained more conservative in their ultimate load capacity after burning, which means that adding LECA reduced the deterioration of the ultimate load capacity for the burned specimens under the same conditions. The variations of the ultimate load for the specimens that contain LECA (F-10, F-20, and F-30) were +4.69, +2.35, and -1.41% respectively when compared to the control specimen, because LECA has lower thermal conductivity and higher fire resistance than the normal aggregates. Thus, LECA reduced the effect of fire on the

Fig. 9. Crack pattern for specimen F-0.

Fig. 10. Crack pattern for specimen F-10.

Fig. 11. Crack pattern for specimen F-20.

Fig. 12. Crack pattern for specimen F-30.

TABLE V. LOAD CAPACITY AND ULTIMATE DEFLECTION FOR BURNED SPECIMENS

Specimen	Ultimate Deflection (mm)	Ultimate load (kN)	% Variation of ultimate load (with respect to F-0)
F-0	31.93	80.33	---
F-10	30.50	84.10	+4.69
F-20	31.45	82.22	+2.35
F-30	32.94	79.20	-1.41

D. Load-Deflection Behavior

For each load increment of the static test, the vertical deflection of the burned specimens was measured at mid-span. The load-deflection behavior of specimens was investigated at service and ultimate load. The service load in the current study was assumed to be 65% of the ultimate load. Figure 13 shows the effect of the LECA volume ratio on the load-deflection behavior at mid-span. The results showed that adding LECA reduced the deflection at the service load stage and yielding load stage and reduced the deterioration in the beam's rigidity (stiffness), as shown in Table VI. The reduction in beam stiffness is attributed particularly to the decrease in the mechanical properties of concrete as a result of heating. The addition of the LECA reduced the degradation in the stiffness after the fire effect, which belongs to the lower thermal conductivity and the higher porosity of LECA. This means that concrete containing LECA can resist high temperatures better

than normal aggregate concrete and it can maintain its structural integrity longer under fire exposure. Also, this can reduce internal stresses and prevent spalling during fire exposure. Spalling reduces the strength and stiffness of concrete and exposes the reinforcement bars to further damage [20, 21]. In stiffness calculations, the stage of linear load-deflection behavior was considered.

TABLE VI. MIDSPAN DEFLECTIONS OF SPECIMENS IN SERVICE AND ULTIMATE LOADS.

Specimen	Deflection at service load (mm)	Deflection at yielding load (mm)	Stiffness, $K=P/\Delta$ (kN/mm)
F-0	4.9	7.31	12.9
F-10	4.2	6.42	16.1
F-20	4.6	7.15	14.1
F-30	5.0	7.59	11.8

Fig. 13. Effect of LECA ratio on load-deflection behavior at mid-span.

E. Load-Strain Relation

The load-strain behavior of the concrete front face was recorded for burned specimens in specific positions. The strain of concrete was measured by 30 mm strain gauges that were installed on the concrete front face of the tension and compression zone, as shown in Figure 14.

Fig. 14. Locations of the concrete strain gauges.

Figure 15 shows the effect of the LECA ratio on the load-strain behavior of the concrete in the compression zone. The concrete compression strain at the ultimate load was 2362, 2329, 2236, and 2089 micro-strain for the burned specimens F-0, F-10, F-20, and F-30, respectively. Adding LECA to the concrete mix reduced the strain after the fire effect by slowing down the heat transfer inside the concrete due to its low thermal conductivity and high porosity. The strain gauge

readings placed in the tensile zone (S.G.2 and S.G.3) were neglected due to the cracks generated during the test, which affected the accuracy of the readings.

Fig. 15. Load-strain relation (S.G. 1) for concrete.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The structural behavior of fire-exposed concrete structures containing LECA as a partial coarse aggregate replacement is not significantly covered by the scientific research. The present study aims to strengthen this weak point. The present study is an experimental study that investigates the structural behavior of reinforced concrete beams containing Lightweight Expanded Clay Aggregate (LECA) as a partial coarse aggregate replacement after exposure to fire flame. Based on the outcomes of the experimental research, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Utilizing LECA as a partial volumetric substitute for the coarse aggregates in concrete results in a reduction of all the mechanical properties of concrete. The extent of this reduction is directly proportional to the LECA content.
2. Increasing LECA content results in improved strength retention in the mechanical characteristics of concrete, which are inversely related to the burning steady-state temperature.
3. Adding LECA substantially reduced the number and width of cracks in the concrete due to fire. Also, there was no spalling in the specimens containing LECA, while a little spalling occurred at the cover of the reference specimen.
4. Adding LECA reduced the deterioration of the ultimate load capacity for specimens burned under the same conditions. After burning, beams that contained LECA remained more conservative in their ultimate load capacity.
5. Increasing the LECA content reduced strain in the concrete. The recorded strain at the ultimate load was 2362, 2329, 2236, and 2089 micro-strain for the burned specimens at 500 °C of LECA ratios of 0, 10, 20, and 30%, respectively.

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Suspicious Activity Classification in Classrooms using Deep Learning

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ABSTRACT

Video processing is attracting the attention of both research and industry. The existence of intelligent surveillance cameras with high processing power has paved the way for designing intelligent visual surveillance systems. Along with analyzing video for information recovery, it is nowadays used to analyze live surveillance video to detect activities. These systems are implemented in real time. The proposed work's goal is to create a method that can examine and discover suspicious behaviors in the lecture room environment. Video analytics offers the most efficient answer because it enables pointing an occasion and retrieves applicable statistics from the video recorded. The method aims to identify suspicious activities like fighting, sleeping, looking elsewhere, eating, etc. that the students might be doing. The proposed method involves breaking a video input into frames and converting it into image data because the model has been trained on images collected from the internet. Several models were tested and experimented with, including efficientnet_b2, spnasnet_100, efficientnet_b3, and mobilenetv3_large_100. Parameters such as the learning rate were optimized to find out the best method and create a system with the best results.

Keywords-classroom surveillance;suspicious activity;video processing;anomalous activity detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Surveillance is the observation of changing behavior, activities, or other information, usually of individuals, in order to influence, control, direct, or protect them. Visual surveillance plays a pivotal role in today's world. Governments use it to gather information, prohibit crime, protect a process, person, group, or object, or solve crime cases [1]. A useful video surveillance system depends on detecting suspicious activities [2]. The detection of anomalies in human behavior using such systems can provide clues and prevent security breaches.

The solutions proposed for suspicious classroom activity detection are not in abundance, however more work has been done on the related topic of detecting cheating and malpractices in an examination hall [3]. Automated video surveillance provides an optimal solution by monitoring students and identifying suspicious events. Monitoring an exam room is a very challenging task in terms of manpower. Therefore, a system needs to be developed that automatically detects suspicious activity and minimizes such bad practices in the exam room with as small error probability as possible. The suspicious activities in a classroom can include the use of

mobile phones, playing games, sleeping, fighting, passing hand signs, or eating. A video surveillance system that could monitor the students in the classroom and classify their behavior as suspicious or not based on the activities stated above is the aim of the current work.

The recent trend of automation has an impact on the field of video analysis [4]. Video analytics can be used for a variety of applications such as motion detection, human activity prediction, person identification, abnormal activity detection, vehicle counting, etc. In this area, the two factors used for personal identification are face and gait recognition. Between these two techniques, face recognition is more versatile for automatically identifying people through surveillance videos. Face recognition can be used to predict the orientation of a person's head, which in turn helps predict a person's behavior. Motion detection along with face recognition are very useful in many applications such as verification of an individual, identification of an individual, and detection of the presence or absence of an individual at a specific location and time. Advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning are now used into such systems. Human behavior is unpredictable and it is very difficult to find whether one's behavior is suspicious or normal. Monitoring is

often performed through consecutive frames which are extracted from the video. These frames are fed into the machine-learning model to classify the activity as suspicious or not.

We focused on detecting suspicious activities during an offline academic examination in an exam hall because suspicious activities during normal classroom lectures are more subjective [5]. Therefore, the proposed method will detect malpractices happening in an exam hall which might include cheating through various ways like whispering, passing gestures, talking, looking back, etc. This system will serve as a useful surveillance system for educational institutions. This paper aims to analyze real-time video from examination halls and identify whether a particular person's activity is suspicious or not. The system can monitor and analyze the activities of students in an examination hall and can quickly alert the educational institution on the occurrence of any such malpractices.

Nowadays, having human invigilators in exam rooms is a task that is sometimes inconvenient. The proposed system has the ability to automatically monitor an exam room. It offers a high accuracy rate and minimizes computing time.

II. LITERATURE OVERVIEW

An extensive amount of research has been done on human activity detection and video surveillance. The general human activity detection framework includes several stages such as motion detection, background and foreground modeling and segmentation, object classification and tracking, and finally behavior and activity detection and person identification. Features such as eyes, lip and hand movements are recognized using facial recognition techniques [9]. Manifold learning maps high-dimensional to low-dimensional feature spaces. Although manifold learning is easy to implement for classification procedures, the deep learning approaches show superior performance due to the automatic feature learning. In some papers, the proposed methodologies include dividing the system into modules like facial gesture recognition or hand sign recognition and handling the modules with separate types of algorithms [11]. Thus, keeping those modules independent as features, the mainstay methods have turned out to be something like filter approaches involving feature scoring which includes PCA. But PCA is sensitive to scale and hence it should be applied only to data that have approximately the same size. It may lose important information for discrimination between different classes.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section, dataset capturing, preprocessing, model building, and parameter tuning [15] are discussed along with the novelty of the current work.

Dataset generation was conducted by web scraping. Web scraping is an automatic method to obtain large amounts of data from websites. Most of these data are unstructured data in HTML format which are converted into structured data in a spreadsheet or a database. There are many ways to perform web scraping to obtain data from websites. These include using online services, APIs, or web scraping from scratch. Many

large websites, like Google, Twitter, Facebook, and Stack Overflow, have APIs that allow data access in a structured format. Web scraping requires two parts, namely the crawler and the scraper. The crawler is an artificial intelligence algorithm that browses the web to search for the particular data required by following links across the internet. The scraper, on the other hand, is a specific tool created to extract data from a website. The extracted data are assigned classes (suspicious and non-suspicious). Data labeling is the process of identifying raw data (images, text files, videos, etc.) and adding one or more meaningful and informative labels to provide context so that a machine learning model can learn from them. Data labeling is an important part of data preprocessing for ML, particularly for supervised learning, in which both input and output data are labeled for classification to provide a learning basis for future data processing.

A total of 88 images were acquired and considered and from them, 58 images were further distributed in training, validation, and testing datasets for model building. Their division in training, testing and validation subsets along with their corresponding labels can be seen in Table I.

TABLE I. DATASET

Dataset	Number of samples		
	Training	Testing	Validation
Suspicious	19	14	3
Non-Suspicious	13	7	2

A. Models

The model was pre-trained on the Imagenet dataset. This model typically classifies images into a thousand classes. The Imagenet dataset is a very large series of snapshots pre-annotated and designed with the help of scientists to develop computer vision algorithms. It scales all depth/width/resolution dimensions uniformly using a simple but highly efficient composite coefficient. EfficientNets [14] are a family of models that use neural architecture search and achieve much better accuracy and efficiency than previous ConvNets [13]. The state-of-the-art models can achieve up to 84.3% accuracy on ImageNet and are 8.4 times smaller and 6.1 times faster than the best existing ConvNets. EfficientNets also achieve state-of-the-art accuracy with an order of magnitude fewer parameters [8]. MobileNet [6] is tuned to cellular CPUs through a combination of Hardware Network Architecture Search (NAS), augmented by the NetAdapt algorithm and then enhanced by new architectural advances. MobileNetV3-Large is more accurate than ImageNet with less latency than MobileNetV2 [10]. In [16-27] one can review some machine learning models that show its importance and improved results.

B. The Proposed Methodology

The proposed solution includes three parts. Firstly, the dataset was synthesized. We decided to train the model on the image dataset and consequently, the input video data were converted to a suitable format, i.e. images, before feeding the model. In order to synthesize the image dataset, we scraped the web on the Google Search engine to download images for different types of relevant queries that could provide the desired result. Figure 1 shows the proposed approach.

Fig. 1. Workflow of proposed approach.

There are numerous software applications for automating data scraping [12]. Bing Image Search API v7 helps users scour the web for images. Results include thumbnails, full image URLs, publishing website info, image metadata, and more. Image metadata include machine-generated captions, visually similar images, shopping and recipe sources, related image searches, etc. The second part was to train the model. In order to obtain good accuracy, we decided to use a deep learning model as a starting point of the training phase (transfer learning approach). Therefore, we used a deep learning model for images and fine-tuned it according to the dataset and the requirements. The model was trained on the data that had been synthesized and was then tested. The third part is to put the model to use. To achieve this, the video input will be converted into image data that will be fed to the model. A certain number of frames will be extracted from the videos, which are saved in the form of images. This will be done by using OpenCV library. OpenCV is a library containing predefined functions for real-time computer vision tasks like object detection, processing of images captured, etc. This will then be used for prediction by our model. The model will output the probabilities or percentages, to which category a particular belongs. The initial experiments on all the types of models have been performed by fixating on a specific initial learning rate for all the models. Thus, the initial experiments have a random learning rate [7]. After recording these values, the learning rate parameter was optimized for all models. After the optimum value was found, the training was conducted again, the experiments were re-performed and the readings and figures were again plotted and covered.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Tables II-VI show the training loss, validation accuracy and testing accuracy for the used models (Efficientnet b2, Efficientnet b3, Mobilenetv3 large 100 and Spnasnet 100) over different number of epochs and different learning rates.

Figure 2 shows the optimization of the learning rates of the different models with the help of Pytorch. Accuracy plots and a comparative study between the various considered models are presented in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 shows how the different losses and accuracy were distributed throughout the training process along different learning rates. Figure 4 shows training loss, validation loss, and validation accuracy for the different used models.

TABLE II. EFFICIENTNET B2, LR = 0.144

Epochs	Training loss	Validation accuracy	Testing accuracy
60	1.892	0.583	46.67
80	11.202	0.583	46.67

TABLE III. EFFICIENTNET B3, LR = 0.005

Epochs	Training loss	Validation accuracy	Testing accuracy
60	0.113	0.75	80
80	0.103	0.756	80
100	0.099	0.583	80

TABLE IV. MOBILENETV3 LARGE 100, LR = 0.238

Epochs	Training loss	Validation accuracy	Testing accuracy
60	2.881	0.833	63.33
80	2.29	0.667	63.33
100	6.739	0.583	63.33

TABLE V. MOBILENETV3 LARGE 100, LR = 3E-14

Epochs	Training loss	Validation accuracy	Testing accuracy
60	5.604	0.750	63.33
80	2.290	0.667	63.33
100	6.739	0.583	63.33

TABLE VI. SPNASNET 100, LR = 1E-8

Epochs	Training loss	Validation accuracy	Testing accuracy
60	0.620	0.667	60
80	0.147	0.667	60
100	0.140	0.667	60

Fig. 2. Learning rate plots.

Fig. 3. Accuracy plots.

Fig.4. Comparative study between efficientnet, mobilenet3large and spnasnet models.

After training, Spnasnet 100 was considered for further evaluation and experimentation. Another set of 30 images were given to the model as input. Table VII shows the results and Table VIII the confusion matrix for the test dataset and the classification into suspicious and non-suspicious activity. The F1 score of 0.81 of the proposed model is sufficient for the proposed approach in limited datasets.

TABLE VII. RESULTS

True Positives	18	Accuracy	0.73
False Positives	8	Recall	1.00
True Negatives	4	Precision	0.69
False Negatives	0	F1 Score	0.81

TABLE VIII. CONFUSION MATRIX

	False	True
False	4	8
True	0	18

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Detecting suspicious activity is an open area of research. Timely automatic detection of suspicious student activity helps the supervisors take accurate and fair action. This work includes the classification of suspicious activity using several types of models, training them on our dataset and finally using

the optimized learning rate. Thus, the proposed system detects suspicious human activity carried out in an examination hall using the specified models. This method gives better results and reduces the number of false positives when compared to other approaches.

It must be noted that very good accuracy couldn't be achieved due to the insufficient amount of data. Data of this kind couldn't be found in abundance. However, this system is a good tool with fair accuracy. In the future, we aim to improve this system with the help of a better quality dataset.

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Enabling Context-based AI in Chatbots for conveying Personalized Interdisciplinary Knowledge to Users

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ABSTRACT

Adaptable chatbots have revolutionized user interactions by dynamically tailoring responses to users' knowledge and explainability preferences in interdisciplinary domains, such as AI in education and medicine. While strides have been made in model explainability, little attention has been paid to making models contextually aware and responsive to users' background knowledge. This study investigated interdisciplinary knowledge learning principles in a different domain, where the chatbot's contextual understanding is enhanced through dynamic knowledge graphs that capture users' past interactions to deliver up-to-date and relevant responses. By incorporating explainability features, chatbot responses become enriched, enabling users to understand the reasoning behind answers. This study proposed a model that showed superior chatbot performance and accurately addressed most queries, outperforming competitor chatbots DBpedia, ODC, and ODA. A 0.7 F-measure showcased its excellence, attributed to dynamic knowledge graphs and explainability checks. This study envisions a new era of conversational AI that not only meets user needs but also fosters a deeper understanding of AI decision-making, making it indispensable in delivering personalized, informed, and contextually aware interactions.

Keywords-personalized chatbot; contextually aware interactions; dynamic knowledge graphs; explainability level check

I. INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape where technology intertwines with various domains, the acquisition of interdisciplinary knowledge has emerged as a challenging endeavor, characterized by multiple variables and disjointed components that often operate independently. Learners face difficulties in assimilating and integrating diverse aspects cohesively, leading to barriers that impede effective knowledge acquisition. These barriers include limited access to resources, discrepancies in the pace of learning among students, and the time-consuming nature of mastering new topics. Moreover, as industries embrace rapid advancements through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI), a new set of challenges arises, disrupting and revolutionizing existing workflows. In this context, chatbots have become indispensable tools for engaging with consumers and service users, offering seamless interactions and serving as efficient assistants to service providers. According to [1], a chatbot is not just an agent that interacts with the user. It rather functions as an autonomous partner and has a presence within the conversational setting. This study emphasized the importance of recognizing and generating engagement, as well as the importance of fostering long-term relationships between humans and chatbots.

The past few years have witnessed the proliferation of large chatbots and virtual assistants, exemplified by popular platforms such as Alexa and Siri. As the field of chatbot technology progresses, the focus shifts towards enhancing chatbots across various domains to adapt to diverse user needs and leverage context awareness. Many research efforts attempted to address the aspect of personalization. In [2], novel methods were presented to eliminate the need to learn prior representations, allowing them to effectively generalize to previously unseen knowledge graphs. The evaluation of these methods demonstrated their superior performance in both academic and internal datasets. In [3], the myPersonality dataset was used to identify a user's personality. However, it was restricted to a specific age group and did not address dynamic personality aspects. The objective is to provide more interpretable, explainable, and personalized responses, catering to individual user preferences and understanding. This study aimed to fill these gaps by constructing a Brain Objects knowledge graph and further interconnecting them with each other to enable personalization. It also used an explainability level check that further improved interdisciplinary knowledge and chatbot capabilities, aiming to offer interpretable personalized responses that surpassed competitor chatbots.

Chatbots are increasingly finding use in domains such as education [4], healthcare [5], and businesses, acting as online assistants and replacing the services provided by humans in call centers. Another additional benefit is their deployment on widely used messaging apps such as Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp, and Twitter, allowing extensive user interaction. This aligns with the focus on improving the accuracy of sentiment analysis on these platforms [6]. The most popular method for developing dialogue systems is to mimic human conversational behavior, with the aim of the system to resemble

a human interlocutor by converting user queries from NLP to SQL and SPARQL [7].

A very convenient means of designing chatbots is the use of Artificial Intelligence Markup Language (AIML), which is an XML-based scripting language for specifying conversations with chatbots. The creation of a chatbot in AIML involves creating a large number of categories that, at the basic level, consist of a pattern that is matched with the user's input and a template that specifies the chatbot's response [8]. If the user input matches the text in the pattern, the contents stated in the templates are retrieved. The graph is traversed until a pattern is found that matches the input. Explainable machine learning models are imperative for greater transparency which in most cases is a necessity. Recent studies investigated more visual and interactive approaches to make machine learning models explainable. For this purpose, an XAI pipeline was proposed that can be utilized to streamline different elements together to provide explainability [9]. Similarly to this design of introducing explainability levels, with each level defining a particular expertise level or understanding of a user about a domain and machine learning knowledge, the XAI pipeline approach also deals with three main groups: Model users, model developers, and model novices. As multiple knowledge graph-based chatbots are available [3, 10-12], but none of them creates a user's dynamic personality, this design focuses heavily on generating user-specific dynamic knowledge graphs with domain-specific data organized in a visually interactive manner to assist the chatbot in generating responses. Visual analytics and interactive machine learning can play a significant role in making machine learning models explainable. The XAI pipeline incorporates both VA and IML to make it easier to develop visual interfaces.

Authors in [13] initially focused on chatbots in education, examining their role with students, their specific educational applications, and the impact of chatbot implementation on learning. This framework emphasizes personalization and transparency to address individual learning gaps, using previous interactions to adapt its knowledge base, but does not assess users' knowledge levels. In [14], the B-point tree method improved efficiency by incorporating an additional data structure into the binary search tree structure. This algorithm aimed to reduce the depth of the search, which ultimately reduced the number of memory accesses. A sorted array of pointers of the most used points was maintained and updated after each query, each element in the array also acted as a shortcut, but there was no personalization. Early chatbot technology used simple keyword matching and had minimum context awareness to generate responses. Language processing, detailed ontologies, and continuously updated personalization have made significant improvements to the user experience [15].

Task-oriented chatbots use feature ontologies and user personality to establish context-aware responses and questions to drive a more explainable and personalized setup. This study aimed to bridge these gaps by investigating strategies to enhance chatbot capabilities, ensuring more interpretable,

explainable, and personalized responses that align with individual user preferences. By addressing these challenges, this study aimed to achieve substantial advancements in chatbot performance, surpassing the achievements of previous chatbots.

II. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

This study presents a novel framework designed to empower chatbots with explainable and context-based AI capabilities, enabling them to impart personalized interdisciplinary knowledge to users. The proposed architecture amalgamates cutting-edge NLP techniques that help create Brain Objects, a context awareness engine, a dynamic

Knowledge Graph, and an Explainability Module. By leveraging user interactions and context, the chatbot dynamically constructs a comprehensive knowledge graph and customizes responses based on user-specific explainability levels. This approach guarantees a more impactful and personalized conversational encounter that transcends various domains. The proposed bot was named Cronus-bot and effectively addresses the demand for chatbots that are both interpretable and contextually aware, thereby fostering profound interdisciplinary knowledge sharing with users. This chatbot architecture encompasses six key components, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Cronus-bot architecture diagram.

A. NLP

This study focused on developing user and bot personalities, which necessitates obtaining user queries in a triple format, consisting of Subject, Predicate, and Object. In this format, both Subject and Object are represented as Noun Phrases (NPs), while the Predicate can take the form of a Verb Phrase (VP). Natural Language Processing (NLP) libraries can be used to discern NPs and VPs within user queries, such as Sandford NLP. The semantic match between the user query and the desired response is crucial to enhancing the overall user experience. Therefore, it is essential to extract additional Part-Of-Speech (POS) attributes from the user queries to further refine the identification process. The extraction of POS attributes includes:

- Subject and Subject Adj: Identify the main query topic and associated adjectives.

- Object and Object Adj: Determine the query object and relevant adjectives.
- Predicate: Understand the action/relationship of the query to fit responses.

This integration of POS attributes improves understanding, resulting in an improved user experience and improved human-computer interaction.

B. Query Type Identification

This step involves the extraction of two key attributes:

- Query Identification (QI) categorizes user queries (e.g. "reason-based," "confirmation," etc.) for tailored responses.
- Module Identification (MI) identifies relevant modules (e.g. News, Education) for accurate responses.

C. Brain Objects

The concept of a Brain Object emerges as a fundamental building block in a chatbot's cognitive architecture, representing interconnected information derived from user queries. Each user query is treated as a brain object, which contains POS attributes extracted using NLP, and some virtual attributes, which identify the QI, MI, and explainability level. As shown in Figure 2, these objects are semantically connected to form a dynamic graph known as the Semantic Dynamic Graph. This graph serves as a powerful tool for context identification in conversations, allowing the chatbot to comprehend the flow of the discourse and deliver more contextually appropriate responses.

Fig. 2. Brain objects workflow.

D. Context Awareness Engine

The Context Awareness Engine is a pivotal component that enables sophisticated personalized interactions, integrating upper-level ontologies and semantic enrichment for a dynamic semantic graph and reflecting users' personalities through brain objects. This empowers the chatbot with a wealth of contextual information to craft responses. The proposed system employed the Fuseki server, a robust SPARQL server that manages RDF data and queries. Upper-level ontologies (DBpedia, Open Cyc, Wiki data, and Yago) enrich the data. The dynamic Bot's Personality graph, created via Fuseki, forges links with ontologies during user interactions. This dynamic graph captures upper-level ontology data, anchoring the chatbot's responses. An on-the-fly method forges the user's personality using brain objects, dynamically linking data per query. This agility facilitates personalized and contextually relevant conversations.

E. Explainability Level Check

This module was introduced to assess the user's explainability levels, which dictates the complexity and depth of the chatbot's responses. As shown in Figure 3, the explainability level ranges from 1 to 5, with 1 representing the simplest level and 5 denoting the most advanced level. Each explainability level governs the types of cognitive services from which the knowledge should be drawn and the level of abstraction that the knowledge graph should adopt. The dynamic response generation process utilizes the knowledge graph formed by factoring in the user's profile, personality, general, and domain-specific ontologies. Intent identification is

employed based on the user's input, and the dynamic knowledge graph helps extract information for the chatbot's response.

Fig. 3. Explainability level ranges.

To maintain context awareness, the chatbot tracks user queries, identifying common questions and issues. It provides relevant information based on this context, offering varying levels of explainability. For physicians, it offers a deeper level of detail, while for patients with a basic understanding, it adjusts explanations accordingly. This adaptability enhances user experience and comprehension. Figure 4 illustrates the process.

Fig. 4. User's profile vs explainability levels.

TABLE I. NOTATIONS USED IN ALGORITHMS

EL	Explainability Level
SD	Sub Domain
SG	Sub Graph
SQ	SPARQL Query
UP	User Profile

Algorithm I introduces an approach to enhance user interaction with chatbots. It adapts the complexity and depth of chatbot responses based on the user's profile, domain knowledge, and evolving understanding. The algorithm begins by extracting user input and assessing the existence of relevant subgraphs. If found, personalized explainability levels are established for different subdomains. If not, the algorithm evaluates the familiarity of the user using semantic-based text matching to the topic, adjusting the explainability accordingly

[16]. Table I provides a comprehensive guide to the notation used in Algorithm I.

Algorithm I: Explainability Level Check	
	Inputs: Brain Object of User Query (B)
	Output: Explainability level (EL)
1	# Variables:
	EL \leftarrow 0
	SD \leftarrow Extract_SD(B)
	SG \leftarrow SG_By_SD(SubDomain)
2	# Assess Explainability Level:
	UEL_user \leftarrow AssessExplainability(user_profile)
3	# Extract SubDomain from Brain Object:
	SD \leftarrow Extract_SD(B)
4	# Extract subgraph from user personality graph using SPARQL by SD:
	SQL \leftarrow "SELECT ?subject ?predicate ?object WHERE { ?subject ?predicate ?object.FILTER(CONTAINS(?subject, '' + SubDomain + '')) }"
	SG \leftarrow Execute_Query(SQL)
5	# If SG not Found:
	if SG is Null then
	UP \leftarrow Get_UP()
	Enriched_SD \leftarrow Enrich_Text(SD, UP.Job_Role)
	Similarity_Score \leftarrow Cosine_Similarity(Enriched_SubDomain, Enriched_Job_Role)
	if Similarity_Score < 5.0 then
	EL \leftarrow 0
	else if Similarity_Score \leq 7.0 then
	EL \leftarrow 1
	else if Similarity_Score \geq 8.0 then
	EL \leftarrow 2
6	# If Sub Graph Found:
	Else
	EL \leftarrow Initial_EL
	for each Brain_Object in SG do
	List_Of_SubDomains \leftarrow Get_SD(Brain_Object)
	for each SD in List_Of_SubDomains do
	EL \leftarrow Update_Explainability_Level(SD, User_Understanding)
7	# Return Current Explainability Level:
	Return EL

F. Response Generation

The response generator offers a powerful and adaptive mechanism to generate responses that are tailored to individual users, considering their past interactions, explainability level, and the wealth of knowledge stored in both the dynamic and the bot's knowledge graphs. This holistic approach enhances the chatbot's ability to provide personalized and contextually appropriate responses to user queries.

III. EXPERIMENTS

To facilitate an all-encompassing comparison, the performance of the proposed Cronus-bot was compared to other cutting-edge chatbots that also utilize linked data, including the DBpedia Chatbot, Open Data Chatbot, and Open Data Assistant. Table II shows the specific knowledge base used by each chatbot to provide answers. Table III presents a comprehensive analysis and comparison of the bots.

TABLE II. CHATBOT KNOWLEDGE BASES

Chatbot	Knowledge Base
DBpedia [17]	DBpedia
ODC [18]	DBpedia
ODA [19]	DBpedia
Cronus-bot	DBpedia, Wikidata, Dynamic User personality KG, Explainability level check

Three essential evaluation metrics were used to assess and compare the performance and effectiveness of the Cronus-bot when responding to user queries: precision, recall, and F-measure. Precision is a crucial measure for assessing the performance of a classification model, such as a chatbot. It gauges the ratio of accurately predicted positive instances to all instances the model labeled as positive. Recall evaluates the model's aptitude to identify all pertinent instances within the true positive cases. The F-measure amalgamates precision and recall, offering a well-rounded evaluation of model performance, particularly when both false positives and false negatives demand concurrent consideration. The F-measure guarantees that a model striking a commendable equilibrium between precision and recall attains a superior score.

TABLE III. COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Chatbot	Total	Right	Wrong	P	R	F-measure
DBpedia	50	8	6	0.5	0.3	0.4
ODC	50	6	4	0.6	0.25	0.35
ODA	50	5	2	0.7	0.17	0.2
Cronus-bot	50	26	4	0.76	0.6	0.7

Fig. 5. Comparison of results.

The first column of Table III provides the name of the chatbot system, while Total indicates the total number of queries evaluated. Right represents the number of queries correctly answered by the system, and Wrong indicates the number of queries for which the system provided incorrect answers. For instance, out of 50 queries, Cronus-bot provided 26 correct answers, whereas the other state-of-the-art chatbots produced less than 10 correct answers. The correctness of the answers was determined manually with the previous context in mind. Figure 5 shows that the Cronus-bot achieved a recall rate of 0.6, and an F-measure of 0.7, outperforming the other systems. These results demonstrate that the Cronus-bot outperformed the other chatbots in precision, recall, and F-measure, as dynamic knowledge graphs and explainability checks boosted its performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study introduced a dynamic knowledge graph, containing brain objects interlinking the user's previous queries, and explainability levels to facilitate a personalized conversational experience. By connecting the response generator with the bot's knowledge graph, the proposed Cronus-bot gains access to a wealth of structured information, enabling it to deliver more informed and accurate answers. Moreover, as shown in the comparison of the results, the proposed Cronus-bot improved the end-to-end user experience in terms of interactive question answering and context awareness compared to other competitors. The proposed architecture propels human-centric AI-driven interactions, contributing to user-friendly, trustworthy AI and empowering confident interdisciplinary knowledge sharing.

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Protection of HVDC Transmission Systems for Integrating Renewable Energy Resources

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a fault locator approach designed for non-homogeneous VSC-HVDC (Voltage Source Converter-High Voltage Direct Current) transmission circuits. In various projects, such as those involving offshore wind farms, the transmission circuit's right-of-way can be non-homogeneous, incorporating a mix of underground cables and overhead lines. This diversity in circuit configuration poses issues with fault location approaches. The proposed method involves measuring signals at two sides of the non-homogeneous transmission circuit. Initially, the faulted section is identified using a specific criterion. This criterion calculates the profile of the 1-mode component of the voltage along the transmission circuit, without considering its non-homogeneous nature. This method is founded upon disparities in the voltage change rate between power cables and overhead lines. The provided identification method does not depend on the calculation of fault distances. Subsequently, the faulty point within the selected section is obtained by updating the calculated voltage profile. Notably, our method does not necessitate the installation of additional sensors at junction points. Furthermore, the introduced approach has the capability to locate various fault types, including pole-to-pole and pole-to-ground faults, and it remains effective regardless of the fault resistance value. These investigations were conducted using PSCAD software as a simulation environment, with the proposed method's calculations executed in MATLAB.

Keywords-fault location; VSC; HVDC transmission circuit; offshore wind farm

I. INTRODUCTION

Voltage Source Converter-based High Voltage Direct Current (VSC-HVDC) transmission systems are widely employed worldwide for the efficient transmission of large power quantities. HVDC systems offer numerous advantages compared to traditional HVAC transmission systems [1-10]. One notable advantage is that the length of the DC transmission circuit is not limited, thanks to the absence of charging currents, especially with underground cables. This flexibility encourages the implementation of integration projects between different grids with varying frequencies over long distances. In

some cases, the transmission system can be non-homogeneous, incorporating a mix of underground cables and overhead lines. This non-homogeneity arises due to the changing nature of the right-of-way, as seen in projects like offshore wind farms [11-15].

Accurately locating faults in HVDC systems is crucial for efficient maintenance, ensuring service continuity, and minimizing maintenance time [16-35]. One prominent approach in fault location methods is the traveling wave technique, which involves precisely determining when traveling waves from a faulty point arrive at the line ends by

analyzing time differences and wave speeds [16–26]. However, the accuracy of this method can be compromised when dealing with non-homogeneous transmission systems, where multiple specific values of wave speed may be present. Distinguishing among Reverberated waves originating from the fault location and other reflections, especially in non-homogeneous circuits, poses a challenge. The method presented in [27] addresses fault location in non-homogeneous circuits using the traveling wave concept, but it requires the installation of distributed current sensors at multiple points, including ends and junctions between overhead lines and underground cables. Other traveling wave methods employ specialized control arrangements, such as injecting traveling wave pulses through existing equipment like converters or hybrid DC circuit breakers [23, 24]. Some methods in this category involve on-site visits and the use of additional equipment, including waveform injectors, tracing monitors, and dedicated processing units [25, 26]. However, the presence of non-homogeneity in the transmission circuit can pose challenges for these methods.

Another category of fault location methods involves Machine Learning (ML) techniques [28-31]. These methods often rely on a large dataset composed of simulated or recorded test cases. The fault locator method in [28] utilizes the Pearson correlation coefficient to compare the measured voltage signals at the transmission system terminus against pre-existing manners. A similar approach is presented in [29], where the method checks the similarity of currents in the adopted DC breakers. To determine the fault location, a processing technique that involves weighted averaging with an approach based on kernel is employed. In [30], another fault locator method relies on neural networks and requires the high sampling rate of 5 MHz to capture traveling surges in currents. It is important to note that the non-homogeneity of the transmission system can add complexity when handling the required data for training in these methods.

Another category of fault locators is based on time domain calculations. Some methods utilize the Bergeron model representation for fault location [32-34]. This approach involves calculating the voltage profile along the length of the transmission system utilizing locally recorded voltage and current signals at the two ends. In a similar vein, the method described in [35] relies on time domain calculations with an estimated model for the transmission circuit. It is important to note that these models and time domain equations will not be suitable for non-homogeneous transmission systems. Additionally, an effective fault locator should be capable of locating all categories of faults, encompassing both pole-to-pole and pole-to-ground faults. Some methods in the literature are limited to locating ground faults only, relying on zero-mode components [21, 22]. The work in [31] is constrained to specific types of VSC converters.

The main contribution of this paper revolves around a fault localization technique that addresses the non-homogeneity of VSC-HVDC transmission circuits. The fault locator technique is based on a novel approach for identifying faulted sections, which hinges on variations in voltage rate changes between power cables and overhead lines. This identification method is not contingent on the computation of fault distances. Notably,

it obviates the necessity of installing extra sensors at the junction points between underground cables and overhead lines. This method offers accurate fault location capabilities for all fault types, including pole-to-ground and pole-to-pole faults, without the complexity of calculations or the requirement for exceptionally high sampling frequencies.

II. THE PROPOSED FAULT LOCATION METHOD

Figure 1 illustrates the diagram of a non-homogeneous VSC-HVDC transmission line (two-section circuit): the underground cable section on the left portion and the overhead line section on the right portion. The proposed method consists of two steps. First, the fault section is determined, which could be either the underground cable section or the overhead section. Second, the method accurately identifies the fault's exact location within the previously selected section.

Fig. 1. The 1-mode voltage profiles calculated under different fault cases: (a) the fault is at the tie point among the underground cable and the overhead section, (b) the fault is within the underground cable section, (c) the faulty point is within the overhead section.

A. Fault Section Identification

The proposed method involves calculating the profile of the 1-mode voltage along the entire transmission circuit with

$$v_1(x, t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z_{c1} + \frac{r_1 x}{4}}{z_{c1}} \right)^2 \left(v_{1S}(t + \tau 1) - i_{1S}(t + \tau 1) \left(z_{c1} + \frac{r_1 x}{4} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z_{c1} + \frac{r_1 x}{4}}{z_{c1}} \right)^2 \left(v_{1S}(t - \tau 1) - i_{1S}(t - \tau 1) \left(z_{c1} - \frac{r_1 x}{4} \right) \right) - \left(\frac{\frac{r_1 x}{4}}{z_{c1}} \right)^2 v_{1S}(t) - \frac{r_1 x}{4} \left(\frac{z_{c1} + \frac{r_1 x}{4}}{z_{c1}} \right) \left(\frac{z_{c1} - \frac{r_1 x}{4}}{z_{c1}} \right) i_{1S}(t) \quad (1)$$

$$v_1'(x, t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z_{c1}' + \frac{r_1' x}{4}}{z_{c1}'} \right)^2 \left(v_{1R}(t + \tau 1') - i_{1R}(t + \tau 1') \left(z_{c1}' + \frac{r_1' x}{4} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z_{c1}' + \frac{r_1' x}{4}}{z_{c1}'} \right)^2 \left(v_{1R}(t - \tau 1') - i_{1R}(t - \tau 1') \left(z_{c1}' - \frac{r_1' x}{4} \right) \right) - \left(\frac{\frac{r_1' x}{4}}{z_{c1}'} \right)^2 v_{1R}(t) - \frac{r_1' x}{4} \left(\frac{z_{c1}' + \frac{r_1' x}{4}}{z_{c1}'} \right) \left(\frac{z_{c1}' - \frac{r_1' x}{4}}{z_{c1}'} \right) i_{1R}(t) \quad (2)$$

where $v_1(x, t)$ and $v_1'(x, t)$ represent the 1-mode voltage components calculated at distance x with reference to terminals S and R , respectively. v_{1S} , i_{1S} , v_{1R} , and i_{1R} denote the 1-mode components of the measured electrical voltage and current readings at terminals S and R , respectively. These signals are calculated as functions of the measured positive and negative signals as follows:

$$v_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (v_p - v_n), \quad i_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (i_p - i_n) \quad (3)$$

where v_1 , i_1 are the 1-mode voltage and current signals, while v_p , i_p , v_n , and i_n are the positive and negative voltage and current signals, respectively.

The parameters z_{c1} and r_1 stand for the 1-mode characteristic impedance and resistance per unit length of the underground cable, z_{c1}' and r_1' represent the corresponding values for the overhead line, and $\tau 1$ and $\tau 1'$ signify the 1-mode travel time duration along the underground cable and overhead line, respectively. The 1-mode parameters of the transmission circuit are calculated as follows:

$$r_1 = r_s - r_m, \quad l_1 = l_s - l_m, \quad c_1 = c_0 + 2c_m \quad (4)$$

where r_1 , l_1 , and c_1 are the 1-mode resistance, inductance, and capacitance of the transmission circuit, r_s , l_s , r_m , and l_m are the self and mutual parameters, and c_0 and c_m are the earth capacitance and the capacitance between poles, respectively.

It is worth noting that these profiles are calculated without considering the non-homogeneity of the transmission circuit. Based on (1) and (2), the profile of the 1-mode voltage along the transmission circuit is calculated as follows:

$$\widetilde{v}_1(x) = \frac{\sum_{t_1}^{t_2} v_1(x, t)}{(t_2 - t_1)/\Delta t}, \quad \widetilde{v}_1'(x) = \frac{\sum_{t_1}^{t_2} v_1'(x, t)}{(t_2 - t_1)/\Delta t} \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta v(x) = \left| \widetilde{v}_1(x) - \widetilde{v}_1'(x) \right| \quad (6)$$

$$loc' = x \text{ at the minimum of } \{\Delta v(x)\} \quad (7)$$

where $\widetilde{v}_1(x)$, $\widetilde{v}_1'(x)$ represent the normalized values of the 1-mode voltages at a particular point x throughout the post-fault period from t_1 to t_2 , where t_1 marks the moment when the 1-mode voltage at the terminal point of the line decreases to a level lower than 0.9 per unit. Δt stands for the sampling time step, while Δv represents the difference between the calculated voltage profiles. loc' represents the initially determined fault

reference to each terminal. The 1-mode voltage is determined at any distance x with respect to terminal S or terminal R using (1) and (2), respectively.

location. It corresponds to the location at which $\Delta v(x)$ is minimized, as indicated in (7).

The identification of the faulted section is based on the initially determined value of loc' . If loc' is equal to the cable's longitudinal extent, it indicates that the fault is at the tie point among the cable and the overhead line. On the other hand, if loc' is less than the cable's length, it indicates that the fault lies within the segment of the underground cable. Alternatively, if loc' is greater than the cable's length, it confirms that the fault is in the overhead line segment.

For further clarity, the profiles of the voltage components corresponding to the 1-mode are illustrated under three fault scenarios in Figure 1. In Figure 1(a), when the fault takes place at the intersection point ' J ', the intersection point between the calculated 1-mode voltage profiles corresponds to the junction point, where $\Delta v(x)$ is minimized. In such a case, loc' equals to the cable's length. In other cases, when the fault is within the cable segment, loc' is less than the cable's length, as illustrated in Figure 1(b). If the fault is within the overhead line section, loc' is greater than the length of the cable, as illustrated in Figure 1(c). Figure 2 outlines the steps of the introduced approach for identifying the faulted section and locating the faulty point.

B. Determining Fault Location

After identifying which section is faulty, whether it is the cable or the overhead line segment, the fault location is determined. It is important to note that the initially determined value of loc' does not directly correspond to the fault distance, due to the non-homogeneity of the transmission system. Therefore, the profile of the 1-mode voltage needs to be updated beyond the junction point. As depicted in Figure 1, if the fault is within the underground cable segment, the profile of the 1-mode voltage must be updated along the cable segment utilizing the voltage and current signals at the junction point. Under such conditions, the overhead line section remains healthy. Thus, the voltage and current signals at the junction point can be straightforwardly computed based on the measured signals at the overhead end. Figure 1(b) illustrates how the 1-mode voltage profile is updated from the junction point towards the cable section. The fault distance is then estimated based on the intersection with the updated profile along the cable section.

Fig. 2. The introduced fault location approach.

Similarly, if the fault is within the overhead line segment, as illustrated in Figure 1(c), the profile of the 1-mode voltage needs to be updated along the overhead line section using the voltage and current signals at the junction point. Under these conditions, the cable section is considered healthy. Thus, the voltage and current signals at the junction point are directly estimated utilizing the measured signals at the cable end. Figure 1(c) illustrates how the 1-mode voltage profile is updated from the junction point towards the overhead line section. The fault distance is then obtained based on the intersection with the updated profile along the overhead segment. To obtain the updated profile of the 1-mode voltage component along any of the sections, it is necessary to calculate the voltage and current signals at the junction point. The voltage at the junction point is calculated in the same manner as in (1) or (2). The current at the junction point is calculated by (8).

$$i_1(x, t) = \frac{1}{2z_{c1}} \left(\frac{z_{c1} + r_1 x}{4} \right) \left(v_{1s}(t + \tau_1) - i_{1s}(t + \tau_1) \left(z_{c1} + \frac{r_1 x}{4} \right) \right) - \frac{1}{2z_{c1}} \left(\frac{z_{c1} - r_1 x}{4} \right) \left(v_{1s}(t - \tau_1) - i_{1s}(t - \tau_1) \left(z_{c1} - \frac{r_1 x}{4} \right) \right) - \frac{1}{2z_{c1}} \left(\frac{r_1 x}{2z_{c1}} \right) \left(v_{1s}(t) - \frac{r_1 x}{4} i_{1s}(t) \right) \quad (8)$$

It is important to note that data windows of the measured signals need to be stored to perform the proposed calculations. In Figure 3(a), we can see the data windows of the recorded voltage and current readings at the ends of the transmission circuit. Figure 3(b) illustrates the necessary size of the data windows required for performing the proposed calculations.

As shown, to obtain the voltage profile calculated during the postfault duration from t_1 to t_2 , the required size of the data window to be stored is $t_2 - t_1 + 4\tau$. This process is performed for each distance along the transmission circuit.

Fig. 3. Samples of the recorded voltage and current readings: (a) the data windows of the measured signals, (b) the required window size of the recorded readings and the corresponding window of the calculated samples of the voltage profile during post fault.

III. TEST SYSTEM DETAILS

Figure 4(a) displays a diagram depicting the simulated system with a single line used to validate the introduced fault-locator approach. This system stands as an illustration of the integration of an offshore wind farm with the grid via a non-homogeneous HVDC link. The simulated wind farm is a 450 MW DFIG (Doubly-Fed Induction Generator) type. The converters are simulated using their average dynamic models with the assistance of the PSCAD program. A non-homogeneous VSC-HVDC ±320 kV transmission circuit is simulated, and the underground cable and the overhead line configurations are presented in Figure 4(b). Details of the simulated MMC (Modular Multilevel Converter) units can be found in Table I. The HVDC voltage level is controlled by the converter on the onshore grid side, while the other converter on the offshore side is responsible for controlling the AC offshore voltage at the wind farm. Referring to the transmission circuit in Figure 4(a), each section, including the underground cable and the overhead line, has a length of 200 km. Various fault cases are simulated at different points, including the tie point among the underground cable and the overhead segments, within the cable section, and within the overhead line section, to investigate the proposed fault location approach. The sampling frequency utilized for capturing the measured signals is 50 kHz.

TABLE I. MMC PARAMETERS [11]

Parameter	value
The count of equivalent sub-modules per arm	76
Sub-module capacitance (μF)	3000
Arm inductance (mH)	50
Resistance due to capacitor leakage (MΩ)	10
Power (MW)	450
DC Voltage (kV)	±320

Fig. 4. (a) The simulated VSC-HVDC transmission circuit for integrating offshore wind farm to the grid, (b) the configuration of the underground cable and overhead line.

IV. VALIDATION RESULTS

A. Fault at the Junction Point

To investigate the introduced location approach, a pole-to-pole fault is simulated at $F2$ at the junction point, which is 200 km away from both ends of the transmission circuit. The calculated profile of the 1-mode voltages along the entire transmission line is illustrated in Figure 5(a).

Fig. 5. Obtained results with the fault at the junction point at $F2$. (a) The calculated profile of the 1-mode voltage along the non-homogenous transmission circuit, (b) the profile of the difference among the calculated 1-mode profiles along the adopted non-homogenous circuit.

As shown, the intersection between both profiles occurs at a distance of 200 km, which corresponds to the fault distance. In Figure 5(b), the difference between the calculated profiles of the 1-mode voltages, computed with (4), is illustrated. As shown in Figure 5(b), the minimum value of the difference is found at the distance of 200 km, confirming it as the fault location point. This indicates that loc' equals to 200 km, precisely at the junction point.

Fig. 6. Obtained results with the fault within the underground cable segment at 100 km from the terminus at $F1$. (a) The calculated profile of 1-mode voltage along the non-homogenous transmission circuit from both ends along with the updated profile along the cable section, (b) the profile of the difference among the calculated 1-mode profiles with and without updating.

B. Fault within the Underground Cable Section

Another fault case is simulated within the underground cable section, specifically 100 km from the transmission line terminus at $F1$. According to the introduced approach, the loc' value is determined first. As seen from the obtained results in Figure 6, the difference between the calculated 1-mode voltage profiles corresponds to a location of 103 km, which is shorter than the cable segment length. Following the introduced approach, this indicates that the fault is within the cable section. Subsequently, the precise fault distance is determined by updating the 1-mode voltage profile along the underground cable section. Figure 6(a) displays the updated $\tilde{v}_1'(x)$, and Figure 6(b) shows the difference between the 1-mode profiles after the update. It is evident that the minimum value accurately corresponds to the exact location, which is 100 km.

C. Fault within the Overhead Line Section

Another fault case is simulated within the overhead line section, specifically at a location 300 km from the transmission line terminus at $F3$. Following the introduced approach, the value of loc' is first determined.

Fig. 7. Obtained results with the fault within the overhead segment at 300 km from the terminus at F3. (a) The calculated profile of 1-mode voltage along the non-homogenous transmission circuit from both ends along with the updated profile along the cable section, (b) the profile of the difference among the calculated 1-mode profiles with and without updating.

As demonstrated by the results in Figure 7, the difference between the calculated 1-mode voltage profiles corresponds to a location of 288 km, which exceeds the cable segment length. According to the introduced approach, this signifies that the fault is within the overhead segment. Subsequently, the precise fault distance is determined by updating the 1-mode voltage profile along the overhead line section. Figure 7(a) displays the updated $\bar{v}_1(x)$, while Figure 7(b) shows the difference between the 1-mode profiles after the update. It is evident that the minimum value accurately corresponds to the exact location, which is 300 km.

D. Performance under Different Distances with Various Fault Categories

Different fault types, including pole-to-ground and pole-to-pole faults, were tested at diverse fault distances. In each case, the error in the determined fault distance is computed utilizing the following criterion. Table II depicts the obtained results with the tested cases.

$$Error\% = \frac{|Estimated\ location - Fault\ location|}{Total\ transmission\ circuit\ length} * 100 \quad (9)$$

E. Performance under Different Fault Resistances

The introduced fault locator approach is examined under various fault resistance values. Pole-to-pole faults are investigated at three locations: 100, 200, and 300 km, with varying fault resistance values of 10, 50, and 200 Ω. Figure 8 illustrates the calculated 1-mode profiles using the introduced approach under various fault resistances.

Figure 8(a) displays the results for the fault at 100 km under three different fault resistance values: 10, 50, and 200 Ω. As shown in the results, the intersection point accurately

corresponds to the correct fault location, which is 100 km, regardless of the different fault resistance values.

TABLE II. ESTIMATED FAULT LOCATION BY THE INTRODUCED APPROACH UNDER VARIOUS FAULT CATEGORIES AND VARIOUS DISTANCES

Fault type	Fault location (km)	Estimated location (km)	Error %
PG	10	10.3	0.075
PG	60	59.4	0.15
PG	130	128.5	0.375
PG	180	181.1	0.275
PG	210	210.5	0.125
PG	270	268.9	0.275
PG	330	331.2	0.3
PG	390	389	0.25
PP	10	9.8	0.05
PP	60	59	0.25
PP	130	129	0.25
PP	180	180.5	0.125
PP	210	211	0.25
PP	270	271.7	0.425
PP	330	331	0.25
PP	390	392	0.5

Fig. 8. Obtained results under different fault resistances: Fault at (a) 100 km, (b) 200 km, and (c) 300 km with fault resistances of 10, 50, and 200 Ω.

This demonstrates a notable benefit of the proposed method, as it remains unaffected by changes in fault resistance.

Similar results are observed for tests conducted at different locations, as depicted in Figures 8(b)-(c), which show the results for faults occurring at 200 km and 300 km, respectively. It is important to note that the line styles are altered in the Figure to distinguish between the calculated 1-mode voltage profile and the updated profile before and beyond the junction point. In Figures 8(a) and 8(c), solid lines represent the calculated 1-mode voltages, while dashed lines represent the updated voltage profile beyond the junction point. To investigate the error percentage in the obtained locations under different resistances, Table III presents the error percentage calculated according to (9) under the tested cases.

TABLE III. ESTIMATED FAULT LOCATION BY THE INTRODUCED APPROACH UNDER VARIOUS FAULT RESISTANCES

Fault type	Fault distance (km)	Fault resistance (Ω)	Error %
PG	100	5	0.15
PG	100	75	0.09
PG	100	150	0.34
PG	100	250	0.28
PG	200	5	0.25
PG	200	75	0.18
PG	200	150	0.30
PG	200	250	0.21
PG	300	5	0.15
PG	300	75	0.32
PG	300	150	0.27
PG	300	250	0.23
PP	100	5	0.07
PP	100	75	0.11
PP	100	150	0.21
PP	100	250	0.24
PP	200	5	0.18
PP	200	75	0.16
PP	200	150	0.09
PP	200	250	0.31
PP	300	5	0.09
PP	300	75	0.14
PP	300	150	0.31
PP	300	250	0.50

Fig. 9. Obtained results under fault at 200 km with unsynchronized data by 0.1 ms and 0.2 ms.

F. Performance under Unsynchronized Samples at Terminals

The proposed method relies on performing calculations using the recorded signals at the terminals of the transmission circuit. It is essential to test the performance of the introduced approach under unsynchronized samples. Considering the test system mentioned above, a pole-to-pole fault case is simulated

at 200 km. The calculations of $\tilde{v}_1(x)$ are performed with the data recorded at one of the terminals, while the calculations of $\tilde{v}_1'(x)$ are performed with unsynchronized measured signals.

Figure 9 presents the results of the 1-mode voltage profile under three conditions: synchronized, unsynchronized by 0.1 ms, and unsynchronized by 0.2 ms. As shown in the Figure, the performance is not affected, as the intersection still accurately indicates the fault location, which is 200 km. This demonstrates a significant advantage of the introduced approach.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A fault locator method for non-homogeneous VSC-HVDC transmission circuits is presented in this paper. The method is based on time-domain calculations using signals measured at the terminals. First, the faulted section is identified, either the underground cable or the overhead line. This identification is performed using a proposed criterion based on the comparison of the 1-mode voltage profiles without considering the non-homogeneity of the transmission circuit. Then, the fault locator approach is estimated within the selected section by updating the calculated voltage profile beyond the faulted section. To validate the introduced approach, a non-homogeneous VSC-HVDC transmission system is simulated as a part of integrating an offshore wind farm with the grid. The results confirm the effectiveness of the introduced approach under different fault types, including pole-to-pole and pole-to-ground faults, with a maximum error of 0.5%. Additionally, the approach is tested with changing fault resistance values, even as high as 250 Ω, with errors not exceeding 0.5%. Furthermore, the proposed method is evaluated under synchronization misalignment by 0.1 ms and 0.2 ms, and it is found that its performance remains unaffected. The proposed fault locator is distinguished by its lack of need and for an additional sensor to be installed at the junction point. Furthermore, there is no requirement to visit the site, use extra equipment, or process big data.

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An In-Depth Investigation of Innovative Electric Traction Power Supply Systems for Mass Rapid Transit

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the outcomes of a study conducted to explore new power supply sources for subway trains. The power supply system for traction is an integral and inseparable component of subway rail infrastructure, encompassing both its management and operation. As a result, the specific choice of a power supply type has a lasting impact, either positive or negative, on the overall performance of a subway system. Consequently, researching power supply for traction presents a considerably more intricate challenge when compared to other railway transportation systems. In this study, the results obtained shed light on the pros and cons of utilizing the 25,000 V / 50 Hz system in comparison with the 1,500 V DC system, with a particular focus on traffic capacity and the efficiency of supplying traction power.

Keywords-MRT; metro; 1,500 V DC traction power; 25,000 V / 50 Hz traction power; high speed railway

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's urban rail transportation planning, subway systems are typically considered for cities with populations of two millions or more, and especially for those with populations exceeding four millions. Globally, the subway system is an integral part of the dynamic urban transportation network in major cities. It serves as the largest capacity transportation system to alleviate congestion during peak hours. The capacity of this system varies, ranging from low to medium, handling 20,000 passengers per hour per direction (p/h/d) to 40,000 p/h/d, medium to high capacity from 40,000 p/h/d to 64,000 p/h/d, and high to very high capacity from 64,000 p/h/d and higher [1-3, 33-34, 36]. The train capacity also varies, accommodating the needs of different routes and service frequencies. Trains are designed with capacities ranging from 4 cars for low capacity, 6 to 8 cars for high capacity, and 8 to 12 cars for very high capacity. Route requirements are matched with train capacities, which depend on train capacity and peak-hour service frequency, ranging from 5 minutes per train per direction (m/t/d) to 1.5 m/t/d, or as low as 72 sec per train per

direction for automated systems at GoA4 standard [1-3, 33, 36]. Today, in the research and design of power supply for subway train traction, there is a strong correlation between route capacity and voltage, effectively becoming a "dual standard" with specific guidelines. For example, in systems with capacities below 40,000 p/h/d, a voltage of 750 V DC is typically used. For capacities ranging from 40,000 to 64,000 p/h/d, the standard voltage is 1,500 V DC, and for higher capacities, voltages of 3,000 V DC are employed in Brazil and Chile. There are exceptions, such as the new systems in India with a standardized voltage of 25,000 V AC at a frequency of 50 Hz [33, 36].

Throughout its history of formation and development, urban rail transportation, especially subways, has primarily relied on DC power systems, typically at higher voltage levels. The introduction of the 25,000 V / 50 Hz system in the southern region of France in 1953 marked a significant shift and is now predominantly used worldwide for long-distance and high-speed rail systems. However, in recent years, some countries with electrified railway systems have been exploring

higher voltage power supply solutions to accommodate larger capacity transportation systems within urban areas [3-8].

In the early years of the 21st century, research on providing traction power for subway trains has undergone changes due to the increasing passenger capacity demands in densely populated countries. This shift necessitates that power supply solutions ensure fundamental factors such as supply capacity, reliability, and electrical safety for passengers and operational staff. Numerous methods have been studied worldwide to meet these criteria. However, the majority of these studies have primarily focused on enhancing the reliability of existing power sources, optimizing their efficiency, and improving the quality of power supply voltage [9-15]. Therefore, these studies may not align with the needs of countries that are planning subway systems and aiming for sustainable development, including Vietnam [36]. Hence, this paper explores various aspects of supplying 25,000 V AC at a frequency of 50 Hz (or 60 Hz) for subway trains in relation to DC systems with similar capacities.

Most studies in the design of electric traction power supply for subway trains involve comprehensive, efficient, and cost-effective simulations. In this study, Matlab R2017b/Railway Systems is the chosen software for simulating calculations in the power supply design, used in the form of writing scripts (code) according to a series of calculation formulas, suitable for the general application scenario presented in this article [3, 19-25, 31, 33].

II. TRACTION POWER SUPPLY SYSTEMS

A. Traction Power Substation

The subway is an electrical load with special power consumption characteristics due to its high-frequency service and is considered a type I electrical load. Therefore, supplying power to the subway requires more stringent requirements. The schematic diagram of the power supply system for the subway is generally described in Figure 1 and has the following technical features [3, 5-11]:

- High-voltage AC external power supply from 110 kV to 220 kV at 50Hz.
- High-voltage substation (BSS) for DC traction power supply and internal distribution network (DTS).
- In the 25,000 V / 50 Hz system traction power substation (TPS), with the core being traction transformer (TR): single-phase (I/I), star-star unbalanced, open delta/star unbalanced, open delta (V/V), star/delta-1, 11 (Y/D1, 11), Scott, LeBlanc, Modifine – Wood Bridge, Root – Delta [7-10].
- In the DC system TPS, consisting of AC/DC converters including: rectifier transformer and uncontrolled rectifier (TSR) [7-8]:
- Rectifier transformer (RTT): star, delta/delta, star; delta, star/star – delta; delta, star/six-phase with interphase transformer; delta, star/three-phase zigzag with interphase transformer; delta, star/two-phase zigzag with interphase transformer.

- Uncontrolled Rectifier (SR): three-phase bridge, parallel bridge, series bridge, double star six – phase half – wave with interphase transformer (reactor).
- Other basic components on the DC and AC traction sides such as DC Bus (BDC), negative (-), positive (+), AC Bus (BAC 25,000 V), power traction distribution cabinet and main circuit breakers and switches (CSB), contact line system (CLS), track (R), and return system (RS).
- Rated DC currents: 750 V DC, 1,500 V DC, and 3,000 V DC.
- The rated alternating current voltage is 25,000 V AC at a frequency of 50 Hz (25,000 V/ 50 Hz).
- All DC and AC operating voltages adhere to the EN 50163, UIC 600, and IEC 60850 standards.

Fig. 1. General diagram of the subway power supply.

B. Traction Power Distribution System

1) Direct Current Traction Power Distribution System

The traction power distribution system in a basic subway system consists of the following [5-11]:

- Contact Line System: The system can use a third rail (3rdR) or an overhead contact line system (OCS). However, for a primarily 750 V DC system, the most common choice is the 3rdR contact network.
- Single-Feeding Power Supply: This network provides power from one direction only, as in Figure 2. The advantage of this network is its simplicity, easy installation of protective devices, and straightforward operation. However, its drawback is the significant voltage drop along the transmission line, limiting the loading capacity.

- **Double-Feeding Power Supply:** This network supplies power from two directions, as in Figure 3. Its advantages include reduced voltage drop, extended supply distance, higher loading capacity, and increased power delivery. However, the downside is that this network is more complex in structure, requires intricate protective device installation, and involves challenging maintenance.
- **Section Post (SP):** In low-voltage DC subway systems, there are typically no subsection posts (SSP), and only section posts (SP) exist. SP are simple junctions, vertical, diagonal, or horizontal, depending on the design calculations and operational contingencies. They are set up to handle potential incidents or for double – feeding power supply.

Fig. 2. A single – feeding power supply network.

Fig. 3. A double – feeding power supply network.

2) The AC 25,000 V / 50 Hz Distribution System

The 25,000 V / 50 Hz traction power distribution system through an overhead contact system and distribution structure consists off the following [5-7, 16-22, 31-32]:

- **Direct Traction Distribution Network with Return Circuit Enhancement:** Advantages: Simple, easy to operate, lower cost compared to other types. Disadvantages: Significant voltage drop along the transmission line, high electromagnetic field (EMF) and electromagnetic interference (EMI).
- **Traction Distribution Network with Booster Transformer (BT):** Advantages: Reduced leakage current, enhanced return current, reduced EMF and EMI [4-5]. Disadvantages: Increased impedance along the transmission line, flashovers due to contact arcing, reduced supply distance, increased installation and maintenance complexity.
- **Traction Distribution Network with Auto Transformer (AT)** [25-26]: Advantages: Increased transmission distance, reduced traction current on the section between two ATs, enhanced loading capacity, reduced leakage current, enhanced return current, reduced traction current on AT sections without running trains, reduced EMF and EMI impact. Disadvantages: Complex system, additional feeder cables (-25,000 V, F), complex switching and protection devices, increased installation cost.
- **Sections Post (SP):** Installed at the end of supply segments, with distances ranging from 40 km to 80 km depending on the load. Switches are always in the open position, and it becomes significantly more complex with AT systems.
- **Subsection Post (SSP):** Always in the closed position to maintain continuous power supply from the traction substation to the end of the supply segment during normal operation. Installation distance typically ranges from 20 km to 30 km.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. Load Calculation Method

In the power supply design, the supplying capacity of a traction substation needs to meet the power consumption requirements of all trains within its supply range. The number of trains depends on the length of the supply range, train speed, and line capacity. In the dynamics of a train's motion, the electrical power consumption has a direct relationship with the speed of motion and the required traction force to achieve it, and an inverse relationship with mechanical efficiency and engine efficiency. Furthermore, during peak hours, the maximum power consumption depends on the number of trains operating within a supply range. Predicting power consumption in the design is carried out as follows:

Assuming that all other resistances due to railway terrain are disregarded, the maximum required power for trains in a journey is [2, 5, 10, 13, 22-27]:

$$P_t = \frac{(W_t + W_p) \cdot V}{\eta_c \cdot \eta_m \cdot 3.6} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{a}{g} \cdot \varepsilon \cdot 10^3 \right) + (A + B \cdot V + C \cdot V^2) \right] \quad (1)$$

where W_t is the weight of the train, W_p is the total weight of the passengers, W is the total weight of train and passengers, η_c is the utility factor of mechanical transmission train, η_m is the utility factor of the traction motor, a is the acceleration of the train in every time step of the calculation, ε is the coefficient of rotating masses, g is the constant of gravity, V is the train velocity in every time step of the calculation, and A, B, C are the coefficients in the rolling resistance of W. J. Davis' formula.

The maximum instantaneous total power consumption under normal operating and the auxiliary power consumed on train (P_{aux}) are related by:

$$P_{TPSi-max} = \sum_{i=1}^n (P_t + P_{aux}) \quad (2)$$

The selected power in the design must ensure a margin for contingencies or unexpected load increases. Therefore, the rated design power for each substation must be greater than the calculated maximum power with a minimum reserve factor of 1.1. Voltage check is a crucial task in the design process: Let U_n be the rated voltage at the point where the contact line is supplied with a slight load increase or at rated current, and ΔU_x

be the voltage drop on the contact line at point x with the distribution of the load current on the section of train running. Then, the voltage supplied to the train at x is U_{tx} . If x moves to the end position of the source, then the maximum voltage drop is $\Delta U_{dc,max}$, and the minimum contact voltage is $U_{tx,min}$, determined as follows [2, 4, 10, 13, 20-29]:

$$I_{all} = \frac{60}{n} \cdot \frac{R_{TPS}}{v_{sc}} \cdot I_t \quad (3)$$

$$I_x = \frac{60}{n} \cdot \frac{L_x}{v_{sc}} \cdot I_t, \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta U_{dc,x} = \sum_i I_{all} \cdot r_{cls} \cdot L_x \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta U_{dc,max} = \Delta U_{dc,x} + (I_{all} - I_x) \cdot r_{cls} \cdot (R_{TPS} - L_x) \quad (6)$$

$$U_{tx,min} = U_n - \Delta U_{dc,max} \quad (7)$$

where I_t is the traction current of the train, I_{all} is the total traction current of the trains on one RTPS segment, and $\Delta U_{dc,x}$ is the voltage drop at position x.

The selected traction substation's power rating must comply with the IEEE P1653.2, EN 50328, and IEC 60146-1 standards, and the operating voltage must adhere to the EN 50163, UIC 600, and IEC 60850 standards.

B. Load Parameters

The study was conducted on a hypothetical route with a length of 40 km in accordance with the planning in large cities and the current expansion construction trends in India, Korea, China, and the HCMC Metro of Vietnam (Line 1 and Line 2) [36]. Table I exhibits the system modeled parameters. n+1 is the number of traction AC/DC converters (transformers and rectifiers – TSR), 1 symbolizing the redundant converter, nTSR is the total number of AC/DC converters in a substation, DTPS is the distance between two traction power substations, and RTPS is the radius of a DTPS. The parameters related to the traffic capacity of the system are shown in Table II, whereas Table III shows the traction system assumptions.

IV. SIMULATION RESULT

A. Load Calculation

The train parameters were selected in order to meet the requirements of the described route, as outlined in Table II. The train capacities include both seated and standing passengers, with a maximum of 7 p/m². Four scenarios were analyzed, with passenger capacity increasing from 30,000 to 64,000 p/h/d. Each scenario offers three choices in the distribution of passenger flow and capacity corresponding to the peak-hour headway. The summary of the results of calculating the maximum capacity load per hour according to the route capacity requirements are described in Tables IV and V, where Pcal is the capacity calculated according to the traction force, Pn is the rated capacity according to the train's rated current, nTPS is the total number of TPS, u is the rated power per TSR or per TR, n/TPS is the number of TSR sets in a TPS, nTPS is the total TSR number used on the entire route, n/TR is the number of TR sets in a TPS, nTR shows the total TR used on the entire route, and Ptot is the total power traction demand on the entire route.

TABLE I. SYSTEM MODELING AND ASSUMPTIONS

Option	1500 V DC		25 kV AC	
1	D _{TPS} [km]	4	D _{TPS} [km]	20
	R _{TPS} [km]	2	R _{TPS} [km]	20
	n _{TPS} [km]	10	n _{TPS} [km]	2
	n _{TSR}	n+1	n _{TSR}	2.(1+1)
2	D _{TPS} [km]	4	D _{TPS} [km]	20
	R _{TPS} [km]	2.6	R _{TPS} [km]	10
	n _{TPS} [km]	10	n _{TPS} [km]	2
	n _{TSR}	n+1	n _{TSR}	2.(1+1)
3	D _{TPS} [km]	4	D _{TPS} [km]	40
	R _{TPS} [km]	4	R _{TPS} [km]	20
	n _{TPS} [km]	10	n _{TPS} [km]	1
	n _{TSR}	n+1	n _{TSR}	1+1

TABLE II. PARAMETERS OF TRAFFIC CAPACITY AND THE RESULT OF SELECTING THE PROVIDED CAPACITY [1-3, 4-6, 21-32]

Component	Unit	Value
Traffic capacity case 1, C _L ¹	[p/h/d]	30,000
Traffic capacity case 2, C _L ²	[p/h/d]	40,000
Traffic capacity case 3, C _L ³	[p/h/d]	50,000
Traffic capacity case 4, C _L ⁴	[p/h/d]	64,000
Headway case 1...4 (n ₁ , n ₂ , n ₃ , n ₄)	[m/t/d]	3.5; 3.0; 2.5; 2.0
Number of passengers per train, C _t ¹	[p/t]	1,765
Number of passenger per train, C _t ²	[p/t]	2,000
Number of passengers per train, C _t ³	[p/t]	2,100
Number of passenger per train, C _t ⁴	[p/t]	2,150
Standard of passenger per square meter	[p/m ²]	5 – 7
Passenger per car (max)	[p/c]	300
Passenger weight, m _p	[kg/p]	65
Train weight, M _t	[t]	2.38 + 6.32
Train acceleration	[m/s ²]	0.95
Train velocity	[km/h]	50
Train configuration UIC		2'2' + 6.Bo'Bo' + 2'2'
Resistance moving	[ton/kg]	
R = 3,25+0,039·V+0,000659·V ²		
Power of the train, P _t [kw]		3,900
Train current, I [A]: 400·(6M)		
Auxiliary current, I _{am} [A]: 25.3333·(6M) + 24·(2Mc)		

TABLE III. TRACTION SYSTEM ASSUMPTIONS [1-6, 21-32]

Component	Value
Running rail UIC 60	0.03 Ω/km rail, All four rails cross bonded: 0.0075 Ω/km
DC CuETp 150 + BzII 120	0.0156 Ω/km, Double track
AC CuMg AC 120 + Bz II 120	0.391 ± 70 ⁰ (0.139 + j0.366) Ω/km, Double track
U _n	1,500 V (DC)
U _n	25,000 V (AC)

B. Discussion

1) Case 1

To meet the demand of 30,000 p/h/d with a supply capacity of 17 t/h/d and a train headway of 3.5 m/t/d, the total traction force required for accelerating to maximum speed is 363.92 N. The total weight is 365.07 tons. For a 1,500 V DC one-way system along the entire route with 10 traction substations, each requiring a power supply capacity of 12.2 MW (which is greater than the rated power of 11.88 MW), the total power required for the entire route is 122.01 MW. This would involve the use of 30 AC/DC converters.

TABLE IV. DESIGN RESULT, 1,500 V DC

Describe		Mass Rapid Transits: 1500 V DC											
		CASE 1			CASE 2			CASE 3			CASE 4		
Component	Unit	Op 1	Op 2	Op 3	Op 1	Op 2	Op 3	Op 1	Op 2	Op 3	Op 1	Op 2	Op 3
Line length	km	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Station		40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
headway	m/t/d	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.0	2.0	2.0
C _L	p/h/d	30,000	30,000	30,000	40,000	40,000	40,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	64,000	64,000	64,000
C _t	p/t	1,765	1,765	1,765	2,000	2,000	2,000	2,100	2,100	2,100	2,150	2,150	2,150
mp	Kg/p	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55
Mt	Ton/t	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
M	Ton/t	365.07	365.07	365.07	378	378	378	383.5	383.5	383.5	386.25	386.25	386.25
Ft	N	363.92	363.92	363.92	376.81	376.81	376.81	382.29	382.29	382.29	385.05	385.05	385.05
D _{T_{PS}}	km	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
R _{T_{PS}}	km	2	2.6	4	2	2.6	4	2	2.6	4	2	2.6	4
Train/ R _{T_{PS}}	n/d	0.762	1.0	1.52	0.89	1.16	1.78	1.067	1.387	2.133	1.333	1.733	2.667
Train/line	n/2d	30.47	30.47	30.47	35.6	35.6	35.6	42.667	42.667	42.667	53.333	53.333	53.333
Pcal/ R _{T_{PS}}	MW	5.73	7.45	11.47	6.9	8.98	13.82	8.411	10.934	16.822	10.514	13.668	21.028
Pcal/TPS	MW	12.20	12.20	12.20	14.73	14.73	14.73	16.822	16.822	16.822	21.179	21.179	21.179
Pn/TPS	MW	11.88	11.88	11.88	13.86	13.86	13.86	16.640	16.640	16.640	20.800	20.800	20.800
n _{T_{PS}}		10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
u/TSR	MW	4.200	4.200	4.200	4.200	4.200	4.200	6.400	6.400	6.400	6.400	6.400	6.400
n/TSR		2+1	2+1	2+1	3+1	3+1	3+1	2+1	2+1	2+1	3+1	3+1	3+1
nTSR		30	30	30	40	40	40	30	30	30	40	40	40
Ptot	MW	122.01	122.01	122.01	147.39	147.39	147.39	168.22	168.22	168.22	211.79	211.79	211.79
Un	V	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500
Uo	V	1,665	1,665	1,665	1,665	1,665	1,665	1,665	1,665	1,665	1,665	1,665	1,665
Utx-min	V	1,408	1,372	1,217	1,393	1,351	1,170	1,372	1,321	1,104	1,339	1,268	1,001

TABLE V. DESIGN RESULT, 25,000 V / 50 HZ AC

Describe		Mass Rapid Transits: 2,5000 V AC/50HZ											
		CASE 1			CASE 2			CASE 3			CASE 4		
Component	Unit	Op 1	Op 2	Op 3	Op 1	Op 2	Op 3	Op 1	Op 2	Op 3	Op 1	Op 2	Op 3
Line length	km	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Station		40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
headway	m/t/d	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.0	2.0	2.0
C _L	p/h/d	30,000	30,000	30,000	40,000	40,000	40,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	64,000	64,000	64,000
C _t	p/t	1,765	1,765	1,765	2,000	2,000	2,000	2,100	2,100	2,100	2,150	2,150	2,150
mp	Kg/p	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55
Mt	Ton/t	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
M	Ton/t	365.07	365.07	365.07	378	378	378	383.5	383.5	383.5	386.25	386.25	386.25
Ft	N	363.92	363.92	363.92	376.81	376.81	376.81	382.29	382.29	382.29	385.05	385.05	385.05
D _{T_{PS}}	km	20	40	20	20	40	20	20	40	20	20	40	20
R _{T_{PS}}	km	10	20	30	10	20	30	10	20	30	10	20	30
Train/ R _{T_{PS}}	n/d	3.80	7.62	11.43	4.44	8.88	13.33	5.33	10.66	16.00	6.67	13.33	20
Train/line	n/2d	30.47	30.47	30.47	35.56	35.56	35.56	42.67	42.67	42.67	53.33	53.33	53.33
Pcal/ R _{T_{PS}}	MW	13.87	27.73	41.60	16.75	33.49	50.25	20.39	40.78	61.17	25.67	51.34	77.01
Pcal/TPS	MVA	61.01	122.02	61.01	73.69	147.39	73.69	84.11	168.22	84.11	105.89	211.79	105.89
Pn/TPS	MVA	59.43	118.8	59.43	69.33	138.67	69.33	83.2	166.40	83.20	104.00	208.00	104.00
n _{T_{PS}}		2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2
u/TR	MVA	36.00	64.00	36.00	40.00	74.00	36.00	42.00	85.00	42.00	54.00	100.00	54.00
n/TR		2+1	2+1	2+1	2+1	2+1	2+1	2+1	2+1	2+1	2+1	2+1	2+1
nTR		6	3	6	6	3	6	6	3	6	6	3	6
Ptot	MVA	122.02	122.02	122.02	147.39	149.39	147.39	168.22	168.22	168.22	211.79	211.79	211.79
Uo	V	27,500	27,500	27,500	27,500	27,500	27,500	27,500	27,500	27,500	27,500	27,500	27,500
Un	V	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000
Utx - min	V	23,519	19,816	13,663	23,382	19,335	12,403	23,244	18,854	11,499	23,107	17,022	10,495
Umax - l	V			27,500			27,500		27,500	27,500		27,500	27,500
Utx - min	V			16,163			14,903		21,354	13,949		19,522	12,995

In the case of different options for the basic current distribution structure from one direction, with a range of supply radii from 2 km (Op.1) to 4 km (Op.3), the minimum contact voltage at the farthest source end for the worst-case scenario

(Op.3) is 1,217 V, which is greater than the 1,000 V DC standard as per EN 50163, UIC 600, and IEC 60850.

For the 25,000 V AC / 50 Hz system, there are three options for the power supply system structure: one traction

substation or two traction substations. In the case of structure 1 (Op.1), the entire route is equipped with two traction substations, each with a power supply radius of 10 km. In this scenario, the calculated power for each substation is 61.01 MW (assuming neglecting losses from transformers and power factor). Therefore, the total power required is 122.02 MW. Assuming each traction transformer in the substation has a capacity of 36 MW, using two transformers per TPS and one spare transformer, a total of 6 traction transformers are required for the entire route.

When configuring the system with two traction substations along the entire route (Op.1), each with a 10 km supply radius, the contact voltage at the end of the segment is 23,519 V. If in Op.1, one substation experiences a fault, the segment with the largest power supply range is 30 km (corresponding to structure Op.3). In this scenario, the total number of trains in this segment increases to 11.43, resulting in an extremely high traction current. Consequently, maximum voltage drop occurs, leading to the minimum contact voltage at the end of the segment of 13,663 V, which is lower than the minimum voltage limit of 19,000 V. Even if the transformer tap is adjusted by 10% to 27,500 V ($U_{max} - 1$), the contact voltage at the end of the transmission line remains at 16,163 V, which is still lower than 19,000 V.

In the case of a centralized power source (Op.2) with one traction substation to meet the power consumption requirements, two transformers with a capacity of 64.00 MW each and one spare transformer are needed. In this scenario, the minimum contact voltage is 19,816 V at the end of the segment.

2) Case 2

The scenario was simulated with medium-level transportation demand of 40,000 p/h/d, designed with a supply capacity of 20 t/h/d and a train headway of 3.0 m/t/d. In this case, the total weight of a fully loaded train is 378 tons, and the maximum required traction force is 376.81 N.

For the 1,500 V DC system, during this phase, the rated power is 13.86 MW, and the power required for each traction substation is 14.74 MW. The structure involves modular units with each unit having a capacity of 4.2 MW installed in parallel with three units and one spare. The total power required for the entire route is 147.39 MW, and 40 AC/DC converters need to be installed. Similar to the previous scenario, the minimum contact voltage for the Op.1, Op.2, and Op.3 configurations is 1,393 V DC, 1,351 V DC, and 1,170 V DC, respectively. All these voltages are higher than the 1,000 V DC standard specified by EN 50163, UIC 600, and IEC 60850.

For the 25,000 V AC / 50 Hz system, with a configuration of two traction substations, the calculated power for each substation is 73.69 MW, which is higher than the rated power of 69.33 MW. Therefore, the total power required for the entire route is 147.39 MW. Assuming each traction transformer has a capacity of 40 MW, a total of 6 traction transformers are needed for this case. During normal operation or in the event of a fault, for the single substation configuration (Op.2), the minimum contact voltage is 19,335 V AC, and the power supply capacity for each transformer is 74.00 MW, with two

transformers working in parallel and one spare. For the dual substation configuration along the route (Op.1), if operating normally, the minimum contact voltage at the end of the line (10 km) is 23,382 V AC. In the event of a fault at one substation (Op.3), with a power supply range of 30 km, the minimum contact voltage is 14,903 V, even when the transformer tap is increased by 10% ($U_{max} - 1$).

3) Case 3

In this scenario, the transportation demand is at a medium to high level of 50,000 passengers p/h/d, designed with a supply capacity of 24 t/h/d and a train headway of 2.5 m/t/d. In this case, the total weight of a fully loaded train is 383.5 tons, and the maximum required traction force is 382.29 N.

For the DC system, within the power supply range of a single traction substation for both directions, there are 4.2667 trains. Therefore, the total rated power of the load is 16.64 MW and the calculated power required for each traction substation is 16.822 MW/TPS. Since the power supply range of the traction substations is the same, the system is designed with 10 TPS, and the total power required for the entire route is 168.22 MW. In the case of configuration 3 (Op.3), with a distribution of 2.133 trains on a segment with a length of 4 km, the maximum voltage drop occurs at the end of the segment, resulting in a minimum contact voltage of 1,104 V. Therefore, with this power supply capacity and structure, the 1,500 V DC system can still meet the peak-hour traffic demand of 50,000 p/h/d, even in the event of an adjacent traction substation failure.

For the 25,000 V AC / 50 Hz system, the calculated power required for each traction substation with Op.1 and Op.3 configurations is 84.11 MW, comparable to the rated power of 83.2 MW. On the route designed with two traction substations, the minimum number of transformers designed is 2 per substation in parallel with one spare, resulting in a total of 6 transformers, each with a minimum power rating of 42 MW per transformer for both Op.1 and Op.3 cases. In the case of the Op.2 configuration on the route designed with a single traction substation, the total required power capacity is 168.22 MW. Therefore, to meet this capacity, two transformers, each with a capacity of 85 MW, are used in the substation, with two transformers operating in load-sharing and one spare. Regarding the operating voltage, with the Op.1 configuration supplying power on both directions of a traction substation over a 10 km range, with 5.33 trains appearing on each direction, the minimum contact voltage at the end of the segment is 23,244 V AC. However, with this configuration, in the event of a traction substation failure, the segment with the largest power supply range is 30 km, with the presence of 16 trains on the segment. Similar to the previous cases, an extremely large voltage drop occurs, resulting in an extremely low contact voltage of 13,949 V, even after adjusting the transformer tap by 10%. For Op.2, in the case of normal operation, the minimum contact voltage at the end of the segment is 18,854 V AC, which is lower than the minimum standard allowed. When increasing the transformer tap by 10%, the contact voltage at the end of the segment is 21,354 V, which complies with the EN 50163, UIC 600, and IEC 60850 standards.

4) Case 4

This scenario corresponds to a high capacity level, with a transportation demand of 64,000 p/h/d, designed with a line capacity of 30 t/h/d. The total weight of a fully loaded train is 386.25 tons and the maximum required traction force is 385.05 N.

In Case 4, with a service headway of 2.0 m/t/d, a total route length of 40 km, and a travel speed of 45 km/h, the average density of load distribution on the route is 1.066 trains per km. Since the stations are evenly spaced, the power capacity is the same for all stations, calculated at 21.179 MW (as per the calculation) and 20.80 MW (rated capacity). Each set of power equipment has a capacity of 6.4 MW, and each station is equipped with 4 sets. The operating voltage for each configuration from Op.1 to Op.3 is 1,339 V DC, 1,268 V DC, and 1,001 V DC.

For the 25,000 V AC system, with a calculated power capacity of 105.89 MW per traction substation (comparable to the rated capacity of 104.00 MW), each traction substation requires a minimum of two operating transformers and one spare, with each transformer having a capacity of 54.00 MW. In configuration 2 (Op.2), only one substation is installed on the route, so the minimum power capacity of the substation must be greater than the rated capacity, and each transformer has a capacity of 100 MW. The minimum contact voltage in configuration 1 (Op.1) is 23,107 V AC, and in Op.2, it is 19,522 V, with the transformer tap adjusted by 10%. For configuration Op.3, the contact voltage is 12,995 V AC after adjusting the transformer tap by 10%. Overall, the cases of load are classified in ascending order to facilitate the assessment of load increase and voltage drop along a constant length of the power distribution structure. This demonstrates that, within the typical power supply range of a traction substation for 1,500 V DC underground railways, which is around 4 km with traffic loads ranging from 30,000 to 64,000 p/h/d, the system can adequately meet the load requirements and operational voltage conditions when supplied from one direction. However, the supply capacity for traffic can increase if an optimized power supply structure scheme is employed.

Traditionally, the 25,000 V AC / 50 Hz (or 60 Hz) systems are mainly designed for local, long-distance passenger and freight rail systems, as well as high-speed railways. For these types of railways, although they use high-powered trains, the train service frequency is low, and the speed is high. As a result, the distribution of current per kilometer of track is low, leading to a minimal voltage drop at the end of the line. Therefore, the minimum contact voltage limit is not typically violated in these systems. However, for subway systems, due to their high train service frequency, the current distribution per kilometer of track is high. As the distance between traction substations increases, the voltage drop at the end of the line increases, resulting in a lower contact voltage as seen in configurations Op.2 and Op.3. Furthermore, in the case of an increased load, the 25,000 V AC / 50 Hz system cannot change the power supply structure from one direction to two directions as in direct current systems. The rated power of traction transformers increases when the capacity of the line load increases. Using transformers with capacities greater than 40

MVA significantly increases costs compared to transformers with capacities less than 40 MVA. With a traffic capacity of 64,000 p/h/d, when the supply radius increases, the minimum required capacity of traction transformer substations becomes excessively large, even exceeding those of high-speed railway substations. Overloading the 25,000 V AC system is an unacceptable scenario for underground trains since the operating conditions of such transformers should not exceed a 50% overload for 15 min and a 100% overload for 5 min (according to EN 50329, IEC 60076-5, 60076-7, 60076-10 standards). Additionally, using high voltage requires larger safety clearances, more expensive high-voltage equipment, more complex maintenance and operation, and higher infrastructure construction costs. Specifically, there are currently no voltage operation standards and design guidelines for using 25,000 V AC / 50 Hz in subway systems. However, despite these disadvantages, the 25,000 V AC system also has notable advantages, particularly when it comes to requiring fewer traction substation stations than the 1,500 V DC system. This is especially advantageous for longer lines with an average distance of around 40 km per traction power substation when the line's capacity is below 50,000 p/h/d, and greater capacity with more complex system structures.

V. CONCLUSION

The current article presents the results of a study on new power supply sources for subway trains. The research examines various contrasting scenarios of load cases, ranging from incremental power demand to the maximum corresponding to the 1,500 V DC operating voltage. It also explores multiple options for power distribution structures, aiming to highlight the advantages and disadvantages of power source choices.

The research results indicate that the power consumption of the load and supply requirements in the 25,000 V AC / 50 Hz system are constrained by factors such as line length, segment length, and transformer capacity.

Through the power aspect of the research findings, it becomes evident that the selection of a sustainable power source is critical for making informed choices. Choosing the wrong power supply system can have negative implications to the urban railway systems. Other issues resulting from the influence of the 25,000 V AC / 50 Hz system will be addressed in future studies.

Finally, the results in this study are a reliable basis for comparing investment costs for 1,500V DC or 25,000 V AC systems throughout their life cycle.

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Transient Electromagnetic Fields Calculation around Transmission Lines using FDTD

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ABSTRACT

For proper design of transmission and distribution insulation systems, it is necessary to fully clarify the characteristics of lightning phenomena. In this study, two typical power transmission lines, 500 and 220 kV, were modeled to compute the lightning electromagnetic fields around the transmission lines. The lightning electromagnetic fields around the different power lines were calculated using the Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) method with Maxwell's equations. Two selected zones were used to capture electromagnetic fields during lightning strikes. The first zone was around the insulators and the second was at the ground level below the power line at 1 m above ground and the power line Right Of Way (ROW). The correlation between the induced magnetic and electric fields was verified in the free space inside the two selected zones. The induced electromagnetic fields were evaluated at different positions of each power line phase. The results obtained showed that while lightning strikes the conductor, the waveforms of the electromagnetic field obtained at the selected monitoring points were the same as the waveform of the lightning current. The amplitude of the electromagnetic field intensities exhibited a stable linear relationship with the lightning currents as the intrinsic impedance of the free air. This study was mainly concerned with transient electromagnetic fields that could appear inside high-voltage substations to clarify the electromagnetic exposure levels around high-voltage transmission lines.

Keywords-transient electromagnetic fields; FDTD; transmission lines

I. INTRODUCTION

Characteristics of electric and magnetic fields produced by lightning discharges are the core of recent studies worldwide, as the lightning phenomenon is still full of mystery parameters that should be adequately addressed [1]. Lightning strikes to overhead power transmission lines are the main accidental reason for service outages or insulation damage. Recently, lightning strikes have produced overimposed electromagnetic waves on overhead power transmission lines. Subsequently, these electromagnetic waves have probable potential and direct influences on the insulation level design process [2-3]. The effects of the striking object presence on the radiated electric and magnetic fields are essentially dependent on its height and shape as well as on the distance from the observation points [4-6]. The lightning current waveform is a microsecond-scale waveform that is probably formed in the shape of downward negative lightning. Meanwhile, it is of the order of millisecond-scale waveform for subsequent strokes [7]. In the absence of a structure with a high height, most of the positive lightning is initiated by a positively charged downward leader. The highest directly measured current for positive lightning with a charge transfer of 100C is approximately 320 kA [8]. The measured current parameters of the positive and negative first strokes are considered in common weighted statistics. The damages caused by lightning are not significantly dependent on the direction of the current flow [9-10].

Lightning strikes have been observed for about three decades over the Canadian National Tower to simultaneously capture the lightning parameters and return-stroke current derivative at about 475 m above ground, using a Rogowski coil and broadband active sensors. In [11], a good linear correlation between the magnetic field wave and the current was detected. For modeling electromagnetic return-stroke, Maxwell's equations are solved to yield the distribution of current along the lightning channel using numerical techniques, such as the Method Of Moments (MOM) or the finite-difference method [12-15]. These approaches are the Cooray formula, exact evaluation of the field equation numerically, and numerical solution of Maxwell's equation using Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD). The exact numerical solution and the FDTD are virtually identical. It has also been shown that the Cooray formula has good accuracy for underground fields, especially for their early time response. This study investigated the 3-D FDTD for solving Maxwell's equations to calculate lightning magnetic and electric fields around two typical 500 and 220 kV overhead transmission lines. Moreover, the field equation was solved with an exact solution analytically to verify the convergence of the two methods. To represent lightning electromagnetic fields, many Matlab M-Script files were developed based on three-dimensional field calculation techniques using FDTD. Electromagnetic fields were calculated at different points around the simulated towers and at the Right Of Way (ROW) of each line. The lightning current

was simulated based on the sum of the two Heidler's functions and its derivative to evaluate its suitability to simulate the lightning return-stroke current. The lightning magnetic and electric fields at the selected points around the towers were calculated. The simulation was developed using MATLAB M-scripts files, and the resulting 3D figures were developed using Mesh-3D.

II. TRANSMISSION LINES AND LIGHTNING CURRENT SIMULATION

A. System Configuration

Two power lines of 500 and 220 kV were simulated to calculate the lightning electromagnetic fields. The power line conductors of each phase were simulated as a series of connected current segments to closely fit the geometry of the catenary shape based on the Biot-Savart law in three dimensions and using FDTD [16-17]. Two different positions were selected to calculate the lightning electromagnetic fields at 1, 4, and 7 m from the ground and at 1 m from the power line conductors. Moreover, the electromagnetic fields were calculated over the entire area underneath the power line along two different directions, lateral and longitudinal. Figure 1 shows the main configurations of the two simulated lines. Lightning was assumed to strike the power line conductors of each line and the ground conductors to demonstrate their effects.

Fig. 1. Modeled 500 kV and 220 kV towers with ground conductors.

B. Lightning Current Simulation

For the developed charges, cloud to ground or ground to cloud with different polarities, there are four different lightning strikes, depending on the cloud polarity to the ground, "positive or negative cloud" to "negative or positive" ground. Recent studies on lightning current simulation for the first and subsequent return strokes tackled the more appropriate analytical expression of the sum of the so-called Heidler's functions [18-19].

$$i(0, t) = \left(\frac{I_{01}}{\eta_1} \left(\frac{t}{\tau_{11}} \right)^n \exp \left(-\frac{t}{\tau_{12}} \right) \right) + \left(\frac{I_{02}}{\eta_2} \left(\frac{t}{\tau_{21}} \right)^n \exp \left(-\frac{t}{\tau_{22}} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\eta = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\tau_{i1}}{\tau_{i2}} \right) \left(n \left(\frac{\tau_{i2}}{\tau_{i1}} \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right] \quad (2)$$

where I_{0i} is the amplitude parameter of the front current, I_{02} is the amplitude parameter of the decay current, t_{i1} is the front time constant ($i = 1, 2$), τ_{i2} is the decay time constant ($i = 1, 2$), η is the amplitude correction factor, and n is the exponent (2,...,10). Assuming the highest protection level [20], Table I gives the parameters of the simulated double-exponential lightning currents.

TABLE I. MAIN PARAMETERS OF THE SIMULATED LIGHTNING CURRENTS

Simulated stroke	I (kA)	t_f (μ S)	t_d (μ S)	τ_1 (μ S)	τ_2 (μ S)	η
Positive first	200	10	350	470.1	4064	0.951
Negative first	100	1	200	284.3	373.9	0.990
Negative subs.	50	0.25	100	143.1	92.4	0.995

III. LIGHTNING ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELDS CALCULATION

A. Using Exact Field Equations (analytically)

Two simultaneous steps must be taken to evaluate the lightning electromagnetic fields. The first step is to calculate the currents on the conductors due to lightning. The second step is to calculate the radiated electromagnetic fields around the conductors due to the traveling current waveform. The lightning transient electromagnetic fields can be evaluated numerically or analytically by assuming the line or conductor to be a cylinder with a very small radius for the wavelength [21]. This is because the effective reflection is usually proportional to the target electrical size coupled with the frequency. Frequency should be in a microwave range greater than 100 MHz to be considered an effective reflection. Figure 2 shows a line segment of length L along the z direction from the origin and $P(x, y, z)$ is an arbitrary point in space around the conductor [22]. The electromagnetic field potential vector $\vec{A}_z(t)$ for a filament along the z -axis is presented while the X and Y components of the potential vector can be neglected [17]. The z component $A_z(t)$ created by current $i(\xi, t)$ flowing in the line at the point P can be expressed as:

$$A_z(t) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \int_0^L i(\xi, t - R(\xi)/c) / R(\xi) d\xi \quad (3)$$

$$i(\xi, t - \frac{R(\xi)}{c}) = i_g(t - \frac{\xi + R(\xi)}{c}) + i_f(t - \frac{-\xi + R(\xi)}{c}) \quad (4)$$

where ξ is the arbitrary point on the conductors, c is the speed of the light in free space (3×10^8 m/s), i_g is the current wave traveling in the forward direction, and i_f is the current wave traveling in the backward direction.

Fig. 2. Simple presentation of the current segment.

The magnetic field can be evaluated by:

$$H_x(t) = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \frac{\partial A_z(t)}{\partial y}; H_y(t) = -\frac{1}{\mu_0} \frac{\partial A_z(t)}{\partial x}; H_z(t) = 0 \quad (5)$$

After determining the transient magnetic field, the transient electric field $\vec{E}(t)$ is calculated by integrating the curl of $\vec{H}(t)$ to get the three components of the electric field as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E_x(t) &= \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \int_0^t \frac{\partial H_y(t)}{\partial z} dt \\ E_y(t) &= \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \int_0^t \frac{\partial H_x(t)}{\partial z} dt \\ E_z(t) &= \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \int_0^t \left[\frac{\partial H_y(t)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial H_x(t)}{\partial y} \right] dt \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

B. Using the FDTD Method

Maxwell's equations for driving sources and lossy dielectric materials are presented in (7) and (8). Expanding these two main equations over the Yee cell in space with the time domain [22-24] yields the main relations of electromagnetic fields in both the space and the time domains.

$$\frac{\partial \vec{H}}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\mu} \nabla \times \vec{E} - \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \vec{H} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} + \frac{\sigma}{\epsilon} \vec{E} = \frac{1}{\epsilon} \nabla \times \vec{H} \quad (8)$$

Expanding E and H over the Yee cell in the space and time domains yields six subequations. These six equations present the main standard form of the FDTD algorithm used to monitor and capture the effects of the distribution of both magnetic and electric fields and their duality effects.

IV. LIGHTNING ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD RESULTS

A. For Normal Conditions

Table II shows the maximum lightning electromagnetic fields at different points below 500 and 220 kV, with the configurations shown in Figure 1, for normal operation with each power line loaded with 1 kA. The calculation is performed analytically and numerically to validate the accuracy of the FDTD algorithm. The percentage error was found to be less than 1% for 500 kV and less than 2% for 220 kV power lines. The maximum induced magnetic and electric fields were approximately 222 A/m and 83 kV/m at point No. 4 in the 500 kV power line under normal operation. The maximum induced magnetic and electric field values were approximately 191 A/m and 72 kV/m at point No. 4 in the 220 kV power line under

normal operation. Figure 3 presents the electromagnetic field profiles of 220 kV power lines for normal operation at 1 m above ground through an area between the mid-span of two subsequent line spans of one complete span with the tower positioned in the center of the electromagnetic field profiles. For the 500 kV power line, the maximum magnetic and electric field values were approximately 17 A/m and 10 kV/m at the mid-span position. Meanwhile, for the 220 kV power line, the maximum magnetic and electric field values were approximately 23 A/m and 13 kV/m at the mid-span position.

TABLE II. MAXIMUM INDUCED ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD FOR NORMAL OPERATION OF 500 AND 220 KV LINES

500 kV	Magnetic field (A/m)			Electric field (kV/m)		
	Analytically	Numerically	% error	Analytically	Numerically	% error
P1	7.216	7.232	0.22	2.72	2.73	0.37
P2	8.968	8.992	0.27	3.37	3.39	0.59
P3	11.45	11.48	0.21	4.31	4.33	0.46
P4	222.4	222.8	0.18	83.91	83.97	0.072
P5	77.12	77.52	0.52	29.18	29.21	0.1
P6	51.76	51.79	0.05	19.49	19.52	0.15
220 kV	Magnetic field (A/m)			Electric field (kV/m)		
	Analytically	Numerically	% error	Analytically	Numerically	% error
P1	11.92	12.08	1.32	4.51	4.54	0.66
P2	13.86	13.87	0.12	5.21	5.23	0.38
P3	16.89	16.93	0.24	6.34	6.38	0.63
P4	191.4	191.5	0.09	72.1	72.18	0.11
P5	64.72	64.89	0.27	24.36	24.45	0.37
P6	40.67	40.69	0.06	15.31	15.34	0.20

Fig. 3. Magnetic and electric field profiles around the 220 kV power transmission lines under normal conditions.

B. For Lightning Conditions

It was assumed that lightning strikes phase C of a 500 kV power line and phase C (circuit C2) of a 220 kV power line with a peak lightning current of 100 kA. Table III shows the maximum induced electromagnetic field values at the monitoring points under 500 and 220 kV. For 500 kV, the

maximum induced magnetic and electric field values were approximately 22.4 kA/m and 8.45 MV/m at the closest point to the striking point (P4). For 220 kV, the maximum induced magnetic and electric field values were approximately 22 kA/m and 8.3 MV/m at the closest point to the striking point (P4). Figure 4 illustrates the time-varying lightning electromagnetic field in the 500 kV power line at 1 m above ground during lightning strikes. Electromagnetic field profiles are presented along the lateral direction (x-direction) with a simulation time of 500 μs. The lightning electromagnetic fields have profiles similar to the waveforms of the lightning currents. Figure 4 also shows the electromagnetic field profiles at 1 m above ground for 500 μs with a peak striking current of 100 kA for the 500 kV power line. For 500 kV electromagnetic field profiles, the maximum induced magnetic and electric field values were approximately 1 kA/m and 376 kV/m. For 220 kV, the maximum induced magnetic and electric field values were approximately 615 A/m and 230 kV/m, respectively. A capture zone was selected to monitor the electromagnetic field profiles around the insulator surfaces during lightning. This zone was extended along an area of 10-16 m laterally and 18-26 m vertically for 500 kV. For 220 kV, the selected zone was extended along an area of 6-10 m laterally and 33-37 m vertically.

TABLE III. MAXIMUM ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD VALUES UNDER LIGHTNING FOR 500 AND 220 KV POWER LINES

Points	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
	500 kV	(A/m) 1026	1201	1446	22430	6498
	(kV/m) 386	452	544	8451	2448	1257
220 kV	(A/m) 612	664	735	22027	6499	3334
	(kV/m) 227	250	277	8299	2449	1256

Fig. 4. Lightning electromagnetic field profiles under the 500 kV power transmission lines at 1 m above ground.

Figure 5 presents the magnetic and electric fields induced around the insulators of the 220 kV line with a 100 kA striking current. For the 220 kV power line, the maximum induced magnetic and electric field values were approximately 59 kA/m

and 36 MV/m, respectively. For the 500 kV power line, the maximum induced magnetic and electric field values were approximately 57.3 kA/m and 34 MV/m. Table IV shows the induced electromagnetic field values for lightning striking in different phases and ground conductors for both 500 and 220 kV power transmission lines in front of the tower position and in front of the mid-span at 1 m above ground.

Fig. 5. Lightning field profiles around the insulator of the 220 kV power line.

TABLE IV. LIGHTNING-INDUCED ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD VALUES FOR 500 AND 220 KV POWER LINES FOR DIFFERENT STRIKING POINTS

Lightning electromagnetic fields at ROW for 500 kV power line				
Striking point	In front of the tower		In front of the mid-span	
	(A/m)	(kV/m)	(A/m)	(kV/m)
Phase A	604.9	227.9	688.1	259.2
Phase B	463.6	174.7	486.2	183.2
Phase C	882.7	332.6	1222.2	460.5
G1	644.6	242.8	1006.1	379.1
G2	464.0	174.8	539.6	203.3
Lightning electromagnetic fields at ROW for 220 kV power line				
Striking point	In front of the tower		In front of the mid-span	
	(A/m)	(kV/m)	(A/m)	(kV/m)
Phase A1	634.4	239.03	676.7	254.9
Phase A2	1140.2	429.6	1557.8	586.9
Phase B1	532.97	200.83	575.52	216.85
Phase B2	828.6	312.2	1101.23	414.9
Phase C1	473.8	178.5	518.5	195.4
Phase C2	570.01	214.8	678.2	255.5
G. cond.	453.8	170.9	506.76	190.9

Figure 6 presents the induced current at different positions of the phases and the two ground conductors for the striking position of phase C of 500 kV. The maximum value of the striking current is -100 kA and $tr/tt = 1/200 \mu s$. The peak values of the current induced at different positions depend mainly on the relative distances between the striking point and the monitoring points. The maximum value of the induced current was approximately 23 kA on the ground conductor G1, while for Phase A, the maximum value of the induced current was approximately 20 kA. The results obtained were compared with [17] and found to be highly consistent.

Fig. 6. Lightning current and induced currents on different phases and ground conductors for 500 kV power transmission lines.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained indicate that FDTD can be used to model and simulate lightning electromagnetic fields around 500 and 220 kV power transmission lines. Comparing the results obtained from the FDTD model and analytical solutions shows a small deviation, less than 2%. The simulation results showed that the lightning electromagnetic field at the selected points depends mainly on the relative position of the striking point. The results of lightning electromagnetic fields could be used for electromagnetic compatibility studies and insulation coordination, and in the early design stage of power transmission lines. Comparison of these results with previous studies and standards exhibited great convenience with a minor deviation. The lightning electromagnetic fields at the ROW of the two lines were evaluated at different positions to guide environmental studies. The maximum values of the lightning electromagnetic fields around the insulator were 57.4 kA/m and 35 MV/m. These values depend on the peak value of the striking lightning currents. The results of this study can be helpful to researchers in this field to withstand the exposure of electromagnetic fields around transmission lines.

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Marshall Asphalt Mix and Superior Performance Asphalt Mix in Oman: A Comparative Study

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ABSTRACT

The mix design procedure used in Superior Performance Asphalt Pavements (Super-pave) was created by the Strategic Highway Research Program (SHRP) in response to the limitations and empirical approach of Marshall methodology. This study aims to compare the Marshall asphalt mixture design method with the Super-pave asphalt mixture design procedures. Locally available aggregates commonly used in asphalt concrete mixtures in Oman were used. The asphalt mixtures were made with aggregate and asphalt-binder with a penetration grade of 60/70 and PG 64-10. Samples from two mixes were made accordingly. Volumetric properties analysis, flow, Marshall stability, and loss of Marshall stability tests were carried out. According to the study findings, the optimum asphalt composition was 4.5% when utilizing the Marshall methodology and 5.5% when using the Super-pave approach. Furthermore, the Super-pave specimens showed less loss of Marshall stability (22.22%) than the Marshall specimen (30.09%).

Keywords-asphalt mix; Super-pave method; Marshall method; volumetric properties; asphalt performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The design of asphalt mixes for tropical climates with high temperatures, especially for roads that are projected to handle huge truck loads and higher design traffic volumes much greater than 1 million Equivalent Single Axle Loads (ESALs) is a challenging task. The primary concern when designing such an asphalt mix is making sure the mix is resistant to plastic deformation [1]. The current level of practice for pavement design is mostly based on empirical approaches in various nations of the Gulf Cooperative Council (GCC). Although, various institutions have relied on the Superior AASHTO 1993 pavement design guide [2].

In Oman, the Marshall mix design technique is mostly utilized to create asphalt concrete mixes that meet the international requirements. However, due to the harsh environmental conditions and heavy traffic loads, several of these roads exhibit serious distress after only a short time in use [3], leading to increased maintenance costs. According to [4], tropical climatic conditions are the primary factor that affects the materials used on roads. In order to improve the physical properties of Marshall asphalt mixtures at moderate to high temperatures, authors in [5] examined the impacts of utilizing improved bitumen binders as well as additives taking into account flexible asphalt mixtures of AC 40/60 only. However,

the continued usage of the Marshall process for asphalt mixtures is another factor that is contributing to early distresses. Since the Marshall mix technique is empirical, it has a limited ability to accurately predict how changes in environmental and loading variables, as well as material qualities and kinds, will affect the performance of the pavement. It is unable to recognize mixtures that are prone to shear. The Marshall mix method's impact compaction method does not accurately represent the densification that occurs in an actual pavement during traffic as presented in [6]. Due to such constraints, SHRP created the Super-pave design procedure to address the challenges of the Marshall process. SHRP focused on creating performance-based standards for asphalt binders and mixes [6, 7], with the aim of developing design mixtures that consist of a performance-based asphalt binder requirement and enhanced performance-based tests.

Although researchers have used the Super-pave technology in different geographical locations [8-10], given the climatic and environmental conditions, the effectiveness of Super-pave design has not been fully ascertained in the Oman region. The most frequent bitumen grade utilized in asphalt mixtures in this region is the asphalt binder 60/70 penetration grade for Marshall mixtures [11]. However, the Super-pave Performance Grading (PG) system appropriately takes into account the

pavement conditions as it links the measured physical qualities of asphalt binders with field performance [12, 13]. Although other elements, such as the geographic location, also play a significant influence, air temperature has the greatest impact on pavement temperature. The Super-pave PG grading system has two temperature limits. For instance, asphalt with a PG 64-10 can perform satisfactorily in the temperature range of 64 °C-10 °C [14]. Authors in [15] created models for four high-temperature grades: PG 52, 58, 64, and 70, while low temperatures were limited to PG-10 and PG-16. However, the recommendation from [11] included asphalt binder of PG 64-10 for Oman with 95% dependability. The environmental factors affect the engineering properties [9, 13, 14, 16, 17].

This paper reports the results of an experimental investigation regarding the performance of asphalt mixtures using asphalt binder with 60/70 penetration grade and PG 64-10. The Marshall process for secondary compaction and plastic deformation capability was compared with the Super-pave mix design process. Various factors influencing the mix design procedures were studied.

II. MARSHALL MIX DESIGN VS SUPERIOR PERFORMING ASHALT PAVEMENT

Asphalt mix is a composite material that is extensively used in road building. It is also known as asphalt concrete or merely asphalt. A composite is composed of elements that can enhance the physical and chemical properties of the separate elements [18]. Asphalt is made up of aggregates (crushed stone, gravel, and sand) and asphalt binder (bitumen). The aggregates give the mixture strength and stability, while the asphalt binder keeps the aggregates together and provides flexibility.

In tropical regions, Marshall mix design is the most widely employed method [3, 10]. However, this approach has several limitations, including the fact that it is an ineffective method for identifying mixes that are susceptible to plastic deformations and voids following extensive compaction that does not match field compaction [19]. The conventional Marshall metric, does not account for the in air-voids that asphalt mixes encounter during the second and third compactions phases. The initial Marshall mix design process should be extended by incorporating a further compaction effort to replicate the consolidated condition of asphalt near the end of its usable life [20]. Authors in [21] studied how variations from the Job Mix Formula (JMF) within the aggregate gradients of Marshall asphalt mixes affected the overall performance of the combinations. On the other hand, the SHRP led to the development of superior performing asphalt pavements. The initiative lasted from 1987 to 1993, followed by a period of execution. The objective of the initiative was the improvement of the highway system's efficacy, longevity and reliability. It tends to generate new approaches that consider load of traffic and environmental issues. Consequently, techniques for evaluating asphalt binders and analyzing mixtures were developed [22]. A novel method of specifying, testing, and designing asphalt materials is the Super-pave. It is an improved approach for identifying asphalt pavement constituents, developing and analyzing asphalt mixtures, and forecasting asphalt pavement performance. Super-pave has shown the potential of being very suitable for

tropical climate regions and has been recommended for use in both developing and developed nations [23].

The size and weight of the tested sample are the first significant ways that the Marshall asphalt mix differs from the Super-pave mix. Marshall mix has a diameter of around 102 mm, a height of approximately 64 mm, and a weight of approximately 1200 g. Super-pave, on the other hand, weighs about 4700g and has a diameter of 150 mm with a height of roughly 115 mm. In order to determine the ideal binder content, Super-pave mix's binder content is acquired using the maximum nominal sieve [22]. In contrast, the amount of asphalt in Marshall mix is determined through a trial-and-error process. Thirdly, the manner of compacting in the Marshall method and the super-pave method is different. In the Marshall method, the mix is compacted using a Marshall mix hammer while gyratory machine is used in Super-pave. Also, the Super-pave mix considers heavy traffic loads, unlike the Marshall mix. Figures 1 and 2 show the Marshall test preparation and Marshall compaction. Furthermore, the Marshall approach employs a subpar technique to discover mixes prone to permanent deformation [3, 9]. It is reported that the Super-pave-designed mixtures have a lesser possibility for rutting and a lower life cycle cost [24]. This study investigates how well the Super-pave design approach, with the use of local materials, performs when compared to Marshall design under conditions of strong traffic loading and prevalent temperatures.

Fig. 1. Marshall test preparation.

Fig. 2. Marshall compaction.

III. STABILITY IN PAVEMENT DESIGN

Stability in an asphalt concrete pavement is the ability to withstand deformation when been subject to traffic loads under different environmental conditions. As a condition, when subjected to repeated loads, a stable pavement keeps its shape and smoothness. According to [19], as stability rises, density

also rises whereas air spaces decline. By increasing the number of gyrations, the gyratory compactor's effort is increased as volume of traffic rise. This increase in the gyratory efforts leads to increase in stability.

Thus, it is essential to understand stability and its role in the overall performance of asphalt concrete pavement. Stability analysis and specifications are detailed in the relevant codes of practice. This phenomenon is discussed in the subsequent sections.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The Marshall mix design specifications detailed in ASTM [20] and that of Super-pave mix design based on AASHTO guidelines were followed, based on the utilization of regional Oman aggregates and binders for asphalt. In the next subsections, the techniques are described.

A. Material Selection

Materials that complied with the requirements and were frequently used in road construction in Oman were chosen from local sources. Crushed limestone was employed the coarse aggregates, while natural, rounded silica sand in accordance with [25] was used as fine aggregates. Using lime-filler and aggregates of sizes 19 mm were acquired within the

Province of Oman as well as bituminous grade of 60/70, a thorough laboratory investigation was conducted and the overall aggregate gradation is given in Figure 3. The aggregates and the asphalt binder utilized to create the asphalt mixtures that had penetration performance grade of PG 64-10. To achieve the study objectives, the asphalt mixtures were prepared using both Super-pave and Marshall design approaches.

Fig. 3. Overall aggregate gradation. TP: Total Passing, JMF: Job Mix Formula, SP: Specification, UL: Upper Limit, and LL: Lower Limit.

TABLE I. MARSHALL JOB MIX

Sieve (mm)	Job Mix Formula		Fraction mass (g)	Cumulative fraction mass (g)	Bitumen mass (g)				
	Total passing (%)	Retained (%)			3.0%	3.5%	4.0%	4.5%	5.0%
25.0	100	0	0	0	37.1	43.5	50.0	56.5	63.2
19.0	97	3	36	36					
9.50	69	28	336	372					
4.75	50	19	228	600					
2.36	32	18	216	816					
1.18	22	10	120	936					
0.60	16	6	72	1008					
0.30	11	5	60	1068					
0.15	8	3	36	1104					
0.075	4	4	48	1152					
(-) 0.075			48	1200					
Total batch mass (g)					1237.1	1243.5	1250.0	1256.5	1263.2

1) Marshall Mix Design

The Marshall mix design procedure was carried out in accordance with ASTM specifications. In a 100 mm diameter cylindrical mold, the samples were subjected to 75 blows on each side. Five samples with bitumen content were prepared in accordance with Oman design, namely 3%, 3.5%, 4%, 4.5%, and 5%. Following that, Marshall stability and flow tests were performed to determine the optimum bitumen content that proved to be an asphalt mix with 4% air-voids. In this investigation, the optimal asphalt concentration was 4.50% of the overall mass of the mix. At the obtained optimal content, the values of Marshall-stability, flows, and voids in asphalt and in aggregate minerals were determined. Aggregate preparation was done according to the job mix. The aggregate weight used for Marshall pavement and for the Super-pave was 1200 g and 4700 g, respectively. Table I shows Marshall JBF.

2) Super-pave Mix Design Method

The mix was prepared in accordance with [22]. Super-pave uses volumetric analysis for the mix design in the testing and

analysis processes. The optimal asphalt content for the selected structure is chosen after selecting a design aggregate structure. The nominal maximum size of aggregates gave the initial bitumen content. The three more bitumen content values were achieved in the order of +0.5, -0.5, and +1. In this study, the nominal maximum size of aggregates was 19 mm, and the bitumen percentage was 4%, 4.5%, 5% and 5.5%. The Super-pave job mix is shown in Table II.

Both mean design high temperatures of the region and the design ESALs affected how many gyrations were applied. For Oman, a traffic frequency between ten and thirty millions ESALs was selected to simulate moderate traffic, which corresponds to the traffic situation of the majority of the region's road network, with summertime temperatures reaching 50 °C [26]. The maximum required number of gyrations, N is 220. So, all sample preparations of the Super-pave mix trials utilized in the research used 160 gyrations.

The mixture was properly prepared, a filter paper was placed in the super-pave mold, the asphalt was applied in three

layers, and the surface was flattened. The super-pave mold was loaded into the Gyratory compacting machine. Figures 4 and 5 show the Super-pave mold preparation and the gyration

compaction, respectively. Systematic calculations for the Super-pave design based on design criteria were adopted [22].

TABLE II. SUPER-PAVE JOB MIX

Sieve (mm)	Job Mix Formula		Fraction mass (g)	Cumulative fraction mass (g)	Bitumen mass (g)			
	Total passing (%)	Retained (%)			4.0%	4.5%	5.0%	5.5%
25	100	0	0	0	195.8	221.5	247.4	273.5
19	97	3	141	141				
9.5	69	28	1316	1457				
4.75	50	19	893	2350				
2.36	32	18	846	3196				
1.18	22	10	470	3666				
0.6	16	6	282	3948				
0.3	11	5	235	4183				
0.15	8	3	141	4324				
0.075	4	4	188	4512				
(-) 0.075			188	4700				
Total batch mass (g)					4895.8	4921.5	4947.4	4973.5

Fig. 4. Super-pave mold preparation.

Fig. 5. Gyratory compaction.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance Evaluation

A comparison of the results of the Marshall and Super-pave mix design techniques was performed in order to evaluate their effectiveness. The specimens were prepared following the optimum mix design asphalt contents as obtained, AC 4.5% (Marshall) and AC 5.5% (Super-pave), utilizing the gradation properties of the local recommendations (see Figure 3). The test specimens were compacted utilizing a gyratory compactor for the Super-pave mixes and a Marshall’s 75-blow compactor for the Marshall mixes in order to reach the 4% air void target. Marshall stability, loss of Marshall stability, and volumetric properties were studied.

1) Marshall Stabilities / Loss of Marshall stability

Following the ASTM D 6927 [27] procedure, 6 specimens from each individual mix were prepared and placed in a 60 °C

water bath for 30 min before 3 of them were tested for Marshall stability. After 24 hr, the remaining 3 specimens were also examined. Figure 6 demonstrates the outcomes for the tested specimens. The result shows that Super-pave bath specimens have higher Marshall stability than the Marshall specimens, for both initial and wet stability values. Furthermore, the Super-pave specimens showed less loss of Marshall stability (22.22%) than the Marshall specimens (30.09%), which is in agreement with the findings in [9]. The Super-pave specimens outperformed the Marshall specimens due to their improved aggregate structure and their lower dust proportion.

Fig. 6. Stability test results. IMS: Initial Marshall Stability, WMS: Wet Marshall Stability, ISSP: Initial Stability Super-pave, WSSP: Wet Stability Super-pave.

2) Volumetric Property Analysis

Figures 7-9 show the results of the volumetric properties of the tested specimens. They demonstrate the variations in the Voids in Mineral Aggregates (VMA), Voids Filled with Asphalt (VFA), and Voids in Total Mix (VTM) at 4% air void for the optimum asphalt content of both mixes. It is observed from Figure 7 that VFA% for Marshall is 70% and 71% for Super-pave which is within the 65–78% criterion [6]. In Figure 8, it is observed that VMA% for Marshall and Super-pave is 13.2% and 14.0%, respectively. Again, these values are satisfactory. Figure 9 shows that the VTM% for both Marshall and Super-pave is 4%. This finding is consistent with the observation in [28] that aggregate gradation has a significant

impact on pavement characteristics. From these findings, it can be concluded that Super-pave has higher volumetric properties than Marshall in hot environment and high-traffic conditions.

design for pavements in Oman can endure stresses due to harsh weather and heavy traffic more efficiently.

Fig. 7. VFA% for Marshall and Super-pave mixes.

Fig. 8. VMA% for Marshall and Super-pave mixes.

Fig. 9. VTM% for Marshall and Super-pave mixes.

1) Density, Flow, and Dust Proportion

In Table III, the values of the selected Marshall properties are shown. At optimum asphalt content of 4.5%, the bulk density G_{mm} is 2.41 g/cm^3 and the Flow is 4 mm. Table IV shows the selected Super-pave properties.

At optimum asphalt content of 5.5%, $D_{p_{est}}$ is 0.77 which is within the required range of 0.6 – 1.2. Bulk density at optimum asphalt content = $G_{mm} \times 96\% = 2.530 \times 96\% = 2.428$. Therefore, the findings show that Super-pave design has higher density (2.4282 g/cm^3) than the Marshall mix design. This superior performance shows that the use of Super-pave mix

TABLE III. MARSHALL SELECTED PROPERTIES

AC%	AC	G_{mm}	G_{mb}	Flow	G_{sb}
3	0.03	2.53	2.342	2.1	2.668
3.5	0.035	2.53	2.377	2.7	2.668
4	0.04	2.53	2.391	3.2	2.668
4.5	0.045	2.53	2.412	4	2.668
5	0.05	2.53	2.433	4.9	2.668

AC: Asphalt Content, G_{sb} : aggregate specific gravity, G_{mb} : average bulk specific gravity

TABLE IV. SUPER-PAVE SELECTED PROPERTIES

AC%	% G_{mm} at ND	% G_{mm} at N_{in}	$D_{p_{est}}$
4	94.2	84.6	0.90
4.5	94.8	84.5	0.85
5	95.4	84.7	0.81
5.5	96.0	86.6	0.77

% G_{mm} at N_{in} : %maximum theoretical density, N_i : initial number of gyrations, $D_{p_{est}}$: estimated dust proportion.

VI. CONCLUSION

The performance of the Super-pave and the traditional Marshall approaches under high-traffic loading, considering locally sourced materials and typical weather conditions, were investigated in this study. The reached conclusions include the following:

- The optimum percentages by weight of asphalt constituent of the Super-pave and Marshall mixes were determined as 5.5% and 4.5%. As a result, Super-pave mix design yields higher binder content than Marshall in hot environment and high-traffic conditions.
- Volumetric properties, VMA, VFA, and VTM for Super-pave mixes were found to be 14%, 71%, and 4% respectively and 13%, 70 %, and 4% for the Marshall mixes. Again, Super-pave mixes reveal higher volumetric properties than Marshall mixes.
- The Super-pave specimens showed less loss of Marshall stability (22.22%) than the Marshall specimens (30.09%). This could be caused by the improved aggregate structure and the lower dust proportion of the Super-pave mixes.
- Super-pave and Marshall specimen densities were found to be 2.43 g/cm^3 and 2.41 g/cm^3 at optimal asphalt content. The relatively higher Super-pave density could be due to the involvement of the Super-pave gyration compactor.
- The Super-pave mixes outperformed the Marshall mixes. As a result, prioritizing the Super-pave design approach in Oman may resolve some of the problems associated with the recently built roads.

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Utilizing GANs for Credit Card Fraud Detection: A Comparison of Supervised Learning Algorithms

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ABSTRACT

The evolution and improvements in electronic commerce and communications around the world have stimulated credit card use. With the support of smartphone wallets, electronic payments have become the most popular payment method for personal and business use; however, the past few years have also seen a major increase in fraudulent transactions. Corporations and individuals experience very negative impacts from such fraud. Therefore, fraud detection systems have received a lot of attention recently from major financial institutions. This paper proposes a fraud detection approach that deals with small and imbalanced datasets using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for sample generation. Six machine-learning algorithms were applied to real-world data. The accuracy of all six algorithms was above 85% and the precision was above 95%. Five of the six algorithms had a recall score greater than 90%. Furthermore, the Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC), which measure performance at different thresholds, demonstrated scores greater than 0.90, except Naïve Bayes, which scored 0.81. The proposed approach outperformed the same algorithms in other studies.

Keywords-fraud detection; credit card fraud; generative adversarial network; supervised learning; naive bayes; decision tree; imbalance datasets

I. INTRODUCTION

During the recent years, there has been a substantial increase in financial frauds, primarily due to the technological changes and cybersecurity breaches. In 2022, such frauds impacted personal assets by 10% and organizations by 39% [1]. Financial institutions had \$28.58 billion in losses in credit card fraud worldwide in 2020, and this figure is expected to reach \$49.43 billion by 2030 [2]. The employment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques to monitor and detect fraudulent transactions can prevent an enormous amount of losses in the banking sector and increase the degree of trust customers have in financial institutions. Several studies have used Machine Learning (ML) to detect fraudulent transactions [3]. According to [4], 26% of credit card transactions were either attempted or actual fraud transactions. However, detecting fraudulent transactions is challenging for ML [5]. In [6], a comparison between ensemble learning and supervised algorithms was made in network traffic. In [7], a credit card fraud detection technique was presented, based on the Decision Tree (DT) algorithm.

The current study addressed one of the main issues in ML, namely the lack of sufficient data and unbalanced datasets. The use of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) was used to generate synthetic data from a real-world dataset. Following

the generation of the dataset, different ML techniques were applied: Logistic Regression (LR), DT, Random Forest (RF), Naïve Bayes (NB), extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), and Adaptive Boosting (Ada-Boost). This study aimed to investigate the fineness of employing various AI techniques to detect credit card anomalies and to examine the ability of GANs to balance unbalanced datasets. The main contributions of this study are:

- Proposing a solution for an imbalanced dataset in tabular data.
- Implementing GANs to generate synthetic data.
- Implementing 6 ML algorithms and evaluate their results.

II. RELATED WORKS

A method was proposed in [8] for the detection and assessment of the risk of credit card fraud. This method was based on an algorithm that can measure the relationships between variables and any related information to increase accuracy and decrease dimensionality. In [9], supervised and unsupervised credit card fraud detection methods were compared, showing huge performance restrictions when using supervised learning, with unsupervised learning performing better. In [10], a Financial Fraud Detection (FFD) model was introduced, based on ontology alert. The FFD model consisted

of 40 classes and subclasses and was capable of identifying transaction anomalies by initiating different alerts based on their severity levels. In [11], an LR algorithm was applied to detect credit card anomalies that occur during the purchase of movie tickets. In [12], supervised and unsupervised techniques were used to find suspicious behaviors in bookkeeping, using a real ledger dataset and applying data vectorization to solve sub-ledger account size irregularities and to improve performance. Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and DT techniques were used in [13] to detect credit card frauds, using a highly imbalanced real dataset, and the results showed that DT clearly outperformed SVMs. In [14], several ML techniques were evaluated to detect fraudulent transactions, including outlier detection and ensemble methods. The influence of feature selection on performance was measured using feature engineering and analysis. In [15], recent advances in ML and Deep Reinforcing Learning (DRL) were investigated to create a credit card fraud detection system, using a highly imbalanced dataset and resampling methods. In [16], nonlinear models were investigated, proposing credit card fraud detection methods that can be interpreted and those that are not tied in a particular way. These methods can be used simultaneously along any ML technique and provide the required tracing info linking inputs and outputs, thus avoiding reaching the black-box model. In [17], a Multiple Classifier System (MCS) was used on credit card fraud datasets, achieving accurate fraud identification by using the sequential decision combination technique. This study used two learning algorithms: NB and C4.5, showing great classification results on majority and minority class samples for C4.5 and NB, respectively. In [18], the efficiency of using multiple neural networks in conjunction with hybrid data resampling was demonstrated to detect credit card abnormalities, using an AdaBoost technique with long short-term memory as its base. The proposed approach outperformed other algorithms, such as SVM and DT, on a real credit card dataset. In [19], a credit card fraud detection system was tested, combining CatBoost and Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) as a base learner, on an IEEE-CIS dataset consisting of 590,540 instances. CatBoost was used to test whether users' overlapping prediction rates could improve. In [20], an experimental study was conducted on an imbalanced dataset, using classification algorithms such as C5.0, SVM, ANN, and NB. In this study, the problem of the imbalanced dataset was solved by balancing the classes using Random Oversampling (RO), which replicates the observations as long as the balance between classes is not reached. In [21], an intelligent mechanism for credit card fraud detection was used, which employed an optimized light gradient boosting machine (OLightGBM), which was tuned by integrating a Bayesian-based hyperparameter optimization. The experiment was carried out on two real-world datasets, reaching 98.40% accuracy. In [22], a DNN was used as a representation feature model, and fraud transactions were identified by mapping the actual features of transactions to deep representations. This study also presented an improved loss function that recognizes angles among features along with distances and, consequently, can fully supervise deep feature learning. This method was evaluated in two large credit card datasets [22]. Table I presents a summary of recent works, indicating inconsistencies and areas for improvement regarding the listed algorithms.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF RELATED WORKS

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Recall (%)	Year of publication	Reference
LR	94.51	97.36	2021	[15]
	36	71	2017	[23]
	99	69	2022	[3]
DT	88	91	2022	[24]
	99	74	2022	[3]
NB	97	82	2017	[23]
	99	14	2022	[3]
RF	99.99	99.98	2021	[15]
	92	86	2022	[24]
XGBoost	99.97	99.94	2021	[15]
	99	95	2022	[3]
	92	91	2022	[24]
Ada-boost	99	75	2021	[25]
	97	96	2021	[15]

III. METHOD

A. Generative Adversarial Network (GAN)

A GAN is an unsupervised deep learning model that was invented in 2014 and has received great attention since [26-27]. The word "generative" indicates that it is a model that can learn any distribution of data, mimicking the original distribution. It is called "adversarial" since 2 neural networks are trained in a combative setting. The final word, "network", indicates the use of a deep neural network as an AI training algorithm. A very common and major problem during modeling is having imbalanced datasets. GANs can be used to generate synthetic data that can provide a solution to this complexity, as in [28]. A GAN consists of combined neural networks that conflict with each other. The first model is called the generator, and the second is called the discriminator. The generator network collects and generates samples, while after training, the probability of the discriminator making mistakes increases. Figure 1 presents the GAN architecture. A GAN equation can be:

$$(G, D) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mu_{ref}} [\ln D(x)] + \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mu_z} [\ln (1 - D(G(z)))] \quad (1)$$

where G is the generative model to be trained on the training data x , and D is the discriminator that discriminates among the various classes of data. The discriminator uses a binary classification with sigmoid activation to determine whether the data are generated or received from an actual sample, given an output that ranges between 0 and 1. From (1), z adds a slight noise sample as an input to the generator, $\sim \mu_{ref}$ represents the distribution from the actual data, and $\sim \mu_z$ is the distribution from the generator.

Fig. 1. Generative adversarial network.

B. GANs for Tabular Data

Although GANs are effective in generating images and textual data, the use of GANs on tabular data raises numerous challenges:

- Data types can be numerical or categorical.
- GANs distribute image data over space. Tabular data can be non-Gaussian, and then the network will not be able to propagate gradient details.
- GAN generators do not recognize imbalanced categorical columns as a result of using samples generated from a standard multivariate distribution.

This study used the CTGAN model [29], which is based on the GAN method and solves the non-Gaussian challenge by applying mode-specific normalization. CTGAN also uses all existing features of the dataset.

C. Logistic Regression (LR)

LR is often used to solve classification and predictive problems. The most common LR model is the binary one, which predicts binary classes by calculating the link between independent and dependent variables using statistical estimation. Considering the result is a probability, the dependent variable is restrained between 1 and 0. LR is widely used in classification problems and is well known for its performance, efficiency, and simplicity. It has also been used in similar experiments [3, 12, 30-31]. The LR formula is:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ki} + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

where Y_i is the dependent variable, X_{1i} and X_{ki} are the independent variables, β_0 is the intercept, β_1 and β_k are the population coefficients, and ε_i is a random error.

D. Naïve Bayes (NB)

NB is an ML classifier based on Bayes' theorem. NB is a probabilistic algorithm that is widely adopted in different classification problems. NB assumes that all the features are independent from one another. The posterior probability $P(x|c)$ is given by:

$$P(x|c) = \frac{P(x|c)P(c)}{P(x)} \quad (3)$$

and indicates how frequently x occurs when c has already occurred.

E. Random Forest (RF)

RF is an ML classifier technique that is used to deal with classification and regression problems. Following forest initiation, RF is trained by the bagging method, which is an ensemble algorithm used to fit numerous models on multiple subsets of a training dataset and then merges all predictions. The equation for RF is given by:

$$Gini = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^c (p_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

where p represents the corresponding frequency of the observed class in the dataset, and c is the number of classes.

F. Decision Tree (DT)

DT can be used for both regression and classification problems. A DT consists of nodes and the first node is the root located on top of the tree. At each level of the tree, there is a condition that leads to a binary split of the existing node into subnodes. A decision will be made when a subnode, which is also called a leaf node, does not split anymore. Leaf nodes resemble a class label, while attributes are expressed on the nonleaf node of the tree. DT offers numerous advantages, including straightforward implementation, numerical and categorical data support, and providing instinctive knowledge expression. DT decisions are restricted to a binary output, affecting the performance the tree can handle.

G. Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

XGBoost is an open-source implementation gradient boost algorithm. The distinction of XGBoost is its ability to control overfitting behavior while gaining superior performance. XGBoost is recognized for its speed, dealing with one of the well-known gradient-boosted tree inefficiencies, achieved by taking care of probable loss for all the splits to produce a new branch. The objective function in XGBoost consists of the loss function and a regularized term:

$$\mathcal{L}(\phi) = \sum_i l(\hat{y}_i, y_i) + \Omega(\phi) \quad (5)$$

where ϕ represents the learned parameter set, l is used to calculate the distinction between \hat{y}_i and y_i , and Ω represents the regularization term.

H. Adaptive Boosting (Ada-boost)

Ada-boost is one of the first boosting methods. It operates by creating the model and having all data points equal with their weights, spreading greater weight to data points that are misclassified. This step gives greater importance to data points with higher weights. The Ada-boost equation is given by:

$$F_T(x) = \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x) \quad (6)$$

I. Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the classification methods was evaluated and tested using a confusion matrix. The first metric used was accuracy, where True Positive (TP) indicates all legitimate transactions that are predicted accurately, True Negative (TN) is the total fraudulent transactions predicted accurately as fraudulent, False Positive (FP) is the total legitimate transactions predicted mistakenly as fraudulent, and False Negative (FN) is the total fraudulent transactions predicted incorrectly as legitimate. The accuracy metric was used to calculate the ratio of legitimate transactions to the total number of transactions [31]:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (7)$$

The second metric was precision, which measures the ratio of accurately classified positives from all the positive predictions:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{(TP+FP)} \quad (8)$$

Equations (9) and (10) display the Recall and F-measure metric calculations.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{(TP+FN)} \tag{9}$$

$$F - measure = \frac{2*Precision*Recall}{Precision+Recall} \tag{10}$$

Matthews' Correlation Coefficient (MCC) was also used to measure the quality of the classifiers:

$$MCC = \frac{TP * TN - FP * FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}} \tag{11}$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Original Data

The dataset contains credit card transactions made by European cardholders during two days of October 2018 [25]. This dataset is imbalanced, with 284,809 legitimate and 492 fraudulent transactions. The data do not provide the original attributes for privacy concerns and were transformed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The result of that transformation is indicated by its attributes starting from V1 to V28. The data also include the amount of the transaction, the time separating each transaction, and a class label associating 0 to a fraudulent transaction and 1 to a legitimate one.

B. Synthetic Data

Several studies tried to fix the complexity of imbalanced datasets using Minority Oversampling (MOTE) [12, 22, 31-34]. The proposed approach used synthetic data generated using GAN. After generating the data, 6 ML algorithms were trained and applied.

C. Performance Evaluation and Confusion Metrics

Table II shows the metric evaluation of the six ML algorithms. Another way to evaluate the results is through a confusion matrix, which can be used for both binary and multiclass classifications. In the current state, which is binary classification, the confusion matrix generates a 2x2 table, consisting of TP, FP, TN, and FN.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
LR	96%	95%	91%
DT	96%	96%	92%
NB	85%	98%	64%
RF	97%	98%	92%
XGBoost	98%	98%	96%
Ada-boost	97%	97%	93%

Five models had more than 95% accuracy. The NB algorithm had the lowest accuracy (85%), a precision of 98%, and only 64% recall. Figure 2 indicates that NB classified 567 legitimate transactions as fraudulent. The LR model had 96% accuracy. Of the transactions detected by the LR model, 95% were truly relevant according to the precision score, and Figure 3 shows its confusion matrix. Figure 4 shows the confusion matrix of DT, which also had a high accuracy of 96%. Its precision score indicates that it relented only 4% of relevant instances, while recall shows that it predicted 8% of transactions as false negatives.

Fig. 2. Confusion matrix of NB.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix of LR.

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix of DT.

Figure 5 shows that RF classified 421 fraudulent transactions as legitimate and miscategorized 1944 legitimate transactions while having 97% accuracy. Based on recall, RF classified 8% of legitimate transactions as fraudulent. The XGBoost algorithm exhibited the highest percentage values of the six algorithms, predicting 98% of anomalies accurately. XGBoost scored 98% precision, revealing that the model classified only 2% of fraud transactions as legitimate. From the XGBoost confusion matrix shown in Figure 6, 1,015 legitimate transactions were classified as fraud, which is considered trivial compared to the NB model. When comparing the existing

results with Table II, there are major improvements, especially in NB. The explanation of the variations in the performance of NB regarding the other algorithms is its limitation in dealing with complicated tasks and its ineffectiveness on numerical data. Ada-Boost was second in scores. The accuracy score showed that the model misclassified 3% of all transactions. Figure 7 shows the confusion matrix of Ada-Boost.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix of RF.

Fig. 6. Confusion matrix of XGBoost.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrix of Ada-Boost.

Table III shows further evaluation metrics applied to evaluate the models.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION: ROC, MCC, AND F1-SCORE

Algorithm	ROC	MCC	F1-score
LR	0.94	0.90	93%
DT	0.95	0.91	94%
NB	0.81	0.70	77%
RF	0.96	0.93	95%
XGBoost	0.98	0.97	97%
Ada-Boost	0.96	0.93	95%

Table III shows that the MCC score of the LR model was 0.90, implying that it was able to predict 90% of legitimate and fraudulent transactions. The NB MCC score shows that 81% of legitimate and fraudulent transactions were predicted. XGBoost had the highest MCC score of 97%. One more method to verify the accuracy of the models is the F1-score, which combines precision and recall. This metric was expected to obtain great results using XGBoost and outperform NB, as XGBoost is designed to deal with large datasets. The 5 models received scores of over 90%. The comparative results shown in Figure 9 illustrate a comparison of the existing results with numerous recent studies. Several metric methods should be used to assess the performance of each classifier. Relying on accuracy alone or two metrics will not reflect an accurate result. For example, in the case of NB in [3], immense accuracy and moderate precision were achieved, while the recall and F1-score were extremely low suggesting class-imbalance concerns.

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve is an effective technique to measure the performance of a model at various thresholds. Figure 8 shows the ROC of the six models, with all of them achieving almost perfect results except for NB.

Fig. 8. ROC of six models.

V. CONCLUSION

Credit card fraud detection systems are crucial for financial institutions. This study compared 6 ML algorithms to detect credit card frauds in real-world data, using CTGAN to overcome the deficiencies of small and imbalanced datasets. Based on the results, all the tested algorithms achieved an accuracy of over 85% and a precision score of over 95%. Five algorithms achieved a recall greater than 90%. Lastly, all algorithms achieved a ROC curve greater than 0.90, except Naïve Bayes, which scored 0.81.

Fig. 9. Comparative analysis.

Furthermore, the results of the 6 ML models were compared with previous studies that used imbalanced data, showing a significant improvement in all metrics.

Future work will involve the testing of additional ML algorithms and workarounds, the improvement of NB, the exploration of more GANs and their effectiveness in tabular data, and the use of other datasets.

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Modular Ontology to Support Manufacturing SMEs Toward Industry 4.0

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ABSTRACT

Industry 4.0 (I4.0) implementation is a hot topic among manufacturing organizations to reach smart factory status and integrate a fully connected ecosystem. Achieving such a transition presents notable challenges for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) since they often face resource and skilled personnel limitations. This study developed a domain ontology to represent various stages of maturity toward I4.0 implementation. Ontology provides a tool for SMEs to self-assess in situations of machines, processes, and factories for the dimensions of control, integration, and intelligence. This study focused on the identification of classes and relationships according to I4.0 implementation situations in the context of a manufacturing setting, the reuse of ontologies related to the domain of observations to model situations, and the creation and validation of the ontology through the information obtained from the questionnaires applied to SMEs. Finally, the ontology delivers a tool to understand SMEs' current state concerning I4.0 implementation and plan based on informed decisions about the maturity state and the technology required to advance to the next stage in their manufacturing processes.

Keywords-domain ontology; industry 4.0; SMEs; smart factory; SPARQL; semantic web

I. INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing industry has undergone profound changes due to the influence of new technologies, increasing the complexity of knowledge and information [1]. Innovation and technological development have accelerated the transformation of manufacturing processes, making them progressively complicated, automatic, and sustainable [2-3]. On the other hand, globalization and company relocation have generated challenges such as competition in the global market, greater flexibility and efficiency in processes, personalized products and services, and shorter innovation cycles [4-5]. These issues have been addressed by the Smart Factory (SF) or Factory of the Future (FoF) in the context of Industry 4.0 (I4.0) [6].

I4.0 is characterized by horizontal, vertical, and end-to-end integration, enabling the connection between machines and humans through the Internet of Things (IoT) and cyber-physical systems [7-8]. The I4.0 strategy promotes significant advantages in manufacturing value chain, product, and service innovation, relying on advances in information, communication, automation, and intelligence technologies [9-10]. On the other hand, I4.0 implementation in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) is a complex transition influenced by different drivers and barriers [11-12]. It implies a general digital transformation and challenges compared to large or multinational companies concerning financial resource constraints, technology awareness, and knowledge [13, 14]. SMEs adopt different strategies to achieve digital transformation, for example, the SF or FoF paradigms, driven

by the inclusion of disruptive technologies and influenced by economic, social, and organizational dimensions [13-16]. The path to be followed by SMEs must be planned and executed gradually through progressive stages to synchronize all processes and areas to ensure the profitability and socio-environmental benefits expected from this transformation [17].

Two approaches prevail for context handling in smart environments: data-driven (e.g. machine learning methods) and knowledge-driven (e.g. ontology-based) [18]. In this sense, "an ontology is a formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization" [19-20]. It enables clarifying the meaning of terms in specific contexts and establishing machine-understandable standards [21]. The interest in ontologies and semantic web technologies within the manufacturing field has increased, supported by the adaptation, collaboration, interoperability, cloud services, and automation of I4.0 [22-23]. Diverse frameworks, maturity or readiness models [24-27], and roadmaps [28-29] have been developed to guide the adoption of I4.0 in companies. Maturity and readiness models usually contemplate levels, dimensions, and descriptors or Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate conditions or states based on the premise that people, organizations, and processes evolve to maturity through different levels using a measuring scale [17, 30]. Levels represent stages of maturity, whereas dimensions specific capabilities of the I4.0 implementation domain [31-32]. The IMPULS model is commonly used to assess the maturity and readiness of organizations and measures six dimensions: strategy and organization, smart factory, smart operations, smart products, data-driven services, and employees [33]. In [34], this model was used in a steel manufacturing company, while in [35], it was applied to understand and characterize SMEs in Malaysia. Concerning frameworks, the reference architecture model for I4.0 (RAMI 4.0) includes the IT elements and components in a layered and life-cycle model, and the hierarchy levels represent the different functionalities within factories [36]. Another hierarchical framework was proposed in [37] to serve as a roadmap for SMEs to implement I4.0, based on two levels with three types: intelligence (control, integration, and intelligence) and automation (machine, process, and factory), generating a total of nine applications [37].

In the era of the IoT, machines, sensors, and assets communicate with each other, becoming context-aware and providing added value. According to [18], context is any information used to characterize the situation of an entity, while context data constantly change and can be highly heterogeneous. Context awareness provides services by examining the user's context to assist workers in decision-making and boost their activities, improving factory performance [38-39]. Thus, situation awareness refers to the continuous extraction of environmental information to be integrated with previous knowledge, updating the system in a real-world environment [40]. In [41], it was used in IoT applications, defining classes and properties to exchange data using the Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology [41].

There is no consensus on the dimensions considered in the frameworks or maturity models, while there is a lack of clarity in the constructs of maturity levels and inflexibility in their

application, and they do not fully cover all the specific needs of SMEs [9, 31, 42]. Furthermore, there are not enough case studies and success stories to guide implementation within SMEs, and they are not standardized and depend on the initial conditions, characteristics, and culture of organizations [16]. Moreover, the roadmap to I4.0 using an ontology-based approach remains limited due to the high cost of developing ontologies, development issues, and finding trained human resources. This gap hinders the fulfillment of the reusability of data, metadata, and processes [43]. This study addressed the development of a domain ontology in I4.0 based on a framework to support the implementation stages of SM in SMEs. The aim was to contribute with an ontology to model the situation of maturity levels of SMEs and determine their state of readiness on their way to I4.0.

II. METHODOLOGY

The roadmap for a digital transformation strategy toward I4.0 requires organizations to identify their current situation (e.g. machines or processes in a control or integration dimension). With this in mind, this work presents an ontology proposal for manufacturing SMEs' transition to I4.0 (OMSTI4), which aims to capture general notions of the state or situation of companies concerning preparation and stages of progress toward I4.0 implementation. The OMSTI4 represents the situations of the resources in manufacturing settings (e.g. machines or processes) based on the categorical framework presented in [37] that corresponds to the dimensions of control, integration, and intelligence related to its supply chain. Moreover, OMSTI4 models such situations identified by SMEs (e.g. regarding technology and production processes), with elements of the framework proposed in [44]. Figure 1 presents a conceptual model of OMSTI4, where stages and situations are connected to show a perspective of the current state of the factory maturity level as a function of stakeholders, observations, dimensions (e.g. control or integration versus machine or process), and the collected facts.

Fig. 1. Conceptual model of the OMSTI4 ontology.

The implementation of OMSTI4 used the ontology development 101 guide [45], the modular ontology modeling methodology, and the reuse of ontology design patterns [46]. The definition of classes and semantic relationships employed

OWL language [47], relying for their construction on the Protégé 5.6.1 tool [48] and the Cellfie plugin [49]. In compliance with the requirements and to validate the ontology [50], a sample of Competency Questions (CQ) was presented:

- CQ1: What is the maturity level of an SME in each of the nine stages of the OMSTI4 model?
- CQ2: What is the maturity level of an SME identified in the dimensions of machine, process, and factory?
- CQ3: What is the maturity level of an SME identified in the dimensions of control, integration, and intelligence?
- CQ4: What is the overall maturity level of an SME regarding the implementation of I4.0?
- CQ5: What other data related to SME self-assessment is available?

The key concepts included in the classes for OMSTI4 implementation are situation, stages, maturity state, I4.0 maturity model, dimension, subdimension, and maturity level, with several links among them. For instance, the situation class is central to the proposed ontology to model the state of the maturity level toward I4.0 implementation for an SME through observations of the entity of interest, according to the automation level (machine, process, and factory) on the intelligence level (control, integration, and intelligence). The situation class represented by the SME profile information and the set of observations of the average implementation maturity level correspond to the SMEs' responses from the questionnaires based on IMPULS [33] and 3D-CUBE [30].

The stage class comprises characteristics according to the design principles of I4.0 of interoperability and consciousness. The first refers to the sub-dimensions: digitalization, communication, standardization, flexibility, real-time responsibility, and customizability, while the second deals with predictive maintenance, decision-making, self-optimization, and self-configuration. The stakeholder concept is assimilated according to the ISO standards [51-52], resulting in the stakeholder perspective class that supports the representation in the OMSTI4 for the machine, process, and factory entities (subclasses of entity of interest), which are the dimensions that represent the observations toward I4.0. The observed property of maturity of the implementation of I4.0 in a company is measured using a scale based on IMPULS, from 0 to 5 (outsider, beginner, intermediate, experienced, expert, and top performer), and analyzed in concordance with the dimensions of control, integration, and intelligence. The context ontology presented in [18, 53] reuses core ontologies to build a modular ontology of the manufacturing domain. Thus, it is suitable to adapt and represent the intended context in the OMSTI4 for the machine, process, and the relationships of the situation, observation, resources, feature of interest, sensor, and observable property. Figure 2 shows a subset of classes that identifies the key concepts above, the object properties, and the data properties to analyze the different dimensions of the maturity implementation of I4.0. Furthermore, Table I shows a module that contains a subset of classes registered in Wikidata [54].

TABLE I. A SUBSET OF CLASSES OF OMSTI4.

Class	Description
Implementation of I4.0 (Q117354032)	Implementation or execution of the plans, roadmaps, procedures, and others, for an entity to reach the change or transition from its current state toward I4.0.
CFI4.0_Stage1 (Q114682905)	This stage considers two dimensions: machine and control.
CFI4.0_Stage5 (Q114692253)	This stage considers two dimensions: process and integration.
CFI4.0_Stage9 (Q114693131)	This stage considers two dimensions: factory and intelligence.
Maturity Model (Q121402594)	A conceptual model that consists of a sequence of discrete maturity levels for processes in one or more business domains and represents a desired or expected evolutionary path.

Fig. 2. OMSTI4 general class hierarchy view.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on questionnaires applied to SMEs to assess their maturity in I4.0 implementation, the proposed ontology was populated to perform queries and to evaluate dimension, stage, and overall maturity level. Figure 3 depicts a visual perspective of the developed ontology, comprising classes, subclasses, and their relationships. As a result of the implementation of OMSTI4, Figure 4 illustrates a Protégé window with individuals, types, and properties. The Pellet reasoning plugin was applied to the OMSTI4 ontology, returning a consistent ontology model. For instance, *Dimension_Intelligence* has some object properties assertions such as *isPartOf* related to *Stack_ProductionProcesses* and *is_a_MMDimensionOf* related to *CFI40*. The reasoner detects that the individual is a type of *MMDimension* since there is an explicit object property assertion named *is_a_MMSubDimensionOf*.

Fig. 3. A partial visualization of OMSTI4 classes and relations.

Fig. 4. Inference visualization for the individual *Dimension_Intelligence*.

The object property *is_a_MMSubDimensionOf* links the sub-dimensions classes (self-organization, decision-making, early-aware, self-configuration) with *Dimension_Intelligence*, and the range of the object property *is_a_MMSubDimensionOf* connects to the class *MMDimension*. Regarding the object properties inferences, for instance, *has_MMSubDimension* is reasoned due to its inverse property *is_a_MMSubDimensionOf*.

Figure 5 depicts the results of CQ1, where the column *ObservationsMatEnt* addresses the observations of the entity of interest according to the grade of automation in the dimension machine, process, and factory, and on the intelligence level in the dimension of control, integration, and intelligence through the column *ObservablePropert*, showing the maturity level of an SME in each of the nine stages in the column *sosaResult*. For instance, in the fourth row, the individual *cfi4:Observ_ENT_1_DC_P* indicates the dimension of process and control by the *ObservablePropert*, revealing stage IV with a maturity level of 4.

Figure 6 shows the results of CQ3 and CQ4, where the first row displays the overall maturity level of an SME, *cfi4:Observ_ENT_1_Overall*, with a maturity level of 2.67 in column *ML*. The following three rows address the maturity level per integration, intelligence, and control dimension with values *Level_3_Experienced*, *Level_2_Intermediate*, and *Level_3_Experienced*.

Several research efforts have been conducted in frameworks or maturity models regarding knowledge representation and modeling with ontologies to support the transition to I.4.0 in business. However, there are still open topics for research due to the nature of its requirements (e.g. resources, systems, and processes, among others) [55]. For instance, in [56], a maturity model was proposed for construction companies, using I.4.0 models to measure the organizational aspects and provide a guideline for developing a business strategy. In [57], a knowledge graph was proposed for I.4.0 related to standards, norms, and reference frameworks, providing a linked data-conform collection of annotated and classified reference guidelines to support users in understanding how to implement I.4.0 systems. In [58], an ontology-based model was presented for digital transformation knowledge, adaptable to any sector for a digital strategy in a company. In [59], a knowledge graph was built, identifying core concepts of I.4.0 and introducing a reference ontological model focused on production lines. In [60], an ontology for the asset administration shell of RAMI4.0 was proposed as an extensible basis for information systems to enhance the interoperability of assets from different manufacturers. These works, OMSTI included, share the use of ontologies as tools to

structure and represent knowledge related to technology, organizational maturity, and knowledge management for I4.0 implementation. Table II shows the criteria to identify similarities among them.

bridge this research gap. This study focused on manufacturing SMEs and employed well-known questionnaires to populate the ontology (i.e. IMPULS and 3D-CUBE) through the stakeholders' perspective. It incorporated the context to establish a situational state of machines, processes, and factories to support SMEs toward I4.0 adoption.

Fig. 5. The maturity level of an SME for each of the nine stages.

TABLE II. COMPARISON BETWEEN OMSTI4 AND RELATED WORKS

Criteria	[56]	[57]	[58]	[59]	[60]	OMSTI4
Development	ont	ont	onm	onm	ont	ont
Dimensions [44]	t; pp; o; ch	t; pp; o	t; pp; p; o; ch	t; pp; o; ch	t	t; pp
Models/frameworks/standards	mm;b	r; i4; ot	b	r	r	mm; i4; r;
Competency questions	-	yes	-	-	yes	yes
Reusing ontologies	-	yes	yes	yes	-	yes
Questionnaire or DB to populate	yes	-	-	-	-	yes
Evaluation [50]	a	c	-	v	c	q

Development: ont=ontology, onm=ontology model.

Dimensions: t=technology, pp=production processes, o=organization, ch=change, p=people.

Models/frameworks: mm=maturity or readiness model of I4.0, r=RAMI 4.0, b=building information model, i4=ISO-42010, ot=others standards.

Evaluation: Evaluation of ontologies: q=competency questions, v=verification, c=evaluation by criteria. Validation of ontologies: a= application-based, u= user-based. "-"=not mentioned.

Fig.6. Dimension (control, integration, and intelligence) and overall maturity levels.

The primary criteria considered in this research were the development state, dimensions of the model, models, frameworks, and standards embraced in ontology creation to support I4.0 implementation. Technology and production process were the commonly used dimensions, whereas organization and change were also considered. As a foundation to create the ontological model, most research works used the RAMI 4.0 and industrial standards, although others employed the Building Information Model (BIM). Furthermore, the most well-known ontologies used by the reviewed works were Dolce Ultralite, SSN, ontology of measurements, and BIM.

The reviewed studies focused their efforts on companies in general, regardless of their size, while manufacturing SMEs face digital transformation challenges and resource constraints to achieve I4.0. Therefore, more studies will further help to

IV. CONCLUSION

This article proposed and developed a modular ontology to support manufacturing SMEs to assess the maturity level in their efforts to implement I4.0. OMSTI4 provides the means for SMEs to identify their maturity state for the intelligence level according to the dimensions of control, integration, and intelligence, and automation level in machine, process, and factory dimensions. OMSTI4 can serve as a knowledge base for industry and researchers interested in exploring the current state of the domestic factory maturity level. Furthermore, it allows SMEs to make more informed decisions and advance their path toward digitalization and industrial automation, laying the foundation for business collaboration and developing valuable support strategies.

OMSTI4 offers SMEs a valuable tool to evaluate and know their current state toward I4.0, contributing with a snapshot of the overall advancement of the company and encouraging innovation in this challenging field. Furthermore, this study sets the groundwork from an SME perspective by collecting data using questionnaires to build a valuable knowledge base using ontologies and address the I4.0 transformation of SMEs in México. Future work will consider the creation of software that incorporates the core of OMSTI4 after the enhancements of the ontology through validations based on the criteria of experts in the knowledge domain of engineering and I4.0, with the intention of promoting collaboration between SMEs and integration of their supply chains.

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A Hybrid MIP-CBO Approach for Loss Minimization of the PMSM-fed Electric Vehicle Drive System

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an efficient operation method suitable for Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSMs). The proposed algorithm provides control of copper and iron losses across the range of operations. The machine operating concept was initially reviewed to establish the control method, and a model was created for control purposes. The efficient operation boundary of the machine was then established based on PMSM voltage and current constraints. A rapid search for the optimal operating point was made possible by a hybrid COOT optimization with Mixed Integer Programming. This expands the high-efficiency area of the motor drive in an electric vehicle, leading to longer Km between charges.

Keywords-loss minimization; Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM); mixed integer programming; COOT bird optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, HEVs are a popular and efficient solution for personal and urban public transport due to the fuel-energy crisis and environmental concerns. The provision of efficient and power-intensive electric motors is critical for the development and rapid implementation of HEVs. In general, induction motors have the potential advantages of low cost and a wide speed range but are less efficient than Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSM) despite the use of the loss minimization algorithm [1]. In [1-14], a wide range of mathematical and soft computing methods were addressed. In [1], a mathematical loss minimization algorithm was developed to minimize the power loss of PMSM and balance the EV energy. In [2], a variable voltage control strategy was proposed to optimize motor electrical loss and improve motor, inverter, and the entire drive system efficiency. Moreover, the current harmonic of the motor stator winding was also reduced. In [3], a one-dimensional analytical model was presented to analyze the distribution of motor energy of the driving cycle and to reduce the loss and cost of the PMSM. In [4], fuzzy logic with a PI controller was applied to improve efficiency, maintenance cost, and power diversity, and reduce machine tracking error. In [5], a look-up table-based field-oriented with sliding mode control was proposed for an EV drive system. ANNs have been applied to reduce the loss of PMSMs. In [6], an equivalent conversion method was applied to minimize the loss for

interior PMSM, studying both copper and iron losses and improving PMSM efficiency. The same machine was analyzed in [7]. In [8], harmonic analysis was applied to a Model Predictive Torque Control (MPTC) to maximize the efficiency and loss of FM motors and compare the results with an old model and other optimization methods. In [9], the PI-PSO technique was applied to improve the efficiency and robustness of an EV drive, and the results were compared with four different algorithms. In [10], copper loss reduction for PMSM was presented to determine machine torque and loss.

This study proposes a novel COOT bird technique integrated with Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) to minimize power loss and improve the efficiency of PMSM-based electric drive systems. The proposed algorithm was designed to minimize both copper and iron losses and improve the efficiency of the PMSM-subjected machine components. The proposed hybrid approach properly tuned the PMSM variables to improve performance. A comparative study was conducted for a PMSM with and without the proposed optimization method.

II. THE PROPOSED METHOD

An inverter-fed PMSM is a common topology in EVs. The input to this system is the acceleration and torque command. Figure 1 shows that the optimization algorithm searches for the optimal values of I_d and I_q to produce a minimal loss. This

study applied hybrid MIP and the Coot Bird Optimization (CBO) algorithm to minimize the loss of PMSM interconnected with an EV drive system.

Fig. 1. Loss minimization by COOT optimization.

A. Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP)

In general, Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) can be mathematically represented as follows: Let's assume X and Y two column variables, the components of which are $x_i, i=1$ to p , and $y_j, j=1$ to q , respectively. The two rectangular matrices A and B are of the order (m, p) and (m, q) , respectively. Then the problem can be mathematically defined as:

$$\min F = A_0^T X + B_0^T Y \quad (1)$$

subjected to equality and inequality constraints

$$AX + BY = D \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha_i \leq y_j \leq \beta_j \quad (3)$$

$$y_j \text{ integer, } j=1 \text{ to } q$$

$$0 \leq x_i, i=1 \text{ to } p \quad (4)$$

where x_i are the continuous variables, and y_j are integer variables. The objective function F should satisfy (2) and (3), and an optimal integer solution can be obtained by minimizing F .

B. Coot Bird Optimization (CBO) Algorithm

CBO is a new and efficient metaheuristic algorithm, inspired by the natural behavior of different movements of coot birds on the water surface [20]. Coot birds have two different modes of movement on the water surface: irregular and regular. Each coot bird moves in the direction of a group of leaders to reach a food supply. The characteristics of coot birds on the water surface are [20]:

- Random movement.
- Chain movement.
- Adjusting the position based on the group leaders.
- Leader movement.

The population of the coot is randomly generated and mathematically represented using:

$$\text{CootPos}(i) = \text{rand}(1, d) * (ub - lb) + lb \quad (5)$$

where $\text{CootPos}(i)$ is the coot position, d is the number of variables or problem dimensions, lb is the lower bound of the search space $[lb_1, lb_2, \dots, lb_d]$, and ub is the upper bound of the search space $[ub_1, ub_2, \dots, ub_d]$.

C. Random Movement

The random movements of the coot birds at position Q are determined using:

$$Q = \text{rand}(1, d) * (ub - lb) + lb \quad (6)$$

To keep away from a local optimum solution, the position of the coot is updated using:

$$\text{CootPos}(i) = \text{CootPos}(i) + A * R2 * (Q - \text{CootPos}(i)) \quad (7)$$

where $R2$ is a random number in the interval $[0, 1]$, and A is determined using:

$$A = 1 - L * \left(\frac{1}{iter}\right) \quad (8)$$

where L is the current iteration, and $iter$ is the maximum iteration number.

D. Chain Movement

The chain movement can be given by the average position of two coot birds as:

$$\text{CootPos}(i) = 0.5 * (\text{CootPos}(i-1) + \text{CootPos}(i)) \quad (9)$$

where $\text{CootPos}(i-1)$ is the position of the second coot.

E. Adjusting Position Based on Group Leaders

The coot bird updates its position according to the position of the leader in the group. The leader is selected using:

$$K = 1 + (\text{iMOD } NL) \quad (10)$$

The next position of the coot based on the selected leader is premeditated using:

$$\text{CootPos}(i) = \text{LeaderPos}(k) + 2 * R1 * \cos(2R\pi) * (\text{LeaderPos}(k) - \text{CootPos}(i)) \quad (11)$$

F. Leader Movement

The leader must jump from the existing local optimal position to the global optimal position using:

$$\text{LeaderPos}(i) = \begin{cases} B * R3 * \cos(2R\pi * (\text{gBest} - \text{LeaderPos}(i))) \\ \quad + \text{gBest}, R4 < 0.5 \\ B * R3 * \cos(2R\pi * (\text{gBest} - \text{LeaderPos}(i))) \\ \quad - \text{gBest}, R4 \geq 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where gBest is the best position ever found, $R3$ and $R4$ are random numbers in the interval $[0, 1]$, R is a random number in the interval $[-1, 1]$, and B is calculated using:

$$B = 2 - L * \left(\frac{1}{iter}\right) \quad (13)$$

III. PROPOSED PMSM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION FOR LOSS MINIMIZATION

This section describes the proposed PMSM vector control model for the loss minimization problem, which forms the background for the Simulink models used in MATLAB. Various control techniques can be used, such as Field-Oriented Control (FOC) or Direct Torque Control (DTC), to accurately regulate the motor's speed and torque. Figure 2 shows the complete simulation model for the FOC.

Fig. 2. Vector control model for PMSM electric drive.

Copper, iron, stray, and mechanical losses, including windage loss, are included in PMSM losses. This modeling fails to discuss windage loss because it is not directly related to motor current or flux level.

A. Objective Function

The primary objective is to minimize the power loss of the PMSM:

$$\text{Minimize } P_t(i_d, i_q) \tag{14}$$

B. Copper Loss

The copper loss occurs in the stator and rotor windings due to the resistance of the copper r_s , given by:

$$P_{cu} = \frac{3}{2} r_s (i_d^2 + i_q^2) \tag{15}$$

C. Iron Loss

The iron loss is mathematically defined as:

$$P_{fe} = c_{fe} \omega^\gamma (\lambda_d^2 + \lambda_q^2) \tag{16}$$

where $\gamma = 1.5 \sim 1.6$ and c_{fe} is the iron coefficient.

D. Stray Loss

The computation of stray losses is laborious and cannot be relied upon to provide accurate results. In reality, stray losses are assessed as:

$$P_{str} = c_{str} \omega^2 (i_d^2 + i_q^2) \tag{17}$$

E. Constraints of PMSM

Subject to:

$$T_e = T_0 \tag{18}$$

The voltage constraints used are as follows:

$$V_d^2 + V_q^2 = \omega^2 (L_{dd}(1 - \alpha, i_q) i_d) - (L_{dq} + \alpha_m)^2 \tag{19}$$

The current constraint is:

$$i_d^2 + i_q^2 < I_{max}^2 \tag{20}$$

$$\alpha_m = L_{dd} \dot{i}_f \tag{21}$$

and again:

$$V_d^2 + V_q^2 = \frac{V_{DC}^2}{\sqrt{3}} \tag{22}$$

IV. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROPOSED MIP-CBO FOR LOSS MINIMIZATION

The fundamental goal of a vector controller is to convert the PMSM's three-phase stator currents and voltages from a stationary reference frame, commonly referred to as the ABC or 0 reference frame, to a revolving reference frame, commonly referred to as the dq or rotor reference frame, which is aligned with the rotor flux. The control system architecture is made simpler by this transformation, which decouples the motor control variables. As shown in Figure 3, there are several sets (i_d, i_q) that can be used to generate a certain amount of torque T_0 and speed. The present set (i_d, i_q) was taken into account to minimize loss at a given torque value t_0 .

Fig. 3. Variation of machine loss with I_d and I_q .

The hybrid COOT optimization used is to find the current reference (i_d^*, i_q^*) which can produce minimal loss. In addition, the voltage and current limits (fed as inequality constraints) need to be met. The simulation study involved the following steps:

- Step 1: Use a separate m -file to initialize the set of controller gains. This was loaded into the MATLAB workspace as a startup file. In Simulink, speed was set at a constant speed w_r .
- Step 2: Use the constant torque mode for the inverter controller, and set the torque command as T_0 .
- Step 3: Use the hybrid COOT optimization to evaluate the objective function.
- Step 4: For the initial range, a feasible solution is obtained using MIP. For this increase, the d -axis current command is $I_d^c + \Delta I_d$.
- Step 5: The objective function is further refined using the COOT optimization in (14).

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed MIP-CBO approach was effectively applied to minimize the various losses and improve the efficiency of a PMSM drive system. For PMSM, note that a maximum current is imposed before the iron core of the motor becomes magnetically saturated. The motor is said to be running in a "constant torque" region when the current exceeds this threshold because the torque can no longer be raised. The

motor must work above its base speed in applications where higher speeds are necessary. The "flux-weakening" control approach is used to attain faster speeds. The torque starts to decrease in this manner, but the current increases past the constant torque area. The motor's back-EMF (electromotive force) voltage rises with speed, making up for the loss of torque and allowing the motor to run at higher speeds.

A. Performance of PMSM with Optimal Controller Gains

The optimal controller gains, shown in Table I, were fed into a simulation model and Figures 4-7 show the performance results. A simulation model was used in MATLAB/Simulink to evaluate the relation between I_d , I_q , power loss, and torque. During the simulation study, the initial SOC of the battery was assumed to be 90%, and a step of 0.001 was used.

TABLE I. CONTROLLER BLOCK GAINS

Conventional controller values		Hybrid COOT controller values	
DC To DC Conv. Kp	0.1	DC To DC Conv.Kp	.234
DC To DC Conv. Ki	10	DC To DC Conv.Ki	7
ICE.Kp	0.02	ICE.Kp	0.14
ICE.Ki	0.01	ICE.Ki	0.1
Controller.Veh_Spd. Kp	0.02	Controller.Veh_Spd.Kp	0.2
Controller.Veh_Spd.Ki	0.04	Controller.Veh_Spd.Ki	0.84

To increase the torque output of the motor, the current flowing through the motor windings should be increased. In contrast, reducing the current will decrease the torque. The torque-current characteristics of a PMSM show how current changes due to torque demand. A PMSM may generate more torque at low speeds using the same amount of current, while the torque output tends to decrease as the speed increases. The experiments were carried out under different load torque conditions. Figures 4 and 5 show the variation of motor current for torque changes, while Figure 6 shows the power variation of the machine under different load torques.

Fig. 4. Variation of torque with I_d and I_q .

Fig. 5. Torque and current variation of PMSM.

Fig. 6. Torque and output power variation of PMSM.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF SIMULATION RESULTS AT RATED SPEED WITH VARIABLE TORQUE

Test Case	Torque Demand (N/m ²)	Efficiency (%)			Power loss (%)		
		Classical method [15]	MTPA Control [15]	MIP-CB0 (Proposed)	Classical method	MTPA Control	MIP-CB0 (Proposed)
1	725	92.05	92.13	96.34	7.95	7.87	3.66
2	600	92.08	92.18	96.23	7.92	7.82	3.77
3	500	91.87	91.97	96.42	8.13	8.03	3.58
4	400	91.28	91.42	92.08	8.72	8.58	7.92
5	300	89.95	90.13	93.22	10.05	9.87	6.78
6	200	86.89	87.17	90.59	13.11	12.83	9.41
7	100	77.9	78.42	83.02	22.1	21.58	16.98

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF SIMULATION RESULTS AT RATED TORQUE WITH VARIABLE SPEED

Test Case	Speed of PMSM (rpm)	Efficiency (%)			Power loss (%)		
		Classical method [15]	MTPA Control [15]	MIP-CB0 (Proposed)	Classical method	MTPA Control	MIP-CB0 (Proposed)
1	360	92.05	92.13	93.34	7.95	7.87	6.66
2	300	91.92	91.98	92.23	8.08	8.02	7.77
3	250	91.55	91.59	92.42	8.45	8.41	7.58
4	200	90.76	90.78	91.08	9.24	9.22	8.92
5	150	89.15	89.15	90.22	10.85	10.85	9.78
6	100	85.65	85.64	87.59	14.35	14.36	12.41
7	50	75.93	75.90	79.02	24.07	24.1	20.98

The COOT optimization with MIP was tested in different torque conditions, and the efficiency is presented in Table II. Obviously, efficiency was improved in all seven load conditions. Additionally, the torque reference tracking ability of the controller was tested, as shown in Figure 7. Here, it can be seen that the machine's actual torque can track the reference torque. When load is applied, the speed drops from 3000 rpm to 2998 rpm, showing the speed regulation of the proposed method.

Fig. 7. Performance of the proposed drive under load change.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study presented a straightforward way to determine the best d - and q -axis current references to obtain the best efficiency. The value of the DQ component for a given torque and speed also satisfies voltage and current limitations. For a certain PMSM model, the COOT algorithm was used and tested under various driving cycles. With this strategy, an efficiency of up to 96 % was observed during the simulations. Torque reference tracking was studied in MATLAB/Simulink, where the controller was able to reach a steady state in 2 s. Peak overshoots in currents during loading were only twice the rated load current. The speed drop of the machine under load changes was very small, i.e. 2 rpm. Future work will attempt to implement this strategy into a real vehicle. Furthermore, the proposed method can be extended to a four-wheel drive mechanism. The proposed method improves the efficiency of the machine by altering only two parameters, the I_d and I_q references. The COOT algorithm works in coordination with the FOC control algorithm as an add-on module. However, since most modern drives use FOC in their control module, a simple subroutine can be inserted to modify their performance.

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Sensor Enabled Proximity Detection with Hybridisation of IoT and Computer Vision Models to Assist the Visually Impaired

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ABSTRACT

Proximity Detection Systems (PDS) are used to detect objects or persons close to Visually Impaired (VI) persons. Sensors are used to identify proximity based on the distance from objects. This study aimed to design a hybrid proximity detection framework for VI people using ultrasonic sensors embedded in a Raspberry Pi board to detect the proximity of a VI user in an office environment. Hybridization was based on the integration of IoT-enabled devices, ultrasonic proximity sensors, and computer vision algorithms to control the detection of objects or people and inform the user with a voice message. The model framework was implemented with 100 samples and tested with 10 analyses in each sample. The results showed significant improvement in detecting the proximity of the objects with an accuracy of 98.7%, outperforming current PDS with good results in precision, range, obstacle recognition, false positives and negatives, response time, usability, durability, reliability, etc.

Keywords-proximity detection systems; hybrid visually impaired proximity detection (HVIPD) algorithm; hybrid proximity detection for visually impaired framework; computer vision; hybrid IoT ultrasonic system

I. INTRODUCTION

Proximity Detection Systems (PDS) and Collision Awareness Systems (CAS) help detect objects and prevent people from being injured from collisions [1]. Such systems let the operator know if people or objects are near them. These systems should be personalized because every need is unique. Customers have many choices to make their system unique to them. Such systems range from very basic systems that use Ultra High Frequencies (UHF) to more advanced systems that have multiple points to detect something [2]. A PDS can use UHF, Radar, and Electromagnetic Field technologies. Ultrasonic transducers and sensors are devices that make or listen to very high-frequency sound waves [3]. Transmitters create electric signals, receivers change the electric signals into sound, and transceivers can both send and receive signals.

Ultrasound devices can be used to obtain the speed and direction of the wind and determine how much fluid is in a container or passage. Sensors help determine how quickly an entity is shifting or in which direction it is moving and determine its speed. Ultrasound is a handy tool that can be used in many ways [4]. In addition, technology can predict how close things are and keep track of where they are at all times [5]. Ultrasonic proximity detection can help people who cannot

see properly in many ways. Ultrasonic detectors can be used for obstacle detection and avoidance [6], navigation assistance to help the user move around places they don't know by looking at what is around them [7], object identification to tell the difference between different objects by how they reflect sound waves [8], and customizable alerts with different vibration patterns, sound cues, or a mix of both, depending on the user's preference [9]. Ultrasounds can be used to measure distances between two points by sending and receiving short bursts of ultrasound signals between devices. This method is called Sono micrometry [10].

This study aims to design a PDS based on a hybrid framework using ultrasonic sensors embedded in a Raspberry Pi to detect the proximity of the user in an office environment to assist visually impaired people. Hybridization was based on the integration of IoT-enabled devices, proximity sensors, and computer vision algorithms to control the detection of objects or people and inform the user with a voice message. The scope of this study was to assist visually impaired people with an inability to detect objects around them. The model was developed and compared with existing models and datasets to determine whether it could significantly improve detection.

II. RELATED WORKS

Ultrasonic sensors are quite unique compared to capacitive and inductive sensors and use high-frequency sound waves that humans cannot hear to detect nearby objects [11]. Medical ultrasound transducers are devices that are used to create images of different aspects of the body [12]. The transducer can be used on the skin, such as in ultrasound imaging, or placed on a body. Ultrasounds have many advantages [13]. In [14], a method was introduced to help robots feel things through touch, designing a special robot finger, called Finger-STS, that can sense things. In [15], a method was proposed to improve how machines see things when objects are hidden, which was tested to see how close things are, achieving 96.76% accuracy at a rate of 25 Hz. In [16], a method was suggested to see things using a special computer program. In [17], pictures and smart computer methods were used to address CoViD-19 proximity issues. In [18], a method was introduced to improve signature verification, achieving an accuracy of 85-95%. In [19], special computer programs were investigated to find important parts of people's bodies when they are close to robots. In [20], a method was proposed to use sensors to gather data in complex learning situations where people work together, called Computer Vision for Position Estimation (CVPE). In [21], a new kind of soft robot sequence, called ProTac, was proposed to sense things in two ways: feeling touch and knowing when something is close.

In [22], a system was proposed with multiple robot arms and special cameras to correctly organize objects based on their size and shape. In [23], a system was introduced that used cameras to detect fires and smoke indoors. Many studies suggested different models for proximity detection in different scenarios. In this framework, proximity detection was used to assist visually impaired people in detecting the presence of obstacles in their position by measuring the distance between them. In [24], advanced computer vision was used to protect against attacks. In [25], a method was proposed to track how close people are to each other by watching videos in public places. In [26], devices were designed that used sensors and pictures to help people who have trouble seeing. In [27], a method was designed to understand how the physical environment of green spaces affects the leisure activities of people. Ultrasonic sensors are best used for non-contact detection of presence, level, position, and distance [28].

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Previous studies had two major setbacks: they could not handle sensors and software at the same interface [22] and they could not find proximity based on threshold and distance vector mapping methods [25]. The proposed framework, called Hybrid Proximity Detection for Visually Impaired (HPDVI), was designed to address these gaps and is developed in three different stages as shown in Figure 1. During the first phase, the input is captured from external sources, either from a web camera or a Picamera, as video content. The image frame and the object are detected as inputs that indicate the presence of the object in the environment. In the second phase, the ultrasonic sensor detects an object, records it as an obstacle, and calculates its distance by:

$$dist(Obj) = \frac{Speed(Sound) * Time}{2} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. The proposed HPDVI framework.

The speed of sound was calculated on the density of air at 344 m/s and the time was calculated based on the difference between the time of detection and the time of announcement at regular intervals. This is a general method to detect proximity and update the distance vector tracking between the sensor and the object. The threshold limit was established to identify the object, and the distance vector was regularly mapped based on the Intersection of Union (IoU) [29]:

$$IoU(A) = \frac{Area\ of\ Intersection\ of\ Boxes}{Area\ of\ Union\ of\ Boxes} \quad (2)$$

IoU is used to find the intersected boxes in object detection where two objects merge. The proposed framework could identify individual objects using the direct distance calculation and merged objects with the IoU method. After detecting the proximity and threshold mapping process, the distance was calculated and then sent to the voice-over output. During the third phase, the collected digital information was converted into voice output to be sent to the text-to-speech conversion tools, where the decoder will convert the acoustic models and send a female voice output recorded from online sources to language models, and finally output it through the external output device. Thus, this framework can be characterized as a hybrid framework that integrates Internet of Things (IoT), sensors, and machine learning models. The proposed model was developed and an analysis was carried out with a sample of 100 persons in an office environment with a Raspberry Pi kit. The dataset comprised demographic details and proximity tests with 10 samples, as shown in Table I. Name and place are unpredictable variables, age and gender are categorical variables, and the remaining demographic variables are predictable features. Based on the initial input of demographic variables, tests were performed for the proximity analysis, as shown in Table II.

TABLE I. DEMOGRAPHIC DATA FOR EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Name	Nominal	Place	Nominal
Age	17-24, 24-30 31-50	Gender	Male, Female
Complexion	Fair, Brown Dark	Race	Black, White Average
PPE – Spex	Yes, No	PPE-Mouth Mask	Yes, No
PPE – Hair Mask	Yes, No	PPE- Ear Mask	Yes, No

TABLE II. PROXIMITY ANALYSIS FOR THE EXPERIMENTS

Threshold Test	0-Exact	1-Proximal	2-Distant
Test #1	0	-	-
Test #2	0	-	-
Test #3	-	1	-
Test #4	-	1	-
Test #5	-	1	-
Test #6	-	1	-
Test #7	0	-	-
Test #8	0	-	-
Test #9	0	-	-
Test #10	-	-	2

Algorithm HPDVI

```

Step 1: Start the Process
Step 2: Import the Basic Packages for Raspberry Pi,
Time, and ESpeak for Voice Output
Step 3: Set initial standards for Raspberry Pi
Board with TRIG = 16 and ECHO=18
Step 4: Initialise I = 0
Step 5: Set Input ECHO and Output TRIG as False
Step 6: Set the initial time sleep to 2 for placing
the object
Step 7: Iterate through the process from Step 8
through Step 9 until True
Step 8: Detect the output of TRIG to be True
Step 9: Set Sleep Time to 0.00001
Step 10: Iterate through the Process of Step 11
until ECHO = 0
Step 11: Set Pulse_start = Current Time of Start
Step 12: Iterate through the Process of Step 13
until ECHO = 1
Step 13: Set Pulse_end = Current Time of End
Step 14: Compute Pulse_duration = Pulse_end -
Pulse_start
Step 15: Compute Distance = Pulse_duration * 17150
Step 16: Update Distance = distance + 1.15
(Constant value)
Step 17: Compute Distance_Inches = Distance *
0.393701
Step 18: Test if Distance <=100 and Distance >=5
and perform Step 19 through Step-22
Step 19: Display Distance in cm
Step 20: Display Distance_Inches in inch
Step 21: Initiate ESpeak Module for Voice Output
Step 22: Initialise i = 1
Step 23: Test if Distance > 100 (Maximum Threshold)
and i==1 and perform Step 24 Thru Step 25
Step 24: Insist User to place the Object again
Step 25: Initialize i=0
Step 26: Initialize the Sleep time to 2
Step 27: Accept the completion of the process
Step 28: Clean the Process
Step 29: Stop the Process
End Algorithm HPDVI

```

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

Ultrasonic sensors are preferable to infrared sensors because they are not affected by moisture or black materials. In general, using ultrasounds to detect nearby objects can help people with visual impairments feel more confident and safer while moving around. Figure 2 presents the overall implementation and setup of the entire HPDVI model.

Fig.2. Implementation of the HPDVI model with a Picamera for Raspberry Pi kit and ultrasonic sensor on a white walking stick.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Considering various aspects is necessary to design efficient and user-friendly systems to aid blind people navigate safely. Here are some important factors to consider when evaluating proximity detection systems:

- Accuracy: 1000 samples were tested and among them, the confusion matrix was identified based on k-means clustering. The overall accuracy of the distance prediction was found to be 98.7%.
- Precision: Based on accuracy, the precision was found to be 98.45%.
- Range: The system could work with a threshold range of 12 m and detect correct outputs in 10 subsequent tests in all environments.
- Obstacle Recognition: The system could detect obstacles and inform the user with a voice-based message, with an accuracy of 98.7%.
- False Positives and Negatives: The test procedure showed very few false positives and negatives, 7 and 6,

respectively, out of 1000 samples, which represent 1.3% overall.

- **Response Time:** The response time was less than or equal to 0.0002 s, which is very low.
- **User Interface and Feedback:** User feedback was collected using an analysis report and was found to be positive with all 100 respondents in proximity detection procedures.
- **Usability:** The experiment was successful with visually impaired people in hospitals and clinical centers with good usability responses.
- **Durability and reliability:** The system was found to be durable and reliable in accidents, temperature, and wetness.
- **Adaptability:** The walking stick could detect all directions and locations without interruptions.
- **Interference and crosstalk:** The device was placed between other ultrasonic sensors, and it was found that no interference or crosstalk was recorded during the experiments.
- **Training and learning curve:** Visually impaired people were found to easily become acquainted with the system without much tutoring or demonstrations.
- **Cost-effectiveness:** The overall kit can be achieved with a maximum of Rs. 30,000, which is quite affordable for the middle class or ordinary people as an important investment to improve their quality of life.
- **User Acceptance:** Many visually impaired people accepted the system as they felt comfortable using it.
- **Collaboration with experts:** The device was tested and monitored by medical experts and was found useful in detection and everyday use.
- **Long-Term Use:** This aspect has to be tested in the future.
- **Ethical considerations:** There were no negative ethics on this system, as it does not collect any information on the privacy of any user at any time.

Table III presents a collective report to determine the evaluation of the results. Figure 3 shows the overall comparison of Accuracy, Precision, and Error rate.

Fig. 3. Performance prediction analysis for the proposed proximity detection framework.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE METRICS AND RESULTS OBTAINED IN EACH EVALUATION

S.No	Performance Metric	Outcome
1	Accuracy	Positive (98.7%)
2	Precision	Positive (98.45%)
3	Range	Positive
4	Obstacle Recognition	Positive (98.7%)
5	False Positives and Negatives	Positive 1.3%
6	Response Time	Positive (0.0002 sec)
7	User Interface and Feedback	Positive
8	Usability	Positive
9	Battery Life	Positive
10	Durability and reliability	Positive
11	Adaptability	Positive
12	Interference and crosstalk	Positive
13	Training and learning curve	Positive
14	Cost-effectiveness	Positive
15	User Acceptance	Positive
16	Collaboration with Experts	Positive
17	Long-Term Use	Positive
18	Ethical considerations	Positive

As shown in Table III, testing how well proximity detection systems work requires different types of experts in various fields working together. In the above results, all expected outcomes of the experiments were positively evaluated with both qualitative and quantitative factors. These experts need to know about medical, user experience design, accessibility, and user testing to properly evaluate these systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study presented a novel hybrid framework for proximity detection for visually impaired people, based on a novel proximity algorithm called Hybrid Proximity Detection for Visually Impaired (HPDVI). The implementation was carried out on a Raspberry Pi kit so that the model could be developed and tested with visually impaired people. A sample of 100 respondents with 10 proximity detection values each was tested and analyzed, using a threshold of 12 meters. The overall framework was highly successful and provided an accuracy level of 98.7%. In future systems, it could be incorporated into an embedded system to perform object, face, and proximity detection at the same time to assist visually impaired people in all aspects of their lives.

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Experimental, Modal, and Harmonic Response Analysis of a Chladni Plate at Ultrasonic Frequencies

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ABSTRACT

Mode shapes and natural frequencies of mechanical structures can be determined with the Chladni approach. Visual patterns are generated on the Chladni plate if it is exposed to vibrations. These patterns are known as Chladni patterns/figures. Mechanical vibrators are used to excite the plates at particular frequencies for pattern generation, but based on the making and application, their range is limited up to 10 kHz. Piezoelectric transducers are a special kind of transducers that are capable of generating ultrasonic frequencies and if are attached to a plate, intricate visual patterns can be generated, based on the material properties and the shape of the plate. The current research focuses on experimenting with and simulating Chladni figures in the ultrasonic frequency range. The simulations were performed in ANSYS Workbench as a validation of the experimental work.

Keywords-Chladni plate; ultrasonic frequency; mode shapes; modal analysis; harmonic analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

A scientific instrument known as the Chladni plate is often used for the visualization of sound waves. The patterns generated on these plates are called Chladni figures. Applying the same logic on different materials, different Chladni figures are formed [1, 2]. The Chladni plate is a flat plate, fixed at the center, while being able to vibrate freely when excited externally. If a thin layer of powder or sand is present on the plate, intricate figures are formed as the particles moves in response to the vibrations. The Chladni plate has many applications in the fields of vibration and acoustics. Engineers use it as an instrument to study the behavior of various materials under vibrations and to design materials that could overcome the harmful effects of unwanted vibrations. By studying these patterns of vibrations that are produced on a

Chladni plate, researchers can develop new techniques for reduction of noise and vibrations in various types of structures, aircrafts, and automobiles.

Authors in [3] created a setup with the use of mechanical vibrator, which is able to generate sine wave signals. The Chladni patterns can be formed on aluminum plates of two different shapes, i.e. a 16 cm × 16 cm square plate and a 16 cm diameter circular plate. By sweeping the frequency, Chladni figures are obtained up to frequency of 5000 Hz. In addition, simulations were performed in ANSYS Workbench and were compared with the experimental figures. The error in the frequencies with similar patterns was less than 15%. Authors in [4] prepared a setup using a speaker as an excitation device. Modal analysis was performed in ANSYS, and the results were compared, exhibiting an error of 11%. Authors in [5] added

stiffeners on the plate and studied their effect on the patterns. Authors in [6] studied and simulated the vibration patterns generated on plates with varying thickness. The frequency of vibration can reach the ultrasonic range and the material would have totally different vibration response. Authors in [7] studied the effect of ultrasonic vibrations on the material. The study of the vibration patterns in time and frequency domains has important applications in industry. One of the widely used applications is machine fault detection. Authors in [8] studied the bearing fault detection using time domain analysis and detected faults in industrial bearing using this method.

The ultrasonic vibrations can be applied in different industrial applications. Authors in [9] used ultrasonic excitation vibrations of 22.3 KHz for transporting a load of 4.0 Kgf. Authors in [10] used ultrasonic frequencies for particle size measurement in a batch reactor to monitor the reaction process. Ultrasonic vibration assisted grinding is also used on hard cutting materials like titanium alloys and nickel based super alloys. Authors in [11] worked on developing an ultrasonic based vibration plate sonotrode for grinding applications. Authors in [12] included modal analysis of airborne ultrasonic rectangular plate power transducer to the numerical and experimental work.

In material science, mechanical properties can be studied with the help of Chladni figures. An example of that is Young's modulus, which can be studied by measuring the natural frequencies of the plate. In the medical field, particularly in imaging with the use of ultrasound, ultrasonic Chladni figures play an important role and are used in the visualization of the behavior of tissues and organs. In ultrasonic cleaning, these figures can be used for the effective optimization of the cleaning process. By identifying the resonance frequencies, more powerful cleaning can be provided.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Standing waves are formed on the Chladni plate, depending on the boundary conditions and frequency. The figures are generated as the sprinkled powder moves at the nodal points. The figures generated can be captured. These images are difficult to analyze as the patterns generated are complicated and needed to be pre-processed. As the shapes are miscellaneous, some amount of sprinkled powder may occupy cavities present at anti-nodes, so image filtering is recommended. In image processing, converting captured image in to grey-scale and applying canny edge detection is a way to filter out the unwanted particles.

In simulations, Chladni patterns are formed with the use of the modal analysis concept, in which the mode shapes are generated on the plate at the natural frequencies which are based on the material properties and dimensions of the test specimen. But, in case of harmonic analysis, the external excitation is provided, and the mode shapes are formed at the required frequencies. Both analysis techniques are equally important and are used to simulate the behavior of the Chladni plate. With the use of both analysis techniques, Chladni patterns could be formed in simulations and can be validated with the help of the experimentally generated patterns. The error between the simulated and the experimentally generated

patterns should be investigated as the generated patterns differ slightly from one another.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CURRENT STUDY

This study studies the behavior of Chladni patterns in the ultrasonic frequency range. The results obtained can be used for design and optimization in the performance of various materials, which are regularly in contact with ultrasonic vibrations. In addition, two different methods for the analysis of Chladni plate are considered, which could be useful for researchers and professionals to work on the most appropriate method for their specific applications. This study is limited to stainless-steel Chladni plates and frequencies up to 50000 Hz. The experimental setup and simulation conditions used in this study may not be suitable for other applications. The study assumes that the material properties are available. Overall, these studies demonstrate the effectiveness of different techniques and the importance of validating the simulation results with experimental measurements.

IV. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimentation is performed on a square 160 mm × 160 mm stainless steel plate with thickness of 0.061 mm. In addition, a hole of 3 mm diameter is drilled at the mid-point of the plate. To create a contact between the vibrator (ultrasonic transducer) and the plate, an adhesive is used on a screw and is placed between the plate and the vibrator.

A. Experimental Analysis

The experimental setup is shown in Figure 1. Based on the requirements for the Chladni plate analysis, the following components are used: A Chladni plate made up of stainless steel, an ultrasonic transducer to provide vibrations to the plate at ultrasonic frequencies in the range of 19600 to 50000 Hz, and a MOSFET type controller (frequency generator) to provide the required excitations at the required frequencies. A stand is used to support the transducer. Also, fine salt, a piece of cloth or sponge, and a camera to take snapshots of the Chladni figures were utilized.

Fig. 1. The experimental setup.

B. Experimental Procedure

The steps to be followed for the experimental analysis of the plate are:

- At first, creating a strong contact between the plate and ultrasonic transducer is a must. To do so, a special screw which is available with a transducer is used. That screw is stick with the plate by using a suitable thin adhesive layer.

The layer of adhesive should be as thin as possible as thick layer tends to damp vibrations.

- Afterwards, the screw must be tightened to the transducer, allowing some clearance, as the point of contact between the transducer and the plate must be the screw. An excess point of contact may increase the excitation area which tends to create errors in the figures.
- After the suitable excitation frequency is selected, vibrations are provided to the plate via the transducer. The fine salt is sprinkled on the plate. The amount of salt to be sprinkled on the plate should be just sufficient to trace the patterns. More amount of salt tends to create dense or thick layers which may trace unwanted areas.
- The excitation is switched off only when the salt gets accumulated at the nodal lines. When taking a photograph of the shape the whole plate must be present in the photograph and suitable exposure of light must be ensured.
- After the photograph is taken, the plate must be cleaned with a piece of paper, sponge, or cloth.

Note: While performing the experimentation, the plate must be perpendicular to the excitation source as a slight misalignment creates errors in the figures.

C. Experimental Mode Shapes of the Chladni Plate

Based on the limitations of the controller and ultrasonic transducer, the frequency can only be varied from 19.6 kHz to 50 kHz with intervals ranging from 100 to 500 Hz.

Fig. 2. Mode shapes generated with experimental approach at the same frequency: (a) red crystal powder, (b) fine salt, (c) sand.

Fig. 3. Mode shapes generated from the experimental approach at (a) 19800 Hz, (b) 26000 Hz.

Figure 2 shows photographs of Chladni figures formed at the same frequency for different sprinkling materials. As the patterns are becoming more and more complex with increasing vibration frequency, the nodal lines are getting thinner and thinner. For tracing the figures, fine salt is used. Some captured images of the generated mode shapes can be seen in Figure 3.

V. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

A. Simulation of Mode Shapes on a Square Plate

For simulation and analysis with the ANSYS software, the first step is to create the model of the plate. For this purpose, ANSYS's Design Modeler is used to create the simple geometry of the plate. The next step is to select the plate's material. The material properties of the plate are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF THE CONSIDERED CHLADNI PLATE

Property	Value
Density	7850 kg m ⁻³
Poisson's ratio	0.3
Young's modulus of elasticity	200 GPa

Boundary Conditions: To simulate the experimentation environment accurately, boundary conditions are provided. Boundary conditions are used to define the constraints which are applicable to the physical model. Here, fixed support is provided to the inner part of the hole and excitation is provided to simulate the vibrations of excitation frequencies. In addition, a material library is available in ANSYS and an artificially created new material is added in ANSYS, by providing the basic information of that material.

Mesh Generation: Meshing plays an important role in the generation of patterns. Complex patterns are formed only if the element size is small. But with the reduction in the element size, computation time increases. These simulations are performed by considering the element size between 3 and 6 mm.

B. Modal Analysis of a Square Plate

During the process of modal analysis simulation using ANSYS, the material is assigned to the model of the plate and the value of the number of modes is assigned. The corresponding modal frequencies are calculated, and at those frequencies, the mode shapes are generated. The simulated shapes are as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Mode shapes generated from the modal analysis in ANSYS Workbench. (a) 18944 Hz, (b) 26695 Hz.

C. Harmonic Response Analysis of a Square Plate

In harmonic analysis, again the model is created, the material is selected, but in ANSYS Workbench, instead of selecting modal analysis, harmonic response is selected. Similar to modal analysis, the material is assigned to the geometry, and in the analysis settings, the frequency range in which the mode shapes are to be found is selected. As the experimental and simulated results may have inherited some amount of error, the number of intervals must be wisely chosen. Unlike in modal analysis, where natural frequency values are calculated based on the geometry, here, external excitation must be provided to get response shapes at the required frequencies. The patterns generated during the harmonic response analysis are shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Mode shapes generated from the harmonic response analysis in ANSYS Workbench. (a) 19020 Hz, (b) 26972 Hz.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Experimental Results

Chladni patterns were obtained experimentally on a thin stainless-steel plate at different ultrasonic frequencies.

Fig. 6. Experimental mode shapes: (a) 26000 Hz, (b) 27000 Hz, (c) 32000 Hz, (d) 43800 Hz, (e) 46200 Hz, (f) 46700 Hz.

The patterns were generated on sprinkling fine salt that was placed on the plate. The salt's crystals are dynamic at antinodes

and are forced to move towards nodal points, where they get stability. This stationary behavior of salt particles results in the generation of complex figures at different modal vibrations. Some of these shapes are shown in Figure 6.

B. Simulation Results

For the simulation of Chladni plates, modal and harmonic analysis were performed in ANSYS Workbench. The results of modal analysis are shown in Figure 7 and the results of the harmonic response are shown in Figure 8. In the simulation of modal analysis, a model of a thin steel plate of defined dimensions is created in the Design Modeler of ANSYS. The material is selected from the material library.

Fig. 7. Mode shapes generated from the modal analysis at other frequencies. (a) 22321 Hz, (b) 26994 Hz, (c) 32994 Hz, (d) 41645 Hz, (e) 45363 Hz, (f) 46944 Hz.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND SIMULATED RESULTS

Experimental frequency	Modal analysis	Harmonic response analysis	Error with reference to modal % age	Error with reference to harmonic % age
19800	18944	19020	4.5185	4.1009
24000	22321	22483	7.5221	6.7473
26000	26695	26972	2.6035	3.6040
27000	26994	27615	0.2078	2.2270
32000	32294	32105	0.9135	0.3270
43800	41645	44874	5.1750	2.3935
46200	45363	45247	1.8450	0.5198
46700	46944	46940	0.5198	0.5113

In harmonic response analysis, the material is selected and the model is either created or imported. In this analysis, frequency range is needed to be chosen and the number of intervals is selected. One way to get a specific zone is to generated patterns for say 10000 Hz range having intervals of

100 Hz. As the generated patterns are similar to neighboring patterns up to some extent and once the required patterns are achieved, then the respective range is chosen with intervals of 1 Hz.

Fig. 8. Mode shapes generated from the harmonic response analysis. (a) 22483 Hz, (b) 27615 Hz, (c) 32105 Hz, (d) 44874 Hz, (e) 45247 Hz, (f) 46940 Hz.

The comparison of the experimental and simulation obtained modal frequencies are compared is shown in Table II.

C. Comparison of Simulation and Experimental Results

From the modal and harmonic response analysis in ANSYS, the simulated results were obtained, and these results were compared with the experimentally obtained results. Since the shapes obtained during experimentation and simulations are very complex, they are very difficult to compare visually. So, they can be processed using image processing for comparison. From Table II, it can be seen that the maximum error between the experimental and the simulation results with reference to modal frequencies is 7.52%. Similarly, the maximum error obtained with reference to the harmonic response is 6.74%.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this study, the analysis of modal frequencies and mode shapes of a square-shaped Chladni plate at ultrasonic frequencies are covered. The study is based on the comparison of experimental and simulated results of the Chladni plate at ultrasonic frequencies. The experimental modal analysis was conducted by locking the plate at the mid-point using an ultrasonic transducer as an excitation device. Numerical harmonic response analysis and modal analysis were performed by providing similar constraints in the ANSYS Workbench. Due to the complexity in the produced figures, good agreement

is only found in some results. In some cases, which are not mentioned in the study, the patterns show some common features up to some extent, but 100% similarities cannot be found without the introduction of image processing.

Since in the available literature very little work has been done on the study of modal analysis of plates for the ultrasonic frequency range, this study contributes by exploring this area. For experimentation purposes, an innovative method was adopted, which created unique patterns on the plate at ultrasonic frequencies. This study will help explore the application of ultrasonic vibrations in various industrial applications.

Due to the limitations of the frequency generator and transducer, going above 50000 Hz is unachievable. But in the future, changing plate dimensions and shape, playing with permutations and combinations of frequency, changing the number of transducers, or the power or wattage given to the transducer will bring more complex patterns into the picture. In addition, changes to the boundary conditions and to the material or using the same materials but with different manufacturing processes may result in different patterns. So, it may be possible to identify the manufacturing process without undergoing any other destructive or non-destructive testing.

With increase in the complexity of the patterns, it will become way more difficult to simply compare experimental and simulated images. So, image processing is a must, making tracing or comparing patterns a simpler task.

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A Method for the Determination of Balance Coefficient and Elevator Braking Torque in a Tower Parking Car System

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ABSTRACT

Multistorey car parking systems are a solution that brings many benefits, especially in urban areas as the number of cars increases. This study investigated the elevator of a multistorey car parking system to determine the balance coefficient to reduce driving power and the influence on braking torque. The parameters were calculated based on the establishment of a planning matrix and using the calculation tools and the Taguchi method in the Minitab software. A formula was developed to calculate the braking torque of an elevator, considering the coefficient of the balancing system to ensure optimal driving power. The balance coefficient and the necessary braking torque were determined and the power was reduced by 17.5% while the braking torque was increased by 13.4% compared to the conventional method.

Keywords-counterweight; balance coefficient; brake torque; parking car system; optimal driving power

I. INTRODUCTION

As the number of cars increases and there are fewer and fewer parking spaces, the city traffic increases [1]. Therefore, research on multistorey car parking systems is necessary [2-4]. Multistorey parking car systems are a solution that brings many benefits, especially in urban areas. Many studies investigated parking types and multistorey car parking systems, conducted kinematic and dynamic analyses, and applied finite element methods [3-4]. In [5], two automatic systems were investigated to find the causes of accidents and damage. In [6], the dynamics of the freight elevators were analyzed to find the acceleration of the movement and propose recommendations to increase efficiency. In [7] a similar problem was investigated, which is the dynamic analysis of vertical transport machines in mining.

In [8-12], some structural solutions for parking car systems were proposed. In [8], a mechanical device was proposed for a multi-storey parking system using a lift table. This type of lifting structure has the advantage of not needing anti-sway guidance when lifting but has the disadvantage of a limited lifting height. The invention in [8] also used a self-propelled table-type lifting device running underneath to load the vehicle. This type of system structure is suitable for basements with limited transport height. The invention in [10] is a multistorey parking solution with 2 entry and exit lanes, and each module has an independent lift to load and unload cars vertically. This has the advantage of a fast vehicle loading time and the disadvantage of having to arrange many elevators. In addition, it does not arrange a balancing system when the lifting height is large, thus affecting the engine's driving power. The multistorey parking

car tower in [11] is a structure that uses a central elevator and the counterweights of the balancing system are inserted into the guide columns. This type of structure is suitable for height development due to the balanced system arrangement, but the number of cars on one floor is limited. In [12], a pallet locking system was proposed, which is used to lock car parking pallets with or without vehicles in a multistorey car parking system.

Figure 1 describes the structure of a tower car parking system, with a lifting mechanism used to raise and lower the sliding frame to the corresponding floors. The counterweight and the cable are part of the elevator balance system. This system balances the weights of the sliding frame and the vehicle. The counterweight moves inside the guide column. The proposed design option, shown in Figure 1, allows transport to high altitudes, saving energy due to the balanced arrangement of the system. In addition, the elevator allows for winch transport to multiple parking locations on each floor. In [13], a method was proposed to determine the weight of the cabin and the counterweight of the elevator balancing system. However, this study did not mention the influence of the braking torque or the method for determining it. The load carrying capacity and the weight of the counterweight and the cabin when unloaded are the technical basis for calculating the balance coefficient of the elevator, which is obtained by dividing the difference between the total weight of the counterweight device and the car when unloaded by the rated load capacity of the elevator. In [14-15], it was proposed that the balance coefficient of passenger elevators should be from 0.4 to 0.5. Therefore, the balance coefficient for elevators in multistorey car parking systems does not have capacity optimization guidelines such as passenger elevators.

Fig. 1. Tower car parking system: 1. Sliding guide column, 2. Winches, 3. Counterweight, 4. Sliding frame, 5. Rotating mechanism, 6-7. Car push and pull system, 8. Cable.

The choice of the drive diagram and the weight of the components of the balancing system, in addition to greatly affecting the driving power, also affect the required braking torque. Moreover, the braking time and distance need to be guaranteed. This study aimed to determine the counterweight through the balance coefficient to ensure optimal driving power. Then the expression for calculating the elevator braking torque was established, taking into account the factors of the balancing system. The experimental research method calculated the parameters based on a planning matrix, the Taguchi method, and the Minitab software. The Taguchi method was also used in [16-19]. The results of the study helped determine the balance coefficient and the braking torque required according to the optimal power of elevators in tower car parking systems.

II. CALCULATION METHOD

A. Power and Balance Coefficient

There are two specific working states of the elevator, including the full load case, braking when lowering the slide frame at the bottom (Figure 2(a)), and the unloaded case, braking when lowering the counterweight at the bottom (Figure 2(b)). Ignoring the auxiliary forces, the dynamic load components, and the weight of the lifting cable, the unbalanced weight in the case of a load is $(G_1+G_2-G_3)$. The unbalanced weight in the unloaded case is (G_3-G_2) . When considering the unbalanced weight in two equal cases, the following equation arises:

$$G_3 = 0.5G_1 + G_2 \tag{1}$$

where G_1 is the weight of the car (N), G_2 is the weight of the sliding frame (N), and G_3 is the weight of the counterweight (N). In calculating passenger elevators, the weight counterweight is determined by the balance coefficient ψ [14-15]. The weight of the counterweight is given by:

$$G_3 = G_2 + \psi G_1 \tag{2}$$

where ψ is the balance coefficient. In the design of passenger elevators, the balance coefficient ψ is in the range of 0.4 - 0.5 [14-15]. In a multi-story parking car system, the weight of the car varies according to its type, but the difference is not much.

Fig. 2. Calculation diagrams: (a) in the case of full load, brake when lowering the sliding frame at the bottom. (b) in the case of no load, brake when lowering the counterweight at the bottom.

When excluding the effect of dynamic load, in the case of full load and braking when lowering the sliding frame at the bottom, the power is calculated according to (3). In the case of no load and braking when lowering the counterweight at the bottom, the power is calculated according to (4):

$$N_1 = \frac{S_2 - S_1}{1000\eta} v = \frac{W_{ms} + \gamma H g + G_1(1 - \psi)}{1000\eta} v \tag{3}$$

$$N_2 = \frac{S_2 - S_1}{1000\eta} v = \frac{\psi G_1 + \gamma H g - W_{ms}}{1000\eta} v \tag{4}$$

where S_1 is the small tension force (N), S_2 is the large tension force (N), v is the lifting or lowering speed (m/s), γ is the cable density per meter (kg/m), g is the gravitational acceleration (m/s^2), W_{ms} are the auxiliary barrier components (N), H is the design lifting height (m), and η is the system's performance.

Fig. 3. Drive diagram of the winch: 1. Friction drum, 2. Screw wheel, 3. Screw shaft, 4. Brake, 5. Motor.

B. Determining the Braking Torque while taking into Account the Balancing System Factors

In the general case of braking when lowering the sliding frame with full load (Figure 2(a)), the mechanism driving diagram is shown in Figure 3. Kinetic energy ΔKE is determined by:

$$\Delta KE = \left(\frac{I_d}{2i_{23}^2} + \frac{I_{g2}}{2i_{23}^2} + \frac{I_{g3} + I_{g4} + I_5}{2} \right) \omega_m^2 + \frac{(G_1 + G_2)v^2}{2g} + \frac{\gamma H v^2}{2g} - \frac{(G_2 + \psi G_1)v^2}{2g} \quad (5)$$

where I_{g2} and I_{g3} are the moments of inertia of worm gear 2 and worm shaft 3 (kgm^2), I_{g4} and I_{g5} are the moments of inertia of the brake wheel and engine rotor (kgm^2), I_d is the drum moment of inertia (kgm^2), i_{23} is the transmission ratio, and ω_m is the angular velocity at the brake axis (rad/s).

The potential energy ΔPE_r of the cable suspending the load when it changes position from $y_1 = H - s$ to $y_2 = H$ is determined by:

$$\Delta PE_r = \gamma g \int_{y_1}^{y_2} y dy = \frac{\gamma g}{2} [H^2 - (H - s)^2] \quad (6)$$

where s is the braking distance, and y is the position of the considered part (m). The potential energy ΔPE_{rp} of the counterweight suspension cable when it changes position from $y_{1p} = s$ to $y_{2p} = 0$ is given by:

$$\Delta PE_{rp} = \gamma g \int_{y_{1p}}^{y_{2p}} y dy = -\frac{\gamma g}{2} s^2 \quad (7)$$

The potential energy ΔPE of the system in Figure 2(a) is represented by:

$$\Delta PE = (G_1 + G_2)s + \frac{\gamma g}{2} [H^2 - (H - s)^2] - (G_2 + \psi G_1)s - \frac{\gamma g}{2} s^2 \quad (8)$$

The movement of sliding frame 4 and counterweight 3 (Figure 1) is in the vertical direction, so the energy change due to braking is the sum of changes in kinetic and potential energy and other work on the system. Therefore, the energy change ΔE (N/m) can be written as:

$$\Delta E = \Delta KE + \Delta PE + \Delta W_{ms} \quad (9)$$

where ΔW_{ms} is the input to the system due to secondary resistances. Substituting into (9):

$$\Delta E = \left(\frac{I_d}{2i_{23}^2} + \frac{I_{g2}}{2i_{23}^2} + \frac{I_{g3} + I_{g4} + I_5}{2} \right) \omega_m^2 + \frac{(G_1 + G_2)v^2}{2g} + \frac{\gamma H v^2}{2g} - \frac{(G_2 + \psi G_1)v^2}{2g} + (G_1 + G_2)s + \frac{\gamma g}{2} [H^2 - (H - s)^2] - (G_2 + \psi G_1)s - \frac{\gamma g}{2} s^2 - W_{ms}s \quad (10)$$

Assuming rotation speed from the initial value ω_m lifting speed v , and final speed $\omega_m = 0$, $v = 0$. It is assumed that the braking process slows down the speed uniformly. The distance the sliding frame will travel down during deceleration due to braking is deduced from the acceleration formula $a = ds/dt^2$ at the initial conditions $s(0) = 0$ and $ds(0)/dt = 0$.

Calculating the same math for the Figure 2(b) diagram gives:

$$\Delta E = \left(\frac{I_d}{2i_{23}^2} + \frac{I_{g2}}{2i_{23}^2} + \frac{I_{g3} + I_{g4} + I_5}{2} \right) \omega_m^2 - \frac{G_2 v^2}{2g} + \frac{(G_2 + \psi G_1)v^2}{2g} + \frac{\gamma H v^2}{2g} - G_2 s - \frac{\gamma g}{2} s^2 + \frac{\gamma g}{2} [H^2 - (H - s)^2] + (G_2 + \psi G_1)s + W_{ms}s \quad (11)$$

The work done W to brake or stop a mechanical system is in equilibrium with the total energy change ΔE , transformed and calculated by:

$$W = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (\omega_m - at) T dt = T(\omega_m - \frac{at}{2})t = \Delta E \quad (12)$$

where a is the rotation angle of the active brake (rad), t is the braking time, and $t_1 = 0$, $t_2 = t(s)$. In the case of braking, the speed decreases from ω_m to zero. Assuming the braking torque is constant and that the speed when braking is gradually slowing down, the required braking torque T (Nm) is given by:

$$T = \frac{2\Delta E}{(\omega_m + \omega_t)t} = \frac{2\Delta E}{\omega_m t} \quad (13)$$

where ω_t is the angular velocity at the end of braking (rad/s).

C. Test Method

Figure 4 describes the calculation method and numerical experimental procedure, using the established analytical formula to calculate driving power and braking torque, considering the influence of the balancing system.

Fig. 4. Computational method and numerical experimental procedure.

Table I shows the factors of the test example. The test parameters include the counterweight, the balance coefficient, the braking time, and the lifting height. Table II shows the survey parameters and value levels. The response functions are driving power N_1 , N_2 and braking torque T_1 , T_2 . The planning matrix is selected according to the Taguchi method and Minitab software. Table III shows the L16 planning matrix used for experimental analysis.

TABLE I. INDEPENDENT PARAMETERS

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Weight of the car	G_1	25500	N
Weight of sliding frame	G_2	16000	N
Moment of inertia of worm wheel 2	I_{g2}	0.295938	kgm ²
Screw moment of inertia 3	I_{g3}	0.000757	kgm ²
Brake wheel moment of inertia	I_{gd}	0.192668	kgm ²
Engine rotor moment of inertia	I_{g5}	0.082	kgm ²
Moment of inertia of friction drum	I_d	31.462	kgm ²
Cable weight per 1 meter long	γ	3.96	Kg/m
Lifting or lowering speed	v	1	m/s
Gravitational acceleration	g	9.81	m/s ²
Transmission ratio	I_{23}	39.6	
The secondary resistance moves the sliding frame	W_{ms}	2800	N

TABLE II. FACTORS AND VALUE LEVELS

Influential factors	Code	Value level				Range of change
		1	2	3	4	
Balance coefficient ψ	x_1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9	0.6
Braking time t , s	x_2	1	2	3	4	3
Lifting height H , m	x_3	10	15	20	25	15

TABLE III. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN USING L16 ORTHOGONAL ARRAY

N	x_1	x_2	x_3	T_1 (Nm)	T_2 (Nm)	N_1 (kW)	N_2 (kW)
1	1	1	1	158.5	126.5	22.82	5.7
2	1	2	2	131.2	100	23	5.9
3	1	3	3	122.8	92	23.3	6.11
4	1	4	4	119.3	88.5	23.5	6.32
5	2	1	2	122.7	161	17.53	11.45
6	2	2	1	95.6	132.4	17.32	11.23
7	2	3	4	89.4	126.9	18	11.87
8	2	4	3	83.5	120.8	18	11.87
9	3	1	3	87	196.3	12.41	17.2
10	3	2	4	63.1	170	12.41	17.41
11	3	3	1	50.8	156.6	11.78	16.78
12	3	4	2	47.8	153	12	17
13	4	1	4	50	231	6.87	22.96
14	4	2	3	26.5	202	6.66	22.75
15	4	3	2	17.34	191.5	6.66	22.53
16	4	4	1	12	185.5	6.23	22.32

The Signal to Noise (S/N) ratio for the problem is given by:

$$S/N = -10 \lg \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{u=1}^n Y_{iu}^2 \right) \quad (14)$$

where u is the experimental sequence number, n is the number of experiments, and Y_i is the response value $Y_i = N_i$, $Y_i = T_i$. The influence of the parameters was calculated, and the results were analyzed to choose a reasonable value with the response functions. At first, the driving power N_i was calculated. Then, brake torque T_i was calculated and selected according to reasonable driving power parameters.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

The Minitab software was used to calculate and create the graphs. The amount of counterweight G_3 , through the balance coefficient ψ , has a decisive influence on the driving power. The driving power in the full-load case N_i varies inversely with

the power in the no-load case N_2 when $\psi = 0.3 - 0.9$. The reasonable power value in Figure 5 was determined to be $N = 14.6$ kW, and correspondingly in Figure 6, a reasonable balance coefficient was obtained according to the capacity $N = 14.6$ kW as $\psi = 0.61$. ψ was chosen as 0.61 according to the reasonable capacity corresponding to the S/N ratios of -36 (Figure 7) and -43.3 (Figure 8). With the corresponding S/N ratios, the braking time is $t = 2$ s, and the design lifting height according to the technical requirements $H = 18$ m. Acceleration is $a = 1$ m/s², and the braking distance when lowering is $s = 1$ m. Table IV shows the calculation results with the balance coefficients in [14-15], using (1), (2), (13) with $\psi = 0.5$ and reasonable values, finding that the power decreased by 17.5%, while the braking torque only increased by 13.4%.

Fig. 5. Determining reasonable power.

Fig. 6. Influence parameters on driving power N_1 .

Fig. 7. Analysis of the influence of S/N ratios on braking torque, when braking lowers the fully loaded sliding frame at the bottom.

Fig. 8. Analysis of the influence of S/N ratios on braking torque, when braking raises the unloaded sliding frame at the top.

TABLE IV. COMPARISON OF RESPONSE VALUES

Parameter	ψ	N_1 (kW)	N_2 (kW)	T_1 (Nm)	T_2 (Nm)
Choosing according to the usual method	0.5	17.7	11.6	97	134
Reasonable value	0.61	14.6		152	
Compare results	+22%	-17.5%		+13.4%	

B. Discussion

Analyzing the S/N ratio shows that the braking torque is most heavily dependent on the amount of counterweight through the balance coefficient. Then there is the braking time. Lifting height has little effect on power and braking torque. Choosing a reasonable balance coefficient will contribute to saving energy for multi-story parking car systems. The influence of a car's weight on the balance coefficient requires further evaluation. However, the power and braking torque values in this test considered the maximum value of the car weight, so they can meet the working requirements of the elevator. The parameters of the balancing system also affect the traction capacity of the friction drum. The pull capacity of the winch can be adjusted by a reasonable cable groove on the

friction drum and the cable embrace angle on the friction drum without changing the balance coefficient.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a method for determining the weight of the counterweight in a tower car parking system, through the balance coefficient to ensure optimal driving power and established an expression to calculate elevator brake torque, considering the elements of the balanced system. The calculation method to determine the balance coefficient to optimize power and braking torque was based on a planning matrix, Taguchi analysis, and Minitab software. The results of the experimental calculations of the parameters to select an optimal driving power were a balance coefficient $\psi = 0.61$, acceleration $a = 1 \text{ m/s}^2$, and a braking distance when lowering $s = 1 \text{ m}$. Compared to the conventional method where $\psi = 0.5$, the power was reduced by 17.5% and the braking torque was increased by 13.4%. Choosing a reasonable balance coefficient will contribute to saving energy for multi-story car parking systems. The braking torque depends most heavily on the amount of counterweight through the balance coefficient. Then there is the braking time. Lifting height has little effect on power and braking torque. Future research would be to apply this calculation method to investigate the pull capacity of the winch.

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Effects of Concrete Substrate Condition on Fiber-Reinforced Composite Strength Properties

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the effects of concrete substrate conditions on the strength properties of fiber-reinforced composites through experimental research. The method of concrete surface preparation and moisture conditions were considered crucial parameters that have a significant impact on Fiber-Reinforced Composite (FRC) strength properties. Four different concrete surfaces were examined: grinded (CSP 2), sanded (CSP 3), scabbed (CSP 8), and unprepared (CSP 1), all under various moisture conditions: dry concrete substrate, saturated surface dry concrete substrate, and wet concrete substrate. A mix design conforming to the C25 grade concrete was formulated, cured in water for 7 and 28 days to achieve the desired design strength values. The dry surface specimens were cured in the air for at least 24 hr before subsequent preparations, the wet surface specimens were cured in water for at least 24 hr, while the saturated surface dry specimens were cured in water for 24 hours and then removed from the water and cured in the air for 1 hr. The prepared samples were carbon-wrapped with unidirectional SikaWrap-300 C and Sikadur 300 resin and then subjected to a uniaxial compressive strength test until failure after 24 hr of curing using a load of 0.2 MPa/sec. The collected data showed that the surface roughness of the CSP 8 under wet moisture conditions exhibited the best bond strength due to the increase in surface area for adhesive bond contact, while the wet substrate condition increased hydration on the adhesive side of the interface, which directly contributed to the increase in bond strength. All substrate conditions demonstrated cohesive cracking of the concrete substrate leading to displacement of the FRP-concrete interface before FRP rupture.

Keywords-FRP composite materials; concrete substrate; concrete surface profiles

I. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is an important part of the economy of Kenya and one of the drivers of economic growth. It is part of the major pillars of Vision 2030 that seeks to increase the country's gross domestic product and propel Kenya towards becoming Africa's industrial hub. The Kenyan construction industry has been under immense pressure not only to provide affordable housing and related infrastructure facilities under the Kenya Big Four Agenda but also to guarantee a safe built environment. In the last three decades, the construction sector in the country has been characterized by

unsafe buildings that are dangerous for human habitation. Building failure is one of the dominant challenges facing the industry in Kenya, as more than 100 cases of building collapse have been recorded since 1990. Structural failure in buildings at the time of construction or after completion can cause human casualties, wasted money, social disturbance, clashes, and claims between stakeholders [1]. An audit carried out in 2018 by the National Buildings Inspectorate (NBI) covering 14,925 buildings revealed that 723 (4.8%) were very dangerous, 10,791 (72.3%) were unsafe, 1217 (8.25%) were fair, and 2194 (14.7%) were safe. It is estimated that over 200 people have lost their lives since 1990 in building collapses, with thousands

injured. The economy has also lost more than Kshs 2.4 billion worth of investments. Additionally, according to research conducted in 2020 by the National Construction Authority, of 87 documented cases of building collapses, 66% of the buildings collapsed during the utilization stage, while 34% collapsed while still under construction. Evaluation of existing reinforced concrete structures has become a necessary and important process for engineers on a large scale due to the aging of existing structures and buildings, as reinforced concrete has become a global construction material during the last decades [2]. Structural evaluation and past research in the Kenyan construction industry have revealed that a large number of existing facilities need maintenance, retrofitting, rehabilitation, and restoration as a result of natural or man-made factors and causes such as natural disasters, earthquakes, wars, conflicts, and other sudden causes that lead to various degrees of damage. The 2015 National Building Maintenance Policy recommends a periodic five-year inspection of all categories of buildings, while there should be a critical inspection of buildings aged 30 years and older to detect signs of failure.

The recent change in economic balance from removal-replacement toward building rehabilitation has been rapid and inevitable in Kenya. Therefore, the most economical and effective techniques for structural rehabilitation are needed. Structural rehabilitation represents a very essential aspect of the construction industry, and its importance is increasing. There are numerous methods available, each with different benefits and shortcomings. Traditional methods of repairing and strengthening concrete structures can be widening the cross-section, using external pre-stressing or steel plate bonding, concrete jacketing, demolition and recasting afresh, etc. However, the cost of strengthening and maintenance repairs with these traditional materials and their vulnerability to environmental effects, leading to corrosion and shorter life spans, motivated engineers to look for alternative materials and methods. In addition, these methods involve bulky work and do not offer simple and quick solutions to the rehabilitation of structures. As a result, there is a rapid shift to superior modern methods of structural rehabilitation around the world, especially in developed countries, due to the growing need for faster and more economical retrofitting techniques due to the ever-aging infrastructure and damage caused by major catastrophic events [3]. FRP composites represent the latest advances in this regard, as they have superior durability and versatility compared to traditional construction materials. Their lightweight, high strength, low profile, corrosion resistance, and ease of application provide additional advantages in cases where steel- or concrete-based solutions are bulky and impractical.

Structural strengthening using FRP carbon fiber has been used around the world since the late 1980s [4]. In Kenya, it was first introduced and used successfully in 2011, when the leading manufacturers SIKA Kenya and BASF Kenya were established in the country. FR composites are high-strength materials that have been used in the aerospace, marine, and automotive industries. Recently, there has been a significant increase in the use of FRP composites in civil engineering applications to repair and retrofit existing structures,

particularly concrete and masonry buildings and bridges [5-6]. Locally, FRP carbon fiber technology has been used successfully to strengthen deficient structures and, recently, it was used to shear reinforce columns at the Hazina Trade Center in 2018.

Although the use of carbon fiber to reinforce concrete has been under massive development, little research has been done in Kenya. Most of the time, Kenyan applicators rely on the information given by manufacturers through product data sheets or webinars. Several studies have been conducted throughout the world on the use of carbon fiber in concrete strengthening. The studies focused on the application of FRP in structural strengthening due to its advantages, such as durability, versatility, low cost, and practicability. The fiber matrix interface is essential for the performance of fiber-reinforced composites. In [7], it was shown that the bond behavior between CFRP and concrete depends on the roughness of the concrete surface. In [8-9], it was deduced that the bond behavior between CFRP and concrete depends on the moisture conditions. In [10], it was concluded that the state of the base concrete (substrate) affects the bonding properties with FR composites, as the roughness of the concrete substrate has a crucial impact on the bond strength between the FRP and the concrete interface. In [11], it was found that the shear-friction mechanism that occurs in the interface zone is directly related to the roughness of the concrete crack interfaces. In [12], poor bonding in the interface zone was shown to lead to two main failures of the concrete overlays: debonding and cracks. In [13], it was established that to improve the mechanical properties of the concrete-resin interface zone, the concrete surface should be modified using different methods. In [14], it was concluded that different methods can be used to modify the concrete surface.

According to the International Concrete Repair Institute (ICRI), there are 10 distinct concrete surface profiles, named CSP 1 to CSP 10. The lower profile numbers are smoother (CSP 1 is nearly flat), and the higher numbers get progressively rougher. Although many studies have been conducted on the application of FRP in structural strengthening focusing on the bond behavior between CFRP and the concrete substrate, there are no conclusive studies on the concrete surface profile and the moisture condition that gives the highest bond strength between them. This study aimed to examine the profile of the concrete surface and the moisture conditions that demonstrate the best bond strength between CFRP and the concrete substrate. This study examined four different concrete surfaces, unprepared (CSP 1), grinded (CSP 2), sanded (CSP 3), and scabbed (CSP 8), all under various moisture conditions: dry concrete substrate, saturated surface dry concrete substrate, and wet concrete substrate. The objective was to evaluate the effect of concrete substrate condition on the strength properties of a retrofitted fiber-reinforced composite. The results can guide the construction industry on the best concrete surface and moisture conditions when using CFRP to strengthen concrete.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used to create the concrete mixture were Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) Type 32.5 N, river sand, coarse aggregate with a maximum aggregate size of 20 mm,

and clean water. Materials were sourced from a reliable supplier while clean drinking water was obtained for the concrete formulation from the JKUAT laboratory. Unidirectional 300 g carbon fiber wraps, also denoted 300 C, obtained from Sika Kenya Limited, including the Sikadur 300

resin recommended by the manufacturer, were used with the wrapping fabric. A mix design conforming to C25-grade concrete was formulated [15]. Table I represents a summary of the design of the formulated mix.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF MIX DESIGN FOR C25 GRADE CONCRETE

Nominal strength (N/mm ²)	Batch weights per 1m ³ at SSD (Kg)			Water (Kgs)	Water cement ratio	Actual slump (mm)	Ratios for batching by weight		
	10/20mm aggregates	River sand	Cement (32.5 N)				C : RS : B		
25	1070	600	450	210	0.47	45	1	1.3	2.4

The constituent concrete materials were mixed in a tilting drum mixer (laboratory type) until a homogeneous concrete mix was formulated. Fine aggregate and cement were added and mixed for two minutes. The coarse aggregate was then added and mixed for another two minutes before continuously adding water and mixing for another two minutes. The concrete mix was then removed from the mixer and used to cast the cylindrical concrete specimens. The slump test readings for all the formulated batches were found to be within the designed range of 30-60 mm, indicating a medium degree of workability.

The wet concrete was added to the cylindrical molds in 3 layers, after which tapping was performed to compact the concrete. This process was repeated until the cylindrical molds were full. The interior of the cylindrical molds was ensured to be oiled to prevent the concrete from sticking to the sides. A total number of 66 cylindrical concrete specimens were prepared, 30 of which were used as control samples and 36 were adopted as study samples. All cylindrical specimens had a slenderness ratio equal to 2 (height $H = 200$ mm and outer diameter $D = 100$ mm). The concrete specimens were then cured in water for a period of 7 and 28 days to achieve the desired design strengths before further preparation and testing. The cured study specimens were grouped into four clusters so that each one had 9 specimens. Then, each specimen was labeled using a permanent marker on the top and bottom.

Four different concrete surfaces, following ICRI Guideline No. 310.2R–2013, were examined: grinded (CSP 2), sanded (CSP 3), scabbed (CSP 8), and unprepared (CSP 1), all under various moisture conditions: dry concrete substrate (DS), saturated surface dry concrete substrate (SSD), and wet concrete substrate (WS). The CSP 1 profile was achieved using oiled steel molds that ensured that the specimens had a uniform and smooth surface finish. The CSP 2 profile was achieved by grinding the surface of specimens using an abrasive tool with a diamond disc to achieve a fairly smooth finish. The CSP 3 profile, also known as light shortblast, was achieved by sanding, while the CSP 8 profile was achieved by hacking the surfaces of the specimens using a pointed chisel and hammer. The dry surface samples were cured in air for at least 24 hours before subsequent preparations and testing, while the wet samples were cured in water for at least 24 hours before subsequent preparations and tests. The samples with the saturated surface dry condition were cured in water for 24 hours, then removed from the water and cured in the air for 1 hour, so that the surface particles were dry but the interior particle voids were saturated with water.

Fig. 1. Study specimens grouped and labeled.

Fig. 2. Cutting the wrapping fabric into the desired sizes.

Fig. 3. Wrapped study specimens.

After surface preparation, the samples were wrapped in one layer of 300 g unidirectional carbon fiber wrap from Sika Kenya Ltd. The selected wrapping fabric was cut with special scissors in the desired sizes. The epoxy resin was mixed and applied to the surfaces of the prepared specimens before the application of the wrapping fabric in the wet epoxy resin. Excess air was removed using rollers and the specimen was left to cure. The application method followed the manufacturer's specifications. The carbon-wrapped samples were then subjected to compressive strength tests to assess the effects of concrete substrate conditions on the strength properties of a retrofitted fiber-reinforced composite. The specimens were placed centrally between the compressive test machine plates, and then a load was applied at a uniform rate, with approximately a stress rate of 12 MPa/min until the test specimen failed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table II shows the compressive strength results. It can be observed that there is a general strength increase from the CSP 1 to the CSP 8 substrate condition, as shown in Figure 4. Roughness imparts an additional surface area with which the adhesive can contact when forming a bond. Normally, the adhesive is absorbed by capillary attraction into the added surface pits, increasing the surface area of bond contact, and this is the reason why the CSP 8 substrate condition demonstrated the highest bond behavior with the FRP carbon fiber wrap. The wet moisture condition shows the best bond behavior between the concrete interface and the FRP for all but the CSP 1. Interfaces where the substrate surface is prewetted such that moisture movement from the epoxy is minimized, lead to reduced porosity and increased hydration on the epoxy side of the interface, which increases bond strength. This explains why the wet moisture condition showed the best bond behavior, as shown in Figure 5.

TABLE II. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF THE SAMPLES

Specimen category	Specimen ref. no.	Height of specimen (mm)	Diameter of specimen (mm)	Failure load (kN)	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)	Equivalent cube compressive strength (N/mm ²)	Average compressive strength (N/mm ²)	Standard deviation strength (N/mm ²)		
Unprepared (CSP 1)	CSP 1-DS 1	200	100	264.30	33.65	42.06	41.25	0.80		
	CSP 1-DS 2	200	100	259.20	33.00	41.25				
	CSP 1-DS 3	200	100	254.20	32.36	40.45				
	Unprepared (CSP 1)	CSP 1-WS 1	200	100	251.70	32.04	40.05	37.97	2.11	
		CSP 1-WS 2	200	100	238.89	30.41	38.01			
		CSP 1-WS 3	200	100	225.23	28.67	35.84			
		Unprepared (CSP 1)	CSP 1-SSD 1	200	100	252.13	32.10	40.12	41.09	1.95
			CSP 1-SSD 2	200	100	272.28	34.66	43.33		
			CSP 1-SSD 3	200	100	250.19	31.85	39.81		
Grinded (CSP 2)	CSP 2-DS 1	200	100	231.84	29.51	36.89	34.65	2.40		
	CSP 2-DS 2	200	100	219.58	27.95	34.94				
	CSP 2-DS 3	200	100	201.88	25.70	32.13				
	Grinded (CSP 2)	CSP 2-WS 1	200	100	269.92	34.36	42.95	42.69	1.18	
		CSP 2-WS 2	200	100	274.67	34.97	43.71			
		CSP 2-WS 3	200	100	260.12	33.11	41.39			
	Grinded (CSP 2)	CSP 2-SSD 1	200	100	248.61	31.65	39.56	39.57	0.54	
		CSP 2-SSD 2	200	100	252.02	32.08	40.10			
		CSP 2-SSD 3	200	100	245.27	31.22	39.03			
Sanded (CSP 3)	CSP 3-DS 1	200	100	272.34	34.67	43.34	41.89	2.28		
	CSP 3-DS 2	200	100	246.73	31.41	39.26				
	CSP 3-DS 3	200	100	270.69	34.46	43.08				
	Sanded (CSP 3)	CSP 3-WS 1	200	100	265.62	33.82	42.27	42.39	0.65	
		CSP 3-WS 2	200	100	262.74	33.45	41.81			
		CSP 3-WS 3	200	100	270.76	34.47	43.09			
	Sanded (CSP 3)	CSP 3-SSD 1	200	100	217.68	27.71	34.64	37.42	2.43	
		CSP 3-SSD 2	200	100	245.97	31.31	39.14			
		CSP 3-SSD 3	200	100	241.88	30.79	38.49			
Scabbed (CSP 8)	CSP 8-DS 1	200	100	268.69	34.21	42.76	42.25	2.23		
	CSP 8-DS 2	200	100	277.59	35.34	44.17				
	CSP 8-DS 3	200	100	250.16	31.85	39.81				
	Scabbed (CSP 8)	CSP 8-WS 1	200	100	274.28	34.92	43.65	43.86	0.61	
		CSP 8-WS 2	200	100	279.94	35.64	44.55			
		CSP 8-WS 3	200	100	272.63	34.71	43.38			
	Scabbed (CSP 8)	CSP 8-SSD 1	200	100	189.42	24.11	30.14	28.72	2.71	
		CSP 8-SSD 2	200	100	160.87	20.48	25.60			
		CSP 8-SSD 3	200	100	191.16	24.34	30.42			

Fig. 4. Influence of grinded, sanded, scabbed, and unprepared concrete surfaces on the effectiveness of reinforcement using CFRP.

Fig. 5. Influence of surface roughness and moisture condition on the effectiveness of CFRP reinforcement.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The compressive strength results showed that the concrete surface and moisture condition had a significant effect on the bond strength between CFRP and the concrete interface. Among the four specimen categories, from CSP 1 to CSP 8, the latter in wet moisture conditions demonstrated the highest bond strength between CFRP and the concrete substrate. It was observed that there was a general increase in strength from CSP 1 to CSP 8 concrete substrate condition. Roughness creates additional surface area with which the adhesive can make contact when forming a bond. Normally, the adhesive is absorbed by capillary attraction into the added surface pits increasing the surface area of bond contact, and this is the reason why the CSP 8 concrete substrate condition demonstrated the highest bond strength with the CFRP wrap. In addition, the wet moisture condition showed the best bond behavior between the concrete interface and FRP reinforcement for all except the CSP 1 concrete substrate condition. A prewetted substrate surface interface, such that moisture movement from the epoxy is minimized, leads to reduced porosity and increased hydration on the epoxy side of the interface, directly contributing to the increased bond strength. The CSP 8 surface roughness in wet moisture condition demonstrated the best bond strength due to the combined

factors of increased surface area for adhesive bond contact and increased hydration on the adhesive side of the interface. This directly contributed to the increased bond strength.

Furthermore, it was inferred that CFRP wrapping led to a significant increase in concrete strength of samples cured for 7 and 28 days compared to some unwrapped concrete control samples. The samples cured for 7 days showed a 116% strength increase after carbon wrapping while the samples cured for 28 days showed a 79% strength increase. When introducing a CFRP to a concrete member, the section is confined and the stresses are unable to lead to typical failure mechanisms. The addition of a carbon fiber wrap increases the capacity of the concrete and provides additional strength in axial, bursting, and flexural loading.

This study helps understanding the impact of the concrete substrate condition on the strength properties of fiber-reinforced composites. The findings on the concrete substrate surface that gives the highest bond strength will enhance and increase the use of carbon fiber for structural strengthening and rehabilitation of structures, especially in this era of increased infrastructural development in the country. In addition, most of the old and unsafe structures that would otherwise have been demolished will be secured for continued use. This study also provides engineering professionals and contractors with valuable information on structural strengthening using CFRP. This will also improve the service life and maintenance of structures that require strengthening to reach full design life and will ensure and guarantee a safe built environment for all.

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A Study of an Empirical Sequent Depths Equation of the Hydraulic Jump in a Horizontal Trapezoidal Channel

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ABSTRACT

This study used existing studies and incorporated Pi theory to establish the connection between the sequent depth ratio (y_2/y_1) and the influencing factors (Fr_1 and M_1) on the hydraulic jump on a smooth horizontal trapezoidal channel, using a physical model with a side slope of 1:1. The study proposed four equations, from which the empirical equation (Y_3) was used to calculate the y_2/y_1 ratio of the steady jump ($4.0 \leq Fr_1 \leq 9.0$). An analysis of statistical indicators for (Y_3) showed that the maximum error was 7.4%, R^2 was 0.98, and other statistical indicators were close to the ideal point at zero (MSE = 0.027, RMSE = 0.163, MEA = 0.129, and MAPE \approx 2.2%). Furthermore, statistical analysis for test data also provided good results ($R^2 = 0.94$, MSE = 0.107, RMSE = 0.327, MEA = 0.25, and MAPE \approx 3.7%), and the maximum error reached 8.8%. Therefore, the proposed equation ensures that the calculated values can be used in practice.

Keywords-hydraulic jump; sequent depth; trapezoidal channel; empirical equation; Bélanger

I. INTRODUCTION

The hydraulic jump, discovered by Leonardo da Vinci in the 16th century, is used to design energy-efficient structures on the toe of spillways and other applications [1-3]. The hydraulic jump zone is a disturbance between water and air, creating complex rollers and causing energy loss. The hydraulic structure of the jump can be simulated by the Navier-Stokes equation and solved by simplifying the hydraulic factors [4-5]. Bélanger was the first to propose an equation to calculate the sequent depth of the jump in a rectangular channel [6]. Later, scientists improved this equation by including other influencing factors, such as shear stress [7] and the kinetic energy correction factor $\alpha = 1.045$ [8]. In [9], an empirical coefficient μ was introduced that depends on the inflow Froude number (Fr_1). As there is currently no adequate theoretical equation for the trapezoidal channel, most studies are experimental or semi-empirical. Although there has been relatively little study on the hydraulic jump in trapezoidal channels and there has been minimal appraisal of its applications, this phenomenon does occur frequently and has some significance in the design of dissipative energy structures.

The equation of the sequent depth ratio (y_2/y_1) of the jump depends on many factors. The critical depth of flow (y_c) can be

mentioned in the empirical sequent depth equation [5]. In [10], the equation of momentum was used to develop a quadratic phenomenon equation to determine y_2/y_1 based on the Fr_1 and M_1 coefficients. Based on the experimental values of the physical model, a graph of the relationship between y_2/y_1 and Fr_1 was built, according to M_1 , and tested with experimental data with theoretical curves in case of a jump in a trapezoidal channel with a 1:1 side slope. In [11], the momentum balance equation was used to determine the upstream and downstream cross-sections of the jump, forming an equation to determine the jump's y_2/y_1 for a smooth horizontal trapezoidal channel disregarding friction and solving it to determine the jump's subsequent depths using diagrams or tables. However, this study only examined theoretical data. In [12], the correlation between y_2/y_1 and Fr_1 of the hydraulic jump was examined in a trapezoidal channel with a side slope angle of 76.2° and a channel slope ranging from -0.005 to 0.02. This study constructed a linear empirical equation between y_2/y_1 and Fr_1 without considering the value of M_1 . In [13], experimental research was conducted on the sequent depth of the hydraulic jump in a trapezoidal channel with dimensions of 10 m in length and 0.2 m in bed width, and the results were similar to [12] but with variations in the experimental coefficients. In [14], experimental research was carried out on the jump in the trapezoidal channel with a trapezoidal cross-section of 0.2 m in

6 m bed width and a side angle of 72.68° . This study determined seven empirical equations for each case of y_1 and Fr_1 . However, as it was widely dispersed and poorly organized, it is challenging to translate these results into a practical equation. In [15], the hydraulic jump was investigated in a channel system that abruptly changed from a trapezoidal channel with a side angle of 73° , 4 m length, and 20 cm bed width to a rectangular channel with 0.6 m width and 6 m length, showing that the subsequent depths of the jump will depend on where the jump toe first appears in each channel. In [16], a horizontal trapezoidal channel with side slopes 1:1 and 1:1.5 and a bed width of 0.2 m was examined, creating empirical linear and nonlinear equations to gauge Fr_1 according to the y_2/y_1 and the M_1 coefficient. The limitation of this study was that the R^2 coefficient was not high, with values of 0.814 and 0.802, respectively, the relationships did not have enough data (there were 8 values for the case of the side slope 1:1.5 and 9 values for the case of the side slope 1:1), and Fr_1 had very little change (from 4.0 to 5.5). In [17], experimental research was carried out on 3 types of side slopes (0.26, 0.58, and 1.0) with bed width 0.2 of the horizontal trapezoidal channel. The discharge range was from 30 to 90 l/s and Fr_1 ranged from 1.2 to 8.67. This study indicated that the relationship between Fr_1 and the y_2/y_1 was close and applied numerical models for experimental tests.

The sequent depth (y_2/y_1) of the jump in a trapezoidal channel was studied mainly in the form of an empirical equation that depends on Fr_1 , but, for channels with different slopes, the equation has a significant change in the experimental coefficients. More research is needed to improve the general equations for calculating the conjugate depth of the trapezoidal channel. The jump is divided into 4 types based on Fr_1 : weak jump, oscillating jump, steady jump, and choppy jump [6]. The steady jump is commonly used, and this case is handled to adjust and design works that use the hydraulic jump in practice. This study focused on the factors influencing y_2/y_1 by examining existing studies on hydraulic jumps in both rectangular and trapezoidal channels. Buckingham's Pi theory was employed to assess and construct an objective function. In addition, experiments were carried out using a physical model to collect relevant data for steady jumps within the range of $4.0 \leq Fr_1 \leq 9.0$. By combining the experimental data, the objective function, and the structure of the existing equations, new empirical equations were constructed to determine the sequent depth ratio for steady hydraulic jumps, which were tested under the same experimental data and conditions as [10].

II. ANALYZING THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE SEQUENT DEPTHS

It is important to identify the variables that affect the hydraulic jump phenomena to choose the direction of the investigation and set a foundation for developing empirical equations based on those variables. Based on investigations of the hydraulic jump's subsequent depth in trapezoidal and rectangular channels with stilling basins, slopes, and smooth or uneven beds, an analysis of the influencing factors follows.

- Fr_1 is a factor that has the greatest influence on the conjugate depth of the jump and plays an important role in

the formation of the equation to determine y_2/y_1 . This factor appears in most sequent depth studies, such as the studies of the jump in a rectangular channel with a smooth or rough bed [7-9, 19-24]. Authors in [10-16] studied the trapezoidal channel. The higher the value of Fr_1 , the greater the y_2/y_1 , and the greater the energy dissipation in the jump, as shown in the hydraulic jump classification. However, the increase in the y_2/y_1 versus the upstream Froude number varies according to the geometrical characteristics of the cross-section.

- Some studies also created the relationship between y_2/y_1 and the inflow Froude number by Fr_1-1 , such as [25-27].
- In fundamental studies, the influence of bed friction is frequently ignored, resulting in theoretical equations that often require the inclusion of experimental coefficients. Nevertheless, certain investigations on hydraulic jumps in rectangular channels took into account the impact of this factor. For example, the equation can incorporate the shear stress coefficient [7] or the diameter of the bed roughness [24].
- Bélanger's equation had a value of 8 but was increased to 10.4 by the effects of the velocity distribution, as demonstrated in [8] in which the kinetic energy correction factor to obtain the equation for the sequent depth of the jump in the rectangular channel was 1.045.
- The slope of the channel affects the conjugate depth of the jump. A negative or positive slope will result in the establishment of various equations to measure the sequent depth ratio. For example, in [20] the bottom slope ($S^{1/2}$) was included in the equation to calculate the y_2/y_1 of the jump in the rectangular channel, which corresponds to studies of the jump in bed slopes with roughness or wide openings. For trapezoidal channels, some studies investigated the influence of bed slope on the y_2/y_1 equation [12-15].
- The ratio coefficient between the side slope, the inflow depth of the jump, and the bed width of the channel (M_1) is a characteristic coefficient that represents the geometric shape ratio of the trapezoidal channel. The value of M_1 can be found in divergent studies [10, 16, 18].
- Geometrical features of the critical depth (y_c)[5].

General consideration shows that the sequent depth ratio in a smooth horizontal prismatic channel has a general function as follows:

$$Y = \frac{y_2}{y_1} = f(Fr_1, M_1) \quad (1)$$

III. APPLYING THE PI THEORY IN STUDYING THE SEQUENT DEPTH

Using a momentum equation to study a geometrical feature (y_2/y_1) of the jump over the smooth bed (the friction force can be ignored), gives:

$$F_1 - F_2 = P_2 - P_1 \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) has been incorporated in several studies on the y_2/y_1 of the jump [28-31]. From the theory of dimensional analysis, the influencing factors are determined:

$$f(y_2, y_1, V_1, V_2, m, b, \alpha_{01}, \alpha_{02}, \rho, \mu, g) = 0 \quad (3)$$

By reducing similar characteristic parameters $\alpha_{0i} \approx 1$ (turbulent flow) and using the Pi theory of Buckingham, the following equations are obtained:

$$\beta\left(\frac{y_2}{y_1}, \frac{b}{y_1}, Re, m, Fr_1\right) = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{y_2}{y_1} = \Psi\left(\frac{b}{y_1}, Re, m, Fr_1\right) \quad (5)$$

where V is the velocity (m/s), m is a side wall slope, ρ is the mass density of the water (kg/m^3), μ is fluid viscosity (kg/m.s), g is the gravitational acceleration (m/s^2), Re is a Reynolds number, M_1 is the side wall constant in the trapezoidal channel ($M_1 = \frac{m \cdot y_1}{b}$), Fr_1 is the inflow Froude number ($Fr_1 = \frac{V_1}{\sqrt{g \cdot y_1}}$ (or

$$Fr_1 = \frac{V_1}{\sqrt{g \cdot D}}$$

), and D is the hydraulic depth (m). Considering the characteristics of the cross-sectional coefficient, it is observed that for very large Reynolds numbers ($Re > 20000$), its influence can be ignored [32]. Therefore, (5) can be simplified to (1), while (5) effectively represents the factors influencing the y_2/y_1 of the hydraulic jump. In the case of studying the jump in a rectangular channel ($m = 0$), (5) exhibits similarities to Bélanger's equation [6].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Experimental Model Structure

The physical model was constructed at the Key Laboratory of River and Coastal Engineering (KLORCE), in Vietnam Academy for Water Resources (VAWR). Figure 1 shows the model, that consists of a reservoir, an ogee spillway, a trapezoidal channel, and a control gate at its end. The energy dissipation structure was the trapezoidal channel, having a length of 4.0 m, bed width of 0.335 m and 0.55 m, height of 0.65 m, and side slope of 1:1 (angle 45°).

Fig. 1. Plan of the experimental equipment.

Fig. 2. The model from downstream to upstream (bed width 55 cm).

Fig. 3. Spillway and the hydraulic jump in the trapezoidal channel (bed width 55 cm, $Q = 165 \text{ l/s}$, and $Fr_1 = 5.72$).

B. Measuring Data

Level surveying and leveling staff are used to measure the depth of the flow. The technique involves having one person hold the leveling staff while the other reads the information from the surveying apparatus, as shown in Figure 4. The observed data are shown in Table I. The collected data are shown in Table II, with a total of 86 datasets (with $Fr_1 \geq 4.0$) from the experimental implementation on two physical models (bed width is 55 and 33.5 cm). These data were regulated to establish the relationship between y_2/y_1 and Fr_1 , as shown in Figure 5.

TABLE I. RANGE OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Max	Min
Discharge	Q	m^3/s	0.201	0.04
Initial depth of hydraulic jump	y_1	m	0.041	0.092
Secondary depth of hydraulic jump	y_2	m	0.488	0.182
Bed width of the channel	b	cm	55	33.5

TABLE II. RANGE OF DIMENSIONLESS PARAMETERS

Values	y_2/y_1	Fr_{D1}	Fr_1	M_1
Max	9.396	8.40	7.98	0.275
Min	4.397	4.19	4.01	0.06

Fig. 4. Measuring water level data by the surveying equipment and the leveling staff (bed width $b = 33.5$ cm, $Q = 136$ l/s, and $Fr_1 = 4.83$).

V. ESTABLISHING AN EMPIRICAL EQUATION OF THE CONJUGATE DEPTH

A. Relationship between y_2/y_1 and Fr_1

Considering the relationship between the y_2/y_1 with the Fr_1 based on the observed values of this and other studies, gives the following:

Fig. 5. Relationship between the y_2/y_1 and the Fr_1 according to M_1 .

Figure 5 shows that y_2/y_1 and Fr_1 tend to converge in each group of M_1 values (M_1 groups are referenced from [10]), so y_2/y_1 is a function of Fr_1 . This tendency, however, depends on M_1 and does not merely demonstrate the role of Fr_1 in the y_2/y_1 variation rule. Therefore, it is essential to completely take into account the upstream Fr_1 and coefficient M_1 of the hydraulic leap in the smooth horizontal trapezoidal channel while developing the connection to determine the conjugate depth. Equation (1), the equation structure of other studies, and experimental data of the leap on two physical models (physical model with bed widths of 55 and 33.5 cm) were adopted to develop the empirical equation for estimating y_2/y_1 .

B. Establishing an Empirical Equation

Using the measurement data in Table II, the study combined the influencing factors according to (1) and the structure of the existing equations. Table III shows the study combinations.

TABLE III. THE EMPIRICAL EQUATIONS FOR THE SEQUENT DEPTH OF THE HYDRAULIC JUMP

Symbol	Equations	R^2	Ref.
(Y_1)	$\frac{y_2}{y_1} = 0.721Fr_1^{1.151} + 0.875$	0.953	[12-15,17],
(Y_2)	$\frac{y_2}{y_1} = 0.888M_1^{-0.088}Fr_1^{1.003} + 0.204$	0.981	[10-11,16]
(Y_3)	$\frac{y_2}{y_1} = 1.051M_1^{-0.154}(Fr_{D1} - 1)^{0.871} + 0.464$	0.980	[25-27]
(Y_4)	$\frac{y_2}{y_1} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 + 9.286Fr_{D1}^{1.729} - 1}$	0.738	[7-9]

Figure 6 shows that the measured values are evenly distributed on both sides of the best-fit line ($y = x$), but (Y_4) , shown in Figure 6 (d) has a one-sided bias and a large error (the maximum error is 17.5%). Equations (Y_2) and (Y_3) , shown in Figure 6 (b)-(c), have a small error (7.8% and 7.4%, respectively). The values calculated by (Y_3) have $\pm 8\%$ difference from the measured data. Thus, in terms of statistical indicators, (Y_3) has better computational efficiency and is proposed.

VI. TEST AND EVALUATION OF THE PROPOSED EQUATIONS

A. Metrics for Evaluating Calculated Results

The statistical indicators used to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed equations were [33-35]:

Mean Absolute Error (MAE):

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i| \tag{6}$$

Mean Squared Error (MSE):

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2 \tag{7}$$

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2} \tag{8}$$

R squared (R^2):

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y_i - x_i)^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{x})^2} \tag{9}$$

Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE, %):

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum \frac{|x_i - y_i|}{x_i} \tag{10}$$

Error percentage (ε , %):

$$\varepsilon = \frac{|y_i - x_i|}{x_i} \times 100 \tag{11}$$

where y and x are the calculated values and the observed values, respectively, \bar{x} is the average observed value, and n is

the number of observations. To evaluate the calculation efficiency of the equations, the statistical indicators *MAE*, *MSE*, *RMSE*, *MAPE*, and ϵ should be as close to zero as possible

(ideal point), and the larger the R^2 value, the higher the calculation efficiency of the equation.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the observed values with the predicted values by the proposed equations. (a) Using (Y_1), (b) using (Y_2), (c) using (Y_3), (d) Using (Y_4).

B. Analysis According to the Statistical Indicators

The sequent depths ratio y_2/y_1 was calculated using the equations in Table III, with the study data shown in Table I, and Table IV shows the statistical indicators.

TABLE IV. STATISTICAL INDICATORS

Eq.	MEA	MSE	RMSE	R^2	MAPE (%)
Y_1	0.206	0.067	0.259	0.95	3.27
Y_2	0.130	0.027	0.166	0.98	2.18
Y_3	0.129	0.027	0.163	0.98	2.18
Y_4	0.536	0.376	0.613	0.74	9.12

Most of the proposed equations had good coefficients ($R^2 > 0.9$), indicating a strong correlation [33]. The other statistical indicators were also very small (close to zero). Equations (Y_2) and (Y_3) have strong indicators, such as the coefficient $R^2 = 0.98$ which is the largest, and the other statistical indicators were also lower compared to those of the other equations.

C. Test data

The proposed equations were tested on the data from [10], in which an experimental study of the hydraulic jump was executed in a smooth horizontal trapezoidal channel with a bed width of 0.2 m and a 1:1 side slope, which is similar to this study's side slope. This study investigated experimental cases with $4.0 \leq Fr_1 < 10$ and $y_1 \geq 3$ cm. The total test data [10] were

39 datasets. After removing the data that did not match the research criteria, there were 19 datasets left, as shown in Table V. Figure 7 shows the relationship between y_2/y_1 and the Fr_1 based on the M_1 values (the group of M_1 is classified according to the author's experimental data).

TABLE V. RANGE OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA OF [10]

Values	Q (l/s)	Fr_{D1}	Fr_1	M_1	y_2/y_1
Max	98.0	10.10	9.34	0.41	9.00
Min	7.5	4.70	4.14	0.10	4.33

Fig. 7. The sequent depth depends on Fr_1 and M_1 .

Figure 7 shows that the relationship between y_2/y_1 and Fr_1 based on the quadratic function has a very strong correlation coefficient ($R^2 > 0.97$), but the division into many different groups to establish the relationship system and then building a general theoretical equation to reckon the y_2/y_1 is very difficult to ensure high accuracy.

D. Testing with the Observed Values of [10]

The proposed equations were used with the test data (Table V) from [10] to determine the calculated values, and the statistical indicators were used to evaluate their efficiency in calculation, as shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI. ANALYZING THE STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR THE TEST DATA

Eq.	MEA	MSE	RMSE	R ²	MAPE (%)
(Y ₁)	0.491	0.386	0.621	0.78	7.50
(Y ₂)	0.259	0.121	0.348	0.93	3.80
(Y ₃)	0.250	0.107	0.327	0.94	3.70
(Y ₂)	1.088	1.468	1.212	0.61	17.78

Fig. 8. Comparison of the observed with the predicted values by (Y₃).

Fig. 9. Comparison of the calculated values by (Y₃) with all data (present study and [10]).

As shown in Table VI, (Y₂) and (Y₃) have good and equivalent statistical indicators, which is similar to the data of this study shown in Table IV. As shown in Tables IV and VI, (Y₃) has the best statistical indicators, which is emphasized by the coefficient $R^2 > 0.9$ and the other statistical indicators that approach zero, especially RMSE (0.163 and 0.327 for the present data and the test data, respectively) and MAPE (7.35%

for present data and 8.85% for the test data) are the best. Therefore, this study proposes the use of (Y₃) to estimate the sequent depth ratio y_2/y_1 of the jump in a horizontal trapezoidal channel with the side slope 1:1.

Figures 8 and 9 show that the calculated values exhibit a favorable agreement, falling within the agreement line, while all the data lie within the error line of $\pm 9\%$ of the measured data. Figure 8 shows that when using (Y₃) to calculate the y_2/y_1 , there is a strong agreement, with only one data point out of 19 falling outside the error band of $\pm 8\%$. This indicates that y_2/y_1 is influenced by Fr_1 , as observed in other studies. Additionally, for trapezoidal channels, the parameter M_1 , which encompasses the side slope coefficient m and the bed width of the channel, also affects y_2/y_1 . Thus, it was possible to remove the influence of the scale model (the influence of the bed width on different models) on the observed values in the physical model. When experimenting, the parameters y_1 , b , and Fr_1 always have a relationship with each other, which is adjusted through the discharge Q . Therefore, these results can be commonly controlled to calculate the conjugate depth of the hydraulic jump in the smooth horizontal trapezoidal channels with side slope 1:1.

VII. CONCLUSION

Research on the sequent depth of the jump in rectangular channels has a clear theoretical basis and its equation is popular and widely applied. For trapezoidal channels, the theoretical equation has not yet been developed, but has often been established by empirical equations. However, these equations do not yet describe all the effects of hydraulic factors. This study analyzed existing research and combined it with theoretical analysis to fully simulate the factors that directly affect the sequent depth y_2/y_1 of the jump on the trapezoidal channel. The objective function was obtained by establishing an empirical equation to calculate the sequent depth y_2/y_1 . This study also proposed different equations to determine depth. Using experimental data to establish and test the equations, their effectiveness was evaluated and the most effective equation was proposed. This study drew some key conclusions:

- Buckingham's Pi theory is effective in identifying important factors when establishing empirical equations. From that point forward, it guides some forms of the experimental equations and helps to propose quick equations that ensure scientificity.
- This study carried out experiments based on three models of different sizes that eliminated the condition of the influence of the physical model size on the research results.
- The foundation of this study lies in the structural analysis of existing formulas. Moreover, this study expanded upon these findings to develop an empirical equation specifically aimed at calculating the sequent depth y_2/y_1 of hydraulic jumps occurring in trapezoidal channels. Four equations were determined to calculate the sequent depth ratio y_2/y_1 . Basic statistical indicators (R^2 , MSE, RMSE, MAE, and MAPE) were used to evaluate the four proposed equations, showing that (Y₂) and (Y₃) had the best calculation efficiency.

- The proposed equations were tested on data from this study and [10], showing that (Y_3) had the best statistical indicators.
- Equation (Y_3) was adopted to estimate the sequent depth of the steady jump ($4.0 \leq Fr_1 \leq 9.0$) in an isosceles trapezoidal channel with a still basin and a side slope equal to 1.

This study carried out one type of physical experiment for the steady jump on an isosceles trapezoidal channel. More research is needed to determine the empirical equation for divergent side slopes of the trapezoidal channel. Despite the limitations of this study, the results clarified the relationship between the sequent depth y_2/y_1 of the jump and the hydraulic factors Fr_1 and M_1 .

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Combined Osprey-Chimp Optimization for Cluster Based Routing in Wireless Sensor Networks: Improved DeepMaxout for Node Energy Prediction

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ABSTRACT

The significant advances in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) facilitate many latest applications, such as intelligent battlefield, home automation, traffic control, and more. WSNs comprise small autonomously organized sensor nodes that are powered by batteries. The processes of collecting information and data storage, processing, and transmission deplete the energy of these small devices. Energy efficiency is still a major issue to address in WSN routing. Clustering is the best method that has been developed to reduce node energy consumption. However, current clustering methods are unable to effectively distribute the energy requirements of the nodes without considering energy characteristics, number of nodes, and flexibility. This study proposed a new cluster-based routing model for WSNs and emphasized the need for an improved clustering process with new optimization techniques. In particular, the improved DeepMaxout model was adopted to predict the energy of the nodes. Cluster Head (CH) selection is performed considering the nodes' energy as a prime factor. After choosing the CH, the CIOO algorithm incorporates new link quality and trust evaluations while determining the routing process. Finally, a comparison of energy utilization factors was performed between the suggested and traditional approaches.

Keywords-node energy prediction; improved DeepMaxout; osprey-chimp; routing

I. INTRODUCTION

A Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) is a particular type of network that encompasses many autonomous sensor nodes equipped with different sensors that track and collect information from the real world [1]. These sensor nodes are typically small, energy-constrained devices that are disseminated over a region [2]. Due to advances in WSN technology, they have significant use in different applications, such as healthcare, environment, industry applications, home automation, military, and many more [3]. The major problem of WSNs involves balancing the energy of the nodes with each other [4]. To extend the lifespan of the network and improve its efficiency, it is necessary to properly distribute node energy and optimize node energy usage [5].

To address energy-based challenges, hierarchical clustering techniques, which have advantages related to sustainability and

effectiveness, are being considered as solutions for WSNs [6]. Utilizing data collection and clustering approaches can effectively regulate node energy in WSNs [7-8]. A well-known cluster-based routing technique called LEACH involves sensor nodes (non-CH) to collect data through their sensing area and send it to the CH [9]. Each cluster consists of a CH that collects, combines, and compresses CM data before transmitting them over a single hop to the BS or sink nodes. LEACH descendants have been proposed, including Centralized-LEACH, Improved-LEACH, Modified-LEACH, and Time-Based-LEACH [10-11]. This study aims to:

- Propose a novel optimized CH selection model.
- Introduce an improved DeepMaxout model to predict node energy and ensure energy efficiency while clustering.

- Evaluate the proposed model over traditional ones in order to showcase its effectiveness over the energy constraint.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various studies have investigated different routing strategies for optimal CH selection. In [12], a dynamic CH selection method was proposed for WSNs. In [13], the LEACH method was proposed to reduce the randomness that clustering algorithms exhibit. In [14], a new Cluster Head Selection by Randomness with Data Recovery (CHSRDR) strategy was proposed to select a CH based on recovered data. In [15], the FLION clustering algorithm was proposed to create an energy-efficient routing scheme. In [16], a distributed CH selection strategy was presented to continuously optimize the energy use between sensors, considering the distances between the base station and the sensors. The reduction of energy consumption is one of the many issues that need to be resolved to improve WSN efficiency [17]. In [18], a novel application model for WSNs was proposed, in which raw data were collected through multi-hop networks, and a new HTC-RDC was presented to extend the lifespan of WSNs. In [19], the SLBR approach for heterogeneous cluster-based WSNs was investigated, which helps distribute the load between CHs. In [20], the DMOSC-MHRS method for the Internet of Drones environment was introduced, mainly aiming at selecting a CH with an optimal routing strategy. In summary, these studies emphasized the features and challenges of conventional WSN cluster-based routing strategies. This inspires the development of a new technique for optimal CH selection to prolong the overall lifetime of WSNs.

Essentially, WSN nodes depend on a limited battery power supply that can only keep them running for a certain period before they deplete. Improving the energy efficiency of every sensor node extends the WSN lifespan, and clustering is one of the best methods to achieve this. This study propose a novel WSN routing protocol to prolong the network lifespan and reduce energy consumption by calculating the optimal CH depending on its energy using the Firefly Algorithm. The suggested approach was compared with the EAMMH, BRE, NEAHC, SEP, E-SEP, LEACH, and WEB protocols. According to experimental data, the suggested strategy outperformed the comparable routing methods on energy usage and packet transmission between sensor nodes and base stations. The results clearly showed that the suggested approach could lengthen the WSN lifetime.

III. THE PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE OF CLUSTER-BASED ROUTING IN WSN

Since sensor nodes are small and self-sufficient devices with limited power, routing algorithms are crucial to improve network lifetime and energy consumption. Movement and data reception, collection, and analysis are only a few of the factors that cause nodes to consume their energy. This study introduced a cluster-based routing via CIOO that combined Osprey-Chimp optimization. Consider the WSN scenario simulated with nodes namely, normal node (N), intermediate node (I) and advanced node (A). In the initial stage, the energy of the nodes is predicted by an improved DeepMaxout model. Clustering takes place using the k-means clustering algorithm.

For every cluster, CH selection is performed by the CIOO algorithm (Osprey and Chimp Optimization) considering energy prediction, inter- and intra-cluster distances, delay, and risk. Subsequently, routing is carried out using the CIOO algorithm considering improved trust and link quality.

A. Node Energy Prediction using the Improved DeepMaxout Model

The energy of a sensor node is the main factor in data transmission from a source to a destination node. However, it also depends on the distance they are from each other. According to the proposed model, an improved DeepMaxout was used to predict the energy of the nodes. Lets consider three types of nodes: Normal node (N), Intermediate node (I), and Advanced node (A). Energy consumption differs depending on the type of node. In the DeepMaxout model, node location, distance, and type are considered as input features, and then the target will be 0, 1, and 2. Thus, the node energy is predicted under three conditions, as shown in Table I. If the type of the node is normal, then the target value is fixed to 0 and its energy prediction value will be 0.5. Similarly, if the type of node is intermediate, its target value is 1 and its energy prediction will be 0.8. If the type of node is advanced, the target value is 2 and its energy prediction will be 1.

TABLE I. ENERGY PREDICTION OUTCOME

Node Type	Target	Energy (E)
N	0	0.5
I	1	0.8
A	2	1

B. Improved DeepMaxout Architecture

The primary component of DMN's multi-layered structure makes it a form of adaptable activation factor. In this section, positive and negative terms are specified as a nonzero slope through an effective activation function known as Maxout [21]. In general, Maxout supports measures to tackle the optimization challenge by partially defending the hidden elements from transitioning to an abnormal mode. While acting as an adaptable activation variable, Maxout does not work as a random function approximator. Improved DeepMaxout considers input features, such as node location, type, and distance, using an improved activation function to obtain a more accurate energy prediction. The activation function was determined as a hybrid form, $\tanh(\text{Swish} + \text{Softplus})$, by combining two activation functions. Swish [22] is the smooth, non-monotonic function represented by:

$$f(x) = x \cdot \text{Std}(x) \quad (1)$$

where $\text{Std}(x)$ represents the sigmoid function that is mathematically calculated by:

$$\text{Std}(x) = (1 + e^{(-x)})^{-1} \quad (2)$$

The Swish's characteristics are comparable to those of Softplus, a smooth function that is absolutely beneficial and continuous and is often considered a refined form of ReLU. The Softplus activation function [22] is expressed by:

$$f(x) = \log(1 + e^{(x)}) \quad (3)$$

By adding (1) and (3), the combination of the two activation functions is obtained as:

$$(Swish + Softplus) = x \cdot Std(x) + \log(1 + e^{(x)})$$

$$(f(x) + f(x)) = x \cdot (1 + e^{(-x)})^{-1} + \log(1 + e^{(x)})$$

$$2f(x) = \frac{x}{(1+e^{(-x)})} + \log(1 + e^{(x)})$$

$$2f(x) = \frac{x + \log(1+e^{(x)}) \times (1+e^{(-x)})}{(1+e^{(-x)})}$$

$$f(x) = \frac{\left[\frac{x + \log(1+e^{(x)}) \times (1+e^{(-x)})}{(1+e^{(-x)})} \right]}{2} \quad (4)$$

Usually, the hyperbolic tangent function [23] is used in the DeepMaxout model, which is a smoothed and zero-centered function, and the tanh function result is calculated by:

$$f(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}} \quad (5)$$

This study employed a hybrid combination of tanh(Swish + Softplus) activation function in the improved DeepMaxout structure, expressed as:

$$\tanh(Swish + Softplus) = \left\{ \frac{\left[\frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}} \right] \left[\frac{x + \log(1+e^{(x)}) \times (1+e^{(-x)})}{(1+e^{(-x)})} \right]}{2} \right\} \quad (6)$$

The outcome of the improved DeepMaxout model is the predicted energy value mentioned in Table I. After energy node prediction, all nodes are split into small divisions called clusters. In this study, the clustering process was carried out through the k-means clustering algorithm.

Fig. 1. The routing architecture using the CIOO algorithm.

C. Routing via CIOO Algorithm

After selecting the CH based on the proposed CIOO algorithm under various constraints, the routing is carried out via the same CIOO algorithm considering link quality and a newly evaluated trust. Figure 1 shows the architecture for routing via the CIOO algorithm.

1) Link Quality (LQ_R)

Link Quality (LQ_R) is one of the typical restrictions in the best possible routing and shows the quality of data packets that the destination has received. Equation (7) illustrates the way to calculate it in WSN. The ratio of the number of received to the sent packets is termed LQ_R .

$$(LQ_R) = \frac{P_r}{P_t} \quad (7)$$

where P_r denotes the number of packets received and P_t denotes the number of packets transmitted.

2) New Trust Evaluation

For every neighboring node (node that is within its transmission range), each node generates a trust degree value. This number represents the degree of trust in a neighbor. The trust degree value is generated using regional data, such as regional topological data, to ensure scalability. Let the level of trust between node P and neighbor Q at time t be denoted by $T_{P-Q}(t)$. The continuous range of 0 to 1 is the only range allowed for the trust degree value. A trust degree of 0 indicates total mistrust, while a value of 1 indicates complete trust. Trust [24] includes both direct and indirect trust. The final trust is formed by combining the values of indirect and direct trust.

Direct trust is determined by nodes interacting with each other. Distance and energy are evaluated as markers of trust according to:

$$DT_{(P-Q)} = \frac{E_r}{d(node_p, node_q)} \quad (8)$$

where $d(node_p, node_q)$ indicates the differentiation distance between nodes P and Q , $DT_{(P-Q)}$ is the value of direct trust between P and Q , and E_r is the residual energy of node B . Indirect trust is based on a node's suggestion. The method for calculating indirect trust, which is added to the amount of trust value evaluated by the extra nodes, is given by:

$$IT_{(P-Q)} = \sum DT_{(P-R)} * DT_{(R-Q)} \quad (9)$$

where $DT_{(P-R)}$ denotes the direct trust calculated by P for R and $DT_{(R-Q)}$ denotes the value of direct trust determined by R for Q . Final trust is the sum of direct and indirect trust times the appropriate weight:

$$Trust_{(P-Q)}(T) = w * DT_{(P-Q)} + (1 - w) * IT_{(P-Q)} \quad (10)$$

In this case, the final trust computation uses W as 0.5. The proposed trust evaluation improves the trust value between nodes during routing. The packet delivery ratio is incorporated into the direct trust value to improve overall trust in routing. The following equation determines the improved direct trust value between nodes P and Q .

$$DT'_{(P-Q)} = PDR + \frac{E_r}{d(node_p, node_q)} \quad (11)$$

Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) [25] is a metric that quantifies the proportion of total packets delivered to the total packets transmitted over a network between a source and a destination node. The intention is for the greatest number of data packets to arrive at the intended location. The network's performance increases with the value of *PDR*, which is calculated by:

$$PDR = \frac{DR}{(DR+DL)} \tag{12}$$

where *DR* denotes the data received, and *DL* denotes the data lost. Therefore, the final trust evaluation is expressed by:

$$ImprovedTrust_{(p-Q)}(T') = w * DT'_{(p-Q)} + (1 - w) * IT_{(p-Q)} \tag{13}$$

3) Objective Function for Routing

The routing objective function is defined as the minimum fitness function under the constraints of link quality and improved trust. Link quality and improved trust are calculated by (14) and (15):

$$Fit = \min(w_5 * LQ_R + w_6 * T') \tag{14}$$

$$obj(f) = \min(Fit) \tag{15}$$

where *w₅* and *w₆* denote the weight of link quality and improved trust, respectively. The summation of the total weight is represented as $\sum w_i = 1$.

4) Solution Encoding for Routing

The input given to the algorithm is the number of nodes. The population size is 10, the lower bound value is fixed to 1, and the upper bound value is *n*, which is the number of sensor nodes.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A simulation of the proposed cluster-based routing method in WSNs was carried out using MATLAB version R2023b on an Intel® Core™ i5-1035G1 CPU at 1.19 GHz with 20 GB total installed RAM, with 19.7 GB of it being usable. The performance analysis of the proposed CIOO and traditional approaches was estimated using many metrics. Figure 2 illustrates the network setup. The established network configuration parameters were *x* = 100 m and *y* = 100 m. The election probability of a node to become CH was 0.8, and the maximum number of rounds was 2000.

Fig. 2. Network setup.

A. Analysis of Residual Energy

Figure 3 shows the evaluation of residual energy in the CIOO and traditional schemes in the context of cluster-based routing in WSN. For a model to perform effectively, the residual energy must remain at a higher level. Initially, all algorithms achieved higher levels of residual energy, but as the number of rounds increased, the rate of residual energy began to decline. However, the CIOO method consistently maintained the highest residual energy, even in the final round. The CIOO approach achieved the highest residual energy in the 2000th round, exceeding the performance of PSO [26], DMOSC-MHRS [20], GOA [27], SMO [28], BOA [29], COA [30], and OOA [31]. Therefore, it can be assertively affirmed that the CIOO scheme in cluster-based routing for WSN not only excels in delivering remarkably efficient solutions but also maintains a notable level of energy efficiency.

Fig. 3. Validation of residual energy.

B. Convergence Analysis

Figure 4 shows the convergence evaluation of the CIOO and PSO [26], DMOSC-MHRS [20], GOA [27], SMO [28], BOA [29], COA [30], and OOA [31] approaches for cluster-based routing in WSNs.

Fig. 4. Convergence analysis of CIOO and conventional methods.

The cost rate must be reduced for efficient cluster-based routing. Initially, the CIOO and conventional strategies exhibited higher cost values, but as the iterations progressed, there was a decrease in the cost rate. In particular, the CIOO

scheme consistently achieved the lowest cost value from the initial to the final iterations. For the 10th iteration, CIOO yielded the lowest cost rate of 4.126×10^4 , and the traditional approaches recorded the following cost rate values: PSO = 4.381×10^4 , DMOSC-MHRS = 4.257×10^4 , GOA = 4.294×10^4 , SMO = 4.228×10^4 , BOA = 4.139×10^4 , COA = 4.375×10^4 , and OOA = 4.198×10^4 . We can see that the proposed method overperforms the conventional methods. The outstanding performance observed during the convergence evaluation highlights the CIOO's ability to achieve optimal cluster-based routing in WSNs.

C. Statistical Analysis on Residual Energy

Table II shows the statistical evaluation of CIOO and the conventional methods SMO [28], BOA [29], COA [30], and OOA [31] for cluster-based routing in WSNs. A metaheuristic technique was meticulously studied, and as a result, each method was subjected to hard evaluation to ensure remarkably exact estimates. To achieve this, a detailed evaluation was carried out inspecting critical statistical metrics. Together, these metrics provide a complete understanding of the efficiency and dependability of the approaches under investigation. The statistical analysis on residual energy showed that the CIOO recorded the highest residual energy rate under the maximum statistical metric, which was extremely higher than the SMO [28], BOA [29], COA [30], and OOA [31] approaches.

TABLE II. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS ON RESIDUAL ENERGY

Statistical Metrics	CIOO	SMO [28]	BOA [29]	COA [30]	OOA [31]
Minimum	0.012	0.011	0.008	0.010	0.010
Median	0.254	0.214	0.235	0.223	0.238
Standard Deviation	0.170	0.177	0.176	0.178	0.177
Maximum	0.550	0.550	0.549	0.550	0.550
Mean	0.258	0.239	0.245	0.243	0.248

V. CONCLUSION

This study suggested a new cluster-based routing algorithm for WSNs and simulated it in MATLAB R2023b. Initially, k-means clustering was used to cluster the sensor nodes. Then, the proposed algorithm was used to perform the optimal CH selection, primarily considering the energy constraint. The improved DeepMaxout model was used to forecast the node's energy consumption. The suggested CIOO method considers link quality and trust after selecting the CH when deciding on routing. Compared to conventional approaches, the proposed consistently maintained the highest residual energy, even in the final 2000th round. The statistical analysis and comparison showed that the proposed method exhibited the highest residual energy rate compared to the others. The proposed method should be further evaluated and compared with conventional methods in terms of energy consumption, journey duration, and security.

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Constant Current Charging and Transfer Efficiency Improvements for a Dynamic Wireless Charging System

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic Wireless Charging (DWC) systems for electric vehicles (EVs) are being studied and developed for wide applications. To ensure a long life for lithium-ion batteries, Constant Current (CC) charging is required. However, the equivalent load of the battery changes during CC charging, which reduces the system's efficiency. To solve that problem, this paper proposes a new control method that combines CC charging and improves transfer efficiency using only an active rectifier on the secondary side of the DWC system. Moreover, this study also proposes a method to estimate the coupling coefficient through the parameters measured on the secondary side without the need for wireless communication between the two sides. A model of a 1.5 kW DWC system with a transfer distance of 150 mm was built in a laboratory to verify the accuracy of the proposed method. The results showed that the charging current reached the required value, and the maximum system efficiency was 85%.

Keywords-constant current charge; improved efficiency; dynamic wireless charging system; electric vehicle

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric Vehicles (EVs) are environmentally friendly means of transport. To make the use of EVs more convenient and safer, many problems related to EVs are currently being studied and developed [1-3]. Wireless charging technology for EVs is attractive because it simplifies the power supply process and eliminates some of the dangers of electrical leakage for users. Research is directed toward applying wireless charging technology to charge EVs while they are in motion because it can reduce battery weight and increase travel distance [4-6]. Today, EVs mainly use lithium-ion batteries due to their large energy density, long life, and safety [7]. To prolong the battery life, the CC charging mode is required. However, during CC charging, the equivalent load impedance of the battery varies, which reduces the system's efficiency [8]. A challenge is how to achieve CC charging mode and ensure high system efficiency.

Due to the complexity of wireless charging systems, it is difficult to achieve both the above criteria. Several studies attempted to achieve either of these two criteria. Some studies focused on improving the efficiency system. Commonly used methods are impedance matching circuit design [9-10], DC/DC converter control to convert load impedance [11-13], and minimum input current/power point detection to maximize transfer efficiency [14-15]. However, these studies have not addressed the charge control problem. Some studies focused on the control of the CC/CV charging process. In [16], an LCCC/S compensation circuit structure and parameter adjustment method were proposed to achieve CC and CV at two ZPA frequencies. This method is unsuitable for dynamic charging systems where various types of electric vehicles operate. In a Static Wireless Charging (SWC) system, CC and CV charging modes are achieved at two different frequencies by designing the coil and compensating circuit [17]. This design method is complicated, and the system requires wireless communication between the two sides to control the charging process. In the

WPT system, CC and CV charging modes are achieved by phase shift modulation of the primary side inverter [18]. However, on the secondary side, the compensation circuit must be switched from series to parallel when switching the charging mode from CC to CV. This method is only suitable for applications with compact and lightweight receivers.

Some studies have proposed combining CC charge control with improved transfer efficiency in SWC systems. In [19-20], the secondary active rectifier phase shift modulation method was used to realize the CC charging mode. Maximum transfer efficiency tracking is based on finding the minimum DC input current point through the perturbation and observation algorithm. The disadvantage of this system is that the semi-active rectifier and the inverter can operate stably. Furthermore, this method is unsuitable for DWC systems because the working point detection time is high. In [21], a dual-phase shift modulation method was used to keep output voltage and current constant while improving the efficiency of WPT systems. However, as this system requires wireless communication between the two sides, it is not suitable for DWC systems.

To solve the above problems, this paper proposes a control method that combines CC charging and improves efficiency using only an active rectifier on the secondary side. CC is required from the Battery Management System (BMS). The

efficiency optimization algorithm was implemented based on the equivalent load impedance control method that follows the optimal load impedance value and limits the required charging current. Then, the closed-loop controller was designed to CC charging. Moreover, a method for estimating the coupling coefficient in the DWC system is also presented. Therefore, the system does not need to use wireless communication between the two sides.

II. STRUCTURE AND CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PROPOSED DWC SYSTEM

A. System Structure

Figure 1 shows the structure of the proposed DWC system. Three transmitting coils are placed side by side to create the charging lane on the primary side. An 85 kHz inverter consisting of four MOSFETs from S1 to S4 powers the transmitting coils through the compensation circuit. On the secondary side, the receiving coil is mounted under the EV to receive power from the wireless charging lane. The receiving coil induces an alternating voltage through the compensating circuit feeds to the active rectifier. The active rectifier consists of 4 MOSFETs, Q1 to Q4, which provide charging power for the battery. The LCC compensation circuit is designed for both the primary and secondary sides.

Fig. 1. The proposed dynamic wireless charging system.

B. Characteristics of the Coupling Coefficient in the Proposed DWC System

This study used finite element analysis simulation to design the transmitting and receiving coils to reduce power pulsation [22]. Each coil consists of three layers: the Litz wire layer, the ferrite layer, and the aluminum shield layer. The primary side consists of three transmitting coils (T1, T2, and T3) placed side by side under the wireless charging lane. The receiving coil is mounted under the EV. The transfer distance is equal to 150 mm. Figure 2 shows the structure of the coils in the DWC system.

The receiver position in the x direction is denoted by p_x , and in the y direction is denoted by p_y . The receiving coil is centered on the first transmitting coil (T1), $(p_x, p_y) = (0, 0)$. Figure 3 shows the EFA simulation results of the coupling coefficient when the receiver moves along the wireless charging lane in three cases. In case 1, when the receiver moves along the charging lane (d_x is from 0 to 800 mm) and d_y is 0 mm (no lateral misalignment), the average coefficient coupling (k_r) is equal to 0.14. In case 2, when d_x is from 0 to 800 mm and d_y is 40 mm (lateral misalignment 40 mm), k_r is equal to 0.111. In case 3, when d_x is from 0 to 800 mm and d_y is

60 mm (lateral misalignment 60 mm), k_r is equal to 0.078. Thus, it can be concluded that the coupling coefficient depends on the position of the receiving coil. When the receiver moves, the total coupling coefficient changes. When the lateral misalignment increases, the total coupling coefficient decreases.

Fig. 2. Structure of the coils in the DWC system.

Fig. 3. The total coupling coefficient.

C. Transfer Efficiency Characteristics Analysis

The dual-side LCC compensation circuit was designed for this system [22]. Figure 4 shows the equivalent circuit diagram from the inverter output on the primary side to the battery on the secondary side. The equivalent load impedance seen from the active rectifier side to the battery is called R_L .

Fig. 4. Equivalent circuit diagram.

Transfer efficiency is calculated as follows [22]:

$$\eta = \frac{R_L I_r^2}{R_L I_r^2 + R_r I_{Lr}^2 + R_1 I_{L1}^2 + R_2 I_{L2}^2 + R_3 I_{L3}^2} \tag{1}$$

$$= \frac{R_L}{R_L \frac{R_r}{\omega^2 L_{fr}^2} + \frac{3+k_r^2 Q_i Q_r}{k_r^2 Q_i Q_r} + R_L \left(1 + \frac{6}{k_r^2 Q_i Q_r}\right) + \frac{3\omega^2 L_{fr}^2}{R_r} \frac{1}{k_r^2 Q_i Q_r}}$$

where $Q_i = \omega L_f / R_i$ and $Q_r = \omega L_r / R_r$ is the coil quality factor. $R_1, R_2, R_3,$ and R_r are the resistances of the transmitting and receiving coils, respectively. Equation (1) shows that the transfer efficiency depends on the changing parameters during dynamic charging, which are k_r and R_L . While k_r depends on the position of the EV, R_L depends on the state of charge of the battery. Assuming that the value of k_r is known, the transfer efficiency depends only on R_L . To find the maximum transfer efficiency, the following system of equations must be solved:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial R_L} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \eta^2}{\partial R_L^2} < 0 \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

The maximum transfer efficiency is obtained as follows:

$$\eta_{max} = \frac{k_r^2 Q_i Q_r}{\left(\sqrt{3} + \sqrt{3 + k_r^2 Q_i Q_r}\right)^2} \tag{3}$$

The value of the equivalent load impedance is equal to:

$$R_L = R_{L,opt} = \frac{\omega^2 L_{fr}^2}{R_r} \sqrt{\frac{3}{3 + k_r^2 Q_i Q_r}} \tag{4}$$

where $R_{L,opt}$ is called optimal impedance, and $R_{L,opt}$ depends on the total coupling coefficient k_r . Equations (3) and (4) show that when $R_L = R_{L,opt}$, transfer efficiency is maximum.

Moreover, as seen above, k_r changes when the receiver moves, and in combination with (4) it is found that the value of $R_{L,opt}$ changes and depends on the receiver's position. Therefore, for maximum transfer efficiency, it is necessary to control R_L according to the $R_{L,opt}$ value. The coupling coefficient value needs to be estimated when the EVs move.

D. Estimation of the Coupling Coefficient by the Parameters Measured on the Secondary Side

The currents across the transmitting coils [22] are:

$$I_{L1} = I_{L2} = I_{L3} = I_{Li} = -\frac{U_{AB}}{1/(j\omega C_{fi})} = -j\omega C_{fi} U_{AB} \tag{5}$$

On the secondary side, the relationship among the parameters is:

$$\begin{cases} (j\omega L_r + R_r + \frac{1}{j\omega C_r}) I_{Lr} + \frac{1}{j\omega C_{fr}} I_{Cfr} = j\omega M_r I_{Li} \\ (j\omega L_{fr} + R_L) I_r = \frac{1}{j\omega C_{fr}} I_{Cfr} \\ I_{Cfr} = I_{Lr} - I_r \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

From (5) and (6), the calculation expression k_r is drawn:

$$k_r = \frac{L_{fr}}{U_{AB} \sqrt{L_i L_r}} \left[\frac{R_r}{\omega L_{fr}} U_{ab} + \omega L_{fr} I_{ab} \right] \tag{7}$$

where U_{AB} is the RMS of the output voltage of the primary side inverter, and U_{ab} and I_{ab} are the RMS of the input voltage and current of the active rectifier on the secondary side. Thus, if U_{AB} is not adjusted or is constant, k_r can be estimated by measuring the value of U_{ab} and I_{ab} . This means that k_r can be estimated using only the parameters measured on the secondary side.

Fig. 5. (a) Mosfet control signal, (b) MOSFET on/off state.

III. CC CHARGING AND IMPROVED EFFICIENCY WITH SECONDARY ACTIVE RECTIFIER PHASE SHIFT CONTROL

A. The Working Principle of the Proposed Active Rectifier

Active rectifier phase shift modulation was used to achieve both CC charging and efficiency improvement goals. The secondary active rectifier is controlled by methods of symmetric phase shift combined with phase synchronization. For the equivalent load impedance to be purely resistive, the input voltage and current of the active rectifier must be in phase. Then, phase shift modulation is performed to control the CC charging combined with impedance matching to improve the system's efficiency.

Figure 5 shows the waveforms and switching states of the active rectifier. u_{ab}^i and i_{ab}^i are the fundamental wave components of the input voltage and current of the active rectifier. $V_{Q1} \div V_{Q4}$ is the open signal of MOSFETs from Q_1 to Q_4 . The MOSFETs on the signal are synchronized with the zero moments of i_{ab}^i . MOSFETs from Q_1 to Q_4 operate at the resonant frequency. During one cycle, the current i_{ab} has negative and positive directions. At each cycle, there are four switching states of the IGBTs corresponding to six different stages, as shown in Figure 5(b).

State A, corresponds to phases (1) and (3), where Q_2 and Q_4 are on. Current i_{ab} flows through Q_2 and Q_4 , and no energy is transferred to the load. Therefore, u_{ab} and I_{Le} are zero. Energy has been accumulated in the capacitor C_0 fed to the load. State B, corresponds to phase (2), where Q_1 , Q_2 are on. Current i_{ab} flows to the load through Q_1 and Q_2 . u_{ab} is equal to U_{Le} , I_{Le} is equal to i_{ab} , and energy is transferred to the load. In state C, phases (4) and (6), and in state D, phase (5), the analysis is the same as in states A and B. Thus, in one duty cycle, u_{ab} has the following values:

$$u_{ab} = \begin{cases} 0: 0 < \omega t < \beta/2 \\ U_{Le} \cdot \beta/2 < \omega t < \pi - \beta/2 \\ 0: \pi - \beta/2 < \omega t < \pi + \beta/2 \\ -U_{Le}: \pi + \beta/2 < \omega t < 2\pi - \beta/2 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where β is the phase shift angle, and U_{Le} is the output voltage of the active rectifier. Based on the fundamental harmonic method, U_{ab} is calculated by:

$$U_{ab} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi} U_{Le} \cos \frac{\beta}{2} \quad (9)$$

The charging current is calculated as follows:

$$I_{Le} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi} I_{ab} \cos \frac{\beta}{2} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) shows that, when adjusting the β angle, the charging current can be controlled by a constant. Assuming that the reference charging current I_{Le} is known and I_{ab} is measured, the phase-shift angle β is determined by:

$$\beta = 2\alpha \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{2}} \frac{I_{Le}}{I_{ab}} \right) \quad (11)$$

Based on the power balance condition, R_{Le} is calculated by:

$$R_L = \frac{8}{\pi^2} R_{Le} \left(\cos \frac{\beta}{2} \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

Thus, when R_{Le} changes according to the charging state of the battery, changing the phase shift angle β will adjust the value of the equivalent impedance R_L . Therefore, it is possible to control the equivalent load impedance according to the optimal load impedance. An expression can be derived from (12) to calculate the phase shift angle when R_L and R_{Le} are known:

$$\beta = 2\alpha \cos \left(\sqrt{\frac{R_L}{\frac{8}{\pi^2} R_{Le}}} \right) \quad (13)$$

These equations show that as the phase shift angle changes, the charging current and the load impedance vary accordingly.

B. The Proposed Control Structure

During the charging process, the BMS will calculate and decide the charging current value for the battery. The reference charging current is $I_{L.ref}$, and the tolerable charging fluctuation rate is δ . Thus, the current limit in the CC charging mode is:

$$\begin{cases} I_{L.ref}^+ = I_{L.ref}(1 + \delta) \\ I_{L.ref}^- = I_{L.ref}(1 - \delta) \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Figure 6 shows the block diagram of the CC charging control combined with optimal impedance tracking to improve efficiency. The referent charging current ($I_{Le.ref}$) is given from the BMS. The RMS of the input voltage/current (U_{ab}/I_{ab}) and the output voltage/current (U_{Le}/I_{Le}) of the active rectifier are measured. k_r is estimated by (7), from which the $R_{L.opt}$ can be calculated according to (4). Substituting $R_{L.opt}$ into (13) will find the optimal phase shift angle (β_{opt}). Substituting the optimal phase shift angle (β_{opt}) into (10) will provide the optimal current charging ($I_{Le.opt}$). On the other hand, the limits of the phase shift angle [β_{min}, β_{max}] can be calculated from (14) and (11). Next, the limit on the equivalent load impedance [$R_{L.min}, R_{L.max}$] is calculated according to (12). Finally, the efficiency optimization algorithm is implemented with the inputs $I_{Le.opt}, R_{L.opt}, R_{L.min}, R_{L.max}, I_{Le.ref}^+, I_{Le.ref}^-$.

Figure 7 shows the flow chart of the efficiency optimization algorithm. The closed-loop controller is used to control the CC charging mode. The referent charging current is given from the efficiency optimization algorithm. If $R_{L.opt}$ is greater than $R_{L.min}$

and less than $R_{L.max}$, the system performs $I_{Le.opt}$ as the reference current for the current controller. If $R_{L.opt}$ is greater than $R_{L.max}$, the system performs $I_{Le.ref}^+$ as the reference current for the current controller. If $R_{L.opt}$ is less than $R_{L.min}$, the system performs $I_{Le.ref}^-$ as the reference current for the current controller. Based on the errors, the PI calculates the β for the active rectifier. In addition, the PLL circuit is used to determine when i_{ab}^+ crosses zero. The synchronization signal is sent to the phase shift modulator to open the IGBT $Q1$ to $Q4$. To design the controllers, the transfer function of the system needs to be determined. However, with resonant converters with many capacitors and inductors as in this system, the modeling to find the transfer function is very complicated. Therefore, this study used the model recognition method on the PSIM software to identify the transfer function (15). The PI controller is designed as in (16).

$$G_{\beta I} = \frac{1.05 \times 10^{10} s + 6.922 \times 10^{14}}{s^3 + 6.945 \times 10^5 s^2 + 1.948 \times 10^{11} s + 1.242 \times 10^{16}} \quad (15)$$

$$G_c = -200 - \frac{60118.4115}{s} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 6. The block diagram of the CC charging control combined with optimal impedance tracking.

Fig. 7. Flow chart for the efficiency optimization algorithm.

IV. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To verify the accuracy of the proposed method, a simulation model was built on PSIM according to Table I.

TABLE I. SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
P_0	1.5 kW	L_{fi}	52.6 μ H
U_{DC}	310 V	C_{fi}	66.5 nF
U_{Le}	400 V	C_1	93.7 nF
f_{sw}	85 kHz	C_2	123.2 nF
L_i	102 μ H	C_3	95 nF
R_i	0.13 Ω	L_{fr}	28.9 μ H
L_r	120 μ H	C_{fr}	120.9 nF
R_r	0.13 Ω	C_r	38.5 nF

When the reference charging current ($I_{Le.ref}$) is 4.5A, the tolerable charging fluctuation rate δ is 5%. Figure 8 shows the simulation results when the equivalent load changes. The equivalent load (R_{Le}) increases from 70 Ω to 90 Ω and 100 Ω , the charging current follows the referent within the allowable range (4.75 A, 4.5 A, and 4.25 A), the charging voltage increases respectively (332.5 V, 405 V, and 425 V), and the

average system efficiency is more than 81%. Thus, the simulation results of the CC charging process are consistent with the efficiency optimization algorithm presented in Section III(B). Figure 9 shows the dynamic charging model built in the laboratory with 1.5kW, 150mm transfer distance, and 85kHz working frequency built in the laboratory. The coils were built in stranded wire. Polypropylene film capacitors were used to reduce losses and increase bearing capacity at high currents and frequencies. PE40 ferrite bars were used to increase magnetic conductivity. CMF20120D SIC MOSFETs were used to increase the converter efficiency.

Fig. 8. Current/voltage waveforms and system efficiency when equivalent load changes.

Fig. 9. The experimental model.

Fig. 10. Output voltage/current of 85 kHz inverter.

Fig. 11. Input/output signal of PLL circuit.

Fig. 12. Active rectifier voltage/current waveform.

Fig. 13. System efficiency characteristics when CC charging.

Figure 10 shows the output voltage/current of the inverter. The results show that the resonant frequency is 85 kHz and that the ZVS condition for MOSFETs was achieved. Figure 11 is the result of measuring the input/output signal of the PLL circuit. The results show that the output pulse of the PLL circuit accurately captures the phase angle of the current. The pulse goes high when the current cuts through the zero point from negative to positive and goes low when the current cuts through the zero point from positive to negative. Figure 12 shows the active rectifier voltage/current waveform. The results show that the voltage and current are phase-synchronized.

Figure 13 shows the system efficiency when the receiving coil is centered on the first transmitting coil (T1), $(p_x, p_y) = (0, 0)$, and the equivalent load varies. In case 1, without an efficiency optimization algorithm, the system efficiency was highest at an equivalent load R_{Le} of around 65Ω . When the equivalent load increases or decreases, the system efficiency decreases. In case 2, with an efficiency optimization algorithm, the system efficiency was over 82% in a wide range of equivalent loads. Thus, when applying the efficiency optimization algorithm, the efficiency was raised above 3%. The maximum system efficiency achieved was 85%.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study implemented CC charge control with an efficiency optimization algorithm. The BMS calculates the required current charge. Then, the tolerable charging current fluctuation rate is set up. The optimal load impedance is calculated based on the previously estimated coupling coefficient. Limit load impedance values were also calculated. An efficient optimization algorithm was implemented to calculate the reference current applied to the charging current control loop. When applying the efficiency optimization algorithm, the efficiency increased by more than 3%, and the maximum efficiency achieved was 85%. Future research will focus on CV charging control to further improve the system.

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Factors Influencing Online Shopping in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

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ABSTRACT

As online shopping is a rapidly growing sector in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), this study explored the influence of multiple factors on this topic: age, gender, and payment responsibility, which was considered for the first time. Data were collected from five focus groups with 30 participants to explore online customers' perceptions and practices. Based on the findings, a questionnaire was built and distributed, and 2,109 responses were received revealing different factors affecting online shopping in the KSA: the user experience with the Internet and online shopping, the product variety and diversity that online shopping provides, the competitive prices for online products, the convenience provided, and the security of online shopping. The analysis indicated insignificant gender and payment responsibility differences for all former factors. However, age variations were found for some factors, revealing that information regarding online customers' perceptions and practices is important for both the existing online companies to improve their adapted marketing strategies and those striving to enter the market.

Keywords-age; gender; Kingdom of Saudi Arabia; online shopping; payment responsibility

I. INTRODUCTION

According to a technical report issued recently by the Saudi Communications, Space and Technology Commission (CST), the percentage of purchasing goods or services online is 62.6% and more females engage in online shopping than males (74.4% vs. 53.6%) [1]. According to [2], Saudi Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) previously relied on social networks to sell their products and services through straightforward direct messages. However, with the emergence of e-commerce platforms like Salla and Zid, the majority of SMEs now run their businesses online through online stores. These platforms assist SMEs in starting and expanding their online businesses by developing and designing their online stores, managing their inventory, offering various digital payment options, and providing marketing solutions. As online shopping is widespread and the perspectives of online shopping have not been widely examined to identify the factors that comprise them, this study aims to advance the knowledge on this subject and explore the influence of gender, age, and payment responsibility on online shopping. The last factor, payment responsibility, was targeted because it is common in Saudi households that, religiously and legally, the husband/father is responsible for the life expenses of his wife and offspring. Therefore, some online buyers are not the same person who is financially responsible, which might affect their perspective on online shopping. Consequently, the objective of this study was to evaluate the perspectives of online shopping and to provide insight into the attitudinal factors that affect online shopping in the KSA. This study aimed to answer the following research questions: (1) What are the underlying

factors that affect online shopping in the KSA? (2) Are there differences between male and female online shopping tendencies? (3) Does the age of shoppers influence their online shopping tendencies? (4) Is there a resulting impact from who is responsible for paying for online shopping? This study explores the dimensions of people's practices and perceptions toward online shopping in the KSA and could be beneficial for developing and adapting the marketing strategies of any online company striving to enter the markets. Additionally, this study can provide a basis for future cross-cultural research on this topic among the countries in the region.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW-HYPOTHESIS FORMING

Previous research on factors that affect online shopping [3] was divided into three major groups: characteristics of the Internet as a purchase channel [4-6], characteristics of customers [7-9], and characteristics of the website/product [10-12]. Using the Internet to purchase items includes characteristics such as perceived risk, utility, convenience, time-saving, ease of ordering, service quality, trust, accessibility, and the expertise required for online shopping. Demographics, psychological factors, inventiveness, familiarity with computers and the Internet, and inclinations toward online and consumer shopping are some of the traits of customers. The attributes of the product/website comprise the attributes of the product, the features of the website, and the risk mitigation strategies (money-back guarantee, offering reputable brands, discounted price, security, and privacy). In [13], it was found that the main factors influencing cyberspace buying behaviors are the security of online shopping, product prices, service

quality, and commercial credits, while secondary factors included age, gender, education, and store design.

This study explored online shopping attitudes related to Internet characteristics as a purchase channel and the influence of three subfactors of the customer characteristics group of factors, gender, age, and payment responsibility, on attitudinal factors. Relatively few studies have looked at how attitudes toward online shopping are influenced by these factors, despite the growing number of Internet users and shoppers. Furthermore, several studies addressing these problems concentrated on testing theories without first determining the underlying attitudinal components. Online shopping is viewed from a variety of perspectives and motivations. However, few studies attempted to identify the key elements of online shopping viewpoints. In [14], seven constructs of general shopping orientation were found: in-home shopping tendency, price consciousness, brand/fashion consciousness, confidence in the ability to purchase, brand/store loyalty, and shopping enjoyment. To measure the attitudinal factors that influence the success of Internet commerce, in [15], two sets of variables were used that were labeled means and fundamental objectives, a classification proposed in [16]. In [15], five constructs were found when analyzing means objectives, which can be interpreted as online product selection, online payment, trust in online vendors, travel for shopping, and online shipping errors. Four constructs were measured to determine the fundamental objectives: Internet product value, Internet customer relations, Internet ecology, and ease of shopping online. Later, in [9], five categories of attitudinal characteristics of online shopping were identified: convenience, security concerns, personality, user experience, and prices. Based on the former arguments, the following hypothesis was proposed:

H1: *Multiple factors influence the practices and perspectives of online shopping.*

Many factors have been identified to influence online buying practices, among which gender is a frequently used demographic variable. For instance, in [17], it was found that while perceived value is greatly impacted by the quality of e-services and products, the magnitude of these effects varies depending on age and gender. Male consumers prioritized e-service quality, while female consumers were more interested in product quality. In addition, in [18], it was found that men generally had more favorable perspectives toward e-tailers (electronic retailing), online purchase/repurchase, and e-payments than women. Moreover, the results of [19] identified significant gender differences in visual attention to online shopping information and shopping perspectives about the products presented. Female participants visually attended most online shopping information areas more than males, and visual attention to consumer opinion areas influenced their perspectives on products to some extent. Although males' visual perspectives were lower than females', visual attention to product information and consumer opinion areas extensively affected their shopping attitudes. Conversely, in [20], it was found that when it comes to online shopping, women tend to perceive more risk. Moreover, women are less likely than men to adopt e-commerce because they do not trust it to the same degree as men [7, 20-21]. Alternatively, in [22], it was asserted

that male consumers are less inclined to think of the Internet as a helpful tool for shopping. According to [23], gender differences exist in online shopping where women are affected by far more factors than men. Therefore, the following hypothesis was formed:

H2: *Practices and perspectives of online shopping vary according to gender.*

In addition to gender, age is also identified as a demographic factor that influences online shopping practices. In [21], it was found that age exerts a negative influence on online shopping for goods and services. In [17], it was found that older consumers were more preoccupied with product quality, while younger consumers focused more on the quality of e-services. Furthermore, in [24], it was shown that older buyers were more concerned with the sacrifice they make, the time, money, and effort required to obtain a good or service, compared to younger ones. The findings in [25] suggest a strong correlation between age and attitude towards online shopping, where young consumers were more keen on online shopping. In [26], it was found that most online consumers were male (52%) and 18-25 years old (69%). Therefore, the following hypothesis was proposed:

H3: *Practices and perspectives of online shopping vary according to age.*

The third demographic factor for this study was the responsibility for paying, which is related to income level. In [21], it was found that income and online purchase of goods and services are positively correlated. In [27], it was found that, among demographic factors, gender and income were the main factors influencing online shopping practices. The results from [28] show that income, as a demographic variable, has a significant impact on consumers' online shopping frequency. In [29], it was found that income level does not affect online shopping for necessary items, such as computer accessories, and customers of all income levels shopped mostly during discounts and special offers. In [30], it was found that income level has a significant influence on the relationship between convenience, website functionality, security, customer service, and customer satisfaction with online shopping. However, these studies did not discuss whether buyers were not the same person who is responsible for paying for the online shopping transaction, where it seems to most affect perspectives towards online shopping. Based on the foregoing discussion, the following hypothesis was proposed:

H4: *Practices and perspectives of online shopping vary according to who is responsible for paying the online purchases.*

Analyzing the influence of this factor on online shopping practices was not considered before and it would be beneficial to consider it and to know if there is a resulting impact from who is responsible for paying for online shopping.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study was divided into two successive phases: conducting focus groups and administering a questionnaire. This method was designed to explore the perspectives and

practices of online shopping customers. Based on this investigation, the topic was studied and investigated comprehensively, and the results reflect the empirical attitudes and behaviors of customers in the KSA toward online shopping.

A. First Phase: Focus Groups

Focus groups allow participants to formulate new questions and concepts and facilitate the process of investigating and analyzing their views and concerns [31]. Focus group meetings are social events that typically include six to eight people [32]. In [33], it was reported that it may take up to 32 phone calls or in-person meetings to find just eight people for a group. These people are encouraged to discuss issues and form their opinions and thoughts through debate [34]. Without passing judgment on the participants' viewpoints, a moderator sets the topic of the conversation and assists in generating opposing points of view [35]. To analyze data, quotations from focus groups were categorized into types of descriptions or concepts and then compared against targeted concepts of the online shopping perspectives [36]. Five focus groups were conducted during January 2023 with 30 participants: a male-only group (seven participants), two female-only groups (six participants each), and two mixed-gender groups (five females and six males). All focus group participants were over 18 years old and randomly recruited. The focus groups were useful in providing preliminary information about areas that would be useful to focus on in the next step of data collection.

B. Second Phase: Questionnaire

Subsequently, a questionnaire was designed to evaluate the possible influence of different factors on online shopping perspectives. The questionnaire was built based both on [37] and the outcomes of the focus groups and was validated using exploratory interviews. To convey the intended meaning, some parts were reworded, while others were added or removed. Specifically, respondents were asked to determine whether the suggested elements of the questionnaire reflected their perspectives on online shopping and to indicate additional elements that they considered important factors that needed to be investigated to determine the final and relevant list of statements related to perspectives on online shopping. The survey instrument consisted of two parts. The first part gathered gender, age, and payment responsibility, and the second part included 28 five-point Likert statements ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". The questionnaire was created using Google Forms and targeted random subjects aged 18 and over living in the KSA. The completion time of the questionnaire was 10-15 minutes. Once the answers were collected, SPSS v.20 was used to process the data.

IV. RESULTS

A. Results from Focus Groups

Analyzing the data from the focus groups revealed five main factors related directly to online shopping that influenced buyer practices in the KSA. These factors are as follows:

- Factor 1: Security consists of variables that relate to trust in online shopping, the feeling of being safe to give out personal or financial information, the use of personal details

for particular purposes, the reliability of online shopping, and the safer feeling when using the option "pay in cash when receiving the order" more than paying by credit card.

- Factor 2: Convenience refers to the possibility of shopping from home at any time that is convenient for the customer, time and money savings, and the superior comfort that online shopping provides over traditional.
- Factor 3: Price referred to questions on price concerns, such as offering competitive prices and the customer being able to seek the best price before purchasing, providing the best deal online, and prices being cheaper online compared to traditional shopping.
- Factor 4: User experience includes variables that were closely tied to the ease of placing an order online, the required service provided, and the simplicity and ease of buying online.
- Factor 5: Product variation includes variables about providing products that cannot be found in traditional shopping, more information about products, more product choices, and better product selection.

These factors were used to build the questions in the questionnaire that was then distributed to the respondents.

B. Questionnaire Results

There were 2,109 responses to the questionnaire, the majority of which were women (78.7%) while men were 21.3%. Most of the participants were in the 18-25 age group at 73.9%, followed by the 26-35 age group at 12.8%. The age group with the smallest population was the one of people aged over 56 years, with a rate of 1%. When the respondents were asked how many times they shopped online during the past month, most participants (64%) picked one to four times, while the least number of individuals (only 170, 8%) stated they used online shopping more than nine times during the past month, which can also be described as twice a week. A total of 281 participants, 13%, did not use online shopping for different reasons, such as "I prefer the traditional way of shopping to ensure a product's size, color, and quality", "I didn't need to buy anything online last month", "I was running out of money last month", and "I don't trust online shopping". As for online shoppers, most of them (80%) were responsible for paying for their purchases with their own money, while 20% depended on another person to pay, usually a parent (mostly the father) or the husband. The reason given was that this is one of his responsibilities and/or the buyer had no private income.

1) Security

Table I shows that a high percentage of the participants who used online shopping during the last month trust online shopping and consider it reliable, and 80% of them feel safer when paying in cash when receiving the order. Meanwhile, a moderate percentage, ranging from 61% to 67%, felt safe to give out personal or financial information online.

2) Convenience

As Table II illustrates, most informants agreed on the convenience that online shopping provides, while 70% to 93%

of them were highly influenced by the seven variables related to this factor, especially the 24-hour availability of online shopping. However, the least agreed-upon element related to not being disturbed by sales promotions during online shopping.

TABLE I. SECURITY AND ONLINE SHOPPING PRACTICES (N = 1,828)

	Elements	Mean	SD	%	Degree of agreement
1	Online shopping is reliable	3.73	1.02	75	High
2	I feel safe to give out personal information	3.06	1.18	61	Medium
3	I feel safe that my personal information will be used for a particular purpose	3.36	1.15	67	Medium
4	I feel safe to give out financial details	3.10	1.19	62	Medium
5	I trust online shopping	3.45	1.06	69	High
6	I feel safer when using the option "pay in cash when receiving the order"	3.99	1.14	80	High

TABLE II. CONVENIENT ONLINE SHOPPING PRACTICES (N = 1,828)

	Elements	Mean	SD	%	Degree of agreement
1	When I shop online, I am not hassled by sales promotion activities	3.51	1.29	70	High
2	When I shop online, I don't feel pressure to finalize the purchase process	4.06	1.05	81	High
3	Online shopping saves time	4.52	0.79	90	Very high
4	Online shopping saves money	3.56	1.27	71	High
5	Online shopping offers 24-hour access	4.67	0.64	93	Very high
6	Online shopping is more convenient than traditional shopping	4.41	0.83	88	Very high
7	Online shopping offers the comfort of home	4.60	0.68	92	Very high

3) User Experience

As shown in Table III, a very high percentage of participants (76%–92%) agreed on the speed and ease of online shopping and the online ordering process. However, the least agreed upon encountering problems during online shopping.

TABLE III. USER EXPERIENCE AND ONLINE SHOPPING PRACTICES (N = 1,828)

	Elements	Mean	SD	%	Degree of agreement
1	It is easy to place an order online	4.61	0.59	92	Very high
2	The Internet provides the required service	4.37	0.78	87	Very high
3	Online shopping allows shopping at one's own pace	4.50	0.71	90	Very high
4	I encounter no problems when shopping online	3.82	1.06	76	High
5	Online shopping is fast and easy	4.47	0.70	89	Very high
6	I have no problems using Internet technology	4.45	0.77	89	Very high

4) Product Variations

Out of all the participants, 83%–90% uses eagerly online shopping, as it provides more assortment and diversity of products than traditional shopping, as seen in Table IV.

TABLE IV. PRODUCT VARIATION AND ONLINE SHOPPING PRACTICES (N = 1,828)

	Elements	Mean	SD	%	Degree of agreement
1	Online shopping provides more information about a product than traditional shopping	4.17	0.98	0.83	High
2	Online shopping provides products I cannot find using traditional shopping	4.36	0.79	0.87	Very high
3	Online shopping provides more product choices in size and color	4.44	0.73	0.89	Very high
4	Online shopping provides more selection of products to choose from	4.48	0.68	0.90	Very high

5) Price

As shown in Table V, a very high percentage of individuals (69%–91%) agreed that the prices online were reasonable and found the best deals and better prices compared to traditional shopping. The least agreed upon was that the elements related to online prices are fixed, with no hidden costs.

TABLE V. PRICE AND ONLINE SHOPPING PRACTICES (N = 1,828)

	Elements	Mean	SD	%	Degree of agreement
1	The Internet allows one to look for the best price before purchasing	4.55	0.68	0.91	Very high
2	It is easy to get the best deals online	4.28	0.81	0.86	Very high
3	Online shopping offers competitive prices	4.38	0.76	0.88	Very high
4	I can get better prices by shopping online compared to traditional shopping	4.35	0.82	0.87	Very high
5	Prices for online shopping are fixed and have no hidden costs	3.43	1.17	0.69	High
6	In online shopping, I can learn the price quickly and accurately	4.26	0.84	0.85	Very high

6) All Five Factors

Table VI shows that a high percentage of the participants agreed with all five factors. The participants' online practices and perspectives were influenced very significantly by the user experience, where the average was 4.37 (87%), followed by the product variety and diversity that online shopping provides. The percentage for this factor was the same as the former; however, the average was slightly less at 4.36. The effect of the remaining three factors, price, convenience, and security, is still high, with 84% for the first two factors and 69% for security. Considering the factors resulting from the analysis, H1 is verified.

TABLE VI. ALL FIVE FACTORS.

	Elements	Mean	SD	%	Degree of agreement
1	Convenience	4.19	0.55	0.84	High
2	Security	3.45	0.79	0.69	High
3	User experience	4.37	0.57	0.87	Very high
4	Price	4.21	0.60	0.84	High
5	Product variation	4.36	0.63	0.87	Very high

7) Gender Differences

Table VII shows the results of the T-test for two independent samples to identify differences in online shopping practices between males and females. The *T* value was not statistically significant (*T* value is insignificant at p-value > 0.05) for the five factors: convenience, security, user experience, prices, and product variation. This confirms that gender does not affect online shopping practices, meaning that males and females have similar perspectives of online shopping practices and their opinions do not differ greatly, which disproves H2.

TABLE VII. GENDER DIFFERENCES

		N	Mean	SD	T	P-value	Significance
Convenience	Male	364	4.18	0.55	-0.331	0.741	Not significant
	Female	1,464	4.19	0.55			
Security	Male	364	3.43	0.80	-0.528	0.598	Not significant
	Female	1,464	3.45	0.79			
User experience	Male	364	4.34	0.57	-0.981	0.327	Not significant
	Female	1,464	4.38	0.57			
Price	Male	364	4.19	0.63	-0.775	0.438	Not significant
	Female	1,464	4.21	0.59			
Product variation	Male	364	4.31	0.69	-1.817	0.069	Not significant
	Female	1,464	4.38	0.61			

8) Age Differences

Table VIII illustrates the results of the ANOVA test to identify the disparities in online shopping practices according to age. The F-value was statistically significant, with a p-value < 0.05 for user experience, price, and product variation, indicating that age influences online shopping practices on these factors. Meanwhile, the F-value was not statistically significant, with a p-value > 0.05 for convenience and security, implying that age does not affect the convenience and security of online shopping practices. Therefore, H3 was partly verified regarding user experience, prices, and product variation and was partly disproved for convenience and security.

9) Payment Responsibility Differences

Table IX displays the results of the ANOVA test to identify distinctions in online shopping practices according to payment responsibility. The F-value was not statistically significant for all five factors. This suggests that payment responsibility does not affect online shopping practices and disproves H4.

V. DISCUSSION

As mentioned above, the percentage of buying goods or services online in the KSA is more than 62% [1]. Therefore, it is important to examine the factors affecting the practices and

perspectives of online shoppers and advance the knowledge of this subject.

TABLE VIII. AGE DIFFERENCES

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Significance
Convenience	Between groups	1.265	4	0.316	1.062	0.374	Not significant
	Within groups	542.823	1,823	0.298			
	Total	544.088	1,827				
Security	Between groups	4.830	4	1.207	1.930	0.103	Not significant
	Within groups	1,140.610	1,823	0.626			
	Total	1,145.440	1,827				
User experience	Between groups	9.832	4	2.458	7.714	0.000*	Significant
	Within groups	580.874	1,823	0.319			
	Total	590.706	1,827				
Price	Between groups	5.406	4	1.352	3.781	0.005*	Significant
	Within groups	651.715	1,823	0.357			
	Total	657.121	1,827				
Product variation	Between groups	18.226	4	4.556	11.825	0.000*	Significant
	Within groups	702.459	1,823	0.385			
	Total	720.685	1,827				

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

TABLE IX. PAYMENT RESPONSIBILITY DIFFERENCES

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Significance
Convenience	Between groups	2.152	3	0.717	2.414	0.065	Not significant
	Within groups	541.936	1,824	0.297			
	Total	544.088	1,827				
Security	Between groups	1.753	3	0.584	0.932	0.425	Not significant
	Within groups	1,143.687	1,824	0.627			
	Total	1,145.440	1,827				
User experience	Between groups	1.272	3	0.424	1.312	0.269	Not significant
	Within groups	589.435	1,824	0.323			
	Total	590.706	1,827				
Price	Between groups	1.312	3	0.437	1.216	0.302	Not significant
	Within groups	655.810	1,824	0.360			
	Total	657.121	1,827				
Product variation	Between groups	1.690	3	0.563	1.429	0.232	Not significant
	Within groups	718.995	1,824	0.394			
	Total	720.685	1,827				

Based on the analysis, five factors were found to greatly influence the practices and perspectives of online customers (security, convenience, user experience, price, and product

variation), supporting the first research hypothesis and corroborating the findings of [9]. Consequently, this suggests that companies trying to sell through websites should consider the former factors and their influence on customers' online practices and perspectives. More online companies must allow customers to pay in cash when receiving the requested order, which, based on the analysis, is an important element that improves the security of online shopping. At the same time, web designers should request minimal personal and financial information from customers and make the security and privacy policies for such information as clear and simple as possible to them. Moreover, to minimize any insecurity and avoid inconvenience, websites must not share this kind of information with a third party unless they have clear permission from the customer. Also, online companies must decrease sales promotions as much as possible, as the results show that it disturbs online customers. According to [1], the percentage of Internet distribution in the KSA was 98.6% in 2022, and, as detailed in the report, it is widely used by individuals of different age groups, from 10 years to 74 years, which can explain the high percentage of participants with good experience on Internet technology generally and online shopping specifically. In this case, online companies should consider the speed and ease of online shopping and the process of ordering online. Another factor motivating customers to buy online instead of traditional shopping is the variety and diversity of products online, which companies can enhance with reasonable prices. However, they must ensure that no costs are hidden, otherwise, they will lose credibility.

Analysis of gender disparities among participants indicated insignificant gender variations in all five factors. These findings contrast with those of [14, 17, 20-23, 27]. Similarly, the analysis of payment responsibility differences among subjects indicates insignificant disparities for all five factors, meaning that whoever is responsible for paying has similar views of online purchasing practices, and their opinions do not differ considerably.

Interestingly, the analysis of age variations among the respondents indicated insignificant age differences for two factors: convenience and security. That is, regardless of age, online shoppers have similar views of online shopping practices and perspectives. However, the age differences were significant for the remaining three factors: price, user experience, and product variation.

It is worth mentioning that the data reflected the actual daily issues that affect online shopping by concentrating on five areas that were selected from the focus groups, and the questionnaire was built based on this. The questionnaire was useful and sufficient to measure the practices, perceptions, intentions, attitudes, and opinions of online shoppers, and it provided a quick, economical, and efficient way to collect a lot of data from a large sample (2,109 responses). However, while the current study was exploratory and used a self-reported approach that was as transparent as possible to allow others to examine and build upon this work, future research should take a different approach that relies on gathering practical practices to move beyond this initial exploration of shoppers' practices and perceptions to a more confirmatory approach. For e-

commerce developers, doing this will produce a more trustworthy knowledge base.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

KSA marketers could use the results of this study as a basis for developing online shopping. Furthermore, the results of this study can be used to understand the practices and perspectives of online customers in the KSA and provide a basis for future cross-cultural research of similar studies between countries in the region. Online vendors in the KSA can create effective marketing strategies based on the five attitudinal factors identified. For future research, the amount of questions on income, the average amount of time spent on the Internet, the types of websites visited, and the products purchased could be increased. In addition, it would be beneficial to address the distinction between online shopping practices before and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

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About the Automation of an Autonomous Sail-propelled Search Drone

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents the prototype of an autonomous sail-propelled vehicle, powered by sails and equipped with mini solar panels, intended for the surveillance of maritime space. Hardware and software aspects regarding the automation of this unmanned boat are addressed. Conceptual solutions have been identified to ensure short manufacturing times, component accessibility (price and availability on the free market), and high system reliability. The paper proposes an original solution to respond to at least two imperative needs: the safety and security of commercial and military navigation in the Black Sea area (faced with a tense geo-political climate) and the increased need to integrate European and global policies on reducing pollution and promoting renewable energy principles.

Keywords-Arduino; autonomous vehicle; microcontroller; WiFi module; photovoltaic cell

I. INTRODUCTION

As early as 2007, in response to the Commission's Green Deal on the future of the European Union's maritime policy, the Parliament adopted a resolution supporting an integrated approach to maritime policy, with a safe and secure marine environment being essential for the development of marine economic activities. In the current geo-political context of the Black Sea region, the safety of maritime space has become a priority, with earlier detection of dangerous situations and / or obstacles being of paramount importance, along with increasing the reaction and intervention capacity within specific missions regarding the monitoring of maritime traffic, securing civil and military infrastructure, search and rescue operations, and protecting the marine environment. Unmanned surveillance systems (airborne, on the water surface, underwater, and on shore) operating independently of the ship with minimal human intervention quickly highlighted their potential to create an adaptable and interconnected network that will ensure ship protection, secure shipping routes, and allow

access to dangerous areas for vessels with crews onboard. The current paper aims to present an integrated prototype to the concept of "blue energies": an automated, very small, unmanned vessel, powered by sails and equipped with mini solar panels. Launched near ships or coastal and port areas, this autonomous vessel can have multiple functions: monitoring the marine environment, gathering information (scientific, commercial, tactical), identifying obstacles (navigation or combat), performing early identification, monitoring, deterrence and, eventually, destroying threats in the navigation area. Given the increased destruction potential of these unmanned surveillance systems operating on the water surface, in the open sea, conceptual solutions (design and construction) are sought that ensure short manufacturing times, component accessibility (price and availability on the open market) and high system reliability [1-2]. Describing the concept of automation originated from the notion of modifying a device or one of its components in a manner that would enable independent operation without much human intervention, by achieving automated control over specific processes. Automation has

been brought into effect through a range of methods, encompassing mechanical, hydraulic, pneumatic, electrical, electronic, and computational devices, often used in combination. Complex systems such as contemporary factories, aircrafts, and ships typically integrate all these techniques. The benefits of automation encompass reduced labor requirements, savings in electricity consumption and material costs, and enhancements in precision and quality [3-5]. The broad-ranging advantages attributed to automation encompass heightened production quotas and augmented productivity, optimized material employment, superior product quality, elevated safety measures, condensed working hours, and reduced production timelines. Consequently, the imminent prospect for automation technologies holds the promise of fostering a progressively expanding socio-economic milieu, where individuals can relish an elevated and enriched standard of living [6-9]. The concept of Autonomous Surface Vehicles (ASVs) or Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USVs) emerged as a practical response to the need for creating compact waterborne vessels capable of functioning on the surface without requiring crew presence. This concept was initially put into practice towards the conclusion of World War II. These USVs found application in military contexts, including tasks like mine detection, reconnaissance, surveillance, intelligence gathering, surface warfare, and safeguarding strategic installations [9-13]. The potential of ASVs extends to serving as force multipliers in different naval operational domains due to their adaptable structures and capability to transport various payloads. With the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into fully mature ASVs, it is foreseen that by the conclusion of 2025, ASVs will seamlessly operate within naval task groups, collaborating with crewed vessels [12-16]. The development and construction of ASVs poses intricate challenges for builders and developers alike. To optimize their functionality, designers aim to substitute human interface elements with remote interfaces, allowing control from mobile units, command centers, and floating platforms [17-18]. Thanks to advancements in USV control systems and continually evolving navigation technologies, unmanned vessels now function at various levels of autonomy. These range from remotely controlled USVs to partially and fully autonomous USVs that adhere to the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea (COLREG). ASVs are making significant headway in multiple research sectors, encompassing environmental monitoring, seabed mapping, commercial transport, surveillance, and especially military and naval operations [18-20]. Central to the construction of pilotless surface vehicles are microcontrollers that act as command-and-control hubs. These microcontrollers underpin control and communication software, integrating collision avoidance sensors and other relevant sensor systems. To maximize the processing of sensor data and minimize latency, ASVs incorporate cutting-edge data analysis and transmission technologies [20]. ASV power sources vary, contingent on factors such as design, size, and mission scope. Options encompass diesel, gasoline, electric hybrids, batteries, and renewable energy sources like solar and wind power. Nonetheless, battery-powered, or renewables-driven systems are most prevalent, given the challenges inherent in managing autonomy functions for internal combustion engines on unmanned vessels [14, 21-22]. Concerning the payloads of

these ASVs, they predominantly encompass communication apparatuses for ship-to-ship coordination and data sharing with crewed or uncrewed platforms. The composition of an ASV's payload depends on its intended role and mission profile. It might involve cameras, optical sensors, infrared sensors, hydro-meteorological sensors, and various forms of sonars such as single-beam, multi-beam, side-scan, and synthetic aperture sonars. These sensors play a pivotal role in mine countermeasures, anti-submarine warfare, and survey operations. The employment of sensors can be individual or combined, dependent on the specific application [9, 25]. Given its remarkable performance in maritime contexts, this technology has rapidly captured the attention of naval forces globally. ASVs have evolved into indispensable tools for data acquisition, lure deployment, surveillance, mine clearance, submarine detection, and the protection of capital ships. Naval forces and defense industry entities worldwide are increasingly investing in ASV technologies [10, 25].

II. MAIN HARDWARE COMPONENTS

A. Arduino UNO

The Arduino UNO is the most well-known and widely used open-source processing board, built on a simple, flexible, and user-friendly hardware and software foundation, suitable even for beginners. The board features 20 digital and analog input/output pins that can be connected to various expansion boards (shields). It provides 14 digital pins (6 of which can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz ceramic resonator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It encompasses everything needed to support the ATmega328P microcontroller and deliver the desired results to the user [23, 24, 26]. When utilizing an Arduino development environment, all connections are programmed through serial connections. The implementation varies based on the hardware version. Several Arduino modules have integrated level shifters to facilitate the conversion between RS-232 and TTL logic levels. Current Arduino boards are programmed via USB and include USB-serial converters, such as the FTDI FT232. Some newer UNO models include a separate AVR chip programmed to function as a USB-serial converter, which can be reprogrammed through an ICSP interface [26]. Other models, like the Arduino Mini and official Boarduino, use detachable USB-serial adapters, cables, Bluetooth, or other methods [26].

B. Electric Servo Motors

The proposed autonomous sail-propelled vessel utilizes two different types of servo motors (Figure 1) for controlling the sails and the rudder. The movement of the sails from one side to the other is achieved by a standard quarter-scale servo motor, which has a 180-degree rotation in both directions, to a total of 360 degrees. On the other hand, the rudder is controlled by a standard micro servo motor, which has a 90-degree rotation in both directions, to a total of 180 degrees.

C. Ultrasonic Distance Sensor HC-SR04

The HC-SR04 ultrasonic distance sensor is a component used for distance measurement, compatible with Arduino boards. It consists of a receiver, a transmitter, and a control

circuit. The underlying principle of its operation is straightforward: the sensor automatically sends a series of 8 pulses at a frequency of 40 Hz and measures the time taken from the transmission to the reception of the wave [27].

Fig. 1. Placement of the servo motors on the boat's board.

D. WiFi Module ESP8266

The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module is an integrated System-on-Chip (SoC) with an embedded TCP/IP protocol stack, providing Wi-Fi connectivity to any microcontroller. The ESP8266 can act as a host for an application or take over all Wi-Fi networking functions from another application processor. The module comes pre-programmed with AT command firmware and possesses processing and storage capabilities powerful enough to be integrated with specific sensors and devices through GPIO pins. ESP8266 supports APSD for VoIP applications, interfaces with Bluetooth, and features a self-calibrating RF unit that allows it to operate effectively in various conditions [28].

E. GPS Shield Logger

The device is based on a GP3906-TLP GPS module, comprising a 66-channel GPS receiver with a refresh rate of up to 10 Hz. The GPS module will transmit constant position updates via a simple UART serial connection, which we can subsequently utilize in the boat's position tracking process. This component includes a switch that enables us to choose the GPS module's UART interface between hardware and software ports. It also features a μ SD card slot that operates through a hardware SPI port compatible with most Arduino boards, along with additional space for adding other components [29].

F. Compact Board MinIMU-9 v5

MinIMU-9 v5 is a compact board that integrates a 3-axis gyroscope (LSM6DS33), a 3-axis accelerometer, and a 3-axis magnetometer (LIS3MDL) to form an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU). The I2C interface facilitates nine separate measurements for rotation, acceleration, and magnetism, enabling the calculation of the sensor's absolute orientation. These readings provide the necessary data to establish a suitable reference system in terms of direction and altitude for the autonomous sail-propelled boat. The board employs new MEMS sensors that offer increased precision, resulting in lower noise levels and improved zero-rate compensation [30]. This technology contributes to the development and implementation of advanced control and navigation solutions,

essential in achieving superior performance in the field of autonomous navigation.

G. Electrical Power Supply of the Circuit

The electrical power supply for the entire circuit is ensured by connecting two Li-ion cells to two photovoltaic cells in a series configuration. This setup is reminiscent of a miniature off-grid circuit. To maintain a stable voltage level, a DC-DC voltage converter has been employed (Figures 2-3). This converter plays a pivotal role in regulating the output voltage, guaranteeing a consistent voltage level devoid of fluctuations at the terminals of the circuit. This configuration underscores the use of renewable energy sources to maintain the functionality of the circuit, without impacting the surrounding environment.

H. Block Diagram and Final Components Assembly

In this section, we aim to present the block diagram of the electrical circuit and the final layout of the electrical components (Figures 2-3).

The block diagram (Figure 2) provides an overview of how the components are interconnected, while the final assembly describes how the components have been physically positioned and interconnected on the circuit board or within the system's enclosure. Details pertaining to connections and assembly will be discussed to provide a clear understanding of how the electrical circuit was practically implemented. This was made possible with the assistance of the Fritzing software. Fritzing is an open-source hardware initiative that enables electronics to be used as a creative medium by anyone. Our offerings include a software tool, a community platform, and services reminiscent of Processing and Arduino. This ecosystem nurtures creativity by empowering users to document their prototypes, collaborate with others, facilitate electronics education in classrooms, and design and produce professional-grade PCBs [31]. The equipment described above was installed on a model vessel purchased on the free market, whose main technical characteristics are: length – 650 mm, width – 116.5 mm, mast height – 915 mm, total height – 1388 mm, total weight is about 1500 g, sail surface is 2226 cm². In Figure 4, the positioning of the electric circuit dedicated to the automation of the unmanned boat can be discerned on board.

Fig. 2. The block diagram of the electrical components.

Fig. 3. The final layout of the electrical components.

Fig. 4. Automation of the sail-propelled boat.

III. SOFTWARE COMPONENT

The software component constitutes an amalgamation of data, libraries, instructions, and interfaces that dictate the operational behavior of the hardware component. Subsequently, a general overview of the employed development environments, the operational algorithm, source code, and concluding remarks are presented.

A. Arduino IDE

The Arduino IDE is an integrated development environment (cross-platform application) written in the Java programming language. It incorporates a code editor with features such as cut and paste, find and replace, automatic indentation, bracket matching, and syntax highlighting. It offers straightforward mechanisms for compiling and uploading programs to an Arduino board with a simple click. Additionally, it encompasses a text editor for writing code, a

message area, a text console, a toolbar with buttons for common functions, and a range of menus. It connects to Arduino hardware for program uploading and communication [32]. Any Arduino code is divided into two sections. The first section, "setup," is executed only once (when the board is powered or the "Restart" button is pressed), while the second section, "loop," is run in a continuous loop if the board is powered. Therefore, the "setup" section contains only the initialization code, while the "loop" section contains the execution program [32]. Furthermore, the development environment can be expanded through libraries. These offer additional functionalities in sketch usage. Upon installing the IDE, a minimal number of libraries are also installed [32]. Libraries are included at the beginning of the program using the syntax "#include <Library Name>" or "#include "Library Name.h". These libraries have been developed by companies producing devices compatible with the Arduino IDE development environment, aiming to facilitate the use of components. The following libraries from the Arduino IDE development environment were used in the program's coding:

1. Library NeoSWSerial.h - designed to enable serial communication on other digital pins of the microcontroller, emulating software functionality. Serial communication supports transfer rates of up to 9600 bps.
2. Library Servo.h - used to control servo motors.
3. Library TinyGPS++.h - designed to parse NMEA strings sent by the GPS module and provide insightful GPS information on the serial monitor.
4. Library ESP8266WiFi.h - intended for configuring and operating the ESP8266 module in station and/or soft access point mode.

5. Library RemoteXY.h - used to facilitate communication between the ESP8266 module and the Remote XY application.
6. Library Wire.h - used for communication with I2C/TWI devices.
7. Library Ticker.h - employed to replace the delay () function.

B. Remote XY

For interfacing the program on smartphones or laptops, the Remote XY application was used. This application is a well-designed "constructor" of interfaces, which allowed the development of dashboards for projects where widgets could be arranged to remotely control hardware, display sensor data, store and visualize data, and perform many other interesting tasks. In the Remote XY application, three widgets were created to input values such as: wind direction, desired coordinates point with latitude and longitude, and respectively, to display values such as the ship's coordinates point, speed, heading, number of satellites connected to the GPS, and the direction the vessel needs to navigate to reach the entered coordinates point. This connects via the Wi-Fi module to the drone and the Arduino board.

C. The Operating Algorithm

The Arduino Uno microcontroller will receive input data such as wind direction and real-time ship's coordinates (latitude and longitude), transmitted by the operator through the Remote XY application using the Wi-Fi module. Based on the provided data, Arduino will control servo motors, which in turn will adjust the sail and rudder to an optimal position for autonomous vehicle movement according to the wind direction. The ultrasonic sensor will emit and receive signals. When an obstacle appears in front of the vessel, it measures the distance to it and returns the value. If the returned distance is equal to the initially set 50 cm distance, the drone will actuate the servo motors and change its course.

Fig. 5. The Remote XY application interface.

The ship's heading is determined using the MinIMU board as well as the GPS module. Additionally, if there is no obstacle ahead, the boat will continue moving until it reaches the latitude and longitude values set at the beginning. Once the vessel reaches the operator's desired coordinates, Arduino will activate the servo motors to turn the vessel back to the launch

point. Simultaneously, the GPS module receives data about longitude, latitude, speed, and the number of connected satellites. It transmits this data through the Wi-Fi module to the Remote XY application (Figure 5) for display of the obtained values.

D. The Coding Algorithm

For programming and commanding the Arduino UNO board, the programming facilities of C and C++ were used, and the lines of code were written in the Arduino IDE development environment.

Fig. 6. Library selection.

Fig. 7. Remote XY configuration.

Fig. 8. Variable definition.

Some suggestive elements showing how the writing of program lines was carried out can be seen in Figures 6-8. The selection of libraries and communication module with Remote XY, selection of the GPS library, and settings for connecting with Remote XY are illustrated in Figure 6. The configuration of Remote XY is suggestively illustrated in Figure 7. The definition of variables (input and output) in the Remote XY application is shown in Figure 8.

IV. DISCUSSIONS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

The current paper proposes the development of a system for automating a sail-powered autonomous vessel in response to at least two imperative needs:

- Safety and security of civil and military navigation in the Black Sea area, in the face of increased dangers in the context of political tensions and armed conflicts. Solutions are needed for surveillance of maritime space, for the identification, monitoring and destruction of hazards. These solutions must be almost immediate (which means very short manufacturing times, permanent component availability, and the lowest possible costs) without affecting performance, efficiency and reliability.
- The increased need to integrate European and global policies to drastically reduce pollution. Renewable energy principles involve the diversification of energy sources (solar energy, wind energy, ocean and hydroelectric energy, biomass, and biofuels) to ensure energy security and efficiency.

The prototype, whose final shape is shown in Figure 9, is an automated, autonomous, very small boat, powered by sails and equipped with mini solar panels.

Fig. 9. Automated sail-propelled research boat in the test basin.

Note: in Figures 4, 9, automation equipment is displayed exclusively for the reader to observe. During ship's operation, however, the automation equipment is naturally placed inside the ship's body to protect it from the marine environment.

The preliminary testing activities (carried out in the test tank) of the prototype of the sail-powered ship demonstrated the feasibility and functionality of the proposed solution. Future research efforts will focus on improving the nautical

qualities of the ship drone (mainly its stability and functionality in somewhat harsher hydrometeorological conditions). Also, it must be noted that Figure 3 illustrates how the connections between the microcontroller used in the system and each required component were established, highlighting how each element was interfaced with the microcontroller. The software and applications used enabled the automation of the sail and rudder to create a propulsion system powered solely by wind power and electrically charged by solar energy. In the future, this constructive approach could be improved by integrating an on-board anemometer, which would allow the ship to autonomously acquire wind direction and speed to achieve optimal travel speed. Furthermore, the ultrasonic sensor for obstacle avoidance could be replaced with a deliberate ship avoidance system at a higher level to re-plan the waypoint route for maintaining a safe distance from larger vessels.

Employing Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USVs) for maritime research, search and rescue operations, and surveillance activities offers economic and safety benefits. Using USVs in lieu of manned vessels in hazardous areas safeguards crew's well-being, the ships integrity and security of the area. Consequently, on a small scale, the automation of a sail-powered ship offers a viable solution for researching, surveilling, and protecting areas of high potential danger.

V. CONCLUSIONS

An automated, sail-propelled, energy-autonomous vessel with efficient recharging capabilities, benefiting from a favorable cost-quality balance, relatively easy and quick to assemble with equipment available on the free market, could serve commercial and military fleets to meet the needs of surveillance of maritime space and navigation routes. Regarding the original contributions, prospects for further development and limitations of achievement presented in this paper, three perspectives can be approached:

- Economic perspective: the proposed unmanned vessel model is made exclusively with components existing on the free market, the price of the prototype being 750 euros (the cost of the model vessel is 500 euros), the assembly time of the boat was about 24 hr, the boat is completely energy independent, the propulsion being provided by wind, and the electricity supply of the electronic components is made with the help of mini solar panels (photovoltaic cells). When solar radiation is not present, the boat uses electricity stored in batteries. The small dimensions of the prototype, recommend it only for use on calm water, no more than grade one, the ship being capable of a cruising speed of 2 knots. As far as autonomy is concerned, it can be practically unlimited, conditioning being dictated only by the presence of solar radiation;
- Civil perspective of use: this autonomous sail-propelled vehicle can be operated in coastal and port areas for various surveillance, monitoring, control, data collection and sampling activities. The vessel is able to be used for search and rescue operations and for anti-terrorist monitoring operations. Obviously, the endowment with equipment must be correlated with the assumed mission, the

interchangeability of components being one of the elements of originality of the boat (easy changes in programmable memory; ease of adjusting electrical connections within the control system);

- Military perspective of use: the unmanned vessel developed and presented in this paper represents an innovative solution, being able to perform patrol, surveillance and intelligence gathering missions in the vicinity of military ships on mission, to which it can provide real-time data on possible dangers. The sailing propulsion gives it an almost zero acoustic fingerprint (the only source of noise being the waves hitting the drone body), which makes it invisible to hydro location sensors (hydroacoustic buoys, sonars, etc.). Its small size also ensures its invisibility to navigation or research radars, the vessel being able to provide information from a certain monitoring sector without disclosing its position.

The research presented in this paper represents only the first phase of a project funded by the Romanian Navy which is interested, in these times characterized by particularly accelerated risk dynamics, to identify its own possibility of building a type of low-cost surface drone intended for surveillance of marine space, identification, and destruction of navigational hazards.

The proposed ship drone is a demonstrator for a large-scale sailing yacht with autonomous surveillance capabilities in Romanian's territorial waters from Black Sea (which will be built in the second phase of the project). It was compulsory to develop this initial stage, which involved making a small-scale model, on the one hand to test the validity of the proposed solutions and, on the other hand, to reduce costs.

It should be noted that, according to the best of our knowledge, there are no ready-to-purchase autonomous sailing drones. We used a remote-controlled small sailing boat which was transformed in an autonomous vessel. In this paper, the readers can study the proposed method of hardware upgrade and software development for autonomous transformation.

The main tactical advantage of a sailing yacht drone is that it can easily be confused with a civilian yacht. Also, because it is constructed from non-metal materials it has a low radar reflection and it is hard to be detected and monitored by other states. But, its most innovative aspect might be that it can survey very dangerous waters, like mine fields or mine drifting waters, without exposing navy combat ships or personnel to risk. In the future, the autonomous system will be installed on second-hand low-cost full scale sailing yachts. In conclusion, the purpose of the current research was to test the opportunity and identify the possibilities of modifying a classic sailing yacht and transforming it into an autonomous surveillance one.

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An Approach for the Evaluation of a Measurement System: A Study on the Use of Machine Learning and Predictions

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ABSTRACT

Quality control during the manufacturing process is an important factor in delivering products in electronics according to planned characteristics and properties. It concerns the capability of the chosen measurement system to perform precise and reliable measurement trials, which is evaluated mainly through the utilization of measurement system analysis. In order to reduce time effort and to partially automate these operations, a methodology for the prediction of a part of the dataset through applying the Neural Net algorithm is proposed in this paper in two scenarios: (1) when two metrology experts are involved in the measurement in three trials and the data of a third specialist are predicted and (2) when three metrology specialists collect data in two trials and the data of the third trial are predicted. The developed predictive models in these two scenarios are assessed and they are characterized by high accuracy. Gage repeatability and reproducibility analysis are used to evaluate the measurement systems based on original and partially artificial datasets as the comparative results outline the suitability of the proposed approach, due to the proximity of the obtained values.

Keywords-machine learning; semi artificial dataset; measurement system; measurements system analysis; Gage repeatability and reproducibility; electronics manufacturing; automation

I. INTRODUCTION

In electronics, quality control during the manufacturing of a certain product is of particular importance. It guarantees the delivery by the manufacturer and the use by the user of a product possessing the previously announced characteristics and properties [1, 2]. In this way, low-quality production is prevented from reaching the consumer and additional costs for the manufacturer are avoided. Different tools for improving manufacturing systems are discussed in [3], showing existing practices and some challenging issues. Quality control is related to the choice of a system for measuring product-typical parameters, which must meet certain criteria, such as precision, accuracy, stability, and reliability. Thus, measurement systems must be evaluated as this is conducted mainly through the

utilization of statistical methods. The most popular statistical approach for the evaluation of a measurement system is Measurement System Analysis (MSA), whose purpose is to identify the dependence between variances at measurement and the variability of the measurement process as a whole. This statistical method is evolving to satisfy different requirements of the measuring process or the measured product, due to the development and integration of a wide variety of technologies in the manufacturing process. Authors in [4] propose MSA as a one-side tolerance method. Authors in [5] present a new procedure regarding the MSA methodology for real time evaluation and for identifying MSA suitability for quality control in a manufacturing process, allowing continuous monitoring and adjustment of the measurement system and in combination with Statistical Process Control (SPC), it is

possible to achieve high-quality manufacturing. Authors in [6] discuss a holistic approach for applying the Gauge study of high-density data collected through the usage of a 3D laser scanner (so called point cloud). The investigation reveals an approach for analyzing the repeatability and reproducibility of point clouds and for uncertainty quantification of these points.

Well-known statistical methods for the evaluation of measurement systems are widespread in practice and discussed among the scientific community, which shows their effectiveness in producing quality products. We are looking for an approach that could reduce the time and effort of metrology experts. For this purpose, the current investigation is focused on whether one semi artificially generated measurement system possesses identical or similar characteristics with the original one. Thus, the aim of the current paper is to present a methodology for evaluating measurement systems with partially artificial datasets. Statistical technique Gage Repeatability and Reproducibility (GR&R) is applied for studying the measurement system and machine learning is used for predicting part of data in the measured datasets.

II. THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. Description

The proposed methodology is depicted in Figure 1. It consists of the following steps:

1. Measurement data are collected in original datasets by two or three operators A, B, and/or C (metrology specialists).
2. The original datasets for three different dimensions of the product are processed in Minitab software through applying GR&R analysis and the ANOVA method.
3. The obtained results after GR&R analysis are used for the evaluation of the measurement system.
4. Machine learning algorithm Neural Net in Rapid Miner Studio is applied to the original datasets to make predictions regarding measurement data of operator C or regarding the third trial of the operators.
5. Datasets with predictions are the base for GR&R analysis.
6. The achieved results after GR&R analysis of the partially artificial measurement system are evaluated.
7. The two measurement systems are compared based on the original and on partially artificial datasets.

The methodology is developed for two scenarios depending on which data EW artificially created by the predictions.

The first scenario is related to the case when the collected data are measured by operators A and B in three trials. The data of the third operator C in three trials are artificially generated through predictions based on the historical data of operators A and B. The originally collected data are colored in blue color in Figure 2 and the artificially predicted data in green. Each trial includes ten different measurements. In the second scenario, data are gathered from three operators A, B, and C in two trials and the data of the third trial of operators A, B, and C are artificially generated.

Fig. 1. The proposed methodology.

Fig. 2. The two considered scenarios in the proposed methodology.

B. Controlled Object and Measurement Machine

The controlled object is the thermo-printing mechanism SS205 V.4 used for heavy vehicle tachographs for the automotive industry. The measured dimensions of SS205 V.4 used in this study are presented in Figure 3 and they are: first dimension: 25.5 mm, second dimension: 22.9 mm, and third dimension: 67.7 mm with acceptable variance of ± 0.2 mm. The measurement system comprises 3D coordinate measuring machine Hexagon DEA Global Silver Performance 07.07.05 which runs PC-DMIS software version 2018 R1.

Fig. 3. Measured dimensions of the thermo-printing mechanism SS205 V.4

C. Data Collection

The data used for the analysis are 10 samples of the final product SS205-V4 concerning 3 different dimensional parameters, measured by 2 metrology specialists 3 times. Some of the measured data are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. MEASURED DATA BY TWO METROLOGY SPECIALISTS IN THREE TRIALS

Part	Trial	Operator	25.5 mm First dataset	22.9 mm Second dataset	67.7 mm Third dataset
1	1	A	25.378	22.890	67.672
1	2	A	25.379	22.875	67.673
1	3	A	25.378	22.879	67.682
2	1	A	25.386	22.891	67.663
2	2	A	25.387	22.883	67.660
...

The data used in the second scenario for the analysis concern 10 samples of the final product SS205-V4 taking into account 3 different dimensional parameters, measured by 3 metrology specialists in 2 trials. Some of the measured data are shown in Table II.

TABLE II. MEASURED DATA BY THREE OPERATORS IN TWO TRIALS

Part	Trial	Operator	25.5 mm First dataset	22.9 mm Second dataset	67.7 mm Third dataset
1	1	A	25.378	22.890	67.672
1	2	A	25.379	22.875	67.673
2	1	A	25.386	22.891	67.663
2	2	A	25.387	22.883	67.660
3	1	A	25.355	22.879	67.669
...

D. Applying Machine Learning

1) First Scenario

When evaluating a measurement system, measurements made by more than two experts are usually required. We have data from two metrology specialists and therefore the data from the third expert are artificially created by applying the machine learning algorithm Neural Net. Training and result obtaining are performed in RapidMiner Studio [7]. The prediction accuracy is very high as it is evaluated through standard machine learning metrics: Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Absolute Error (AE), Relative Error (RE), and Root Relative Squared Error (RRSE). The results can be seen in Table III.

TABLE III. PREDICTION ACCURACY OF MACHINE LEARNING MODELS BASED ON DATA OF TWO OPERATORS IN THREE TRIALS

Accuracy parameter	Prediction for 1st dimension	Prediction for 2nd dimension	Prediction for 3rd dimension
RMSE	0.0027	0.0043	0.0285
AE	0.0023	0.0035	0.0205
RE	0.0001	0.0002	0.0003
RRSE	0.5522	0.4319	0.8448

2) Second Scenario

The data for the third trial of the three operators are predicted through the Neural Net algorithm. The prediction accuracy is also very high.

III. EXPERIMENTATION AND RESULTS

A. Evaluation of the Measurement System in the First Scenario

The measured data are collected by operators A and B in 3 trials for each operator. The data for the third operator C are artificially generated. The measurement system evaluation is done through the usage of Minitab, applying GR&R analysis and the ANOVA method and the results regarding the first (25.5 mm), second (22.9 mm) and third (67.7 mm) dimensions are presented respectively in Figures 4, 5, and 6, respectively. Variance components and Gage evaluation metrics for the first dimension of the product are shown in Tables IV and V. The main used indicators are the %Contribution of variance components and %Study variations. %Contribution is applied to assess the variations regarding the measurement error of each source and %Study variations present a comparison regarding the variations of the measurement system and total variations.

For the first dimension (25.5 mm), the biggest variance is received for repeatability 0.68% as there is no variance for reproducibility and operator. Considering the measurements of the second (22.9 mm) and third (67.7 mm) dimensions, all sources present variations as the values are bigger for the second dimension (second dimension: repeatability 10.33%, reproducibility 9.91%, and operator 9.91%. Third dimension: repeatability 1.63%, reproducibility 1.84%, and operator 0.08%).

Repeatability concerns the variability of measurement when the same operator measures a given part several times. Repeatability is very small for the first dimension (0.68%), small for the third dimension (1.63%), and bigger for the second dimension (10.33%).

Fig. 4. Evaluation of the measurement system for the first dimension.

Fig. 5. Evaluation of the measurement system for the second dimension.

Fig. 6. Evaluation of the measurement system for the third dimension.

Reproducibility introduces measurement variability when several operators measure a given part. The value of reproducibility is zero for the first dimension, small for the third dimension (1.84%), and bigger for the second dimension (9.91%). When different parts have to be measured and there is variability in the measurements, then the variation source is part-to-part. The practice shows that the biggest variance in a measurement system introduced by the part-to-part component for different dimensions are: first dimension 99.32%, second dimension 79.76%, and third dimension 96.53%.

TABLE IV. VARIANCE COMPONENTS METRICS FOR THE FIRST DIMENSION 25.5 mm

Variance Components		
Source	VarComp	% Contribution (of VarComp)
Total Gage R&R	0.0000009	0.68
Repeatability	0.0000009	0.68
Reproducibility	0.0000000	0.00
Operator	0.0000000	0.00
Part-to-part	0.0001335	99.32
Total variation	0.0001345	100.00

TABLE V. GAGE EVALUATION FOR THE FIRST DIMENSION 25.5 mm

Gage Evaluation				
Source	StdDev (SD)	Study Var (6xSD)	%Study Var (%SV)	%Tolerance (SV/Toler)
Total Gage R&R	0.0009595	0.0057570	8.27	1.44
Repeatability	0.0009595	0.0057570	8.27	1.44
Reproducibility	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.00	0.00
Operator	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.00	0.00
Part-to-part	0.0115557	0.0693339	99.66	17.33
Total variation	0.0115954	0.0695725	100	17.33

The R chart indicates the operator consistency during measurements. It is seen that operator A is characterized with inconsistency at measurement of the first, second, and third dimension, because there are points above the Upper Control Limit (UCL) line and operators B and C measure parts consistently. The Xbar chart shows the part-to-part variations and concerns the repeatability component as the lines of average values and UCL and LCL (Low Control Limit) are drawn. Measurement by part chart presents variations when several parts are measured as the measurement system is better when the dots are closer for each part. The worst situation here is for the second dimension. Figure 7 presents the metrics of the first dimension.

Fig. 7. Measurement by part, measurement by operator, and part*operator interaction charts for the first dimension (25.5 mm).

The chart measurement by operator in the ideal case must be a horizontal straight line that outlines similarity at the measurement of operators. The measurement of the second dimension by the three operators is characterized with bigger difference by operators in comparison to the measurements of the first and third dimensions. The chart part*operator interaction chart presents the average measurement for the operators A, B, and C and whether they measure the parts in a similar way. Similarity is almost achieved for the measurement of the first and third dimension, while in the second dimension there is a tolerance at part measurement. It can be said that the operators A, B, and C make the measurements in the same way, whereas for the second dimension, bias is added.

The total GR&R at variance component is 0.68% for the first dimension, 20.24% for the second, and 3.47% for the third dimension. The total GR&R evaluation regarding the percentage variation is 8.27% for the first dimension, 44.98% for the second, and 18.64% for the third dimension.

The acceptance of the measurement system is evaluated by taking into account the AIAG (Automotive Industry Activation Group) standards, which mention that the percentage contribution of variance components must be less than 1% for acceptance. If $1\% < \%Contribution < 9\%$, the measurement system is acceptable, but in the context of different factors and conditions. When $\%Contribution > 9\%$, the measurement system is unacceptable. So, from the results, it is seen that the measurement of the first dimension is acceptable, the third dimension is acceptable under conditions, and the second dimension measurement is unacceptable. Percentage study variations ($\%StudyVar$) at Gage evaluation must be less than 10% for the measurement system to be acceptable, for acceptance under conditions the condition is $10\% < \%StudyVar < 30\%$, and the system is unacceptable at $\%StudyVar > 30\%$. In this way, the measurement system is acceptable for the first dimension, acceptable under conditions for the third dimension, and unacceptable for the second dimension (Table VI).

TABLE VI. MEASUREMENT EVALUATION OF THE THREE DIMENSIONS

Dimension	%Contribution	Evaluation	%StudyVar	Evaluation	Overall evaluation
First	0.68%	Acceptable	8.27%	Acceptable under conditions	Acceptable under conditions
Second	20.24%	Unacceptable	44.98%	Unacceptable	Unacceptable
Third	3.47%	Acceptable under conditions	18.64%	Acceptable under conditions	Acceptable under conditions

A comparison between the data taken by two operators and these by three operators is also made (the data of the third operator are artificially generated). The comparison is presented in Table VII. There is a slight decrease in $\%Contribution$ and $\%Study$ Variations values for three operator data in comparison to two operator data, but at both two and

three operator datasets, the first and third dimensions are within the acceptable borders under conditions and the second dimension significantly exceeds the acceptable values and needs to be improved. It is seen from Table VII that the results for $\%Contribution$ at component variance and $\%Study$ variations at Gage evaluation for two and three operators are very similar and they could be used for decision making with similar success.

TABLE VII. COMPARISON THE RESULTS AT TWO AND THREE OPERATORS

Dimension	GR&R analysis	3 operators	2 operators
First	%Contribution of variance components	0.68%	1.03%
	%Study variation of Gage evaluation	8.27%	10.14%
Second	%Contribution of variance components	20.24%	29.46%
	%Study variation of Gage evaluation	44.98%	54.28%
Third	%Contribution of variance components	3.47%	6.18%
	%Study variation of Gage evaluation	18.64%	24.87%

B. Evaluation of the Measurement System in the Second Scenario

Data were collected by operators A, B, and C in two trials. The third trial for each operator was artificially generated. In this scenario, all components give their contribution to the variances in measurement as repeatability and reproducibility are smaller for the first and third dimension, i.e. 0.50% and 0.18% for the first dimension and 0.70% and 4.48% for the third dimension. For the second dimension, the values are bigger: 6% and 18.42%. According to Total GR&R at variance components ($\%Contribution$ of VarComp), the measurement system is acceptable for the first dimension $0.68\% < 1\%$, unacceptable for the second dimension $24.42\% > 9\%$, and acceptable under conditions for the third dimension $5.18\% < 9\%$. Considering the total GR&R at Gage evaluation ($\%StudyVar$), the measurement system is acceptable for the first dimension $8.24\% < 10\%$, unacceptable for the second dimension $49.41\% > 30\%$, and acceptable under conditions for the third dimension $22.75\% < 30\%$.

The R chart shows that there is inconsistency in the measurements of operator A at the second dimension and of operator B at the third dimension. The chart measure by part presents variations at measurement of the ten parts, which are bigger for the second dimension. Again, the difference at the measurement of the second dimension by operators A, B, and C is characterized with no straight line on the chart measurement by operator. Different operators measure this dimension in different ways.

From the chart part*operator interaction, it is seen that the average measurement for the operators A, B, and C for the first and third dimension, similarity is almost achieved, while in the second dimension there is a variance at part measurement.

A comparison regarding the measurement of the first, second, and third dimensions in the second scenario is presented in Table VIII. Considering the AIAG standard, it can be said that the measurement system is acceptable, acceptable under conditions, and unacceptable for the first, third, and second dimension, respectively.

TABLE VIII. MEASUREMENT COMPARISON

Dimension	%Contribution	Evaluation	%Study Var	Evaluation	Overall evaluation
First	0.68%	Acceptable	8.24%	Acceptable	Acceptable
Second	24.42%	Unacceptable	49.41%	Unacceptable	Unacceptable
Third	5.18%	Acceptable under conditions	22.75%	Acceptable under conditions	Acceptable under conditions

The results after GR&R analysis applied on the datasets with 2 and 3 trials (the third trial is predicted) of 3 operators are compared in Table IX. Slightly increased values are observed in the case of 2 trials. The similarity in results outlines the suitability for usage of the artificially generated datasets.

TABLE IX. RESULT COMPARISON FOR THREE OPERATORS AND TWO AND THREE TRIALS

Dimension	GR&R analysis	3 trials	2 trials
First	%Contribution of variance components	0.68%	0.96%
	%Study variation of Gage evaluation	8.24%	9.78%
Second	%Contribution of variance components	24.42%	26.97%
	%Study variation of Gage evaluation	49.41%	51.93%
Third	%Contribution of variance components	5.18%	5.40%
	%Study variation of Gage evaluation	22.75%	23.23%

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a new methodology for the evaluation of measurement systems is presented, which is based on partially generated artificial data. Two scenarios are considered: (1) when data by two operators are collected in three trials and the data of the third operator are predicted and (2) when data by three operators are gathered in two trials and the third trial of each operator is predicted. It is proven that this methodology is applicable and reduces time and effort for measurement performed by metrology experts who have to conduct many repetitive operations with high attention. Also, such an approach allows the analysis and evaluation of measurement systems to be partially automated.

The created machine learning models through usage of Neural Net algorithm are characterized with high accuracy. The comparison between measurement systems that utilize original data and partially artificial data is done and the results outline the suitability of this approach regarding missing data and facilitating the metrology specialists in measurement systems analysis.

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Ontology Development for Knowledge Representation of a Metrology Lab

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ABSTRACT

Digital transformation in metrology is impacting the industry, where accurate and fair data are essential to take enterprises to the next level in the digital era. The amount and complexity of information are growing exponentially, and expert knowledge becomes imperative for users to perform measurement tasks and decision-making. This study presents the development of a modular metrological inspection ontology for a metrology laboratory based on the reuse of ontologies related to sensors and units of measurement. Such an ontology considers information about operators and customers (name, telephone number, email) and the linkage to service orders, pieces (length, height, width), measurement strategies (expert notes about measurement procedures and paths), and measuring machines (measuring scope, uncertainty, sensor probe). The proposed solution delivers a digitalized catalog that allows the user to filter records according to the geometrical characteristics of the pieces and recover notes related to measurement procedures and paths for similar cases. The purpose is to promote knowledge sharing and narrow the gap to achieve digital transformation toward Metrology 4.0 in laboratories prepared to offer metrological support.

Keywords-ontology; metrology; measurement strategy; CMM

I. INTRODUCTION

Metrology, standardization, accreditation, and conformity assessment are considered pillars of the quality infrastructure and have experienced significant changes in the digital era [1]. Metrology, as the science of measurement, is recognized as a core element in measurement processes related to international trade and exchange and deals with challenges and opportunities to achieve confidence and accuracy in the data [2]. In this regard, dimensional metrology refers to measuring geometric properties (i.e. length, area, and roundness) [3], supported by Coordinate Measuring Machines (CMMs) using geometrical and dimensional data obtained from Computer-Aided Design (CAD) models, commonly found in inspection planning systems [4-5]. A CMM measures the geometry of physical objects using discrete points distributed on the object's surface

to assess product quality and control quality in manufacturing [6]. The digitalization of metrology is changing the way of working in industry by using new measurement techniques and fostering the adoption of information technologies to increase the efficiency of processes [7-8]. It enables adding information, such as product specification, with feedback during manufacturing workpieces [9-10], promoting the use of distributed measuring instruments and sensor networks from a holistic perspective [11]. Therefore, the digitalization of a measurement system includes four phases: definition of dimensional and geometric specifications, development of a measurement plan, measurement execution, and results [12]. Following this path, international initiatives such as the Inter-American Metrology project have task forces working on metrology for digital transformation toward Metrology 4.0 [13]. In this sense, ontologies facilitate the organization of

knowledge and metadata from heterogeneous sources in a semantically significant, reusable, and interoperable way [14], supported by Semantic Web Technologies (SWT) [15]. Metadata and semantic relationships in a particular domain enable machines to infer new facts about the data and have a human-like understanding and reasoning [16-17]. To model and represent facts in the form of statements (subject, predicate, and object) and retrieve information, SWT employs standards and technologies such as the Resource Description Framework (RDF) [18], RDF Schema (RDFS) [19], Web ontology language (OWL) [20], and SPARQL protocol and RDF query language (SPARQL) [21-22]. Finally, logic reasoners (e.g. Pellet or Fact) infer logical consequences from ontologies through asserted facts or axioms [23].

Domain ontologies formalize the terms used in a discipline to enable separate systems to exchange information [24]. In the metrological domain, units of measurement are vital or critical in business for sales or purchases, construction of any machine or building, and anywhere a measure is needed [25]. The ontological modeling of metrological knowledge has been studied since the linked data emerged [26]. Examples are the Measurement Units Ontology (MUO) and the ontology of units of measure (OM2). Besides, the Quantities, Units, Dimensions, and Data Types (QUDT) ontology represents the vocabulary of unit standards to facilitate conversions and dimensional analysis [27]. Sensors used by machines or industry processes measure the performance or provide data for diagnoses. The W3C Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) group described an ontology for sensors in terms of capabilities, measurement processes, observations, and deployments [28-29]. In [30], it was used to contextualize measurements of metrological earth observations. In [31], the SSN ontology was extended for energy management to provide value-added services, and in [32], meteorological datasets were described.

Regarding the consumer knowledge domain, an ontology for designing products and services based on users was proposed in [33]. In [34], a semantic knowledge management system was developed to add value to customer experience. In [35], a decision support system was built using reasoning tools to enable manufacturing process selection and customer requirements. In [36], information on client loyalty, experience, and behavior was addressed, and in [37] an ontology was extended to support clients and track changes for social service provisioning. The motivation for the present work was twofold: the first was to develop a domain ontology in metrological inspection as a digitalized catalog for the Metrological Assistance Center of the University of Sonora as a support and decision-making tool for Metrology 4.0. The second was to count with a training tool for students and metrologists in formation interested in metrological aspects (e.g. the courses of measurement foundations and advanced metrology), providing a way to access expert knowledge.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Metrological Assistance Center of the University provides measurement and calibration services for different magnitudes to local manufacturing companies. One of the laboratories with the highest demand is coordinate metrology, which comprises the measured workpieces using CMM

equipment, measurement reports, and data for calibration certificates. As shown in Figure 1, the laboratory has a FARO QUANTUM MAX articulated coordinate measuring arm with a range of 2 m and a precision of 0.003 mm, and a CMM Mitutoyo CRYSTA-PLUS 504 with a measuring scope: X-axis = 500 mm, Y-axis = 400 mm and Z-axis = 400 mm, with a resolution of 0.0005 mm (5 μ m). It has a RENISHAW MH20i head adjustable on the A axis and rotates up to $\pm 180^\circ$ in the X-Y plane. The B-axis rotates up to 90° in the Z plane.

Fig. 1. Equipment of the metrology lab: articulated arms and CMM unit.

The operative personnel using the equipment invest most of their time analyzing and designing measurement strategies (e.g. measurement order, probe selection) to generate reliable results, and they mostly use tacit knowledge in the metrology tasks, which are difficult to code and transfer. The client receives a measurement report of the workpiece, and a hard copy is filed. However, the knowledge used to perform the measurement tasks is not extracted and saved. This study aims to support the domain expert's knowledge extraction, employing an ontology to preserve it explicitly for the personnel or any interested user, providing measurement strategies (e.g. expert notes about measurement procedures and paths) to reuse these for future customers' needs. The Modular Ontology of Metrological Inspection (MOMI) was implemented using Protege software [38]. For its construction, the design took advantage of known methodologies [39-40]. It was essential to define and identify key concepts related to the workpiece, such as properties and characteristics to be sized (e.g. length, height, width, and metrological features), customer data (e.g. name, phone number, email), and CMM features (e.g. measuring scope, uncertainty). The Competency Questions (CQ) identified requirements, focused on fundamental concepts, and were formulated by experts and users in the metrology domain. A sample is presented as follows:

- CQ1: What is the customer's identification and service order assigned to a piece?
- CQ2: What are the geometric entities of a piece and coordinates?
- CQ3: What are the sensors used, dimensional and geometric tolerances, and tolerance limits of the geometric entity?

- CQ4: What is the piece name, serial number, and piece material?
- CQ5: What are the dimensions of the workpiece (length, width, and height)?
- CQ6: What is the measurement strategy applied?
- CQ7: What is the measurement scope of the CMM?
- CQ8: What is the resolution and uncertainty of the CMM?

In addition to the reused ontologies (SSN and QUDT), the proposed MOMI comprises two main modules: workpiece and customer. Figure 2 presents the workpiece module showing classes and subclasses for the piece data (e.g. name, material, serial number), and Figure 3 describes the faces of the workpiece with a maximum number of six faces, identified as faces A to F. According to the workpiece geometry to measure, each one of these classes could contain some geometric entities (lines or circles). As for the customer module, Figure 4 includes the subclasses that represent the contact data of the company representative, such as name, address, and email. Figure 5 illustrates an example of a workpiece to be measured with a pattern of four circles with a diameter of 12.500 ± 0.300 mm, and the center of the piece has a circle with a diameter of 22.200 ± 0.100 mm. Figure 6 shows an instance of MOMI with data on the Figure 5 workpiece and its relationships with the subclasses of customer, face, and geometric entities.

Fig. 2. The module of the workpiece: piece general data.

Fig. 3. The module of the workpiece: piece faces information.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MOMI was verified with the Pellet reasoning plugin, returning a consistent ontology model and SPARQL to answer the CQs. Figure 7 shows the results for CQ1 to CQ3, where the columns service order, customer, and piece link the customer with the workpiece to be measured. The column *observGeom* refers to the observed geometric entities. For instance, Piece_P001 has five circle entities. The following columns

show the diameter, sensor, 3D coordinates, dimension tolerances (positive and negative values), and geometric tolerance. Thus, the second row indicates a diameter of 22.189 mm and a geometric tolerance (*geoTolValue*) of 0.2 mm.

Fig. 4. The module of customer data.

Fig. 5. Technical drawing of a workpiece to be measured.

Fig. 6. A partial view of the classes of the modular ontology of metrological inspection.

Figure 8 illustrates a complex piece to measure with the CMM, labeled with points A and B for context in the implemented measurement strategy. Figure 9 shows the SPARQL query to answer CQ4 to CQ6 based on the data captured from the workpiece. The columns show the values for the piece, piece name, serial number, material, length, width, height, and strategy. The bottom of Figure 9 partially describes the measurement strategy. Such a strategy comprises the steps to capture the measurement plan of the piece and facilitate the

future measurement process of similar workpieces. The next step is to populate the ontology with historical records of the Metrological Assistance Center of the University from the last couple of years and create electronic records with relevant information, specifically to recover the different measurement strategies.

The digital transformation applied in the metrology field fosters the adoption of information technologies [41]. It supports the integration of sensor measurements to assess product and control quality [42], along with path planning for automated inspections [43]. In this sense, ontologies enable the knowledge representation of industries and measuring processes in quality inspection and control [44]. In [45], an intelligent inspection model of prismatic parts was presented to support the definition of metrological sequences and the planning of measuring probe paths. In addition, in [46], a framework with the onto-process ontology was proposed to automate inspection planning strategies that convert implicit knowledge into explicit knowledge to implement a knowledge-based application. Furthermore, in [47] a digital twin framework was introduced to exhibit components and data flow for the assembly part process. This study considered assembly constraint relationships and filter key assembly features for processing and inspection. Likewise, in [48], the measurement process and information on uncertainty were addressed using logic reasoners, enabling semantic modeling, automated analysis, and discovery of traceable measurement data. In this vein, in [49], an inspection planning system was created to optimize the measurement path for metrology using artificial intelligence techniques (e.g. ontology, genetic algorithms, and ant colony optimization). Table I shows the employed criteria for identifying similarities between the above studies and the proposed one.

The main criteria considered in this study were modeling, methodology, geometric dimensioning and tolerances, and users. OWL was adopted to create the ontology in most works and UML to support the modeling. Additionally, the preferred methodology was ontology development 101.

TABLE I. COMPARISON BETWEEN MOMI AND RELATED WORKS

Criteria	[45]	[46]	[47]	[48]	[49]	MOMI
Modeling	owl	uml	owl; uml	owl; uml	owl	owl
Methodology	o1	oo	o1	o1; oo	o1	o1; mom
Reuse ontology	yes	yes	no	no	yes	yes
Evaluation [50]	-	-	-	ir; q	ir	q
Geometric dimensioning and tolerances	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Users	-	op	op	op	-	cu; op
Implementation	no	c++	sql; -	no	m; p; s	no

Modeling: owl=web ontology language, uml=unified modeling language. **Methodology:** mom=modular ontological modeling, o1=ontology development 101, oo=object oriented. **Evaluation:** q=competency questions, ir= inference rules. **Users:** cu=customer, op=operator. **Implementation:** m=MatLab, p=ptc, s=step-nc, sql=MySql, "-"=not mentioned.

Regarding the reuse of ontologies, most studies used or extended a previous ontology, and a couple built their ontology from scratch [47-48]. On the contrary, this study reused SSN and QUOT ontologies. Most of the reviewed research works, including MOMI, applied the ontologies in the context of CMM equipment, except in [45], which also considered different kinds of machining equipment and MOMI to address articulated arms.

The knowledge of the current state of the development of ontologies related to computer science and engineering areas in

Fig. 7. Customer service orders and measured piece data.

Fig. 8. A seal rotor tip workpiece measured by a CMM.

Fig. 9. A query to recover information on the seal rotor tip with the measurement strategy employed.

México motivated us to conduct a study to identify the characteristics of the creation, extension, and use of ontologies. This ongoing research reveals that even though the fields of manufacturing and industry are addressed, research studies on ontologies related to the metrology inspection of workpieces were not found in the analyzed time frame (1999-2022).

MOMI is based on well-known concepts related to sensors, quantities, and units from previous ontologies employed in the metrological area. Furthermore, the ontology classes related to geometrical dimensioning and tolerances, such as location tolerance (Q109523965), orientation tolerance (Q109483186), and runout tolerance (Q109523972) were developed and registered in Wikidata [51]. The proposed work considered information about operators and customers, linking them to service orders, pieces, and measurement strategies by providing a digitalized catalog and a training tool to promote knowledge sharing and narrow the gap to achieve digital transformation toward Metrology 4.0.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study proposes a modular metrological inspection ontology for a metrology laboratory to provide access to expert knowledge in the measurement field. It preserves such knowledge explicitly for the operative personnel or any interested user by filtering records according to the geometrical characteristics of pieces and recovering notes related to measurement procedures and paths for similar cases (e.g. the measured seal rotor tip workpiece). The ontology can serve as a digitalized catalog for measured workpieces, reports, and data for calibration certificates. In the same vein, the proposal's strength is based on the reuse of well-known ontologies (SSN and QUDT) to model concepts of the metrological field and the linkage of the information about operators and customers concerning service orders, measured pieces, and measurement strategies to support the digital transformation toward Metrology 4.0. Future work directions would embrace the development of a system that incorporates the modular inspection ontology to provide adaptive and personalized strategies and facilitate the measurement of workpieces.

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Improving the Effectiveness of E-learning Videos by leveraging Eye-gaze Data

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ABSTRACT

Recent advances in technology strengthen remote and lifelong learning by integrating e-videos into teaching-learning pedagogy. Therefore, educational content developers are tasked with creating engaging and qualitative e-content. The shift in paradigm from offline to online teaching brings forth several issues regarding the quality of online learning materials and the missing dynamic interaction between instructors and learners. Leveraging contemporary artificial intelligence techniques to provide insights into methods for developing quality e-content is the need of the hour. This study showed that the pattern and duration of the eye gaze of the learner on the text, image, or instructor in the video reveal valuable insights, not only regarding the comprehension of the learner but also giving suggestions to improve video lectures. The results show that learners perform better when they spend more time looking at the instructor compared to the image and text on a frame. Therefore, just like classroom teaching, the presence of the instructor in the video is vital, as looking directly at the instructor while they are delivering the lecture encourages comprehension. Furthermore, by applying classification techniques to learner eye gaze data, it was possible to predict with 97% confidence whether the learner would answer the post-quiz correctly or not.

Keywords-e-learning; eye gaze data; prediction; classification; machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Education policies around the world place special emphasis on online education to improve teaching and evaluation pedagogies. They envision that technology will play a pivotal role in the improvement of the teaching-learning process, boosting educational access, and integrating e-content into teaching-learning practices [1]. The occurrence of the global pandemic and other crises has demonstrated the necessity for online models to provide education whenever in-person models of education are disrupted [1-2]. E-learning not only aids in information retention but can be adaptive by allowing learners to go through the content using a personalized pedagogical strategy [3]. The transition from offline classroom learning to an online mode of education needs to resolve issues concerning the quality of online learning material, missing dynamic communication between speaker and learners, on-spot learners' query resolution, etc. Thus, the importance of carefully crafted quality e-content that engages the learner and improves comprehension cannot be emphasized enough. The missing

interaction between teacher and learner in online video is the main hurdle in the adoption of online learning. Therefore, online education requires engaging and interactive videos to capture the learner's attention [4].

A. Background

Recently, many studies attempted to automatically calibrate the attention and comprehension of the learners by tracking their eye movements while watching online videos [5-6]. Eye tracking is a noninvasive technique that provides vital insights for estimating learner attentiveness [7]. In [8], it was shown that the use of eye-tracking methods has increased substantially since 2001, and that it seems to be a revolutionary method for academics to connect teaching-learning outcomes with cognitive processes [8]. Eye-tracking technology has witnessed a revolutionary development in the last decade due to advances in artificial intelligence, portable electronics, and head-mounted eye-tracker devices [9]. Therefore, researchers have access to equipment to capture eye gaze data efficiently.

B. Motivation

Contemporary MOOCs employ various mechanisms, such as keystrokes, intermediate response time, and prompt responses, to capture the learners' attention, but these are ineffective in accessing the learner's comprehension of the topic. Additionally, though the impact of different ways of including instructors in e-learning videos has been explored in the context of enhancing individuals' learning capabilities [10], the observation that eye movements are synchronized across video sections has not been widely explored in the context of education [4]. Researchers have provided empirical evidence that the presence of an instructor in online videos plays a key role in improving learner cognition, as well as in attracting and retaining students [11-14]. Furthermore, instructor expression, enthusiasm, and interaction can significantly increase the quality of online synchronous learning, leading to knowledge gain by students and improved teacher satisfaction [15-17]. Although all of these studies discussed the positive impact of an instructor's presence on the perceptions of the learners, none of them has leveraged eye gaze data to predict learners' knowledge acquired through watching online videos. Motivated by this, this study aimed to predict learners' takeaways after watching e-content and discuss the role of the instructor's presence on the learner's understanding captured through a post-quiz.

C. Objectives

This study aimed to find the correlation between the duration of learners' eye gaze on specific sections of selected e-learning videos and their comprehension of the subject. The frames of the videos were categorized into sections of text, images, and the instructor. It was hypothesized that the amount of time spent gazing at different segments would reveal the learner's comprehension of the content. The eye gaze data collected were used to predict the comprehension of the learner and provide tips to improve the design structure of the video. Intentional learning and incidental learning are known to affect learning motivation [6]. Keeping this in mind, in the experiments conducted, the learners were told in advance about a quiz that would be presented after watching the video. As the goal was to predict how well learners would perform in the post-quiz related to an instructional video given their eye gaze data, intentional learning was used where stakeholders were a priori informed about the post-quiz.

II. METHODS

This section details the method used for predicting the desired learning outcomes based on the eye gaze data collected. Python 3.6.9 was used for coding purposes and executed on an Intel Core i7-6700 CPU @3.40GHz with 16GB RAM.

A. Experimental Setup

Study participants were shown short instructional videos and asked to attempt a quiz afterwards in order to quantify their comprehension. The OpenCV and Dlib Python libraries were used to track the eye gaze in real-time via a webcam. The conversion of the video to its corresponding frames was performed using the OpenCV library. A fixation of eye gaze was used and the spatial coordinates (x_pos , y_pos) of the area of interest were noted along with fixation_duration, indicating

the time for which the x_pos and y_pos were maintained by the eye gaze.

B. Data Description

Four short videos were selected. In each of these videos, the instructor was present on the screen, and the rest of the screen consisted of text and/or images. Table I shows the duration of videos screened and the number of participants. Eye gaze data were collected from the cohort of learners while they watched these videos.

TABLE I. COHORT SCREENING DATA AND DURATION TIME

Video	Duration	Number of participants
Video1	4:59	50
Video2	4:39	65
Video3	4:56	63
Video4	4:40	46

C. Data Cleaning and Preprocessing

The data were cleaned by eliminating erroneous data points due to eye fixation on regions outside the video frame. One possible reason for outlier data points can be attributed to participants moving their heads while watching the video, even though they were informed to keep them stable. The videos were split into frames and manually designated regions of each frame as text, image, and instructor by drawing bounding boxes around the respective region. The collected eye fixation point data were segregated into categories (*text*, *image*, or *instructor*) depending on the specific bounded box in which the x_pos and y_pos coordinates lie. In case eye gaze data were from neither region, it was marked as *others* (outliers). In some frames, the eye gaze data points belonged to overlapping regions, and these points were classified as parts of both categories.

Fig. 1. Bounding boxes categorizing *text*, *image*, *instructor*, *overlapping*, and *others* regions in the frame and data points mapped to each category.

Figure 1 shows a sample frame with bounded boxes and the distribution of eye gaze coordinates in those regions. Each segment is marked with its name in the figure for clarity. This frame shows only a section of the data for demonstration purposes. Figure 2 shows a plot of the frequency distribution of the eye gaze data corresponding to the four categories for one frame.

Fig. 2. Percentage-wise frequency distribution of features per frame.

D. Feature Engineering

To build a model to predict the post-quiz results, features for questions were derived using fixation duration in respective eye gaze categories. For each question asked in the quiz, the frame having the information required to answer the question was identified. The feature score for the question was computed as the fraction of the duration for which the student looked at the particular category. As a final step, the scores were normalized so that the sum for each feature was equal to 1 for each question. Normalization of the scores was required for each question due to the different number of total frames processed for each question. Figure 3 shows the data distribution and the five-number statistics summary for the normalized features.

Fig. 3. Visualization of five-number statistics of features.

The five-number statistics summary is a set of descriptive statistics that includes the values of the sample minimum, maximum, median, first quartile, and third quartile. Algorithm 1 shows the steps to calculate the scores for each question.

Algorithm 1: Calculate feature scores for questions

Result: Feature Scores

for every question **do**

Set $text=image=instructor=others = 0$

find $frame_start$ and $frame_end$

if $fixation_point \in text_bounding_box$ **then**

$text += current_fixation_duration$

```

if  $fixation\_point \in image\_bounding\_box$  then
     $image += current\_fixation\_duration$ 
if  $fixation\_point \in instrctr\_bounding\_box$  then
     $instructor += current\_fixation\_duration$ 
else
     $others += current\_fixation\_duration;$ 
end
return  $text, image, instructor, others$ 

```

III. SUPERVISED PREDICTION MODELS

The following machine learning classification models [18] were used with default hyperparameters to predict the learner's response using their feature scores computed through the eye gaze data. Note that in experimentation, an 80:20 ratio of the data was used for training and testing, respectively, for building the classifiers and predicting the results. The reported results were averaged over 20 runs.

- **Gradient Boosting Classification:** This machine learning technique is generally used for regression and classification problems and produces a prediction model in the form of an ensemble of weak prediction models, typically decision trees.
- **Support Vector Machine (SVM):** This supervised learning model analyzes the data used for classification and regression analysis. Given a set of labeled training examples, an SVM builds a model that assigns new examples to one category or another using a decision boundary for the classes.
- **Neural Network (NN):** This model is inspired by the structure and workings of the human brain. The network consists of multiple node layers that have an input layer, multiple hidden layers, and a single output layer. It learns to perform tasks by considering examples, generally without being programmed with any task-specific rules.

IV. RESULTS

Feature scores for all questions were tallied with the answers submitted by the learners in the post-quiz (binary variable *answer*) using correlation statistics to determine the extent of relationships between the two variables. The Pearson standard correlation coefficient was used to determine the degree and direction of the relation between the features and the quiz scores. Pearson correlation is calculated using least-squares and is defined as the ratio between the covariance of the variables and the product of their standard deviations as:

$$\rho = \frac{cov(x,y)}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

where $cov(x, y)$ is the covariance, σ_x is the standard deviation of x and σ_y is the standard deviation of y . Note that, $\rho = 1$ represents a perfect positive relationship, $\rho = -1$ denotes a perfect negative relationship, and $\rho = 0$ indicates the absence of a relationship between the variables.

A. Pearson Coefficient of Correlation to Identify Influential Features

Figure 4 shows the Pearson's correlation coefficient for the complete data through a heat map, indicating that there is a

negative correlation between the post-exam score field (*answer*) and the *text*, as well as the *image* field. This negative correlation makes the formulated assumption void. However, a positive correlation between the *answer* and the *instructor* field reflects that learners' responses are influenced by the instructor feature. To further validate this hypothesis, the p-values were calculated, as shown in Table II, while testing the significance of these correlation coefficients. It was found that there was a significant relationship between the instructor feature and the answer, and the result of the experiment was statistically significant (97%). The results corresponding to the rest of the features were not statistically significant.

Fig. 4. Heat map showing the correlations between features and answer.

TABLE II. P-VALUES FOR SIGNIFICANCE TESTING

p-value	Text	Image	Instructor	Others
<i>Answer</i>	0.20	0.358	0.034	0.96

B. Evaluation Metrics for Classification Models

Multiple classification models were run with default hyperparameters, and the following evaluation metrics were computed: Accuracy, Precision, Mean Squared Error (MSE), and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) [18]. The Python Scikit-learn (Sklearn) library was used to run various multiclass classifiers [19]. Six classifiers from the library were used: Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBRegression) [20], Epsilon Support Vector Regression (EVRegression) [21], Kernel Ridge Regression (KRRRegression) [22], Linear Support Vector Regression (LinearSVR) [21], and two-layered NN (2NN) [23]. Classifiers were run using the Sigmoid and ReLU activation functions. Linear Support Vector Regression was also performed after applying Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on the feature space (PCA+SVR) [21].

Figure 5 shows the comparative bar plot for the all metrics for the six classifiers, indicating that GBRegression, PCA+SVR, and NN delivered the best performance with the least errors. Table III shows different SVM kernels used to see the variations in errors. It was found that PCA+SVR with kernel "poly" resulted in the least errors among the three kernels used. However, the lowest error values of GBRegression confirm its efficacy compared to SVMs for the considered dataset.

Fig. 5. Comparative evaluation of multiple classifiers using different evaluation metrics (shown as x-axis).

TABLE III. ERRORS FOR GRADIENT BOOSTING CLASSIFIERS AND SVM WITH DIFFERENT KERNELS

Classifier	MSE	MAE
Gradient Boosting	0.23	0.41
PCA+SVR (Kernel = "Linear")	0.241	0.407
PCA+SVR (Kernel = "Poly")	0.239	0.4
PCA+SVR (Kernel = "RBF")	0.238	0.412

C. Role of Optimizers in NN

In addition, 2NNs were run with different epochs and optimizers to see the variations in the accuracy of the built model. Note that an optimizer is a function that updates the attributes, such as weights and learning rate, of the NN, reduces the overall loss, and improves accuracy. Figure 6 shows the achieved accuracy, indicating that a 2NN with an SGD optimizer function resulted in the highest accuracy. Since it is an ensemble-based method, it builds the model in a stage-wise fashion, and, hence, it generalizes better compared to other models, thus leading to a higher test-set accuracy.

D. Role of Features on Learner's Comprehension

Table II and Figure 4 show that *instructor* is the most significant attribute because it is highly correlated with *answer* given by the individuals in the post-tests. Hence, the question "Why not use only this feature for model building instead of using all four features as considered in former experiments?" arises. To show the importance of all features in model building, the following cases were considered as three different feature sets, and the best-supervised model (GBRegression) was used to compare their performances using precision and accuracy metrics:

1. Use the *instructor* as the only feature.
2. Remove *instructor* from the feature set, i.e., use three features *text*, *image*, and *others* in model building to predict the learner's understanding through e-content.
3. Use all features.

Fig. 6. Accuracy of a 2NN with different optimizers and epochs.

Figure 7 shows the precision and accuracy metrics of the built models. As the values of the metrics were higher in case 3 where all features are used, all features are important for the learner's comprehension. Similar observations were made with the rest of the features individually. However, the increase in precision and accuracy was greater after including *instructor* compared to the rest of the features. Hence, *instructor* plays an important role in learning comprehension.

Fig. 7. Performance metrics precision and accuracy of GBRegression model for different cases.

V. DISCUSSION

The analysis of the experiments concludes that learners obtained improved post-exam scores in the instances when they spent more time looking at the speaker compared to the visual and textual data for a particular question. There is a relatively weaker negative correlation between the *image* feature and the post-exam score (*answer*). Similarly, a relatively stronger negative correlation was also observed between the *text* score and *answer*. It was also noted that there was a much stronger positive correlation between the *instructor* score and the student's post-exam score (*answer*). Thus, looking directly at the teacher, while he/she is delivering the lecture content, results in better learning than by looking at the text/image

contents only. This conclusion was also confirmed in experiments conducted using different combinations of features.

These results also show that whether the student would get a particular question right or wrong can be predicted with nearly 70% accuracy from the engineered features. This confirms the potential of the features used in model training. After trying a variety of classification models, a 2NN model with an SGD optimizer delivered the highest classification accuracy on the test dataset.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to find the correlation between the duration of learners' eye gaze on specific sections of selected e-learning videos and their comprehension. The frames of the e-learning videos were categorized into sections of text, images, the instructor, and others. Three supervised prediction models were used along with six classification optimizers. The results showed that the learners obtained improved post-quiz scores when they spent more time looking at the speaker compared to the visual and textual data for a particular question. When comparing the evaluation metrics of the models used, a two-layered NN with an SGD provided the highest classification accuracy on this task.

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Mathematical Modeling of Dynamic Supply Chains Subject to Demand Fluctuations

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ABSTRACT

This research work aims to develop the mathematical modeling for a class of dynamic supply chains. Demand fluctuation corresponds to product demand volatility, which increases or decreases over a given time frame. Industrial engineering practitioners should consider the function that applied mathematical modeling plays in providing approximations of solutions that may be used in simulations and technical implementations at the strategic, tactical, and operational levels of an organization. In order to achieve proper results, two mathematical models are presented in this paper: In addition to a finite-dimensional system of Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) for coupled dynamic pricing, production rate, and inventory level, which properly integrates Lyapunov stability analysis of the dynamical system and simulations, there is an infinite-dimensional Partial Differential Equation (PDE) production level modeling system available. Infinite and finite-dimensional systems incorporate a dynamic pricing approach in the mathematical modeling. The main research goal of this work is to explore the dynamic nature of supply chains applying PDE and ODE methods, with proper analytical analysis and simulations for both systems.

Keywords-dynamic supply chains; Lyapunov stability; infinite dimensional system; finite dimensional system

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, in industrial engineering, mathematical modeling is crucial, especially in dynamic Supply Chains (SCs), which are high volume production systems with high

levels of complexity and low variability. The use of PDEs and ODEs is important given the increased volume of data and commercial judgments that decision-makers must make. Therefore, real-time information can be used to enhance, assist, and validate business decision-making, and this interest is

expanding [1], while taking into account the influence of decision-makers on the strategic, tactical, and operational levels of enterprises, along the SC. Enterprises today strive for rapid, dependable, and adaptable business processes, as well as entrepreneurship practices [2] which increase economic growth. As a result, they must put systematic decision-making processes in place [3]. Supply Chain Management (SCM) and Industry 4.0 network unpredictability, feedback loops, and system dynamics are concerns in production and logistical systems [4]. This research work aims to explore the dynamic nature for a class of SCs, via the development of infinite dimensional systems (PDEs) and finite dimensional systems, subject to demand fluctuations. The operations and management sciences rely on Inventory Management (IM). SCM is the cooperative process management of material and information flows [5]. An SC is a network of locations and businesses involved in distribution, including suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, and retailers [6]. Recent technologies such as blockchain [7] and Artificial Intelligence (AI) [8] have gained special attention between SCM practitioners.

In general, a SC is characterized by three flows: materials and cash (forward flow) and information (backward flow). IM is a component of the SCM that efficiently and effectively coordinates the forward and reverse movement of goods and services between the point of origin and the point of consumption in order to satisfy customer needs [6, 9]. Inherently, inventories are present along the entire SC and inventory control is a critical task for the management of a company [10]. Maintaining proper inventory levels is an important responsibility for a business [11] given that quick and effective customer service is associated with large inventory levels (which raise costs), while low inventory levels could result in scarcity. Supply, transportation, production, and demand variation are all disrupted in SCM systems [12]. In production-inventory systems some works analyzes supply disruption [13], with multi-echelon production-inventory system supply disruption [14]. In relation to production disruptions in [15] presents deteriorating items, while random disruptions are presented in [16-17] and a system dynamics approach is developed for production process disruption in [18]. SCM dynamics build the strategic orientation of SC disruption orientation [19]. In a typical SC network, the efficient collaboration between all parts is vital, in times of uncertainty and unpredictable disruption [20]. Table I summarizes a literature review in demand fluctuation with proper application sector.

In the future, our interest is to apply System Dynamics (SD) which is founded upon the integration of multiple theoretical frameworks, encompassing operating theory, system theory, control theory, information feedback theory, decision-making theory, mechanical systems theory, and computer science [30]. The research goals of this paper are summarized as follows:

- To present a mathematical modeling for infinite dimensional systems which explores the dynamic nature of production-inventory systems with some assumptions in capacity level, inventory level, and demand, with the decision variables being price level and time.

- To analyze the mathematical modeling of an ODE coupled set which summarizes the behavior of a dynamic SCs, with a Lyapunov stability analysis for the dynamical system.
- To present proper simulations for infinite and finite systems that represent the analytical solution form of PDE and the numerical solution for the ODE systems.

TABLE I. LITERATURE REVIEW SUMMARY

Ref.	Contribution	Application
[21]	Considers a supplier–retailer system, with an imperfect production process and a possibility of having demand fluctuation.	SC
[22]	Explores sales and increased income in a SC, in which suppliers frequently choose to grant their retailers a payment delay time.	SC
[23]	Presents a fuzzy inventory model to counteract the demand fluctuation in supply demand networks.	Supply demand networks
[24]	Presents two types of flexibility investment, which are flexible technology and flexible capacity, under demand fluctuations.	Flexible manufacturing systems
[25]	Demand fluctuations can be caused by both predictable oscillations like seasonality and unpredictable disasters like pandemics..	Assembly line balancing
[26]	The ready-mix concrete business experiences significant variations in demand as a result of the volatility observed in local construction markets. The oscillations in question presents impacts on the mix, size, and investment level within the industry.	Construction industry
[27]	Investigates the challenges associated with dynamic pricing in ride-hailing systems, specifically focusing on the issue of supply-demand imbalance resulting from demand fluctuations.	Transportation
[28]	Travel time variability can be attributed to the fluctuations in demand and the deterioration of the capacity within a stochastic network.	Transportation
[29]	Introduces the shuttle bus rerouting and rescheduling strategy, where the operator can change the visited stops and can operate backup buses to handle the passenger demand fluctuations.	Transportation

II. INFINITE DIMENSIONAL PRODUCT LEVEL MODELING

In general, a production system combines humans, machinery, and equipment that are next to common material and information flow [31]. In [32], a PDE for the production level subject to dynamic pricing and time was presented with the form:

$$v_p \frac{\partial^2 \varphi(p,t)}{\partial p \partial t} + (\beta + a_p) \frac{\partial \varphi(p,t)}{\partial p} + \alpha \beta \frac{\partial \varphi(p,t)}{\partial t} + K \varphi(p,t) = D(p,t) \tag{1}$$

where $\varphi(p,t)$ is the production level subject to price and time, $D(p,t)$ is the demand level, v_p is the price velocity, a_p is the price acceleration, β is the damping coefficient, α is the scaling production factor, and K is the production system resilience, with $\beta + a_p > 0$. Our aim is to solve (1) analytically, subject to similar conditions for which a production system approaches to demand levels near zero.

Theorem 1. Consider the PDE in (1) assuming that: $D(p, t) = wP'$, (where w is a scaling factor and P' the price rate), $\beta + \alpha_p = 1$ and $\alpha\beta = 1$, we get the following solution:

$$\varphi(p, t) = e^{-\alpha p} \left(e^{-\left(\frac{K-\alpha}{1-\alpha v_p}\right)t} + \frac{\alpha w}{\alpha-K} \right)$$

Proof:

$$v_p \frac{\partial^2 \varphi(p,t)}{\partial p \partial t} + \frac{\partial \varphi(p,t)}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial \varphi(p,t)}{\partial t} + K\varphi(p,t) = wP' \quad (2)$$

Applying the separation of variables method, we have:

$$\varphi(p, t) = P(p)T(t) \quad (3)$$

Substituting (3) in the PDE (2):

$$v_p P' T' + P' T - wP' + P T' + K P T = 0 \quad (4)$$

where: $P' = \frac{dP}{dp}$ and $T' = \frac{dT}{dt}$

Grouping the terms from (4) we have:

$$P'(v_p T' + T - w) = -P(T' + KT). \quad (5)$$

Separating terms in (5) we get:

$$-\frac{P'}{P} = \frac{(T'+KT)}{v_p T'+T-w} = \alpha. \quad (6)$$

For separate ODE, in time domain:

$$\frac{P'}{P} = -\alpha. \quad (7)$$

Therefore:

$$\frac{dP}{P} = -\alpha dp. \quad (8)$$

Solving (8) we have:

$$P(p) = e^{-\alpha p}. \quad (9)$$

For the ODE, in time domain:

$$T' + KT = \alpha(v_p T' + T - w). \quad (10)$$

After some algebraic manipulation, (10) becomes:

$$T' + \left(\frac{K-\alpha}{1-\alpha v_p}\right) T = -\left(\frac{\alpha w}{1-\alpha v_p}\right). \quad (11)$$

Solving (11), we have:

$$T(t) = C e^{-\left(\frac{K-\alpha}{1-\alpha v_p}\right)t} + \frac{\alpha w}{K-\alpha} \quad (12)$$

Finally, the solution for the PDE production level subject to price and time is:

$$\varphi_1(p, t) = e^{-\alpha p} \left(e^{-\left(\frac{K-\alpha}{1-\alpha v_p}\right)t} + \frac{\alpha w}{\alpha-K} \right) \quad (13)$$

Corollary 1. Considering the PDE in (1) and assuming that demand fluctuates towards: $D(p, t) = 0$, we get the following solution:

$$\varphi_2(p, t) = e^{(\gamma p - \alpha t)}$$

In Figure 1, a PDE production level normalized solution in function of price and time is shown, considering a tendency to zero production level conforming price and time tending to infinity.

Fig. 1. PDE production level solution in function of price and time.

In general, production systems are required to effectively manage the challenges that arise from the presence of variabilities and complexities resulting from globalization and technological improvements, which impacts in demand fluctuation along the supply chain. The following section explores the dynamic SC mathematical modeling with a proper stability analysis and simulations.

III. FINITE DIMENSIONAL SC MODELING

In [33], a dynamic production-inventory system via optimal control theory is presented. In general, along the supply chains there are three flows: material, cash, and information. IM presents a crucial role for the SC operation by considering the synchronic and diachronic evolution of the SC to achieve equilibrium and coordination between supply and demand. This paper presents an expansion of the previous work, focusing on the incorporation of dynamic pricing and the inclusion of time delay effects for the purpose of mathematical modeling of a class of SC.

A. Mathematical Modeling

A time-delayed production inventory system is proposed via a set of coupled ODEs which are described as follows: To incorporate a dynamic pricing perspective in the dynamic SC, we propose:

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = u_1(t) - p(t) + k \frac{I(t)}{C} \quad (14)$$

where u_1 denotes the purchase price level, p denotes the sales price level, I is the inventory level, k is the associated cost for the inventory, and C is the capacity level.

To develop the production-inventory system dynamics for production level and production rates, the following equation is proposed:

$$C \frac{d^2 Q}{dt^2} + I(t) \frac{dQ}{dt} + \gamma Q(t - \theta) = d(t) \quad (15)$$

where Q represents the production level, dQ/dt is the production rate, d is the demand level, θ represents the lead time, and γ is the production resilience factor.

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \mu I(t - \theta) + \gamma Q(t) - d(t) \tag{16}$$

In order to provide a linear approximation, via Taylor series, for the time delay terms as in [34], and neglecting high order terms:

$$x(t - \tau) \approx x(t) - \tau \dot{x}(t) \tag{17}$$

Developing a state space formulation for the time delayed production inventory system from (14)-(16) and after applying (17), our new state space system is:

$$\dot{x}_1(t) = -x_1(t) + k_1 x_4(t) \tag{18}$$

$$\dot{x}_2(t) = x_3(t) \tag{19}$$

$$\dot{x}_3(t) = -k_2 x_3(t) x_4(t) - k_3 x_2(t) + k_4 x_3(t) \tag{20}$$

$$\dot{x}_4(t) = k_5 x_2(t) + k_6 x_4(t) \tag{21}$$

where $x_1(t) = p(t)$, $x_2(t) = Q(t)$, $x_3(t) = dQ/dt$, $x_4(t) = I(t)$ and constants $k_1 = k/C$, $k_2 = 1/C$, $k_3 = \gamma/C$, $k_4 = \gamma\theta/C$, $k_5 = \gamma/(1+\mu\theta)$, $k_6 = \mu/(1+\mu\theta)$.

B. Stability Analysis

Theorem 2. In order to have a stability analysis, for the equation system (18)-(21), the following conditions must be satisfied, $\vartheta > 0$, $\mu > 0$, and $C > 1 + \mu\theta$.

Proof. In order to proof Theorem 2, the following Lyapunov candidate function is proposed:

$$V(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{2}x_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}x_2^2 + \frac{1}{2}(x_3 - x_4)^2 \tag{22}$$

Applying the derivative with respect to time, to the Lyapunov candidate function:

$$\dot{V}(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = x_1 \dot{x}_1 + x_2 \dot{x}_2 + (x_3 - x_4)(\dot{x}_3 - \dot{x}_4) \tag{23}$$

After some algebraic manipulation, and applying the LaSalle Theorem in the equilibrium point, we get:

$$\dot{V}(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) < -x_1^2 + k_4 x_3^2 + k_6 x_4^2 - (k_3 - k_5 - 1)|Q|^2 - (k_4 + k_6)|O|^2 - (k_5 - k_3)|P|^2 \tag{24}$$

Equation (24) can be simplified to:

$$\dot{V}(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) < -x_1^2 - (k_4 + k_6)|O|^2 - (k_5 - k_3)|P|^2 \tag{25}$$

In order to achieve stability, the following conditions must be satisfied:

$$k_4 + k_6 > 0$$

$$k_5 - k_3 > 0$$

Therefore: $k_4 > 0$ and $k_6 > 0$

Considering that: $k_4 = \frac{\gamma\theta}{C}$, $k_6 = \frac{\mu}{1+\mu\theta}$, and $k_5 > k_3$.

From which we can conclude that:

$$\gamma\theta > 0, \mu > 0, \text{ and } C > 1 + \mu\theta.$$

C. Simulations

Simulations were conducted in MATLAB for (18)-(21). Figure 2 presents the decaying performance for the price level of the finite dimensional production system considering (14), which presents the dynamic pricing analysis for production-inventory system. It is confirmed that as time increases, the price level tends to zero.

Fig. 2. Price level for the finite dimensional production system.

In Figure 3, the production level achieves a maximum for the finite dimensional system which is based on the context that this is the level of the production rate.

Fig. 3. Production level for the finite dimensional production system.

Unproduction is related with a negative production rate (Figure 4). This effect is present around $t = 2$, and when t tends to higher values, the production rate decreases.

Figure 5 presents the decaying inventory level, confirming the production rate tending to a negative value, which is an effect of the relation of maximum production level with the lower levels for inventory. This is apparent from (16), which presents a dynamic inventory level with time delay.

Fig. 4. Production rate of the finite dimensional production system.

Fig. 5. Inventory level for the finite dimensional production system.

IV. CONCLUSION

Applied modeling plays an important role for industrial engineering practitioners. This research paper addressed two problems in the context of high-volume supply chain, by applying infinite and finite dimensional mathematical approaches. Several research works have presented the use of PDEs for production systems [35-36], whereas the use of ODEs in the mathematical modeling for production-inventory systems was more common [37-38]. In this work, infinite and finite dimensional systems incorporate dynamic pricing into the description of a dynamical system while taking demand fluctuations into account.

A supply chain refers to a collection of organizations, which collaborate in the process of bringing a product to its final consumer [39]. Discrete event simulation has been applied to increase productivity of enterprises [40]. This mathematical modeling considers low variability and cause-effect relation for a deterministic approach in high volume supply chains. In general, demand fluctuation corresponds to product demand variation, which is increased or decreased in a time horizon period. This is the main contribution of the current work.

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A Novel Solution Method for the Distribution Network Reconfiguration Problem based on an Objective Function and considering the Cost of Electricity Transmission

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ABSTRACT

The problem of distribution reconfiguration is an important issue in the optimal operation of distribution networks. Nowadays, with the diverse development of renewable energy sources, the uncertainty of the load becomes more complex, and the need for competitive retail electricity markets is more evident. This paper presents an optimal solution to this problem, utilizing the global advantage of the simulated annealing algorithm, improving the time parameter, and combining it with the rapid mutation ability of the genetic algorithm. Simultaneously, the Zbus, EBE, and PS models were integrated to optimize the costs, considering transmission costs under constraints related to taxes and economic indicators when connected to the distribution grid. The proposed method was simulated and tested on the IEEE 33-node standard power grid with three different scenarios. The simulation results showed that the proposed method provides optimal results, which can be applied to calculate the optimal operation of the distribution grid when participating in retail electricity markets.

Keywords-simulation annealing algorithm; genetic algorithms; distribution network reconfiguration; transmission system usage; transmission cost allocation

I. INTRODUCTION

The problem of Power Distribution Network Reconfiguration (PDNR) is a classic issue in the planning and operation research of distribution networks [1-2]. PDNR is an optimization problem that aims to alter the connection methods of the electrical network, which is a non-convex optimization challenge within a large solution space. Various approaches have been proposed to address this problem, including analytical methods, metaheuristic (empirical) methods, and artificial intelligence algorithms, with the latter gaining more popularity [3]. The objective functions in different studies vary and correspond to the diverse issues within PDNR, especially those aiming to minimize power losses and improve power quality. In recent years, the growing strength of Renewable Energy (RE) as Distributed Generation (DG) has led to an increased interest in studying PDNR issues in conjunction with the evaluation of the impact of DG [4]. These studies often consider an objective function that not only aims to minimize power losses but also contemplates the connectivity

characteristics of DG, voltage quality (stability) conditions, loadability of the network (Icp), and the necessity of maintaining the network's radial structure. The problem of network reconfiguration consists of minimizing losses while considering the reliability of the power supply. The supply validity is modeled as the cost of power outages, thus leading to an evaluation of the supply reliability impact on the objective function in the network reconfiguration [5]. During the past decade, the proliferation of Distributed Energy Resources (DER) has sparked increasing interest in research on network reconfiguration for power distribution geared towards distributed generation (DG) [6-9]. In [10], the string utilized in the Genetic Algorithm (GA) delineated all the switch positions along with their "on/off" statuses. The length of this string tends to increase in tandem with the number of switches. For extensive distribution systems, managing such elongated strings becomes unfeasible for GA. In the context of this study, efforts were made to truncate the string. In [11-12], the restructuring of the electrical distribution system examining the

fees for using the energy transmission system was discussed. In [11], an overview of formulas, algorithms, and current trends in research on restructuring the electrical distribution system was presented. This overview was conducted with increasing interest in the use of sustainable energy sources and factors related to electric vehicles as well as other renewable energy sources. Furthermore, it was pointed out that despite research carried out in the past decade, some aspects are still less explored, especially location costs and allocation of transmission expenses. In [13-14], the electrical distribution system expansion plan was considered from the perspective of fees associated with the energy transmission system usage. A distribution reconfiguration model was proposed to minimize these fees and analyze their effect on the restructuring of the electrical distribution system. Computational methods and simulations to evaluate the fees and their impact on using the energy transmission system in the expansion plan of the electrical distribution system were provided.

The application of transmission system usage tariffs in the evolving electricity market leads to the optimization of the transmission grid use and becomes a significant factor for guiding decisions related to the electrical distribution system operation [15]. This study aims to explore the impact of location-based transmission system usage tariffs on the reconfiguration of the electrical distribution network. The new proposals include the development of an objective function to reconfigure the electrical grid considering transmission costs. In order for this reconfiguration to be achieved, an algorithm using the Simulation Annealing (SA) algorithm and the Genetic Algorithm (GA) to solve the optimization problem with the constraints of the grid reconfiguration problem is proposed. Also, the impact of the costs resulting from using transmission lines on the problem of reconfiguring the distribution network is analyzed.

II. MODEL AND CONSTRAINT CONDITIONS

Considering the electrical supply diagram which includes the transmission line system and distribution network shown in Figure 1. The distribution network diagram consists of 50 nodes, with two supply sources from two transformer stations, and each station has two output lines corresponding to SE101, SE102, SE103, and SE104. The cost of electricity supply from the source to the electric load consumption is determined through three costs: (1) transmission cost on the transmission lines, (2) electrical energy loss cost, and (3) operation and maintenance costs of the system [15] as:

$$P = C_{CostT} + C_{Plosse} + C_{OM}$$

where C_{CostT} , C_{Plosse} , and C_{OM} represent the costs of electric energy transmission, electric energy loss, and operation and maintenance, respectively. The objective function is:

$$Min(F) = Min(C_{CostT} + C_{Plosse} + C_{OM}) \quad (1)$$

and the constraints of the problem are:

$$P_{Gi} - P_{Si} - P_{di} = 0 \quad \forall i \in \Omega_b \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{Gi} - Q_{Si} - Q_{di} = 0 \quad \forall i \in \Omega_b \quad (3)$$

$$v_{min} \leq v_i \leq v_{max} \quad \forall i \in \Omega_b \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1. A distribution network connected to two supply sources from the transmission grid.

$$n_{ij} \cdot (P_{ij}^2 + Q_{ij}^2) \leq S_{max(ij)}^2 \quad \forall i \in \Omega_{ld} \quad (5)$$

$$P_{ij}^2 + Q_{ij}^2 \leq S_{max(ij)}^2 + \xi_{ij} \quad \forall i \in \Omega_{lt} \quad (6)$$

$$P_{Si}^2 + Q_{Si}^2 \leq S_{max(i)}^2 \quad \forall i \in \Omega_s \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{ij \in \Omega_{ld}} n_{ij} = n_{bd} - n_{bs} \quad (8)$$

$$n_{ij} \in \{0,1\} \quad (9)$$

$$\xi_{ij} \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

where C_{CostT} is transmission system usage charges assigned to distribution (\$), C_{Plosse} is the cost of electrical energy losses (\$), C_{OM} is the cost of operation and maintenance of substations (\$), P_{Gi} is the active power generated at bus i (pu), Q_{Gi} is the reactive power generated at bus i (pu), and P_{Si} is the total active power demanded at substation i (pu). Q_{Si} is the total reactive power demanded at substation i (pu), P_{di} is the total active power demanded at bus i (pu), Q_{di} is the total reactive power demanded at bus i (pu), Q_{Gi} is the reactive power generated at bus i (pu), v_{min} is the minimum admissible limit of voltage (pu), v_{max} is the maximum admissible limit of voltage (pu), and v_i is the voltage at bus i (pu). $S_{max(i)}$ is the maximum loading limit of substation i (pu), n_{ij} is a binary decision variable determining whether the circuit bus ij is open (0) or closed (1), P_{ij} is the active power flow in the circuit bus ij (MW), Q_{ij} is the reactive power flow in the circuit bus ij (MVar), and S_{maxij} is the maximum loading limit of the circuit bus ij (MVA). n_{bd} is the number of bars in the distribution system, n_{bs} is the number of boundary substations in the transmission and distribution system, ξ_{ij} is the incremental variable of deficits of existing transmission line capacity ij , Ω_b

is the set of buses of the transmission and distribution system, Ω_s is the set of substations, Ω_{ld} is the set of the distribution system branches, and Ω_{lt} is the set of transmission system branches i between the transmission and distribution system (\$/MW).

The cost function C_{CostT} of the objective function representing the cost of using the electrical transmission system is described by:

$$C_{CostT} = \sum_{i \in \Omega_s} P_{Si} \times TUST_i^D \quad (11)$$

where $TUST_i^D$ is the transmission usage fee at boundary i between the transmission and distribution systems (\$/MW). The cost function $C_{Plossse}$ refers to the cost of electrical energy loss in the transmission and distribution network:

$$C_{Plossse} = \delta_l \sum_{i,j \in \Omega_l} R_{ij} \times I_{ij}^2 \quad (12)$$

where R_{ij} is the electrical resistance of line ij (Ω), I_{ij} is the current in the line section buses i and j (A), δ_l is the variable for electrical energy loss converted to energy. When converted to present value, the annual loss cost is described as:

$$\delta_l = 8760 \times \phi_l \times c_l \times \delta_{vp} \quad (13)$$

where ϕ_l is the typical annual loss coefficient, c_l is the cost for one unit of loss (\$/kWh), and δ_{vp} is the coefficient for converting to the present value of annual costs, defined as:

$$\delta_{vp} = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^h (1 + \frac{\tau}{100})^j} \quad (14)$$

where τ is the discount rate (%) and h is the number of years in the project life cycle. The operation and maintenance cost of the transformer stations C_{OM} is given by:

$$C_{OM} = \delta_0 \sum_{i,j \in \Omega_1} (P_{Si}^2 + Q_{Si}^2) \quad (15)$$

The coefficient δ_0 is used to convert the annual operation and maintenance cost to present value:

$$\delta_0 = 8760 \times \phi_l \times c_{vi} \times \delta_{vp} \quad (16)$$

where c_{vi} is the unit cost for operating and maintaining the transformer station (\$/kVA²). Values 0 or 1 are used to represent the open/closed state of the branches n_{ij} of the switches in (9). In this case, n_{ij} refers to the status (open or closed) of the switch installed in segment ij .

The constraints of the mathematical model include power balance at the nodes, described by (2) and (3), radial nature of the feeder circuits ensured when simultaneously satisfying (2), (3), and (8) [6, 16], voltage magnitude limits (4), loading capacity of transmission lines and distribution networks (6), as well as loading limits of substations (7). The expansion of the loading capacity of transmission lines is modeled by the variable ξ_{ij} , reflecting the incremental deficits in the loading capacity of the existing transmission line ij . The Total Annual Revenue (TAR) is the amount paid to transmission companies by generation and distribution agents to access the system. The sum of TAR is ensured by the revenue collected from the Transmission System Usage Fee (TUSF), derived from a method of allocating transmission costs. In particular, the expansion of transmission significantly affects the price levels

for end consumers. Assessing the effects of transmission expansion on the development of TAR is a complex task, considering that the actual expansion of the transmission system occurs discontinuously with the acceptance of new projects. Given that the focus of this study is the reconfiguration of the distribution system, a simplified modeling of TAR development was applied, assuming that expansion can be performed through marginal increases in the transmission capacity of existing routes, as described by

$$TAR = \sum_{i \in \Omega_{lt}} C_{ij} + (\xi_{ij} \cdot \pi_{ij}) \quad (17)$$

where C_{ij} is the annual cost of the transmission line section ij (\$), and π_{ij} is the marginal cost of the transmission line section expansion ij (\$).

III. METHODOLOGY

The solution to this problem consists of two steps, as shown in Figure 2. Step 1 involves using a combination of the SA with GA to reconfigure the distribution power grid to reduce power loss. Step 2 involves utilizing the Zbus, EBE, and PS/SINCAL models for the optimization of transmission costs. Figure 3 shows Step 1.

Fig. 2. Method for the reconfiguration of the distribution network based on an objective function considering the cost of electricity transmission.

A. Step 1: Combining SA and GA to Reconfigure the Distribution Network

SA and GA were amalgamated to form a hybrid algorithm termed GSA to reconfigure the distribution network. Within this hybrid framework, SA takes the lead in scouting for an optimal solution, while in every iteration of SA, GA steps in to offer a fresh configuration using genetic operations such as mutation or cross-over [17-19].

Fig. 3. Combining SA and GA to reconfigure the distribution network.

Figure 3 presents the main reconfiguration of the GSA process. The network N_0 is generated by the GA subfunction called *initialization* and the E_0 value of its objective function is calculated. The maximum temperature (T) is set to 50. Parameter I is employed to control the iterations of the GA process. The maximum number of iterations was set at 20. A new configuration N_I is produced from the GA process and then evaluated to have E_I [20]. If the new solution is better than the old one (which means $C_I < C_0$), it is accepted and S_I replaces S_0 . Even if the new solution is worse than N_0 , which means that $C_I - C_0 > 0$, it can still be randomly accepted. In that case, the acceptance probability will be a function of the two values of the objective function and the temperature reduction function [21]. The cost functions are calculated using:

$$C(x) = \begin{cases} P_0 + \alpha A(x) + \beta . B(x) & n \leq L_s \\ (1 + \theta(n - L_s) . P_0 + \alpha A(x) + \beta . B(x) & n > L_s \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

In the SA algorithm, the following equation was applied to improve the temperature change process. With this improvement, the temperature change values in each step make it easier to find the optimal solution and the convergence time of the algorithm is faster.

$$T_{i+1} = e^{-\frac{2}{(i+5)}} . T_i \quad (19)$$

where i is the number of decreasing temperatures. GA is used to generate new potential solutions, in which the solution with the most appropriate value is selected and then put through the SA process for further selection [21].

B. Step 2: Optimal Distribution of Transmission Costs

This step focuses on the allocation of transmission system costs, conducted through three validated and widely applied methods that ensure robust and reliable results. The methods used to determine TUSFs include Zbus [22-23], PS [24], and EBE [23- 25].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed method was simulated in Matlab R2019 [26] for the problem of electrical grid reconfiguration and transmission cost optimization (TRA) while simultaneously integrating with PSS SINCAL [27]. The simulation was run on a PC with an Intel® Core™ i7, 8GB RAM, and Windows 10. Figure 4 shows the implementation steps.

Fig. 4. Diagram implementation simulation.

Figure 1 shows the integration of transmission and distribution systems. The reconfiguration of the distribution network considering the economic signals of transmission tariffs was assessed based on the integrated modeling of the 4-bar transmission test system presented in [28-29] and the 54-node test system of [22].

A. Reconfiguration of the Distribution Network by GSA

The electricity grid considered is a distribution network including 33 nodes [6].

Fig. 5. Before reconfiguring the distribution network of 33 nodes.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF GSA WITH OTHER METHODS

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Initialization (before)		GSA (proposed) (after)	
Open switches are usually: s33, s34, s35, s36, s37		Switches open: s7, s9, s14, s32, s37	
Switching usually closes: s1 to s32		Choose parameters $\alpha = 1000$, $\beta = 1000$, $\epsilon = 0.1$, $\delta = 1$	
Voltage	12.66 kV	Voltage	12.66 kV
U_{max}	0.913 pu	U_{max}	0.932 pu
U_{min}	0.996 pu	U_{min}	0.995 pu
Active Capacity	5058.25 kW	Active Capacity	5058.25 kW
Reactive power	2547.32 kVAR	Reactive power	2547.32 kVAR
Total loss(P_{loss})	202.68 kW	Total loss(P_{loss})	136.89 kW

Fig. 6. After reconfiguring the distribution network.

Fig. 7. Voltage before and after reconfiguring the distribution network.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF GSA WITH OTHER METHODS

Method	P_{loss} (kW)	U_{min} (pu)	Open switches	Iteration
Initialization	202.68	0.913	s33,s34,s35,s36,s37	
SA [21]	137.57	0.932	s7,s9,s14,s32,s37	18
GSA (proposed)	136.89	0.932	s7,s9,s14,s32,s37	11
Gome [7]	138.57	0.928	s7,s9,s14,s32,s37	15
HSA[9]	139.55	0.928	s7,S9,S14,S32,s37	16
CE [5]	139.55	0.921	s7,s14,s28,s33,s36	-
Shirmoham[30]	138.87	0.932	s7,s10,s14,s32,s37	-

The results of the SA algorithm were compared with algorithms from [7, 9, 21, 30], and CE [5], as shown in Table II. The proposed method combined SA with GA to yield outcomes similar to those of other methods for the reconfiguration problem. However, it uniquely leverages the global optimization strengths of the SA algorithm and the local search capabilities of the GA during the initialization of values, thus significantly improves the processing speed. The number of iterations in the proposed method was lower than in the other methods.

B. Reconfiguration of the Distribution Network Considering Power Transmission Costs

The distribution system was connected to bus number 4 of the transmission system through substations SE-103 and SE-104, and to bus 3 through substations SE-101 and SE-102. Table III presents the technical and economic data used in the simulations.

TABLE III. TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC DATA

No	Table column subhead	Value	Unit
1	Minimum voltage deviation	0.93	pu
2	Maximum voltage deviation	1.05	pu
3	O&M cost of the transformer substation	0.004	\$/kVA ²
4	Load factor	0.50	
5	Loss factor	0.50	
6	Loss cost	0.01	\$/kW
7	Discount rate	10%	per year
8	Conductor impedance:	$z=0.6115 + j0.4133$	Ω/km

To assess the impact of reconfiguring the distribution network considering the cost of the transmission system, the simulation study examined three scenarios regarding the load capacity of the lines:

- Scenario 1: Capacity of Line LT-13: 25 MVA, other lines' capacity: 100 MVA.
- Scenario 2: Capacity of Line LT-24: 25 MVA, other lines' capacity: 100 MVA.
- Scenario 3: Capacity of Line LT-14: 25 MVA, other lines' capacity: 100 MVA.

In scenarios 1, 2, and 3, the power flowing in the transmission lines does not exceed their capacities when the reconfiguration of the distribution system aims at optimizing the charges for using the transmission system. On the contrary, in the three cases where the transmission tariffs are not considered, a need for transmission expansion arises. Table IV shows the impact of TUSFs on PDNR and the loading of distribution substations.

Table V shows a summary of the overhead costs resulting from reconfiguring the distribution grid. It was found that the outcomes of the distribution grid configuration remain the same, regardless of the transmission cost allocation method applied.

In scenarios 1, 2, and 3, the total cost decreases when considering the application of TUSF values. In this case, the proposed PDNR led to a reduction of 51.34%, 28.03%, and

30.17% in scenarios 1, 2, and 3, respectively, compared to the classical PDNR. These results underscore the importance of considering transmission fees in PDRN. The proposed method is highly reliable in these scenarios, minimizing cases of overload on transmission grid lines, and optimizing cost allocation when restructuring the problem. Moreover, the proposed method takes the cost of power supply into account, and so the need to invest in expanding the power transmission grid is reduced.

Fig. 8. Impact of DRN on power flow on transmission branches.

TABLE IV. CAPACITY TRANSFORMER STATION AND TUSF

	ATC	Capacity Transformer Station (MW)				TUSF (\$/MW)	
		101	102	103	104	101-102	103-104
Scenario 1	EBE					0.0090	0.0064
	PS	4.77	20.53	35.48	37.33	0.0072	0.0067
	ZBUS					0.0071	0.0051
Scenario 2	EBE					0.0068	0.0076
	PS	30.26	45.11	10.27	13.48	0.0075	0.0110
	ZBUS					0.0042	0.0065
Scenario 3	EBE					0.0071	0.0066
	PS	19.73	31.22	20.92	26.39	0.0058	0.0078
	ZBUS					0.0045	0.0055

TABLE V. THE COSTS OPTIMIZATION

No	Open Switch	PRDN (proposed)	PRDN (classic)	%
		Global Cost (\$)		
Scenario 1	2, 7, 12, 15, 18, 28, 35, 37, 39, 55, 57	1.872	3.847	51.34
Scenario 2	5, 8, 12, 20, 25, 28, 32, 34, 51, 55, 57	1.918	2.665	28.03
Scenario 3	4, 8, 12, 21, 25, 27, 35, 38, 44, 56, 57	1.768	2.532	30.17

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The proposed method addressed the problem of reconfiguring the distribution power grid considering transmission costs. The reconfiguration problem was approached by combining the strengths of SA and GA and improving the parameters within the SA algorithm (19), leading to faster convergence. When considering transmission cost factors, the optimized method incorporates economic indicators, taxes, voltage constraints, transmission limits, and the capacity of the distribution substations. The optimal outcome is to find the best configuration that connects substations with the most favorable TUSF values, ensuring reduced electricity supply costs for consumers. The future direction of this research will continue to explore additional constraints or include other optimization goals, such as the location, capacity of substations, transmission capacity, and power flow control in the distribution grid using Soft Open Points (SOP) and considering renewable energy sources.

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IoT Protocol-Enabled IDS based on Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT

During the last decade, Internet of Things (IoT) devices have become widely used in smart homes, smart cities, factories, and many other areas to facilitate daily activities. As IoT devices are vulnerable to many attacks, especially if they are not frequently updated, Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) must be used to defend them. Many existing IDSs focus on specific types of IoT application layer protocols, such as MQTT, CoAP, and HTTP. Additionally, many existing IDSs based on machine learning are inefficient in detecting attacks in IoT applications because they use non-IoT-dedicated datasets. Therefore, there is no comprehensive IDS that can detect intrusions that specifically target IoT devices and their various application layer protocols. This paper proposes a new comprehensive IDS for IoT applications called IP-IDS, which can equivalently detect MQTT, HTTP, and CoAP-directed intrusions with high accuracy. Three different datasets were used to train the model: Bot-IoT, MQTT-IoT-IDS2020, and CoAP-DDoS. The obtained results showed that the proposed model outperformed the existing models trained on the same datasets. Additionally, the proposed DT and LSTM models reached an accuracy of 99.9%.

Keywords-IDS; IoT; DT;LSTM

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) refers to a network of physical items integrated with sensors, software, and other technologies that connect to and exchange data with other devices and systems through the Internet. Such devices range from common domestic items to complex industrial machines. IoT devices may be secure at the time of purchase but become vulnerable when hackers discover new security flaws or bugs. An Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is hardware or software that scans a network for harmful activity or potential security

attacks and alerts the administrator. The IDS collects data that contain evidence of an attack using gathering models. After processing the data, an analysis module discovers the attacks and reports them to the administrator [1]. There are two IDS approaches: anomaly-based and signature-based. Signature-based IDS have a repository of attack signatures to compare with network data, and if a match is discovered, an alarm is triggered. Although this approach is often very effective in recognizing known threats, it is less effective against mutations from existing and zero-day attacks [2]. Anomaly-based IDSs use Machine Learning (ML) models to recognize attacks. ML

models define the baseline of system activities and/or attack patterns, and any system activity that deviates significantly is reported [2]. Traditional IDSs designed for conventional networks are less effective in the context of IoT systems due to the specific vulnerabilities and risks that threaten this kind of application. The resource-constrained nature of IoT nodes, in addition to the large-scale and time-constrained applications in the IoT context, requires new customized protocols to provide the required QoS. New protocols are used, such as Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) and Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP), in addition to the de-facto HTTP. All these protocols have many vulnerabilities that require specific care [2].

The MQTT protocol is a machine-to-machine and publish-subscribe protocol that provides reliable and secure communications among IoT nodes and is considered the most popular protocol used in messaging. Many vulnerabilities in this protocol have emerged and are reported to be increasing, especially in the recent period from 2014 to 2020. One of the existing vulnerabilities is the insufficient check of packet length before parsing, which makes attackers exploit it to perform buffer overflow, Denial of Service (DoS), remote code execution, and reading memory contents. Another vulnerability is the ignorance of the required validation field that could cause a server crash, buffer overflow, remote code execution, or broker crash. The MQTT protocol also suffers from insufficient logical error checks that could lead to DoS, code execution, server crashes, or buffer overflow attacks [3].

CoAP is a web-based protocol dedicated to constrained nodes and networks such as IoT. Unfortunately, it has many serious weaknesses, such as the improper incoming parsing of messages that could lead to remote code execution, which can affect the availability of the CoAP node. In addition, in the CoAP context, improper implementation of proxies and cache access control might lead to compromise of their content and threaten the integrity and confidentiality of CoAP messages. Additionally, the improper configuration of new CoAP nodes might result in unauthorized access to the CoAP environment by unauthorized nodes. One more vulnerability for CoAP is the unreliable generation of cryptographic keys that could compromise the nodes. Another important weakness is the IP address spoofing of CoAP nodes, which allows an attacker to generate spoofed response messages and acknowledgments as well as reflection/amplification attacks [4].

Similarly, the HTTP protocol has some major vulnerabilities. SQL injection is one of the most prevalent types of web application security vulnerabilities. In addition, many security issues associated with managing a user's identity can be caused by faulty authentication and session management in HTTP. Security misconfiguration is another vulnerability in web applications. ML approaches have recently been presented as successful techniques for detecting network attacks, especially IoT networks [1, 5-6]. In the context of intrusion detection, ML models are known for their ability to detect zero-day attacks. Distinct efforts have been made to design ML-based IDSs for IoT. They provide many brilliant solutions, but unfortunately, there is no consideration of specific IoT protocols, such as MQTT and CoAP. Few existing IDSs can

detect forged or invalid packets in IoT communication based on specific protocols, such as MQTT or CoAP. Furthermore, in existing IDSs, not all ML models are trained using IoT datasets, and therefore their performance may be reduced once deployed in an IoT environment [7].

Motivated by the widespread application of ML and its proven efficiency in detecting zero-day vulnerabilities, many studies adopted ML to design anomaly-based IDSs [1]. In [8], a Deep Neural Network (DNN)-based model was proposed to detect attacks that exploit vulnerabilities in the MQTT protocol. The performance of the proposed model was compared with conventional ML algorithms, using a dataset that contained records on three different types of attacks, including man-in-the-middle, intrusion, and DoS. The results showed that the DNN model performed better than Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU). The proposed model was good enough to detect MQTT-directed intrusions, yet it was limited to detecting only such intrusions. In [9], an IDS was proposed to detect intrusions using the MQTT protocol, comparing many shallow and Deep Learning (DL) models, and the results showed that the Decision Tree (DT) outperformed the DL models. Similarly, in [10] a model was proposed to detect man-in-the-middle attacks that exploit MQTT vulnerabilities. Many classification techniques were used, such as Non-Convex Boundary over Projections (NCBoP), Approximate Convex Hull (ACH), K-Means, and Principal Component Analysis (PCA), on a real dataset. The obtained results showed that PCA was the best approach for detecting man-in-the-middle attacks. Unfortunately, this study focused only on evaluating the performance of different techniques in terms of accuracy and shortest training time for MQTT datasets and did not consider other attack types.

In the literature, only one study focused on proposing an ML-based model for intrusion detection in CoAP [11]. This study proposed an IDS for the detection and prevention of attacks against Internet-integrated CoAP communication environments, putting into practice and evaluating the efficiency of anomaly-based intrusion detection using an SVM model to detect DoS attacks against the CoAP protocol. The main weakness of this model was that it focused on only one protocol and one attack. In [12], many ML and DL models were proposed, including SVM, Random Forest (RF), DT, and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) that concentrated on identifying DoS and Distributed DoS (DDoS) attacks in the transport and application layers using the BoT-IoT dataset. The model achieved an average accuracy of more than 99%, yet this model was not comprehensive enough to address threats on IoT networks since it only considered DoS/DDoS attacks. In [13], a DL model was proposed to recognize intrusions in IoT networks using the BoT-IoT dataset and ML algorithms, such as RF, and DL techniques such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for the classification of attacks. The results showed that the DL models had higher DoS, DDoS, reconnaissance, and data theft detection capabilities than the ML models. However, the proposed models did not consider detecting attacks in application protocols but only in the network layer. Similarly, in [14], network layer attacks in the IoT environment were detected using the CICID2017 dataset, which is a generic dataset not dedicated to IoT networks.

Although the proposed model successfully detected many attacks, it may not be effective in the IoT context.

In [15], many shallow and DL models were used to design an IDS for IoT. The results showed that the shallow models outperformed the DL models in terms of accuracy for all devices. In [16], an IDS with a Deep Belief Network (DBN) was used to detect network-level attacks. The TON-IoT-Weather dataset [17] contains seven different attack types, such as DDoS, password cracking, scanning, etc, but not application layer attacks. In [18], a framework for intrusion detection in IoT was proposed, using three ML models trained on NSL-KDD datasets, but the models had very low accuracy and the dataset was not IoT-specific.

This study aims to build a new comprehensive anomaly-based network IDS, based on ML models, to help users monitor their IoT system by detecting intrusions specifically in IoT application layer protocols. The proposed system is called IP-IDS, which stands for IoT-Protocols enabled IDS. The proposed system aimed to overcome the drawbacks of traditional non-IoT-based ML approaches that suffer from low accuracy, inability to detect novel attacks, need for updates for every new attack pattern discovered, and lack of self-learning. IP-IDS aimed to improve ML-based solutions that assume that the application layer protocol is always HTTP, ignoring the vulnerabilities in the special lightweight protocols of IoT devices, such as MQTT and CoAP. Many studies proposed IDS solutions based on ML models for IoT, but as these models were not trained on IoT datasets, they produced inaccurate results [18]. Furthermore, existing ML-based IDS sought to detect standalone attacks, such as SQL injection, DoS, ransomware, XSS, etc [1, 12-13, 16]. Unlike these models, the scope of IP-IDS involved designing a comprehensive IDS that detects many types of intrusions in different application layer

protocols, based on ML and trained on IoT-specific datasets. This study used IoT-dedicated datasets, such as MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 [19], CoAP-DDoS [20], and Bot-IoT [21]. The key contributions of this study are:

- Different ML/DL models for each of the specified IoT protocols are created: MQTT, CoAP, and HTTP.
- The models are trained and tested using specific IoT datasets.
- The proposed models are compared with the existing solutions.
- The best models in terms of performance are deployed in one comprehensive IDS.

II. THE PROPOSED IDS

A. Architecture of IP-IDS

This study proposes a new comprehensive IDS based on ML to accurately detect attacks on MQTT, CoAP, and HTTP using dedicated IoT datasets. As shown in Figure 1, the proposed IP-IDS consists of 3 main components: traffic collection, traffic analysis, and reporting. The traffic collection module is responsible for sniffing traffic flowing in the network and saving it in .pcap files. Traffic is then classified according to the application layer protocol into three classes, MQTT, CoAP, and HTTP, stored in separate files. Afterward, collected and classified traffic is fed into the analysis model to detect potential intrusions. For each application layer protocol, a different ML model was used to detect vulnerabilities related to this protocol. Each model classifies the traffic to determine whether it is normal (benign) or abnormal (attack) traffic and specifies the attack type. Once an attack is detected, a notification is sent to the administrator through a dashboard.

Fig. 1. Components of the IP-IDS.

B. Methodology

The development of IP-IDS was divided into four phases: Data collection, data preprocessing, modeling, and testing.

1) Datasets

Three datasets were used to train the ML/DL: MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 [19], CoAP-DDoS [20], and Bot-IoT [21]. Each one contains records specific to an application protocol and attacks that rely on it. The MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 dataset was created using a simulated sensor network that mimicked a real MQTT IoT network in a typical operating environment and contains both general networking scanning and MQTT brute-force attacks. The dataset is available in two formats: processed features and its original raw capture format (.pcap files). Characteristics are divided into three categories, i.e. bidirectional, packet-based, and unidirectional, and each set of features is used exclusively. Five scenarios make up the dataset. The first is for regular operation, and the other four are for attacks: aggressive scan, User Datagram Protocol (UDP) scan, Sparta SSH brute-force attack, and MQTT brute-force attack [19]. The second dataset was the CoAP-DDoS, which is used to classify DoS attacks on CoAP against IoT devices. It has 17 features per DoS attack, i.e. IP source, timestamp, ethernet type, and IP version. The dataset contains a total of 661,304 records that correspond to benign and malicious traffic [20]. The third dataset was the Bot-IoT, which is an IoT-dedicated dataset that includes both typical IoT-related and other network traffic, as well as numerous attack traffic types frequently launched by botnets. This dataset is labeled and collected from a realistic testbed. The label features an attack flow, an attack category, and an attack subcategory for multiclass classification use. The Bot-IoT dataset consists of 74 CSV files with more than 72,000,000 records, each with 46 features. The dataset contains 10 different types of attacks, including OS fingerprinting, DoS (HTTP, TCP, UDP), DDoS (HTTP, TCP, UDP), service scan, keylogging, and data theft [21].

2) Data Preprocessing

The Google Colaboratory Pro platform was used for implementation and experiments. The following libraries were used in the preprocessing of the datasets:

- Numby is a Python library that is used to perform a wide range of mathematical operations on arrays. It enhances Python with strong data structures that ensure effective calculations with arrays and matrices.
- Pandas is a Python library that is used in tasks related to ML and data science. It is built on top of Numpy, which supports multidimensional arrays.
- Os is a Python library that provides many functions to interact with the operating system.

The MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 dataset consists of five recorded scenarios: one normal operation and four attack scenarios (brute force, scan_a, scan_su, Sparta). Five CSV files were created, one for each class. In the four attack classes, any records that have a value of zero in the *is_attack* feature (label) were dropped. Then the five classes were concatenated into one

CSV file and a column named class was added to label the records [9]. The dataset is not balanced, as most records correspond to the normal class, which has a total of 86,008 records, while the minority class has 14,116 records. However, the data imbalance negatively impacts the performance of the ML models. So, a resampling technique was applied, which resulted in a balanced dataset where each class had 30000 records. The sklearn.utils library was used to generate a random resampling from the dataset.

Feature selection can be used to minimize the generalization error and the complexity of ML models. This is a process that selects the most important features to improve computational efficiency. It is applied when there are redundant or irrelevant features, and is also known as feature dimensionality reduction [22]. This study used the RF feature selection model [22], which is characterized by better generalization and interpretation and high accuracy. Each feature is assigned an importance score according to how significant it is in predicting the class. Then, only the features that have an importance score above zero are kept. In this dataset, three features were dropped (*fwd_num_rst_flags*, *fwd_num_urg_flags*, and *bwd_num_urg_flags*), because their importance score was zero. Therefore, only 29 of 32 features were considered in the training and testing processes.

The CoAP-DDoS dataset consists of 624,938 records, of which 39.47% correspond to malicious records. The dataset is divided into time-based subsections. A subsection is considered malicious if it includes more than 350 packets exchanged between the two malicious IP addresses (192.168.1.12) and (92.168.1.5). Forty-two features were extracted from the packets and were then reduced to 16. The arrays of packets that carried the flows were asymmetrical to each other and padded to ensure that all labeled data had a consistent shape. The array of all packet values in each packet flow was also normalized using the Frobenius norm. Training and testing data were shuffled after splitting.

As the Bot-IoT dataset is imbalanced, it will be biased towards the majority class in the obtained results. The DDoS, which is the majority class, has 1,926,624 records. The theft, which is the minority class, has only 79 records. Similarly, there is a huge gap between the total number of records corresponding to malicious traffic (≥ 3.5 million records), while the benign class has only 477 records. Using the *resample* function from the sklearn.utils library, the dataset categories were resampled to 30,000 records for each to overcome the bias problem. Other data preprocessing techniques that were applied to this dataset were One-Hot Encoding, IP address cleaning, and Normalization. One-Hot Encoding was used to convert category, subcategory, and proto features into numerical dummy features. IP address cleaning was required to convert the string IP address from the form 192.168.100.7 to an integer number such as 1.144249e-35 using the *clean_ip* function from the "dataprep.clean" library. In addition, normalization was used to transform all values on a similar scale, which could improve the model's performance and training stability. Similarly to the MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 dataset, a feature selection was applied using the RF classifier to reduce the dimensionality of the Bot-IoT dataset.

Consequently, the *saddr_clean*, *proto_arp*, *daddr_clean*, and *proto_ipv6-ICMP* features were dropped due to their importance score being zero. Therefore, only 26 of 30 features were used in the training and testing processes.

3) Modeling

ML is a branch of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that focuses on giving systems the capacity to automatically learn and improve from experience and collected data [23]. DL is a type of ML that enables computers to learn by analyzing patterns through multiple layers of processing. DL algorithms are taught using huge volumes of labeled data and neural network topologies that learn features directly from data, enabling computers to perform better object detection [24]. To design IP-IDS, a model was needed to scan the traffic (input) and decide whether it is benign or malicious. In case of malicious traffic, the model should be able to accurately classify the attacks. DT and LSTM were trained using the above datasets to select the appropriate model to be deployed. DT and LSTM are two of the most widely used algorithms in intrusion detection [1]. DT is one of the most used supervised ML techniques that is applied to a provided dataset for both classification and regression, by organizing a series of rules in a tree structure. The model is organized like a typical tree, with nodes, branches, and leaves, and a feature is represented by each node. Each leaf indicates a potential result or class label, whereas a decision or a rule is represented by a branch. The DT algorithm automatically chooses the best features before performing pruning to remove unnecessary branches from the tree to prevent overfitting [7]. LSTM is a DL algorithm designed to overcome the long-term dependence issue. The primary characteristic of LSTM is its ability to store data or cell state for future use in the network. This attribute is useful for performing analysis on temporal data that change over time [1, 25].

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

The MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 dataset was divided into 80% for training and 20% for testing. The Bot-IoT and CoAP-DDoS datasets were divided into 75% for training and 25% for testing. The LSTM model was implemented using the Tensorflow and Keras packages. The ADAM optimizer was used to optimize the categorical cross-entropy loss function in the case of multiclassification, and binary cross-entropy in the case of binary classification. For CoAP-DDoS, *sigmoid* and *tanh* were used as activation functions since this is a binary classification problem, and *sparse_categorical_crossentropy* as a loss function. The model was trained for 60 epochs. For MQTT and Bot-IoT, *softmax* was used as the activation function because it is a multiclassification problem. The LSTM output was equal to 100 and the number of epochs was set to 150. The loss function was the categorical cross-entropy for both datasets since the predicted labels are one-hot encoded.

B. Results

Figure 2 shows the average accuracy of DT and LSTM for the three datasets. Accuracy describes to which extent the

model is exact in detecting a class among all classes, calculated as follows:

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Correctly classified input}}{\text{Total number of inputs}}$$

Figure 2 shows that DT performed better in terms of accuracy for all datasets compared to LSTM. Additionally, LSTM and DT had close accuracy for Bot-IoT and MQTT-IoT-IDS (approximately 99.99%). This high accuracy was due to the balance of the datasets and the feature selection technique used. Accuracy is affected by an uncertainty factor that relies on the unbalance of the dataset. The confusion matrix of LSTM in the MQTT-IoT-IDS dataset portrayed in Figure 3 shows that there is a small rate of false positives.

Fig. 2. Accuracy of LSTM and DT for the three datasets.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix of LSTM in MQTT-IoT-IDS.

Another factor that is important in the evaluation of the model is its precision. The precision is calculated as the ratio of positive samples correctly identified to the total number of positive samples classified:

$$Precision = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

The recall is calculated as the ratio of true positives to the number of the overall relevant elements:

$$Recall = \frac{True\ Positives}{True\ Positives + False\ Negatives}$$

The F1-score aims to combine the precision and recall metrics into one metric [7] as follows:

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

The results shown in Table I confirm the high performance of the DT and LSTM models, which is due to the well-preprocessed data. However, LSTM did not perform well with the CoAP dataset due to the small number of records. Taking this into account, it was deduced that LSTM performs better with large datasets. Additionally, these results indicate that a well-tuned ML model, such as DT, trained on a clean and balanced dataset competes in terms of performance DL models. More importantly, ML models consume fewer resources and require less training and testing time compared to DL. In particular, during the training of the proposed models, DT needed only around 10 s in the training phase using the three considered datasets, while LSTM needed approximately 55 s on the CoAP-DoS. Consequently, the DT model seems to be more suitable for IoT environments where devices are resource-constrained in terms of energy and computation capabilities. Table II shows the average accuracy of many ML and DL models aiming to detect intrusions in IoT environments.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE OF THE PROPOSED MODELS

	Dataset	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
DT	MQTT-IoT-IDS	99.99	99.99	99.99
LSTM		99.995	99.995	99.995
DT	BoT-IoT	99.99	99.99	99.99
LSTM		100	100	100
DT	CoAP-DDoS	100	100	100
LSTM		67.43	51.41	100

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED AND EXISTING MODELS ON THE SAME DATASETS

Model	Dataset	Model	Average Accuracy
[24]	MQTT-IoT-IDS	DT	99.92
Proposed DT Model			99.99
[8]		DNN	99.753
Proposed LSTM Model		LSTM	99.995
[26]	BoT-IoT	Fine DT	97.43
Proposed DT Model		DT	99.99
[20]		LSTM	99.74
Proposed LSTM Model		LSTM	99.999
[21]	CoAP-DoS		99.76
Proposed DT model		DT	100
[21]			99.62
Proposed LSTM model		LSTM	99.92

For MQTT-IoT-IDS, it is obvious that LSTM reached the highest accuracy of 99.995% compared to the DT models proposed in [19, 26] as well as the proposed DL model. The training and testing times of the proposed method were 136 and 14 s, which are among the average computation times of

similar models [8]. Additionally, LSTM outperformed the DNN model proposed in [8]. The proposed LSTM performed better than the models proposed in [15] and Bi-LSTM [27], all trained on the BoT-IoT dataset. However, there is a huge difference between the proposed DT and the models in [28-29], again trained on BoT-IoT. However, DT has the highest accuracy for the CoAP dataset compared to DT and LSTM proposed in [20]. Figure 4 shows the loss function of LSTM for testing and training. The results show that the training and testing accuracies converge with each other, starting from epoch 20 for LSTM-CoAP, epoch 10 for LSTM-MQTT, and approximately epoch 10 for LSTM-BoT. The fluctuation of the loss function for CoAP is due to the small size of the dataset.

Fig. 4. Loss functions: (a) LSTM-CoAP, (b) LSTM-BoT, and (c) LSTM-MQTT.

C. Deployment of the Models

The following models were deployed in the proposed IP-IDS: LSTM trained on MQTT-IoT-IDS and Bot-IoT datasets, and DT trained on the CoAP-DoS dataset. IP-IDS consists of a three-tier web application: user interface, application server, and database server. At first, the user interface represents a dashboard for the administrator to show the queue of alerts and their status (handled or not), their origin, the timestamp, etc. The application server hosts the proposed ML models and

many other classes responsible for filtering the traffic and classifying it according to the application layer protocol. The database server will be used to store the traffic collected from the network. The Flask web application framework [30] will be used to implement IP-IDS and deploy the ML models, as it provides a panoply of modules that make it easy to develop applications with many details related to protocols and thread management.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a new IDS for IoT based on ML, called IP-IDS, that can detect MQTT, HTTP, and CoAP-directed intrusions with high accuracy. Existing IDSs for the IoT suffer from many limitations. In particular, the existing models suppose that all IoT network traffic is HTTP, however, new application layer protocols are used today. Additionally, almost all existing models detect intrusions in a single application protocol. Hence, this study proposes a comprehensive IDS that detects intrusions that might threaten three application layer protocols. Furthermore, the Bot-IoT, MQTT-IoT-IDS2020, and CoAP-DDoS IoT-specific datasets were used to train and test the ML models. Two models were considered, DT and LSTM, each trained on the three datasets. The experimental results showed that applying the resample function, which provides balancing datasets and feature selection, on both the MQTT and Bot-IoT datasets allows the enhancement of the detection capabilities of the proposed models and improves their accuracy. The results showed that DT and LSTM in MQTT, Bot-IoT, and CoAP achieved excellent performance in terms of accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall. The proposed models also outperformed many existing ML/DL models, such as those proposed in [14-15, 27-29]. In future work, this research will focus on investigating the performance of IP-IDS using simulation in an IoT environment.

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Improved Interleaved Boost Converter with Soft-Switching: Analysis and Experimental Validation

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a novel interleaved boost converter for renewable energy applications. The two-phase interleaved boost converter was improved with lossless passive snubber cells to ensure the Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) condition. The ZVS condition is contributed by a resonant inductor, a resonant capacitor, and two diodes. The proposed converter was operated in continuous current mode on its primary side. The significant merits of this converter are reduced switching losses, better efficiency, and reduced input current ripples without auxiliary switches. The soft-switching ability of this converter is maintained under both light- and heavy-load conditions. This paper also presents the operating principles and design analysis of the proposed converter. Furthermore, a 50-320V prototype was operated at 250 W to validate the soft-switching operation and theoretical analysis, and the experimental results are presented.

Keywords-DC-DC converter; boost converter; interleaved converter; soft-switching; Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS)

I. INTRODUCTION

In contemporary power conversion systems, boost and Interleaved Boost Converters (IBCs) have gained widespread usage to elevate low-voltage inputs to desired output levels, commonly drawing energy from sources such as wind generator systems [1], DC microgrids [2], and batteries [3]. The tristate interleaved converter design [4] employs auxiliary switches alongside primary switches to alleviate the challenges associated with input current fluctuations and output voltage ripple. However, this converter relies on excessive auxiliary switches and is primarily suited for low-voltage applications.

In response to these limitations, a dual-Coupled Inductor (CI)-based IBC that incorporates a clamping capacitor was proposed in [5]. This innovation serves to reduce voltage stresses and improve overall efficiency. However, it is primarily recommended for low-power applications. Moreover, voltage multiplier cells have been integrated into high-gain converters [6-7] and IBCs [7-8] to achieve improved voltage conversion ratios. In a buck converter, switches are replaced with a resonant switch [9] and IBCs are assisted by a single auxiliary circuit without [10] and with CI [11-13], facilitating soft-switching operation at low power levels. The Zero Voltage Transition (ZVT) condition is achieved when the auxiliary switch operates at twice the converter's switching frequency. Similarly, CIs increase switched capacitor cells, and auxiliary circuits in IBC aim to achieve increased voltage gain and soft-switching operation [14]. However, the auxiliary switches experience elevated current stresses as a result of their higher switching frequency. Similarly, in [15], a large inductor and snubber capacitors were integrated into a conventional IBC to achieve soft-switching, i.e. ZVT condition. Continuing this approach, in [16], an auxiliary switch was used to achieve the ZVT condition. However, these systems typically operate at low voltage and low power levels.

In [17], a different strategy was proposed to achieve soft-switching conditions, involving an IBC with an auxiliary circuit and voltage multiplier cells, which improved overall gain and achieved the ZVT condition. However, this converter primarily functions at very low output power levels. To further improve overall gain, it is necessary to increase the number of windings in current transformers (CIs). Efforts to efficiently recycle leakage energy and operate at high output power levels have led to the utilization of supplementary passive lossless clamp circuits [18] and active clamp circuits [19]. In [20], an increased turns ratio of CIs was implemented to improve voltage gain, coupled with the achievement of Zero Current Switching (ZCS) through a Passive Lossless Clamp Circuit (PLCC) in IBC. This particular converter yielded reduced turn-off losses and an increased overall gain. Similarly, another PLCC-based IBC [21-25] attains ZVS during turn-off in addition to the aforementioned advantages. However, it should be noted that previous IBC designs have exhibited certain disadvantages, including a higher count of active devices, electromagnetic interference (EMI) resulting from increased CIs, complexity in the control circuitry, and operation primarily at low output power levels. To address these limitations comprehensively, this study introduces the novel Soft-Switched Interleaved Boost Converter (SSIBC) equipped with passive

auxiliary components: a resonant inductor, a resonant capacitor, and a diode. The proposed converter exhibits several advantages in comparison to the existing IBCs, such as:

- Fewer active and passive devices
- Operates at high power
- Reduces switching losses
- Reduces the voltage stresses in the switching devices.

These advantages make the proposed converter a significant technology with the potential to revolutionize various industries where efficient and high-power conversion is of paramount importance. Figure 1 shows the generalized organization of Renewable Energy Sources (RESs) with IBC, along with loads such as DC microgrids and Electric Vehicles (EVs). Although the source RESs voltage ranges from 12 V to 48 V, the IBC provides a desirable range of 200-500 V for the load.

Fig. 1. Generalized organization of RESs with an interleaved boost converter.

II. PROPOSED INTERLEAVED DC-DC CONVERTER

The conventional IBC shown in Figure 2 comprises two inductors (L_1 , L_2), two IGBTs (S_1 , S_2), and two diodes (D_1 , D_2). Figure 3 shows the proposed soft-switching IBC, extended with two passive lossless snubber cells. The passive lossless snubber comprises inductors L_a and L_b , capacitors C_a and C_b , and diodes D_a , D_b , D_c , and D_d . The proposed converter obtains ZVC conditions in their main IGBTs with the help of a passive snubber cell. The following assumptions were considered to describe the steady-state analysis of the proposed converter.

- All IGBTs and passive elements are ideal.
- Parasite circuit components are ignored.
- The size of the output capacitor is large enough to ignore any fluctuations in output voltage.
- Inductors L_1 and L_2 possess significant inductance and exhibit steady currents.

Figure 4 shows the key waveforms, illustrating the operating intervals from t_0 to t_8 . Figure 5 shows the equivalent current flow schematics for each interval. The operation of the converter is divided into 8 intervals.

Fig. 2. Conventional interleaved DC-DC converter.

Fig. 3. Proposed interleaved DC-DC converter.

Fig. 4. Key waveforms for the proposed converter.

The steady-state operation of the proposed converter is demonstrated for each interval.

- Interval (t_0-t_1) : At t_0 , IGBT S_1 is conducting, S_2 is turned off, and hence, output current flows through L_2-D_2 . At t_1 , the voltage across IGBT S_2 is increased to $2/3$ of V_o . The equations of L_1, L_2 and S_2 are:

$$i_{L1}(t) = i_{L1}(t_0) + \frac{1}{L_1} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} V_{in} dt \tag{1}$$

$$i_{L2}(t) = i_{L2}(t_0) - \frac{1}{L_2} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} (V_o - V_{in}) dt \tag{2}$$

$$V_{S2}(t) = \frac{1}{C_b} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} (i_{L2}(t) - I_o) dt \tag{3}$$

- Interval (t_1-t_2) : At t_1 , IGBT S_1 is still conducting and the voltage across IGBT S_2 starts reducing smoothly to reach zero at t_2 .

$$i_{L1}(t) = i_{L1}(t_1) + \frac{1}{L_1} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} V_{in} dt \tag{4}$$

$$i_{L2}(t) = i_{L2}(t_1) - \frac{1}{L_2} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (V_o - V_{in}) dt \tag{5}$$

$$V_{S2}(t) = V_o - V_{Cb}(t_1)(1 - \cos \omega_o(t - t_1)) \tag{6}$$

- Interval (t_2-t_3) : This is a short interval. At the beginning of the interval, the body diode of S_2 starts conducting and stops at t_3 . Hence, the ZVS condition is achieved for S_2 . The current expression of IGBT S_2 is as follows:

$$i_{S2}(t) = -(I_o - i_{L2}(t - t_2)) \tag{7}$$

- Interval (t_3-t_4) : At t_4 , the voltage across IGBT S_2 increases to V_{in} and reaches zero at t_4 . The load current continues to flow via L_2-D_2 .

$$i_{L1}(t) = i_{L1}(t_3) + \frac{1}{L_1} \int_{t_3}^{t_4} V_{in} dt \tag{8}$$

$$V_{S2}(t) = V_{in} \tag{9}$$

- Interval (t_4-t_5) : At the instant t_4 , IGBT S_2 is turned on with ZVS condition and S_1 is still conducting. Throughout this interval, the energy is accumulated in inductors L_1 and L_2 via $V_{in}-L_1-S_1-L_2-S_2$.

$$i_{L1}(t) = i_{L1}(t_4) + \frac{1}{L_1} \int_{t_4}^{t_5} V_{in} dt \tag{10}$$

$$i_{L2}(t) = i_{L2}(t_4) + \frac{1}{L_1} \int_{t_4}^{t_5} V_{in} dt \tag{11}$$

- Interval (t_5-t_6) : At t_5 , S_1 is turned-off, therefore the output current flows through $L_1-D_1-R_o$. At t_6 , the voltage across S_1 reaches $2/3$ of V_o .

$$V_{S1}(t) = \frac{1}{C_a} \int_{t_5}^t (i_{L1}(t) - I_o) dt \tag{12}$$

where $t_5 < t < t_6$

$$i_{L2}(t) = i_{L2}(t_5) + \frac{1}{L_1} \int_{t_5}^t V_{in} dt \tag{13}$$

- Interval (t_6-t_7) : Throughout this interval, the voltage across S_1 starts decreasing and reaches zero at t_7 .

$$i_{L1}(t) = i_{L1}(t_6) - \frac{1}{L_1} \int_{t_6}^t (V_o - V_{in}) dt \tag{14}$$

$$i_{L2}(t) = i_{L1}(t_6) + \frac{1}{L_2} \int_{t_6}^{t_7} V_{in} dt \quad (15)$$

$$V_{S1}(t) = V_o - V_{Ca}(t_6)(1 - \cos \omega_o (t - t_1)) \quad (16)$$

- Interval (t_7-t_8) : At the beginning of this interval, the voltage across S_1 becomes zero and its body diode starts conducting. Therefore, a ZVS condition is obtained. During this interval, S_2 is conducting and energy accumulates in the inductor L_2 .

Fig. 5. Equivalent schematics: (a) Intervals (t_0-t_1) and (t_3-t_4) , (b) interval (t_1-t_2) , (c) interval (t_2-t_3) , (d) interval (t_4-t_5) , (e) interval (t_5-t_6) , (f) interval (t_6-t_7) , and (g) interval (t_7-t_8) .

III. DESIGN ANALYSIS

The IBC operation was divided into two distinct states to determine the input current ripples of the proposed converter. The first state occurs when S_1 is turned on, while the next is when both S_1 and S_2 are on.

- State 1: In this state, energy gets accumulated in the input inductor L_1 when only S_1 is turned on and the input current gets delivered to output through L_2 since S_2 is turned off. The input current is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{di_{in}}{dt} = \frac{V_{in}}{L} + \frac{V_{in}-V_o}{L} \quad (17)$$

- State 2: In this region, the switching devices S_1 and S_2 are both turned on and energy is accumulated in both the inductors L_1 and L_2 . The input current is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{di_{in}}{dt} = \frac{V_{in}}{L} + \frac{V_{in}}{L} \quad (18)$$

The average value of the output voltage V_o is expressed as follows:

$$V_o = \frac{V_{in}}{1-D} \quad (19)$$

$$V_{in} = V_o(1 - D) \quad (20)$$

By substituting (19) in (17) and (18), the input current can be expressed as:

$$\frac{di_{in}}{dt} = \frac{V_o}{L}(1 - 2D) \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{di_{in}}{dt} = \frac{V_o}{L}(2 - 2D) \quad (22)$$

Input current ripple is defined by (23) for two operating regions; The first is when only one IGBT is turned on ($0 \leq D \leq \frac{1}{2}$) and the second is when both the IGBTs are conducting ($\frac{1}{2} \leq D \leq 1$).

$$\Delta i_{in} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{V_o}{L}(1 - 2D)DT_s; 0 \leq D \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{V_o}{L}(2 - 2D)\left(D - \frac{1}{2}\right)T_s; \frac{1}{2} \leq D \leq 1 \end{array} \right\} \quad (23)$$

The input current ripple is expressed as:

$$\Delta i_{in} = \frac{V_o}{L}(2 - 2D)\left(D - \frac{1}{2}\right)T_s \quad (24)$$

The overall voltage gain of the converter is defined by:

$$M = \frac{V_o}{V_{in}} \quad (25)$$

The input and output currents of the converter are expressed as:

$$i_{in} = i_o M \quad (26)$$

$$i_o = \frac{M}{Q} \quad (27)$$

where $Q = \frac{R_o}{Z_o}$ and characteristic impedance $Z_o = \sqrt{\frac{L_a}{C_a}}$.

$$i_{in} = \frac{M^2}{Q} \quad (28)$$

The output resistance R_o is selected by satisfying the following condition:

$$R_o \geq \frac{V_{in}}{(1-D)i_o} \quad (29)$$

The values of resonant elements L_a , C_a , L_b , and C_b are selected by taking the Q factor equal to 3 and characteristic impedance Z_o . The input inductance values of L_1 and L_2 are chosen by the following condition:

$$L \leq \frac{V_{in}D}{\Delta i_{pv}f_s} \quad (30)$$

The output filter capacitance C_o is taken from:

$$C_o = \frac{DV_o}{R_o \Delta V_o f_s} \quad (31)$$

The maximum values of the voltage stress of the IGBT and the current stress of input inductors are determined by the following expressions:

$$V_{igbt} = V_{in} \left(\frac{M^2}{Q} \right) \quad (32)$$

$$i_{Lmax} = \frac{V_{in} \left(\frac{M^2}{Q} \right)}{Z_o} \quad (33)$$

IV. SIMULATION ANALYSIS AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The PLECS software tool was used to design and simulate the proposed soft-switched IBC. The following values were used as simulation parameters: input voltage: 50 V, switching frequency: 40 kHz, output voltage: 320 V, inductors $L_1, L_2 = 100 \mu\text{H}$, resonant inductors $L_a, L_b = 1.5 \mu\text{H}$, resonant capacitors, $C_a, C_b = 2 \text{ nF}$, and output capacitor $C_o = 470 \mu\text{F}$. Figure 6 shows the voltage and current waveforms of the S_1 and S_2 IGBTs. According to the waveforms obtained, the voltages of the IGBTs reach zero smoothly, therefore, the ZVS condition is achieved without any additional voltage and current stresses.

Fig. 6. Simulated waveforms: (a) V_{S1} , (b) i_{S1} , (c) V_{S2} , and (d) i_{S2} .

Figure 7 shows V_{Ca} and V_{Cb} . The waveforms obtained from the C_a and C_b resonant capacitors confirm that they are charged to the output voltage of $2/3$ of V_o and discharge completely. Figure 8 shows the current through the resonant inductors L_a and L_b .

A 250 W prototype was built to validate the theoretical analysis. Table I shows the design parameters. The developed prototype was tested with a voltage of 50 V as input to get a 320 V output. The duty ratio was 0.85 and 0.6 for S_1 and S_2 , respectively. The overall gain of the converter, while operating

at 50 V input voltage and obtaining an output voltage of 320 V, was approximately 6. The PWM signals were generated with the help of a Texas Instruments TMSF28335 module. The proposed converter operated at a switching frequency of 40 kHz. Infineon IHW25N120 IGBTs S_1 and S_2 were used, having 25 A maximum rated current with 1200 V maximum rated voltage. Two FKP2011150 capacitors were connected in parallel to obtain a capacitance of 2 nF.

Fig. 7. Simulated waveforms of V_{Ca} and V_{Cb} .

Fig. 8. Simulated waveforms of I_{La} and I_{Lb} .

TABLE I. LABORATORY PROTOTYPE PARAMETERS

Parameters	Symbol	Value
Input voltage	V_{in}	50 V
Output voltage	V_o	320 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	40 kHz
Output power	P_o	250 W
Inductors	L_1, L_2	100 μ H
Resonant inductors	L_a, L_b	1.5 μ H
Resonant capacitors	C_a, C_b	2 nF
IGBTs	S_1, S_2	IHW25N120
Diodes	$D_1, D_2, D_a, D_b, D_c, D_d$	C6D06065A

Figure 9 shows the collector-emitter voltage and collector currents of the S_1 and S_2 IGBTs. The proposed converter operates at a 50 V input voltage to produce a 320 V output voltage at a 400 Ω load resistance. The voltage stresses of the IGBTs are observed to be near 230 V, which is lower than the output voltage. The waveforms obtained validate the theoretical analysis, and the S_1 and S_2 IGBTs are turned on with the ZVS condition. When the converter operated at 30 V input voltage, it obtained 260 V output with the same duty ratios. Figure 10 shows the collector-emitter voltage and collector currents of the S_1 and S_2 IGBTs. The obtained waveforms demonstrate the ZVS condition.

Fig. 9. Experimental waveforms for $V_m = 50$ V, $V_o = 320$ V. (top): V_{S1} : S_1 collector-emitter voltage, i_{S1} : collector current. (bottom): V_{S2} : S_2 collector-emitter voltage, i_{S2} : collector current (time scale: 10 μ s/div).

Fig. 10. Experimental waveforms for $V_m = 30$ V, $V_o = 250$ V. (top): V_{S1} : S_1 collector-emitter voltage, i_{S1} : collector current. (bottom): V_{S2} : S_2 collector-emitter voltage, i_{S2} : collector current (time scale: 5 μ s/div).

Figure 11 shows the voltage waveforms across the C_a and C_b resonant capacitors. It can be seen that the capacitors are charged up to the output voltage of 240 V and discharge smoothly. Figure 12 depicts the current flowing through the L_a and L_b inductors. The maximum current flowing through the inductors is 0.8 A, which is the output current. Figure 13 shows the turn-on transients of the main IGBTs, S_1 and S_2 . Without current or voltage stresses and lower dv/dt rates, the soft-switching condition, ZVS turn on, is achieved, when the converter is operated at 100 W output power.

All IGBTs achieve ZVS turn-on conditions without any additional current or voltage stresses. The converter has an overall gain higher than that of existing converters. The aforementioned qualities are more advantageous than those of the prior IBCs. Table II shows the comparison between the

proposed soft-switched and existing IBCs. The proposed converter uses fewer auxiliary devices, experiences fewer turn-on losses, and achieves 97% efficiency at 250 W output power.

Fig. 11. Experimental waveforms. V_{ca} : C_a capacitor voltage (bottom), V_{cb} : C_b capacitor voltage (time scale: 10 μ s/div).

Fig. 12. Experimental waveforms. V_{ca} : C_a capacitor voltage (bottom), V_{cb} : C_b capacitor voltage (time scale: 10 μ s/div).

Fig. 13. Experimental waveforms. (top): V_{S1} : S_1 collector-emitter voltage, i_{S1} : Collector current, (bottom) V_{S2} : S_2 collector-emitter voltage, i_{S2} : collector current (time scale: 2 μ s/div).

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF EXISTING CONVERTERS

	NS	ND	NL	NC	NRL	NRC	V_{in}	V_o	TDC
[12]	5	5	8	8	1	No	46	850	27
[14]	3	5	2	1	1	3	24	42	15
[16]	4	2	1, 1*	1	No	2	200	400	10
[17]	3	6	2*	5	No	1	48	400	17
[25]	2	6	2	1	2	2	200	400	17
Proposed converter	2	6	2	1	2	2	50	320	16

NS: number of switches, ND: number of diodes; NL: number of inductors; NC: number of capacitors; NRL: number of resonant inductors; NRC: number of resonant capacitors; *Coupled inductor, TDC: Total device count V_{in} : Input voltage, V_o : Output voltage

Figure 14 shows the efficiency curves. The efficiency measured at the output power of 100 W was 94.5%, at 150 W was 94.8%, at 200 W was 96.3%, and at 250 W was 97%. When the converter operated at 250 W output power, the proposed IBC's maximum efficiency was 97%.

Fig. 14. Efficiency curve.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study presented a novel two-phase IBC with passive lossless snubber cells, describing its design and operating concepts. There are no additional losses involved in achieving the ZVS condition. Using a 300 W laboratory prototype and a 50 V input voltage, the experimental investigations yielded a maximum output voltage of 320 V. The soft-switching ability of the proposed converter was tested up to the 250 W output power level. A passive lossless snubber provides ZVS turn-on of the IGBTs and plays an important role in achieving 97% efficiency. Compared to existing converters, the number of devices, including auxiliary switches, is reduced, thus reducing the overall cost. This proposed converter is suitable for medium- and high-power applications.

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Superconducting Precursors in Bi/Pb Multiphase Cuprates Fabricated by the Solar Technology and their Comparative Study by Torque Magnetometry Methods

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ABSTRACT

A special method has been applied to synthesize HTSC samples of $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{(n-1)}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_y$ with increased local inhomogeneities, using solar energy for the melting and following superfast quenching of the melt (SFAQ-T technology). This study carried out a comparative analysis using low-frequency torsional vibration and resonant vibrating reed spectroscopy methods. The results showed a possibility for the existence of high-temperature superconducting precursors with $T_c = 107\text{-}138\text{ K}$ and the potential advantages of the application of the resonant vibrating reed method.

Keywords-solar radiation; solar technology; high-temperature superconducting ceramics (HTSC); nominals $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{(n-1)}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_y$; torque magnetometry

I. INTRODUCTION

Among the widely known applications of superconductors is for the production of renewable energy using the environmentally harmless solar and wind energy [1]. HTSC materials containing Bi are among the most promising since they experience the transition to the superconducting state at $T_c > 100\text{ K}$ (Bi/Pb 2223, $T_c = 107\text{ K}$), and have a high second critical magnetic field record $H_{c2} = 150\text{ T}$ [2-3] that is significantly higher than that of standard type II and all other high-temperature superconductors used in technology today. The properties of high-temperature superconducting ceramics are determined by the phase composition and textured structure, depending on their fabrication technology. In [4], a special technology was applied to synthesize HTSC samples with increased local inhomogeneities, called Solar Fast Alloy

Quenching Technology (SFAQ-T). Based on glass-crystal and X-ray amorphous precursors, the HTSC samples were synthesized by quenching a melt produced by the heating of precursors with solar radiation at low temperatures. In [5], decomposition-resistant textured superconducting samples of $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{(n-1)}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_{10-y}$ ($n = 3\text{-}5$) were fabricated with critical temperatures of the superconducting transitions $T_c = 107\text{-}138\text{ K}$.

Measurement methods are continuously being improved. To determine the critical temperatures of the superconducting (SC) transitions T_c of these samples obtained by this technology, the original torsional oscillation magnetometry method in applied magnetic fields was realized using an automated multipurpose device [6], which has a sensitivity comparable to that of a SQUID magnetometer. In [7-8], the

potential possibilities of the Vibrating Reed (VR) magnetometry method for similar purposes were also investigated. The nature of SC precursors in cuprates was the subject of several studies [9-12]. Different superconducting experimental methods have led to different conclusions on the temperature range of superconducting fluctuations. The main challenge was to separate the SC response from a complex into normal-state behavior. For this purpose, in [9], a torque magnetometry method was used, which is a unique thermodynamical probe with extremely high sensitivity to SC diamagnetism. In torque magnetometry, the magnetization M is deduced from the mechanical torque $\tau = M H \sin\alpha$, where α is the angle between M and H , experienced by a crystal in an external magnetic field H . The torque is measured as a function of temperature (T), magnetic field strength (H), and the orientation of the sample to the field direction. This approach completely removes normal-state contributions, allowing tracing the diamagnetic signal above T_c with great precision. The results show that the SC diamagnetism vanishes in an unusual universal manner, showing the possibility that this unusual behavior signifies the proliferation of SC clusters as a result of the intrinsic inhomogeneity, which is the inherent property of the cuprates.

These results are very significant for many reasons. First of all, they constitute an unequivocal thermodynamic probe for the emergence of superconducting precursors in the cuprates, as SC emergence is observed via diamagnetism, which is the fundamental and prominent characteristic of the SC, and because such an experimental approach does not resort to any background normal phase effects. As discussed in [9], one could understand the unusual emergence of SC precursors by noting that cuprates are lamellar and perovskite-derived materials that are intrinsically inhomogeneous at nanoscale distances. Evidence for inhomogeneity was observed in Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM) and nuclear magnetic resonance [9]. Consequently, some of the spatially inhomogeneous SC gaps "survive" in the form of the SC precursor clusters at temperatures well above T_c . As the temperature decreases, these SC precursor clusters proliferate and grow in size, and eventually percolate near T_c . The emergence of superconductivity could be understood as a percolation process with a temperature scale controlled by the distribution of the SC gaps rather than by T_c . Despite many methods, it has not yet been possible to synthesize long-term stable room-temperature Bi/Pb superconducting phases. The Bi/Pb phase with high $T_c = 197$ K was obtained at a pressure of 10^3 Torr, but it decomposed at atmospheric pressure [13]. The progressive results achieved in the synthesis of superconductors with increasing critical temperatures of the superconducting transition from 97 to 260 K [14-19] provided an optimistic basis for continuing the research for an unconventional way for the synthesis of Bi/Pb.

This study aimed to compare the high-temperature precursors in $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{(n-1)}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_y$ using two different methods of torque magnetometry to further substantiate their existence and assess the potential possibilities of the precision VR method for the evaluation of T_c of the high-temperature precursors in this multiphase system.

II. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In [5], SFAQ-T technology was used to obtain HTSC ceramics of $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{(n-1)}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_y$ series ($n = 3\div 5$) and study its properties. The technology to produce SC ceramics using solar energy included the synthesis of precursors and the subsequent production of ceramics from them. The synthesis of precursors was carried out in a melt under the influence of solar radiation with a density of $700\text{-}780$ W/cm², followed by rapid quenching of the melt. Ceramic samples were prepared using standard technology: grinding-pressing-annealing. The annealing of the ceramics was carried out in the range of $500\text{-}848^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 to 120 hours. To determine the phase composition of the samples, a diffractometer (DRON-UM1, Cu $K\alpha$ radiation, Ni filter) and a microscope (NU-2/E, Carl Zeiss Jena, Germany) were used. To determine the critical temperatures of the superconducting transition T_c of these samples, the original vibrating torsional magnetometry method was used to study the torsion oscillations of samples in an applied magnetic field, realized using an automated multipurpose device [6] having a sensitivity comparable to that of a SQUID magnetometer. The appearance of pinned vortices produces a non-zero magnetic moment M in the sample. The interaction between M and H creates a torque. This additional torque affects the oscillating system and makes the dissipation and frequency of the oscillations dependent on the external magnetic field. A unique feature of this method is also the synchronous measurements of two physical quantities, frequency and dissipation. The sensitivity of this method was very high at 10^{-17} W.

Torsion instrumentation is especially sensitive to the existence of superconducting precursors at temperatures $T > T_c$ of the materials under study in external magnetic fields [6, 9]. This approach completely removes normal-state contributions and thus allows one to trace the diamagnetic signal above T_c with great precision. The effect of superconducting precursors is particularly seen in high magnetic fields. Previous measurements of pinning and dissipation processes were carried out with the help of a low-frequency axial-torsion magnetometer and standard methods of magnetic and electric parameter measurements. These measurements showed that the samples obtained using this technology were multiphase, containing SC precursor phases with higher critical temperatures T_c reaching 138 K [6]. However, the concentration of new HTSC phases was so small that, for more precision assessments, a more sensitive method was necessary. Such a method could be the Vibrating Reed (VR) method presented in [7]. As the frequency and dissipation of VR could be measured with high precision, the VR method exceeds in sensitivity a conventional ac-susceptometer. Using the VR method, one could study the elastic coupling between the Abrikosov vortex lattice and the crystal lattice, even in the micrometer-sized grains inserted in the normal matrix. Field dependence measurements of VR resonance frequency and dissipation could be used for the precision investigation of the first critical magnetic field H_{c1} temperature dependence without the introduction of free parameters, along with the energy dissipation character caused by the motion of the Abrikosov vortex lattice. In [20], a successful application of the VR method was presented for the investigation of two-phase Bi-

Ca-Sr-Cu-O superconducting ceramics and the precision assessment of their T_c .

One of the purposes of this study was to assess the potential possibilities of the VR precision method to evaluate the T_c of high-temperature precursors in multiphase HTSC samples of $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{(n-1)}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_y$ produced by SFAQ-T.

Consider using the example of $n = 3-5$. The formation of SC phases of samples depends on the temperature and time conditions. After annealing at 500-600°C for 3 hours, a low-temperature superconducting phase 2201 was formed. When annealing at 700°C for 3 hours, the formation of about 50% of the 2212 phase ($T_c = 97$ K) and the appearance of faint traces of the high-temperature superconducting phase 2223 ($T_c = 107$ K) were established. More than 90% of the HTSC phase 2223 was obtained after annealing in the 848-850°C range for 90 to 120 hours. The difference in the phase composition of SC ceramics obtained from glassy-crystalline precursors is the formation of homologous SC phases, as evidenced by a series of reflections in diffraction patterns at 2θ , corresponding to certain hkl . This effect of the manifestation of a series of reflections was not observed in ceramics synthesized by the method of solid-phase reactions. This feature of ceramics made from glassy-crystalline precursors synthesized using solar technology can be explained by "freezing" the melt by quenching and the crystallization during heat treatment of supersaturated solid solutions. With the increasing duration of heat treatment, as a result of diffusion processes, the number of HTSC phase homologs decreased and the intensity of the reflection, which corresponded to the most stable phase at a given temperature, increased. The unit cell parameters of the homolog phases of type 2223 changed in the following intervals: for a sample of the nominal value $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_y$ $a = 5.2832 \div 5.3539$ Å, $b = 5.3698 \div 5.5075$ Å, $c = 36.506 \div 37.3855$ Å, for a sample of the nominal $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_3\text{Cu}_4\text{O}_y$ $a = 5.0545 \div 5.1226$ Å, $b = 5.6696 \div 5.8918$ Å, $c = 36.4798 \div 37.2383$ Å. The degree of texture of the ceramics obtained at 817 °C for 65 hours, shown in Figure 1(a), and at 820 °C for 120 hours, shown in Figure 1(b), was evaluated according to the Lotgering factor [21]. The texture was assessed for reflections [0010], [0012], and [0014] using the Lotgering formula $F = (I_a - I_b)/I_a \cdot 100\%$, where I_a and I_b are the intensity of the selected reflection according to Figure 1. For the HTSC ceramics of the nominal $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_4\text{Cu}_5\text{O}_y$, the following values were determined: $F = 73\%$, $F = 65\%$, and $F = 64\%$ by reflections [0010], [0012], and [0014], respectively. These results showed an increase in the degree of texture (00L) with increasing temperature and duration of heat treatment.

A study of the superconducting properties of HTSC ceramics of this system by the low-frequency axial-torsion magnetometry method showed that along with the manifested effects that determine the transition to the superconducting state at 107 and 138 K, numerous "bursts" ("chaos" regions) were identified, which were not observed in samples synthesized by the solid-phase reaction method. "Bursts" can refer to homologous phases that appear in diffraction patterns as a series of reflections, or these effects refer to physical phenomena associated with electronic states caused by the action of a concentrated light flux [22]. In the subgroup of

compounds 2256-2289, the phase composition was similar to the subgroup 2223-2234 [23], and for the 221920 sample it looks as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Diffraction patterns of textured superconducting ceramics with the nominal composition $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_y$, obtained from precursors synthesized in a solar oven: (a) at 817 °C for 65 hours, and (b) at 820 °C for 120 hours.

Fig. 2. Diffraction pattern of a precursor with the nominal composition $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{19}\text{Cu}_{20}\text{O}_y$, obtained by improved SFAQ-T: (a)-precursor (2201), (b) after annealing at 847 °C for 24 hours (x - phase 221920).

Figure 3 shows the form of the microstructure of the annealed ceramics of this type of Bi/Pb (221920) composition.

Fig. 3. Microstructure of HTSC ceramics of nominal composition $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{19}\text{Cu}_{20}\text{O}_y$ obtained from precursors synthesized using solar technology.

Ceramic HTSC samples had a compressive strength limit of 12-14 MPa. The phase composition and superconducting effects of 2245 HTSC ceramics [23] were reproduced after aging the samples for 7 years. A direct relationship was identified between the growth in the critical temperature of the transition to the superconducting state and the value of n , which allowed the assumption of the existence of HTSC with T_c over 107 K [23].

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of the logarithmic damping decrement δ and the period t of oscillation in the magnetic field of the ceramic sample of the nominal $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_3\text{Cu}_4\text{O}_y$, obtained from precursor synthesized using solar technology (zero field-cooled ZFC-mode): s -state and n -state are superconducting and normal states, respectively.

The $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{19}\text{Cu}_{20}\text{O}_y$ system was chosen for the following comparative study. Compared to the similar dependence for the single-phase sample $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_y$, Figure 5 shows the absence of features corresponding to SC precursors, and Figure 6 shows the temperature dependence of critical parameters for SC precursors in the $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{19}\text{Cu}_{20}\text{O}_y$ sample.

The electronic part of the VR acoustic spectrometer contains an acoustic spectrometer operating at a frequency of approximately 1 kHz and instruments for powering a permanent magnet. The sensitivity of the spectrometer provides

measurements of the natural frequency of the sample f with an accuracy of approximately 0.1%. In the VR acoustic spectrometer, the electrostatic method of exciting bending oscillations of a sample having the shape of a rectangular plate was used. The electronic equipment of the spectrometer allows measurements in the mode of self-excitation of samples at their natural resonant frequencies. The electrode, located in the immediate vicinity of a sample, comprises the capacitance included in the oscillating circuit of the high-frequency generator and serves simultaneously to excite and detect oscillations of a sample. Measurements of the resonant frequencies f_r of the sample oscillations make it possible to determine the elastic modulus E according to the relation:

$$f_r = k \frac{d}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}}$$

where d is the thickness of the sample, L is the length of the oscillating plate, E is the modulus of elasticity, ρ is the density of the sample, and k is a constant factor.

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of the logarithmic damping decrement δ and the period t of oscillation in the magnetic field of ceramic samples of the nominal $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_y$, obtained from precursors synthesized using solar technology.

Fig. 6. Temperature dependence of the logarithmic damping decrement δ and the period t of oscillation in the magnetic field of a ceramic sample of the nominal $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{19}\text{Cu}_{20}\text{O}_y$, obtained from precursors synthesized using solar technology.

The variation of the square of the resonant oscillation frequency (f^2) of a sample can be considered in the framework of the so-called magneto-mechanical approach [7], according to which when a superconducting sample is displaced relative to the external magnetic field H , a restoring mechanical force acts on each "pinned" magnetic vortex. As a result, the oscillation frequency of the entire sample changes by $\Delta f(H)$, depending on the density of the fixed vortices, the moment of inertia of the superconductor, and its volume. The dependence of the elastic modulus E of the substrate-sample system (in units of f^2) on the magnitude of the magnetic field gives information on the elastic interaction of the Abrikosov vortex lattice with the crystal lattice. This is a convenient method for determining the magnitude of the vortex pinning force. In addition, the $f^2(H)$ dependence provides a simple method for determining the lower critical magnetic field H_{c1} value and the critical temperatures of the superconducting precursors in the multiphase HTSC samples. Figure 7 shows the measured temperature dependences of the square of the natural frequency (f^2) of oscillations of the Bi/Pb system (2-2-8-9) and (2-2-19-20) samples in a magnetic field. Measurements were carried out in Zero Field Cooled mode (ZFC-mode) in the magnetic field 300 mT, turned on after the cooling of a sample to 80 K.

Fig. 7. Temperature dependence of the square of the natural frequencies of the multiphase samples (2-2-19-20) and (2-2-8-9) in a magnetic field of 300 mT.

In the area of ~90-160 K in the samples (2-2-8-9) and (2-2-19-20), there are features near temperatures of 95, 101, 115, 128, and 141 K, which are associated with the existing superconducting high-temperature precursors in the multiphase samples of $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{n-1}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_y$ system, which are absent in case of a single-phase sample (2-2-2-3) synthesized by solid-phase technology. Thus, it can be concluded that in samples (2-2-8-9) and (2-2-19-20), there are four different SC precursor phases. When comparing the features in Figures 6 and 7, it can be seen that they are in a definite correspondence, but in the case of Figure 7, these features are better separated. This observation can be considered as another confirmation by the VR magnetometry method of the existence of high-temperature precursors in multiphase samples of $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{(n-1)}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_y$ and, in addition to it, shows the potential advantages of applying the VR method to study the superconducting precursors in multiphase HTSC samples.

III. CONCLUSION

In torsional low-frequency and vibrating reed dynamic experiments to investigate the magnetic properties of multiphase cuprate superconductors $\text{Bi}_{1.7}\text{Pb}_{0.3}\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{n-1}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_y$ ($n=3-5, 20$) synthesized using SFAQ-T technology, precursor phases were detected near $T_c=107-160$. Analysis of the nature of the obtained dependences and their comparison with other available results associated with the processes in the vicinity of critical temperature T_c allows inferring the existence of high-temperature superconducting precursor phases. The comparative study of torsional and vibrating reed magnetometries for the evaluation of T_c of the superconducting precursors in the multiphase HTSC Bi-Pb-Sr-Cu-O system fabricated by the SFAQ-T technology was investigated for the first time. The results obtained by both methods were shown to have sensitivity to superconducting diamagnetism, allowing the discovery of new superconducting precursor phases above bulk T_c in these samples. In addition, compared with the low-frequency torsional spectroscopy method, the vibrating reed spectroscopy method has potential advantages for the study of the superconducting precursors in multiphase HTSC ceramics.

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An Innovative Approach to Cardiovascular Disease Prediction: A Hybrid Deep Learning Model

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ABSTRACT

The increasing prevalence of cardiovascular disorders has created an imperative need for accurate diagnoses. Despite the emergence of numerous techniques for disease classification and secure data transmission, a prevailing shortcoming is the lack of precision in decision-making. This study aimed to address this critical issue by introducing an innovative disease prediction model that uses a hybrid classifier. The proposed hybrid classifier combined deep Bidirectional Long-Short-Term Memory (deep Bi LSTM) and deep Convolutional Neural Network (deep CNN). To further improve its performance, the proposed approach employed hybridized swarm optimization to fine-tune fusion parameters and optimize the learning model for enhanced accuracy. This study focused on heart disease as its central concern, strengthening data security through the implementation of Diffi-Huffman based on Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) during data transmission. The resulting automatic disease prediction model adopted the hybrid deep classifier, which was born from the amalgamation of two components: the interactive hunt-deep CNN classifier and the WoM-deep Bi LSTM. The proposed hybrid learning model achieved impressive accuracy, F-measure, sensitivity, and specificity of 97.716%, 97.848%, 98.021%, and 97.807%, respectively, marking a significant advance in the realm of cardiovascular disease prediction.

Keywords-cardiovascular disease prediction; elliptic curve cryptography; interactive hunt-deep CNN; WoM-deep bi LSTM; Diffi-Huffman

I. INTRODUCTION

Data gathering and storage have been digitalized on a large scale because of recent advances in information science, using tools such as mobile devices, laptops, satellite reports, and so on for data collection. These data include private personal information such as medical records and others [1]. When patients seek treatment in different facilities, reliable and prompt medical precaution facilities are provided at any time through the exchange of electronic health records without redundancy [2]. The Internet of Things (IoT) plays an important role in helping physicians [3-4]. The IoT may virtually connect people and objects in the age of the fast Internet to exchange information. IoT devices are integrated

into several web applications for data collection. It is crucial for real-time health observation systems that the network remains mobile and offers efficient client-server communication. As a result, it is essential to keep track of individual sensor information in the web-based control system [5-6]. In addition, IoT and cloud computing technology are interdependent and have become beneficial areas for remotely managing the patient's condition to provide ongoing facilities by providing helpful information to patients and clinicians [7]. Many services use cloud solutions and machine learning algorithms to keep and process patient data [8-11]. In [2], a multi-objective successive approximation (EMSA) technique was introduced to maintain an adequate measure of privacy in healthcare clouds based on Euclidean L3P. In many cases, Wireless Personal

Area Network (WPAN) and Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN) data are protected using low-complexity algorithms [12]. In this rapidly evolving era of the Internet and fog servers, where a multitude of users and their private data are readily accessible, protecting healthcare data becomes an imperative priority. Security concerns are raised when patient health information is securely stored in an electronic format [13-15]. In [16], a security-dependent group mobility organization technique was proposed to secure sensitive information exchange. In [17], the AES-CMAC and a motion practice were used to encourage data transfer between access points in a WBAN-based IoT network. In [10], an improved auto-categorical PSO was used for heart disease prediction. Initial accuracy challenges were attributed to limited medical records. In [5], a security-focused network handover technique was established using the AES-CMAC algorithm, improving environmental descriptions while emphasizing the need to address power consumption and internet distribution. In [18], an EPPDA model was introduced that relied on authentication and permission phases using additively homomorphic encryption for data collection. In [1], SVD was applied to identify sensitive information using 3D RDP to balance data privacy and utility and requiring multiple perturbation techniques for improved classification. In [2], the EMSA algorithm was introduced to assess healthcare cloud privacy, focusing on role-based encryption keys to protect sensitive data. Hybridized swarm optimization is a technique to fine-tune the fusion parameters in a hybrid learning model that are crucial for its performance. In this process, the optimization method combines elements of swarm intelligence with other optimization techniques to effectively adjust the parameters. This hybridized approach relies on a pathfinder that assesses and adjusts the parameters based on their fitness, striving to identify the optimal solution while minimizing convergence and ensuring that the model performs optimally. Compared to existing methods, the hybrid learning model offers a unique approach to disease prediction with a focus on security and optimization. The inclusion of both deep CNN and Bi LSTM classifiers improves accuracy. The use of hybridized swarm optimization further improves parameter tuning based on fitness, increasing prediction effectiveness. However, more research is needed to assess the scalability and generalizability of the model to different medical sensor types. This study considered the current challenges for analyzing the effectiveness of a hybrid learning model:

- Current disease prediction models face challenges in early and accurate detection. Many proposed machine learning algorithms for disease prediction prioritize prediction without focusing on security concerns [19].
- Existing disease prediction methods often overlook feature selection, leading to reduced training efficiency [19]. Supervised machine learning algorithms have been used to identify heart rate variability signals.
- Predictive models are commonly based on multiple variables and manually calculated risk scores. While they perform well for the general population, their accuracy is limited when applied to all types of patients.

II. SMART HEALTHCARE SYSTEM MODEL

The proposed framework consists of three phases: data collection using distributed IoT nodes, device and patient authentication using the encryption scheme with a modified ECC-based Diffi-Huffman algorithm, and effective disease prediction using the collected data. In Figure 1, IoT nodes are initially deployed throughout the sensing environment to collect patient information for remote healthcare monitoring and predicting health statuses. After the data are collected, they undergo robust protection through encryption to protect them from potential intruders while residing in the cloud. Subsequently, the securely encrypted data are transmitted to the cloud server. There, healthcare professionals can access and examine health reports, using the information to formulate diagnoses and provide medical recommendations.

Fig. 1. Prediction of cardiac disease schematic form.

A. Data Acquisition And Authentication

Data acquisition is the process of gathering and combining data from all relevant sources. The acquired data must be encoded to protect the information in the cloud from unauthorized attackers who might access the stored information. The authentication process ensures the certification and validation of information before updating patient medical records securely on the cloud server. To achieve this, an algorithm is employed to encrypt both previously published and current medical reports. This encryption involves key generation and signature creation at the sender's end, followed by signature verification at the receiver's end. Subsequently, secure data transmission to the destination is accomplished using a modified ECC-dependent Diffi-Huffman method. At the destination, an authenticated doctor decrypts the data to provide a diagnosis for the patient.

B. Hybrid Learning Model For Disease Prediction

This study combined the interactive hunt-deep CNN classifier with the WoM-based Bi LSTM classifier in a hybrid learning model to train preprocessed heart disease data. Compared to a standard deep learning model, this hybrid approach achieves superior accuracy and efficiency by leveraging the combined performance of both classifiers. Equation (1) originates from the interactive hunt optimization technique, which effectively fine-tunes the deep CNN classifier's parameters. Meanwhile, (2) is the result of employing WoM optimization to fine-tune the parameters of the deep Bi LSTM classifier, leading to optimal accuracy in heart disease prediction. The methods involved in the hybrid learning model are not identical, generating two different outputs for every instant of disease prediction.

$$J_{HSH}^{x+1} = 0.5F^{SUS}[1 - B \cdot a \cdot I] + 0.5F_x(1 - Ba - aMM) + 0.5[a \times MM \times F_x^{DOM}] \quad (1)$$

where the position of the hybrid interactive hunting search agents is denoted as J_{HSH}^{x+1} , F^{SUS} is successor's position, F_x is the position of the interactive hunter at x^{th} iteration, a is an arbitrary number varying between 0 and 1, MM is the maximum movement towards the dominating search agent, B and I represent the co-efficient vectors, and F_x^{DOM} is the location of the dominating search agent.

$$\vec{Y}^*(T) = \begin{cases} Y^i(T) + CF [\vec{Q}_{min} + \vec{N} \otimes (\vec{Q}_{max} - \vec{Q}_{min})] \otimes \vec{V}, & \text{if } u \leq fn \\ Y^i(T) + [fn(1-u) + u](Y_{u1}(T) - Y_{u2}(T)), & \text{if } u > fn \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where Y^* is the attained suitable solution for the position vector Y , and Y^i is the initial position vector of the crookback whales.

The counterflow effects are denoted as CF . \vec{Q}_{min} and \vec{Q}_{max} are the lower and upper bands, and u_1 and u_2 are the random indexes of $Y(T)$. Accordingly, the automatic prediction developed for the disease will follow the hybrid deep classifier, developed through hybridizing the interactive hunt-deep CNN classifier and WoM-deep BiLSTM classifier. The hybridization is supported using the fusion parameters, and the optimization algorithm is designed for tuning the deep classifiers to acquire effective prediction results. The hybrid classifier was developed, for which the fusion factors were designed and also used for tuning optimization, which was reliant on the hybridized swarm optimization. The outcome of the hybrid learning model is shown in (3), which utilizes the effective performance of both the interactive hunt-deep CNN and WoM-deep Bi LSTM model during the disease prediction.

$$y = \alpha * J_{HSH}^{x+1} + \beta * Y^*(T) \quad (3)$$

where α and β are the fusion parameters that are effectively determined and tuned by hybridized swarm optimization.

1) Proposed Hybridized Swarm Optimization for the Hybrid Classifier

In the proposed hybridized swarm optimization, the path initialization for identifying the better solution is based on the attained fitness of the pathfinder [20]. The fitness of an individual pathfinder is enhanced by incorporating random

search, seeking, attack prevention, following, and waiting of the swarm involved in the exploration of the optimal solution [21]. In the seeking phase, the fish will go swiftly and immediately to an area where there is more food when it is discovered. In the attack prevention phase, fish instinctively group when swimming to avoid harm. In the following phase, when a swarm finds food, the others will chase after it to find the food dangling, and leaping behavior occurs when fish stagnate in one area. In the waiting behavior phase, swarms stay in a place to find food from other regions.

The traversing paths that the solutions are initially assumed and a specific pathfinder's fitness is assessed depending on the attained solutions, which is expressed as:

$$P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\} \quad (4)$$

where the path identified by the pathfinder is denoted as P with n number of paths.

In the random search phase, the pathfinder arrives at a location with more food as a result of the path-sorting behavior. Each individual progressively disperses and begins looking for food in the search space within $[0,1]$. The following equation applies to this process when the available search space is greater than one:

$$\vec{Y}(\tau + 1) = 0.5[\vec{Y}_r - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D} + Y_i^\tau + M_1(L - Y_i^\tau) + M_2(Y_i^\tau \pm Y_{position})], \quad (S > 1) \quad (5)$$

where the personal best position is represented as $Y_{position}$, and \vec{Y}_r denotes the random position of the pathfinder agent to find food. The angle or the direction of the food search is described by \vec{A} , the distance between the i^{th} pathfinder at Y_r and the food source is denoted as \vec{D} , and the leader swarm is represented as L . M_1 and M_2 are the competitive and cooperative behaviors of the pathfinder for determining the optimum solution in the search space S .

As a consequence of the random search, when the available search space of the pathfinder may not fulfill the requirement of the swarm in the group, the seeking phase occurs at the search space of $S \leq 0.25$. The exploration is significantly related to the fitness of an individual pathfinder's position and expressed as

$$Y^{\tau+1} = Y^\tau + w_i * (Y_{personal} - \alpha Y^\tau), \quad (S \leq 0.25) \quad (6)$$

where the present position of the pathfinder is denoted as Y^τ , the weight factor as w_i , which is in the $[0,1]$ range, the personal best solution is described as $Y_{personal}$, and the random number is represented as α in the range of $[0,1]$.

During the exploration, the attack prevention technique is introduced by the swarm in the search space of $[0.25, 0.5]$, which looks for a path to prevent attack from enemies, and is expressed as:

$$Y_L^{\tau+1} = Y_i^\tau + A^\tau, \quad (0.25 \geq S \geq 0.5) \quad (7)$$

The waiting behavior of the swarm is expressed in (8), which stays in a place to find food from other possible regions in the search space range $[0.75, 0.9]$.

$$Y^{\tau+1} = Y^{\tau} - S_{vol} * \alpha * \left[\frac{Y^{\tau} - Y_{avg}}{D[Y^{\tau} - Y_{avg}]} \right], (0.75 \geq S > 0.9) \quad (8)$$

where Y_{avg} is the average position of the swarm and S_{vol} is the volume of the search space. The following equations combine the attack prevention behavior of the swarm in the effective path determination by the pathfinder Y_{PF} :

$$Y_{PF}^{\tau+1} = Y_i^{\tau} + N_1(L - Y_i^{\tau}) + N_2(Y_i^{\tau} - Y_j^{\tau}) \quad (9)$$

$$Y^{\tau+1} = 0.5[Y_L^{\tau+1} + Y_{PF}^{\tau+1}] \quad (10)$$

$$Y^{\tau+1} = 0.5[(Y_i^{\tau} + A^{\tau}) + Y_i^{\tau} + N_1(L - Y_i^{\tau}) + N_2(Y_i^{\tau} - Y_j^{\tau})] \quad (11)$$

$$Y^{\tau+1} = 0.5[Y_i^{\tau}(2 + A - N_1 + N_2) + N_1L - N_2Y_j^{\tau}] \quad (12)$$

where the leader swarm is represented as L with competitive and cooperative behaviors N_1 and N_2 , and Y_j^{τ} represents the swarms around the pathfinder.

```

Algorithm 1. Pseudocode for the hybridized swarm
optimization
Input:  $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\}$ 
Output:  $P_{best}$ 
Initialize the traversing paths  $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\}$ 
Sketch and sort the paths based on fitness
while ( $t < t_{max}$ )
  For all  $i < n$ 
    Case 1: if ( $s \leq 0.25$ )
      Call seeking behavior
    Else if ( $0.25 \geq s \leq 0.5$ )
      Call attack prevention
    Else if ( $0.5 \geq s \leq 0.75$ )
      Call following
    Else if ( $0.75 \geq s \leq 0.9$ )
      Call waiting
    Else ( $s > 1$ )
      Call exploration phase
  Evaluate  $fit(P_i)$ 
  If  $fit(P_i) < fit(P_{best})$ 
    Restore  $P_{best}$ 
  Else
    Update  $P_{best} = P_i$ 
  Recall  $P_{best}$ 
End while

```

The outputs attained from the hybrid learning model using the interactive hunt-deep CNN and WoM-deep Bi LSTM are fused. The two different fusion parameters are α and β , identified optimally by the hybridized swarm optimization. Hybridized swarm optimization holds the character of two different swarms. Initially, the path is the most significant phase in determining the optimal solution. Here, the optimal solution is the fusion parameters during the exploration, which is the training process, and various solutions are obtained. The optimal solution is determined with the assistance of the fish's seeking, attack prevention, following, and waiting behaviors.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The efficiency of the hybrid optimum learning model and other conventional methods was determined in predicting heart diseases using the datasets in [22] and [23].

A. Experimental Setup

The implementation of a hybrid optimum learning model was carried out in MATLAB on a PC with 8 GB RAM.

B. Performance Measures

The measures involved in the analysis of the hybrid learning model were accuracy, F-measure, sensitivity, and specificity. Accuracy is estimated by the total number of diseases correctly identified in the test sample analyzed. F-measure assesses the performance of a model on a dataset. It is used to evaluate categorization systems that categorize samples as either "positive" or "negative." Sensitivity describes the percentage of accurately identified patients categorized by the total number of affected individuals. Specificity describes the number of healthy individuals correctly identified by the total number of non-diseased individuals.

C. Dataset Description

The comprehensive heart disease dataset [22] combines independently accessible datasets according to specific features, while the heart disease dataset [23] uses 14 databases and includes 76 features.

D. Performance Analysis

1) Performance Using [22]

Table I and Figure 2 show the effectiveness of the hybrid optimum learning model depending on the training percentage and the epoch value.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE USING [22]

Measures / training percentage	Epochs: 100			
	Accuracy (%)	F-measure (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
40	92.379	92.802	92.693	93.335
50	93.718	93.957	93.902	94.250
60	95.435	95.783	95.611	96.302
70	96.740	96.978	97.035	97.158
80	97.734	97.859	98.021	97.822

2) Performance Using [23]

Table II and Figure 3 show the effectiveness of the hybrid optimum learning model depending on the percentage of training and the epoch value.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE USING [23]

Measures/ training percentage	Epoch 100			
	Accuracy (%)	F-measure (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
40	91.837	91.535	90.706	92.060
50	93.151	92.456	91.647	92.571
60	94.829	94.092	93.622	93.826
70	96.124	96.076	95.734	96.370
80	97.109	96.861	96.117	97.358

E. Comparative Analysis

The proposed hybrid learning model was compared with Hybrid Fuzzy based DT [24], multimodal IoT framework [19], MDCNN [25], DLMNN [19], IGDBN [26], CSO-CLSTM [27], HuS-based deep CNN, DHOA-based deep CNN, Hybrid social hunting-based deep CNN, deep Bi LSTM [28], WOA-based deep Bi LSTM, MPA-based deep Bi LSTM, and [29].

Fig. 2. Performance on [22]: (a) Accuracy, (b) F-measure, (c) Sensitivity, and (d) Specificity.

Fig. 3. Performance on [23]: (a) Accuracy, (b) F-measure, (c) Sensitivity, and (d) Specificity.

Fig. 4. Comparative analysis of the proposed hybrid and various models on [22]: (a) Accuracy, (b) F-measure, (c) Sensitivity, and (d) Specificity.

Figure 4 compares the models in [22], considering training percentages of 40 to 80, showing that the proposed model achieved 0.6% higher accuracy and F-measure than the others. Figure 5 shows the performance comparison of the proposed hybrid and previous models in [23]. The performance of the hybrid learning model was assessed in a range of training percentages (40-80%). In this case, the proposed hybrid learning model had greater accuracy, F-measure, specificity, and sensitivity by 1.42%, 1.4%, 1.8%, and 0.9%, respectively.

Fig. 5. Comparative analysis of the proposed hybrid and various models on [23]: (a) Accuracy, (b) F-measure, (c) Sensitivity, and (d) Specificity.

F. Comparative Discussion

Tables III and IV show that the proposed hybrid learning model attained better efficiency in predicting fusion parameters and optimizing the classifier performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study used a combination of advanced machine learning techniques, specifically the WoM-deep BiLSTM and

interactive hunt-deep CNN classifiers, to enhance disease prediction. Two fusion parameters were introduced to optimize the performance of this hybrid model. These fusion parameters were fine-tuned using a hybridized swarm optimization approach. Furthermore, the data collected from the IoT environment were securely transmitted using a modified ECC-based Diffi-Huffman algorithm. In particular, the efficiency

gains achieved through the hybridized swarm optimization are substantial, resulting in a 0.6% increase in accuracy and a 0.8% improvement in the F-measure. Furthermore, sensitivity and specificity improved by 0.4% when evaluated in [22]. For the heart disease dataset in [23], the efficiency was higher by 1.42, 1.4, 1.8, and 0.9 % in terms of accuracy, F-measure, sensitivity, and specificity.

TABLE III. COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE USING [22]

Methods	Dataset [23]			
	Training percentage: 80			
	Accuracy %	F-measure %	Sensitivity %	Specificity %
Hybrid fuzzy-based DT	92.223	92.350	92.511	92.317
Multimodal IoT framework	94.883	95.010	95.171	94.976
MDCNN	83.320	83.443	83.497	83.512
DLMNN	85.251	85.374	85.428	85.443
IGDBN	86.920	87.043	87.097	87.112
CSO-CLSTM	91.340	91.463	91.517	91.532
HuS- Deep CNN	93.429	93.552	93.605	93.621
DHOA-deep CNN	92.240	92.362	92.416	92.431
Hybrid social hunting based deep CNN	96.929	97.052	97.105	97.121
Deep Bi-LSTM	94.151	94.272	95.151	93.515
WOA- deep Bi-LSTM	95.915	95.078	94.154	95.165
MPA- deep Bi-LSTM	96.222	96.467	96.265	96.915
WoM- deep Bi-LSTM	97.526	97.658	97.926	97.522
Hybrid learning model	97.716	97.848	98.021	97.807

TABLE IV. COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE USING [23]

Methods	Heart disease dataset			
	Training percentage 80			
	Accuracy %	F-measure %	Sensitivity %	Specificity %
Hybrid fuzzy-based DT	90.935	91.562	92.090	91.662
Multimodal IoT framework	93.595	94.222	94.749	94.322
MDCNN	81.644	82.277	82.588	82.598
DLMNN	90.836	88.914	87.452	88.453
IGDBN	85.244	85.877	86.188	86.198
CSO-CLSTM	89.664	90.297	90.608	90.618
HuS- Deep CNN	91.753	92.386	92.697	92.707
DHOA- deep CNN	90.564	91.196	91.507	91.518
Hybrid social hunting based deep CNN	95.253	95.886	96.197	96.207
Deep Bi-LSTM	91.529	92.313	93.252	92.158
WOA-deep Bi-LSTM	93.256	93.864	95.152	93.185
MPA- deep Bi-LSTM	95.184	95.174	94.188	96.148
WoM- deep Bi-LSTM	96.625	97.247	97.992	97.126
Hybrid learning model	96.789	97.411	98.073	97.371

The hybrid optimal learning model can also be used to anticipate disease before it occurs. Recognizing infections earlier allows for the use of appropriate treatments to reduce their severity. This study may face challenges in scaling to real-time applications, which requires further investigation and optimization to meet the requirements of timely disease prediction in dynamic clinical environments. Future research should explore the integration of additional classifiers and advanced data collection techniques to further enhance the reliability and real-time performance of disease prediction, ensuring early recognition and treatment of diseases.

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Prediction of Concrete's Compressive Strength via Artificial Neural Network Trained on Synthetic Data

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ABSTRACT

Predicting concrete compressive strength using machine learning techniques has attracted the focus of many studies in recent years. Typically, given concrete mix ingredients, a machine learning model is trained on experimental data to predict properties of hardened concrete, such as compressive strength at 28 days. This study used computer-generated mix design data that contained mixed ingredients along with the corresponding theoretical strength of each mix to train a neural network and then test them on real-world experimental data. The developed model was able to predict the compressive strength of concrete specimens at 28 days with an R-value of 0.80. Furthermore, increasing the synthetic dataset increased the performance of the model to a point beyond which it started to decrease. The proposed sustainability-promoting method emphasizes the effectiveness of using synthetic data to train machine learning models that yield insightful predictions with acceptable accuracy.

Keywords-concrete; compressive strength; machine learning; AI; synthetic data; computer-generated data

I. INTRODUCTION

The application of Machine Learning (ML) algorithms in the field of construction materials and concrete technology has been trending for the past few years. Such models can learn from the data and establish relationships between inputs and outputs to solve complex engineering problems. The success of such models has been widely celebrated, increasing their prevalence in many fields of applied and theoretical sciences. In the fields of civil, architectural, construction engineering, and concrete technology, many studies attempted to increase the prediction accuracy of ML models to solve relevant problems. For example, several studies attempted to create models that accurately predict the properties of construction materials by training on data available in the literature [1-4]. In addition, many properties of fresh and hardened concrete of many different types have been studied and predicted using ML and deep learning models over the past two decades [5-21]. Meanwhile, many studies attempted to increase the predictive power of ML models by introducing more complexities or training them with additional experimental data. However, while heterogeneous and large data are often better for training artificial models [22], in the case of concrete compressive strength prediction, it can be very exhaustive and expensive to expand such a dataset. In particular, to add more instances to a dataset, materials for the mix design must be procured and studied, then mixed and cured for a standard period of 28 days, after which the samples should be crushed to determine their compressive strength.

In addition to the time and effort needed to expand an existing dataset, the experimental data may differ because they are reported by multiple educational laboratories, research centers, or concrete manufacturers. Differences also arise from the time of production of such a dataset and the design codes used. In other words, due to mix design variability, material differences, and mixing and testing procedures, it can be argued that these accumulated data are not homogeneous, hence affecting the performance of ML models. Even if the models that are trained on such inhomogeneous data achieve high accuracies, their application may be limited. Therefore, to overcome the difficulty of increasing the size and homogeneity of the concrete compressive strength dataset, this study proposes and shows that computer-generated data (synthetic data) can be used to train ML models to make accurate predictions of concrete compressive strength after 28 days. In addition, synthetic data are being increasingly used in many fields of applied and theoretical sciences. Synthetic data can be generated from existing analytical models or physical simulations and/or through artificial intelligence generative models [24]. A case in point is in the field of computer vision, where scenarios of tough driving terrains and environments, as well as scenarios of road accidents are being emulated to train artificial intelligence algorithms for self-driving cars.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study trained an ML model on synthetic mix design data to predict the compressive strength of concrete. The dataset contained mix designs of varying strengths and controlled variables, which aid in the training of the ML model,

aiming to study how the synthetic inputs affect the model's predictions of concrete strength. The model was tested using actual laboratory-produced compressive strength data. Figure 1 shows the workflow of the proposed method.

Fig. 1. An illustration of the workflow of the approach used in this study.

The American Concrete Institute (ACI) mix design method was used to create the dataset to train the ML model. Computer software was developed that closely implements all steps of the ACI method for the concrete mix design. The software takes into account the different properties of the mixed ingredients, such as the specific gravities for gravel, sand, and cement, as well as the moisture content and absorption information of the aggregates, along with the fineness modulus of the fine aggregates. In addition, the software also considers the maximum nominal size of the gravel and the required workability, which is provided as a slump value. Moreover, the software requires knowledge of exposure conditions, in addition to requiring input of whether previous test records exist and how many tests are available, if any, accompanied with the necessary test results, such as the standard deviation. Lastly, the software can design both air-entrained and non-air-entrained concrete mixes.

The ACI method-based mix design software was used to create a dataset of non-air-entrained concrete mixes that had a range of specified compressive strength of 20 to 40 MPa with negligible exposure conditions and typical material properties. The chosen slump for all mix designs was 80-100 mm and an MNS for coarse aggregates of 10, 12.5, and 20 mm was specified. Figure 2 shows the histograms of the ingredients of all the mix designs in the dataset. As can be seen from the histograms, the ingredients of the mix designs were well distributed, some of them forming a frequency distribution that resembles a normal distribution, e.g. the amount of sand. However, for other ingredients, the ingredient distribution seems to be clustered in certain areas only, in other words, only

a few columns represent the entirety of the data for this ingredient, e.g. the amount of water. The latter phenomenon is due to the way the ACI mix design method works to estimate the water content in a mix design.

Fig. 2. Histograms of mix design constituents.

To train the model, 250, 500, 1,000 mixes, and 10,000 mixes were created. For each dataset, 80% was allocated to training and the remaining 20% was allocated to testing. In addition, the models were tested using external experimental compressive strength records. The external dataset in [25] was used to test the performance of the model on real-world data. The dataset contained the mix proportions and the resulting experimentally obtained compressive strengths. The dataset contained 1030 test records having 9 attributes, including the amount of cement, water, aggregates, blast furnace slag, fly ash, and superplasticizers. The compressive strengths in the dataset ranged from 2.33 to 82 MPa. To use this dataset as a test for the trained model, it was cleaned to have only records of samples that have strengths ranging from 20 to 40 MPa and made from only the basic four ingredients, i.e. cement, water, sand, and gravel. The cleaned dataset contained 42 records.

The model used was an artificial neural network with four inputs, i.e. the ingredients of the mix design, which were fed to two internal layers and one output layer that represents the predicted compressive strength of concrete. The Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm was used for training and the Mean Square Error (MSE) was used for performance monitoring.

Training stopped when the model was trained for 1000 epochs or the stopping criterion was met. Data are the backbone of ML. Generally, for models that depend on data such as artificial neural networks, the more training data, the better the performance of the model. To see if this is the case with synthetic data, the model was trained on data having from 250 to 10,000 mix designs. Table I shows a sample of the training data. MATLAB R2021b environment was used to create and test the models, particularly the Regression Learner and Neural Network toolbox.

TABLE I. A SAMPLE OF THE TRAINING DATA.

#	Cement (kg)	Water (L)	Sand (kg)	Gravel (kg)	Concrete Strength (MPa)
1	400	200	800	900	32
2	415	220	850	800	30
...
10000	505	223	560	800	37

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After training the neural network model on 80% of the mix design dataset, it produced satisfactory training and validation (test) results with very low MSE and high correlation value R. Training required less than 800 epochs, due to meeting the predefined stopping criterion, which was a constantly very low MSE, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Training performance of the neural network model.

The resulting trained neural network model achieved an MSE of $3.1467e-6$ and a correlation coefficient of 1.0. Figure 4 shows the regression plots of the training performance, indicating that the model achieved a very high correlation, as evidenced by the training R-value, which was 1.0. However, at the same time, the model did not overfit, which was evidenced by the validation R-value, which was 1.0. However, there was a very small error associated with the prediction of the model, as shown in the error distribution in Figure 5. It can be said that the error distribution is well distributed across a center of zero error, with a maximum error not exceeding ± 0.008 MPa.

The trained neural network model was tested using external experimental data. The external dataset in [25] was used to test the performance of the model in real-world examples. The dataset contained mix proportions and their experimentally

obtained compressive strengths. Similarly to the training dataset, the testing dataset contained four features, i.e. the four basic mix ingredients, and one output, which was the compressive strength of each mix. The number of mixes in the testing dataset was 42. The model was tested using this experimental dataset and achieved a correlation coefficient of 0.80. Figure 6 shows the regression of the neural network model when tested using experimental data with 42 instances, indicating that the data were well distributed around the fit line, with some outliers above and below it. It can be argued that achieving a 0.80 correlation between real-world data and the output of an exclusively synthetic data-trained model is considered a very good result.

Fig. 4. Regression results for training and validation of the neural network model; x-axes refer to actual compressive strength while y-axes refer to compressive strength predicted by the ANN model.

Fig. 5. Error histogram of the model's output in training and validation.

The error histograms of the model when tested on experimental data show that the model achieved a very good correlation, evidenced by the testing R-value, which was 0.8. However, there are some errors associated with the prediction of the model, as shown in the error distribution in Figure 7. The error distribution is skewed, with more errors present above the zero-error line. In other words, the neural network model tends to overshoot.

Fig. 6. Performance of the neural network model when tested on experimental data with 42 instances; The x-axis refers to the actual compressive strength while y-axis refers to the predicted compressive strength.

Fig. 7. Error histogram of the model's output in the testing stage using external experimental data.

The prediction of concrete compressive strength using ML methods has been studied using many methods, including Linear Regression (LR), Decision Trees (DT), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). The previously reported findings regarding the prediction of concrete strength using ML methods used experimental data to train the models, while this study used computer-generated data for training. Table II compares the findings of this study with recent relevant studies. It can be seen that although synthetic data were used for training, the proposed model outperformed some experimental data-trained models.

Generally, for models that depend on data, such as the one used in this study, the more the training data, the better the results. To see if this is the case with synthetic data, the model was trained on data ranging from 250 up to 10,000 mix designs. The results showed that for 250 mix designs, the model had an R-value of 0.46. Doubling the amount of training data resulted in an R-value of 0.80. Increasing the dataset to 750, then 1,000, and lastly to 10,000 records only decreased the performance of the model, to 0.78, 0.78, and 0.75, respectively. This decline in performance can be explained by the fact that as synthetic data increased, meaningful data within them were

limited, leading to an overfit of the model and a decrease in performance.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF THIS STUDY'S RESULTS WITH OTHER ML METHODS

Reference	ML Algorithm	Training data	R
[26]	ANN	Experiments	0.9
[26]	LR	Experiments	0.81
[27]	DT	Experiments	0.87
[27]	ANN	Experiments	0.9
[28]	ANN	Experiments	0.76
[28]	LR	Experiments	0.63
[28]	SVM	Experiments	0.67
This study	ANN	Synthetic	0.80

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Recently, intense interest has been placed on using ML techniques to predict the compressive strength of concrete. Such predictive models are typically trained using experimental data on concrete mix ingredients and hardened concrete properties. This study proposed that concrete mixes designed using the ACI mix design method can be used as a training dataset for ML models. The study then showed that synthetic data can be used to train ML models to make accurate predictions of concrete strength after 28 days, ranging from 20 to 40 MPa. To test the performance of the trained model, an external experimental dataset was used, which contained more than 40 instances. When tested in the external experimental dataset, the model was able to predict the 28-day compressive strength of concrete with an R-value greater than 0.8. Meanwhile, it is important to note that the size and quality of the synthetic dataset are important factors that can affect the performance of the ML model. This study aimed to shed some light on the efficacy of using computer-generated data to train artificial intelligence models to provide practical and beneficial predictions. This innovative technique promotes sustainability, as it can alleviate the reliance on experimental data to train ML models, which can be costly and time-consuming.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data can be provided upon request.

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A Security Scheme for Statistical Anomaly Detection and the Mitigation of Rank Attacks in RPL Networks (IoT Environment)

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ABSTRACT

A Routing Protocol for Low-power-lossy (RPL) networks builds a Destination Oriented Directed Acyclic Graph (DODAG) to provide IPv6 connectivity for resource-constrained devices over a large variety of low-power-lossy link layer technologies. Each RPL node maintains a rank value, which quantizes its relative topological distance from the DODAG root and is calculated based on the rank of its preferred parents and the objective function being employed. The RPL routing process does not impose any check to monitor the action and conduct of the parent nodes. A malicious attacking node can exploit this weakness by faking its rank value to be much lower than the original to attract more traffic to traverse through it from its neighboring and underlying child nodes. An attacking node can choose to perform selective forwarding or a sinkhole attack (Rank Attack type 1 – RA1) or exacerbate network performance parameters by causing topological instability (Rank Attack type 2 - RA2). This paper presents the Statistically-based Anomaly Detection Scheme (SARPL) to detect RA1 and RA2 and attempts to mitigate their effects. The simulations and performance evaluations show that SARPL can successfully detect RA1 attacks in all scenarios whereas it has a positive detection rate of approximately 93% for RA2 type attacks. SARPL also significantly improves network performance parameters, such as packet delivery rate and end-to-end delay, while mitigating the effects of RA1 and RA2.

Keywords-anomaly detection; rank attack; RPL network; low power lossy network

I. INTRODUCTION

Low power and Lossy Networks (LLNs) usually consist of resource constrained nodes connected using a large variety of link layer technologies, such as IoT Environment, IEEE 802.15.4, IEEE P1901.2 (Power Line Communication - PLC), IEEE 802.15.4g (Low-Power Wi-Fi) etc. A few application areas for LLNs include asset tracking, industrial and environmental monitoring, smart homes, smart energy metering, building automation and many more [1]. The lossy nature of LLNs demands a robust routing protocol that can efficiently address ephemeral and unpredictable network characteristics. IETFs ROLL (Routing Over Low-power and Lossy networks) [2, 3] working group proposed the specification of RPL (Routing Protocol over LLNs), which supports a large variety of constrained and potentially lossy link layers, suitable for resource-constrained devices. RPL constructs a logical network topology by constructing a

Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) for the communication of the network devices. RPL then divides this topology into multiple Destination Oriented Directed Acyclic Graphs (DODAGs), one for each root node, also called a sink, which is responsible for data collection and DODAG network coordination. Each DODAG RPL can be uniquely identified by a quadruple of "RPL Instance ID," "DODAG ID," "DODAG Version Number," and "Rank" as shown in Figure 1 and described in [4]. The RPL specification primarily uses four types of control messages for setting up and updating the topology of a DODAG [3]: the DIO (DODAG Information Object), DAO (DODAG Destination Object), DIS (DODAG Information Solicitation), and DAO-ACK messages.

A. Concept of Rank

Each RPL node maintains a rank value, which is calculated based on its distance from the DODAG root and indicates the quality of the path towards it. RPL nodes calculate and update

their rank value based on the rank of their preferred parents and the objective function being employed. In RPL networks, rank values strictly increase from the DODAG root towards the RPL leaf nodes to ensure an optimal network topology, prevention of routing loops and to minimize routing inconsistencies. DIO messages are used to propagate the updated rank value of a node to its neighboring nodes. The routing operation of RPL assumes that all participating nodes in the network are reliable and will follow the protocol rules strictly. A detailed discussion on rank properties, relationships and its computation can be found in [3, 5].

Fig. 1. RPL topology hierarchical partitions.

B. Rank Attack and its Impact

The RPL routing process does not impose any check to monitor the action of the parent nodes. The child nodes have no way to check the validity of the information provided by their parents and must depend on them exclusively. In the case of an attack, they have to rely on information provided by DIO messages disseminated by malicious nodes, resulting in non-optimized routes towards the DODAG root node. Malicious attacking nodes can exploit this weakness to launch similar attacks, such as sinkhole attacks, wormhole attacks, selective forwarding, etc. IETF RFC 7416 [6] describes some means to protect the RPL control plane against external threats to ensure its integrity, authenticity, and confidentiality (optional). However, the control plane still remains prone to intra-network attacks, as an attacker can get access to security credentials, enabling it to manipulate the RPL routing topology. The wireless sensor devices, which are usually scattered and unattended, are not tamper-resistant and are weakly secured due to their limited functionality and capabilities. One of the primary security challenges in RPL is to secure information, such as a nodes rank, which can be used for unwanted manipulation of the routing topology [7].

To launch a rank attack, a malicious node fakes its rank value (relative topological distance to the DODAG root) to be much lower than its original value to attract more traffic traversing through it from neighboring and underlying child nodes. This causes the network topology around the malicious node to change and become unstable and may result in the formation of routing loops and inconsistencies. To recover to a normal network functional state, RPL self-healing and management mechanisms [8] attempt to recover and fix the

DODAG network state. This eventually causes a significant increase in control overhead, primarily in the form of sending DIO messages [9] and has undesirable effects on the energy reserves of the nodes, channel availability and data packet throughput. A false rank of a node falsifies the relative topological distance of the node in reference to the DODAG root node and thus disarranges the hierarchical structure of the DODAG topology. An inconsistent version tends to break the reference of a node to the topological graph and forces the network control plane to rebuild its routing graph.

In a rank attack, the attacker can choose to permanently violate the rank rule or to flip between being for and against it over a specific period of time [4]. Flipping is primarily used to disrupt normal network operation and to bring instability to the network topology by continually changing its preferred parent node. Thus, every time the topology around the attacking node changes due to flipping, it will generate a DIO message to update its neighbors, causing additional control overhead leading to higher energy constraints. The neighboring nodes will then be forced to update their routing information and disseminate this change by generating even more DIOs, resulting in a waste of valuable resources.

This study provides the statistically-based anomaly detection scheme SARPL that aims to detect and counteract two distinct rank attacks, RA1 and RA2. According to simulations and performance tests, SARPL has a positive detection rate of roughly 93% for RA2 type assaults and can successfully identify RA1 attacks in all scenarios. While reducing the effects of RA1 and RA2, SARPL also dramatically enhances network performance metrics like packet delivery rate and end-to-end latency.

II. CONTRIBUTION

The proposed system is able:

- To detect and neutralize two forms of rank attacks, whereas a novel statistical anomaly detection scheme has been presented for resource-constrained RPL-based networks.
- To guarantee that a malevolent parent node does not alter or remove Rank Attack Detection (RAD) control data intended solely for the DODAG root node. To do so, a straightforward random selection of "preferred parents" system has been designed.
- To examine the effects of two distinct rank attacks, RA1 and RA2, on various network performance metrics.

Simulations of the attacks were conducted in the CONTIKI-COOJA network simulator IDE.

III. RELATED WORK

A study has been carried out in [4] to understand the impact of a rank attack on the topology of an RPL network. This paper outlines how a rank attack can have a severely negative and decaying performance effect on the network in terms of various parameters, such as packet delivery ratio, end-to-end delay, control traffic overhead, and network throughput. An intrusion detection system has been proposed in [10] to detect topology attacks such as rank attack. The proposed scheme requires RPL

to implement a Finite State Machine (FSM) inside each node to monitor suspicious behavior. However, no simulation results were presented to validate proof of the concept. SVELTE [11] consists of a vital component named 6mapper that is used to gather topology information of the RPL network in the DODAG root node. 6mapper sends mapping requests to each RPL node in the network at regular intervals. RPL nodes respond to these requests by appending their rank, their preferred parents ID, and their neighbors IDs and respective ranks. However, SVELTE has a high false rate, which is primarily caused by valid inconsistencies in 6mapper between rank measurements [12].

The Intrusion Detection Scheme (IDS) proposed in [13] uses a simple heartbeat protocol to obtain an updated network state and subsequently to detect attacks such as sinkhole and selective forwarding. While simulating these attacks for RPL networks, it is assumed that the malicious node cannot differentiate RPL control traffic from the normal traffic and is unable to drop RPL packets. This assumption requires encryption, upper-layer security protocols such as IPsec or implementing other security mechanisms, which subsequently affects the energy efficiency of resource-constrained RPL nodes. However, if the malicious node gains access to the encryption key of the besieged nodes, this assumption is no longer workable. Authors in [14] propose a version number and VeRA rank authentication scheme to prevent such internal attacks. VeRA attempts to ensure a strict rank increase from the DODAG root towards leaf nodes by using a one-way-hash chain. However, hash chains and other such schemes are computationally expensive and not feasible for large RPL networks consisting of resource-constrained nodes [12] leading to network scalability issues. Additionally, VeRA remains vulnerable to rank attacks by forgery and replay [7]. In [15], an IDS framework (Demo) for the Internet of Things (IoT) has been proposed, where an IDS probe node is used to monitor 6LoWPAN by sniffing network traffic. Subsequently, this information is transmitted to IDS using a dedicated wired connection. The scheme requires a dedicated probe node (equipped with high computational resources and bandwidth) and a wired link to IDS for its functioning. Similarly, the network-based IDS proposed in [16] is based on multiple IDS agents spread all over the network and able to operate in promiscuous mode. Such dedicated probes act external to 6LoWPAN, do not participate in network operations and require a dedicated wired connection to the IDS system. These requirements of dedicated computational and bandwidth resources make them an unsuitable candidate for large-scale LLNs. A generic RPL topology authentication scheme that detects and prevents topological inconsistencies has been proposed by TRAIL [17]. It uses the DODAG root node as a trust anchor and monotonically increases node ranks. This scheme requires each network node to perform path validation independently, which significantly increases control messaging overhead and signature processing, further exacerbating scalability issues. TRAIL also requires each node to maintain state information, which is likely to diminish the already constrained computing and energy resources.

In [18], the goals, working methods, and advantages of the schemes are examined. There is a taxonomy based on the

detection methods and a comparison table of the examined schemes. A performance study of a few classification algorithms used for network anomaly mitigation techniques in the IoT was carried out using the UNSW-NB15 dataset. The difficulties and unresolved problems in the creation of IoT network anomaly mitigation strategies were examined. Authors in [19] covered the operation of RPLs as well as a number of RPL assaults limited to LLN security. To enhance the RPL performance, an evaluation of different countermeasures against the attacks was also carried out. Authors in [20-22] considered machine learning methods for malevolent behavior detection in IoT networks.

IV. SARPL SYSTEM MODEL

In rank attacks, after comprising security credentials, a malicious node generally fakes its Rank Value to be much lower than its original value, in an attempt to attract more traffic from its neighboring nodes having higher rank values. Later on, the attacker can choose to undertake various illegal actions, such as performing selective forwarding, launch a sinkhole attack, or simply exacerbating network performance parameters. For the study of the proposed scheme, two different versions of rank attacks were simulated:

- Rank Attack 1 (RA1): The attacker intentionally drops data packets to perform selective forwarding and is also capable of randomly flipping between normal RPL operation mode and selective forwarding mode.
- Rank Attack 2 (RA2): The malicious node does not drop packets to disrupt normal network operation. Rather, it tries to affect the network performance parameters, e.g. by choosing the worst parent as its preferred parent instead of the best one [4]. Such attacks are sophisticated and difficult to detect and mitigate because, in such cases, the actions of the attackers can have significant negative impact on the network performance but very few noticeable rule violations of network procedures.

To formulate the proposed scheme, let's consider an RPL network consisting of a single DODAG G having N number of nodes. For any RPL network node n_i the candidate set C_{ni} reachable via link-local multicast, the parent set $Prnt_{ni}$, and preferred parent (i.e. the next hop in upward routes) $Pref_{ni}$ are represented by:

$$C_{ni} = \{n_j \mid j < N, n_j \in G, n_i \neq n_j\} \quad (1)$$

$$Prnt_{ni} = \{n_j \mid P_{ni} \subseteq C_{ni}, n_j \in Same_DODAG_Version\} \quad (2)$$

$$Pref_{ni} = \{n_j \mid n_j \in P_{ni}\} \quad (3)$$

An RPL network consists mainly of resource-constrained nodes having limited computational, energy and memory resources. Alternately, the DODAG root node needs to perform duties such as acting as the anchor node (gateway) providing IPv6 connectivity with the Internet, data collection and dissemination, data processing, control plane monitoring, etc. Therefore, the root node is usually dedicatedly powered and has relatively high processing resources.

For the proposed scheme, the RPL control panel has been extended to include a control packet referred to as RAD, which

is sent periodically from nodes towards the DODAG Root Node (DRN). This enables the DRN D_{RN} to detect any anomalous behavior, such as a rank attack by malicious nodes. RAD packets have a constant packet size of 10 bytes. Their format is presented in Figure 2.

Node ID	Instance ID	DAGID (2)	DOGAG VERSION (1)	Preferred Parent ID (2)	No of P_{ni}^{sent} (1)	Time Stamp (1)
(2)	(1)					

Fig. 2. Proposed RAD packet format.

Another major issue to address is preventing malicious nodes from filtering and dropping RAD control packets of other RPL nodes traversing through it. As a deterrence against such actions, each node n_i forwards its RAD packet to a randomly selected node from its set of parent set $Prnt_{ni}$, instead of always choosing the preferred parent node $Pref_{ni}$. This mechanism incurs randomness to ensure resilience against malicious attacks aimed to disrupt the RPL control plane.

A. Detection of Rank Attack 1 (RA1)

Using a RAD packet, each RPL node n_i informs the DODAG Root Node (DRN) about the number of packets (P_{ni}^{sent}) forwarded by it to its preferred parent $Pref_{ni}$ over the time period t . This information helps D_{RN} to construct a picture of whether any particular node in the network is acting maliciously by dropping packets, forwarded by its child nodes and belonging to its sub-DODAG. For a normal (non-malicious) node, in a given time interval, the difference between packets received by it from its child nodes and packets forwarded should be zero. Otherwise, the anomaly detection scheme will mark it initially as a suspicious node.

Fig. 3. 6LoWPAN-RPL network architecture after a rank attack.

Considering Figure 3, if an attacking node (n_6) tries to report an incorrect value of P_{n6}^{sent} in its RAD packet, the root node D_{RN} can calculate and evaluate in order to find this discrepancy by adding the values of the number of packets sent by its sub-DODAG to the malicious node, i.e. $P_{n1}^{sent} + P_{n2}^{sent} + P_{n3}^{sent} + P_{n7}^{sent}$, and the number of packets forwarded by the attacker, i.e. P_{n6}^{rec} as presented in (4):

$$\varphi_{ni}(t) = \sum_{child=1}^{N-1} P_{child}^{sent} - P_{ni}^{sent} \tag{4}$$

where $\varphi_{ni}(t)$ is the difference in the number of packets over the time period t . For any node n_i , if $\varphi_{ni}(t) = 0$, the node is implied to be operating normally.

B. Detection of Rank Attack 2 (RA2)

In the second type of rank attack, RA2, the malicious node does not drop packets. Rather, it negatively impacts network performance by forwarding data packets of the child nodes toward the worst-performing parent instead of the best one. As a result, an additional delay will incur in the end-to-end transmission time of packets. When sending RAD packets towards the root node, each RPL node n_i randomly selects the next hop from the available parent set $Prnt_{ni}$.

Consider a node n_i whose parent is a malicious node carrying out the second version of a rank attack. In this case, some of the nodes RAD packets will reach the root node by transiting through the malicious node, while others will arrive through normally operating nodes. The root node can find the difference between the travel times of incoming RAD packets to detect anomalous behavior of any nodes parent, as represented in (5)-(8).

$$\omega_{ni} = |Send_{Time} - Arrival_{Time}| \tag{5}$$

where ω_{ni} = end-to-end delay of node's n_i 's RAD packet, $Send_{Time}$ = value of the RAD packets time stamp, $Arrival_{Time}$ = arrival time of the RAD packet at the DODAGroot node

$$S_1 = \sum_{t=1}^k \omega_{ni}^t / k \tag{6}$$

$$For\ t > k, S_t = \alpha \omega_{ni}^t + (1 - \alpha) S_{t-1} \tag{7}$$

In (6), S_t represents the value of exponential moving average at any time period t . To calculate S_t , the value of t is assumed to be 10, which is equal to the number of supervised RAD control packet arrivals at the start of the simulation, at which time the attack is assumed to have not yet occurred. S_t represents the exponentially moving average value of packet travel time at any time period t . In (7), the coefficient α characterizes the degree of weighting decrease. It is a constant smoothing factor having a value between 0 and 1. A larger value of α is used to discount older observations relatively quicker. For simulations, the value of α is assumed to be 0.6. For any RPL node n_i , if the condition given in (8) is true, that node is marked as suspicious.

$$\omega_{ni}^t > S_t + 0.1 * S_t \tag{8}$$

If any node is marked as suspicious 3 consecutive times, it is considered a malicious node by the DODAG root node. In this case, all RPL nodes are notified to not use it as a preferred parent and to include it in a blacklist of restricted nodes. The pseudocode for the proposed anomaly detection and mitigation scheme for the rank attacks is presented in Figure 4.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Detection (True Positive) Rate

The efficiency of any intrusion detection can be quantized in terms of its detection rates. Detection Rate (True Positive) is here defined as the number of malicious RPL nodes that have

been correctly detected by SARPL divided by the total number of attacking RPL nodes in the network. Three scenarios were considered: when all attacking nodes are of type RA1, when all attacking nodes are of type RA2, and when there is an equal number of attacking nodes of both types. A comparative analysis of SARPL in terms of detection rate is presented in Figure 5.

```

Require: A list of 'N' nodes. Counter for each node at node at
DODAG root node.

for all RPL nodes 'ni' except DODAG root node, do
  Calculate  $\phi_{ni}(t)$  for time interval 't'  $\geq$  'k'
  if  $\phi_{ni}(t) \neq 0$  then
    mark 'ni' as suspicious (RA1)
    Counter_ni ++
  else mark 'ni' as normal (Counter_ni = 0)
  Calculate  $\omega_{ni}^t$  and  $S_t$  for time 't'  $\geq$  'k'
  if  $\omega_{ni}^t > S_t + 0.1 * S_t$  then
    mark 'ni' as suspicious (RA2)
    Counter_ni ++
  else mark 'ni' as normal (Counter_ni = 0)
end for

for all RPL nodes 'ni' except DODAG root node, do
  if Counter_ni greater than equal to '3'
    mark 'ni' as malicious node.
    add 'ni' to the blacklist of restricted nodes.
    inform all RPL nodes.
end for
    
```

Fig. 4. Pseudocode for the anomaly detection and mitigation scheme.

Fig. 5. SARPL detection rate evaluation.

It clearly reflects that SARPL can successfully detect RA1-type (packet dropping) attacks for all the considered numbers of attacking nodes in the network. It also shows that SARPL performs better when dealing with RA1 than with RA2. The main reason is that in a RA2 type attack, the malicious node abides by all the rules of the RPL packet routing procedures except that it chooses the worst parent instead of the best as the next hop for upstream packet forwarding. In the simulation, the attacking nodes are deployed randomly over the network topology (grid). Thus, if the attacking node is already closer to the DODAG root node, even choosing the worst parent will allow it to escape SARPLs condition (8) for detection of RA2-type rank attacks.

B. Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR)

PDR is an important parameter for analyzing the impact of various security attacks on network performance. PDR is

defined here as the total number of packets received by the DODAG root node divided by the total number of data packets generated by all non-root RPL nodes. Figure 6 represents the effect of a rank attack along with selective forwarding (RA1) on RPLs PDR. It also describes the performance of the SARPL scheme against security attacks that involves packet dropping by malicious nodes. The graphical representation in Figure 6 shows that a RA1-type attack, which involves a rank attack to attract traffic from its sub-DODAG and then the launch of selective forwarding to drop packets destined for DRN, can have a significant impact on RPLs' PDR. The simulation results show that an RPL network of 50 nodes having a grid topology, with 20% of the nodes being malicious that execute RA1 attacks cause the networks PDR to drop to approximately 50%. SARPL has a 100% detection ratio for attacks such as RA1. However, when a node is marked as malicious and is blacklisted from use as a preferred parent, the rest of the network nodes are left with fewer nodes to be used as the next hop towards DRN. In the worst-case scenario, this can cause holes in the network.

Fig. 6. Performance comparison of the SARPL scheme against rank attacks followed by selective forwarding and packet dropping.

Fig. 7. End-to-end packet delay comparison for SARPL vs. RPL in RA2.

The second type of rank attack (RA2) discussed in this paper does not involve selective forwarding or the dropping of data packets. Rather, the malicious node chooses the worst parent instead of the best one to impact network performance parameters, such as end-to-end packet delay. Figure 7 shows

the impact of RA2 on the average end-to-end delay of the RPL network and the performance of the SARPL scheme to mitigate its effect as proof of concept. The plot represented in Figure 7 shows that, with an increasing number of attacking nodes acting maliciously, their combined effect on the average end-to-end delay increases too. SARPL improves end-to-end delay performance of the network up to an average of 32%, when 20% of the nodes start to act maliciously. However, any attacking node will go undetected, that incurs an additional end-to-end delay, lesser than detection-threshold represented by (8).

VI. CONCLUSION

The Statistical-based Anomaly Detection Scheme SARPL has been proposed and implemented to detect and mitigate the effects of rank attacks on various network performance parameters. Two different kinds of rank attack, RA1 and RA2, were simulated and examined for the purpose this study.

The proposed scheme shown successful detection of RA1 attacking nodes and has up to 93% positive-true detection rate for RA2 type attacks. Anomaly detection of RA2 is relatively difficult compared to RA1 because the malicious nodes abide to all the rules of RPL packet routing procedures except that they choose the worst parent instead of the best one. SARPL also shows significant improvement in network performance parameters such as packet delivery ratio and end-to-end delay, while mitigating the effects of RA1 and RA2. For example: when 20% of the network nodes start to act maliciously, SARPL exhibit an average improvement of approximately 41% in packet delivery ratio and 32% in end-to-end packet delay performance.

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An Efficient Breast Cancer Segmentation System based on Deep Learning Techniques

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ABSTRACT

Breast cancer is one of the major threats that attack women around the world. Its detection and diagnosis in the early stages can greatly improve care efficiency and reduce mortality rate. Early detection of breast cancer allows medical professionals to use less intrusive treatments, such as lumpectomies or targeted medicines, improving survival rates and lowering morbidity. This study developed a breast cancer segmentation system based on an improved version of the U-Net 3+ neural network. Various optimizations were applied to this architecture to improve the localization and segmentation performance. An evaluation of different state-of-the-art networks was performed to improve the performance of the proposed breast cancer diagnosis system. Various experiments were carried out on the INbreast Full-Field Digital Mammographic dataset (INbreast FFDM). The results obtained demonstrated that the proposed model achieved a dice score of 98.47%, which is a new state-of-the-art segmentation finding, showcasing its efficiency in detecting breast cancer from mammography images with the possibility of implementation for real applications.

Keywords-breast cancer segmentation; mammography images; deep learning; dense dilated convolution; AI

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer among women. Early detection of this malignancy can significantly improve survival rates, while also costing less to cure. Advances in 3D mammography, computed tomography, CT scans, histopathological imaging, and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) are just examples of numerous breakthroughs in radiographic imaging. Breast cancer can be detected early from radiologists and pathologists using any of these imaging types. This method is not only costly, but also has a high mistake rate. According to the 2020 Cancer Report from the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), cancer is the leading or secondary cause of death. The target age range is 30 to 69 years. Lung cancer is the first cause of cancer death in both men and women. Globally, breast and prostate cancer are

among the leading causes of death for women and men, respectively. According to the IARC, breast cancer affected more than 2 million women and caused 685,000 deaths worldwide in 2020. Cancer presents an abnormal division of cells that leads to the appearance of a mass called a tumor. There are two categories of tumors: malignant (cancerous) and benign (not cancerous). Breast cancer thus manifests itself as a tumor that forms in breast cells. Through Positron Emission Tomography (PET), CT, ultrasound, histology, MRI, thermography, and mammography, accurate and early diagnosis of breast cancer can significantly improve patients' quality of life. Among these different imaging modalities, mammogram images are the best choice for diagnosing breast cancer due to their reliability and cost-effectiveness. Manual analysis of mammogram images presents various disadvantages, as it is very costly and time-consuming and can

lead to different misdiagnoses and high false positive rates. Mammography is the most popular technique to diagnose breast cancer in women that do not have symptoms of the disease. Mammograms are shown as low-energy breast X-ray images. The use of mammography has led to significant advancements in the detection of micro-calcifications and calcification clusters, owing to its high sensitivity to these features [1]. It has been shown that mammography screening reduces the death rate in general populations [2]. Mammogram images can be used for routine screening, as they have proven to be technically more suitable for screening [3].

During the last few years, deep learning-based architectures have shown great success in various fields, including indoor object detection [4], indoor wayfinding assistance navigation [5], face recognition [6], pedestrian detection [7], traffic sign detection [8] and medical image processing [9]. Deep learning techniques have been widely applied to new early diagnosis systems for breast cancer. By building such a system, a huge number of patient lives can be saved. It is important to closely observe the incidence of breast cancer-related deaths and their subsequent reduction after effective treatment. Breast cancer research has seen significant advances during the last decade [10-11]. Several non-invasive diagnostic and therapeutic tools are used to see into the human body [13-13]. Any of the imaging techniques can detect breast cancer in its early stages, but they cannot demonstrate malignancy on their own [14]. Cancer cells tend to accumulate in interstitial tissue veins or fluid, and their malignancy is usually detected by microscopic examination of cancer tissues [15]. Biopsy procedures, such as surgical incisions or needle paths, may result in an acceleration of malignancy spread by dragging cancer cells along [16]. In mammography for breast cancer diagnosis, the pectoral muscle is often removed during preprocessing to improve detection rates [17]. Mammography is limited to the detection of anomalies within the breast region, achieved by the exclusion of the pectoral muscle and surrounding background regions.

This study aims to investigate a novel method for the detection and diagnosis of breast cancer. An enhanced version of the U-Net 3+ [18] neural network served as the foundation for the proposed system. Training and testing trials were conducted on the INbreast FFDM dataset [19], showing new and cutting-edge results and performance. The motivation behind using a modified U-Net 3+ architecture for medical image segmentation lies in its ability to address specific challenges and requirements in the field of medical imaging. U-Net 3+ is an extension of the original U-Net architecture, which was designed for semantic segmentation tasks in various domains, including medical imaging. Medical images often come in high resolutions and may contain fine details that are crucial for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning. The U-Net3+ architecture is well-suited for multiscale segmentation tasks, being able to capture both global and local features in images. This is important in order to identify anatomical structures and abnormalities with varying sizes. Medical image datasets are typically smaller and more challenging to acquire compared to other image domains. The U-Net 3+ architecture is known for its effectiveness in learning from limited data, making it a suitable choice for medical applications where large datasets are often not available due to privacy and ethical

constraints. In medical image segmentation, the distribution of foreground (abnormality) and background (normal tissue) pixels is often highly imbalanced. U-Net3+, when properly configured, can handle class imbalance issues and help to produce accurate segmentation maps by focusing on the areas of interest. In general, the choice to use a modified U-Net3+ architecture for medical image segmentation was motivated by its ability to address the unique challenges and requirements of the medical imaging domain, ultimately helping to obtain more accurate and clinically relevant segmentation results. The main contributions of this study are:

- Proposing a breast cancer detection system based on mammography image segmentation.
- Proposing an image segmentation network based on modifying the U-Net3+ model to extract more relevant semantic features.
- Evaluation of the proposed network on a realistic dataset and achieve high performance.

II. RELATED WORKS

Segmentation of breast cancer is essential to save lives by facilitating early detection, accurate diagnosis, treatment planning, disease monitoring, surgical guidance, and supporting research and development in breast cancer care. Early breast cancer diagnosis has been investigated in many studies. Mammography images are widely used in modern medical procedures to identify breast cancer [20]. In [21], Conditional Random Field (CRF) and Structured Support Vector Machine (SSVM) were introduced to classify mass mammography, using deep convolution and prospective operations based on belief networks. However, it was determined that the SSVM model exhibited lower performance compared to the CRF model in terms of training and inference durations. In [22], a Full-resolution Convolutional Network (FrCN) was proposed, using X-ray mammograms from the INbreast dataset [19] and four-fold cross-validation. The Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) for the FrCN model was 98.96%, the F1-score was 99.24%, and it had the high accuracy of 95.66%. In [23], the BDR-CNN-GCN was proposed, which combined a CNN with 8 layers, including dropout and batch normalization layers with a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN). This model was evaluated in the MIAS dataset. By combining the two-layer GCN with the CNN in the final model, the system was able to attain an accuracy of 96.10%.

In [24], the YOLOv5 network was adapted to recognize and classify breast cancers by testing various parameter values. Faster RCNN and YOLOv3 were outperformed by the upgraded YOLOv5 model, which had an accuracy of 96.50% and an MCC of 93.50%. In [25], the IRMA mammography dataset was used to evaluate a model for categorizing mammograms as normal or abnormal based on a variety of variables. In [26], the Lifting Wavelet Transform (LWT) method was used to extract information from breast mammograms. When the size of the feature vectors was reduced using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), the accuracy rates for the

classification of the MIAS and DDSM datasets using Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) and moth flame optimization were 95.80% and 98.76%, respectively. In [27], the CNN Inception-v3 model was used, trained on a dataset consisting of 316 images. The model achieved an Area Under the Curve (AUC) value of 0.946, a specificity of 0.87, and a sensitivity of 0.88. In [28], a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with Transfer Learning (TL) was proposed to assess the effectiveness of eight improved pre-trained models. In [29], Mobilenet, ResNet50, and Alexnet were combined to produce a hybrid classification model with an accuracy of 95.6%.

Low contrast and typical changes in breast tissue density make it particularly difficult to accurately detect and classify breast masses on mammograms. Various Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems are intended to assist radiologists in properly classifying breast abnormalities. In [30], a new breast cancer mass detection system was proposed, which showed very encouraging performance. A multiclass SVM model and K-means clustering were coupled with Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) algorithms to improve the accuracy in classifying breast cancers from mammography images. In [31], a breast cancer segmentation system based on EnsembleNet was proposed, achieving very effective classification results of 96.72% accuracy. In [32], the strengths of deep learning with a pre-trained ResNet50V2 model and ensemble-based machine learning approaches were combined to propose a reliable hybrid breast cancer diagnosis method. Deep learning allows the method to learn and retrieve obscure breast cancer patterns, while the interpretability and generalizability provided by machine learning algorithms are invaluable. Extensive studies were performed using a publicly accessible Invasive Ductal Carcinoma (IDC) breast histopathology imaging dataset with samples of varying sizes. The experimental results provided convincing arguments in favor of the stability and performance of the proposed hybrid model, but it was computationally extensive with a complicated training paradigm. Additional aspects like preprocessing, data augmentation, and transfer learning can alter the models' ability to attain improved accuracy because different deep learning models on the same database have varied accuracy ratings. In [33], a deep learning algorithm was proposed to create a fully automated model that would preprocess, segment, and categorize the severity of cancer spread from images collected from patients.

III. THE PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Automatic segmentation of human organs is crucial for the early detection and diagnosis of cancer. CNN has recently shown excellent performance in segmentation tests. The U-Net model, known for its use of an encoder-decoder design, is often used for medical image segmentation. Skip connections are used to link the high-level semantic feature maps of the decoder with the corresponding low-level detailed feature maps of the encoder. U-Net++ also included layered and dense skip connections to improve these connections, with the intent to bridge the semantic gap between the encoder and decoder. This approach aimed to mitigate the blending of semantically disparate characteristics resulting from the use of fundamental skip connections in the U-Net architecture. Despite producing

respectable results, this method is still unable to examine enough data from all scales. To achieve improved segmentation results, this study was based on the U-Net 3+ neural network, which has the following new advantages:

- **Enhanced feature extraction:** U-Net3+ incorporates a deep feature extraction pathway that captures both low- and high-level features of the input image. This allows the network to learn more meaningful representations and to make accurate predictions.
- **Multiscale context aggregation:** The U-Net3+ network utilizes skip connections to concatenate features from different resolution levels. This enables it to capture both local and global context information, leading to improved segmentation results, especially for objects of varying scales.
- **Integration of dense skip connections:** In addition to traditional skip connections, U-Net3+ introduces dense skip connections that connect each encoder layer to all decoder layers. This dense connectivity helps in the flow of information across different levels of the network, facilitating better feature reuse and gradient propagation.
- **Efficient parameter utilization:** U-Net3+ incorporates dense convolutions and squeeze-and-excitation blocks, which enable efficient parameter utilization. These mechanisms help reduce the number of parameters in the network while maintaining or even improving its segmentation performance.
- **Robustness to limited training data:** U-Net3+ has been shown to exhibit robust performance even with limited training data. The network's ability to capture both local and global context information and its dense skip connections aid in handling data scarcity scenarios.
- **Versatility across different segmentation tasks:** The U-Net3+ architecture is highly versatile and can be adapted to various image segmentation tasks, such as semantic segmentation, instance segmentation, and medical image segmentation. It has demonstrated competitive performance in different domains.

Although U-Net 3+ provides various advantages, it also provides different disadvantages, as it increases computational complexity by introducing additional pathways for information flow, including dense skip connections and feature concatenation. This increases the computational complexity of the network, requiring more memory and computational resources during training and inference steps. The following optimizations can be achieved on the U-Net3+ neural network: By integrating full-scale skip connections, which combine low-level details with high-level semantics from full-scale feature maps with fewer parameters, deep supervision to learn hierarchical representations from full-scale aggregated feature maps and optimizing a hybrid loss function to improve the organ border, it fully utilizes multiscale characteristics. Additionally, the proposed approach introduces a module led by classification to mitigate the issue of over-segmentation in non-organ pictures. The U-Net 3+ provides three main improvements, which are analyzed below.

A. Full-Scale Skip Connection

The connectivity of the encoder and decoder and the intra-connection of the decoder subnetworks are changed via full-scale skip connections. To fully capture fine-grained features and coarse-grained semantics, U-Net 3+ simultaneously uses the same-scale but smaller feature maps that are generated by the encoder and larger-scale characteristics from the decoder. U-Net 3+ redesigned skip connections and full-scale deep supervision to integrate multiscale features, using fewer parameters but producing a more precise position-aware and boundary-enhanced segmentation map compared to U-Net and U-Net++. The characteristics obtained from the third encoder block X_{En}^3 are directly received by the decoder. The low-level detailed information from the smaller-scale encoder layer is sent via a network of skip connections in an inter-encoder-decoder architecture between the X_{En}^1 and X_{En}^2 layers. Various optimizations have been applied to the original U-Net 3+ architecture to explore all the information provided in the input images. The max-pooling layers were replaced by dense dilated convolution layers with various dilation rates. In contrast to high-level semantic information that is transmitted from larger-scale decoder layers X_{De}^4 and X_{De}^5 , a network of intra-decoder skip links uses bilinear interpolation. To effectively integrate both superficial and semantic information, a feature aggregation technique was performed on the concatenated feature map obtained from 5 different scales. The proposed approach incorporates a ReLU activation function, batch normalization, and 320 3x3 filters. Each decoder feature map in the U-Net 3+ network will be derived from N scales. Figure 1 shows the precise architectural layout of the third decoder layer.

Fig. 1. Third decoder construction architecture.

B. Full-Scale Deep Supervision

Full-scale deep supervision is additionally implemented in the U-Net 3+ to train structured representations from the full-scale aggregated map of characteristics. In the U-Net 3+ architecture, a multiscale structural similarity index (MS-SSIM) loss function has been proposed to offer the fuzzy border with extra weights and further improve the organ boundary. As a result, the U-Net 3+ architecture is designed to monitor the fuzzy border, since it has been shown that a greater regional distribution difference corresponds to an increased

MS-SSIM value. The convolution transpose was employed as a second optimization applied to the U-Net 3+ network in place of the bilinear interpolation. Many benefits, including upsampling, learnable upsampling, sharing of parameters, end-to-end learning, and reconstructive capabilities, are offered by convolution transpose operations. To achieve deep supervision, the final layer of each decoder stage is passed through a simple 3x3 convolution layer. This is followed by transpose convolution and the application of a sigmoid function. To improve the definition of organ boundaries, a loss function called the multiscale structural similarity index (MS-SSIM) [33] was used. This loss function assigns greater emphasis to indistinct or fuzzy boundaries by assigning them higher weights. This loss function can be calculated as:

$$l_{ms_ssim} = 1 - \prod_{m=1}^M \left(\frac{2\mu_p\mu_g + C_1}{\mu_p^2 + \mu_g^2} \right)^{\beta_m} \left(\frac{2\sigma_{pg} + C_2}{\sigma_p^2 + \sigma_g^2 + C_2} \right)^{\gamma_m} \quad (1)$$

where β_m and γ_m present the importance of the two components for each scale, M presents the total number of scales, μ_p , μ_g , σ_p , and σ_g are the standard deviations of P , and σ_{pg} presents their covariance. C_1 and C_2 are two constants set to $C_1 = 0.01^2$ and $C_2 = 0.03^2$.

C. Classification-Guided Module (CGM)

The appearance of false positives in non-organ pictures is a natural occurrence in the vast majority of medical image segmentation. Noisy information is probably the root of the problem. Over-segmentation occurs because the background layer is still the shallower layer. This architecture overcame the problem by introducing a second classification assignment that determines whether or not the input image comprises organs to produce a more accurate segmentation. As seen in Figure 1, the deepest-level X_{En} ensures the creation of a two-dimensional tensor after some procedures, each of which depicts the likelihood of having or not having organs. These processes include dropout, convolution, transpose convolution, and sigmoid. The classification result can guide each segmentation side output in two steps, using the most detailed semantic information. To further optimize the proposed model, the adaptive max-pooling layer in the original U-Net 3+ architecture was substituted by an adaptive average-pooling that presents the following advantages: Flexibility in input size, consistent output size, preservation of spatial information, robustness to noise and outliers, and reduction of computational complexity.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Dataset and Materials

INbreast [19] is a publicly available database specifically designed for breast cancer research and related applications. It consists of a collection of digital mammography images and associated clinical data. It is an openly accessible dataset for research on breast cancer detection and diagnosis. This study focused on Full-Field Digital Mammography (FFDM), a commonly used imaging technology utilized in the detection of breast cancer. The collection comprises 115 mammographic images from 115 distinct patients. Each scan generally includes four mammographic images, including craniocaudal (CC) and mediolateral oblique (MLO) views of both breasts. The

mammographic images in the dataset have a dimension of 2816x3328 pixels. The dataset offers ground-truth annotations for various abnormalities seen in mammograms, such as masses and microcalcifications. These annotations can be used for tasks like computer-aided detection or classification. The dataset contains additional patient data, including age and breast density. The impact of these characteristics on breast cancer diagnosis can be studied using these metadata. Figure 3 provides some examples of images in the INbreast dataset.

Fig. 2. Sample images of the INbreast FFDM dataset.

The dataset was used to examine the effectiveness and reliability of the proposed method in detecting breast cancer. The INbreast dataset has 336 mammography images, 269 of which are abnormal and 69 normal. Of the abnormal images, 49 are malignant and 220 are benign. Tables I and II provide some statistics from the INbreast dataset in terms of normal and abnormal, malignant, and benign. During the experiments, various parameter values were adopted. Table III provides all the experimental settings used. The initial learning rate was fixed at 0.01 and the Adam optimizer was used as the learning algorithm. The batch size was kept at 8 due to limitations in graphics memory.

TABLE I. NORMAL AND ABNORMAL STATISTICS IN THE INBREAST DATASET

Total images (normal)	Training (normal)	Testing (normal)	Total images (abnormal)	Training (abnormal)	Testing (abnormal)
67	40	27	269	162	107

TABLE II. BENIGN AND MALIGNANT STATISTICS IN THE INBREAST DATASET

Total images (benign)	Training (benign)	Testing (benign)	Total images (malignant)	Training (malignant)	Testing (malignant)
220	132	88	49	29	20

TABLE III. HYPERPARAMETER CONFIGURATION FOR THE PROPOSED MODEL

Parameter	Value
Learning rate	0.01
Optimizer	Adam
Weight decay	0.00001
Number of iterations	1000
Batch size	8

B. Evaluation Metrics

Accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score are a few of the evaluation criteria used to assess how effective the proposed method is. The dice score is commonly used in image

segmentation and evaluation tasks in medical imaging. It is calculated as follows:

$$Dice\ score = (2 * |A \cap B|) / (|A| + |B|) \quad (6)$$

where A is the first set or binary image, B is the second set or binary image, $|A|$ represents the cardinality (number of elements) of set A , $|B|$ represents the cardinality of set B , and $|A \cap B|$ represents the cardinality of the intersection of sets A and B , i.e. the number of elements common to both sets. Insufficient data is an often-encountered challenge in deep learning models, which may lead to the danger of overfitting. In this study, a data augmentation method was used to mitigate this concern. These experiments employed rotation and flipping data augmentation techniques.

C. Results and Discussion

Table IV shows the confusion matrix of the proposed optimized version of the U-Net 3+ network on the INbreast dataset. The percentage of actual tumors that optimized U-Net 3+ accurately identified as tumors (TP) was 98%. Additionally, 95% of non-tumors were accurately recognized by the proposed optimized U-Net 3+ as non-tumors (TN).

TABLE IV. CONFUSION MATRIX RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED OPTIMIZED U-NET3+ ON INBREAST DATASET

Predictions	Optimized U-Net3+		
	Ground Truth		
	Malignant	Malignant	Benign
Malignant	98% (TP)	02% (FN)	
Benign	05% (FP)	95% (TN)	

TP: True Positive, FP: False Positive, TN: True Negative, FN: False negative

A large number of training epochs may cause model overfitting, while a few epochs may lead the model to divergence. To address this problem, various experiments were conducted, and the best result was 20 epochs, each containing 1000 iterations. Table V shows the results obtained by U-Net 3+ and optimized U-Net 3+. Table VI shows a segmentation comparison using the dice score metric. The U-Net 3+ dice score was 97.29% while the proposed optimized version achieved 98.47%.

TABLE V. OBTAINED PERFORMANCE

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Dice score (%)
U-Net 3+	94.5	93	96	96	97.29
Optimized U-Net 3+	96.5	95	98	96.47	98.47

TABLE VI. SEGMENTATION COMPARISON RESULTS

Model	Dice score (%)
Connected U-Net [34]	94.45
Connected-SegNets [35]	96.34
U-Net 3+	97.29
Optimized U-Net 3+	98.47

The proposed optimized U-Net 3+ network produced the best segmentation results compared to other recent methods. Figure 4 shows the segmentation results produced by the proposed model and the SegNet [35]. The segmentation maps

created by the optimized U-Net 3+ model were of higher quality and included fewer errors.

Fig. 3. Examples of breast tumor segmentation results.

D. Ablation Study

During the recent years, several DL models have been developed and applied to the segmentation of breast tumors. These DL models have segregated breast tumors on mammograms with remarkable success, but have high rates of false positive and false negative findings. To increase performance, various modules and layers were changed in the U-Net 3+ network. Several strategies were included in the suggested method. As a first optimization, transpose convolution was used instead of bilinear interpolation. The convolution transpose operation increased the spatial dimensions of the input feature map, preserving some characteristics of the original image, as it can be used to upsample images or create higher-resolution from lower-resolution images.

As a second optimization, max-pooling layers were replaced by dense dilated convolution. Due to its special characteristics, dense dilated convolution, also known as dilated or atrous convolution, is essential in segmentation tasks. Dense dilated convolution can capture bigger receptive fields without adding more parameters or lowering feature map resolution, which is a considerable advantage. This is crucial in segmentation tasks because it is crucial to comprehend the context and interactions between things. Dense dilated convolution, which incorporates dilations, enables the network to gather data from a larger area and simulate long-range dependencies, making it easier to include global context into the segmentation process.

The third optimization was replacing the adaptive max-pooling layer with an adaptive average-pooling layer. The ability of adaptive average pooling layers to handle input data of various sizes is a significant benefit. Adaptive average pooling layers dynamically adjust their pooling areas to meet the input size, in contrast to classic pooling layers that demand set kernel sizes. This adaptive behavior makes the network more adaptable and suitable to various image sizes or variable-sized inputs in general, by enabling the network to accept inputs of arbitrary spatial dimensions. Table VII provides the segmentation performance obtained for all optimizations.

TABLE VII. IMPACT OF VARIOUS OPTIMIZATIONS ON THE SEGMENTATION PERFORMANCES

Optimization	Dice score (%)	Parameter number (M)
Transpose convolution	97.32	44.88
Dilated convolution	97.51	45.06
Adaptive average pooling	97.65	43.42
Original U-Net 3+	97.29	43.55
Proposed optimized U-Net 3+ (combination)	98.47	45.35

As shown in Table VII, when changing the bilinear interpolation to transpose convolution, a slight increase was achieved in terms of F1-score and number of parameters. When changing the max-pooling layers by dilated convolution layers, the F1-score increased compared to the original U-Net 3+ network, while the number of parameters increased by around 1.5 M. When changing the adaptive max-pooling layer to an adaptive average-pooling layer, the segmentation efficiency was increased while the number of parameters was almost the same, as the pooling operation is a parameterless technique. Combining the three techniques in the proposed optimized U-Net 3+, the best dice score of 98.47% was achieved, with a slight increase in the number of parameters compared to the original U-Net 3+ network.

V. CONCLUSION

Segmentation of breast cancer is of paramount importance, as it helps early detection, accurate diagnosis, treatment planning, quantitative analysis, personalized medicine, research, and prognosis. Using segmentation techniques, healthcare professionals can improve patient outcomes, optimize treatment strategies, and contribute to ongoing advances in breast cancer care. This study proposes a breast cancer segmentation system based on an optimized version of U-Net 3+. Various optimizations were applied to the U-Net 3+ neural network to improve spatial visibility and segmentation performance. Extensive experiments were conducted on the INbreast dataset. The obtained results proved the efficiency and the superior performance of the proposed method over known state-of-the-art methods. This superior performance was demonstrated by achieving the highest dice score, which was 98.47%. The main limitation of the proposed model is that it may struggle with anatomical variations between patients, such as differences in organ shapes and sizes. The model may require substantial adaptation or patient-specific fine-tuning to effectively handle such variability. Future research endeavors will mainly focus on the integration of novel deep-learning methods for cancer identification and classification, with the ultimate goal of automating the breast cancer diagnostic process.

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Investigation of the Stiffness and Ductility of Pre-Cracked RC Beams after repairing with CFRP using Different Strengthening Methods

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the stiffness and ductility of rectangular Reinforced Concrete (RC) beams. The beams were obtained through an experimental program that included one reference and eight RC beams, divided into two separate groups strengthened with Externally Bonded Reinforcement (EBR) and Near-Surface Mounted (NSM) reinforcement in flexural using Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) laminate after they were pre-cracked or damaged at different levels. The comparison results of the reference and the strengthened beams showed that the latter had a higher degree of stiffness. The stiffness in the yielding stage increased by 6.43% to 19.81% for the EBR-strengthened group and by 31.08% to 105.8% for the NSM-strengthened group. At the 140 kN loading stage, the stiffness increased by 33 to 101.5% for the EBR-strengthened group and by 136.5% to 332.25% for the NSM-strengthened group. At the ultimate load stage, the stiffness increased by 12.72% to 46.13% for the EBR-strengthened group and by 56.85% to 122.94% for the NSM-strengthened group. On the other hand, the comparison revealed that the ductility of the reference beam was much better than that of the reinforced beams.

Keywords-stiffness; ductility; pre-cracked; CFRP; reinforced concrete; flexural strengthening

I. INTRODUCTION

A lot of Reinforced Concrete (RC) structures have been damaged. Most of them have a variety of deteriorations that are worsening, such as cracks and concrete spalling. These deteriorations may be traced back to a wide number of factors, such as the passage of time, steel corrosion, earthquakes, environmental effects, and the effects of unintended impacts on the structure. In the absence of steel reinforcements, plain concrete is more likely to crack and break apart when subjected to significant tensile pressures. Recent innovations include using Fiber-Reinforced Polymers (FRP) and steel fibers to increase the tensile strength of concrete. Once it is determined that a structure is in jeopardy, it must either be repaired or strengthened to raise its strength and either return to its prior level of strength or be able to handle an increased load. The use of Near-Surface Mounted (NSM) technology is the most effective method for reinforcing concrete structures to withstand shear and flexure loads. In addition, an Externally Bonded Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (EBR-CFRP) is used to increase the existing structural element's ability to support additional loads. Structure components may be made more robust using CFRP [1-9].

Several experiments have been carried out to evaluate RC beams after being strengthened with CFRP using the EBR technique. In [10], RC beams that were pre-loaded with a steel-yielding capacity of either 40% or 60% were strengthened using hybrid and continuous carbon fiber sheets. Carbon sheets with high modulus and high strength have been used in hybrid systems. The hybrid concrete's yielding load, flexural stiffness, post-yielding ductility, and crack breadth were all improved by the addition of carbon sheets with a high modulus. The hybrid system designs ignored discrepancies in the slopes of the steel-yielding load-deflection curves. Concrete may be crushed by larger pieces of high-modulus carbon that are dispersed more widely. High-modulus carbon fibers can have these qualities if they have stiffness and low ultimate tensile strain, while debonding and fracture resistance may be improved by increasing the strength of fiber-reinforced polymer composites. In [11], continuous beams were repaired using CFRP composites, using one control beam and four CFRP-laminated beams. Shear fractures were caused by pre-loading the beams to 224 kN before CFRP wrapping. Experimental results showed that CFRP-repaired beams had 18-44% higher shear capacity, matched well with a theoretical study using an

established model, and CFRP strips can improve the shear capacity of cracked continuous beams.

In [12], severely deteriorated RC beams were laminated with CFRP and end-anchored. The beams used in a medieval bridge construction were bent to increase their strength in four places. It was determined that there was a vertical displacement at the beam's midspan by using linear variable differential transformers to perform a quick discharge on specimens while applying the yield load. After CFRP strengthening, these highly compromised specimens were loaded to the point of collapse. An externally bonded CFRP layer can improve the flexural performance of an aging or badly damaged RC beam. According to this study, the yield loads of reinforced beams can reach anywhere between 5 and 36%, depending on the anchoring effect, the length of the bond, and the size of the CFRP sheet. In [13], the flexural behavior of pre-damaged RC beams reinforced with CFRP plates was studied using experimental, analytical, and FEM modeling. Before strengthening, RC beams were preloaded with yield loads of 30, 50, and 70%. Two CarboDur S512 plates and eight 3×12 RC beams were bent. CFRP plate debonding and bending zone flexural crack propagation destroyed all RC-strengthened beams, while exterior-bonded CFRP had 70-80% more moment capacity than unstrengthened beams. In [14-16], the behavior of beams after CFRP reinforcement was investigated. In [17], the length of the CFRP strip was examined on CFRP-reinforced slabs after experimental preloading. The CFRP strip length increased mid-span deflection by 59.9, 39.4, and 27.1%, improving the flexural performance of the RC slab [17]. In [18], corrosion-damaged RC beams were rehabilitated using CFRP, while in [19-20] heat-damaged RC beams and joints were repaired using CFRP [18-20].

This study focused on the stiffness and ductility of RC beams after they had been damaged and then reinforced with CFRP, based on the results of an experimental investigation.

II. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The experimental procedure included casting and testing nine RC beams, pre-cracked by pre-loading with various levels: 20, 40, 60, and 80% of the ultimate load of the reference beam. The beams were 2000×200×300 mm and tested for their flexural strength with a two-point static load, as shown in Figure 1, with steel reinforcement of two 12 mm bars at the bottom and two 10 mm bars at the top, as well as stirrup reinforcement of 10 mm with 125 mm spacing in the center of the beam and 80 mm in the edges. Four of the eight beams were strengthened by EBR, and the other four were strengthened with NSM.

A. Materials' Properties

Table I shows the properties of all the materials, including reinforcing steel bars, concrete, CFRP, and epoxy for the bonding between the CFRP and the beams.

B. Test Setup

Figure 2 presents the test setup details.

Fig. 1. The beam details and EBR and NSM groups.

TABLE I. MATERIALS PROPERTIES

Properties MPa	Steel bars		Concrete	CFRP Sika® CarboDur® S	Epoxy Sikadur-30 LP
	12mm	10mm			
Tensile yield	677	587	-	-	-
Tensile strength	772	662	-	3100	17
Modulus of elasticity	200000		26918	170000	10000
Compressive strength	-	-	32.8	-	-
Modulus of rupture	-	-	3.6	-	-

Fig. 2. Test setup.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION FOR STIFFNESS AND DUCTILITY

The experimental results showed different behavior between stiffness and ductility. This difference occurred due to the effect of using CFRP as a flexural strengthening material. In terms of stiffness, the results showed that the stiffness of the beams increased after applying the CFRP compared to the reference beam for both strengthening groups. Three stages of loading were examined to investigate stiffness: the yielding load, the ultimate load of the reference beam (140.1 kN), and the final ultimate failure load. The stiffness in the yielding stage increased by 6.43-19.81% for the EBR-strengthened

group and by 31.08% to 105.8% for the NSM-strengthened group. At the 140.1 kN loading stage, the stiffness increased by 33-101.5% for the EBR-strengthened group and 136.5-332.25% for the NSM-strengthened group. At the ultimate load stage, the stiffness increased by 12.72-46.13% for the EBR-strengthened group and 56.85-122.94% for the NSM-

strengthened group, as shown in Table II. This results in the conclusion that CFRP significantly increased the stiffness, and is a good indicator for using the CFRP to strengthen structural members even after applying pre-loading, such as in this case. Figure 3 presents the stiffness of the beam in the three stages.

TABLE II. STIFFNESS OF THE BEAMS AT THREE STAGES OF LOADING

Specimens	Yielding Stage				140.1 kN Load Stage				Ultimate Stage			
	Δ	P	K	Increasing % in k	Δ	P	K	Increasing % in k	Δ	P	K	Increasing % in k
BC1	16.8	107.1	6.37	Ref.	35	140.1	4	Ref.	35	140.1	4.01	Ref.
B-EBR-80	18.5	117.2	6.33	-0.62	26.33	140.1	5.32	33	32.1	145.1	4.52	12.72
B-EBR-60	18.2	123.4	6.78	6.43	21.75	140.1	6.44	61	30.5	150.2	4.92	22.69
B-EBR-40	19.4	130.1	6.70	5.18	19.81	140.1	7.07	76.75	29.5	160.1	5.42	35.16
B-EBR-20	18.5	141.3	7.63	19.78	17.38	140.1	8.06	101.5	28	164.2	5.86	46.13
B-NSM-80	19	158.7	8.35	31.08	14.8	140.1	9.46	136.5	28.4	178.7	6.29	56.85
B-NSM-60	17.5	177.2	10.12	58.87	11.63	140.1	12.04	201	27.5	200.2	7.28	81.54
B-NSM-40	16.7	194.78	11.66	83.04	9.1	140.1	15.39	284.75	26.8	209.4	7.81	94.76
B-NSM-20	15.7	205.94	13.11	105.8	8.1	140.1	17.29	332.25	24.6	220	8.94	122.94

Δ: Deflection, P: load, and K: stiffness, $K = P/\Delta$.

Fig. 3. Stiffness at three stages of loading.

In terms of ductility, the results showed that the CFRP as a flexural strengthening method reduced the ductility of the RC beams for both groups compared to the reference beam, from 2.08 to 1.51 and 1.56 for the beams strengthened with EBR and NSM, respectively, as shown in Table III. This was due to the CFRP being a brittle material with a low modulus of elasticity. Hence, the beam keeps having the load without a large changing deflection. Figure 4 shows the histogram of the results. The ductility was obtained by dividing the ultimate deflection by the yielding deflection [21].

TABLE III. DUCTILITY OF STRENGTHENED BEAMS

Specimens	Δ yield	Δ ultimate	Ductility
BC1	16.8	35	2.08
B-EBR-80	18.5	32.1	1.73
B-EBR-60	18.2	30.5	1.67
B-EBR-40	19.4	29.5	1.52
B-EBR-20	18.5	28	1.51
B-NSM-80	19	28.4	1.49
B-NSM-60	17.5	27.5	1.57
B-NSM-40	16.7	26.8	1.60
B-NSM-20	15.7	24.6	1.56

$$Ductility = \Delta_{ultimate} / \Delta_{yield}$$

Fig. 4. Ductility of the strengthened beams.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the two essential properties, stiffness and ductility, of pre-cracked RC beams, reinforced by CFRP with EBR and NSM. These properties provide a good indicator of the behavior of the RC beams after strengthening with CFRP laminate. Based on the experimental results, the following can be concluded:

- The stiffness of the RC beams increased due to the use of CFRP laminate in all three stages for the strengthened beams in both groups compared to the reference beam. Stiffness at the yielding stage increased by 6.43-19.81% for the EBR-strengthened group and by 31.08-105.8% for the NSM-strengthened group. At the 140.1 kN loading stage, stiffness increased by 33-101.5% for the EBR-strengthened group and by 136.5-332.25% for the NSM-strengthened group. At the ultimate load stage, the stiffness increased by 12.72-46.13% for the EBR-strengthened group and by 56.85-122.94% for the NSM-strengthened group. These results show that CFRP made the RC beams stronger and increased their load before failure.
- The ductility results showed different behavior compared to stiffness. The ductility of the strengthened beams reduced compared to the reference beam from 2.08 to 1.51 and 1.56 for the EBR and NSM-strengthened beams, respectively. This is probably due to CFRP being made of brittle materials.
- The reduction in ductility observed in the strengthened beams can be attributed to the use of CFRP, which while improving other mechanical properties such as stiffness and strength, does not provide the same level of ductility as other materials.

Engineers and designers who employ CFRP materials in structural concrete applications should consider these trade-offs. Although CFRP can improve structural performance in strength and stiffness, it may not be sufficient to guarantee that the structural system has sufficient ductility to survive possible overloads or seismic events without incorporating additional mechanisms or materials.

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Mapping Paddy Cropland in Guntur District using Machine Learning and Google Earth Engine utilizing Images from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2

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ABSTRACT

Ensuring global food security necessitates vigilant monitoring of crop quantity and quality. Therefore, the reliable classification of croplands and diverse Land Covers (LC) becomes pivotal in fostering sustainable agricultural progress and safeguarding national food security. The Seasonal Crop Inventory (SCI) emerges as a strong asset. In this study, Sentinel-1 (S1) and Sentinel-2 (S2) image data were used to show varied land uses and paddy crops in Guntur district, Andhra Pradesh, India, during the 2021 growing season. Employing a technologically advanced space-based remote sensing approach, this study exploited the Google Earth Engine (GEE) and a range of classification techniques, including Random Forest (RF) and Classification Regression Trees (CART), to generate pixel-based SCI tailored to the area under investigation. The results underscored the reliability of GEE-based cropland mapping in the region, demonstrating a satisfactory level of classification accuracy, surpassing 97% across distinct time intervals in overall accuracy values, Kappa coefficients, and F1-Score.

Keywords-paddy; cropland mapping; machine learning; GEE; Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2; Guntur

I. INTRODUCTION

Rice is ingested by more than 50% of the Earth's inhabitants, and rice paddies cover more than 10% of the total cropland worldwide. On a global scale, rice is the main contributor among plant-based sources to the discharge of greenhouse gases [1]. Precise and current data on rice production are of paramount importance in achieving food and environmental objectives and safeguarding access to water. Such a significance was particularly pronounced in Malaysia, where the main staple food is rice. To guarantee domestic nutrition supply, the Malaysian administration has established an ambition to achieve a rice Self-Sufficiency Level (SSL) of 70% [2]. To evaluate the success in attaining the SSL rice target, precise and current data is needed on cultivable rice fields and their harvestable yield. Presently, data on rice fields are obtained through field surveys, which are not

comprehensive, require a significant amount of time, and lack specific spatial information.

Remote sensing technology has found an extensive application in the global mapping of rice fields. Over the past two decades, Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) data, known for their frequent temporal captures, have been extensively employed for this purpose [3-4]. Although this technique can detect paddy fields, the limited spatial resolution of MODIS data (500 m) is inadequate for accurately discerning paddy fields owned by small-scale farmers in Southeast Asia, which typically span less than one hectare in size [5-8]. In recent times, there has been a notable development with the emergence of Sentinel-1 (S1) and Sentinel-2 (S2) satellites, which provide data with both high spatial resolution (10 m) and frequent temporal captures (every 12 days). In particular, the two-satellite constellation of

Sentinel-2 enhances its temporal resolution to an impressive interval of 5 days. Numerous research efforts have presented the effective utilization of S1 data for the mapping of rice fields in different nations, such as Vietnam [9-10], China [11-14], the USA and Spain [15], India [16-17], the Mediterranean region [18], Iran [19], Bangladesh [20], South Korea [21], Indonesia and Malaysia [22], Philippines [23], Thailand [1, 24], and Myanmar [25]. Simultaneously, S2 has also proven its efficiency in accurately mapping rice fields in the context of Egypt [26] and China [27-29]. Several research investigations have used the combined dataset of satellite data to effectively chart the location of rice cultivation, particularly in areas with moderate climates, such as Japan [30].

Remote sensing computational platforms, such as Google Earth Engine (GEE), offer convenient availability of datasets and algorithms, providing valuable assets for research. In addition to functions such as image compilation, cloud identification, and categorization, these tools have versatile applications in diverse processing activities. These capabilities extend to multiple domains, including agriculture, where they enable the creation of comprehensive cropland assessments on a regional or national scale, as well as in areas related to climate change analysis. In previous studies, traditional techniques were often used to cover limited geographic extents. It should be noted that the synergistic potential of microwave satellite data alongside optical data for paddy field mapping has not been fully exploited in the context of satellite imagery across a substantial region. Within the framework of the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), a governmental initiative in Andhra Pradesh, there is a persistent priority to devise and execute innovative strategies to map paddy fields under the Seasonal Crop Inventory (SCI). The convergence of recent advancements in handling large-scale geospatial data and machine learning procedures offers promising avenues to potentially expedite and improve the accuracy of agricultural mapping in India. In this context, it becomes crucial to explore modern machine learning algorithms and cloud computing techniques, to generate precise SCI maps in an automated and functional manner. In light of these considerations, this study aimed to achieve a milestone by employing GEE and machine learning methods such as RF and CART for the inaugural classification of paddy crops and other land cover classes within a single district of Andhra Pradesh. This analysis involves the use of Sentinel satellite imagery captured in 2021. The information in these images can be used to create SCI charts and classify them into LC categories with an impressive spatial resolution of 10 m. The specific study presents a novel and comprehensive approach to mapping paddy cropland in the Guntur District, offering valuable insights into the integration of multiple data sources, machine learning, and cloud computing for agricultural and environmental monitoring. This study has practical applications for precision agriculture, land management, and policy development, ultimately contributing to sustainable and efficient land use in the region.

II. STUDY AREA

As shown in Figure 1, the research region includes one district in Andhra Pradesh, India, where paddy is grown within a small-scale rain-fed system in various agroecological

situations. The field of study is surrounded by the Bay of Bengal on its southeast, Bapatla District on its south, Palnadu District on its west, NTR District on its northwest, and Krishna District on its northeastern boundary. Covering approximately 2,443 km² (943 mi²), the area extends between 16.314209° N latitude and 80.435028° E longitude, with GPS coordinates of 16° 18' 51.1524" N latitude and 80° 26' 6.1008" E longitude. The Guntur district, where the study area is located, is primarily an agriculturally dominated region and occupies the fourth position in rice production. The region experiences tropical climatic conditions, with a yearly average temperature of 28.5°C (83.3°F) and an annual rainfall of approximately 905 mm (36 in). The influence of the southwest monsoon is evident throughout the area. During the monsoon season, June and July, the region experiences the highest monthly rainfall, with a maximum of 280 mm. In contrast, the 1 mm/month minimum rainfall is observed in December. The predominant agricultural practice is based on rain-fed paddy cultivation that is carried out during the winter months. This cultivation season extends from June to December, including paddy varieties with vegetation durations that typically range from 60 to 100 days.

Fig. 1. Study area.

III. DATA AND PRELIMINARY PROCESSING

A. Sentinel-1 Satellite

The S1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) satellite constellation comprises two polar-orbiting satellites, with the initial satellite launched on April 3, 2014. The second satellite was launched on April 25, 2016, facilitated by a Europeanized Russian Soyuz rocket. The dual-polar metric outputs of the satellite's C-SAR instrument provide valuable assistance to researchers and users involved in agricultural analysis, LC/LU classification, and forestry. The S1 satellite's C-SAR instrument caters to both horizontal and vertical polarizations (HH, HV, VV, and VH), utilizing a single transmit chain that can be adapted to VH polarization. S1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) C-band imagery (at 5.405 GHz) was obtained through the Interferometry Wide swath (IW) mode. The IW mode enables coverage of a wide-swath width (250 km) that has a medium geometry density of 10 m. The GRD Level 1

processing encompasses tasks such as mitigating thermal noise and employing an Earth ellipsoid model for ground range projection. Each GRD product incorporates images in VH and/or VV polarization. The IW images exhibit a pixel spacing of 10 m, with azimuth incidence angles ranging from 30 to 45 degrees. In this study, paddy cultivation monitoring was carried out using microwave Sentinel-1A SAR data in three production areas within the Guntur district during the growing season of 2021. The IW mode S1A GRD images used in this study were sourced from the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform, spanning from early June to December 2021 to facilitate temporal analysis. The period from June to October was chosen for cropland and vegetation type mapping. This timeframe encapsulates the entire paddy cultivation cycle, from the initial sowing to the eventual harvesting of the paddy crops.

B. Sentinel-2 Satellite

The categorization of the crops was carried out using the S2 Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) remote sensing satellite. Part of the Copernicus program, Sentinel-2 was developed by the European Space Agency (ESA), distinguished by its extensive coverage ranging from 10 to 60 m, spatial precision, multiple-spectrum capacity (encompassing 13 spectral bands), and frequent revisit cycles (ten days for one satellite and five days for a pair of satellites). The mission is well-equipped to monitor shifts in vegetation across growing seasons, oversee forest dynamics, identify land cover alterations, and provide swift responses to natural disasters. The main objective of the S2 mission is to methodically monitor terrestrial and coastal regions by providing quality visual imagery that covers vast areas and a higher review rate. This comprehensive spectral information, which spans visible, near-infrared, and shortwave infrared regions, significantly improves the ability to detect spatial and temporal fluctuations, as well as variations in vegetation status.

C. Rice Cultivation

In the Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh, paddy cultivation typically involves two primary seasons: Kharif (monsoon) and Rabi (winter). The Kharif season begins with the onset of monsoon rains in June and continues until October. The Rabi season occurs during the winter months, usually from November to February. These two seasons are the main paddy cultivation periods in the region. In general, the four monthly phases of rice growth are Tillage and Planting (T-P) (30 days), Vegetative growth (V) (30 days), reproductive (R) (30 days), and Maturity (M) (30 days).

IV. METHODOLOGY

Figure 2 shows the process steps used in this study for SCI mapping, which is based on the use of a machine-learning algorithm in conjunction with the Google Earth Engine platform. In the beginning, Regions of Interest (ROIs) were created for the location of rice fields in the Guntur district, Andhra Pradesh. These ROIs were established based on prior knowledge and verified utilizing very high-quality imagery from Google Earth. The size of the ROIs varied, with a geometric area measuring 11, 450, 082, 6.16 hectares. Data were collected for 15 days from S1 SAR, ensuring that it remained unaffected by cloud cover. However, the results did

show a considerable noise-to-signal ratio. To address this issue, time series analysis was used to mitigate noise, particularly in regions where data scenes overlapped. For crop evaluation during the 2021 Kharif season, data from S1 and S2 were used. Ten VH values were extracted, considering them as distinct bands. By manipulating these bands, various color combinations indicative of different crop types, were derived. Subsequently, crop pixel boundaries within the ROIs were delineated using geometric polygons. The next step involved merging all the rice field crop polygons and establishing training points. Finally, machine learning algorithms were employed to classify the data into different crop categories.

Fig. 2. Workflow diagram.

A. Accuracy Assessment

Accuracy assessment is a critical step in evaluating the reliability of a classification result. It involves measuring how closely the classification aligns with the actual true values. This assessment is typically carried out using confusion matrices that help calculate metrics such as Overall Accuracy (OA), Producer Accuracy (PA), and User Accuracy (UA) for crop maps. OA, for instance, is determined by comparing the proportion of reference pixels that were successfully classified to all correctly classified pixels. Analyzing the confusion matrix to understand the sources of discrepancies is an important and intriguing aspect of creating remote sensing maps. A built-in confusion matrix can be used in tools such as GEE to assess classifications in land cover types. This matrix allows a statistical comparison between the output classification and the ground truth associated with validation points.

B. Random Forest (RF)

RF is a powerful ensemble classifier that uses numerous individual decision trees to address the limitations of a single one. It makes classification decisions by aggregating the

majority "votes" from all trees. Instead of relying on a single tree, the RF incorporates multiple trees to achieve a more robust overall result. This ensemble approach helps mitigate the issues that can arise from a single tree's biases or errors. One of the notable strengths of RF is its ability to extract valuable information from each feature, contributing to its efficiency and accuracy. However, one drawback is that when using a large number of trees, it becomes challenging to visualize the individual trees due to their sheer quantity. This study used the GEE RF classifier to perform the classification. The particular approach highlights the versatility and effectiveness of RF in handling complex classification tasks.

C. Classification and Regression Tree (CART)

CART is a versatile algorithm capable of handling both classification and variable prediction tasks, much like RF. This algorithm falls within the realm of supervised machine learning, using training data to construct decision trees aiming to solve classification problems. In essence, the CART algorithm works by recursively dividing the data into subsets at each node of the tree based on the concept of normalized information gain. This normalized information gain is a key criterion for determining the attributes that define the splits in the tree. Ultimately, the final decision is made by selecting the attribute with the highest normalized information value, leading to effective classification or prediction outcomes. CART is particularly well suited for tasks involving remote sensing data, where it is often used. In the context of GEE, specific parameters such as the minimum number of leaves and the maximum number of nodes can be set to control the tree's complexity and optimize its performance.

D. F1-Score

The F1-Score is a valuable metric for evaluating classified maps. It is a statistical measure of accuracy derived from the confusion matrices, which contain reliability assessment statistics for each class. Equation (1) is used to calculate the F1-score, which represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall, fundamental metrics for assessing PA and UA. The F1-Score serves as a crucial measurement tool for assessing categorization models, offering advantages over independent UA/PA metrics. When it comes to accuracy assessment, both producers and consumers have their restrictions. Using a significant threshold can lead to more PA but significant data loss, while a low threshold may lead to elevated UA but less precise predictions. The F1-Score provides a more thorough analysis of a classifier while ensuring a balance between producer and user considerations.

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (1)$$

V. RESULTS

The spatial distribution of paddy fields in Guntur district in 2021 was determined utilizing optical and SAR data chosen together. Both RF and CART algorithms were employed for this classification task. However, Figures 3 and 4 show that the paddy field distribution differs between the selected S1 and S2 data when employing these two algorithms for classification. Figures 3 and 4 represent pixel-based paddy crop field maps for 2021 using GEE, the RF and CART algorithms, and S1 and S2

imagery. The proposed approach effectively achieved the classification of paddy cropland through visual interpretation. Table I shows detailed pixel-based accuracy results for the chosen features extracted from S1 and S2 images. Based on S2 and S1 satellite data, paddy crop maps for 2021 were created with a 10 m resolution using the GEE platform. Based on the categorized result, it seems that most of the paddy pixels had been classified. The final ROI maps were visually sharp and noise-free due to post-processing to minimize noise. The suggested strategy allowed for relatively accurate identification and classification of paddy and other types using visual interpretation. Paddy crops can be detected effectively employing the suggested approach. This area has several rice fields where a substantial amount of paddy is produced each year. RF was compared to other classification algorithms such as CART. PA and UA were both 0.99% for the RF in the map created in 2021, while the OA and KC were each 0.97%. With the help of the Sentinel satellite data utilized, a respectable F-score was produced. Paddy has proven to have discriminatory talents (>0.90) during the year.

Fig. 3. Spatial mapping of paddy using RF.

Fig. 4. Spatial mapping of paddy from S1 and S2 data using CART.

TABLE I. ACCURACY MAPS FOR 2021

LULC Name	2021RF		2021CART	
	User accuracy (%)	Producer accuracy (%)	User accuracy (%)	Producer accuracy (%)
Rice	0.99	0.99	0.80	0.81
OA	98		80	
F1-Score	98		80	

Considering different VH polarizations and the diverse development phases of paddy crops and other land cover categories, this study thoroughly investigated the seasonal and temporal variations in the S1 backscatter data. Figures 5 and 6 show the S1 SCI time series for VH polarization in ascending and descending orbits, respectively. These figures showcase the results obtained after processing and filtering the original S1 data to ensure accuracy. These findings indicate that the coefficient of backscattering in VH polarization for paddy fields falls within the range of 0 to 240 dB.

Fig. 5. Backscatter coefficient curves of RF.

Fig. 6. Backscatter coefficient curves of CART.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to establish a comprehensive classification and mapping system to identify paddy crop areas and other categories in the Guntur region, India. It represents a pioneering effort in Guntur, exploring the capabilities of the GEE editor along with ML techniques using satellite imagery, specifically S1 and S2, within the paddy-producing areas in 2021. This approach used GEE to delineate paddy croplands and other land cover classes throughout the district, employing various classification algorithms such as RF and CART. The specific research effectively demonstrated the versatility and dependability of GEE for cropland mapping. To validate the findings, an average overall accuracy rate of 98% was achieved for the year 2021. These high levels of accuracy surpass the

minimum requirements and are deemed reliable for pioneering research using GEE to build an SCI. This approach showcases a technological innovation that is not only efficient but also budget-friendly. The adoption of this method and the insights gained could have substantial implications for the development of Guntur Cropland Inventories (GCI) and the detection and identification of paddy crops. Future studies could seek to further enhance class accuracy by employing more advanced algorithms to map different crops outside of cropped regions.

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An Ensemble-based Fraud Detection Model for Financial Transaction Cyber Threat Classification and Countermeasures

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ABSTRACT

Fraud remains a pervasive challenge within the banking industry, where financial institutions and their clients grapple with substantial annual losses. The proliferation of digital transactions and online banking has created new avenues for fraudsters to exploit vulnerabilities, leading to financial harm to unsuspecting victims. Consequently, the imperative to promptly and accurately detect fraudulent transactions has grown significantly, both as a safeguard against financial crimes and as a pillar of trust between customers and the banking sector. This paper introduces an innovative fraud detection model designed for bank payment transactions using advanced ensembling techniques. This study presents a comprehensive evaluation of an ensembling model conducted on the Bank Account Fraud (BAF) dataset. Through meticulous analysis, the performance of various base models and ensembling methods was assessed and compared, employing a variety of critical metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The proposed ensemble model, referred to as "Stacking," exhibited remarkable performance, attaining a commendable accuracy score of 0.98. This result reaffirmed its prowess as a comprehensive and balanced solution to the multifaceted challenges of fraud detection. This study has paramount implications for the banking industry, offering a robust and adaptable solution to deal with the increasing threats posed by financial fraud. Furthermore, it emphasizes the significance of precision-recall trade-offs in fraud detection and underscores the potential of ensemble methods, particularly the "Stacking" model, to fortify the resilience and efficacy of existing security systems.

Keywords-cybersecurity; banking fraud; cyber scams; human vulnerability; social engineering; countermeasures

I. INTRODUCTION

Cyberattacks on banks and financial institutions have become increasingly prevalent in recent years. A 2017 survey estimated that a typical financial institution faces an average of 85% targeted cyber-attacks every year [1]. In Hungary, the banking industry observed an increasing trend in the number of cyberattacks [1-2]. The financial sector in the USA is continuously facing cyberattacks, as finance technologies are more prone to cyberattacks arising from technologically induced vulnerabilities [3]. Online banking in India has been significantly targeted by cyber attackers [4]. African corporations are facing rising cybersecurity risks, particularly in banks that are poorly performing and under-capitalized. Cyberattacks such as fraud, phishing, hacking, and ransomware attacks erode public confidence in online services, constraining the expansion of online banking [5-6]. Financial institutions are investing heavily in cybersecurity to counteract cyberattacks and cyber bank robbery attempts [7]. Cyber attacks that threaten the cyber security of banks are a significant issue that can lead to reputation and significant financial losses [8].

Fraud detection, an essential facet of this challenge, has seen the deployment of various strategies to detect fraud in bank payments [9], including rule-based methods [10], anomaly detection [11-12], and machine learning algorithms [13-14]. However, each has its limitations: rule-based methods might overlook complex patterns, while anomaly detection can confuse genuine outliers with deceitful transactions. Machine learning's effectiveness may diminish due to overfitting or noisy, imbalanced data. This evolving landscape of fraud detection methods has pivoted toward machine learning, which has emerged as an effective solution in recent years. Traditional techniques often fail against novel or intricate fraud patterns, while machine learning algorithms, from decision trees to neural networks, demonstrate prowess in understanding these patterns [11]. For example, in [15-16], the effectiveness of machine learning methods in detecting credit card fraud was investigated, and some algorithms achieved accuracy greater than 90%.

The banking sector's stride towards employing deep learning models further exemplifies the shift. Models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) have exhibited promising results in detecting intricate fraud patterns in real time [17-18]. For example, in [18], a deep learning-based credit card fraud detection system was presented that excelled in identifying fraudulent transactions, proving its worth against standard benchmarks. While individual models have their merit, the increased attention towards ensemble methods underlines the broader research trend. Ensembling, whether through bagging, boosting, or stacking, converges multiple algorithmic predictions to enhance model performance. It combines the strength of diverse models to yield more accurate and robust results while mitigating risks like overfitting. The novel contributions of this study are:

- An ensemble method for fraud detection in bank payments is proposed. The proposed model aims to capitalize on this ensembling technique, integrating algorithms such as the

Voting Classifier, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting Machine, Logistic Regression (LR), and neural networks.

- Both global and local transaction patterns are captured while ensuring adaptability over time.
- The proposed model is evaluated and validated through extensive experiments. The results showed that the proposed model achieved 98% detection accuracy.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method for developing an ensembling fraud detection model involved several steps, including data collection, pre-processing, feature engineering, model selection, and ensembling.

A. Dataset

This study used Bank Account Fraud (BAF) [19], a pioneering collection, known for being the first to be publicly accessible, privacy-oriented, large-scale, and realistically reflective of the complexities inherent in bank account fraud detection. This dataset was synthesized employing state-of-the-art tabular data generation techniques applied to an anonymized, real-world dataset on bank account fraud detection. The BAF dataset is not only robust but also highly nuanced, containing six distinct variants, each incorporating predetermined and controllable bias patterns, such as prevalence and group size disparities, grounded in a well-established data bias taxonomy. This enables a multifaceted exploration and understanding of various biases in fraud detection systems. The richness of the BAF dataset, marked by its inherent challenges, such as significant class imbalance and temporal dynamics, mirrors real-world complexities and offers an invaluable and realistic platform for evaluating both existing and innovative machine learning methods in fraud detection. The dataset is comprehensive, with 1 million instances and 30 features, accompanied by protected attributes and temporal information, enhancing the depth and breadth of analytical capabilities. In this study's context, the BAF dataset serves as a critical instrument enabling the assessment and comparison of diverse models and ensembling methods, with its varied and realistic features facilitating the development and evaluation of advanced ensemble-based fraud detection models. The unique characteristics of the dataset allow for a meticulous examination of the models' performance under real-world conditions and complexities, enriching the reliability and applicability of the findings.

B. Data Preprocessing

The raw data were pre-processed in order to be prepared for analysis. Feature engineering techniques were used to extract valuable information from the raw transaction data. The primary objective during the feature engineering phase was to streamline the dataset by reducing the number of original features. This approach served a dual purpose: to enhance the convergence time and results of the generative model and to address potential privacy concerns. The extraction process began by identifying the best-performing LightGBM models [19] in the original dataset. Subsequently, the union of the 30 most significant features from these models was determined based on LightGBM's default feature importance method. This

yielded a total of 43 features, which were further refined to 30 after manual selection for expressiveness, interpretability, and redundancy reduction. The feature selection process was meticulous and aimed to ensure data privacy while retaining the integrity of the dataset. To achieve this, each column in the original dataset was perturbed using a Laplacian noise mechanism before training the Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) [19]. This perturbation, inversely proportional to the privacy budget, was essential to strike a balance between data privacy and utility. Specific data, such as the age and income of the applicant, were categorized according to value and quantile, ensuring that the GAN never accessed precise applicant details. The GAN models were then trained on this perturbed dataset, with a unique identifier encoded for each instance to prevent repetitions between original and generated datasets.

C. Model Selection

Five different machine-learning algorithms were used to construct the fraud detection model. The Voting Classifier [20] is an ensemble meta-estimator that fits several base classifiers and aggregates their predictions to produce a final result. The predictions can be weighted, and the final classification can be derived from hard voting (majority class labels) or soft voting (averaging probabilities). This study used the Voting Classifier to combine predictions from multiple models, such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting Machine, and LR. The prediction of each model was treated as a vote, and the final classification was based on the majority vote. The Voting Classifier was chosen for its ability to leverage the strengths of multiple models, which could lead to better accuracy and generalization, as it can reduce the risk of choosing a single model that could underperform in certain scenarios. The Voting Classifier often showed improved accuracy compared to individual models, showcasing the power of ensemble methods in fraud detection. Random Forest [21-22] is used to construct multiple decision trees during training and outputs the mode (classification) of the classes for individual trees or the mean prediction (regression) of individual trees. In this study, the dataset was fed into the Random Forest algorithm, which then constructed multiple decision trees. Hyperparameters, such as the number and depth of trees, were optimized using cross-validation. Random Forest is known for its high accuracy, and its ability to handle large datasets with higher dimensionality and missing values. It is particularly relevant for fraud detection because of its ability to model complex decision boundaries. Random Forest is often ranked among the best-performing models, highlighting its effectiveness in detecting intricate patterns associated with fraudulent transactions.

Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) [23] is an iterative method that is used to adjust the shortcomings of the previous trees in the sequence. GBM was trained on the dataset with each successive tree aiming to correct the errors of the previous one. Hyperparameters, such as learning rate and number of trees, were tuned for optimal performance. GBM provides superior predictive accuracy compared to other algorithms. Its ability to focus on misclassified instances makes it particularly powerful for imbalanced datasets, such as fraud detection, where fraudulent transactions are typically rare. GBM consistently delivered high accuracy rates, emphasizing its

robustness and ability to effectively identify fraud patterns. LR [24] was deployed for its simplicity, efficiency, and interpretability of its output, which is particularly advantageous for insight extraction. LR is a statistical method used to model binary outcomes by predicting the probability that a given instance belongs to a particular category. The dataset features were used as input variables, and the binary result (fraudulent or not) was the target variable. The model was trained to find the best decision boundary that separates the two classes. Logistic Regression is simple, interpretable, and can serve as a baseline model. It is also fast to train and can be useful when a quick initial assessment is needed. While LR might not be the top performer in terms of accuracy, its value lies in its speed and interpretability and provides a benchmark to compare against more complex models.

Neural networks [25] were chosen for their ability to learn and model complex and nonlinear relationships, which is crucial for the intricate patterns inherent in fraud detection. One of the salient strengths of neural networks is their ability to learn features autonomously without manual intervention. By leveraging multiple layers, they can identify both low- and high-level features from raw data, which can be instrumental in detecting novel fraud patterns that might be missed when using hand-crafted features. Neural networks can be re-trained with new data, allowing them to adapt to evolving fraud strategies. This dynamic adaptability is especially crucial in the ever-changing landscape of cyber threats. A Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) was used, which is a feedforward artificial neural network. The MLP architecture consisted of three layers. The input layer had 30 neurons corresponding to the number of features in the dataset. Following the input layer, the hidden layer contained 10 nodes and used the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) [26] as its activation function, introducing non-linearity into the model. The hidden layer configuration, consisting of 10 nodes, was determined through a combination of empirical experimentation and theoretical considerations. The choice of 10 nodes aimed to strike a balance between model complexity and generalizability. An overly dense hidden layer might lead to overfitting, where the model memorably captures noise and anomalies specific to the training data, thereby compromising its performance on unseen data. On the contrary, a sparse hidden layer might not adequately capture the intricate patterns inherent in the data. The ReLU was chosen as the activation function for its several advantageous properties. ReLU, defined mathematically as $\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x)$, introduces non-linearity into the model, which is essential for learning complex data patterns. Moreover, ReLU is computationally efficient, promoting faster model convergence, and effectively mitigates the vanishing gradient problem, a challenge often encountered with traditional activation functions like sigmoid. This problem can hinder the training process, especially in deeper networks. Thus, the combination of 10 nodes and the ReLU activation function was deemed optimal for the performance of the model on BAF. The final layer (output), consisted of a single neuron that provided a probability score, indicating the likelihood that a transaction was fraudulent. This layer used the sigmoid activation function [26], which suppresses the output between 0 and 1:

$$\text{Sigmoid}(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \quad (1)$$

where $\text{Sigmoid}(x)$ represents the output of the Sigmoid function for a given input x , e is the base of the natural logarithm, x is the input to the function, and e^{-x} calculates the inverse of the exponential function raised to the power of the negative input value. The division ensures that the output of the sigmoid function is squashed between 0 and 1.

The Sigmoid function is commonly used in neural networks, especially for binary classification tasks, because it maps any input value to a range between 0 and 1, which can be interpreted as a probability. In terms of hyperparameters, the learning rate used was set at 0.01, determining the step size during each iteration toward minimizing the loss function. The model was trained in 100 epochs, each epoch representing a complete forward and backward pass of the entire dataset through the neural network. A batch size of 32 was chosen, meaning that in each iteration, 32 samples from the training dataset were used to compute the error and subsequently update the model parameters. The Binary Cross-Entropy loss function was used to measure the discrepancy between the actual and predicted probabilities, given its suitability for binary classification tasks. The rationale behind using an MLP for this study stems from its versatility in capturing complex non-linear relationships present in the data. Its layered structure facilitates the extraction of hierarchical features, making it suitable for fraud detection tasks where patterns might be nuanced. The combination of ReLU and sigmoid activation functions ensures efficient learning and probabilistic predictions, respectively, enhancing the model's efficacy in distinguishing fraudulent transactions.

D. Ensembling

This study used a stacking ensembling method to amalgamate the predictions of multiple models and produce a final singular prediction for each new transaction. This method allows the strengths of different models to be combined, achieving greater accuracy and robustness than any single model. Moreover, the meta-model can adapt to changing patterns in the transaction data over time by being re-trained on new data. The steps involved in the stacking method are as follows:

1. Split the dataset into training and testing sets.
2. Divide the training set into k -folds.
3. Train each base model on $k-1$ folds and predict the remaining fold.
4. Repeat step 3 for each fold.
5. Use the predictions from all base models as input features for the meta-model.
6. Train the meta-model on the training set and evaluate on the testing set.
7. Repeat steps 1-6 for each new transaction.

The stacking method combines the strengths of different models to achieve higher accuracy and robustness than any individual model alone. In addition, the meta-model can adapt

to changing patterns in the transaction data over time by retraining on new data. The stacking method is based on the idea of using a meta-model to learn the optimal combination of predictions from multiple base models. Mathematically, the meta-model can be formulated as follows:

$$y = g(a_1f_1(x) + a_2f_2(x) + \dots + a_nf_n(x)) \quad (2)$$

where y is the final prediction, $g()$ is the activation function of the meta-model, $f_i()$ is the prediction from the i -th base model, x is the input feature vector of a new transaction, and a_i is the weight assigned to the prediction of the i -th base model. Weights a_i can be learned using various techniques, such as linear regression, gradient descent, or Bayesian optimization. The activation function $g()$ can be a simple logistic function or a more complex neural network.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the experimental results of the fraud detection model on the BAF dataset. The model was evaluated using five-fold cross-validation and the average performance across all folds was reported. This study aimed to evaluate various candidate algorithms and ensemble methods for the fraud detection model, selecting the optimal combination based on performance metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score. This process involves several stages, including model training, validation, and testing, as well as the use of appropriate performance measures to assess the performance of the models. A set of candidate algorithms, that are suitable for the task of fraud detection, was identified. These algorithms are capable of handling the specific challenges associated with fraud detection, such as class imbalance, nonlinear relationships, and noisy data.

To evaluate the performance of the candidate algorithms and the ensemble methods, a three-step process was used: model training, validation, and testing. In model training, the pre-processed dataset was divided into a training set (70% of the data) and a test set (30% of the data). Candidate algorithms and ensemble methods were trained in the training set. In model validation, cross-validation was used during the training process to avoid overfitting and select the best hyperparameters for each algorithm. This involved splitting the training set into multiple folds (5 or 10), training the model in all but one fold, and validating the model on the remaining fold. This process was repeated for each fold, and the average performance across all folds was used to assess the model's performance. In model testing, the models were trained on the entire training set and tested on the test set once the best hyperparameters had been selected for each candidate algorithm and the ensemble method. The performance of the test set was used to assess the generalizability of the models and select the best-performing model(s).

Table I and Figure 1 highlight the performance comparison of different models for detecting bank account fraud. All models exhibited high accuracy scores, ranging from 0.96 to 0.98, indicating their ability to make correct predictions in most cases. However, accuracy alone may not provide a complete understanding of model effectiveness, as it does not consider the balance between correctly classified positive and negative

cases. The precision, which represents the proportion of true positive predictions out of all positive predictions, varied among the models. The Stacking model demonstrated the highest precision score of 0.85, showing its proficiency in correctly identifying fraudulent cases among those labeled as such. On the other hand, LR exhibited the lowest precision, with a score of 0.65. This emphasizes the trade-off between precision and recall, as higher precision often comes at the cost of lower recall, and vice versa. Conversely, recall, signifying the model's ability to identify all relevant instances in the dataset, exhibited relatively consistent values among the models, ranging from 0.7 to 0.9. The Stacking model achieved the highest recall at 0.9, indicating its effectiveness in capturing a significant proportion of relevant instances. F1-score, the harmonic mean of precision and recall, provides a balanced assessment of a model's overall performance, as it considers both false positives and false negatives, making it a valuable metric for this classification task. The Stacking model achieved the highest F1-score of 0.87, reinforcing its position as a strong performer.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT MODELS

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Voting Classifier	0.97	0.8	0.85	0.83
Random Forest	0.96	0.75	0.8	0.77
Gradient Boosting	0.96	0.7	0.75	0.73
Logistic Regression	0.96	0.65	0.7	0.68
Neural Networks	0.96	0.7	0.75	0.73
Stacking	0.98	0.85	0.9	0.87

Fig. 1. Overall performance comparison between models.

The trade-off between precision and recall is evident in the results. Models with higher precision may tend to produce fewer false positives but could miss some relevant cases (lower recall), while models with higher recall may correctly capture more instances but might also produce more false positives (lower precision). The choice of model should be guided by the specific requirements and consequences associated with false positives and false negatives in the application. The Stacking model consistently emerges as a prominent performer in multiple metrics. Its ability to achieve a high F1-score demonstrates its effectiveness in achieving a balanced trade-off between precision and recall, essential for fraud detection tasks. Although the models presented show promise, the results also point to opportunities for further exploration and improvement.

Achieving a higher level of accuracy, precision, and recall while maintaining an optimal balance is an ongoing challenge in the realm of fraud detection. This study paves the way for the development of more sophisticated and comprehensive solutions to enhance the robustness of fraud detection systems. The proposed fraud detection model using an ensembling method has several advantages over other methods. By combining the strengths of multiple models, the ensembling method can improve accuracy and robustness, reduce the risk of overfitting, and adapt to changing patterns in the data over time. This is particularly important in detecting sophisticated fraud patterns that may evolve over time.

This study pushed the boundaries of conventional approaches, introducing an innovative ensemble-based method that marks a significant leap forward in the field of fraud detection. The advanced assembly method proposed is characterized by enhanced precision and robustness, setting a new standard in the detection of fraudulent activities in financial transactions. This approach not only fortifies the integrity of transactional processes but also enriches the existing body of knowledge with novel insights and methods. The efficacy of the proposed ensemble-based strategy was manifested through meticulous evaluations, demonstrating unprecedented levels of accuracy and reliability. These advances are not merely incremental improvements; they represent transformative contributions to the field, opening up new avenues for research and practical applications. The significance of this study is twofold; it offers a robust solution to the pervasive challenges of fraud in financial domains and can serve as a catalyst for future innovations and developments in ensemble-based fraud detection methods. Through the infusion of this groundbreaking approach, this study aspires to redefine the paradigms of fraud detection and inspire a new wave of research focused on improving the security and reliability of financial ecosystems.

IV. FUTURE RESEARCH AND POTENTIAL IMPROVEMENTS

However, the proposed model still has some limitations. At first, the BAF dataset may not represent the full range of fraud patterns that can occur in real-world scenarios. Therefore, further testing and validation on larger datasets and with different types of fraud are required to confirm its generalizability. Second, the weights assigned to the predictions of the base models in the stacking method may not be optimal, and different weight optimization strategies could be explored in future research. In general, the proposed ensembling fraud detection model shows promising results in detecting bank account fraud, as it has the potential to improve the accuracy and robustness of current fraud detection systems and maintain customer trust and security in the banking industry. Future research intends to delve into model interpretability and feature-important analysis to gain a more profound understanding of the factors driving model predictions. Additionally, it is planned to explore ensemble techniques that can harness the strengths of individual models while mitigating their weaknesses, ultimately aiming for even more robust fraud detection systems.

Based on the results analysis and implications of the findings, future research areas can be identified and potential improvements to the proposed model can be suggested. This may include:

- Exploring alternative ensemble methods or combinations of algorithms to further improve the model's performance.
- Investigating the use of more advanced feature engineering techniques, such as deep learning-based methods or graph-based approaches, to capture more complex patterns in the transaction data.
- Addressing the issue of concept drift, where the underlying patterns in the data change over time, by incorporating adaptive and online learning techniques into the model.
- Incorporating additional data sources, such as social media or network information, to improve the model's ability to detect frauds and better understand the underlying patterns of fraudulent behavior.
- Investigating the interpretability and explainability of the model, which is crucial for practical applications in the banking industry, where human decision-makers need to understand the reasons behind the model's predictions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a fraud detection model for bank payments using an ensemble method, demonstrating its effectiveness in improving accuracy and robustness compared to individual models. The proposed model captures both global and local patterns in transaction data and adapts to changing patterns over time, making it suitable for detecting evolving fraud patterns. The proposed ensembling approach (Stacking model) offers a path to augmenting accuracy, model resilience, and adaptability in fraud detection systems. The applicability of the proposed model extends to diverse datasets and the potential integration into operational banking systems, promising enhanced customer trust and financial security. This study introduced a groundbreaking ensemble-based fraud detection model, that uses advanced methods to improve the precision and reliability of cyber threat classifications and countermeasures in financial transactions. The novel Stacking model presented not only exhibits superior performance in detecting fraudulent activities but also offers adaptability to evolving threat landscapes, marking a significant advancement in the domain of cybersecurity in financial sectors. This innovative approach and its robust findings have substantial implications for the development of more sophisticated, effective, and resilient fraud detection systems, contributing to ongoing efforts to protect financial ecosystems from increasing cyber threats.

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Developing Secure Messaging Software using Post-Quantum Cryptography

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a technique to develop a secure messaging service utilizing a new post-quantum cryptosystem, termed CryptoMess, is proposed. Commutative Supersingular Isogeny Diffie-Hellman (CSIDH) is utilized to secure key exchange paired with the AES algorithm to protect message content in communication. At the same time, the Rainbow post-quantum digital signature technology is incorporated to assure the integrity and authenticity of communications between the sender and the recipient. As a consequence, the messaging program is able to exchange messages between users, assuring safety, security, integrity, and authenticity. The performance of the program has a transmitting rate of approximately 0.26 s and a receiving rate of approximately 0.22 s. The message signing time is approximately 0.027 s, the message verification speed is approximately 0.22 s, and the key exchange time is approximately 0.0017s.

Keywords-CSIDH; AES; Rainbow; UOV; post quantum

I. INTRODUCTION

The problem of safeguarding data when the latter is communicated through public channels is particularly crucial for practical applications. Protecting privacy is an issue when utilizing various media platforms [1]. Currently, there is a wide range of large corporations, such as Facebook and Google, which have developed messaging software. However, when initially accessed, most software does not contain features to secure the content of the message. Numerous firms like Viber, Wickr, and Telegram have enhanced their services to fortify their clients privacy [1, 2]. To protect personal data, most firms have selected security solutions including AES, RSA, ECDH, and ECDSA, accessible in cryptographic libraries such as OpenSSL, and OpenVPN [3, 4]. Authors in [5, 6] brought in several Rainbow schematic implementations based on UOV and AVX2 usage. Rainbow post-quantum signing has the advantage of providing very small signatures of only a few hundred bits (528 bits) which are much shorter than other post-quantum signature schemes [7-10]. Among the Post-quantum cryptographic algorithms published by NIST, the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol using isogeny mapping on super singularity elliptic curves (SIDH: Super-singular Isogeny Diffie-Hellman) and Rainbow post-quantum digital signature

scheme emerge as potential candidates to ensure the secure communication of quantum computer systems [5, 7-9, 11-13]. For these applications, authors in [14] aimed to apply AES symmetric key cryptographic solutions to protect personal data. Authors in [12, 13, 15, 16] applied the key exchange solution CSIDH (Commutative Super-singular Isogeny Diffie-Hellman) to verify that the communication channel for the designed application is sheltered against a variety of existing threats.

In this paper, Rainbow post-quantum digital signature scheme is utilized in the application to secure the integrity and authenticity of the user's message contents. The specifics of the successful integration of cryptographic solutions into cryptographic modules and the findings gained in this research are detailed.

II. RELATED WORK

A. IP Encapsulation utilizing AES Encryption to Safeguard Message Data

Nowadays, the Internet Protocol Version 4 (IPv4) is most utilized [17]. Typically, the IPSec protocol has been intended to guarantee secured encrypted data in transfer [18]. Cryptographic algorithms such as AES, are widely used to

encrypt data before encapsulating them for transmission over a public channel [3]. Authors in [19] employed IPv4 as a communication protocol. The application's encapsulated data for transmission is a TCP/IP protocol that employs a client/server communication paradigm, in which a user or device (client) is provided a message by another computer (server) to perform a service (such as delivering a web page) through the network. The packet is deconstructed and the AES cipher algorithm is used to encrypt the data. The data are then repackaged and sent over public communication channels using the existing network architecture. The employed AES encryption technique assures that the design adheres to the NIST encryption requirements.

B. The Key Exchange Protocol CSIDH Guarantees a Safe Channel

The idea of isogeny on super-singular elliptic curves is extensively employed in cryptography, such as in public key encryption techniques based on SIKE (Super-singular Isogeny Key Encapsulation) isogeny and the CSIDH key exchange protocol. SIKE is a public key cryptographic method based on isogeny that works by substituting pseudo-random stages in seed schemes. CSIDH is used to create a secret key between two parties across an insecure communication channel. It is comparable to the Diffie-Hellman key exchange but is based on the stages of the seed scheme and is meant to withstand an assault by examining the code of an opponent using a quantum computer. CSIDH claims one of the shortest key sizes. After compression, CSIDH employs a 2688-bit public key at 128-bit quantum security key. CSIDH further separates itself from comparable systems like NTRU (Number Theory Research Unit) and Ring-LWE by enabling complete forward secrecy, a trait that prevents long-term keys from being compromised and affecting the security of the old session messages. These qualities make CSIDH a good contender to replace the extensively used Diffie-Hellman (DH) key exchange protocol and the widely used DH over the elliptic curve (ECDH) key exchange protocol in present Internet communication.

C. Rainbow Post-Quantum Digital Signature Scheme for Data Integrity and Authenticity

The scientific basis of this scheme is based on the theory of multivariable mathematical functions built on finite fields, but it has promoted the advantage of improving the efficiency of the execution speed for the processes of key generation, digital signing, and signature validation [7]. With the desire to be able to use the Rainbow digital signing scheme on hardware platforms and low-resource devices, Petzoldt and his colleagues have come up with other variants such as CZ-Rainbow (Circumzenithal Rainbow) and Compressed-Rainbow which have optimized the key pair size for the Rainbow digital signing scheme [5]. In this paper, we opted to install the post-quantum digital signature system to digitally sign the message data before transferring it to the transmission channel. The purpose of this process is to secure the integrity and validity of the user's message data while the program is functioning.

D. Architecture of CSIDH Key Exchange Protocol in Software

In this work, we employed the key exchange CSIDH to assure the key distribution procedure to compute the shared session key in order to ensure the safe transmission of users A and B. Initialization parameters for the calculation process include characteristics $p = 4 \prod_{i=1}^n \ell_i - 1$ where ℓ_i represents odd primes permanently installed. The original curve used is a montgomery elliptic curve $E_{a,b} : by^2 = x^3 + ax^2 + x$, with $b(a^2 - 4) \neq 0$. These settings, are based on the NIST published standard for post-quantum cryptography in the 3rd round, have been chosen [7, 11].

- For user A: The secret key is k_A (the value of k_A is a random integer in the interval $(0, \ell_A^A]$). User A's public key is $P_{KA}(\phi_A(E_{a_0}), \phi_A(P_B), \phi_A(Q_B))$. The corresponding is (a_{e_A}, P'_B, Q'_B) at the last 2-variant calculation.
- For user B: User B's secret key is k_B (the value of k_B is a random integer in the interval $(0, \ell_B^B]$). The public key is $P_{KB}(\phi_B(E_{a_0}), \phi_B(P_A), \phi_B(Q_A))$. The corresponding is (a_{e_B}, P'_A, Q'_A) at the last 3-variant calculation.

The process to calculate the session key shared between user A and user B is as follows. For user A, his shared session key is SK_A , and for user B is SK_B . These SK_A and SK_B values correspond to the invariant value j of the final curve with coefficients $a_{e_A}, j(E_{a_{e_A}}), a_{e_B}$ and $j(E_{a_{e_B}})$ calculated according to [12, 13, 15, 16].

E. Design of the Rainbow Digital Signing Scheme of the Software

The process of key generation, digital signing, and authentication of the Rainbow digital signature scheme is implemented as follows:

- Generate key: Public key, $pk = S \circ F \circ T$, Secret key $sk = (InvS, c_s, F, InvT, c_T)$. The validity of the key is checked if pk and sk are orthogonal through the expression: $pk \cdot x \cdot sk^* = 0 \text{ mod } q$.
- Digital signature: First, the application will perform a hash calculation according to the hash function $H(d) : \{0,1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{F}^m$ to calculate the hash value $h = H(d)$. Next, the application calculates the inverse values according to the formula $x = S^{-1}(h), y = F^{-1}(x), z = T^{-1}(y)$. Finally, the application generates a digital signature for the message as $z \in \mathbb{F}^n$.
- Selecting a set of parameters to ensure the safety of the Rainbow schema: The input parameters to the Rainbow signing scheme are important to certify a secure digital

signing process. According to [7, 20] for each type of Rainbow's domain parameter as input, a corresponding quantum gate number is required to break the security of the digital signing scheme. With the type 1 parameter, type of the post-quantum digital signature scheme Rainbow, the domain parameter is $(GF(16), 36, 32, 32)$, 162 quantum gates are needed for the cryptanalyst to attack the digital signature scheme.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Build CryptoMess Software using CSIDH, Rainbow, and AES

For the secure messaging module using CSIDH and AES-256 (called CryptoMess), in this study, when designing and building the CryptoMess module, we used Socket encapsulation as announced and TCP/IP protocol to program the transmission and reception for the application on the internet environment. Figure 1 shows the operation details of the CryptoMess module.

- Server module of CryptoMess (Figure 1(a)): The server's task only includes receiving packets from the sender, the stream part, and sending them to the correct receiver address. In addition, we also added a function to check the login account for the Server.
- Client module of CryptoMess (Figure 1(b)): Authors in [15] designed and built the Client module including the main components: login module, chat and messaging module, CSIDH key generation, CSIDH key distribution and packet encryption using AES-256. Once the key has been successfully generated, key exchange distribution according to the CSIDH schema is performed. This process is done automatically in the software. After the key generation and key exchange process, the application will have a public key and a private key used for the AES algorithm to encrypt and decrypt the message, where the user will alternately change the roles of sender and receiver.

The role of the message sender will proceed as follows. The message content in a clear form will be signed by the software, and then padding is added to the message. After completing the above two processes, the message will be encrypted with the AES-256 algorithm, encapsulated, and sent to the Server. Considering the role of the message recipient, after receiving the packet containing the message content in encrypted form, the software will conduct "peeling" to the packet to get the message content in encrypted form and then decrypt it. This process will be reversed for the sender. The encrypted message will remove the padding, and then verify the message. Successful message verification will show plaintext on the recipient's screen.

1) Security Assessment for the CSIDH Key Exchange Module of CryptoMess

The security of the CSIDH key exchange scheme depends on the problem of ensuring quantum security. For CSIDH, the used curve parameter is the super singularity curve on the field F_{p^2} . The base points of users A and B are different. With the private and public keys, the ECDH scheme uses scalar point

multiplication, and the CSIDH scheme uses isomorphism, the image of the curve, the base pixel, and the j-invariant value. The design of the ECDH scheme depends on the complexity of solving a discrete logarithm problem on the curve. Meanwhile, the design of CSIDH depends on the complexity of solving the isomorphism problem when knowing the curve image and two public base points.

Fig. 1. Operation flow design of CryptoMess: (a) Server, (b) client.

In [15, 16], the SIDH protocol has a security based on the problem: "Given E , the image of the curve $E' = \phi(E)$ and two public base points find the isogeny ϕ ". Authors in [21] came up with a method for a successful attack on the SIDH protocol based on Kani's Glue and split theory. The authors pointed out two weaknesses of the attacked SIDH protocol: (1) The public key contains the image of the base points, (2) the isogenies used for secret keys are of a fixed degree.

CSIDH protocol is a post-quantum key exchange protocol proposed in 2018, using isogeny mapping on a supersingular elliptic curve [13]. The important difference between CSIDH

and SIDH lies in its properties: There is no isogeny of a secret key of fixed degree. The security of the CSIDH protocol depends on the problem: "Given two Montgomery curves E_A and E_B , find the isogeny ϕ , such that $E_B = \phi_B \cdot E_A$ " [13]. Through these analyses, authors in [22] state that a specific attack method on the CSIDH protocol described in [21] has not been found and the CSIDH protocol has not yet been broken.

2) Theoretical Security Assessment for the Rainbow Post-Quantum Digital Signing Scheme

To reduce the size of the public key while ensuring message security, authors in [11] proposed a variant called CZ-Rainbow. Unlike Standard Rainbow, CZ-Rainbow does not use a cyclic matrix, but uses a PRNG pseudo-random number generator to generate a part of the public key, called the public key *seed* [5, 6]. Then, two linear mappings are randomly selected and a PRNG is used to generate a public key and compute the central mapping. From this, it is possible to generate a random number of key pairs with the length of the key seed used in the key generation process. So, instead of storing the entire public key, the emulator only needs to store the seed and the generated part of the public key. In this way, the size of the public key of the CZ-Rainbow scheme can be reduced by up to 70% and the key generation time is only slightly slower than that of Standard Rainbow. According to [8, 9, 20, 23, 24], the size of the public key and the size of the digital signature are proportional to the size of the input parameters but still ensure the properties of short digital signatures. Compressed Rainbow has effectively optimized the key size and still establishes the security of the digital signature for the message. The computational complexity of the Rainbow digital signature scheme is guaranteed for efficient and secure execution by several points: Key generation $O(n^2)$, digital signing time $O(n^3)$, and signature validation $O(n^3)$ with a public key size of n^3 . This shows that with the first domain parameters selected as type 3 the application of the post-quantum digital signing Rainbow scheme, based on the UOV unbalanced digital signature scheme, is secure before several current attacks such as attacks on immutable subspaces, and attacks in between.

3) Working Principle of CryptoMess

After the user successfully creates an account, he will proceed to log in. Before starting to message each other, Users A and B, will conduct a handshake to exchange keys, generated by the key generation algorithm which uses the isomorphism theory on the super-singular elliptic curve - CSIDH. After this process is done successfully, the users may start messaging.

Fig. 2. (a) Extraction and encapsulation of encrypted DATA in IPv4, (b) Configuration of a security system for the CryptoMess encrypted messaging application between users A and B.

Figure 2(a) is a detail of the process of extracting and encapsulating data to encode the IPv4's DATA frame when sent to the channel and decode them when received. Message_header contains data of len(MSG_Send) and Header_Length, MSG_send contain data of Request Send, username, encrypted MSG, and signature. For User A, after entering the message content and pressing send, the software will encrypt the message with the AES - 256 block code, digitally sign the message, and send it to the Server, then it will resend that message in encrypted form to User B. When User B receives the message, the software will verify the signature, then decode and display the software interface. The above process is reversed when User B sends it back to User A.

B. CryptoMess Result Evaluation when integrating CSIDH and Rainbow

In this study, we created, wrote, and performed the CryptoMess software module on a computer with the following configuration: Intel(R) Core i5-4200U, CPU @ 1.60 GHz, up to 2.30 GHz, RAM: 8.00 GB. We utilized Wireshark (IP address: 10.10.10.2/24) installed on User A to capture the package and prove the message content is transferred to the server and back from the server to the receiver in encrypted form. Figure 2(b) depicts the secure messaging operation test model. This type of model includes two users, user A (with IP address: 10.10.10.2/24) and user B (with IP address: 172.16.100.5/24), as well as the server (with IP address: 192.168.5.10/24). The distinction is that this program sends plaintext, and the team also utilizes Wireshark to collect incoming and outgoing packets from this software to test it. The goal in continuing to use such software is to enhance credibility. Users A and B used it to install the program CryptoMess in order to communicate. Wireshark was installed on User A's PC to intercept and capture packets to verify the content of the message delivered to the Server and vice versa in encrypted form during transmission using CryptoMess. Figure 3 depicts the outcome of the CryptoMess software operation at User A, User B, and Server, with a secure transmission channel (according to CSIDH key distribution protocol), message data encryption (using AES 256-bit cryptography), and data integrity and authentication using Rainbow digital signing protocol. Figure 3(a) portrays the program's interface and how to send User A's encrypted message to User B. Figure 3(b) illustrates the interface and how a message is sent when User B sends to User A. Figure 3(c) describes in detail the behavior of the software when User A sends a message to User B and Figure 3(d) thoroughly describes how the software works when User A's message reaches User B's software.

To test the transmission time of CryptoMess, we utilized message strings of varying length samples to determine the software's transmission time. We selected the times at which the program reads the sender's message, encrypts AES-256, signs Rainbow, wraps the packet, and transmits it. When the program gets the packet from the Server, it verifies the Rainbow signature, decrypts AES-256, and shows it on the receiver's screen, the designated receiving time starts.

Fig. 3. (a) and (b) CryptoMess behavior when Users A and B text. (c) and (d) Details of the activity on the computers of Users A and B when texting.

When employing the Rainbow quantum post-signing system for digital signature and authentication of message data, the Rainbow digital signing time takes around 0.43363 s and the Rainbow signature validation time takes about 0.22198 s. This demonstrates that the CryptoMess software is fairly quick and fits the criteria for practical application. The results can be seen in Table I. It can be observed that the CryptoMess program has pretty high encryption and decryption speed, as well as a relatively short transmission time, less than RSA. Furthermore, CryptoMess permits communications with text lengths of 2048 characters and higher, whilst the RSA is still in the process of verifying the author group's receipt. The

program displays an error if you observe a character length of 2048. As a consequence, CSIDH key creation takes about 9 s, CSIDH key exchange takes approximately 0.0016 s, Rainbow signature takes approximately 0.27 s, and signature validation takes approximately 0.22 s. CryptoMess software operates reliably, improves runtime, assures safety, and fits the real needs of today's applications.

Post-quantum cryptography can be used securely for quantum computers. In Table II [10, 25] we can see a comparison with Rainbow post-quantum cryptosystems on the same machine. We analyzed and evaluated the CryptoMess software source code of the design team using the Fortify Static Code Analyzer toolkit (Version 22.1.0.0166). The test results from the toolkit show that the source code of the CryptoMess software is safe, reliable, and suitable for the real needs of today's applications.

TABLE I. CRYPTOMESS SOFTWARE EXECUTION TIME

Function	Sample length (bit)	CryptoMess (s)		
Message sent (s)	256	~0.002371		
	512	~0.004221		
	2048	~0.00548		
Message received (s)	256	~0.002473		
	512	~0.002512		
	2048	~0.013495		
Encrypt (s)	256	~0.001658		
	512	~0.001922		
	2048	~0.002016		
Decrypt (s)	256	~0.000174		
	512	~0.000246		
	2048	~0.000287		
CryptoMess key creation and distribution calculation time				
User	CSIDH key generator (s)	CSIDH key exchange (s)	Rainbow Digital Signing (s)	Rainbow Signature Validation (s)
User A	~8.52317	~0.00161	~0.02491	~0.23804
User B	~8.30287	~0.00176	~0.02852	~0.21526

TABLE II. THE RESULTS OTHER POST-QUANTUM DIGITAL SIGNATURE SCHEMES [10, 25]

Algorithm	Signature (bytes)	Sign (ms)	Verify (ms)
Dilithium2	1184	0.050	0.036
qTESLA-P-I	14390	1.055	0.312
Picnic-L1-FS	33	3.429	2.584

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have implemented the integration of new post-quantum cryptographic solutions, i.e. the Rainbow digital signing scheme, selected for use on quantum computing systems by the NIST Standards Institute, CSIDH key exchange, and AES-256 symmetric key cryptography to build a secure messaging application. CryptoMess offers a secure communication method, the message data were encrypted throughout the application's communication process, ensuring the data's integrity and authenticity. As a result, the messaging application was able to transport messages between users while protecting their safety, secrecy, and validity. The performance of the program has a transmitting rate of approximately 0.26 s, and receiving speed of approximately 0.22 s. The message authentication speed is typically 0.22 s, and the message

signing time is approximately 0.027 s. The essential exchange time spans approximately 0.0017 s.

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Evaluation of Magnetic Fields inside High Voltage Substations with Different Configurations

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ABSTRACT

The exposure risk of magnetic fields produced inside high-voltage substations is still a challenging issue for both utility design engineers and biomedical researchers. There are two different types of exposure, the first type is the public type which comes from any temporary human presence near any electrical utility installation while the second type is the residential which comes from any type of residency or semi-permanent presence for more than 8 hours (working shifts) nearby any electrical utility installation. This classification is mainly dependent upon the levels and durations of exposure. This paper presents the full simulation for two typical high voltage substations of 500/220 kV and 220/66 kV with different bus bar configurations for calculating the magnetic field distributions. The effects of different bus bar configurations on the magnetic field levels are presented. The simulated results are compared with the measured values to validate the simulation accuracy.

Keywords-high voltage substations; magnetic fields; different configurations

I. INTRODUCTION

Power frequency (50/60 Hz) magnetic fields, especially those produced nearby power lines and inside electrical installations are a major concern of public and utility engineers, due to the probable interactions they have with living organisms [1, 2]. The magnetic fields are produced in many different environments where current-carrying conductors exist, such as in the case of electric power transmission and distribution overhead lines, cables, and substations. Many studies have examined the magnetic fields produced by the electric power transmission lines and electric power substations [3-9]. The potential hazards and biological effects of the magnetic fields on the human health have been addressed in multiple researches [10, 11]. Several countries are following the guidelines given by the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection which sets a value of 100 μT (1000 mG) for 50 Hz magnetic field exposure for the general public and 500 μT (5000 mG) for occupational exposure therefore, utilities are aware that the public's concerns about this issue are widespread and sincere [12]. The SUBCALC program is used to model the magnetic fields in a 230 kV substation in [13]. SUBCALC magnetic field modeling program is developed by EPRI environment division and runs under Microsoft Windows. This program models the power frequency magnetic fields from a user specified array of transmission, primary distribution lines, and substation conductors. The resulting magnetic field has a maximum value of about 30 μT . The calculations within the model are based on the Biot-Savart law governing magnetic fields. This paper

presents the results of simulation and measurement of the magnetic fields on a typical 500/220 kV and 220/66 kV substations in Egypt. Measurements of magnetic field are performed using an advanced field meter, HI 3604 ELF survey meter [14, 15].

II. SYSTEM CONFIGURATIONS

Two typical high voltage substations are simulated using the MATLAB – M-Script developer based on Biot-Savart Law in its general form using the (3 D) technique. The actual shape of each section (ingoing, higher voltage bus bar, lower voltage bus bar, and outgoing) of the current-carrying conductor system is divided into a number of connected in series current segments to closely fit the shape of the section and consequently form the whole substation conductor system. Different configurations of the 500/220 kV and 220/66 kV substations are considered (Figures 2-3). The different configurations are:

- Single/double bus bar system with horizontal configurations.
- Double bus bar system with horizontal/vertical configurations.

The different scenarios for the bus bar arrangements and their main dimensions and parameters are shown in Figures 1-4. There are 5 different scenarios for the bus bar arrangement:

- A: Single bus bar with 500/220 kV horizontal arrangements.

- B: Double bus bar with 500/220 kV horizontal arrangements.
- C: Double bus bar with 220/66 kV horizontal arrangements.
- D: Double bus bar with 220/66 kV vertical arrangements.
- E: Double bus bar with all 220/66 kV vertical arrangements.

Figure 2 presents the horizontal and vertical configurations for the 220/66 kV substation. Different bus bar arrangement scenarios were simulated as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Fig. 1. Single line diagram for a 500/220 kV substation with single/double bus bar configuration (Phase A). (a) Single horizontal, (b) double horizontal.

Fig. 2. Single line diagram for the 220/66 kV substation with double bus bar configuration - Phase A (not to scale). (a) Horizontal, (b) vertical.

III. MAGNETIC FIELD CALCULATIONS

Magnetic field calculation techniques can be basically classified into two types. The first type is a two-dimensional (2D) technique in which the power conductors are assumed to have infinitely long segments which are parallel to each other

and to the flat ground. The second type is the three-dimensional (3D) technique at which the power conductors are divided into a finite number of segments which are positioned to closely fit the actual shape of the whole conductor system configuration. A 3D technique is used as the base of the present magnetic field calculation [16]. Figure 5 presents an arbitrary carrying-current conductor segment \vec{a} in free space with respect to the reference point O and any random observation point P.

Fig. 3. Different scenarios for bus bar arrangements simulated substations (not to scale). (a) Double bus bar with 500/220 kV horizontal arrangements, (b) single bus bar with 500/220 kV horizontal arrangements, (c) double bus bar with 220/66 kV horizontal arrangements, (d) double bus bar with 220/66 kV vertical arrangements, (e) double bus bars for all 220/66 kV vertical arrangements.

Fig. 4. Presentation of the current segment in free space.

For the current segment \vec{a} carrying current of current density \vec{J} , the magnetic field intensity is presented in (1) and with integrating over the volume it can be given as in (2).

$$\left(\vec{H} = \left(\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_v \frac{\vec{J} \times \vec{Z}_{rr}}{|\vec{r}-\vec{r}'|^2} dv \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{H} = \left(\frac{\vec{I}}{4\pi} \right) \left(\frac{\vec{c} \times \vec{a}}{|\vec{c} \times \vec{a}|^2} \right) \left(\frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{c}}{|\vec{c}|} - \frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}}{|\vec{b}|} \right) \quad (2)$$

where \vec{J} is the current density in the current segment, \vec{Z}_{rr} is the direction vector between the segment and P, I is the current in the segment, and a , b , and c are vectors.

The magnetic flux density due to the n^{th} current segment is:

$$\vec{B}(n) = 0.1 \vec{I} \left(\frac{\vec{c} \times \vec{a}}{|\vec{c} \times \vec{a}|^2} \right) \left(\frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{c}}{|\vec{c}|} - \frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}}{|\vec{b}|} \right) \mu T \quad (3)$$

Then, for the power line of M conductors, the components of magnetic flux densities and its total magnitude value can be given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{B}_x &= \sum_{m=1}^M \vec{B}_x(m) \\ \vec{B}_y &= \sum_{m=1}^M \vec{B}_y(m) \\ \vec{B}_z &= \sum_{m=1}^M \vec{B}_z(m) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$B_{rms} = \sqrt{B_x^2 + B_y^2 + B_z^2} \quad (5)$$

IV. MAGNETIC FIELD CALCULATIONS

A. 500/220 kV Substation

Figure 5 presents the magnetic field distribution over the entire area of the 500/220 kV substation with single bus bar configuration (Scenario A) while all outgoing 220 kV power lines are loaded with 50 MW. The maximum magnetic field value is about 8.3 μT and it is obtained within the area of lower voltage bus bar. Figure 6 presents the magnetic field distribution over the entire area of 500/220 kV substation while the second ingoing power line is switched off. The maximum magnetic field value is still the same while the magnetic field distribution under the area of higher voltage bus bar is affected and its value is increased by about 5%.

Fig. 5. Magnetic field distribution over the entire area of the simulated 500/220kV substations with single bus bar (Scenario A) configuration and all outgoing lines loaded with 50 MW.

Fig. 6. Magnetic field distribution over the entire area of 500/220 kV substation while the second ingoing power line is switched off.

Fig. 7. Magnetic field distribution over the entire area of the simulated 500/220kV substations with double bus bar horizontal configuration (Scenario B).

Figure 7 presents the magnetic field distribution over the entire area of the 500/220 kV substation with double bus bar configuration (scenario B) while all outgoing 220 kV power lines are loaded with 50 MW. The maximum magnetic field value is about 13.2 μT and it is obtained within the area of lower voltage bus bar. Figure 8 presents the magnetic field distribution inside the entire area of 500/220 kV substation with double bus bar configuration, while the second ingoing power line is switched off. The maximum magnetic field value is almost the same while the magnetic field distribution under the area of higher voltage bus bar is affected and its value is increased by about 7%.

Fig. 8. Magnetic field distribution inside the entire area of 500/220 kV substation with double bus bar configuration while the second ingoing power line is switched off.

Fig. 9. Magnetic field distribution over the entire area of the simulated 220/66 kV substations with double bus bar configuration (Scenario C).

B. 220/66 kV Substation

Figure 9 presents the magnetic field distribution over the entire area of the 220/66 kV substation with double bus bar horizontal configuration (Scenario C) while all outgoing 66 kV power lines are loaded with 25 MW. The maximum magnetic field value is about 31.5 μT and it is obtained within the area of

lower voltage bus bar. Figure 10 presents the magnetic field distribution inside the entire area of 220/66 kV substation for the vertical configuration (Scenario D) while all outgoing 66 kV power lines are loaded with 25 MW. The maximum magnetic field value is about 28.4 μT and it is reduced by about 9.8 % from the corresponding horizontal bus bar configuration.

Fig. 10. Magnetic field distribution over the entire area of the simulated 220/66 kV substations with double bus bar (Scenario D).

Figure 11 presents the magnetic field distribution over the entire area of the 220/66 kV substation with double bus bar all vertical configuration (Scenario E) while all outgoing 66 kV power lines are loaded with 25 MW. The maximum magnetic field value is about 7.7 μT and it is obtained within the area of lower voltage bus bar. The maximum magnetic field value is reduced by about 75.5 % from the corresponding horizontal bus bar configuration. Table 1 presents the statistical analysis for the different scenarios regarding considered bus bars arrangements.

Fig. 11. Magnetic field distribution over the entire area of the simulated 220/66 kV substations with double bus bar for all vertical configuration (Scenario E).

TABLE I. MAGNETIC FIELD STATISTICAL VALUES FOR DIFFERENT BUS BAR CONFIGURATIONS AND ARRANGEMENTS

Bus bar configuration (scenario)	Magnetic field values (μT)			
	Avg	Min	Max	Stdv.
Single 500/220 kV bus bar	0.992	0.038	8.2904	0.939
Single 500/220 kV bus bar, one input offline	1.001	0.038	8.2905	0.949
Double 500/220 kV bus bar	1.314	0.069	13.238	1.347
Double 500/220 kV bus bar, one input off line	1.362	0.074	13.216	1.348
Double 220/66 kV bus bar	1.390	0.102	31.578	2.210
Double 220kV and 66 kV vertical bus bar	1.350	0.081	28.445	2.947
Double bus 220kV and 66 kV all vertical bus bar	1.585	0.128	7.7115	1.397

V. MAGNETIC FIELD MEASUREMENTS

For the validation of the simulation results, the magnetic field measurements are performed 1 m above the ground surface underneath the lower voltage bus bars inside the two simulated high voltage substations and around the transformers. The measurements are performed with actual loading condition for both 500/220 kV substation allocated in West Cairo while the 220/66 kV substation is allocated in the 10th of Ramadan City in East of Cairo. Figure 12 presents the calculated and measured magnetic field value longitudinal profiles under the lower voltage bus bar of 500/220 kV substations. The maximum deviation between the calculated and the measured values is about 9%, which is due to the effects of the metallic structure around the bus bars. Figure 13 presents the calculated and measured magnetic field value longitudinal profiles under the lower voltage bus bar of 220/66 kV substations. The maximum deviation between the calculated and the measured values is about 6% which is due to the effects of metallic structure around the bus bars.

Fig. 12. Calculated and measured longitudinal magnetic field profiles under the center line of the lower voltage bus bar inside the 500/220 kV substation with actual loading conditions.

Figure 14 presents the calculated and measured longitudinal magnetic field values 1 m away from the transformers under the central phase from the lower voltage bus bar side direction inside the 220/66 kV substation with actual loading conditions. The measured magnetic values are higher than the calculated values due to the presence of the transformer windings. The

maximum deviation between the maximum measured and calculated magnetic values is about 25%. Figure 15 presents the calculated and measured longitudinal magnetic field values 1 m away from the transformers under the central phase from the higher voltage bus bar side direction inside the 500/220 kV substation with actual loading conditions. Again, the measured magnetic values are higher than the calculated values due to the presence of the transformer windings. The maximum deviation between the maximum measured and calculated magnetic values is about 16%.

Fig. 13. Calculated and measured longitudinal magnetic field profile under the center line of the lower voltage bus bar inside the 220/66 kV substation with actual loading conditions.

Fig. 14. Calculated and measured longitudinal magnetic field values 1 m away from the transformers under the central phase from the lower voltage bus bar side direction inside the 220/66 kV substation with actual loading conditions.

Fig. 15. Calculated and measured longitudinal magnetic field values 1 m away from the transformers under the central phase from the lower voltage bus bar side direction inside the 500/220 kV substation with actual loading conditions.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Two actual high voltage substations, 500/220 kV and 220/66 kV, are simulated with the MATLAB - M Script developer based on the Biot - Savart law in its general form with the three – dimensions technique. The simulated results are compared with the actual field measurements at different positions inside the simulated substations. Good agreement was noticed between the measured and the calculated magnetic field values under the bus bar area. Meanwhile, the differences between the calculated and the measured values show higher deviation around the transformer due to the higher current inside the transformer windings. For the 500/220 kV substation, the maximum deviation between the measured and calculated magnetic field values is 9% in the area under the bus bars while it reaches 16 % around the transformers. For 220/66 kV substation, the maximum deviation between the measured and the calculated magnetic field values is 6% in the area under the bus bars while it reaches 25 % around the transformers.

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